

Table 1 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)**Table 1.** Genes whose mRNA levels increased >2-fold with H₂O₂ treatment

Gene number	Gene name	Fold change	Normalized gene signals				Gene product description
			Treated		Untreated		
			Mean*	p-value	Mean	p-value	
PA0007		5.3	2.1350	0.0270	0.4028	0.0520	HP
PA0038		4.7	1.8950	0.0198	0.4032	0.0983	HP
PA0043		2.1	1.5770	0.0913	0.7510	0.0905	HP
PA0044	<i>exoT</i>	2.2	1.6470	0.0412	0.7486	0.0812	exoenzyme T
PA0053		2.1	1.6630	0.0436	0.7919	0.0732	HP
PA0059	<i>osmC</i>	3.0	1.4550	0.0431	0.4850	0.3000	osmotically inducible protein OsmC
PA0061		6.2	1.4980	0.0044	0.2416	0.2718	HP
PA0063		2.9	1.6200	0.0137	0.5586	0.0210	HP
PA0067	<i>prlC</i>	3.9	1.9580	0.0116	0.5021	0.0008	oligopeptidase A
PA0068		2.5	1.6040	0.0064	0.6416	0.0088	HP
PA0069		7.0	2.1540	0.0047	0.3077	0.0095	CHP
PA0094		3.5	1.5020	0.0020	0.4291	0.0424	HP
PA0095		2.3	1.3810	0.0188	0.6004	0.0123	CHP
PA0105	<i>coxB</i>	12.5	4.1460	0.0732	0.3317	0.2880	cytochrome c oxidase, subunit II
PA0106	<i>coxA</i>	20.7	3.8530	0.0617	0.1861	0.2623	cytochrome c oxidase, subunit I
PA0107		4.1	2.7870	0.0958	0.6798	0.0429	CHP
PA0109		10.4	2.4900	0.0599	0.2394	0.1433	HP
PA0119		8.9	2.1220	0.0014	0.2384	0.0006	Pr. dicarboxylate transporter
PA0120		6.2	2.1180	0.0084	0.3416	0.0164	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0121		3.7	1.9200	0.0095	0.5189	0.0068	HP
PA0122		2.6	1.4760	0.1039	0.5677	0.1339	CHP
PA0125		2.9	1.6180	0.0067	0.5579	0.0078	HP
PA0132		5.1	2.2500	0.1589	0.4412	0.0655	beta-alanine--pyruvate transaminase
PA0133		2.4	1.4690	0.0255	0.6121	0.0093	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0134		2.9	1.5840	0.0072	0.5462	0.0268	Pr. guanine deaminase
PA0139	<i>ahpC</i>	4.1	2.1640	0.0591	0.5278	0.0005	alkyl hydroperoxide reductase subunit C
PA0140	<i>ahpF</i>	10.1	2.1900	0.0007	0.2168	0.0015	alkyl hydroperoxide reductase subunit F
PA0141		3.5	1.9340	0.1183	0.5526	0.1468	CHP
PA0147		2.7	1.6920	0.0191	0.6267	0.0179	Pr. oxidoreductase
PA0149		7.4	1.6400	0.0011	0.2216	0.0350	Pr. sigma-70 factor, ECF subfamily
PA0178		4.5	2.6490	0.0416	0.5887	0.0717	Pr. two-component sensor
PA0179		6.7	2.8090	0.0243	0.4193	0.0024	Pr. two-component response regulator
PA0181		2.7	1.6180	0.0165	0.5993	0.0182	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0200		6.5	1.9940	0.0126	0.3068	0.0619	HP
PA0218		2.2	1.3640	0.0208	0.6200	0.0924	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0229	<i>pcaT</i>	4.1	1.8750	0.0311	0.4573	0.1165	dicarboxylic acid transporter PcaT
PA0230	<i>pcaB</i>	2.7	1.8850	0.0592	0.6981	0.0419	3-carboxy-cis,cis-muconate cycloisomerase
PA0249		6.2	2.1780	0.0136	0.3513	0.0149	Pr. acetyltransferase
PA0250		48.9	2.2950	0.0004	0.0469	0.0038	CHP
PA0256		6.4	1.3320	0.0175	0.2081	0.2810	HP
PA0257		2.2	1.4210	0.1239	0.6459	0.1666	HP
PA0258		3.4	1.6310	0.0405	0.4797	0.0218	HP
PA0259		2.1	1.6170	0.0199	0.7700	0.0447	HP

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PA0268		2.1	1.2820	0.0457	0.6105	0.0636	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0269		2.7	1.7830	0.0217	0.6604	0.0730	CHP
PA0271		2.2	1.4000	0.0837	0.6364	0.0478	HP
PA0275		3.1	1.7230	0.0267	0.5558	0.0078	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0276		20.6	1.9210	0.0022	0.0933	0.2450	HP
PA0278		6.0	2.8730	0.0557	0.4788	0.0290	HP
PA0289		3.8	1.8240	0.0253	0.4800	0.0398	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0297		4.9	1.8910	0.0413	0.3859	0.0830	Pr. glutamine amidotransferase
PA0298		4.2	1.3700	0.0088	0.3262	0.1142	Pr. glutamine synthetase
PA0312		2.8	2.2890	0.0507	0.8175	0.1417	CHP
PA0323		5.2	1.3900	0.0212	0.2673	0.1288	Pr. binding protein component of ABC transporter
PA0336	<i>ygdP</i>	2.6	1.4960	0.0026	0.5754	0.0068	Nudix hydrolase YgdP
PA0355	<i>pfpI</i>	2.2	1.4470	0.1068	0.6577	0.1571	protease PfpI
PA0360		3.4	2.0410	0.0315	0.6003	0.0069	HP
PA0398		2.2	1.4760	0.0982	0.6709	0.0841	HP
PA0405		2.2	1.4040	0.0109	0.6382	0.0520	CHP
PA0441	<i>dht</i>	5.6	1.6890	0.0235	0.3016	0.1242	dihydropyrimidinase
PA0449		17.6	2.3990	0.0060	0.1363	0.0083	HP
PA0451		2.8	1.5760	0.0097	0.5629	0.0654	CHP
PA0462		2.5	1.5660	0.0293	0.6264	0.0727	HP
PA0468		3.0	1.8250	0.0251	0.6083	0.0240	HP
PA0469		2.5	1.7550	0.0423	0.7020	0.0277	HP
PA0470		2.4	1.3830	0.1169	0.5763	0.0822	Pr. hydroxamate-type ferrisiderophore receptor
PA0471		22.0	2.2490	0.0027	0.1022	0.2006	Pr. transmembrane sensor
PA0472		35.1	1.8960	0.0002	0.0540	0.2908	Pr. sigma-70 factor, ECF subfamily
PA0473		2.5	2.0750	0.0756	0.8300	0.1586	Pr. glutathione S-transferase
PA0477		2.2	1.2500	0.0258	0.5682	0.0417	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0479		11.2	2.4630	0.0548	0.2199	0.2507	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0484		3.0	1.7280	0.0842	0.5760	0.2029	CHP
PA0487		2.6	1.6130	0.0343	0.6204	0.0949	Pr. molybdenum transport regulator
PA0489		3.3	1.5390	0.1258	0.4664	0.1140	Pr. phosphoribosyl transferase
PA0490		3.5	1.8550	0.0121	0.5300	0.0401	HP
PA0492		12.4	4.5970	0.0153	0.3707	0.0054	CHP
PA0493		8.0	3.8070	0.0194	0.4759	0.0243	Pr. biotin-requiring enzyme
PA0494		4.6	2.6900	0.0383	0.5848	0.0514	Pr. acyl-CoA carboxylase subunit
PA0495		2.9	2.0400	0.0765	0.7034	0.0891	HP
PA0498		16.3	2.2450	0.0365	0.1377	0.2058	HP
PA0499		5.1	1.2640	0.0374	0.2478	0.0479	Pr. pili assembly chaperone
PA0505		5.3	2.1780	0.0622	0.4109	0.0110	HP
PA0506		3.1	1.7920	0.0266	0.5781	0.0190	Pr. acyl-CoA dehydrogenase
PA0507		2.8	2.0400	0.1984	0.7286	0.0154	Pr. acyl-CoA dehydrogenase
PA0510		3.2	1.6070	0.0336	0.5022	0.1125	Pr. uroporphyrin-III c-methyltransferase
PA0511	<i>nirJ</i>	2.4	1.4220	0.0189	0.5925	0.0491	heme d1 biosynthesis protein NirJ
PA0529		3.6	1.6900	0.0400	0.4694	0.1933	CHP
PA0565		7.1	2.5100	0.0451	0.3535	0.1931	CHP
PA0566		3.6	1.7930	0.0121	0.4981	0.0025	HP
PA0567		8.1	2.0480	0.0160	0.2528	0.2486	CHP
PA0581		2.3	1.6250	0.0238	0.7065	0.0731	CHP
PA0584	<i>cca</i>	2.1	1.7760	0.0330	0.8457	0.1428	tRNA nucleotidyl transferase
PA0586		3.2	1.7100	0.0471	0.5344	0.0818	CHP

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PA0587		3.9	3.0090	0.0715	0.7715	0.0379	CHP
PA0588		6.6	2.7510	0.0135	0.4168	0.0123	CHP
PA0599		3.9	1.4740	0.0018	0.3779	0.0425	HP
PA0610	<i>prtN</i>	4.1	1.8170	0.0072	0.4432	0.0040	transcriptional regulator PrtN
PA0611	<i>prtR</i>	2.1	1.7750	0.0397	0.8452	0.1006	transcriptional regulator PrtR
PA0647		2.8	1.5780	0.0295	0.5636	0.2822	HP
PA0648		4.0	1.6790	0.0219	0.4198	0.0455	HP
PA0656		3.4	2.2030	0.0264	0.6479	0.0559	Pr. HIT family protein
PA0665		2.5	1.7710	0.0855	0.7084	0.1416	CHP
PA0669		2.1	1.3620	0.0159	0.6486	0.0856	Pr. DNA polymerase alpha chain
PA0670		7.0	1.9590	0.0678	0.2799	0.1008	HP
PA0671		22.9	2.4790	0.0070	0.1083	0.0565	HP
PA0672	<i>hemO</i>	24.1	1.9160	0.0007	0.0795	0.2338	heme oxygenase
PA0673		3.6	1.7200	0.0642	0.4778	0.1769	HP
PA0689		2.2	1.4270	0.0265	0.6486	0.0555	HP
PA0713		3.3	1.6330	0.0290	0.4948	0.0387	HP
PA0715		3.4	2.3080	0.0615	0.6788	0.1683	HP
PA0716		2.2	1.4270	0.1209	0.6486	0.0457	HP
PA0729		6.2	2.2010	0.0064	0.3550	0.0532	HP
PA0732		2.7	1.6350	0.0164	0.6056	0.0145	HP
PA0737		2.3	1.5500	0.0136	0.6739	0.0515	HP
PA0738		4.1	1.2450	0.2089	0.3037	0.3214	CHP
PA0739		2.5	1.4860	0.0050	0.5944	0.0065	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0743		4.0	1.8210	0.0349	0.4553	0.1525	Pr. 3-hydroxyisobutyrate dehydrogenase
PA0747		2.6	1.8750	0.0811	0.7212	0.3031	Pr. aldehyde dehydrogenase
PA0784		3.6	1.9620	0.0297	0.5450	0.0144	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0791		2.7	1.4380	0.0043	0.5326	0.0385	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0805		3.3	1.5730	0.0424	0.4767	0.0201	HP
PA0808		3.3	1.3090	0.0365	0.3967	0.1713	HP
PA0810		2.3	1.8150	0.0364	0.7891	0.0676	Pr. haloacid dehalogenase
PA0815		5.1	1.8250	0.0106	0.3578	0.0106	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0816		2.7	1.6550	0.0139	0.6130	0.0631	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0820		3.2	2.1280	0.0440	0.6650	0.0821	HP
PA0821		2.5	1.5040	0.0069	0.6016	0.0181	HP
PA0822		2.1	1.3770	0.0659	0.6557	0.1099	HP
PA0825		6.9	1.5680	0.0123	0.2272	0.2855	HP
PA0826		7.2	2.5780	0.0052	0.3581	0.0065	HP
PA0830		5.6	1.9510	0.0909	0.3484	0.0201	HP
PA0836		4.3	2.1780	0.0107	0.5065	0.0030	Pr. acetate kinase
PA0840		2.3	1.6630	0.3190	0.7230	0.0754	Pr. oxidoreductase
PA0841		2.5	1.8390	0.0504	0.7356	0.0400	HP
PA0848		19.3	3.0440	0.0057	0.1577	0.0680	Pr. alkyl hydroperoxide reductase
PA0849	<i>trxB2</i>	14.2	3.2070	0.0221	0.2258	0.1031	thioredoxin reductase 2
PA0862		6.4	1.8640	0.0109	0.2913	0.0098	HP
PA0874		2.9	1.2760	0.0084	0.4400	0.1300	HP
PA0876		2.3	1.5740	0.0097	0.6843	0.0255	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0877		2.1	1.3130	0.0260	0.6252	0.0959	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0895	<i>aruC</i>	2.3	1.3770	0.0242	0.5987	0.0343	N-succinylglutamate 5-semialdehyde dehydrogenase
PA0906		7.7	2.1840	0.0037	0.2836	0.0089	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0907		2.7	2.2010	0.0307	0.8152	0.0237	HP

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PA0922		10.0	2.2430	0.0015	0.2243	0.0029	HP
PA0923	<i>dinP</i>	2.7	1.7360	0.0150	0.6430	0.0871	DNA damage inducible protein P
PA0931		5.1	1.3340	0.1037	0.2616	0.0510	siderophore receptor protein
PA0941		2.4	1.4020	0.0435	0.5842	0.2407	HP
PA0942		3.3	1.7490	0.0235	0.5300	0.0240	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0962		15.1	2.2320	0.0048	0.1478	0.0001	Pr. dna-binding stress protein
PA0979		2.3	1.5000	0.1024	0.6522	0.0531	CHP
PA0980		2.1	1.6440	0.1034	0.7829	0.0959	HP
PA0982		2.7	1.4980	0.0350	0.5548	0.0378	HP
PA0983		5.2	2.4870	0.0322	0.4783	0.0111	CHP
PA0990		5.3	2.4590	0.0661	0.4640	0.2563	CHP
PA0995	<i>ogt</i>	3.0	1.7210	0.0849	0.5737	0.0050	methylated-DNA--protein-cysteine methyltransferase
PA1029		2.5	1.5880	0.0122	0.6352	0.0203	HP
PA1035		6.1	1.9680	0.0331	0.3226	0.0400	HP
PA1040		2.3	1.9630	0.0488	0.8535	0.0645	HP
PA1041		4.1	3.0540	0.0599	0.7449	0.0456	Pr. outer membrane protein precursor
PA1051		9.7	3.3060	0.1615	0.3408	0.0420	Pr. transporter
PA1052		5.4	1.9120	0.1141	0.3541	0.1356	CHP
PA1077	<i>flgB</i>	2.6	2.0110	0.0111	0.7735	0.0001	flagellar basal-body rod protein FlgB
PA1078	<i>flgC</i>	2.2	1.6500	0.0476	0.7500	0.0986	flagellar basal-body rod protein FlgC
PA1081	<i>flgF</i>	2.3	1.5610	0.0422	0.6787	0.0238	flagellar basal-body rod protein FlgF
PA1082	<i>flgG</i>	2.7	1.7110	0.0266	0.6337	0.0390	flagellar basal-body rod protein FlgG
PA1095		2.6	1.8070	0.0182	0.6950	0.0313	HP
PA1096		3.5	1.5020	0.0619	0.4291	0.0770	HP
PA1097	<i>fleQ</i>	2.8	1.6760	0.0221	0.5986	0.0228	transcriptional regulator FleQ
PA1106		3.9	1.6650	0.0044	0.4269	0.1214	HP
PA1122		5.1	2.1250	0.0068	0.4167	0.0295	Pr. peptide deformylase
PA1124	<i>dgt</i>	2.6	1.8150	0.0190	0.6981	0.0154	deoxyguanosinetriphosphate triphosphohydrolase
PA1135		4.1	2.0360	0.0140	0.4966	0.0215	CHP
PA1137		2.3	1.2840	0.0084	0.5583	0.1877	Pr. oxidoreductase
PA1138		2.6	1.4700	0.0108	0.5654	0.0442	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1166		4.8	1.5750	0.0623	0.3281	0.0801	HP
PA1175	<i>napD</i>	2.9	1.9650	0.0770	0.6776	0.2049	NapD protein of periplasmic nitrate reductase
PA1176	<i>napF</i>	45.3	3.1090	0.0543	0.0686	0.3505	ferredoxin protein NapF
PA1177	<i>napE</i>	5.0	2.9430	0.0489	0.5886	0.0222	periplasmic nitrate reductase protein NapE
PA1190		10.4	5.8970	0.0255	0.5670	0.0313	CHP
PA1191		2.2	1.1800	0.0709	0.5364	0.0252	HP
PA1209		3.0	1.8520	0.0179	0.6173	0.0050	HP
PA1229		4.7	2.0420	0.0171	0.4345	0.0221	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1230		45.0	1.7710	0.0230	0.0394	0.2376	HP
PA1256		2.8	1.3870	0.0724	0.4954	0.1983	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA1260		5.2	2.5790	0.0275	0.4960	0.0734	Pr. binding protein component of ABC transporter
PA1269		3.2	1.4260	0.0009	0.4456	0.0156	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1283		2.6	1.5410	0.0233	0.5927	0.0647	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1289		9.5	4.5310	0.0213	0.4769	0.0185	HP
PA1290		2.9	1.7600	0.0249	0.6069	0.0047	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1298		3.1	1.3670	0.0246	0.4410	0.0780	CHP
PA1300		5.1	1.8860	0.0023	0.3698	0.0111	Pr. sigma-70 factor, ECF subfamily
PA1301		5.0	2.0100	0.0178	0.4020	0.0704	Pr. transmembrane sensor
PA1302		2.8	1.4670	0.0022	0.5239	0.0700	Pr. heme utilization protein precursor

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PA1311	<i>phnX</i>	4.3	1.7570	0.1000	0.4086	0.2019	2-phosphonoacetaldehyde hydrolase
PA1316		4.3	1.4300	0.0129	0.3326	0.1199	Pr. MFS transporter
PA1322		4.1	1.3900	0.0928	0.3390	0.1172	Pr. TonB-dependent receptor
PA1323		3.3	1.7890	0.0099	0.5421	0.0800	HP
PA1324		2.9	1.5050	0.0070	0.5190	0.0155	HP
PA1328		5.5	1.5750	0.0232	0.2864	0.2044	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1347		2.1	1.5740	0.0511	0.7495	0.0419	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1348		5.0	2.6340	0.0229	0.5268	0.0515	HP
PA1362		3.2	1.6590	0.0595	0.5184	0.0223	HP
PA1366		3.0	1.7890	0.0067	0.5963	0.0605	HP
PA1368		2.4	1.3940	0.0313	0.5808	0.2470	HP
PA1369		2.1	1.7340	0.0255	0.8257	0.1306	HP
PA1376	<i>aceK</i>	3.3	2.1400	0.0243	0.6485	0.0084	isocitrate dehydrogenase kinase/phosphatase
PA1377		2.5	1.9400	0.0373	0.7760	0.0249	CHP
PA1378		2.3	1.6710	0.0553	0.7265	0.0167	HP
PA1382		5.6	1.9060	0.0587	0.3404	0.0299	Pr. type II secretion system protein
PA1386		2.5	1.5500	0.0378	0.6200	0.0921	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA1387		2.5	1.2900	0.0795	0.5160	0.3046	HP
PA1392		3.2	1.0530	0.0948	0.3291	0.1393	HP
PA1401		2.2	1.3020	0.0222	0.5918	0.0317	HP
PA1402		2.3	1.2470	0.1036	0.5422	0.1536	HP
PA1408		2.1	1.2970	0.0066	0.6176	0.0341	HP
PA1414		8.7	2.7010	0.0496	0.3105	0.0847	HP
PA1420		12.4	6.2270	0.2109	0.5022	0.0712	HP
PA1421	<i>gbuA</i>	11.5	6.8170	0.2152	0.5928	0.0080	guanidinobutyrase
PA1431	<i>rsaL</i>	2.7	1.5620	0.0174	0.5785	0.0258	regulatory protein RsaL
PA1466		12.6	2.0690	0.0008	0.1642	0.0028	HP
PA1474		2.4	1.5430	0.0497	0.6429	0.0338	HP
PA1484		3.1	1.7010	0.0353	0.5487	0.0353	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1505	<i>moaA2</i>	6.0	1.9310	0.0017	0.3218	0.0201	molybdopterin biosynthetic protein A2
PA1506		2.1	1.4270	0.0211	0.6795	0.0250	HP
PA1509		2.7	2.3850	0.0255	0.8833	0.2275	HP
PA1514		2.6	1.5430	0.0050	0.5935	0.0979	CHP
PA1515	<i>alc</i>	3.4	1.7930	0.0405	0.5274	0.0191	allantoicase
PA1516		3.2	1.8870	0.0222	0.5897	0.0067	HP
PA1517		4.4	1.8980	0.0082	0.4314	0.0034	CHP
PA1518		2.3	1.5110	0.0166	0.6570	0.2563	CHP
PA1523	<i>xdhB</i>	3.5	1.5570	0.0019	0.4449	0.0571	xanthine dehydrogenase
PA1524	<i>xdhA</i>	9.4	1.6600	0.0029	0.1766	0.2757	xanthine dehydrogenase
PA1525		3.7	1.4660	0.0068	0.3962	0.0236	Pr. alkane hydroxylase
PA1538		3.0	1.4800	0.0049	0.4933	0.0437	Pr. flavin-containing monooxygenase
PA1539		2.7	1.7240	0.0417	0.6385	0.0701	HP
PA1540		18.4	2.5380	0.0125	0.1379	0.0111	CHP
PA1541		18.0	2.2590	0.0015	0.1255	0.0231	Pr. drug efflux transporter
PA1542		5.2	1.9680	0.1470	0.3785	0.0210	HP
PA1545		4.5	2.4150	0.0215	0.5367	0.0319	HP
PA1555		3.0	1.7100	0.3832	0.5700	0.1001	Pr. cytochrome c
PA1557		3.6	2.4840	0.3393	0.6900	0.1693	Pr. cytochrome oxidase subunit (cbb3-type)
PA1558		2.7	1.5830	0.0224	0.5863	0.0224	HP
PA1561	<i>aer</i>	4.1	1.7360	0.0254	0.4234	0.0191	aerotaxis receptor Aer

Table 1 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA1562	<i>acnA</i>	2.2	1.3510	0.0822	0.6141	0.0442	aconitate hydratase 1
PA1572		2.6	1.7260	0.0085	0.6638	0.0046	CHP
PA1573		2.2	1.4910	0.0562	0.6777	0.0548	CHP
PA1603		2.2	1.4390	0.0180	0.6541	0.0219	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1604		2.8	1.4280	0.0092	0.5100	0.0424	HP
PA1605		2.3	1.3720	0.0193	0.5965	0.0205	HP
PA1607		3.8	1.7150	0.0030	0.4513	0.0044	CHP
PA1617		6.8	2.3330	0.0060	0.3431	0.0023	Pr. AMP-binding enzyme
PA1619		2.2	1.6590	0.0312	0.7541	0.1035	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1621		2.9	2.1170	0.0136	0.7300	0.0372	Pr. hydrolase
PA1645		2.3	1.7440	0.0358	0.7583	0.1196	HP
PA1648		2.8	1.9580	0.1477	0.6993	0.1419	Pr. oxidoreductase
PA1650		14.3	1.7390	0.0393	0.1216	0.3553	Pr. transporter
PA1672		6.0	2.0990	0.0306	0.3498	0.0845	HP
PA1673		3.5	2.0470	0.1317	0.5849	0.0884	HP
PA1680		2.2	1.3120	0.0099	0.5964	0.0126	HP
PA1686	<i>alkA</i>	2.8	1.7690	0.0154	0.6318	0.0141	DNA-3-methyladenine glycosidase II
PA1729		2.6	1.5390	0.0079	0.5919	0.0119	CHP
PA1730		2.2	1.6380	0.0378	0.7445	0.0641	CHP
PA1738		4.7	2.1950	0.0121	0.4670	0.0053	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1742		3.6	1.5350	0.0069	0.4264	0.0136	Pr. amidotransferase
PA1745		3.2	2.1610	0.0421	0.6753	0.1976	HP
PA1749		2.3	1.5010	0.0065	0.6526	0.0168	HP
PA1751		2.3	1.6400	0.0718	0.7130	0.1251	HP
PA1753		2.1	1.6450	0.0189	0.7833	0.0522	CHP
PA1759		3.9	2.0690	0.0051	0.5305	0.0070	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1784		2.2	1.6260	0.0126	0.7391	0.0387	HP
PA1789		3.7	1.8210	0.0257	0.4922	0.1974	HP
PA1817		4.5	2.1620	0.0056	0.4804	0.0634	HP
PA1826		3.7	1.5140	0.0015	0.4092	0.1067	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1836		2.6	1.8360	0.1420	0.7062	0.2728	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1847		2.9	1.6200	0.0384	0.5586	0.0468	CHP
PA1859		2.1	1.5350	0.0556	0.7310	0.0942	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1864		2.9	1.6440	0.0335	0.5669	0.0670	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1865		3.6	1.7710	0.0176	0.4919	0.0045	HP
PA1874		2.4	1.8150	0.0220	0.7563	0.0754	HP
PA1882		2.4	1.6900	0.0265	0.7042	0.0395	Pr. transporter
PA1885		2.2	1.8290	0.0691	0.8314	0.0708	CHP
PA1898		2.6	1.6510	0.0112	0.6350	0.0288	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1910		11.5	1.4840	0.0007	0.1290	0.2860	Pr. tonB-dependent receptor protein
PA1911		19.8	1.9760	0.0003	0.0998	0.0602	Pr. transmembrane sensor
PA1912		10.5	3.2300	0.0710	0.3076	0.0032	Pr. sigma-70 factor, ECF subfamily
PA1915		3.1	1.3940	0.0051	0.4497	0.0834	HP
PA1935		2.3	1.6960	0.1181	0.7374	0.0774	HP
PA1936		2.7	1.2810	0.0783	0.4744	0.2987	HP
PA1942		8.0	2.2580	0.0734	0.2823	0.0397	HP
PA1943		2.5	1.7630	0.0366	0.7052	0.0162	HP
PA1944		2.2	1.5330	0.0246	0.6968	0.1151	HP
PA1946	<i>rbsB</i>	5.0	2.3320	0.0073	0.4664	0.0261	binding protein component precursor of ABC ribose transporter

Table 1 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA1947	<i>rbsA</i>	3.5	1.6490	0.0064	0.4711	0.0096	ribose transport protein RbsA
PA1948	<i>rbsC</i>	2.5	1.4870	0.0057	0.5948	0.0665	membrane protein component of ABC ribose transporter
PA1951		26.7	3.2280	0.0356	0.1209	0.0497	HP
PA1954		3.9	1.1290	0.0084	0.2895	0.3063	HP
PA1963		5.0	1.8690	0.0333	0.3738	0.2012	HP
PA1991		2.3	1.6980	0.0694	0.7383	0.0284	Pr. iron-containing alcohol dehydrogenase
PA1997		3.8	1.8850	0.0386	0.4961	0.0013	Pr. AMP-binding enzyme
PA2016		3.3	1.6440	0.0024	0.4982	0.0140	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2017		2.8	1.9280	0.0097	0.6886	0.0129	HP
PA2021		2.7	2.0260	0.0216	0.7504	0.0536	HP
PA2024		5.2	2.2600	0.0628	0.4346	0.0048	Pr. ring-cleaving dioxygenase
PA2025	<i>gor</i>	3.6	1.6260	0.0130	0.4517	0.0140	glutathione reductase
PA2033		13.1	2.2120	0.0037	0.1689	0.0600	HP
PA2034		13.9	2.2020	0.0126	0.1584	0.2252	HP
PA2047		2.5	1.7320	0.0392	0.6928	0.0616	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2052	<i>cynS</i>	2.3	1.6620	0.0183	0.7226	0.0002	cyanate lyase
PA2053	<i>cynT</i>	4.1	2.0540	0.0093	0.5010	0.0223	carbonate dehydratase
PA2075		3.8	1.3750	0.1357	0.3618	0.1229	HP
PA2082		3.0	2.0280	0.0235	0.6760	0.0232	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2100		4.6	2.1290	0.0050	0.4628	0.0004	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2101		6.2	1.6980	0.0186	0.2739	0.0734	CHP
PA2102		3.3	1.6870	0.0054	0.5112	0.0414	HP
PA2103		2.1	1.5960	0.0227	0.7600	0.0836	Pr. molybdopterin biosynthesis protein MoeB
PA2120		3.1	1.7140	0.0657	0.5529	0.0662	HP
PA2121		4.8	2.4140	0.0290	0.5029	0.0041	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2122		2.6	1.3180	0.0309	0.5069	0.0542	HP
PA2123		2.4	1.5220	0.0343	0.6342	0.0315	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2127		3.4	2.3270	0.0178	0.6844	0.1007	CHP
PA2145		3.4	1.8120	0.0269	0.5329	0.0323	HP
PA2174		2.8	1.9480	0.0590	0.6957	0.1338	HP
PA2176		7.7	1.5320	0.0272	0.1990	0.1566	HP
PA2182		2.4	1.5800	0.0161	0.6583	0.0113	HP
PA2206		2.7	1.7150	0.0195	0.6352	0.0048	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2209		3.2	1.6550	0.1182	0.5172	0.2460	HP
PA2210		2.1	1.4130	0.0692	0.6729	0.0741	Pr. MFS transporter
PA2211		3.7	1.5000	0.0015	0.4054	0.1642	CHP
PA2212		5.1	1.2960	0.0072	0.2541	0.3008	CHP
PA2219	<i>opdE</i>	2.8	1.4250	0.0451	0.5089	0.1544	membrane protein OpdE
PA2220		2.9	1.6460	0.0246	0.5676	0.0217	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2246	<i>bkdR</i>	2.4	1.6050	0.0589	0.6688	0.1049	transcriptional regulator BkdR
PA2247	<i>bkdA1</i>	2.4	1.5180	0.0107	0.6325	0.0043	2-oxoisovalerate dehydrogenase (alpha subunit)
PA2259	<i>ptxS</i>	8.5	2.0590	0.0008	0.2422	0.0041	transcriptional regulator PtxS
PA2260		7.6	2.7650	0.0122	0.3638	0.0004	HP
PA2261		8.4	2.8960	0.0127	0.3448	0.0014	Pr. 2-ketogluconate kinase
PA2262		4.9	2.5420	0.0276	0.5188	0.0071	Pr. 2-ketogluconate transporter
PA2263		2.3	1.5050	0.0317	0.6543	0.0014	Pr. 2-hydroxyacid dehydrogenase
PA2288		23.5	2.0670	0.0015	0.0880	0.0085	HP
PA2320	<i>gntR</i>	6.2	1.8590	0.0011	0.2998	0.0131	transcriptional regulator GntR
PA2337	<i>mtlR</i>	2.9	1.4570	0.0272	0.5024	0.0236	transcriptional regulator MtlR
PA2363		2.1	1.5100	0.1046	0.7190	0.1437	HP

Table 1 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA2364		5.2	2.3030	0.0133	0.4429	0.0286	HP
PA2365		2.7	2.0300	0.0235	0.7519	0.0449	CHP
PA2372		3.7	1.7730	0.0180	0.4792	0.0395	HP
PA2373		3.6	1.3260	0.0302	0.3683	0.2821	CHP
PA2375		3.6	1.3940	0.0031	0.3872	0.1136	HP
PA2417		4.2	2.4570	0.0485	0.5850	0.0493	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2422		2.4	1.5110	0.0271	0.6296	0.0455	HP
PA2423		2.7	1.2810	0.0540	0.4744	0.0544	HP
PA2426	<i>pvdS</i>	12.7	2.5780	0.0140	0.2030	0.0118	sigma factor PvdS
PA2432		4.1	1.5510	0.0634	0.3783	0.1158	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2433		2.8	1.5560	0.0110	0.5557	0.0032	HP
PA2456		2.1	1.4960	0.1471	0.7124	0.0309	HP
PA2457		3.4	1.9510	0.0282	0.5738	0.0032	HP
PA2466		4.8	1.8560	0.0123	0.3867	0.3172	Pr. TonB-dependent receptor
PA2467		4.7	1.6780	0.0147	0.3570	0.1262	Pr. transmembrane sensor
PA2468		19.3	1.9800	0.0588	0.1026	0.2844	Pr. sigma-70 factor, ECF subfamily
PA2481		3.0	2.0230	0.0290	0.6743	0.0480	HP
PA2482		3.1	1.8920	0.0239	0.6103	0.0432	Pr. cytochrome c
PA2483		5.0	1.7630	0.0010	0.3526	0.0038	CHP
PA2484		2.1	1.3720	0.0152	0.6533	0.0218	CHP
PA2485		15.2	2.4790	0.0043	0.1631	0.0220	HP
PA2486		9.4	2.1910	0.0031	0.2331	0.0050	HP
PA2487		2.9	1.4060	0.0191	0.4848	0.0408	HP
PA2501		3.6	2.1180	0.0482	0.5883	0.0113	HP
PA2504		2.5	2.2300	0.0246	0.8920	0.1081	HP
PA2519	<i>xyIS</i>	2.8	2.1280	0.0716	0.7600	0.0024	transcriptional regulator XylS
PA2523		4.0	1.8640	0.0105	0.4660	0.0013	Pr. two-component response regulator
PA2554		2.1	1.4070	0.1399	0.6700	0.2273	Pr. short-chain dehydrogenase
PA2555		3.1	2.2780	0.0268	0.7348	0.1836	Pr. AMP-binding enzyme
PA2556		2.9	1.4360	0.0467	0.4952	0.0905	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2557		5.4	2.6590	0.0520	0.4924	0.0989	Pr. AMP-binding enzyme
PA2559		2.6	1.7690	0.0693	0.6804	0.0766	HP
PA2560		3.8	1.7330	0.0284	0.4561	0.0119	HP
PA2562		2.2	1.2830	0.0186	0.5832	0.0170	HP
PA2567		2.2	1.4120	0.0179	0.6418	0.0176	HP
PA2569		2.2	1.6110	0.0323	0.7323	0.0973	HP
PA2572		5.6	2.4200	0.0522	0.4321	0.2480	Pr. two-component response regulator
PA2573		6.0	2.5070	0.0086	0.4178	0.0191	Pr. chemotaxis transducer
PA2576		2.1	1.3110	0.1571	0.6243	0.1370	HP
PA2577		10.1	1.9830	0.0051	0.1963	0.1636	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2578		3.9	1.6110	0.0104	0.4131	0.0486	Pr. acetyltransferase
PA2600		8.4	5.1520	0.2805	0.6133	0.1543	HP
PA2601		2.3	1.5200	0.0157	0.6609	0.0293	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2604		2.6	1.6130	0.0162	0.6204	0.0333	CHP
PA2621		2.3	1.4590	0.0719	0.6343	0.0381	CHP
PA2633		2.5	1.7400	0.0301	0.6960	0.0925	HP
PA2663		2.1	1.4510	0.0377	0.6910	0.0230	HP
PA2665		2.7	1.5340	0.0084	0.5681	0.0473	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2668		2.5	1.5640	0.0413	0.6256	0.0286	HP
PA2686	<i>pfeR</i>	21.1	3.5550	0.1219	0.1685	0.0425	two-component response regulator PfeR

Table 1 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA2687	<i>pfeS</i>	27.2	2.3480	0.0063	0.0863	0.0499	two-component sensor PfeS
PA2688	<i>pfeA</i>	4.3	1.6900	0.0186	0.3930	0.0729	Ferric enterobactin receptor, outer membrane PfeA precursor
PA2693		2.5	1.7680	0.0642	0.7072	0.2312	CHP
PA2696		5.0	1.3440	0.0323	0.2688	0.1513	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2707		2.9	1.6330	0.0152	0.5631	0.0536	HP
PA2713		2.4	1.7290	0.0416	0.7204	0.0050	CHP
PA2718		3.4	2.6050	0.0435	0.7662	0.0454	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2723		4.5	1.9540	0.0051	0.4342	0.0008	HP
PA2725		2.2	1.2980	0.0180	0.5900	0.0674	Pr. chaperone
PA2737		2.3	1.3610	0.0473	0.5917	0.0248	CHP
PA2738	<i>himA</i>	2.3	1.3970	0.1469	0.6074	0.0235	integration host factor, alpha subunit
PA2746		3.0	1.9130	0.0748	0.6377	0.0339	HP
PA2751		2.1	1.2700	0.0177	0.6048	0.0641	CHP
PA2754		6.7	2.0290	0.0024	0.3028	0.0344	CHP
PA2756		3.0	2.1500	0.0264	0.7167	0.1671	HP
PA2758		2.3	1.4530	0.0023	0.6317	0.0300	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2759		2.1	1.2430	0.0402	0.5919	0.0510	HP
PA2788		2.6	1.8940	0.0383	0.7285	0.0747	Pr. chemotaxis transducer
PA2790		2.3	1.5490	0.0334	0.6735	0.0788	HP
PA2794		2.6	1.6440	0.0462	0.6323	0.0526	HP
PA2799		3.6	1.6390	0.0305	0.4553	0.2836	HP
PA2805		4.0	1.6410	0.1264	0.4103	0.0262	HP
PA2820		3.4	2.6780	0.0460	0.7876	0.0909	HP
PA2821		3.4	2.0760	0.0264	0.6106	0.0364	Pr. glutathione S-transferase
PA2825		18.3	2.5890	0.0039	0.1415	0.0029	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2826		22.5	2.5050	0.0042	0.1113	0.0004	Pr. glutathione peroxidase
PA2827		6.8	1.9090	0.0005	0.2807	0.0021	CHP
PA2839		3.3	1.4380	0.0122	0.4358	0.0192	CHP
PA2843		3.6	2.2720	0.0370	0.6311	0.0046	Pr. aldolase
PA2845		4.7	2.0070	0.0466	0.4270	0.0189	HP
PA2846		3.4	1.7410	0.0045	0.5121	0.0263	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2848		2.5	1.4980	0.0030	0.5992	0.0275	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2849		15.0	2.1510	0.0020	0.1434	0.0008	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2850	<i>ohr</i>	22.5	2.7010	0.0050	0.1200	0.0015	organic hydroperoxide resistance protein
PA2868		17.4	2.3070	0.0100	0.1326	0.0096	HP
PA2869		3.0	1.4610	0.0060	0.4870	0.0086	HP
PA2879		3.2	1.8540	0.0106	0.5794	0.0049	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2883		5.3	1.9110	0.0040	0.3606	0.0027	HP
PA2885		3.5	2.3420	0.0217	0.6691	0.0179	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2929		5.5	3.8030	0.0697	0.6915	0.1538	HP
PA2930		2.4	1.3570	0.0308	0.5654	0.0821	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2937		9.9	2.1620	0.0119	0.2184	0.2010	HP
PA2989		2.1	1.4570	0.0451	0.6938	0.2724	HP
PA3006	<i>psrA</i>	4.9	2.1270	0.0200	0.4341	0.0178	transcriptional regulator PsrA
PA3007	<i>lexA</i>	11.5	2.0870	0.0003	0.1815	0.0003	repressor protein LexA
PA3008		13.9	2.6000	0.0024	0.1871	0.0044	HP
PA3017		2.8	1.9630	0.0087	0.7011	0.0156	CHP
PA3032	<i>snr1</i>	2.3	1.3130	0.0085	0.5709	0.0162	cytochrome c Snr1
PA3034		2.8	1.3710	0.0081	0.4896	0.0720	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA3040		2.4	1.7410	0.0595	0.7254	0.0611	CHP

Table 1 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA3041		2.2	1.4750	0.0313	0.6705	0.0936	HP
PA3044		2.4	1.2530	0.1399	0.5221	0.2362	Pr. two-component sensor
PA3049	<i>rmf</i>	12.0	2.3430	0.0061	0.1953	0.0523	ribosome modulation factor
PA3051		4.9	1.7470	0.1251	0.3565	0.1846	HP
PA3052		2.4	1.6200	0.0231	0.6750	0.0215	HP
PA3056		2.6	1.8380	0.0743	0.7069	0.0591	HP
PA3057		2.6	1.7550	0.0122	0.6750	0.0346	HP
PA3089		10.8	1.9390	0.0052	0.1795	0.1357	HP
PA3123		2.8	1.7870	0.0193	0.6382	0.0677	CHP
PA3124		3.0	1.8770	0.0209	0.6257	0.0801	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA3127		2.7	1.6340	0.0165	0.6052	0.0123	HP
PA3128		3.3	1.8040	0.0110	0.5467	0.0773	Pr. short-chain dehydrogenase
PA3142		4.1	1.8990	0.0603	0.4632	0.1814	HP
PA3161	<i>himD</i>	4.7	2.1240	0.0078	0.4519	0.0101	integration host factor beta subunit
PA3177		2.3	1.9560	0.0383	0.8504	0.1877	HP
PA3195	<i>gapA</i>	2.2	1.8240	0.0165	0.8291	0.0104	glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase
PA3211		2.4	1.5650	0.0223	0.6521	0.0166	Pr. permease of ABC transporter
PA3216		2.3	1.5290	0.0369	0.6648	0.0655	HP
PA3225		2.2	1.6780	0.0165	0.7627	0.0298	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA3234		2.6	1.7590	0.0461	0.6765	0.0680	Pr. sodium:solute symporter
PA3235		3.6	2.2660	0.0346	0.6294	0.0233	CHP
PA3237		218.0	2.7660	0.0038	0.0127	0.0035	HP
PA3238		4.4	1.8470	0.0051	0.4198	0.0048	HP
PA3239		3.1	1.8670	0.0074	0.6023	0.0038	CHP
PA3240		5.8	3.0420	0.0377	0.5245	0.0120	CHP
PA3248		2.1	1.3980	0.0019	0.6657	0.0087	HP
PA3260		2.1	1.6800	0.0853	0.8000	0.1055	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA3277		3.1	2.1230	0.2062	0.6848	0.2206	Pr. short-chain dehydrogenase
PA3278		5.3	1.5710	0.0464	0.2964	0.2647	HP
PA3281		5.9	1.9060	0.0269	0.3231	0.0178	HP
PA3282		7.4	2.3150	0.0325	0.3128	0.1339	HP
PA3283		10.3	2.1230	0.0109	0.2061	0.0016	CHP
PA3284		4.4	2.1250	0.0153	0.4830	0.0074	HP
PA3286		2.3	1.7730	0.0446	0.7709	0.0669	HP
PA3287		80.0	2.2990	0.0004	0.0287	0.0013	CHP
PA3288		4.0	2.4140	0.0070	0.6035	0.0059	HP
PA3289		6.2	1.8280	0.0067	0.2948	0.1625	HP
PA3306		4.6	1.9720	0.0078	0.4287	0.0042	HP
PA3307		2.7	1.6830	0.0648	0.6233	0.0097	HP
PA3320		8.0	1.5800	0.0371	0.1975	0.1512	HP
PA3342		2.8	1.7110	0.0349	0.6111	0.0819	HP
PA3343		6.3	1.7290	0.0140	0.2744	0.2524	HP
PA3347		2.5	1.6250	0.0342	0.6500	0.1034	HP
PA3348		2.1	1.7290	0.0669	0.8233	0.0700	Pr. chemotaxis protein methyltransferase
PA3349		2.7	2.1560	0.0280	0.7985	0.0107	Pr. chemotaxis protein
PA3350		2.2	1.6390	0.0229	0.7450	0.0327	HP
PA3351		2.3	1.3740	0.0028	0.5974	0.0263	HP
PA3366	<i>amiE</i>	3.3	2.1270	0.0134	0.6445	0.1642	aliphatic amidase
PA3369		3.1	1.9890	0.0107	0.6416	0.0020	HP
PA3370		2.8	1.8730	0.0645	0.6689	0.1388	HP

Table 1 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA3371		2.9	1.7100	0.0736	0.5897	0.2822	HP
PA3385		2.7	1.5890	0.0103	0.5885	0.0251	HP
PA3399		2.8	1.5160	0.0186	0.5414	0.1911	HP
PA3408	<i>hasR</i>	2.7	1.1270	0.1610	0.4174	0.1733	Haem uptake outer membrane receptor HasR precursor
PA3409		2.1	1.4700	0.0374	0.7000	0.0862	Pr. transmembrane sensor
PA3410		3.3	1.6950	0.0067	0.5136	0.0314	Pr. sigma-70 factor, ECF subfamily
PA3413		2.9	2.2000	0.0607	0.7586	0.2267	CHP
PA3417		5.3	2.3170	0.0481	0.4372	0.2773	Pr. pyruvate dehydrogenase E1 component, alpha subunit
PA3418	<i>ldh</i>	6.8	2.5550	0.0346	0.3757	0.0095	leucine dehydrogenase
PA3419		3.5	1.9200	0.0233	0.5486	0.0268	HP
PA3423		2.7	1.6000	0.0185	0.5926	0.0212	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA3427		15.4	2.0830	0.1478	0.1353	0.1198	Pr. short-chain dehydrogenases
PA3430		7.4	2.0740	0.0379	0.2803	0.1954	Pr. aldolase
PA3433		2.6	1.4670	0.0260	0.5642	0.0600	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA3451		9.8	1.4760	0.0354	0.1506	0.1152	HP
PA3458		2.5	1.5400	0.0117	0.6160	0.0097	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA3459		9.2	2.1490	0.0115	0.2336	0.1119	Pr. glutamine amidotransferase
PA3460		7.3	2.2820	0.0355	0.3126	0.0042	Pr. acetyltransferase
PA3496		3.5	1.6630	0.1589	0.4751	0.0302	HP
PA3520		8.8	4.0770	0.3090	0.4633	0.2006	HP
PA3526		4.3	1.8380	0.0111	0.4274	0.0693	Pr. outer membrane protein precursor
PA3530		19.2	4.5430	0.1520	0.2366	0.1925	CHP
PA3534		2.7	1.5690	0.1649	0.5811	0.2757	Pr. oxidoreductase
PA3565		3.0	1.7200	0.0177	0.5733	0.0239	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA3571	<i>mmsR</i>	3.5	1.6690	0.0543	0.4769	0.0558	transcriptional regulator MmsR
PA3572		2.6	1.6620	0.0358	0.6392	0.1205	HP
PA3576		2.3	1.5740	0.0327	0.6843	0.0466	HP
PA3577		2.8	1.5190	0.0857	0.5425	0.0198	HP
PA3581	<i>glpF</i>	8.6	2.7410	0.0216	0.3187	0.0116	glycerol uptake facilitator protein
PA3582	<i>glpK</i>	5.7	2.4710	0.0192	0.4335	0.0180	glycerol kinase
PA3584	<i>glpD</i>	15.4	2.1950	0.0356	0.1425	0.0261	glycerol-3-phosphate dehydrogenase
PA3594		2.4	1.5620	0.0060	0.6508	0.0096	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA3600		26.0	2.0860	0.0814	0.0802	0.0571	CHP
PA3601		6.5	1.8790	0.0949	0.2891	0.1543	CHP
PA3614		3.4	1.6850	0.0041	0.4956	0.0033	HP
PA3615		2.8	1.9400	0.0126	0.6929	0.0052	HP
PA3617	<i>recA</i>	2.8	1.6090	0.0018	0.5746	0.0023	RecA protein
PA3622	<i>rpoS</i>	2.2	1.7400	0.0235	0.7909	0.0554	sigma factor RpoS
PA3662		6.1	2.2490	0.0083	0.3687	0.0117	HP
PA3684		2.7	1.8570	0.0242	0.6878	0.1213	HP
PA3687	<i>ppc</i>	2.9	1.8880	0.0356	0.6510	0.0398	phosphoenolpyruvate carboxylase
PA3688		2.1	2.0360	0.0451	0.9695	0.0784	HP
PA3689		3.2	1.6490	0.0040	0.5153	0.0056	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA3690		2.5	1.5750	0.1138	0.6300	0.0558	Pr. metal-transporting P-type ATPase
PA3691		6.8	2.1210	0.0024	0.3119	0.0044	HP
PA3692		4.3	2.2990	0.0133	0.5347	0.0147	Pr. outer membrane protein precursor
PA3698		2.2	1.9630	0.0916	0.8923	0.0822	HP
PA3723		3.3	2.3730	0.0405	0.7191	0.2564	Pr. FMN oxidoreductase
PA3734		3.1	1.6540	0.0223	0.5335	0.0374	HP
PA3740		4.1	2.0700	0.0256	0.5049	0.0128	HP

Table 1 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA3754		2.6	1.8130	0.0148	0.6973	0.0006	HP
PA3755		2.3	2.0020	0.0579	0.8704	0.0140	CHP
PA3756		2.2	1.5560	0.0263	0.7073	0.0425	HP
PA3757		2.8	2.1400	0.0757	0.7643	0.0772	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA3762		2.5	1.6160	0.0334	0.6464	0.0730	HP
PA3792	<i>leuA</i>	3.0	1.5270	0.0054	0.5090	0.0056	2-isopropylmalate synthase
PA3819		3.3	1.5260	0.0026	0.4624	0.0432	CHP
PA3841	<i>exoS</i>	2.8	1.6590	0.0555	0.5925	0.0070	exoenzyme S
PA3844		2.6	1.5790	0.0329	0.6073	0.0961	HP
PA3845		2.3	1.3970	0.0937	0.6074	0.1006	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA3846		3.2	2.0460	0.0222	0.6394	0.0270	HP
PA3850		2.1	1.4860	0.0052	0.7076	0.0067	HP
PA3852		2.5	1.5380	0.0096	0.6152	0.0096	HP
PA3865		2.3	1.3730	0.0094	0.5970	0.0497	Pr. amino acid binding protein
PA3881		3.2	1.9240	0.0642	0.6013	0.0295	HP
PA3882		2.1	1.7380	0.0869	0.8276	0.1161	HP
PA3899		8.3	2.1590	0.0026	0.2601	0.0194	Pr. sigma-70 factor, ECF subfamily
PA3900		5.4	2.0650	0.0158	0.3824	0.1432	Pr. transmembrane sensor
PA3919		16.2	2.4990	0.0101	0.1543	0.0100	CHP
PA3927		3.6	1.7900	0.0392	0.4972	0.1472	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA3944		2.3	1.5200	0.0930	0.6609	0.0589	CHP
PA3945		9.2	2.6010	0.0087	0.2827	0.0302	CHP
PA3969		3.1	1.8060	0.0345	0.5826	0.0193	CHP
PA3970	<i>amn</i>	4.3	1.8720	0.0021	0.4353	0.0108	AMP nucleosidase
PA3971		4.3	2.1920	0.0251	0.5098	0.0041	HP
PA3972		7.6	3.3830	0.0141	0.4451	0.0091	Pr. acyl-CoA dehydrogenase
PA3973		10.4	3.1400	0.0358	0.3019	0.0235	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA3981		2.9	1.5150	0.0009	0.5224	0.0043	CHP
PA3982		2.3	1.4840	0.0065	0.6452	0.0168	CHP
PA3983		2.2	1.7360	0.0467	0.7891	0.0668	CHP
PA3986		3.0	1.8760	0.0072	0.6253	0.0021	HP
PA3995		4.9	1.5780	0.0175	0.3220	0.2853	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA4009		2.2	1.5730	0.0755	0.7150	0.0388	HP
PA4021		2.8	2.3070	0.0422	0.8239	0.0385	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA4026		3.2	1.7740	0.0046	0.5544	0.0037	Pr. acetyltransferase
PA4027		2.5	1.7850	0.0130	0.7140	0.0042	HP
PA4040		2.2	1.6770	0.0778	0.7623	0.0103	HP
PA4070		18.1	2.2540	0.0280	0.1245	0.0812	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA4080		2.6	1.3540	0.0144	0.5208	0.0311	Pr. response regulator
PA4090		7.8	1.9620	0.0007	0.2515	0.0640	HP
PA4094		5.6	2.0780	0.0047	0.3711	0.0003	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA4108		2.2	1.5160	0.0262	0.6891	0.0099	HP
PA4111		3.6	1.8990	0.0092	0.5275	0.0051	HP
PA4115		3.2	1.9870	0.0274	0.6209	0.0210	CHP
PA4155		6.2	1.8290	0.0148	0.2950	0.1518	HP
PA4156		12.4	2.0290	0.0015	0.1636	0.0073	Pr. TonB-dependent receptor
PA4158	<i>fepC</i>	15.9	1.7240	0.0298	0.1084	0.2452	ferric enterobactin transport protein FepC
PA4159	<i>fepB</i>	6.2	2.0700	0.1105	0.3339	0.1241	ferric enterobactin-binding periplasmic protein precursor FepB
PA4160	<i>fepD</i>	6.5	1.9200	0.0294	0.2954	0.0448	ferric enterobactin transport protein FepD
PA4161	<i>fepG</i>	6.9	1.4170	0.0350	0.2054	0.0698	ferric enterobactin transport protein FepG

Table 1 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA4168		14.9	2.2530	0.0078	0.1512	0.0763	Pr. TonB-dependent receptor
PA4170		4.6	1.7810	0.0078	0.3872	0.1799	HP
PA4184		2.4	1.6260	0.0649	0.6775	0.1455	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA4201	<i>ddlA</i>	2.8	1.5900	0.0325	0.5679	0.0310	D-alanine-D-alanine ligase A
PA4202		5.2	1.5760	0.0041	0.3031	0.0240	HP
PA4203		3.5	1.7420	0.0061	0.4977	0.0112	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA4204		2.3	1.4140	0.0090	0.6148	0.0453	CHP
PA4205		2.4	1.3500	0.0714	0.5625	0.0375	HP
PA4219		29.4	3.4170	0.0672	0.1162	0.1619	HP
PA4221	<i>fptA</i>	44.1	7.7130	0.0191	0.1749	0.2192	Fe(III)-pyochelin outer membrane receptor precursor
PA4227	<i>pchR</i>	45.0	1.9880	0.0004	0.0442	0.2436	transcriptional regulator PchR
PA4228	<i>pchD</i>	15.2	6.0310	0.0159	0.3968	0.1529	pyochelin biosynthesis protein PchD
PA4230	<i>pchB</i>	14.5	4.8520	0.0220	0.3346	0.1811	salicylate biosynthesis protein PchB
PA4235	<i>bfrA</i>	2.1	1.7400	0.0762	0.8286	0.1478	bacterioferritin
PA4236	<i>katA</i>	34.1	2.2470	0.0023	0.0659	0.0090	catalase
PA4287		5.6	1.6970	0.1280	0.3030	0.1180	HP
PA4288		10.6	2.3280	0.0167	0.2196	0.0002	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA4293		4.0	1.5480	0.2015	0.3870	0.0939	Pr. two-component sensor
PA4294		4.7	1.6410	0.0116	0.3491	0.0297	HP
PA4296		8.0	2.0150	0.0045	0.2519	0.0033	Pr. two-component response regulator
PA4305		2.1	1.7740	0.0627	0.8448	0.1158	HP
PA4306		3.5	1.9070	0.0933	0.5449	0.0734	HP
PA4311		4.1	2.4240	0.0295	0.5912	0.0189	CHP
PA4315	<i>mvaT</i>	2.2	1.4950	0.0128	0.6795	0.0071	transcriptional regulator MvaT, P16 subunit
PA4324		2.8	1.6340	0.0662	0.5836	0.0450	HP
PA4335		3.3	1.7010	0.0277	0.5155	0.1210	HP
PA4336		2.8	1.8440	0.0086	0.6586	0.0099	CHP
PA4345		8.7	2.1590	0.0426	0.2482	0.2015	HP
PA4352		2.3	1.4130	0.1210	0.6143	0.1496	CHP
PA4353		2.3	1.5430	0.0335	0.6709	0.0173	CHP
PA4354		3.4	1.8970	0.0162	0.5579	0.0113	CHP
PA4361		2.6	1.6250	0.0142	0.6250	0.0686	Pr. oxidoreductase
PA4367		2.5	1.7630	0.0307	0.7052	0.1884	CHP
PA4369		2.1	1.7190	0.0539	0.8186	0.1099	HP
PA4392		2.1	1.4890	0.0825	0.7090	0.0798	CHP
PA4435		3.6	2.1160	0.0197	0.5878	0.0145	Pr. acyl-CoA dehydrogenase
PA4440		2.2	1.8760	0.0715	0.8527	0.1271	HP
PA4463		2.8	1.9690	0.0215	0.7032	0.0038	CHP
PA4464	<i>ptsN</i>	2.1	1.5610	0.0106	0.7433	0.0175	nitrogen regulatory IIA protein
PA4467		8.3	2.9580	0.0078	0.3564	0.0469	HP
PA4468	<i>sodM</i>	53.0	2.7030	0.0064	0.0510	0.1173	superoxide dismutase
PA4469		105.1	2.2770	0.0002	0.0217	0.0351	HP
PA4470	<i>fumC1</i>	64.7	2.0950	0.0001	0.0324	0.0052	fumarate hydratase
PA4471		120.5	2.6260	0.0144	0.0218	0.0781	HP
PA4511		2.4	1.8580	0.0436	0.7742	0.1062	CHP
PA4514		2.6	1.1220	0.1122	0.4315	0.1839	Pr. outer membrane receptor for iron transport
PA4515		6.3	1.6110	0.0028	0.2557	0.1296	CHP
PA4516		3.5	1.7560	0.0519	0.5017	0.1482	HP
PA4520		2.8	1.7450	0.0504	0.6232	0.1473	Pr. chemotaxis transducer
PA4522	<i>ampD</i>	2.8	2.0360	0.0421	0.7271	0.0347	beta-lactamase expression regulator AmpD

Table 1 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA4523		2.4	1.7310	0.0186	0.7213	0.0517	HP
PA4525	<i>pilA</i>	3.1	1.4930	0.0069	0.4816	0.0290	type 4 fimbrial precursor PilA
PA4535		9.7	2.3380	0.0294	0.2410	0.0074	HP
PA4536		4.9	1.8190	0.0032	0.3712	0.0211	HP
PA4537		3.2	1.8010	0.0113	0.5628	0.0405	HP
PA4555	<i>pilY2</i>	2.1	1.3510	0.2145	0.6433	0.0904	type 4 fimbrial biogenesis protein PilY2
PA4570		14.5	3.1180	0.0368	0.2150	0.0070	HP
PA4575		6.2	2.5260	0.0515	0.4074	0.0027	HP
PA4577		9.9	1.5330	0.0314	0.1548	0.2707	HP
PA4582		21.4	3.8430	0.0060	0.1796	0.0041	CHP
PA4583		14.0	4.0880	0.0103	0.2920	0.0126	CHP
PA4584		7.7	3.8540	0.0150	0.5005	0.0562	CHP
PA4608		5.2	2.0710	0.0048	0.3983	0.0080	HP
PA4611		19.0	2.5820	0.0060	0.1359	0.0174	HP
PA4612		21.4	4.9570	0.0220	0.2316	0.0041	CHP
PA4613	<i>katB</i>	56.9	3.3220	0.0033	0.0584	0.0119	catalase
PA4614	<i>mscL</i>	4.1	2.0610	0.0088	0.5027	0.0358	conductance mechanosensitive channel
PA4615		4.8	1.8880	0.0048	0.3933	0.0092	Pr. oxidoreductase
PA4633		4.4	1.8960	0.0118	0.4309	0.0182	Pr. chemotaxis transducer
PA4655	<i>hemH</i>	4.9	2.7110	0.0227	0.5533	0.0177	ferrochelatase
PA4657		3.1	1.5250	0.0021	0.4919	0.0021	HP
PA4658		3.5	1.6890	0.0058	0.4826	0.0080	HP
PA4674		9.9	2.3680	0.0080	0.2392	0.1269	CHP
PA4683		16.0	1.8820	0.0004	0.1176	0.0409	HP
PA4687	<i>hitA</i>	4.0	1.5570	0.0456	0.3893	0.1772	ferric iron-binding periplasmic protein HitA
PA4688	<i>hitB</i>	2.4	1.1790	0.0738	0.4913	0.2524	iron (III)-transport system permease HitB
PA4692		2.3	1.7610	0.1583	0.7657	0.1233	CHP
PA4703		2.8	1.6440	0.0386	0.5871	0.0360	HP
PA4706		3.8	2.0750	0.0343	0.5461	0.0449	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA4707		4.7	3.0550	0.0273	0.6500	0.0483	Pr. permease of ABC transporter
PA4708		8.6	3.0660	0.0164	0.3565	0.0092	HP
PA4709		14.2	2.3640	0.0022	0.1665	0.0029	Pr. hemin degrading factor
PA4710	<i>phuR</i>	5.8	1.6190	0.0113	0.2791	0.1742	Haem/Haemoglobin uptake outer membrane PhuR precursor
PA4711		3.4	1.8110	0.0458	0.5326	0.0244	HP
PA4733	<i>acsB</i>	2.3	1.5590	0.0056	0.6778	0.0241	acetyl-coenzyme A synthetase
PA4751	<i>ftsH</i>	3.2	1.7540	0.0028	0.5481	0.0056	cell division protein FtsH
PA4763	<i>recN</i>	11.7	2.4680	0.0018	0.2109	0.0004	DNA repair protein RecN
PA4770	<i>lldP</i>	2.1	1.3840	0.1258	0.6590	0.0824	L-lactate permease
PA4787		3.1	1.9990	0.0160	0.6448	0.0248	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA4791		2.3	1.3710	0.0649	0.5961	0.0448	HP
PA4793		6.7	1.9700	0.0022	0.2940	0.0075	HP
PA4794		3.8	1.7840	0.0019	0.4695	0.0034	HP
PA4795		3.0	1.8970	0.0116	0.6323	0.0347	HP
PA4796		2.5	1.5010	0.0043	0.6004	0.0081	HP
PA4803		2.8	1.7430	0.0044	0.6225	0.0006	HP
PA4808	<i>selA</i>	2.4	1.5560	0.0078	0.6483	0.0195	L-seryl-tRNA(ser) selenium transferase
PA4811	<i>fdnH</i>	2.5	1.9930	0.2158	0.7972	0.0099	nitrate-inducible formate dehydrogenase, beta subunit
PA4812	<i>fdnG</i>	2.3	1.9630	0.0506	0.8535	0.0909	formate dehydrogenase-O, major subunit
PA4829	<i>lpd3</i>	2.3	1.8000	0.1082	0.7826	0.1447	dihydrolipoamide dehydrogenase 3
PA4831		2.1	1.6090	0.0344	0.7662	0.1839	Pr. transcriptional regulator

Table 1 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA4833		6.3	2.0180	0.0054	0.3203	0.0149	CHP
PA4870		2.5	1.3130	0.0465	0.5252	0.0423	CHP
PA4875		2.1	1.5800	0.0467	0.7524	0.1340	HP
PA4876	<i>osmE</i>	2.8	1.5700	0.0301	0.5607	0.0366	osmotically inducible lipoprotein OsmE
PA4877		2.8	1.5800	0.0419	0.5643	0.0806	HP
PA4878		3.3	2.4670	0.1973	0.7476	0.1417	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA4880		4.2	1.8770	0.0248	0.4469	0.0159	Pr. bacterioferritin
PA4881		5.9	2.2900	0.0456	0.3881	0.0018	HP
PA4885	<i>irlR</i>	2.2	1.3850	0.0127	0.6295	0.0546	two-component response regulator
PA4895		4.8	2.1650	0.0285	0.4510	0.0294	Pr. transmembrane sensor
PA4896		13.7	1.9570	0.0001	0.1428	0.0511	Pr. sigma-70 factor, ECF subfamily
PA4897		2.3	1.2560	0.1162	0.5461	0.1010	HP
PA4904	<i>vanA</i>	2.4	1.4010	0.0140	0.5838	0.0136	vanillate O-demethylase oxygenase subunit
PA4909		2.3	1.6050	0.0757	0.6978	0.2111	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA4910		2.1	1.5310	0.0546	0.7290	0.0267	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA4912		4.7	1.5080	0.0083	0.3209	0.0348	Pr. permease of ABC branched chain amino acid transporter
PA4913		5.4	3.2750	0.0195	0.6065	0.0018	Pr. binding protein component of ABC transporter
PA4915		5.7	1.8680	0.0491	0.3277	0.2009	Pr. chemotaxis transducer
PA4916		2.8	1.9400	0.0622	0.6929	0.0633	HP
PA4917		2.6	1.9330	0.0372	0.7435	0.1102	HP
PA4918		2.9	1.7150	0.0058	0.5914	0.0076	HP
PA4919	<i>pncB1</i>	2.1	1.6130	0.0209	0.7681	0.0940	nicotinate phosphoribosyltransferase
PA4936		3.2	1.6170	0.0015	0.5053	0.0360	Pr. rRNA methylase
PA4937	<i>rnr</i>	3.3	1.7300	0.0017	0.5242	0.0032	exoribonuclease RNase R
PA4979		2.7	1.6640	0.0254	0.6163	0.0352	Pr. acyl-CoA dehydrogenase
PA4980		4.0	1.6480	0.0013	0.4120	0.0168	Pr. enoyl-CoA hydratase/isomerase
PA4983		2.3	1.9690	0.0569	0.8561	0.0211	Pr. two-component response regulator
PA4984		2.9	2.3030	0.0250	0.7941	0.0563	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA5000		2.7	1.4730	0.2036	0.5456	0.0826	Pr. glycosyl transferase
PA5017		2.5	1.4450	0.0143	0.5780	0.0391	CHP
PA5023		3.6	1.8930	0.0388	0.5258	0.1593	CHP
PA5029		2.8	1.7750	0.0237	0.6339	0.0452	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA5056	<i>phaC1</i>	3.6	1.6980	0.0041	0.4717	0.0155	poly(3-hydroxyalkanoic acid) synthase 1
PA5057	<i>phaD</i>	2.1	1.7250	0.0489	0.8214	0.2161	poly(3-hydroxyalkanoic acid) depolymerase
PA5085		2.6	1.9220	0.0115	0.7392	0.0052	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA5086		3.3	2.0610	0.0951	0.6245	0.1769	HP
PA5105	<i>hutC</i>	2.2	1.4040	0.1363	0.6382	0.0213	histidine utilization repressor HutC
PA5106		4.9	1.7980	0.1427	0.3669	0.0276	CHP
PA5112	<i>estA</i>	2.2	1.6510	0.0138	0.7505	0.0192	esterase EstA
PA5122		2.3	1.5010	0.0450	0.6526	0.0772	HP
PA5126		2.2	1.4680	0.0268	0.6673	0.0243	HP
PA5150		2.9	1.7060	0.0206	0.5883	0.0135	Pr. short-chain dehydrogenase
PA5152		3.4	1.6140	0.0012	0.4747	0.0019	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA5153		2.5	1.6150	0.0065	0.6460	0.0196	Pr. periplasmic binding protein
PA5170	<i>arcD</i>	9.9	4.8450	0.2329	0.4894	0.0222	arginine/ornithine antiporter
PA5171	<i>arcA</i>	5.1	2.5190	0.2099	0.4939	0.0289	arginine deiminase
PA5172	<i>arcB</i>	3.1	2.0500	0.2885	0.6613	0.0955	ornithine carbamoyltransferase, catabolic
PA5180		6.3	3.3850	0.0339	0.5373	0.0668	CHP
PA5181		3.4	3.0360	0.0345	0.8929	0.1277	Pr. oxidoreductase
PA5188		8.8	1.4420	0.1551	0.1639	0.2742	Pr. 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydrogenase

Table 1 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA5191		3.1	1.8570	0.0175	0.5990	0.0150	HP
PA5195		2.6	1.7790	0.0334	0.6842	0.0371	Pr. heat shock protein
PA5206	<i>argE</i>	5.5	2.1400	0.0044	0.3891	0.0060	acetylornithine deacetylase
PA5208		2.6	2.0090	0.0276	0.7727	0.1364	CHP
PA5211		2.5	1.3760	0.0241	0.5504	0.0882	CHP
PA5212		4.3	1.8910	0.0050	0.4398	0.0228	HP
PA5217		4.3	1.3990	0.0130	0.3253	0.2197	Pr. binding protein component of ABC iron transporter
PA5218		3.1	1.6230	0.0048	0.5235	0.0369	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA5226		2.5	1.5230	0.0188	0.6092	0.0339	HP
PA5247		2.9	1.6200	0.0088	0.5586	0.0259	CHP
PA5249		3.5	1.6060	0.0911	0.4589	0.1688	HP
PA5255	<i>algQ</i>	4.0	1.9320	0.0040	0.4830	0.0088	Alginate regulatory protein AlgQ
PA5261	<i>algR</i>	3.3	2.0230	0.0618	0.6130	0.0683	alginate biosynthesis regulatory protein AlgR
PA5264		4.6	1.6560	0.0031	0.3600	0.0214	HP
PA5269		2.3	1.5980	0.0063	0.6948	0.0112	HP
PA5272	<i>cyaA</i>	2.1	1.5120	0.0063	0.7200	0.1075	adenylate cyclase
PA5287	<i>amtB</i>	2.1	1.3870	0.0916	0.6605	0.1897	ammonium transporter AmtB
PA5288	<i>glnK</i>	2.6	1.6970	0.0315	0.6527	0.0412	nitrogen regulatory protein P-II 2
PA5291		2.4	1.4090	0.0096	0.5871	0.0320	Pr. choline transporter
PA5303		2.1	1.7980	0.0424	0.8562	0.1503	CHP
PA5304	<i>dadA</i>	3.3	1.8590	0.0165	0.5633	0.0063	D-amino acid dehydrogenase, small subunit
PA5306		2.2	1.4370	0.0936	0.6532	0.0533	CHP
PA5312		3.1	1.4600	0.0066	0.4710	0.0414	Pr. aldehyde dehydrogenase
PA5313		4.0	1.8320	0.0419	0.4580	0.1188	Pr. pyridoxal-dependent aminotransferase
PA5319	<i>radC</i>	2.2	1.5170	0.0153	0.6895	0.0389	DNA repair protein RadC
PA5324		3.0	1.7180	0.0067	0.5727	0.0348	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA5329		3.5	1.6380	0.0132	0.4680	0.0208	CHP
PA5332	<i>crc</i>	2.1	1.4180	0.0236	0.6752	0.0224	catabolite repression control protein
PA5348		2.4	1.5280	0.0059	0.6367	0.0190	Pr. DNA-binding protein
PA5356	<i>glcC</i>	7.0	2.2260	0.0037	0.3180	0.0011	transcriptional regulator GlcC
PA5359		3.6	1.7720	0.0098	0.4922	0.0620	HP
PA5364		2.5	1.8130	0.0256	0.7252	0.0644	Pr. two-component response regulator
PA5378		3.0	1.9330	0.0180	0.6443	0.0259	HP
PA5380		2.4	1.7230	0.0457	0.7179	0.0260	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA5389		2.1	1.6500	0.0768	0.7857	0.1375	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA5396		2.4	1.5120	0.0744	0.6300	0.0374	HP
PA5409		4.3	2.1380	0.0263	0.4972	0.0119	HP
PA5422		2.7	1.5420	0.0192	0.5711	0.0810	HP
PA5432		2.4	1.5860	0.0136	0.6608	0.0365	Pr. acetyltransferase
PA5433		2.2	1.5450	0.0387	0.7023	0.0849	CHP
PA5446		3.7	1.8340	0.0204	0.4957	0.0088	HP
PA5454	<i>rmc</i>	3.8	1.7930	0.0194	0.4718	0.0174	oxidoreductase Rmc
PA5460		5.5	2.6850	0.0395	0.4882	0.0696	HP
PA5465		3.5	1.9370	0.0198	0.5534	0.0386	HP
PA5467		4.3	1.7280	0.0020	0.4019	0.0091	HP
PA5473		2.3	1.4890	0.0075	0.6474	0.0083	CHP
PA5483	<i>algB</i>	2.4	1.6920	0.0204	0.7050	0.0461	two-component response regulator AlgB
PA5494		3.5	1.4520	0.1837	0.4149	0.0779	HP
PA5495	<i>thrB</i>	2.4	1.6140	0.1458	0.6725	0.0412	homoserine kinase
PA5506		2.1	1.9220	0.0762	0.9152	0.2114	HP

Table 1 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA5522	2.6	1.8670	0.0365	0.7181	0.0934	Pr. glutamine synthetase
PA5523	5.8	2.9210	0.0236	0.5036	0.0058	Pr. aminotransferase
PA5524	7.7	2.1830	0.0401	0.2835	0.0060	Pr. short-chain dehydrogenase
PA5525	5.7	2.2360	0.0059	0.3923	0.0026	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA5531 <i>tonB</i>	7.0	2.1350	0.1492	0.3050	0.2303	TonB protein
PA5545	2.7	1.9190	0.1275	0.7107	0.2441	CHP
PA5546	21.9	2.3150	0.0006	0.1057	0.0089	CHP

* Mean of normalized gene signals of five replicates with corresponded *t* test *p*-value. HP, hypothetical protein. CHP, conserved hypothetical protein. Pr., probable.

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)**Table 2.** Genes whose mRNA levels decreased >2-fold with H₂O₂ treatment

Gene number	Gene name	Fold change	Normalized gene signals				Gene product description
			Treated		Untreated		
			Mean	p-value	Mean*	p-value	
PA0008	<i>glyS</i>	4.0	0.3455	0.0404	1.3820	0.0142	glycyl-tRNA synthetase beta chain
PA0009	<i>glyQ</i>	5.4	0.3063	0.0638	1.6540	0.0009	glycyl-tRNA synthetase alpha chain
PA0016	<i>trkA</i>	2.5	0.5924	0.0226	1.4810	0.0397	potassium uptake protein TrkA
PA0017		2.2	0.6823	0.0065	1.5010	0.0209	CHP
PA0022		3.5	0.3917	0.3045	1.3710	0.0207	CHP
PA0045		3.2	0.4813	0.0012	1.5400	0.0006	HP
PA0046		4.7	0.4079	0.0064	1.9170	0.0330	HP
PA0047		3.1	0.4406	0.0280	1.3660	0.0702	HP
PA0048		2.1	0.7067	0.1408	1.4840	0.0894	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0049		2.5	0.5244	0.2248	1.3110	0.1169	HP
PA0086		2.9	0.4279	0.0271	1.2410	0.0140	HP
PA0087		3.0	0.4490	0.0290	1.3470	0.0026	HP
PA0088		3.7	0.3065	0.1311	1.1340	0.0402	HP
PA0156		2.5	0.5616	0.1177	1.4040	0.0864	Pr. RND efflux membrane fusion protein precursor
PA0157		3.4	0.5674	0.0163	1.9290	0.0139	Pr. RND efflux membrane fusion protein precursor
PA0158		15.4	0.1045	0.3354	1.6090	0.0269	Pr. RND efflux transporter
PA0165		9.0	0.2088	0.0197	1.8790	0.0075	HP
PA0169		8.4	0.1718	0.0534	1.4430	0.0758	HP
PA0170		6.4	0.2869	0.0240	1.8360	0.0266	HP
PA0171		14.4	0.1514	0.1656	2.1800	0.0135	HP
PA0172		3.9	0.4251	0.0008	1.6580	0.0044	HP
PA0203		2.8	0.5439	0.1422	1.5230	0.1636	Pr. binding protein component of ABC transporter
PA0236		2.2	0.5655	0.0721	1.2440	0.1988	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0277		6.1	0.2730	0.1865	1.6650	0.0057	CHP
PA0280	<i>cysA</i>	5.0	0.3890	0.0535	1.9450	0.1372	sulfate transport protein CysA
PA0282	<i>cysT</i>	8.6	0.2035	0.0921	1.7500	0.1003	sulfate transport protein CysT
PA0285		2.6	0.7450	0.0887	1.9370	0.0244	CHP
PA0292	<i>aguA</i>	2.4	0.5775	0.1161	1.3860	0.0230	agmatine deiminase
PA0293	<i>aguB</i>	8.8	0.2482	0.1493	2.1840	0.0115	N-carbamoylputrescine amidohydrolase
PA0303	<i>potH</i>	3.4	0.3962	0.0538	1.3470	0.1636	polyamine transport protein PotH
PA0316	<i>serA</i>	3.4	0.4476	0.0384	1.5220	0.0036	D-3-phosphoglycerate dehydrogenase
PA0319		2.2	0.6964	0.0030	1.5320	0.0373	HP
PA0328		3.6	0.4036	0.0325	1.4530	0.0757	HP
PA0330	<i>rpiA</i>	2.5	0.5780	0.0943	1.4450	0.0313	ribose 5-phosphate isomerase
PA0331	<i>ilvA1</i>	2.2	0.6014	0.1630	1.3230	0.0617	threonine dehydratase, biosynthetic
PA0340		2.4	0.5738	0.0375	1.3770	0.0117	CHP
PA0341	<i>lgt</i>	3.1	0.5442	0.0462	1.6870	0.0461	prolipoprotein diacylglyceryl transferase
PA0342	<i>thyA</i>	2.5	0.5300	0.0983	1.3250	0.0259	thymidylate synthase
PA0350	<i>folA</i>	3.0	0.4817	0.1454	1.4450	0.0797	dihydrofolate reductase
PA0352		3.7	0.5995	0.0134	2.2180	0.0170	Pr. transporter
PA0354		6.4	0.3022	0.0048	1.9340	0.0077	CHP
PA0356		2.2	0.6732	0.0584	1.4810	0.0311	HP
PA0358		3.4	0.5785	0.0481	1.9670	0.0186	HP

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA0370		2.7	0.4604	0.0360	1.2430	0.0350	CHP
PA0371		2.4	0.6571	0.1600	1.5770	0.1174	HP
PA0380		4.8	0.4238	0.1039	2.0340	0.0222	CHP
PA0381	<i>thiG</i>	6.4	0.3666	0.0288	2.3460	0.0139	thiamine biosynthesis protein, thiazole moiety
PA0382	<i>micA</i>	24.3	0.0840	0.2686	2.0420	0.0027	DNA mismatch repair protein MicA
PA0385		2.4	0.6842	0.0972	1.6420	0.0278	HP
PA0386		3.4	0.4806	0.0002	1.6340	0.0008	Pr. oxidase
PA0387		2.2	0.6127	0.0544	1.3480	0.0032	CHP
PA0388		2.4	0.5833	0.0303	1.4000	0.0911	HP
PA0389		4.8	0.4175	0.0820	2.0040	0.0324	HP
PA0390	<i>metX</i>	4.8	0.3988	0.1035	1.9140	0.0166	homoserine O-acetyltransferase
PA0400		2.5	0.5096	0.0322	1.2740	0.0681	Pr. cystathionine gamma-lyase
PA0406		3.7	0.3746	0.0850	1.3860	0.0138	HP
PA0410	<i>pilI</i>	2.7	0.4356	0.2150	1.1760	0.2488	twitching motility protein PilI
PA0411	<i>pilJ</i>	3.2	0.4653	0.1629	1.4890	0.0322	twitching motility protein PilJ
PA0412	<i>pilK</i>	2.4	0.7017	0.0055	1.6840	0.0442	methyltransferase PilK
PA0419		2.6	0.6108	0.0522	1.5880	0.0193	CHP
PA0421		2.4	0.5508	0.0987	1.3220	0.0685	HP
PA0425	<i>mexA</i>	3.1	0.5142	0.0952	1.5940	0.0101	RND multidrug efflux membrane fusion protein MexA precursor
PA0426	<i>mexB</i>	3.2	0.5078	0.0867	1.6250	0.0189	RND multidrug efflux transporter MexB
PA0428		2.1	0.7310	0.1741	1.5350	0.0726	Pr. ATP-dependent RNA helicase
PA0430	<i>metF</i>	5.0	0.3246	0.0127	1.6230	0.0181	5,10-methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase
PA0431		3.1	0.5116	0.0401	1.5860	0.0083	HP
PA0432	<i>sahH</i>	2.3	0.6717	0.2100	1.5450	0.0235	S-adenosyl-L-homocysteine hydrolase
PA0437	<i>codA</i>	6.9	0.2603	0.0271	1.7960	0.0047	cytosine deaminase
PA0438	<i>codB</i>	5.3	0.3564	0.1164	1.8890	0.0127	cytosine permease
PA0446		11.3	0.1965	0.2389	2.2200	0.0442	CHP
PA0447	<i>gcdH</i>	4.7	0.3340	0.1148	1.5700	0.0047	glutaryl-CoA dehydrogenase
PA0482	<i>glcB</i>	3.8	0.4126	0.1177	1.5680	0.0147	malate synthase G
PA0501	<i>bioF</i>	2.1	0.6748	0.0102	1.4170	0.0038	8-amino-7-oxononanoate synthase
PA0502		3.1	0.4865	0.0192	1.5080	0.0031	Pr. biotin biosynthesis protein bioH
PA0503		3.2	0.4409	0.0181	1.4110	0.0099	Pr. biotin synthesis protein BioC
PA0504	<i>bioD</i>	2.4	0.6575	0.0035	1.5780	0.0128	dethiobiotin synthase
PA0541		3.3	0.4912	0.1710	1.6210	0.0217	HP
PA0546	<i>metK</i>	7.2	0.2497	0.0118	1.7980	0.0111	methionine adenosyltransferase
PA0547		8.7	0.2777	0.0044	2.4160	0.0057	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA0548	<i>tktA</i>	4.2	0.4795	0.0716	2.0140	0.0116	transketolase
PA0549		3.7	0.4049	0.0041	1.4980	0.0021	HP
PA0551	<i>epd</i>	2.7	0.4907	0.1218	1.3250	0.0296	D-erythrose 4-phosphate dehydrogenase
PA0552	<i>pgk</i>	6.9	0.2777	0.0882	1.9160	0.0153	phosphoglycerate kinase
PA0553		2.9	0.5479	0.0267	1.5890	0.0211	HP
PA0554		3.2	0.5516	0.0513	1.7650	0.0264	HP
PA0555	<i>fda</i>	2.9	0.5190	0.1054	1.5050	0.0160	fructose-1,6-bisphosphate aldolase
PA0556		5.4	0.3857	0.2411	2.0830	0.0781	HP
PA0559		2.8	0.6279	0.0015	1.7580	0.0302	CHP
PA0576	<i>rpoD</i>	3.8	0.4505	0.0016	1.7120	0.0020	sigma factor RpoD
PA0578		11.6	0.2114	0.0235	2.4520	0.0046	CHP
PA0579	<i>rpsU</i>	7.8	0.3036	0.0146	2.3680	0.0103	30S ribosomal protein S21
PA0580	<i>gcp</i>	3.0	0.6137	0.0003	1.8410	0.0171	O-sialoglycoprotein endopeptidase
PA0582	<i>folB</i>	5.3	0.5392	0.2724	2.8580	0.0562	dihydroneopterin aldolase

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA0583		3.0	0.5110	0.2611	1.5330	0.0946	HP
PA0592	<i>ksgA</i>	2.5	0.5512	0.1329	1.3780	0.0287	rRNA (adenine-N6,N6)-dimethyltransferase
PA0593	<i>pdxA</i>	5.1	0.2537	0.0521	1.2940	0.0220	pyridoxal phosphate biosynthetic protein PdxA
PA0594	<i>surA</i>	4.9	0.2733	0.0265	1.3390	0.0209	peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase SurA
PA0595	<i>ostA</i>	4.0	0.3755	0.0477	1.5020	0.0004	organic solvent tolerance protein OstA precursor
PA0603		3.4	0.6762	0.2526	2.2990	0.0473	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA0604		7.3	0.3144	0.3409	2.2950	0.0279	Pr. binding protein component of ABC transporter
PA0605		18.1	0.2062	0.2255	3.7320	0.0298	Pr. permease of ABC transporter
PA0606		3.2	0.7003	0.0218	2.2410	0.0342	Pr. permease of ABC transporter
PA0607	<i>rpe</i>	3.9	0.4338	0.0079	1.6920	0.0270	ribulose-phosphate 3-epimerase
PA0608		3.4	0.4674	0.0290	1.5890	0.0014	Pr. phosphoglycolate phosphatase
PA0632		3.0	0.3960	0.3298	1.1880	0.1269	HP
PA0654	<i>speD</i>	11.9	0.2369	0.0022	2.8190	0.0148	S-adenosylmethionine decarboxylase proenzyme
PA0662	<i>argC</i>	4.4	0.3607	0.2062	1.5870	0.0285	N-acetyl-gamma-glutamyl-phosphate reductase
PA0663		3.9	0.4133	0.0975	1.6120	0.0409	HP
PA0666		6.1	0.3000	0.0562	1.8300	0.0027	CHP
PA0667		4.0	0.4615	0.0096	1.8460	0.0107	CHP
PA0668	<i>tyrZ</i>	3.1	0.5058	0.2893	1.5680	0.0548	tyrosyl-tRNA synthetase 2
PA0703		4.3	0.3093	0.2971	1.3300	0.0952	Pr. MFS transporter
PA0730		4.2	0.4814	0.0263	2.0220	0.0619	Pr. transferase
PA0733		2.1	0.5971	0.0962	1.2540	0.0415	Pr. pseudouridylate synthase
PA0734		3.6	0.3742	0.1411	1.3470	0.0011	HP
PA0742		5.8	0.2647	0.3355	1.5350	0.0749	HP
PA0750	<i>ung</i>	3.8	0.4361	0.2675	1.6570	0.0468	uracil-DNA glycosylase
PA0756		2.5	0.5536	0.1378	1.3840	0.1111	Pr. two-component response regulator
PA0757		3.7	0.5646	0.0561	2.0890	0.0146	Pr. two-component sensor
PA0760		2.7	0.5915	0.0461	1.5970	0.0995	CHP
PA0766	<i>mucD</i>	2.1	0.7424	0.3182	1.5590	0.0749	serine protease MucD precursor
PA0767	<i>lepA</i>	5.5	0.4089	0.0106	2.2490	0.0217	GTP-binding protein LepA
PA0768	<i>lepB</i>	4.5	0.3491	0.0320	1.5710	0.0055	signal peptidase I
PA0769		2.5	0.6908	0.2423	1.7270	0.0386	HP
PA0770	<i>rnc</i>	2.9	0.5286	0.0749	1.5330	0.0594	ribonuclease III
PA0771	<i>era</i>	4.3	0.3963	0.1539	1.7040	0.0362	GTP-binding protein Era
PA0773	<i>pdxJ</i>	2.1	0.7533	0.2004	1.5820	0.0755	pyridoxal phosphate biosynthetic protein PdxJ
PA0774		3.9	0.5441	0.0217	2.1220	0.0272	CHP
PA0775		6.7	0.3370	0.0049	2.2580	0.0146	CHP
PA0783	<i>putP</i>	3.3	0.7121	0.1687	2.3500	0.0417	sodium/proline symporter PutP
PA0793		4.7	0.4813	0.0754	2.2620	0.0237	HP
PA0794		4.3	0.4123	0.1227	1.7730	0.0491	Pr. aconitate hydratase
PA0796	<i>prpB</i>	3.3	0.4264	0.2439	1.4070	0.0656	carboxyphosphoenolpyruvate phosphonmutase
PA0799		3.5	0.4689	0.1380	1.6410	0.0315	Pr. helicase
PA0834		6.1	0.3631	0.0380	2.2150	0.0071	CHP
PA0837	<i>slyD</i>	2.7	0.5337	0.1548	1.4410	0.0165	peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase SlyD
PA0852	<i>cpbD</i>	3.2	0.5309	0.1046	1.6990	0.0730	chitin-binding protein CbpD precursor
PA0857	<i>bolA</i>	2.2	0.6259	0.1556	1.3770	0.0583	morphogene protein BolA
PA0858		3.3	0.5315	0.0363	1.7540	0.0311	CHP
PA0859		2.3	0.7174	0.0665	1.6500	0.0486	HP
PA0860		2.5	0.6340	0.0316	1.5850	0.0146	Pr. ATP-binding/permease fusion ABC transporter
PA0866	<i>aroP2</i>	2.8	0.3771	0.3012	1.0560	0.5976	aromatic amino acid transport protein AroP2
PA0888	<i>aotJ</i>	8.9	0.2445	0.1571	2.1760	0.0097	arginine/ornithine binding protein AotJ

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA0889	<i>aotQ</i>	18.2	0.1610	0.0020	2.9300	0.0062	arginine/ornithine transport protein AotQ
PA0890	<i>aotM</i>	9.4	0.2226	0.0053	2.0920	0.0030	arginine/ornithine transport protein AotM
PA0891		7.5	0.2127	0.0121	1.5950	0.0037	HP
PA0892	<i>aotP</i>	9.0	0.1903	0.0475	1.7130	0.0073	arginine/ornithine transport protein AotP
PA0893	<i>argR</i>	3.2	0.3503	0.0769	1.1210	0.1580	transcriptional regulator ArgR
PA0898	<i>aruD</i>	3.5	0.4463	0.0270	1.5620	0.0284	succinylglutamate 5-semialdehyde dehydrogenase
PA0903	<i>alaS</i>	2.9	0.5503	0.0513	1.5960	0.0107	alanyl-tRNA synthetase
PA0904	<i>lysC</i>	4.1	0.4378	0.0708	1.7950	0.0076	aspartate kinase alpha and beta chain
PA0914		8.2	0.2466	0.1621	2.0220	0.0108	HP
PA0915		21.7	0.1118	0.1066	2.4270	0.0060	CHP
PA0916		11.2	0.2752	0.0064	3.0820	0.0323	CHP
PA0917	<i>kup</i>	3.1	0.5906	0.0249	1.8310	0.0138	potassium uptake protein Kup
PA0919		2.2	0.5518	0.0670	1.2140	0.0662	HP
PA0920		2.9	0.5407	0.0122	1.5680	0.0300	HP
PA0925		2.5	0.6532	0.0138	1.6330	0.0456	HP
PA0926		3.5	0.4531	0.0286	1.5860	0.0013	HP
PA0927	<i>ldhA</i>	4.9	0.3180	0.0186	1.5580	0.0265	D-lactate dehydrogenase (fermentative)
PA0928		2.3	0.7274	0.0143	1.6730	0.0187	sensor/response regulator hybrid
PA0932	<i>cysM</i>	2.4	0.4771	0.1673	1.1450	0.2057	cysteine synthase B
PA0933	<i>ygcA</i>	2.8	0.5836	0.0311	1.6340	0.0121	Pr. RNA methyltransferase
PA0937		2.7	0.4426	0.1602	1.1950	0.0549	CHP
PA0944	<i>purN</i>	7.3	0.2566	0.0645	1.8730	0.0046	phosphoribosylaminoimidazole synthetase
PA0945	<i>purM</i>	10.4	0.1908	0.0750	1.9840	0.0031	phosphoribosylaminoimidazole synthetase
PA0947		3.4	0.4126	0.1351	1.4030	0.0350	CHP
PA0955		4.2	0.3895	0.0116	1.6360	0.0021	HP
PA0956	<i>proS</i>	3.3	0.4612	0.0885	1.5220	0.0064	prolyl-tRNA synthetase
PA0963	<i>aspS</i>	2.7	0.5433	0.0462	1.4670	0.0202	aspartyl-tRNA synthetase
PA0964		2.7	0.5526	0.0643	1.4920	0.0365	CHP
PA0968		2.4	0.7833	0.1968	1.8800	0.0728	CHP
PA0970	<i>tolR</i>	2.2	0.8136	0.0003	1.7900	0.0392	TolR protein
PA0971	<i>tolA</i>	2.4	0.6983	0.1166	1.6760	0.0436	TolA protein
PA0973	<i>oprL</i>	2.2	0.5168	0.0516	1.1370	0.0853	Peptidoglycan associated lipoprotein OprL precursor
PA0974		2.2	0.6618	0.1063	1.4560	0.0190	CHP
PA0975		3.2	0.5944	0.0222	1.9020	0.0498	Pr. radical activating enzyme
PA0996		2.3	0.6448	0.2372	1.4830	0.0626	Pr. coenzyme A ligase
PA0997		3.8	0.3513	0.0548	1.3350	0.1523	HP
PA0998		4.3	0.2533	0.0319	1.0890	0.1353	HP
PA1004	<i>nadA</i>	2.2	0.6259	0.0059	1.3770	0.0272	quinolinate synthetase A
PA1006		3.1	0.4906	0.1779	1.5210	0.1146	CHP
PA1007		2.8	0.5925	0.0479	1.6590	0.0482	CHP
PA1008	<i>bcp</i>	2.9	0.5372	0.1504	1.5580	0.0519	bacterioferritin comigratory protein
PA1010	<i>dapA</i>	2.6	0.4927	0.1533	1.2810	0.0231	dihydrodipicolinate synthase
PA1011		5.2	0.3215	0.0220	1.6720	0.0048	HP
PA1012		4.3	0.4202	0.0783	1.8070	0.0208	CHP
PA1013	<i>purC</i>	4.1	0.4056	0.0559	1.6630	0.0248	phosphoribosylaminoimidazole-succinocarboxamide synthase
PA1014		3.1	0.4477	0.1747	1.3880	0.0434	Pr. glycosyl transferase
PA1018		3.2	0.5491	0.1695	1.7570	0.0496	HP
PA1026		2.4	0.6246	0.1433	1.4990	0.0578	HP
PA1032		3.8	0.4711	0.0007	1.7900	0.0102	Pr. penicillin amidase
PA1037		2.7	0.6300	0.0516	1.7010	0.0428	CHP

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA1043		2.4	0.5738	0.1082	1.3770	0.0761	HP
PA1045		2.1	0.6671	0.1867	1.4010	0.0499	HP
PA1068		2.4	0.5721	0.0290	1.3730	0.0433	Pr. heat shock protein (hsp90 family)
PA1072	<i>braE</i>	2.2	0.6368	0.0384	1.4010	0.0297	branched-chain amino acid transport protein BraE
PA1116		4.8	0.3479	0.0859	1.6700	0.0507	HP
PA1117		2.1	0.7129	0.1452	1.4970	0.0983	HP
PA1126		3.0	0.4940	0.1359	1.4820	0.0396	HP
PA1132		2.4	0.5813	0.0715	1.3950	0.0137	HP
PA1155	<i>nrdB</i>	6.2	0.1921	0.0238	1.1910	0.0602	ribonucleoside reductase, small chain
PA1156	<i>nrdA</i>	4.9	0.4133	0.0042	2.0250	0.0084	ribonucleoside reductase, large chain
PA1157		2.9	0.5055	0.0422	1.4660	0.0451	Pr. two-component response regulator
PA1158		3.5	0.5580	0.0019	1.9530	0.0069	Pr. two-component sensor
PA1161	<i>rrmA</i>	4.1	0.4295	0.0010	1.7610	0.0093	rRNA methyltransferase
PA1162	<i>dapE</i>	2.7	0.6074	0.0091	1.6400	0.0145	succinyl-diaminopimelate desuccinylase
PA1170		4.1	0.4390	0.0755	1.8000	0.0051	CHP
PA1181		2.7	0.5863	0.0745	1.5830	0.0365	CHP
PA1189		2.1	0.6100	0.0587	1.2810	0.0130	CHP
PA1192		4.1	0.4173	0.0655	1.7110	0.0111	CHP
PA1193		3.3	0.4976	0.0393	1.6420	0.0032	HP
PA1194		2.6	0.5938	0.2565	1.5440	0.1802	Pr. amino acid permease
PA1198		7.8	0.3453	0.0647	2.6930	0.0198	CHP
PA1199		4.6	0.3385	0.0107	1.5570	0.0048	Pr. lipoprotein
PA1200		2.9	0.4483	0.0326	1.3000	0.0728	CHP
PA1206		2.1	0.5667	0.1029	1.1900	0.0970	HP
PA1207	<i>kefB</i>	3.0	0.4867	0.0252	1.4600	0.0598	glutathione-regulated potassium-efflux system protein KefB
PA1213		2.6	0.4731	0.2815	1.2300	0.4308	HP
PA1220		4.7	0.2772	0.1900	1.3030	0.1440	HP
PA1222		2.2	0.6823	0.0592	1.5010	0.0187	Pr. membrane-bound lytic murein transglycolase A
PA1228		4.1	0.5151	0.0223	2.1120	0.0212	HP
PA1247	<i>aprE</i>	2.5	0.6496	0.0110	1.6240	0.0059	alkaline protease secretion protein AprE
PA1248	<i>aprF</i>	2.6	0.6019	0.0624	1.5650	0.0137	Alkaline protease secretion outer membrane AprF precursor
PA1271		6.7	0.3563	0.0128	2.3870	0.0163	Pr. tonB-dependent receptor
PA1272	<i>cobO</i>	3.7	0.4784	0.0406	1.7700	0.0181	cob(I)alamin adenosyltransferase
PA1273	<i>cobB</i>	6.9	0.2487	0.0215	1.7160	0.0036	cobyrinic acid a,c-diamide synthase
PA1274		4.4	0.3073	0.0214	1.3520	0.0076	CHP
PA1275	<i>cobD</i>	9.4	0.1423	0.3159	1.3380	0.1215	cobalamin biosynthetic protein CobD
PA1293		2.9	0.4434	0.1203	1.2860	0.0268	HP
PA1294	<i>rnd</i>	2.1	0.6500	0.0617	1.3650	0.0100	ribonuclease D
PA1295		3.1	0.5455	0.0475	1.6910	0.0263	CHP
PA1299		4.5	0.4633	0.0098	2.0850	0.0250	CHP
PA1303		12.1	0.1461	0.1014	1.7680	0.0102	Pr. signal peptidase
PA1304		2.3	0.6317	0.0733	1.4530	0.0942	Pr. oligopeptidase
PA1317	<i>cyoA</i>	2.5	0.5560	0.0451	1.3900	0.0862	cytochrome o ubiquinol oxidase subunit II
PA1367		2.4	0.6188	0.1873	1.4850	0.0733	HP
PA1407		2.7	0.7578	0.0147	2.0460	0.0226	HP
PA1422	<i>gbuR</i>	2.6	0.6081	0.0113	1.5810	0.0437	GbuR
PA1461		2.4	0.5888	0.0371	1.4130	0.0607	Pr. chemotaxis protein
PA1475	<i>ccmA</i>	4.0	0.5198	0.1037	2.0790	0.0183	heme exporter protein CcmA
PA1476	<i>ccmB</i>	12.3	0.1936	0.2873	2.3810	0.0136	heme exporter protein CcmB
PA1477	<i>ccmC</i>	2.5	0.5724	0.0072	1.4310	0.0134	heme exporter protein CcmC

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA1478		4.8	0.3817	0.0262	1.8320	0.0057	HP
PA1479	<i>ccmE</i>	3.8	0.3853	0.0206	1.4640	0.0229	cytochrome C-type biogenesis protein CcmE
PA1480	<i>ccmF</i>	4.6	0.3570	0.0237	1.6420	0.0234	cytochrome C-type biogenesis protein CcmF
PA1481	<i>ccmG</i>	4.2	0.2857	0.0440	1.2000	0.1280	cytochrome C biogenesis protein CcmG
PA1483	<i>cycH</i>	2.7	0.4974	0.0571	1.3430	0.1114	cytochrome c-type biogenesis protein
PA1496		2.9	0.4476	0.3388	1.2980	0.2562	Pr. potassium channel
PA1504		2.1	0.5967	0.2238	1.2530	0.1290	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1529	<i>lig</i>	3.1	0.5484	0.0192	1.7000	0.0209	DNA ligase
PA1530		3.7	0.3705	0.1063	1.3710	0.0624	HP
PA1532	<i>dnaX</i>	2.6	0.4596	0.1532	1.1950	0.0984	DNA polymerase subunits gamma and tau
PA1534	<i>recR</i>	3.1	0.5416	0.0356	1.6790	0.0175	recombination protein RecR
PA1552		5.6	0.2434	0.0242	1.3630	0.0873	Pr. cytochrome c
PA1553		10.9	0.2084	0.0481	2.2720	0.0134	Pr. cytochrome c oxidase subunit
PA1554		11.6	0.1901	0.0321	2.2050	0.0094	Pr. cytochrome oxidase subunit (cbb3-type)
PA1559		4.5	0.4342	0.0306	1.9540	0.0209	HP
PA1560		4.7	0.3968	0.0268	1.8650	0.0479	HP
PA1563		3.1	0.5758	0.0025	1.7850	0.0139	CHP
PA1574		5.4	0.4259	0.1254	2.3000	0.0592	CHP
PA1577		2.4	0.6842	0.0171	1.6420	0.0416	HP
PA1580	<i>gltA</i>	3.7	0.3673	0.0725	1.3590	0.0675	citrate synthase
PA1581	<i>sdhC</i>	4.8	0.3600	0.0411	1.7280	0.0034	succinate dehydrogenase (C subunit)
PA1582	<i>sdhD</i>	5.5	0.3189	0.0536	1.7540	0.0141	succinate dehydrogenase (D subunit)
PA1583	<i>sdhA</i>	6.3	0.2811	0.0166	1.7710	0.0103	succinate dehydrogenase (A subunit)
PA1584	<i>sdhB</i>	5.1	0.2451	0.0196	1.2500	0.0163	succinate dehydrogenase (B subunit)
PA1591		5.5	0.4016	0.0059	2.2090	0.0165	HP
PA1593		3.2	0.4666	0.1063	1.4930	0.0313	HP
PA1594		2.3	0.6726	0.0973	1.5470	0.0685	HP
PA1595		8.2	0.2893	0.0165	2.3720	0.0131	HP
PA1596	<i>htpG</i>	4.1	0.6241	0.0060	2.5590	0.0938	heat shock protein HtpG
PA1609	<i>fabB</i>	2.8	0.4893	0.0459	1.3700	0.0132	beta-ketoacyl-ACP synthase I
PA1610	<i>fabA</i>	3.6	0.4547	0.0362	1.6370	0.0037	beta-hydroxydecanoyl-ACP dehydrase
PA1612		2.3	0.6183	0.0375	1.4220	0.0194	HP
PA1613		2.1	0.6467	0.0312	1.3580	0.0127	HP
PA1626		2.3	0.5696	0.1653	1.3100	0.0715	Pr. MFS transporter
PA1636	<i>kdpD</i>	3.0	0.4003	0.1718	1.2010	0.1654	two-component sensor KdpD
PA1638		7.5	0.2207	0.2036	1.6550	0.0053	CHP
PA1639		2.2	0.5459	0.1998	1.2010	0.3235	HP
PA1655		2.2	0.5468	0.1711	1.2030	0.2647	Pr. glutathione S-transferase
PA1660		2.3	0.6309	0.2072	1.4510	0.0798	HP
PA1664		3.7	0.3889	0.1762	1.4390	0.2691	HP
PA1665		2.1	0.7176	0.0581	1.5070	0.0527	HP
PA1667		2.1	0.7048	0.1219	1.4800	0.1756	HP
PA1668		2.4	0.6783	0.1127	1.6280	0.0266	HP
PA1669		3.6	0.4975	0.0815	1.7910	0.0434	HP
PA1674	<i>folE2</i>	3.0	0.5397	0.1335	1.6190	0.0647	GTP cyclohydrolase I precursor
PA1675		4.1	0.4746	0.0194	1.9460	0.0080	CHP
PA1678		3.2	0.5244	0.0118	1.6780	0.0188	Pr. DNA methylase
PA1681	<i>aroC</i>	3.0	0.3980	0.1629	1.1940	0.0537	chorismate synthase
PA1682		9.5	0.1954	0.0759	1.8560	0.0045	Pr. MFS metabolite transporter
PA1685	<i>masA</i>	2.8	0.6818	0.0171	1.9090	0.0233	enolase-phosphatase E-1

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA1687	<i>speE</i>	7.6	0.3137	0.0176	2.3840	0.0432	spermidine synthase
PA1688		6.0	0.3500	0.0311	2.1000	0.0063	HP
PA1689		6.9	0.2417	0.0195	1.6680	0.0419	CHP
PA1698	<i>popN</i>	2.9	0.4121	0.3218	1.1950	0.0382	Type III secretion outer membrane protein PopN precursor
PA1701		2.5	0.6460	0.0241	1.6150	0.0420	CHP in type III secretion
PA1715	<i>pscB</i>	2.6	0.5138	0.2533	1.3360	0.0496	type III export apparatus protein
PA1726	<i>bglX</i>	2.7	0.4700	0.0148	1.2690	0.0052	periplasmic beta-glucosidase
PA1727		2.9	0.5355	0.0322	1.5530	0.0301	CHP
PA1748		2.7	0.5467	0.1765	1.4760	0.0184	Pr. enoyl-CoA hydratase/isomerase
PA1750		2.5	0.6380	0.1986	1.5950	0.1321	phospho-2-dehydro-3-deoxyheptonate aldolase
PA1757	<i>thrH</i>	6.2	0.3042	0.0002	1.8860	0.0039	homoserine kinase
PA1766		3.2	0.4069	0.0249	1.3020	0.0996	HP
PA1767		3.5	0.5160	0.0624	1.8060	0.0181	HP
PA1768		3.6	0.3789	0.1340	1.3640	0.0088	HP
PA1770	<i>ppsA</i>	2.6	0.6127	0.1498	1.5930	0.0450	phosphoenolpyruvate synthase
PA1771		9.3	0.2187	0.0070	2.0340	0.0042	Pr. esterase/lipase
PA1775		2.1	0.6633	0.0620	1.3930	0.0386	CHP
PA1786		3.3	0.4039	0.3511	1.3330	0.2435	CHP
PA1787	<i>acnB</i>	2.7	0.4137	0.0252	1.1170	0.0636	aconitate hydratase 2
PA1790		7.1	0.2973	0.1909	2.1110	0.0272	HP
PA1791		4.0	0.5185	0.0069	2.0740	0.0211	HP
PA1792		2.4	0.5908	0.0315	1.4180	0.0044	CHP
PA1794	<i>glnS</i>	2.3	0.5561	0.0978	1.2790	0.0325	glutaminyl-tRNA synthetase
PA1795	<i>cysS</i>	2.9	0.4769	0.0412	1.3830	0.0098	cysteinyl-tRNA synthetase
PA1796	<i>folD</i>	3.1	0.4268	0.1075	1.3230	0.0044	5,10-methylene-tetrahydrofolate dehydrogenase / cyclohydrolase
PA1797		3.3	0.6100	0.0473	2.0130	0.0696	HP
PA1798		2.9	0.5217	0.0273	1.5130	0.0060	Pr. two-component sensor
PA1800	<i>tig</i>	5.4	0.3663	0.0725	1.9780	0.0028	trigger factor
PA1805	<i>ppiD</i>	2.8	0.5525	0.0797	1.5470	0.0246	peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase D
PA1808		2.3	0.4961	0.0244	1.1410	0.0884	Pr. permease of ABC transporter
PA1812	<i>mltD</i>	7.1	0.2938	0.0081	2.0860	0.0015	membrane-bound lytic murein transglycosylase D precursor
PA1815	<i>rnhA</i>	2.6	0.5619	0.0619	1.4610	0.0235	ribonuclease H
PA1816	<i>dnaQ</i>	2.3	0.6213	0.0275	1.4290	0.0510	DNA polymerase III, epsilon chain
PA1821		2.4	0.4750	0.1757	1.1400	0.3287	Pr. enoyl-CoA hydratase/isomerase
PA1822		3.6	0.4308	0.0067	1.5510	0.0109	HP
PA1823		2.6	0.4338	0.0383	1.1280	0.2337	CHP
PA1824		10.5	0.3015	0.0456	3.1660	0.0227	CHP
PA1837		7.5	0.2827	0.0190	2.1200	0.0132	HP
PA1838	<i>cysI</i>	11.8	0.2285	0.0246	2.6960	0.0053	sulfite reductase
PA1839		4.9	0.3392	0.1145	1.6620	0.0149	HP
PA1843	<i>metH</i>	2.3	0.5457	0.0155	1.2550	0.0105	methionine synthase
PA1846	<i>cti</i>	2.7	0.5515	0.0506	1.4890	0.0499	cis/trans isomerase
PA1852		2.3	0.4922	0.1934	1.1320	0.2343	HP
PA1853		3.0	0.5577	0.0976	1.6730	0.0536	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA1857		3.0	0.4740	0.1033	1.4220	0.0386	CHP
PA1869		6.8	0.2846	0.0098	1.9350	0.0262	Pr. acyl carrier protein
PA1870		2.3	0.5704	0.3919	1.3120	0.0939	HP
PA1892		8.0	0.2213	0.3596	1.7700	0.1084	HP
PA1893		5.8	0.3288	0.3191	1.9070	0.0753	HP
PA1894		3.0	0.5403	0.2467	1.6210	0.0979	HP

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA1895		3.5	0.5254	0.2703	1.8390	0.0372	HP
PA1903		2.8	0.7457	0.1550	2.0880	0.0407	phenazine biosynthesis protein PhzE
PA1906		2.1	0.6071	0.3609	1.2750	0.3282	HP
PA1926		4.3	0.4223	0.0472	1.8160	0.0161	CHP
PA1940		2.5	0.5968	0.0139	1.4920	0.0077	HP
PA1959	<i>bacA</i>	3.2	0.5853	0.0678	1.8730	0.0394	bacitracin resistance protein
PA1960		3.0	0.5083	0.0264	1.5250	0.0201	HP
PA1964		3.1	0.5129	0.0362	1.5900	0.0030	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA1966		5.2	0.2887	0.1604	1.5010	0.0188	HP
PA1971	<i>braZ</i>	10.8	0.1411	0.2540	1.5240	0.0779	branched chain amino acid transporter BraZ
PA2000		2.8	0.4025	0.2930	1.1270	0.0651	Pr. CoA transferase, subunit B
PA2001	<i>atoB</i>	3.8	0.3182	0.2723	1.2090	0.0034	acetyl-CoA acetyltransferase
PA2002		3.5	0.4674	0.0190	1.6360	0.0224	CHP
PA2012		2.2	0.7295	0.3348	1.6050	0.1545	Pr. acyl-CoA carboxylase alpha chain
PA2018		3.6	0.4175	0.0328	1.5030	0.0402	RND multidrug efflux transporter
PA2019		7.8	0.2923	0.2137	2.2800	0.0100	RND multidrug efflux membrane fusion protein precursor
PA2023	<i>galU</i>	2.9	0.5503	0.0242	1.5960	0.0162	UTP--glucose-1-phosphate uridylyltransferase
PA2042		4.4	0.4336	0.0071	1.9080	0.0095	Pr. transporter (membrane subunit)
PA2063		2.5	0.6408	0.0189	1.6020	0.0082	HP
PA2068		6.0	0.3117	0.0685	1.8700	0.0538	Pr. MFS transporter
PA2069		3.8	0.4729	0.1344	1.7970	0.0534	Pr. carbamoyl transferase
PA2109		4.7	0.2447	0.0373	1.1500	0.0236	HP
PA2110		2.6	0.4708	0.0443	1.2240	0.0437	HP
PA2112		2.2	0.5477	0.0217	1.2050	0.0521	CHP
PA2113		2.1	0.6919	0.0774	1.4530	0.0107	Pr. porin
PA2194	<i>hcnB</i>	6.6	0.2295	0.1042	1.5150	0.0485	hydrogen cyanide synthase HcnB
PA2202		4.3	0.4016	0.0897	1.7270	0.0913	Pr. amino acid permease
PA2203		8.5	0.2516	0.0627	2.1390	0.0523	Pr. amino acid permease
PA2230		3.0	0.4597	0.1050	1.3790	0.0102	HP
PA2233		2.5	0.5192	0.0285	1.2980	0.0349	Pr. glycosyl transferase
PA2234		2.9	0.5659	0.0025	1.6410	0.0159	Pr. exopolysaccharide transporter
PA2235		2.6	0.4504	0.0204	1.1710	0.0905	HP
PA2252		7.2	0.3197	0.1068	2.3020	0.0249	Pr. AGCS sodium/alanine/glycine symporter
PA2279	<i>arsC</i>	6.2	0.2527	0.2768	1.5670	0.0025	ArsC protein
PA2281		2.5	0.5416	0.1373	1.3540	0.0559	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2290	<i>gcd</i>	2.4	0.5829	0.0741	1.3990	0.0423	glucose dehydrogenase
PA2292		3.0	0.4093	0.1973	1.2280	0.3460	HP
PA2323		2.3	0.5504	0.2259	1.2660	0.0586	Pr. glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase
PA2329		2.7	0.7570	0.0971	2.0440	0.0940	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA2352		5.5	0.3416	0.0273	1.8790	0.0127	Pr. glycerophosphoryl diester phosphodiesterase
PA2389		2.9	0.6293	0.0260	1.8250	0.0601	CHP
PA2390		2.8	0.5393	0.0134	1.5100	0.0466	Pr. ATP-binding/permease fusion ABC transporter
PA2403		2.6	0.7119	0.2458	1.8510	0.0977	HP
PA2404		3.8	0.8232	0.1717	3.1280	0.0513	HP
PA2405		4.9	0.8247	0.2232	4.0410	0.0280	HP
PA2406		3.8	0.4879	0.0128	1.8540	0.0544	HP
PA2407		4.5	0.7391	0.0475	3.3260	0.0276	Pr. adhesion protein
PA2408		12.0	0.3738	0.1203	4.4860	0.0737	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA2442	<i>gcvT2</i>	4.5	0.2936	0.0525	1.3210	0.0346	glycine cleavage system protein T2
PA2443	<i>sdaA</i>	6.6	0.2488	0.0436	1.6420	0.0039	L-serine dehydratase

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA2444	<i>glyA2</i>	13.8	0.1254	0.0780	1.7300	0.0078	serine hydroxymethyltransferase
PA2445	<i>gcvP2</i>	5.6	0.2616	0.0793	1.4650	0.0356	glycine cleavage system protein P2
PA2446	<i>gcvH2</i>	4.9	0.3400	0.0857	1.6660	0.0133	glycine cleavage system protein H2
PA2449		4.7	0.3979	0.2981	1.8700	0.0177	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2453		3.5	0.4574	0.0148	1.6010	0.0342	HP
PA2454		3.0	0.5307	0.0112	1.5920	0.0091	HP
PA2455		2.6	0.5808	0.0682	1.5100	0.0142	HP
PA2476	<i>dsbG</i>	2.9	0.4834	0.0228	1.4020	0.0262	thiol:disulfide interchange protein DsbG
PA2502		5.7	0.3172	0.2368	1.8080	0.0195	HP
PA2503		2.7	0.6033	0.0000	1.6290	0.0105	HP
PA2527		2.1	0.6314	0.0168	1.3260	0.0098	Pr. RND efflux transporter
PA2533		3.5	0.5374	0.0464	1.8810	0.0441	Pr. sodium:alanine symporter
PA2536		2.4	0.6808	0.0042	1.6340	0.0219	Pr. phosphatidate cytidyltransferase
PA2542		2.3	0.5926	0.2900	1.3630	0.1766	CHP
PA2545	<i>xthA</i>	2.4	0.5671	0.0871	1.3610	0.0412	exodeoxyribonuclease III
PA2561		2.4	0.6192	0.0429	1.4860	0.0843	Pr. chemotaxis transducer
PA2619	<i>infA</i>	5.9	0.5312	0.0252	3.1340	0.0682	initiation factor
PA2623	<i>icd</i>	2.3	0.5970	0.2273	1.3730	0.0527	isocitrate dehydrogenase
PA2625		4.5	0.3396	0.0530	1.5280	0.0114	CHP
PA2626	<i>trmU</i>	2.6	0.5650	0.0875	1.4690	0.0103	tRNA methyltransferase
PA2627		2.9	0.6172	0.0644	1.7900	0.0135	CHP
PA2629	<i>purB</i>	10.4	0.2115	0.0545	2.2000	0.0047	adenylosuccinate lyase
PA2630		10.4	0.1927	0.0276	2.0040	0.0102	CHP
PA2634		2.3	0.6057	0.0662	1.3930	0.1043	Pr. isocitrate lyase
PA2637	<i>nuoA</i>	6.9	0.2210	0.1135	1.5250	0.0532	NADH dehydrogenase I chain A
PA2638	<i>nuoB</i>	6.6	0.2806	0.0782	1.8520	0.0008	NADH dehydrogenase I chain B
PA2639	<i>nuoD</i>	11.1	0.1957	0.0177	2.1720	0.0340	NADH dehydrogenase I chain C,D
PA2640	<i>nuoE</i>	9.3	0.1535	0.0224	1.4280	0.0890	NADH dehydrogenase I chain E
PA2641	<i>nuoF</i>	5.3	0.2262	0.0266	1.1990	0.0709	NADH dehydrogenase I chain F
PA2642	<i>nuoG</i>	3.4	0.3262	0.0323	1.1090	0.1551	NADH dehydrogenase I chain G
PA2645	<i>nuoJ</i>	2.8	0.4243	0.0548	1.1880	0.1334	NADH dehydrogenase I chain J
PA2646	<i>nuoK</i>	2.2	0.5718	0.0797	1.2580	0.0930	NADH dehydrogenase I chain K
PA2647	<i>nuoL</i>	2.3	0.5930	0.0585	1.3640	0.0406	NADH dehydrogenase I chain L
PA2653		5.1	0.4773	0.0823	2.4340	0.0323	Pr. transporter
PA2660		6.5	0.2742	0.2518	1.7820	0.0287	HP
PA2661		9.6	0.2154	0.2511	2.0680	0.0044	HP
PA2666		2.7	0.6104	0.1273	1.6480	0.0658	Pr. 6-pyruvoyl tetrahydrobiopterin synthase
PA2684		2.5	0.5128	0.0434	1.2820	0.0259	CHP
PA2735		2.4	0.5963	0.1697	1.4310	0.0697	Pr. restriction-modification system protein
PA2739	<i>pheT</i>	4.2	0.3198	0.0134	1.3430	0.0490	phenylalanyl-tRNA synthetase, beta subunit
PA2740	<i>pheS</i>	6.0	0.3397	0.0175	2.0380	0.0059	phenylalanyl-tRNA synthetase, alpha-subunit
PA2744	<i>thrS</i>	4.6	0.3996	0.0357	1.8380	0.0040	threonyl-tRNA synthetase
PA2749	<i>endA</i>	2.8	0.6904	0.0286	1.9330	0.0462	DNA-specific endonuclease I
PA2765		4.2	0.4093	0.1381	1.7190	0.0122	HP
PA2769		5.4	0.5002	0.2996	2.7010	0.0355	HP
PA2770		6.3	0.4613	0.0491	2.9060	0.0140	HP
PA2792		5.0	0.3396	0.2895	1.6980	0.0647	HP
PA2793		2.1	0.6071	0.2164	1.2750	0.1477	HP
PA2795		3.6	0.3406	0.1600	1.2260	0.0008	CHP
PA2798		2.2	0.6455	0.0708	1.4200	0.0422	Pr. two-component response regulator

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA2800		2.5	0.6148	0.1512	1.5370	0.0409	CHP
PA2801		2.2	0.7482	0.1201	1.6460	0.1403	HP
PA2811		2.5	0.6424	0.0809	1.6060	0.0213	Pr. permease of ABC-2 transporter
PA2812		2.5	0.6384	0.1316	1.5960	0.1117	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA2817		3.0	0.5583	0.0164	1.6750	0.0088	HP
PA2822		3.9	0.3818	0.2499	1.4890	0.0133	CHP
PA2823		2.8	0.7232	0.1976	2.0250	0.0447	CHP
PA2828		3.8	0.4597	0.0442	1.7470	0.0167	Pr. aminotransferase
PA2829		12.1	0.1567	0.1884	1.8960	0.0033	HP
PA2831		2.7	0.5219	0.0593	1.4090	0.0220	CHP
PA2840		4.0	0.3765	0.0211	1.5060	0.0045	Pr. ATP-dependent RNA helicase
PA2851	<i>efp</i>	7.4	0.2693	0.0366	1.9930	0.0026	translation elongation factor P
PA2855		3.3	0.5530	0.0228	1.8250	0.0364	HP
PA2876	<i>pyrF</i>	4.5	0.4647	0.0370	2.0910	0.0529	orotidine 5'-phosphate decarboxylase
PA2901		2.8	0.6729	0.2126	1.8840	0.0191	HP
PA2902		2.7	0.4552	0.2499	1.2290	0.2182	HP
PA2903	<i>cobJ</i>	5.1	0.3855	0.1643	1.9660	0.0531	precorrin-3 methylase CobJ
PA2904	<i>cobI</i>	3.6	0.5358	0.1717	1.9290	0.0183	precorrin-2 methyltransferase CobI
PA2905	<i>cobH</i>	3.8	0.4753	0.0150	1.8060	0.0119	precorrin isomerase CobH
PA2906		2.7	0.5856	0.0958	1.5810	0.0296	Pr. oxidoreductase
PA2907	<i>cobL</i>	3.2	0.4566	0.0260	1.4610	0.0114	precorrin-6y-dependent methyltransferase CobL
PA2911		25.8	0.1128	0.0207	2.9100	0.0205	Pr. TonB-dependent receptor
PA2912		5.0	0.3708	0.1833	1.8540	0.0446	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA2945		11.5	0.2075	0.2826	2.3860	0.0107	CHP
PA2947		2.6	0.7900	0.1944	2.0540	0.0320	HP
PA2950		5.3	0.4155	0.0361	2.2020	0.0251	HP
PA2951	<i>etfA</i>	2.1	0.6786	0.1317	1.4250	0.0311	electron transfer flavoprotein alpha-subunit
PA2956		3.3	0.6006	0.0638	1.9820	0.0576	CHP
PA2957		7.6	0.3146	0.0760	2.3910	0.0117	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA2962	<i>tmk</i>	2.3	0.6443	0.2808	1.4820	0.1596	thymidylate kinase
PA2964	<i>pabC</i>	5.2	0.5329	0.0006	2.7710	0.0187	4-amino-4-deoxychorismate lyase
PA2965	<i>fabF1</i>	4.0	0.4250	0.0227	1.7000	0.0021	beta-ketoacyl-acyl carrier protein synthase II
PA2966	<i>acpP</i>	2.9	0.5541	0.0440	1.6070	0.0154	acyl carrier protein
PA2967	<i>fabG</i>	4.7	0.3511	0.0031	1.6500	0.0035	3-oxoacyl-[acyl-carrier-protein] reductase
PA2968	<i>fabD</i>	8.2	0.2854	0.0204	2.3400	0.0154	malonyl-CoA-[acyl-carrier-protein] transacylase
PA2969	<i>plsX</i>	5.5	0.4267	0.0019	2.3470	0.0228	fatty acid biosynthesis protein PlsX
PA2970	<i>rpmF</i>	7.3	0.2411	0.0154	1.7600	0.0447	50S ribosomal protein L32
PA2971		5.2	0.3821	0.0022	1.9870	0.0130	CHP
PA2972		2.8	0.4982	0.2524	1.3950	0.1123	CHP
PA2973		3.1	0.5223	0.0481	1.6190	0.0061	Pr. peptidase
PA2974		2.1	0.6914	0.1850	1.4520	0.0553	Pr. hydrolase
PA2977	<i>murB</i>	2.8	0.4829	0.3243	1.3520	0.0660	UDP-N-acetylpyruvoylglucosamine reductase
PA2978	<i>ptpA</i>	2.4	0.6604	0.2607	1.5850	0.0675	phosphotyrosine protein phosphatase
PA2981	<i>lpxK</i>	2.3	0.6374	0.0238	1.4660	0.0296	tetraacyldisaccharide 4*-kinase
PA2982		2.3	0.6491	0.0107	1.4930	0.0202	CHP
PA2983		4.1	0.4720	0.0942	1.9350	0.0205	Pr. tolQ-type transport protein
PA2986		4.3	0.5123	0.0048	2.2030	0.0234	CHP
PA2987		3.3	0.4436	0.0546	1.4640	0.0239	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA2988		2.7	0.4996	0.0654	1.3490	0.0447	CHP
PA2991	<i>sth</i>	2.1	0.7676	0.1556	1.6120	0.0516	soluble pyridine nucleotide transhydrogenase

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA2993		2.6	0.4869	0.0518	1.2660	0.0360	CHP
PA2994	<i>nqrF</i>	3.5	0.4577	0.0168	1.6020	0.0318	Na ⁺ -translocating NADH:quinone oxidoreductase, subunit Nqr6
PA2995	<i>nqrE</i>	4.8	0.2998	0.0157	1.4390	0.0212	Na ⁺ -translocating NADH:quinone oxidoreductase subunit Nqr5
PA2996	<i>nqrD</i>	5.9	0.3232	0.0186	1.9070	0.0147	Na ⁺ -translocating NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase subunit Nqr4
PA2997	<i>nqrC</i>	3.7	0.3989	0.0112	1.4760	0.0271	Na ⁺ -translocating NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase subunit Nqr3
PA2998	<i>nqrB</i>	4.0	0.3763	0.0160	1.5050	0.0067	Na ⁺ -translocating NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase subunit Nqr2
PA2999	<i>nqrA</i>	5.5	0.3673	0.0451	2.0200	0.0066	Na ⁺ -translocating NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase subunit Nqr1
PA3000	<i>aroP1</i>	3.1	0.5916	0.0261	1.8340	0.0562	aromatic amino acid transport protein AroP1
PA3001		4.8	0.3892	0.0171	1.8680	0.0063	Pr. glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase
PA3003		2.2	0.6941	0.1553	1.5270	0.1361	HP
PA3010		2.4	0.6429	0.0330	1.5430	0.0421	HP
PA3011	<i>topA</i>	4.0	0.5273	0.0415	2.1090	0.0066	DNA topoisomerase I
PA3013	<i>foaB</i>	2.1	0.5710	0.1595	1.1990	0.1253	fatty-acid oxidation complex beta-subunit
PA3019		4.2	0.4674	0.0303	1.9630	0.0296	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA3046		3.1	0.4887	0.1073	1.5150	0.0280	CHP
PA3081		3.3	0.4173	0.0169	1.3770	0.0636	CHP
PA3082	<i>gbt</i>	3.6	0.5253	0.0155	1.8910	0.0251	glycine betaine transmethylase
PA3087		2.1	0.5305	0.3572	1.1140	0.3107	HP
PA3107	<i>metZ</i>	2.7	0.4796	0.0358	1.2950	0.0248	o-succinylhomoserine sulfhydrylase
PA3108	<i>purF</i>	2.6	0.6054	0.0988	1.5740	0.0392	amidophosphoribosyltransferase
PA3111	<i>folC</i>	5.3	0.3868	0.0181	2.0500	0.0087	folylpolyglutamate synthetase
PA3112	<i>accD</i>	12.6	0.1312	0.3160	1.6530	0.0074	acetyl-CoA carboxylase beta subunit
PA3114	<i>truA</i>	2.2	0.6255	0.0043	1.3760	0.0257	tRNA-pseudouridine synthase I
PA3116		12.5	0.1738	0.2415	2.1730	0.0097	Pr. aspartate-semialdehyde dehydrogenase
PA3117	<i>asd</i>	4.3	0.3884	0.0625	1.6700	0.0310	aspartate semialdehyde dehydrogenase
PA3129		4.1	0.4773	0.0510	1.9570	0.0207	CHP
PA3134	<i>gltX</i>	3.9	0.3997	0.1277	1.5590	0.0079	glutamyl-tRNA synthetase
PA3139		5.6	0.3325	0.0464	1.8620	0.0028	Pr. amino acid aminotransferase
PA3148	<i>wbpI</i>	2.1	0.7057	0.1188	1.4820	0.1270	Pr. UDP-N-acetylglucosamine 2-epimerase WbpI
PA3154	<i>wzy</i>	3.5	0.4377	0.3034	1.5320	0.1665	B-band O-antigen polymerase
PA3162	<i>rpsA</i>	8.4	0.2417	0.0068	2.0300	0.0036	30S ribosomal protein S1
PA3163	<i>cmk</i>	4.7	0.3119	0.0127	1.4660	0.0059	cytidylate kinase
PA3164		3.0	0.4557	0.0129	1.3670	0.0056	still frameshift 3-phosphoshikimate 1-carboxyvinyltransferase prephenate dehydrogenase
PA3165	<i>hisC2</i>	4.4	0.3675	0.0059	1.6170	0.0073	histidinol-phosphate aminotransferase
PA3166	<i>pheA</i>	3.7	0.4032	0.0248	1.4920	0.0157	chorismate mutase
PA3167	<i>serC</i>	3.7	0.3978	0.0187	1.4720	0.0526	3-phosphoserine aminotransferase
PA3168	<i>gyrA</i>	3.0	0.5333	0.0589	1.6000	0.0158	DNA gyrase subunit A
PA3169		4.1	0.4371	0.0897	1.7920	0.0147	Pr. initiation factor 2 subunit
PA3171	<i>ubiG</i>	2.9	0.5110	0.0693	1.4820	0.0022	3-demethylubiquinone-9 3-methyltransferase
PA3172		3.2	0.4894	0.0210	1.5660	0.0081	Pr. hydrolase
PA3173		4.0	0.4548	0.0029	1.8190	0.0169	Pr. short-chain dehydrogenase
PA3179		8.1	0.2780	0.0095	2.2520	0.0136	CHP
PA3181		2.4	0.4838	0.2329	1.1610	0.0544	2-keto-3-deoxy-6-phosphogluconate aldolase
PA3187		3.1	0.4177	0.0365	1.2950	0.0799	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA3188		3.7	0.3451	0.0245	1.2770	0.1033	Pr. permease of ABC sugar transporter
PA3189		2.8	0.4607	0.0335	1.2900	0.0942	Pr. permease of ABC sugar transporter

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA3208		2.4	0.6296	0.1687	1.5110	0.1053	CHP
PA3209		5.3	0.4549	0.0267	2.4110	0.0115	CHP
PA3210	<i>trkH</i>	4.6	0.4222	0.0166	1.9420	0.0376	potassium uptake protein TrkH
PA3221	<i>csaA</i>	10.8	0.2036	0.3483	2.1990	0.0701	CsaA protein
PA3222		7.3	0.2136	0.1903	1.5590	0.0136	HP
PA3233		2.2	0.6368	0.2800	1.4010	0.1098	HP
PA3242		2.8	0.5929	0.0479	1.6600	0.0213	Pr. lauroyl acyltransferase
PA3243	<i>minC</i>	2.5	0.5588	0.1055	1.3970	0.0192	cell division inhibitor MinC
PA3244	<i>minD</i>	3.2	0.4847	0.0986	1.5510	0.0129	cell division inhibitor MinD
PA3245	<i>minE</i>	4.5	0.4151	0.0671	1.8680	0.0273	cell division topological specificity factor MinE
PA3246	<i>rluA</i>	5.2	0.3544	0.0026	1.8430	0.0006	pseudouridine synthase RluA
PA3262		2.3	0.6283	0.2021	1.4450	0.1057	Pr. peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase, FkbP-type
PA3263		2.9	0.5221	0.0722	1.5140	0.0244	CHP
PA3268		3.0	0.6847	0.2787	2.0540	0.0841	Pr. TonB-dependent receptor
PA3270		2.1	0.6443	0.1085	1.3530	0.0976	HP
PA3275		2.5	0.6828	0.2017	1.7070	0.1295	CHP
PA3276		6.2	0.2685	0.3068	1.6650	0.0323	HP
PA3297		2.4	0.5921	0.0971	1.4210	0.0848	Pr. ATP-dependent helicase
PA3299	<i>fadD1</i>	8.1	0.1915	0.2841	1.5510	0.0168	long-chain-fatty-acid--CoA ligase
PA3308	<i>hepA</i>	6.8	0.2760	0.0053	1.8770	0.0112	RNA helicase HepA
PA3310		10.2	0.1813	0.2559	1.8490	0.0498	CHP
PA3313		8.2	0.2851	0.1250	2.3380	0.0080	HP
PA3314		9.5	0.2391	0.1558	2.2710	0.0080	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA3315		10.4	0.1662	0.0992	1.7280	0.0415	Pr. permease of ABC transporter
PA3316		6.0	0.2768	0.0729	1.6610	0.0217	Pr. permease of ABC transporter
PA3327		2.6	0.7938	0.0332	2.0640	0.0208	Pr. non-ribosomal peptide synthetase
PA3328		3.6	0.4911	0.2834	1.7680	0.1121	Pr. FAD-dependent monooxygenase
PA3329		2.9	0.6028	0.2302	1.7480	0.1158	HP
PA3330		6.3	0.2956	0.3455	1.8620	0.2033	Pr. short chain dehydrogenase
PA3331		3.1	0.5245	0.3488	1.6260	0.2065	cytochrome P450
PA3332		5.6	0.3071	0.3590	1.7200	0.0624	CHP
PA3333	<i>fabH2</i>	2.2	0.7159	0.3285	1.5750	0.1799	3-oxoacyl-[acyl-carrier-protein] synthase III
PA3334		2.6	0.5927	0.3123	1.5410	0.1636	Pr. acyl carrier protein
PA3344	<i>recQ</i>	2.3	0.5765	0.0285	1.3260	0.0448	ATP-dependent DNA helicase RecQ
PA3388		2.6	0.5031	0.0507	1.3080	0.0359	CHP
PA3397	<i>fpr</i>	3.6	0.5378	0.0317	1.9360	0.0581	ferredoxin--NADP+ reductase
PA3403		3.1	0.5084	0.0051	1.5760	0.0057	HP
PA3435		2.6	0.5296	0.1214	1.3770	0.0511	CHP
PA3453		3.9	0.4936	0.0143	1.9250	0.0105	CHP
PA3468		2.5	0.5372	0.0237	1.3430	0.0112	CHP
PA3473		2.6	0.7062	0.0643	1.8360	0.0446	HP
PA3474		2.5	0.5884	0.0353	1.4710	0.0423	CHP
PA3478	<i>rhlB</i>	2.8	0.6414	0.0453	1.7960	0.0186	rhamnosyltransferase chain B
PA3480		3.8	0.5137	0.1086	1.9520	0.0219	Pr. deoxycytidine triphosphate deaminase
PA3489		3.8	0.4237	0.0252	1.6100	0.0142	CHP
PA3490		7.4	0.2661	0.0066	1.9690	0.0056	Pr. ferredoxin
PA3491		3.0	0.4530	0.0191	1.3590	0.0253	Pr. ferredoxin
PA3493		5.2	0.2602	0.1105	1.3530	0.0465	CHP
PA3494		2.8	0.4300	0.0737	1.2040	0.1499	CHP
PA3525	<i>argG</i>	3.3	0.4748	0.0740	1.5670	0.0191	argininosuccinate synthase

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA3529		2.2	0.6609	0.1880	1.4540	0.0436	Pr. peroxidase
PA3532		2.1	0.6510	0.0584	1.3670	0.1311	HP
PA3537	<i>argF</i>	2.6	0.6746	0.1269	1.7540	0.0303	ornithine carbamoyltransferase, anabolic
PA3552		2.4	0.6529	0.1995	1.5670	0.1692	CHP
PA3553		4.0	0.3843	0.2221	1.5370	0.1400	Pr. glycosyl transferase
PA3555		4.0	0.3450	0.1705	1.3800	0.1291	CHP
PA3562		3.1	0.3984	0.0608	1.2350	0.0619	Pr. phosphotransferase system enzyme I
PA3603	<i>dgkA</i>	2.9	0.5183	0.0228	1.5030	0.0039	diacylglycerol kinase
PA3604		2.3	0.6013	0.0946	1.3830	0.0433	Pr. two-component response regulator
PA3607	<i>potA</i>	5.5	0.4091	0.0684	2.2500	0.0182	polyamine transport protein PotA
PA3608	<i>potB</i>	21.5	0.1233	0.1463	2.6500	0.0179	polyamine transport protein PotB
PA3609	<i>potC</i>	6.1	0.4134	0.0099	2.5220	0.0107	polyamine transport protein PotC
PA3610	<i>potD</i>	12.6	0.1475	0.0861	1.8590	0.0013	polyamine transport protein PotD
PA3620	<i>mutS</i>	3.2	0.5163	0.0512	1.6520	0.0175	DNA mismatch repair protein MutS
PA3621	<i>fdxA</i>	4.5	0.4547	0.0520	2.0460	0.0862	ferredoxin I
PA3626		2.6	0.4842	0.1701	1.2590	0.0404	CHP
PA3631		2.2	0.7223	0.0900	1.5890	0.0813	CHP
PA3632		2.4	0.6233	0.1006	1.4960	0.0441	CHP
PA3635	<i>eno</i>	8.7	0.2053	0.0149	1.7860	0.0016	enolase
PA3636	<i>kdsA</i>	6.1	0.3021	0.0102	1.8430	0.0210	2-dehydro-3-deoxyphosphooctonate aldolase
PA3637	<i>pyrG</i>	5.6	0.3302	0.0446	1.8490	0.0015	CTP synthase
PA3638		6.9	0.3607	0.2175	2.4890	0.0211	CHP
PA3639	<i>accA</i>	2.9	0.5128	0.0522	1.4870	0.0331	acetyl-coenzyme A carboxylase carboxyl transferase (alpha subunit)
PA3640	<i>dnaE</i>	2.5	0.5048	0.0494	1.2620	0.0876	DNA polymerase III, alpha chain
PA3641		8.1	0.2726	0.0214	2.2080	0.0293	Pr. amino acid permease
PA3642	<i>rnhB</i>	4.6	0.5802	0.0181	2.6690	0.0304	ribonuclease HII
PA3643	<i>lpxB</i>	4.4	0.4402	0.0208	1.9370	0.0162	lipid A-disaccharide synthase
PA3644	<i>lpxA</i>	4.7	0.3757	0.0153	1.7660	0.0056	UDP-N-acetylglucosamine acyltransferase
PA3645	<i>fabZ</i>	5.2	0.3554	0.0257	1.8480	0.0044	(3R)-hydroxymyristoyl-[acyl carrier protein] dehydratase
PA3646	<i>lpxD</i>	4.2	0.3224	0.0165	1.3540	0.0016	UDP-3-O-[3-hydroxylauroyl] glucosamine N-acyltransferase
PA3647		5.1	0.2776	0.0906	1.4160	0.0056	Pr. outer membrane protein precursor
PA3648		4.6	0.3963	0.0101	1.8230	0.0089	Pr. outer membrane protein precursor
PA3650	<i>dxr</i>	2.8	0.6089	0.0366	1.7050	0.0599	1-deoxy-d-xylulose 5-phosphate reductoisomerase
PA3651	<i>cdsA</i>	5.2	0.3356	0.0331	1.7450	0.0181	phosphatidate cytidyltransferase
PA3652	<i>uppS</i>	5.9	0.3063	0.0037	1.8070	0.0131	undecaprenyl pyrophosphate synthetase
PA3653	<i>frr</i>	6.0	0.3358	0.0580	2.0150	0.0145	ribosome recycling factor
PA3654	<i>pyrH</i>	10.2	0.2131	0.0297	2.1740	0.0043	uridylylase kinase
PA3655	<i>tsf</i>	6.0	0.2985	0.0243	1.7910	0.0231	elongation factor Ts
PA3658	<i>glnD</i>	2.7	0.5681	0.0053	1.5340	0.0063	protein-PII uridylyltransferase
PA3659		2.6	0.5912	0.1116	1.5370	0.0144	Pr. aminotransferase
PA3665		2.9	0.4855	0.1753	1.4080	0.1260	HP
PA3666	<i>dapD</i>	2.8	0.5432	0.0610	1.5210	0.0020	tetrahydrodipicolinate succinylase
PA3670		3.3	0.4897	0.0045	1.6160	0.0108	HP
PA3671		2.6	0.6838	0.0178	1.7780	0.0445	Pr. permease of ABC transporter
PA3673	<i>plsB</i>	2.3	0.6335	0.0735	1.4570	0.0282	glycerol-3-phosphate acyltransferase
PA3679		2.1	0.5614	0.2726	1.1790	0.1912	HP
PA3685		5.7	0.2874	0.1417	1.6380	0.0529	CHP
PA3686	<i>adk</i>	4.6	0.3798	0.0976	1.7470	0.0151	adenylate kinase
PA3694		2.7	0.5533	0.1964	1.4940	0.0458	HP
PA3696		2.9	0.4366	0.3716	1.2660	0.0984	CHP

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA3700	<i>lysS</i>	6.3	0.3292	0.0086	2.0740	0.0059	lysyl-tRNA synthetase
PA3701	<i>prfB</i>	5.1	0.3324	0.0624	1.6950	0.0029	peptide chain release factor 2
PA3713		8.7	0.2184	0.0588	1.9000	0.0298	HP
PA3716		4.3	0.3170	0.0316	1.3630	0.0005	HP
PA3717		2.3	0.5961	0.1071	1.3710	0.1728	Pr. peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase, FkbP-type
PA3724	<i>lasB</i>	4.2	0.4764	0.2761	2.0010	0.0611	elastase LasB
PA3725	<i>recJ</i>	3.2	0.5363	0.0017	1.7160	0.0314	single-stranded-DNA-specific exonuclease RecJ
PA3726		3.1	0.5503	0.0510	1.7060	0.0070	CHP
PA3735	<i>thrC</i>	3.8	0.3792	0.0088	1.4410	0.0127	threonine synthase
PA3736	<i>hom</i>	5.0	0.3580	0.0330	1.7900	0.0019	homoserine dehydrogenase
PA3741		6.0	0.3152	0.0299	1.8910	0.0127	HP
PA3742	<i>rplS</i>	6.9	0.2351	0.0162	1.6220	0.0279	50S ribosomal protein L19
PA3743	<i>trmD</i>	10.5	0.2332	0.0015	2.4490	0.0045	tRNA (guanine-N1)-methyltransferase
PA3744	<i>rimM</i>	8.2	0.2341	0.0010	1.9200	0.0016	16S rRNA processing protein
PA3745	<i>rpsP</i>	10.1	0.2229	0.0182	2.2510	0.0040	30S ribosomal protein S16
PA3746	<i>ffh</i>	4.8	0.3288	0.0920	1.5780	0.0015	signal recognition particle protein Ffh
PA3750		2.1	0.6400	0.0920	1.3440	0.1382	HP
PA3763	<i>purL</i>	3.7	0.4630	0.0134	1.7130	0.0043	phosphoribosylformylglycinamide synthase
PA3766		4.5	0.4218	0.2337	1.8980	0.0266	Pr. aromatic amino acid transporter
PA3769	<i>guaA</i>	6.2	0.2669	0.0123	1.6550	0.0054	GMP synthase
PA3770	<i>guaB</i>	7.3	0.2727	0.0750	1.9910	0.0042	inosine-5'-monophosphate dehydrogenase
PA3779		2.5	0.5344	0.0185	1.3360	0.0654	HP
PA3780		5.5	0.2760	0.1504	1.5180	0.0418	HP
PA3781		2.6	0.5615	0.0368	1.4600	0.0177	Pr. transporter
PA3784		2.5	0.6084	0.0452	1.5210	0.0537	HP
PA3785		5.8	0.3245	0.1455	1.8820	0.0562	CHP
PA3798		5.7	0.2842	0.3102	1.6200	0.0309	Pr. aminotransferase
PA3799		2.8	0.5100	0.0274	1.4280	0.0342	CHP
PA3800		2.8	0.5107	0.0770	1.4300	0.0619	CHP
PA3801		2.6	0.4554	0.0788	1.1840	0.0569	CHP
PA3802	<i>hisS</i>	4.7	0.3079	0.0740	1.4470	0.0409	histidyl-tRNA synthetase
PA3803	<i>gcpE</i>	4.8	0.2988	0.0249	1.4340	0.0161	Pr. isoprenoid biosynthetic protein GcpE
PA3804		5.6	0.2561	0.0223	1.4340	0.0680	HP
PA3805	<i>pilF</i>	5.5	0.3444	0.0140	1.8940	0.0062	type 4 fimbrial biogenesis protein PilF
PA3806		7.6	0.2732	0.0152	2.0760	0.0106	CHP
PA3807	<i>ndk</i>	5.2	0.3779	0.0113	1.9650	0.0027	nucleoside diphosphate kinase
PA3808		2.4	0.5796	0.0328	1.3910	0.0810	CHP
PA3809	<i>fdx2</i>	2.8	0.4464	0.0424	1.2500	0.1443	ferredoxin [2Fe-2S]
PA3810	<i>hscA</i>	3.8	0.4355	0.0176	1.6550	0.0104	heat shock protein HscA
PA3811	<i>hscB</i>	2.1	0.6867	0.0036	1.4420	0.0305	heat shock protein HscB
PA3816	<i>cysE</i>	2.4	0.5196	0.0433	1.2470	0.0152	O-acetylserine synthase
PA3817		2.2	0.7405	0.0757	1.6290	0.0949	Pr. methyltransferase
PA3818		11.3	0.2080	0.0050	2.3500	0.0026	extragenic suppressor protein SuhB
PA3820	<i>secF</i>	5.3	0.2789	0.0266	1.4780	0.0406	secretion protein SecF
PA3821	<i>secD</i>	9.7	0.2167	0.0744	2.1020	0.0099	secretion protein SecD
PA3822		4.9	0.4192	0.1319	2.0540	0.0303	CHP
PA3823	<i>tgt</i>	6.1	0.3338	0.0424	2.0360	0.0115	queuine tRNA-ribosyltransferase
PA3824	<i>queA</i>	4.9	0.3557	0.0020	1.7430	0.0020	S-adenosylmethionine:trna ribosyltransferase-isomerase
PA3827		8.4	0.2032	0.2750	1.7070	0.0278	CHP
PA3828		3.6	0.4144	0.1081	1.4920	0.0206	CHP

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PA3834	<i>valS</i>	4.7	0.3504	0.0293	1.6470	0.0299	valyl-tRNA synthetase
PA3840		3.4	0.4865	0.2302	1.6540	0.0477	CHP
PA3853		2.8	0.6993	0.0364	1.9580	0.0174	Pr. transferase
PA3854		3.3	0.5109	0.1613	1.6860	0.0383	HP
PA3864		2.2	0.6732	0.0203	1.4810	0.0396	HP
PA3884		2.4	0.6100	0.2210	1.4640	0.0937	HP
PA3887	<i>nhaP</i>	2.9	0.3590	0.2979	1.0410	0.7596	Na ⁺ /H ⁺ antiporter NhaP
PA3903	<i>prfC</i>	5.1	0.3678	0.0873	1.8760	0.0095	peptide chain release factor 3
PA3904		3.4	0.5059	0.0555	1.7200	0.0060	HP
PA3905		5.3	0.3534	0.1136	1.8730	0.0127	HP
PA3906		6.3	0.3424	0.0510	2.1570	0.0085	HP
PA3907		6.0	0.2308	0.0156	1.3850	0.0039	HP
PA3908		5.6	0.2634	0.0174	1.4750	0.0315	HP
PA3922		2.3	0.4948	0.2471	1.1380	0.4621	CHP
PA3925		2.1	0.7395	0.1782	1.5530	0.0503	Pr. acyl-CoA thiolase
PA3940		2.8	0.5918	0.0625	1.6570	0.0333	Pr. DNA binding protein
PA3958		2.4	0.4650	0.3288	1.1160	0.3506	HP
PA3959		2.4	0.5679	0.0628	1.3630	0.0089	HP
PA3967		7.4	0.2908	0.2194	2.1520	0.0065	HP
PA3977	<i>hemL</i>	2.7	0.5722	0.0920	1.5450	0.0075	glutamate-1-semialdehyde 2,1-aminomutase
PA3979		2.8	0.6204	0.0235	1.7370	0.0479	HP
PA3980		5.5	0.3740	0.0437	2.0570	0.0081	CHP
PA3984	<i>Int</i>	11.7	0.1345	0.3172	1.5740	0.0410	apolipoprotein N-acyltransferase
PA3987	<i>leuS</i>	2.2	0.7723	0.3322	1.6990	0.0280	leucyl-tRNA synthetase
PA3988		3.4	0.6382	0.2192	2.1700	0.0485	HP
PA3989	<i>holA</i>	2.5	0.5684	0.0659	1.4210	0.0734	DNA polymerase III, delta subunit
PA3992		2.5	0.4960	0.0417	1.2400	0.0241	HP
PA3997	<i>lipB</i>	2.3	0.6435	0.0231	1.4800	0.0076	lipoate-protein ligase B
PA4002	<i>rodA</i>	2.3	0.6561	0.0435	1.5090	0.0665	rod shape-determining protein
PA4003	<i>pbpA</i>	3.1	0.4626	0.0595	1.4340	0.0107	penicillin-binding protein 2
PA4004		5.6	0.3352	0.0029	1.8770	0.0026	CHP
PA4005		5.6	0.3359	0.0520	1.8810	0.0096	CHP
PA4006	<i>nadD</i>	6.0	0.3275	0.0343	1.9650	0.0119	nicotinic acid mononucleotide adenylyltransferase
PA4007	<i>proA</i>	3.3	0.5076	0.0234	1.6750	0.0093	gamma-glutamyl phosphate reductase
PA4023		2.2	0.6450	0.3034	1.4190	0.0998	Pr. transport protein
PA4029		2.6	0.5450	0.1222	1.4170	0.0442	CHP
PA4030		3.1	0.4194	0.0767	1.3000	0.0190	CHP
PA4031	<i>ppa</i>	6.3	0.3613	0.0210	2.2760	0.0089	inorganic pyrophosphatase
PA4043	<i>ispA</i>	3.3	0.4494	0.0718	1.4830	0.0072	geranyltranstransferase
PA4045		2.8	0.6250	0.0086	1.7500	0.0406	CHP
PA4046		2.1	0.6914	0.0601	1.4520	0.0318	HP
PA4050	<i>pgpA</i>	2.8	0.6539	0.1710	1.8310	0.0233	phosphatidylglycerophosphatase A
PA4051	<i>thiL</i>	6.5	0.3403	0.1435	2.2120	0.0172	thiamine monophosphate kinase
PA4052	<i>nusB</i>	3.3	0.5603	0.0429	1.8490	0.0097	NusB protein
PA4053	<i>ribE</i>	3.3	0.4988	0.0377	1.6460	0.0106	6,7-dimethyl-8-ribityllumazine synthase
PA4054	<i>ribB</i>	7.0	0.2707	0.0063	1.8950	0.0060	GTP cyclohydrolase II
PA4055	<i>ribC</i>	12.9	0.1672	0.1985	2.1570	0.0057	riboflavin synthase alpha chain
PA4059		3.5	0.4200	0.0684	1.4700	0.0040	HP
PA4060		3.6	0.4614	0.0438	1.6610	0.0126	HP
PA4075		2.2	0.5223	0.1933	1.1490	0.2641	HP

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA4113		2.9	0.6572	0.0060	1.9060	0.0108	Pr. MFS transporter
PA4116		2.1	0.6848	0.0849	1.4380	0.0173	HP
PA4130		3.0	0.4663	0.2317	1.3990	0.1965	Pr. sulfite or nitrite reductase
PA4131		34.1	0.1517	0.3044	5.1720	0.0300	Pr. iron-sulfur protein
PA4132		3.4	0.7262	0.1452	2.4690	0.0461	CHP
PA4135		3.5	0.5894	0.1184	2.0630	0.0626	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA4138	<i>tyrS</i>	2.9	0.7052	0.0857	2.0450	0.0737	tyrosyl-tRNA synthetase
PA4140		3.1	0.4477	0.3470	1.3880	0.1067	HP
PA4175	<i>prpL</i>	2.3	0.6357	0.1630	1.4620	0.0768	Pvds-regulated endoprotease, lysyl class
PA4191		3.0	0.8120	0.1792	2.4360	0.0211	Pr. iron/ascorbate oxidoreductase
PA4193		7.7	0.6779	0.0945	5.2200	0.0239	Pr. permease of ABC transporter
PA4195		9.5	0.2169	0.0429	2.0610	0.1317	Pr. binding protein component of ABC transporter
PA4211		3.9	0.7203	0.0927	2.8090	0.0749	Pr. phenazine biosynthesis protein
PA4217	<i>phzS</i>	3.2	0.4681	0.3161	1.4980	0.1837	flavin-containing monooxygenase
PA4233		7.3	0.2582	0.1588	1.8850	0.0143	Pr. MFS transporter
PA4234	<i>uvrA</i>	4.4	0.3889	0.0925	1.7110	0.0034	excinuclease ABC subunit A
PA4237	<i>rplQ</i>	2.8	0.4257	0.0142	1.1920	0.0284	50S ribosomal protein L17
PA4238	<i>rpoA</i>	2.4	0.5213	0.0228	1.2510	0.0660	DNA-directed RNA polymerase alpha chain
PA4239	<i>rpsD</i>	2.7	0.4385	0.0198	1.1840	0.0294	30S ribosomal protein S4
PA4240	<i>rpsK</i>	2.7	0.4730	0.0276	1.2770	0.0673	30S ribosomal protein S11
PA4243	<i>secY</i>	4.3	0.3772	0.0615	1.6220	0.1116	secretion protein SecY
PA4244	<i>rplO</i>	3.0	0.5023	0.0197	1.5070	0.0298	50S ribosomal protein L15
PA4247	<i>rplR</i>	3.3	0.3694	0.0193	1.2190	0.0193	50S ribosomal protein L18
PA4248	<i>rplF</i>	3.0	0.4657	0.0167	1.3970	0.0291	50S ribosomal protein L6
PA4249	<i>rpsH</i>	2.6	0.5050	0.0288	1.3130	0.0861	30S ribosomal protein S8
PA4254	<i>rpsQ</i>	3.1	0.4174	0.0406	1.2940	0.1523	30S ribosomal protein S17
PA4255	<i>rpmC</i>	6.9	0.1825	0.0210	1.2590	0.0182	50S ribosomal protein L29
PA4256	<i>rplP</i>	4.5	0.3116	0.0288	1.4020	0.1417	50S ribosomal protein L16
PA4257	<i>rpsC</i>	4.6	0.2735	0.0200	1.2580	0.0889	30S ribosomal protein S3
PA4258	<i>rplV</i>	4.9	0.3110	0.0200	1.5240	0.0265	50S ribosomal protein L22
PA4259	<i>rpsS</i>	4.9	0.2655	0.0240	1.3010	0.0983	30S ribosomal protein S19
PA4260	<i>rplB</i>	4.5	0.3893	0.0201	1.7520	0.0357	50S ribosomal protein L2
PA4261	<i>rplW</i>	6.1	0.2495	0.0170	1.5220	0.0218	50S ribosomal protein L23
PA4262	<i>rplD</i>	6.4	0.2559	0.0194	1.6380	0.0117	50S ribosomal protein L4
PA4263	<i>rplC</i>	5.9	0.2964	0.0133	1.7490	0.0234	50S ribosomal protein L3
PA4264	<i>rpsJ</i>	3.9	0.3626	0.0131	1.4140	0.0146	30S ribosomal protein S10
PA4265	<i>tufA</i>	3.6	0.3561	0.0190	1.2820	0.0404	elongation factor Tu
PA4266	<i>fusA1</i>	4.0	0.4140	0.0141	1.6560	0.0124	elongation factor G
PA4267	<i>rpsG</i>	3.5	0.5180	0.0076	1.8130	0.0351	30S ribosomal protein S7
PA4268	<i>rpsL</i>	5.0	0.3178	0.0046	1.5890	0.0058	30S ribosomal protein S12
PA4269	<i>rpoC</i>	2.3	0.5661	0.0662	1.3020	0.1128	DNA-directed RNA polymerase beta* chain
PA4270	<i>rpoB</i>	4.4	0.2643	0.0193	1.1630	0.0335	DNA-directed RNA polymerase beta chain
PA4271	<i>rplL</i>	3.2	0.3959	0.0314	1.2670	0.1001	50S ribosomal protein L7 / L12
PA4273	<i>rplA</i>	2.8	0.4764	0.0287	1.3340	0.0535	50S ribosomal protein L1
PA4275	<i>nusG</i>	10.1	0.2607	0.0302	2.6330	0.0040	transcription antitermination protein NusG
PA4276	<i>secE</i>	10.6	0.2079	0.0682	2.2040	0.0065	secretion protein SecE
PA4278		2.9	0.5497	0.1480	1.5940	0.0345	HP
PA4279		2.1	0.7143	0.2105	1.5000	0.0400	HP
PA4280	<i>birA</i>	2.9	0.5066	0.0105	1.4690	0.0324	BirA bifunctional protein
PA4291		2.5	0.6512	0.1139	1.6280	0.0822	HP

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA4292		7.5	0.2633	0.0454	1.9750	0.0093	Pr. phosphate transporter
PA4307	<i>pctC</i>	2.2	0.5809	0.0960	1.2780	0.0520	chemotactic transducer PctC
PA4319		2.5	0.5568	0.0640	1.3920	0.0108	CHP
PA4320		2.2	0.5423	0.0086	1.1930	0.0022	HP
PA4329	<i>pykA</i>	2.7	0.5907	0.0592	1.5950	0.0123	pyruvate kinase II
PA4333		6.4	0.3045	0.0374	1.9490	0.0058	Pr. fumarase
PA4372		7.2	0.3657	0.2115	2.6330	0.1046	HP
PA4373		2.8	0.7868	0.0803	2.2030	0.0514	HP
PA4374		2.1	0.5900	0.1168	1.2390	0.1266	Pr. RND efflux membrane fusion protein precursor
PA4375		3.2	0.6044	0.0236	1.9340	0.0384	Pr. RND efflux transporter
PA4380		3.4	0.4159	0.1820	1.4140	0.0735	Pr. two-component sensor
PA4390		3.1	0.5600	0.0387	1.7360	0.0261	HP
PA4391		2.1	0.6271	0.2116	1.3170	0.0902	HP
PA4402	<i>argJ</i>	6.3	0.3019	0.0075	1.9020	0.0021	glutamate N-acetyltransferase
PA4403	<i>secA</i>	2.9	0.6490	0.1715	1.8820	0.0506	secretion protein SecA
PA4404		3.4	0.6124	0.0028	2.0820	0.0196	HP
PA4427	<i>sspB</i>	2.2	0.5900	0.2318	1.2980	0.0923	stringent starvation protein B
PA4428	<i>sspA</i>	5.1	0.4114	0.0117	2.0980	0.0083	stringent starvation protein A
PA4429		16.3	0.1450	0.2087	2.3640	0.0192	Pr. cytochrome c1 precursor
PA4430		10.6	0.1894	0.0187	2.0080	0.0034	Pr. cytochrome b
PA4431		8.9	0.2564	0.1150	2.2820	0.0141	Pr. iron-sulfur protein
PA4432	<i>rpsI</i>	7.2	0.3781	0.0314	2.7220	0.0095	30S ribosomal protein S9
PA4433	<i>rplM</i>	6.7	0.3191	0.0174	2.1380	0.0165	50S ribosomal protein L13
PA4438		7.5	0.3043	0.1102	2.2820	0.0110	CHP
PA4442	<i>cysN</i>	6.1	0.4166	0.0663	2.5410	0.0223	ATP sulfurylase GTP-binding subunit/APS kinase
PA4443	<i>cysD</i>	5.8	0.3829	0.0633	2.2210	0.0232	ATP sulfurylase small subunit
PA4445		2.9	0.5469	0.0545	1.5860	0.0362	CHP
PA4449	<i>hisG</i>	3.2	0.5181	0.0359	1.6580	0.0122	ATP-phosphoribosyltransferase
PA4450	<i>murA</i>	2.3	0.5683	0.0826	1.3070	0.0131	UDP-N-acetylglucosamine 1-carboxyvinyltransferase
PA4451		2.4	0.4958	0.1604	1.1900	0.2358	CHP
PA4452		3.1	0.4681	0.0202	1.4510	0.0218	CHP
PA4453		2.7	0.5463	0.0571	1.4750	0.0184	CHP
PA4454		2.5	0.5680	0.0426	1.4200	0.0352	CHP
PA4455		5.6	0.3875	0.1459	2.1700	0.0173	Pr. permease of ABC transporter
PA4456		3.9	0.4759	0.1591	1.8560	0.0169	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA4459		2.9	0.7117	0.0894	2.0640	0.0574	CHP
PA4461		2.5	0.6856	0.0220	1.7140	0.0485	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA4478		2.2	0.6323	0.0507	1.3910	0.0306	CHP
PA4479	<i>mreD</i>	6.2	0.2519	0.0168	1.5620	0.0180	rod shape-determining protein MreD
PA4480	<i>mreC</i>	15.3	0.1305	0.0017	1.9960	0.0010	rod shape-determining protein MreC
PA4481	<i>mreB</i>	10.2	0.2070	0.0064	2.1110	0.0016	rod shape-determining protein MreB
PA4482	<i>gatC</i>	3.4	0.3715	0.1678	1.2630	0.3045	Glu-tRNA(Gln) amidotransferase subunit C
PA4483	<i>gatA</i>	3.0	0.5453	0.1111	1.6360	0.0204	Glu-tRNA(Gln) amidotransferase subunit A
PA4484	<i>gatB</i>	4.9	0.2973	0.0109	1.4570	0.0051	Glu-tRNA(Gln) amidotransferase subunit B
PA4485		3.6	0.4178	0.0110	1.5040	0.0381	CHP
PA4502		2.4	0.5229	0.0191	1.2550	0.0183	Pr. binding protein component of ABC transporter
PA4503		5.1	0.2500	0.0230	1.2750	0.0479	Pr. permease of ABC transporter
PA4504		5.7	0.2072	0.0242	1.1810	0.0255	Pr. permease of ABC transporter
PA4512	<i>lpxO1</i>	2.2	0.5350	0.1792	1.1770	0.2025	lipopolysaccharide biosynthetic protein LpxO1
PA4517		2.3	0.6300	0.0145	1.4490	0.0222	CHP

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA4519		7.8	0.4685	0.0880	3.6540	0.0391	Pr. ornithine decarboxylase
PA4543		2.5	0.5968	0.0347	1.4920	0.0672	CHP
PA4544	<i>rluD</i>	2.5	0.6480	0.0017	1.6200	0.0469	pseudouridine synthase
PA4545	<i>comL</i>	3.8	0.4134	0.0953	1.5710	0.0197	competence protein ComL
PA4548		3.9	0.4385	0.0747	1.7100	0.0233	Pr. D-amino acid oxidase
PA4557	<i>lytB</i>	5.2	0.2725	0.0222	1.4170	0.0638	LytB protein
PA4558		4.0	0.3338	0.0849	1.3350	0.0929	Pr. peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase, FkbP-type
PA4559	<i>lspA</i>	4.5	0.2773	0.0327	1.2480	0.0551	prolipoprotein signal peptidase
PA4560	<i>ileS</i>	3.1	0.5606	0.1539	1.7380	0.0275	isoleucyl-tRNA synthetase
PA4561	<i>ribF</i>	2.1	0.5219	0.1822	1.0960	0.3609	riboflavin kinase/FAD synthase
PA4562		4.2	0.4350	0.0151	1.8270	0.0118	CHP
PA4563	<i>rpsT</i>	8.9	0.2321	0.0750	2.0660	0.0029	30S ribosomal protein S20
PA4567	<i>rpmA</i>	4.0	0.4413	0.0296	1.7650	0.0124	50S ribosomal protein L27
PA4568	<i>rplU</i>	3.1	0.5597	0.0674	1.7350	0.0157	50S ribosomal protein L21
PA4569	<i>ispB</i>	7.9	0.2581	0.0075	2.0390	0.0018	octaprenyl-diphosphate synthase
PA4572	<i>fkIB</i>	8.2	0.2933	0.0136	2.4050	0.0130	peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase FklB
PA4574		3.6	0.5703	0.0127	2.0530	0.0161	CHP
PA4589		2.6	0.4485	0.3240	1.1660	0.2096	Pr. outer membrane protein precursor
PA4601		2.2	0.6759	0.1123	1.4870	0.0271	CHP
PA4602	<i>glyA3</i>	8.7	0.3211	0.0402	2.7940	0.0085	serine hydroxymethyltransferase
PA4604		2.2	0.6373	0.0576	1.4020	0.0581	CHP
PA4616		2.7	0.5156	0.0216	1.3920	0.0213	Pr. c4-dicarboxylate-binding protein
PA4625		3.1	0.4939	0.0339	1.5310	0.0581	HP
PA4627		4.1	0.4300	0.0285	1.7630	0.0030	CHP
PA4628	<i>lysP</i>	6.0	0.3405	0.0276	2.0430	0.0132	lysine-specific permease
PA4631		2.5	0.5612	0.0460	1.4030	0.0473	HP
PA4632		3.5	0.4780	0.0369	1.6730	0.0062	HP
PA4636		3.6	0.4328	0.0947	1.5580	0.0159	HP
PA4640	<i>mgoB</i>	9.9	0.2347	0.1262	2.3240	0.0094	malate:quinone oxidoreductase
PA4644		6.5	0.2854	0.2362	1.8550	0.0098	HP
PA4645		5.3	0.3811	0.0272	2.0200	0.0095	Pr. purine/pyrimidine phosphoribosyl transferase
PA4646	<i>upp</i>	8.9	0.2300	0.0332	2.0470	0.0026	uracil phosphoribosyltransferase
PA4647	<i>uraA</i>	6.1	0.3461	0.0442	2.1110	0.0057	uracil permease
PA4662	<i>murI</i>	3.3	0.4721	0.1003	1.5580	0.0293	glutamate racemase
PA4663	<i>moeB</i>	2.4	0.6800	0.0700	1.6320	0.0306	molybdopterin biosynthesis MoeB protein
PA4664	<i>hemK</i>	2.6	0.5619	0.0084	1.4610	0.0343	Pr. methyl transferase
PA4665	<i>prfA</i>	3.7	0.4243	0.0556	1.5700	0.0114	peptide chain release factor 1
PA4668		2.5	0.5860	0.0955	1.4650	0.0395	Pr. lipoprotein localization protein LolB
PA4669	<i>ipk</i>	2.4	0.6204	0.0219	1.4890	0.0556	isopentenyl monophosphate kinase
PA4670	<i>prs</i>	13.9	0.1597	0.0354	2.2200	0.0031	ribose-phosphate pyrophosphokinase
PA4671		4.3	0.2814	0.0208	1.2100	0.1639	Pr. ribosomal protein L25
PA4672		12.6	0.1930	0.0005	2.4320	0.0055	peptidyl-tRNA hydrolase
PA4673		19.2	0.1662	0.0307	3.1910	0.0105	CHP
PA4676		3.4	0.5497	0.0533	1.8690	0.0197	Pr. carbonic anhydrase
PA4684		4.6	0.4415	0.0191	2.0310	0.0105	HP
PA4685		5.7	0.3116	0.0083	1.7760	0.0099	HP
PA4695	<i>ilvH</i>	2.5	0.5560	0.0234	1.3900	0.0418	acetolactate synthase isozyme III small subunit
PA4700	<i>mrcB</i>	3.3	0.4570	0.0503	1.5080	0.0012	penicillin-binding protein 1B
PA4719		5.9	0.3475	0.0051	2.0500	0.0188	Pr. transporter
PA4720	<i>trmA</i>	4.9	0.3610	0.0004	1.7690	0.0004	tRNA (uracil-5-)-methyltransferase

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PA4723	<i>dksA</i>	5.5	0.3645	0.0231	2.0050	0.0037	suppressor protein DksA
PA4724		7.9	0.2158	0.0231	1.7050	0.0229	Pr. aminoacyl-transfer RNA synthetase (class I)
PA4730	<i>panC</i>	3.1	0.5284	0.0530	1.6380	0.0079	pantoate--beta-alanine ligase
PA4731	<i>panD</i>	5.8	0.4045	0.0489	2.3460	0.0331	aspartate 1-decarboxylase precursor
PA4741	<i>rpsO</i>	2.1	0.5838	0.0183	1.2260	0.0426	30S ribosomal protein S15
PA4742	<i>truB</i>	4.1	0.4127	0.0276	1.6920	0.0201	tRNA pseudouridine 55 synthase
PA4743	<i>rbfA</i>	6.4	0.2078	0.0158	1.3300	0.0954	ribosome-binding factor A
PA4744	<i>infB</i>	5.9	0.2427	0.0197	1.4320	0.0369	translation initiation factor IF-2
PA4745	<i>nusA</i>	9.6	0.2331	0.0050	2.2380	0.0031	N utilization substance protein A
PA4746		13.4	0.1701	0.0023	2.2790	0.0050	CHP
PA4747	<i>secG</i>	3.1	0.5371	0.0142	1.6650	0.0294	secretion protein SecG
PA4748	<i>tpiA</i>	5.1	0.4461	0.0215	2.2750	0.0148	triosephosphate isomerase
PA4753		3.0	0.4543	0.1242	1.3630	0.0627	CHP
PA4754		2.8	0.6882	0.0560	1.9270	0.0450	HP
PA4756	<i>carB</i>	3.7	0.3130	0.0205	1.1580	0.1877	carbamoylphosphate synthetase large subunit
PA4757		7.6	0.2863	0.0051	2.1760	0.0055	CHP
PA4758	<i>carA</i>	5.9	0.3166	0.0123	1.8680	0.0026	carbamoyl-phosphate synthase small chain
PA4760	<i>dnaJ</i>	5.4	0.4830	0.0604	2.6080	0.1417	DnaJ protein
PA4762	<i>grpE</i>	3.6	0.6808	0.1678	2.4510	0.1474	heat shock protein GrpE
PA4765	<i>omlA</i>	2.8	0.5168	0.1479	1.4470	0.0054	Outer membrane lipoprotein OmlA precursor
PA4769		2.1	0.5743	0.1583	1.2060	0.2047	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA4773		4.8	0.2919	0.0260	1.4010	0.1702	HP
PA4774		2.8	0.5425	0.1781	1.5190	0.1656	HP
PA4775		2.1	0.7495	0.1093	1.5740	0.0941	HP
PA4789		2.7	0.5637	0.1772	1.5220	0.0294	CHP
PA4790		3.1	0.5506	0.2102	1.7070	0.0416	CHP
PA4817		5.0	0.3168	0.1124	1.5840	0.0411	HP
PA4820		2.3	0.6091	0.1749	1.4010	0.2864	HP
PA4826		6.9	0.3204	0.0241	2.2110	0.0713	HP
PA4839	<i>speA</i>	11.4	0.1831	0.0041	2.0870	0.0037	biosynthetic arginine decarboxylase
PA4840		3.3	0.6730	0.0218	2.2210	0.0672	CHP
PA4845	<i>dipZ</i>	2.7	0.5178	0.0287	1.3980	0.1227	thiol:disulfide interchange protein DipZ
PA4846	<i>aroQ1</i>	4.0	0.3423	0.1396	1.3690	0.0907	3-dehydroquininate dehydratase
PA4847	<i>accB</i>	3.6	0.4647	0.1092	1.6730	0.0061	biotin carboxyl carrier protein (BCCP)
PA4848	<i>accC</i>	3.4	0.4847	0.0423	1.6480	0.0080	biotin carboxylase
PA4849		4.9	0.3690	0.0871	1.8080	0.0999	HP
PA4850	<i>prmA</i>	2.3	0.5691	0.0863	1.3090	0.0388	ribosomal protein L11 methyltransferase
PA4851		2.1	0.5819	0.0912	1.2220	0.0823	HP
PA4852		5.4	0.3630	0.0495	1.9600	0.0069	CHP
PA4853	<i>fis</i>	10.3	0.2196	0.0069	2.2620	0.0105	DNA-binding protein Fis
PA4854	<i>purH</i>	9.5	0.2241	0.0007	2.1290	0.0065	phosphoribosylaminoimidazolecarboxamide formyltransferase
PA4855	<i>purD</i>	10.3	0.1909	0.0189	1.9660	0.0154	phosphoribosylamine--glycine ligase
PA4865	<i>ureA</i>	2.6	0.5288	0.1794	1.3750	0.0303	urease gamma subunit
PA4866		2.6	0.5485	0.0140	1.4260	0.0299	CHP
PA4868	<i>ureC</i>	2.3	0.5891	0.1013	1.3550	0.1175	urease alpha subunit
PA4869		2.5	0.5612	0.1367	1.4030	0.0658	HP
PA4873		2.8	0.6146	0.0196	1.7210	0.0391	Pr. heat-shock protein
PA4887		2.8	0.6982	0.0085	1.9550	0.0827	Pr. MFS transporter
PA4889		3.2	0.3966	0.2076	1.2690	0.1029	Pr. oxidoreductase
PA4890		2.5	0.5196	0.0574	1.2990	0.0191	CHP

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA4923		2.8	0.6946	0.0357	1.9450	0.0696	CHP
PA4928		4.6	0.4070	0.0290	1.8720	0.0057	CHP
PA4932	<i>rplI</i>	3.6	0.6097	0.0391	2.1950	0.1016	50S ribosomal protein L9
PA4933		3.7	0.4881	0.0292	1.8060	0.0805	HP
PA4934	<i>rpsR</i>	2.7	0.4496	0.0529	1.2140	0.0795	30S ribosomal protein S18
PA4938	<i>purA</i>	2.4	0.6725	0.0659	1.6140	0.0169	adenylosuccinate synthetase
PA4956	<i>rhdA</i>	2.5	0.4820	0.1358	1.2050	0.0316	thiosulfate sulfurtransferase
PA4957	<i>psd</i>	3.1	0.5316	0.0121	1.6480	0.0108	phosphatidylserine decarboxylase
PA4959		2.8	0.5811	0.0010	1.6270	0.0112	HP
PA4960		5.3	0.2930	0.1586	1.5530	0.0320	Pr. phosphoserine phosphatase
PA4962		2.4	0.6058	0.2001	1.4540	0.0962	CHP
PA4965		3.1	0.4252	0.0735	1.3180	0.1699	HP
PA4966		3.1	0.5923	0.0398	1.8360	0.0132	HP
PA4974		4.2	0.3840	0.2740	1.6130	0.0237	Pr. outer membrane protein precursor
PA4987		2.1	0.5976	0.1896	1.2550	0.3376	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA4990		2.3	0.4965	0.2956	1.1420	0.2927	SMR multidrug efflux transporter
PA4992		4.5	0.3227	0.2967	1.4520	0.1385	HP
PA4997	<i>msbA</i>	3.4	0.3971	0.0888	1.3500	0.0032	transport protein MsbA
PA4998		2.1	0.5538	0.1420	1.1630	0.0517	CHP
PA4999		2.3	0.5930	0.0330	1.3640	0.0353	HP
PA5005		2.6	0.5823	0.0622	1.5140	0.0162	Pr. carbamoyl transferase
PA5009	<i>waaP</i>	3.5	0.4229	0.0173	1.4800	0.0016	lipopolysaccharide kinase WaaP
PA5010	<i>waaG</i>	3.1	0.4481	0.0160	1.3890	0.0481	UDP-glucose:(heptosyl) LPS alpha 1,3-glucosyltransferase WaaG
PA5011	<i>waaC</i>	2.7	0.5830	0.0102	1.5740	0.0132	heptosyltransferase I
PA5012	<i>waaF</i>	6.5	0.3132	0.0140	2.0360	0.0270	heptosyltransferase II
PA5013	<i>ilvE</i>	2.6	0.5604	0.0536	1.4570	0.0235	branched-chain amino acid transferase
PA5019		2.3	0.6996	0.0976	1.6090	0.1089	CHP
PA5024		19.6	0.2462	0.0247	4.8250	0.0157	CHP
PA5034	<i>hemE</i>	2.3	0.6352	0.2984	1.4610	0.1424	uroporphyrinogen decarboxylase
PA5036	<i>gltB</i>	2.3	0.7330	0.2521	1.6860	0.0507	glutamate synthase large chain precursor
PA5046		4.7	0.4330	0.0903	2.0350	0.0085	malic enzyme
PA5047		2.4	0.6850	0.1177	1.6440	0.0533	HP
PA5048		5.2	0.3348	0.0063	1.7410	0.0118	Pr. nuclease
PA5049	<i>rpmE</i>	5.9	0.4632	0.0288	2.7330	0.1625	50S ribosomal protein L31
PA5051	<i>argS</i>	5.4	0.3719	0.0134	2.0080	0.0121	arginyl-tRNA synthetase
PA5052		6.1	0.2648	0.0223	1.6150	0.0295	HP
PA5065	<i>ubiB</i>	3.4	0.4559	0.0559	1.5500	0.0063	ubiquinone biosynthetic protein UbiB
PA5072		2.9	0.5969	0.0132	1.7310	0.0170	Pr. chemotaxis transducer
PA5074		21.1	0.1093	0.3200	2.3070	0.0100	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA5075		7.6	0.2861	0.0469	2.1740	0.0031	Pr. permease of ABC transporter
PA5076		4.0	0.5413	0.0184	2.1650	0.0247	Pr. binding protein component of ABC transporter
PA5077	<i>mdoH</i>	3.1	0.4939	0.0129	1.5310	0.0120	periplasmic glucans biosynthesis protein MdoH
PA5078		3.1	0.5132	0.0795	1.5910	0.0098	CHP
PA5079		2.5	0.5308	0.0950	1.3270	0.0927	CHP
PA5117	<i>typA</i>	8.5	0.2124	0.0094	1.8050	0.0069	regulatory protein TypA
PA5118	<i>thiI</i>	8.9	0.2909	0.0276	2.5890	0.0062	thiazole biosynthesis protein ThiI
PA5128	<i>secB</i>	7.5	0.2824	0.1224	2.1180	0.0085	secretion protein SecB
PA5129	<i>grx</i>	9.2	0.2151	0.0432	1.9790	0.0012	glutaredoxin
PA5130		7.2	0.2685	0.0895	1.9330	0.0124	CHP
PA5132		2.4	0.5654	0.0278	1.3570	0.0346	HP

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA5136		2.3	0.5974	0.0177	1.3740	0.0066	HP
PA5137		2.7	0.4578	0.3360	1.2360	0.4251	HP
PA5139		7.0	0.3216	0.0034	2.2510	0.0223	HP
PA5140	<i>hisF1</i>	4.9	0.3845	0.0382	1.8840	0.0054	imidazoleglycerol-phosphate synthase, cyclase subunit
PA5141	<i>hisA</i>	3.3	0.4836	0.0027	1.5960	0.0080	phosphoribosylformimino-5-aminoimidazole carboxamide
PA5142	<i>hisH1</i>	2.3	0.6148	0.1253	1.4140	0.0326	glutamine amidotransferase
PA5147	<i>mutY</i>	2.5	0.5812	0.0054	1.4530	0.0145	A / G specific adenine glycosylase
PA5148		2.4	0.5350	0.0285	1.2840	0.0896	CHP
PA5149		2.4	0.5175	0.0537	1.2420	0.0737	CHP
PA5156		3.1	0.5248	0.0608	1.6270	0.0708	HP
PA5161	<i>rmlB</i>	2.2	0.5827	0.1350	1.2820	0.1108	dTDP-D-glucose 4,6-dehydratase
PA5162	<i>rmlD</i>	3.1	0.4990	0.0041	1.5470	0.0072	dTDP-4-dehydrorhamnose reductase
PA5163	<i>rmlA</i>	3.4	0.4538	0.0778	1.5430	0.0059	glucose-1-phosphate thymidyltransferase
PA5164	<i>rmlC</i>	2.6	0.5669	0.0809	1.4740	0.0413	dTDP-4-dehydrorhamnose 3,5-epimerase
PA5174		3.0	0.4817	0.1153	1.4450	0.0203	Pr. beta-ketoacyl synthase
PA5192	<i>pckA</i>	9.1	0.2489	0.0124	2.2650	0.0034	phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase
PA5193	<i>yrfI</i>	7.4	0.2589	0.1867	1.9160	0.0073	heat shock protein HSP33
PA5194		8.0	0.2904	0.1920	2.3230	0.0199	HP
PA5201		5.7	0.3311	0.0451	1.8870	0.0055	CHP
PA5202		7.6	0.2080	0.1465	1.5810	0.0390	HP
PA5204	<i>argA</i>	2.2	0.6564	0.2225	1.4440	0.0664	N-acetylglutamate synthase
PA5214	<i>gcvH1</i>	2.1	0.7495	0.0918	1.5740	0.0398	glycine cleavage system protein H1
PA5215	<i>gcvT1</i>	3.3	0.5870	0.0325	1.9370	0.0257	glycine-cleavage system protein T1
PA5222		2.8	0.6354	0.0418	1.7790	0.0295	HP
PA5239	<i>rho</i>	7.8	0.2629	0.0016	2.0510	0.0028	transcription termination factor Rho
PA5250		3.1	0.5245	0.0329	1.6260	0.0860	CHP
PA5251		3.2	0.4666	0.0381	1.4930	0.0237	HP
PA5252		3.5	0.4291	0.1174	1.5020	0.0240	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA5256	<i>dsbH</i>	5.3	0.2851	0.3164	1.5110	0.0821	disulfide bond formation protein
PA5274	<i>rnk</i>	2.9	0.4093	0.1611	1.1870	0.2213	nucleoside diphosphate kinase regulator
PA5278	<i>dapF</i>	2.1	0.7043	0.1219	1.4790	0.0569	diaminopimelate epimerase
PA5284		5.1	0.2765	0.0594	1.4100	0.0147	HP
PA5285		3.4	0.4465	0.0292	1.5180	0.0045	HP
PA5286		6.5	0.3255	0.0114	2.1160	0.0108	CHP
PA5296	<i>rep</i>	3.6	0.5003	0.0050	1.8010	0.0357	ATP-dependent DNA helicase Rep
PA5298		4.6	0.6952	0.0140	3.1980	0.0427	xanthine phosphoribosyltransferase
PA5300	<i>cycB</i>	4.2	0.4867	0.1121	2.0440	0.0179	cytochrome c5
PA5315	<i>rpmG</i>	7.4	0.4000	0.0123	2.9600	0.0640	50S ribosomal protein L33
PA5316	<i>rpmB</i>	5.2	0.3281	0.0038	1.7060	0.0032	50S ribosomal protein L28
PA5320	<i>coaC</i>	3.2	0.5656	0.1076	1.8100	0.0140	Phosphopantothenoylcysteine synthase
PA5321	<i>dut</i>	3.7	0.5719	0.0620	2.1160	0.0249	deoxyuridine 5'-triphosphate nucleotidohydrolase
PA5322	<i>algC</i>	4.2	0.2979	0.0733	1.2510	0.0092	phosphomannomutase AlgC
PA5333		2.1	0.6419	0.1484	1.3480	0.1782	CHP
PA5335		2.2	0.6664	0.1788	1.4660	0.0578	CHP
PA5336	<i>gmk</i>	5.7	0.2951	0.0543	1.6820	0.0036	guanylate kinase
PA5340		2.3	0.6704	0.1995	1.5420	0.0325	HP
PA5349		2.8	0.4325	0.1105	1.2110	0.0883	Pr. rubredoxin reductase
PA5351		4.8	0.5027	0.0142	2.4130	0.0168	rubredoxin
PA5361	<i>phoR</i>	2.5	0.5356	0.1225	1.3390	0.0748	two-component sensor PhoR
PA5365	<i>phoU</i>	2.5	0.6472	0.0880	1.6180	0.0908	phosphate uptake regulatory protein PhoU

Table 2 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

PA5366	<i>pstB</i>	4.2	0.4343	0.0457	1.8240	0.0459	ATP-binding component of ABC phosphate transporter
PA5367	<i>pstA</i>	7.4	0.2746	0.0269	2.0320	0.0188	membrane protein component of ABC phosphate transporter
PA5368	<i>pstC</i>	4.4	0.3764	0.0092	1.6560	0.0286	membrane protein component of ABC phosphate transporter
PA5369		3.2	0.6713	0.0136	2.1480	0.0951	HP
PA5406		3.5	0.5703	0.0402	1.9960	0.0116	HP
PA5407		5.1	0.4914	0.0236	2.5060	0.0338	HP
PA5415	<i>glyA1</i>	11.8	0.1331	0.0519	1.5700	0.0001	serine hydroxymethyltransferase
PA5425	<i>purK</i>	6.7	0.3331	0.0963	2.2320	0.0191	phosphoribosylaminoimidazole carboxylase
PA5426	<i>purE</i>	5.0	0.4310	0.0073	2.1550	0.0074	phosphoribosylaminoimidazole carboxylase, catalytic subunit
PA5430		2.3	0.6257	0.0290	1.4390	0.0254	HP
PA5434	<i>mtr</i>	5.1	0.3537	0.0024	1.8040	0.0056	tryptophan permease
PA5437		2.9	0.5790	0.1974	1.6790	0.0656	Pr. transcriptional regulator
PA5445		7.5	0.2767	0.0319	2.0750	0.0918	Pr. coenzyme A transferase
PA5464		2.9	0.5707	0.0058	1.6550	0.0116	HP
PA5470		3.0	0.4697	0.1281	1.4090	0.0477	Pr. peptide chain release factor
PA5472		5.2	0.3779	0.0134	1.9650	0.0148	HP
PA5478		2.3	0.6809	0.1109	1.5660	0.0734	CHP
PA5479	<i>gltP</i>	19.3	0.1989	0.1328	3.8380	0.0208	proton-glutamate symporter
PA5490	<i>cc4</i>	3.3	0.5270	0.0508	1.7390	0.0079	cytochrome c4 precursor
PA5491		3.3	0.5515	0.0923	1.8200	0.0115	Pr. cytochrome
PA5502		2.7	0.5748	0.1806	1.5520	0.0755	HP
PA5503		6.9	0.3149	0.0045	2.1730	0.0069	Pr. ATP-binding component of ABC transporter
PA5504		7.4	0.3270	0.0006	2.4200	0.0057	Pr. permease of ABC transporter
PA5505		4.9	0.3253	0.0278	1.5940	0.0277	Pr. TonB-dependent receptor
PA5527		3.7	0.4454	0.2895	1.6480	0.0272	HP
PA5553	<i>atpC</i>	4.2	0.3800	0.0179	1.5960	0.0294	ATP synthase epsilon chain
PA5554	<i>atpD</i>	4.7	0.3091	0.0195	1.4530	0.0341	ATP synthase beta chain
PA5555	<i>atpG</i>	5.5	0.2496	0.0173	1.3730	0.0290	ATP synthase gamma chain
PA5556	<i>atpA</i>	6.9	0.2883	0.0132	1.9890	0.0063	ATP synthase alpha chain
PA5557	<i>atpH</i>	8.3	0.2445	0.0071	2.0290	0.0039	ATP synthase delta chain
PA5558	<i>atpF</i>	5.5	0.3509	0.0109	1.9300	0.0142	ATP synthase B chain
PA5559	<i>atpE</i>	5.8	0.3040	0.0122	1.7630	0.0424	atp synthase C chain
PA5560	<i>atpB</i>	8.9	0.2790	0.0666	2.4830	0.0097	ATP synthase A chain
PA5561	<i>atpI</i>	5.7	0.4902	0.0676	2.7940	0.0141	ATP synthase protein I
PA5562	<i>spoOJ</i>	2.6	0.6150	0.2030	1.5990	0.0172	chromosome partitioning protein Spo0J
PA5564	<i>gidB</i>	6.7	0.3551	0.0118	2.3790	0.0073	glucose inhibited division protein B
PA5565	<i>gidA</i>	5.6	0.3061	0.0289	1.7140	0.0054	glucose-inhibited division protein A
PA5567		2.7	0.7056	0.0373	1.9050	0.0319	CHP
PA5568		6.5	0.3425	0.0076	2.2260	0.0284	CHP
PA5569	<i>rnpA</i>	6.7	0.2846	0.0305	1.9070	0.0012	ribonuclease P protein component
PA5570	<i>rpmH</i>	6.5	0.3015	0.0324	1.9600	0.0025	50S ribosomal protein L34

* Mean of normalized gene signals of five replicates with corresponded *t* test *p*-value. HP, hypothetical protein. CHP, conserved hypothetical protein. Pr., probable.

Table 3 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)**Table 3** List of genes whose mRNAs were not detected in 3 or more of 5 arrays of treated and untreated samples

PA0021, PA0030, PA0031, PA0051, PA0058, PA0062, PA0096, PA0104, PA0111, PA0135, PA0136, PA0138, PA0142, PA0154, PA0166, PA0173, PA0184, PA0186, PA0188, PA0190, PA0198, PA0199, PA0204, PA0205, PA0208, PA0211, PA0212, PA0213, PA0214, PA0216, PA0219, PA0220, PA0222, PA0234, PA0240, PA0242, PA0244, PA0273, PA0287, PA0288, PA0321, PA0324, PA0439, PA0440, PA0442, PA0443, PA0444, PA0450, PA0452, PA0465, PA0474, PA0476, PA0480, PA0512, PA0514, PA0515, PA0516, PA0519, PA0520, PA0523, PA0524, PA0525, PA0528, PA0531, PA0539, PA0543, PA0557, PA0573, PA0641, PA0677, PA0678, PA0679, PA0680, PA0681, PA0682, PA0683, PA0684, PA0685, PA0686, PA0687, PA0688, PA0690, PA0691, PA0695, PA0696, PA0697, PA0698, PA0700, PA0701, PA0702, PA0710, PA0711, PA0714, PA0721, PA0725, PA0740, PA0741, PA0748, PA0790, PA0809, PA0811, PA0823, PA0824, PA0829, PA0842, PA0844, PA0845, PA0847, PA0863, PA0878, PA0879, PA0880, PA0881, PA0882, PA0883, PA0884, PA0885, PA0886, PA0939, PA0977, PA0986, PA0987, PA0989, PA0993, PA1019, PA1024, PA1066, PA1107, PA1108, PA1109, PA1143, PA1144, PA1186, PA1196, PA1210, PA1211, PA1215, PA1223, PA1225, PA1231, PA1232, PA1233, PA1236, PA1237, PA1238, PA1239, PA1240, PA1242, PA1254, PA1257, PA1258, PA1259, PA1262, PA1266, PA1267, PA1270, PA1282, PA1284, PA1310, PA1313, PA1314, PA1325, PA1332, PA1334, PA1344, PA1346, PA1356, PA1380, PA1385, PA1406, PA1416, PA1419, PA1426, PA1436, PA1468, PA1491, PA1492, PA1498, PA1499, PA1500, PA1501, PA1502, PA1503, PA1507, PA1519, PA1521, PA1537, PA1565, PA1567, PA1568, PA1569, PA1598, PA1602, PA1628, PA1631, PA1632, PA1633, PA1635, PA1646, PA1740, PA1743, PA1764, PA1778, PA1779, PA1781, PA1783, PA1785, PA1848, PA1849, PA1855, PA1868, PA1875, PA1876, PA1877, PA1883, PA1908, PA1909, PA1914, PA1916, PA1917, PA1919, PA1921, PA1924, PA1927, PA1928, PA1932, PA1952, PA1953, PA1955, PA1972, PA1974, PA1975, PA1976, PA1979, PA1980, PA1981, PA1982, PA1983, PA2004, PA2032, PA2035, PA2036, PA2036, PA2046, PA2055, PA2056, PA2057, PA2060, PA2061, PA2065, PA2070, PA2073, PA2077, PA2078, PA2087, PA2088, PA2091, PA2092, PA2093, PA2096, PA2099, PA2108, PA2119, PA2124, PA2129, PA2131, PA2132, PA2133, PA2136, PA2137, PA2139, PA2140, PA2141, PA2142, PA2143, PA2144, PA2147, PA2148, PA2150, PA2151, PA2153, PA2154, PA2155, PA2156, PA2158, PA2162, PA2163, PA2167, PA2171, PA2178, PA2179, PA2181, PA2183, PA2186, PA2187, PA2190, PA2192, PA2207, PA2208, PA2213, PA2214, PA2215, PA2217, PA2221, PA2224, PA2228, PA2245, PA2254, PA2257, PA2258, PA2268, PA2269, PA2273, PA2275, PA2283, PA2284, PA2293, PA2294, PA2307, PA2308, PA2309, PA2310, PA2314, PA2335, PA2336, PA2339, PA2343, PA2346, PA2347, PA2348, PA2350, PA2355, PA2356, PA2360, PA2374, PA2418, PA2419, PA2420, PA2421, PA2429, PA2430, PA2438, PA2439, PA2458, PA2469, PA2470, PA2471, PA2472, PA2473, PA2474, PA2478, PA2480, PA2493, PA2494, PA2499, PA2500, PA2508, PA2509, PA2511, PA2512, PA2514, PA2515, PA2516, PA2517, PA2518, PA2520, PA2522, PA2546, PA2548, PA2564, PA2566, PA2571, PA2595, PA2596, PA2636, PA2655, PA2664, PA2670, PA2672, PA2673, PA2676, PA2677, PA2680, PA2681, PA2689, PA2699, PA2704, PA2715, PA2716, PA2717, PA2719, PA2745, PA2750, PA2753, PA2762, PA2768, PA2777, PA2782, PA2785, PA2787, PA2789, PA2804, PA2807, PA2808, PA2814, PA2819, PA2833, PA2835, PA2836, PA2837, PA2838, PA2847, PA2861, PA2881, PA2898, PA2916, PA2919, PA2922, PA2924, PA2925, PA2926, PA2927, PA2933, PA2935, PA2940, PA2944, PA3036, PA3060, PA3063, PA3064, PA3066, PA3069, PA3090, PA3125, PA3180, PA3218, PA3219, PA3231, PA3236, PA3249, PA3252, PA3253, PA3272, PA3273, PA3274, PA3279, PA3311, PA3325, PA3337, PA3359, PA3360, PA3374, PA3375, PA3376, PA3379, PA3380, PA3382, PA3383, PA3384, PA3391, PA3392, PA3393, PA3394, PA3395, PA3396, PA3416, PA3422, PA3428, PA3429, PA3431, PA3447, PA3448, PA3449, PA3457, PA3462, PA3467, PA3498, PA3503, PA3504, PA3505, PA3507, PA3512, PA3513, PA3518, PA3521, PA3522, PA3523, PA3540, PA3541, PA3542, PA3543, PA3544, PA3545, PA3548, PA3549, PA3550, PA3586, PA3588, PA3589, PA3590, PA3591, PA3593, PA3595, PA3596, PA3597, PA3598, PA3613, PA3619, PA3630, PA3681, PA3709, PA3718, PA3749, PA3760, PA3771, PA3772, PA3773, PA3775, PA3782, PA3825, PA3839, PA3867, PA3870, PA3871, PA3874, PA3875, PA3877, PA3883, PA3890, PA3891, PA3897, PA3913, PA3914, PA3926, PA3933, PA3939, PA3953, PA3957, PA3964, PA3991, PA3994, PA4008, PA4038, PA4041, PA4071, PA4072, PA4074, PA4083, PA4084, PA4085, PA4087, PA4088, PA4089, PA4092, PA4095, PA4096, PA4099, PA4100, PA4103, PA4105, PA4122, PA4123, PA4127, PA4128, PA4134, PA4137, PA4147, PA4148, PA4149, PA4150, PA4151, PA4152, PA4153, PA4166, PA4167, PA4169, PA4172, PA4177, PA4179, PA4187, PA4189, PA4295, PA4297, PA4302, PA4341, PA4343, PA4346, PA4383, PA4540, PA4549, PA4587, PA4635, PA4651, PA4652, PA4785, PA4788, PA4813, PA4818, PA4823, PA4824, PA4837, PA4882, PA4883, PA4884, PA4891, PA4898, PA4899, PA4901, PA4903, PA4905, PA4908, PA4911, PA4927, PA4981, PA4985, PA4986, PA4995, PA5032, PA5092, PA5093, PA5096, PA5097, PA5098, PA5099, PA5207, PA5238, PA5265, PA5282, PA5294, PA5297, PA5325, PA5326, PA5328, PA5353, PA5354, PA5381, PA5383, PA5384, PA5385, PA5386, PA5388, PA5390, PA5397, PA5398, PA5399, PA5400, PA5401, PA5416, PA5417, PA5418, PA5419, PA5427, PA5469, PA5480, PA5481, PA5534, PA5538, PA5542, PA0013, PA0014, PA0056, PA0098, PA0145, PA0174, PA0338, PA0435, PA0575, PA0585, PA0600, PA0635, PA0693, PA0717, PA0718, PA0719, PA0727, PA0728, PA0803, PA0807, PA0908, PA0910, PA0985, PA1050, PA1113, PA1123, PA1133, PA1169, PA1183, PA1185, PA1204, PA1217, PA1261, PA1268, PA1345, PA1352, PA1353, PA1381, PA1398, PA1427, PA1428, PA1429, PA1510, PA1634, PA1637, PA1671, PA1699, PA1702, PA1704, PA1856, PA1867, PA1879, PA1887, PA1902, PA1907, PA1918, PA1922, PA1923, PA1961, PA1973, PA1990, PA2026, PA2043, PA2051, PA2058, PA2072, PA2125, PA2130, PA2135, PA2160, PA2161, PA2164, PA2165, PA2170, PA2172, PA2184, PA2188, PA2198, PA2205, PA2244, PA2255, PA2280, PA2296, PA2361, PA2362, PA2368, PA2369, PA2370, PA2371, PA2377, PA2392, PA2431, PA2465, PA2475, PA2490, PA2521, PA2531, PA2547, PA2593, PA2662, PA2669, PA2671, PA2674, PA2697, PA2701, PA2708, PA2721, PA2722, PA2763, PA2806, PA2844, PA2865, PA2873, PA2891, PA2913, PA2914, PA2923, PA3018, PA3024, PA3037, PA3061, PA3062, PA3137, PA3176, PA3269, PA3280, PA3291, PA3336, PA3358, PA3378, PA3381, PA3386, PA3389, PA3405, PA3406, PA3407, PA3454, PA3461, PA3464, PA3486, PA3506, PA3546, PA3547, PA3573, PA3592, PA3606, PA3669, PA3733, PA3739, PA3761, PA3789, PA3790, PA3843, PA3909, PA3912, PA3928, PA4018, PA4033, PA4034, PA4062, PA4066, PA4097, PA4098, PA4107, PA4136, PA4144, PA4210, PA4222, PA4225, PA4304, PA4357, PA4365, PA4541, PA4610, PA4772, PA4802, PA4814, PA4822, PA4834, PA4835, PA4858, PA4860, PA4861, PA4862, PA4894, PA4924, PA5033, PA5059, PA5392, PA5514, PA5530, PA5536, PA5539, PA5540, PA5541, PA5566
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Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)**Table 4.** Probe set expression signal data for each array of untreated and H₂O₂-treated samples *

Nr.	Probe Set Name	Array Number for untreated samples				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	AFFX-YEL002C_WPB1_at	1.0	32.4	10.6	13.3	18.1
2	AFFX-YEL018W_at	35.1	150.5	28.7	27.1	42.4
3	AFFX-YEL024W_RIP1_at	159.4	343.7	110.4	108.9	174.0
4	AFFX-YFL039C_ACT1_at	2.6	0.5	2.4	0.1	0.1
5	AFFX-YER148W_SPT15_at	83.5	198.6	53.6	53.8	124.9
6	AFFX-YER022W_SRB4_at	5.9	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.1
7	AFFX-Athal_GAPDH_at	17.4	29.5	8.4	20.3	16.8
8	AFFX-Athal_ubq_at	2.6	2.0	5.5	10.4	0.4
9	AFFX-Athal_actin_at	9.0	0.3	3.7	0.3	0.1
10	AFFX-Bsubtilis_dapB_at	59.7	114.6	49.4	48.8	68.2
11	AFFX-Bsubtilis_lys_at	100.3	232.9	124.5	145.6	168.2
12	AFFX-Bsubtilis_pheB_at	486.3	947.1	503.5	479.9	574.5
13	AFFX-Bsubtilis_thrC_at	194.0	331.0	111.4	116.6	190.2
14	AFFX-Bsubtilis_trpD_at	37.9	88.7	78.6	76.6	93.6
15	Pae_flgK_at	15.3	11.0	4.2	12.5	8.3
16	Pae_flgL_at	2.0	1.4	3.1	2.4	1.5
17	Pae_orfA_vioA_at	5.5	3.3	12.6	16.5	12.5
18	Pae_orfB_at	44.5	8.9	32.5	32.7	18.6
19	Pae_orfC_at	3.6	3.5	8.3	2.8	3.8
20	Pae_orfD_at	9.0	2.5	5.2	4.9	5.0
21	Pae_orfE_at	18.5	1.5	8.0	9.3	4.1
22	Pae_orfF_at	5.8	10.4	41.6	31.6	20.6
23	Pae_orfG_at	4.8	2.4	17.8	5.1	2.8
24	Pae_orfH_at	14.3	0.8	4.1	2.1	3.5
25	Pae_orfI_at	13.0	10.6	23.6	18.6	10.0
26	Pae_orfJ_at	2.8	4.5	25.8	13.5	2.9
27	Pae_orfK_at	0.9	2.4	2.0	14.8	5.1
28	Pae_orfL_at	2.1	7.6	6.7	4.9	0.6
29	Pae_orfM_at	25.3	1.4	23.8	13.7	11.3
30	Pae_orfN_at	29.7	2.0	4.0	5.9	13.8
31	PA0001_dnaA_at	739.8	515.7	446.2	479.4	568.6
32	PA0002_dnaN_at	1509.1	1084.3	1216.2	1316.0	1311.3
33	PA0003_recF_at	613.0	671.1	344.3	353.1	428.9
34	PA0004_gyrB_at	387.9	538.6	555.1	568.0	537.5
35	PA0005_at	251.7	262.5	197.9	228.3	245.5
36	PA0006_at	121.0	119.1	135.4	73.9	124.0
37	PA0007_at	26.5	33.3	23.1	13.5	39.4
38	PA0008_glyS_at	620.5	508.8	536.3	584.2	565.7
39	PA0009_glyQ_at	812.3	689.1	875.8	800.8	724.0
40	PA0010_tag_at	26.8	40.4	58.0	48.4	55.1
41	PA0011_at	109.0	165.5	117.1	154.6	123.5
42	PA0012_at	68.3	155.3	157.6	106.0	100.3
43	PA0013_at	8.4	54.5	15.7	21.0	50.2
44	PA0014_at	13.8	27.1	27.6	19.2	19.7
45	PA0015_at	111.3	160.9	129.8	108.3	122.8
46	PA0016_trkA_at	297.0	262.8	252.1	271.2	321.3
47	PA0017_at	274.8	247.1	417.6	340.9	306.4
48	PA0018_fmt_at	360.7	323.8	387.2	443.1	397.7
49	PA0019_def_at	1079.3	1366.7	606.2	656.1	791.5
50	PA0020_at	450.5	431.4	342.1	357.2	338.1
51	PA0021_at	1.3	15.2	49.8	35.4	32.3
52	PA0022_at	100.5	97.1	105.1	75.2	80.0
53	PA0023_qor_at	111.4	122.9	142.8	107.4	142.6
54	PA0024_hemF_at	271.5	253.3	176.8	243.0	246.3
55	PA0025_aroE_at	88.6	72.9	109.9	96.6	104.6
56	PA0026_at	249.8	240.5	176.4	183.5	221.2
57	PA0027_at	72.3	74.6	72.3	70.0	107.8
58	PA0028_at	66.3	71.3	116.6	115.2	88.6
59	PA0029_at	65.9	29.6	87.2	60.2	63.5
60	PA0030_at	25.1	15.6	46.1	44.4	23.2
61	PA0031_betC_at	40.0	4.6	17.2	9.3	11.1
62	PA0032_at	58.1	55.5	83.5	96.5	84.1
63	PA0033_at	49.6	54.6	139.1	79.6	99.5
64	PA0034_at	78.1	103.3	196.6	154.7	164.1
65	PA0035_trpA_at	192.9	285.5	909.0	877.4	781.8

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

66	PA0036_trpB_at	358.6	438.7	1465.7	1500.2	1364.5
67	PA0037_trpI_at	51.5	32.4	90.3	77.8	33.0
68	PA0038_at	39.5	124.4	93.5	90.9	107.1
69	PA0039_at	551.0	752.5	481.3	560.4	612.4
70	PA0040_s_at	284.5	428.3	179.6	273.8	393.6
71	PA0041_at	61.7	85.8	90.9	70.8	93.6
72	PA0042_at	109.6	184.7	109.6	143.2	168.7
73	PA0043_at	29.8	37.3	43.3	44.8	48.6
74	PA0044_exoT_at	99.8	62.3	71.3	52.8	72.4
75	PA0045_at	687.8	537.8	624.6	574.2	526.6
76	PA0046_at	444.7	522.5	502.7	514.9	680.1
77	PA0047_at	162.9	163.8	197.6	194.4	212.2
78	PA0048_at	262.1	396.1	378.0	385.3	442.4
79	PA0049_at	881.9	928.2	1274.6	1443.1	1231.8
80	PA0050_r_at	70.5	123.4	237.5	177.8	134.8
81	PA0051_at	2.8	20.6	56.3	39.3	38.8
82	PA0052_at	5.6	27.3	24.7	27.4	60.6
83	PA0053_at	64.5	76.7	100.6	90.8	85.2
84	PA0054_at	110.9	92.1	101.7	103.0	110.7
85	PA0055_at	1002.7	839.7	931.5	875.4	727.0
86	PA0056_at	30.4	26.1	52.5	33.2	28.1
87	PA0057_at	62.2	53.8	84.9	59.9	72.6
88	PA0058_at	51.3	49.0	86.0	57.4	67.4
89	PA0059_osmC_at	10.2	37.5	57.0	59.6	50.9
90	PA0060_at	265.1	283.9	194.4	212.1	251.2
91	PA0061_at	3.0	26.6	35.8	15.6	25.8
92	PA0062_at	33.7	24.0	33.7	19.0	33.1
93	PA0063_at	95.0	100.4	68.5	54.8	63.4
94	PA0064_at	135.7	151.5	107.4	105.5	139.6
95	PA0065_at	301.7	368.8	209.1	262.9	272.6
96	PA0066_at	253.3	259.8	250.3	256.4	299.5
97	PA0067_prLC_at	650.6	603.9	758.4	681.2	631.1
98	PA0068_at	725.6	716.0	535.7	570.6	494.7
99	PA0069_at	23.8	22.9	50.2	28.3	35.2
100	PA0070_at	1694.0	1405.1	2400.2	2418.9	1783.6
101	PA0071_at	97.6	75.0	133.5	124.5	134.1
102	PA0072_at	38.1	48.7	77.2	57.8	55.9
103	PA0073_at	159.9	130.3	375.0	271.5	238.2
104	PA0074_ppkA_at	207.0	189.9	99.3	121.6	149.1
105	PA0075_at	432.9	347.6	229.8	314.5	309.8
106	PA0076_at	150.3	135.7	200.4	197.6	137.0
107	PA0077_at	363.6	226.5	272.9	234.8	201.6
108	PA0078_at	332.5	221.6	299.1	308.9	223.1
109	PA0079_at	446.5	354.7	325.1	311.4	293.9
110	PA0080_at	198.4	138.4	172.5	143.6	134.8
111	PA0081_at	442.8	366.1	333.1	466.3	363.1
112	PA0082_at	197.1	222.1	256.9	256.2	243.6
113	PA0083_at	1675.5	1436.5	1010.7	1222.5	1001.7
114	PA0084_at	1150.0	854.7	809.0	832.0	737.8
115	PA0085_at	984.6	873.2	796.3	765.7	766.8
116	PA0086_at	557.4	386.7	432.8	399.2	305.9
117	PA0087_at	282.2	204.3	214.2	257.2	173.3
118	PA0088_at	227.1	201.8	213.0	221.0	185.5
119	PA0089_at	199.3	150.8	156.9	151.4	159.3
120	PA0090_at	239.6	386.7	301.7	327.4	252.8
121	PA0091_at	75.8	150.0	135.8	120.2	121.4
122	PA0092_at	171.2	184.1	169.8	186.7	159.0
123	PA0093_at	238.1	187.4	260.2	192.8	203.1
124	PA0094_at	301.9	352.5	150.9	228.1	281.4
125	PA0095_at	130.5	168.5	122.0	140.6	127.7
126	PA0096_at	63.2	46.9	70.1	51.2	65.7
127	PA0097_at	54.7	42.6	46.0	48.6	59.7
128	PA0098_at	83.1	53.8	104.8	53.3	61.9
129	PA0099_at	82.3	66.2	28.4	72.2	45.6
130	PA0100_at	83.5	165.5	137.1	97.8	138.2
131	PA0101_at	119.3	139.3	123.4	124.4	135.3
132	PA0102_at	516.7	532.9	286.1	344.1	363.9
133	PA0103_at	101.9	93.9	132.5	136.8	139.7
134	PA0104_at	30.8	41.3	68.3	36.8	61.9
135	PA0105_coxB_at	3.6	12.7	53.5	33.9	29.3
136	PA0106_coxA_at	1.6	6.7	26.4	14.0	30.1
137	PA0107_at	19.2	14.3	27.8	23.3	29.4
138	PA0108_coIII_at	38.2	24.4	38.6	16.7	44.8

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

139	PA0109_at	3.6	14.6	33.0	3.9	29.6
140	PA0110_at	23.5	32.6	58.4	59.9	82.8
141	PA0111_at	41.1	11.2	10.4	3.3	32.0
142	PA0112_at	40.4	22.3	71.2	41.7	60.1
143	PA0113_at	17.0	38.3	97.7	62.2	71.4
144	PA0114_at	144.7	234.1	211.7	180.5	205.1
145	PA0115_at	102.1	97.8	144.3	98.7	108.7
146	PA0116_at	84.7	62.2	100.6	113.2	83.7
147	PA0117_at	100.5	120.2	52.9	54.4	103.7
148	PA0118_at	46.2	39.9	38.0	61.5	45.7
149	PA0119_at	42.1	38.4	50.6	33.8	36.5
150	PA0120_at	63.8	73.1	40.6	62.3	74.5
151	PA0121_at	74.6	60.3	83.4	65.9	93.3
152	PA0122_at	137.1	480.1	258.3	279.0	258.8
153	PA0123_at	83.8	87.0	108.1	92.1	90.1
154	PA0124_at	189.8	158.6	192.3	190.9	174.6
155	PA0125_at	171.3	177.2	128.1	123.2	113.1
156	PA0126_at	478.0	544.1	298.8	357.9	404.0
157	PA0127_at	42.7	48.8	69.8	61.8	63.8
158	PA0128_at	101.5	118.6	135.4	127.6	68.7
159	PA0129_gabP_at	59.2	84.4	129.2	77.7	64.3
160	PA0130_at	126.6	162.4	134.9	139.2	105.0
161	PA0131_at	55.7	252.1	24.1	47.9	71.4
162	PA0132_at	185.4	440.6	110.1	98.0	116.7
163	PA0133_at	74.1	61.2	89.5	66.5	83.3
164	PA0134_at	43.5	38.9	87.3	53.3	57.2
165	PA0135_at	1.0	13.2	25.6	24.3	27.0
166	PA0136_at	5.9	3.4	37.1	8.6	26.6
167	PA0137_at	3.9	20.4	65.0	34.3	31.0
168	PA0138_at	11.0	7.0	30.6	9.7	38.3
169	PA0139_ahpC_at	4014.5	3154.2	3375.6	3991.2	3184.9
170	PA0140_ahpF_at	340.5	384.3	394.8	464.4	418.4
171	PA0141_at	24.5	66.0	59.3	45.1	72.6
172	PA0142_at	39.4	43.6	46.1	65.1	51.1
173	PA0143_at	489.8	571.1	223.0	375.2	403.8
174	PA0144_at	54.1	83.0	122.9	75.3	96.3
175	PA0145_i_at	3.5	13.1	12.9	15.1	23.1
176	PA0146_at	54.8	36.5	44.4	41.0	54.4
177	PA0147_at	63.1	51.7	97.1	86.1	72.1
178	PA0148_at	108.8	138.0	162.8	147.7	165.8
179	PA0149_at	32.5	19.7	123.3	46.2	48.5
180	PA0150_at	81.4	44.5	137.7	89.6	94.2
181	PA0151_at	30.0	39.8	52.1	47.1	55.9
182	PA0152_pcaQ_at	58.3	46.2	81.3	69.9	76.3
183	PA0153_pcaH_at	67.1	53.1	56.2	73.9	101.1
184	PA0154_pcaG_at	124.5	76.9	77.1	43.5	70.6
185	PA0155_pcaR_at	138.2	140.3	135.5	210.9	139.4
186	PA0156_at	271.8	238.3	233.0	267.6	325.4
187	PA0157_at	196.0	301.4	347.5	260.7	253.5
188	PA0158_at	153.0	197.8	219.9	200.1	212.3
189	PA0159_at	227.2	221.1	178.4	234.7	245.0
190	PA0160_at	163.0	277.1	155.9	187.7	201.9
191	PA0161_at	47.6	51.6	35.3	49.4	32.4
192	PA0162_at	185.4	200.6	170.0	168.4	194.7
193	PA0163_at	5.8	19.5	89.9	34.2	36.9
194	PA0164_at	29.2	33.0	97.0	50.0	58.2
195	PA0165_at	897.7	957.4	926.9	1016.8	1024.6
196	PA0166_at	3.2	4.9	39.9	4.4	23.8
197	PA0167_at	262.2	296.3	139.3	172.0	211.2
198	PA0168_at	76.5	135.9	149.9	148.3	159.6
199	PA0169_at	345.9	419.3	248.0	309.5	297.4
200	PA0170_at	433.8	555.9	402.5	401.4	497.7
201	PA0171_at	767.1	471.3	1218.3	829.8	769.4
202	PA0172_at	328.8	303.5	304.2	316.6	310.8
203	PA0173_at	5.5	15.8	4.8	3.7	36.9
204	PA0174_at	14.0	41.5	42.0	45.2	55.0
205	PA0175_at	36.4	48.1	73.1	54.7	52.6
206	PA0176_at	91.8	112.9	137.8	129.8	94.7
207	PA0177_at	27.0	30.7	43.3	26.7	21.6
208	PA0178_at	43.2	62.1	69.4	29.8	54.8
209	PA0179_at	150.5	174.8	139.4	157.8	149.9
210	PA0180_at	110.5	120.4	130.4	133.6	112.1
211	PA0181_at	83.6	88.1	62.7	79.6	86.2

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

212	PA0182_at	19.2	37.2	45.6	41.1	46.8
213	PA0183_atsA_at	37.1	37.1	105.4	60.3	70.1
214	PA0184_at	7.0	7.5	8.6	5.8	14.0
215	PA0185_at	36.9	25.8	61.0	53.9	53.1
216	PA0186_at	21.0	24.2	48.5	17.8	32.2
217	PA0187_at	36.4	25.8	75.0	41.8	49.4
218	PA0188_at	25.2	17.2	23.8	38.6	54.6
219	PA0189_at	66.0	22.8	50.1	17.6	34.6
220	PA0190_at	4.7	11.7	47.7	19.0	21.0
221	PA0191_at	3.5	56.6	51.2	45.0	48.6
222	PA0192_at	49.8	61.9	67.4	71.4	77.8
223	PA0193_at	39.8	54.1	27.4	60.4	50.9
224	PA0194_at	47.3	47.1	56.4	40.3	65.2
225	PA0195_pntA_at	69.7	253.4	318.9	296.1	282.8
226	PA0196_pntB_at	35.9	94.9	106.6	89.8	88.4
227	PA0197_at	20.4	61.9	44.4	85.8	87.2
228	PA0198_exbB1_at	20.3	13.2	53.3	42.6	37.5
229	PA0199_exbD1_at	14.4	55.4	107.5	50.4	89.6
230	PA0200_i_at	9.5	8.7	20.9	30.9	29.9
231	PA0201_at	45.5	336.5	173.3	183.7	237.2
232	PA0202_at	48.4	34.9	58.2	41.7	38.9
233	PA0203_at	30.2	23.4	60.5	30.4	50.4
234	PA0204_at	8.9	2.9	32.3	8.2	29.6
235	PA0205_at	11.3	32.0	72.8	48.5	59.8
236	PA0206_at	24.1	34.1	74.5	75.3	67.9
237	PA0207_at	63.3	64.3	170.1	76.2	87.6
238	PA0208_mdcA_at	48.2	46.4	48.1	67.3	42.1
239	PA0209_at	24.4	23.0	57.9	27.5	48.2
240	PA0210_mdcC_at	16.9	13.3	27.2	22.0	35.1
241	PA0211_mdcD_at	37.2	9.2	52.9	41.7	44.5
242	PA0212_mdcE_at	7.8	15.3	59.9	10.8	31.5
243	PA0213_at	5.0	2.5	23.6	16.9	27.9
244	PA0214_at	19.6	17.6	31.6	9.8	21.4
245	PA0215_at	30.5	33.1	36.3	33.7	35.4
246	PA0216_at	1.6	3.5	31.3	36.2	34.3
247	PA0217_at	57.7	40.5	46.8	50.8	47.0
248	PA0218_at	35.9	47.6	80.9	58.0	72.5
249	PA0219_at	12.6	26.8	44.8	56.3	51.2
250	PA0220_at	24.8	22.2	60.8	37.5	45.7
251	PA0221_at	7.7	32.6	60.3	28.8	42.5
252	PA0222_at	8.1	1.6	4.4	3.8	2.7
253	PA0223_at	55.6	40.4	80.2	65.5	51.6
254	PA0224_at	70.9	68.3	60.2	62.8	75.0
255	PA0225_at	114.1	171.9	230.2	159.5	144.9
256	PA0226_at	65.0	55.8	52.6	11.4	47.2
257	PA0227_at	58.1	49.5	78.0	48.6	70.6
258	PA0228_pcaF_at	29.1	17.2	20.4	24.4	19.0
259	PA0229_pcaT_at	12.8	15.3	16.9	5.4	13.2
260	PA0230_pcaB_at	100.4	52.9	86.5	73.6	103.5
261	PA0231_pcaD_at	98.9	127.2	88.2	93.3	88.7
262	PA0232_pcaC_at	52.6	59.3	56.9	53.0	63.5
263	PA0233_at	59.4	47.8	53.8	47.5	46.3
264	PA0234_at	15.7	17.2	29.3	21.1	34.6
265	PA0235_pcaK_at	50.7	46.4	130.0	65.3	59.3
266	PA0236_at	153.8	112.9	135.8	132.5	174.2
267	PA0237_at	36.6	36.1	60.3	40.3	67.5
268	PA0238_at	40.7	19.7	66.6	56.4	52.9
269	PA0239_at	5.1	14.9	85.3	36.1	67.9
270	PA0240_at	13.9	14.9	34.9	32.3	23.0
271	PA0241_at	38.2	24.2	74.3	39.1	58.6
272	PA0242_at	43.6	29.2	58.0	41.8	58.2
273	PA0243_at	102.8	167.5	31.1	66.6	58.9
274	PA0244_at	28.0	27.5	61.9	31.5	47.3
275	PA0245_aroQ2_at	30.1	57.4	37.9	32.8	47.2
276	PA0246_at	58.8	51.7	66.6	46.1	59.4
277	PA0247_pobA_at	26.6	20.2	47.7	27.2	36.6
278	PA0248_at	61.1	53.0	66.8	45.0	53.6
279	PA0249_at	52.0	53.1	119.8	92.9	67.5
280	PA0250_at	57.2	97.9	65.2	44.9	62.0
281	PA0251_at	6.4	4.3	29.6	7.3	30.6
282	PA0252_at	49.3	48.8	49.4	70.8	44.9
283	PA0253_at	101.0	85.7	110.6	151.5	107.0
284	PA0254_at	69.8	81.9	104.1	65.1	82.9

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

285	PA0255_at	81.7	90.6	157.8	148.3	121.1
286	PA0256_at	2.5	26.1	28.0	15.2	33.5
287	PA0257_at	47.2	56.1	19.7	33.9	32.8
288	PA0258_at	48.2	89.7	47.1	40.0	47.6
289	PA0259_at	109.8	139.3	123.7	133.2	124.2
290	PA0260_at	103.4	112.8	180.0	126.8	147.9
291	PA0261_at	78.5	70.3	115.6	90.3	112.9
292	PA0262_at	65.8	55.7	23.5	29.9	53.7
293	PA0263_hcpC_s_at	87.1	175.2	58.7	68.8	89.2
294	PA0264_at	62.8	96.5	57.5	47.7	53.3
295	PA0265_gabD_at	2599.6	2007.3	1439.9	1505.3	1366.8
296	PA0266_gabT_at	3462.7	2828.0	2179.5	2135.7	1933.3
297	PA0267_at	87.6	101.9	126.0	134.0	136.4
298	PA0268_at	51.9	33.9	71.2	31.6	60.7
299	PA0269_at	103.8	110.5	62.4	99.6	111.8
300	PA0270_at	119.6	118.2	124.9	157.8	161.4
301	PA0271_at	49.3	67.0	63.3	58.7	91.0
302	PA0272_at	33.8	68.2	40.3	44.4	69.7
303	PA0273_at	7.8	5.9	42.4	30.0	28.5
304	PA0274_at	12.2	23.3	46.7	45.4	41.3
305	PA0275_at	64.1	65.5	65.9	70.4	82.8
306	PA0276_at	1.8	17.9	8.4	35.7	35.9
307	PA0277_at	487.3	462.9	448.4	464.9	467.6
308	PA0278_at	21.6	14.4	31.1	29.4	38.6
309	PA0279_at	29.7	34.4	80.0	64.9	68.3
310	PA0280_cysA_at	112.0	484.6	442.7	450.4	402.8
311	PA0281_cysW_at	182.1	785.3	625.9	666.9	651.8
312	PA0282_cysT_at	300.9	681.5	475.0	728.1	718.3
313	PA0283_sbp_at	583.2	1787.3	881.8	1221.2	1193.2
314	PA0284_at	772.2	2787.7	1729.2	2255.1	2005.7
315	PA0285_at	139.7	265.7	255.7	233.7	224.4
316	PA0286_at	486.9	426.8	391.8	456.1	478.1
317	PA0287_at	4.0	9.2	10.6	24.3	22.3
318	PA0288_speB1_at	4.6	19.1	22.2	36.1	35.4
319	PA0289_at	37.7	52.1	70.6	59.3	83.3
320	PA0290_at	65.8	21.9	50.0	43.7	43.8
321	PA0291_oprE_at	866.1	1107.4	1047.2	1180.9	1139.3
322	PA0292_at	1138.1	1331.3	1469.5	1300.6	1211.7
323	PA0293_at	688.4	965.7	785.7	723.2	814.7
324	PA0294_at	105.9	113.9	88.7	140.8	135.8
325	PA0295_at	90.0	64.1	82.5	73.1	65.4
326	PA0296_s_at	2798.6	2020.9	1082.1	1050.8	1147.8
327	PA0297_at	403.7	344.5	89.0	109.3	113.2
328	PA0298_at	904.0	755.9	149.0	251.2	287.5
329	PA0299_at	1620.6	1684.3	1170.4	1231.2	1123.8
330	PA0300_potF2_at	1169.6	1456.9	1103.4	1100.3	1146.5
331	PA0301_potF3_at	348.1	506.4	318.2	279.1	329.0
332	PA0302_potG_at	563.0	679.2	271.2	388.0	414.1
333	PA0303_potH_at	505.8	755.2	474.8	494.7	579.0
334	PA0304_potI_at	98.5	225.0	118.5	122.8	105.3
335	PA0305_at	72.7	81.5	70.3	82.9	87.6
336	PA0306_at	45.7	56.0	69.3	47.4	57.3
337	PA0307_at	81.1	76.6	91.4	45.6	49.6
338	PA0308_at	134.7	144.8	200.0	166.0	204.2
339	PA0309_at	222.7	218.4	183.9	216.9	181.8
340	PA0310_at	253.5	211.6	238.8	229.3	163.3
341	PA0311_at	81.5	39.0	48.1	29.7	59.0
342	PA0312_at	142.2	93.3	235.8	192.8	158.0
343	PA0313_at	93.4	128.9	143.1	143.1	126.4
344	PA0314_at	169.4	213.7	215.5	212.8	228.8
345	PA0315_at	231.0	315.0	225.0	323.5	293.9
346	PA0316_serA_at	762.3	706.7	684.4	758.0	660.3
347	PA0317_at	759.2	574.5	567.8	538.8	609.6
348	PA0318_at	285.9	267.2	297.6	271.1	348.8
349	PA0319_at	307.0	398.6	313.5	324.1	342.5
350	PA0320_at	159.1	185.8	81.1	87.5	91.3
351	PA0321_at	32.1	20.9	6.5	24.9	30.0
352	PA0322_at	6.9	27.8	13.0	2.5	33.6
353	PA0323_at	2.3	7.2	4.2	12.0	16.3
354	PA0324_at	2.5	7.5	10.9	24.8	30.5
355	PA0325_at	40.6	29.0	80.8	45.0	55.1
356	PA0326_at	91.1	64.7	77.4	74.3	67.1
357	PA0327_at	48.7	45.4	9.6	19.4	24.8

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

358	PA0328_at	365.3	159.7	198.9	191.6	232.1
359	PA0329_at	325.5	341.2	305.5	297.8	324.7
360	PA0330_rpiA_at	629.4	614.8	510.5	584.3	618.3
361	PA0331_ilvA1_at	413.9	369.0	284.3	369.7	367.7
362	PA0332_at	141.3	147.7	154.8	165.9	215.4
363	PA0333_at	90.5	79.6	143.6	96.9	101.9
364	PA0334_at	123.5	75.5	111.1	107.2	105.5
365	PA0335_at	406.1	332.1	280.6	310.7	232.8
366	PA0336_at	887.7	935.1	1178.0	1095.8	1021.9
367	PA0337_ptsP_at	572.1	516.1	589.9	473.1	354.4
368	PA0338_at	78.9	86.8	50.6	49.2	64.0
369	PA0339_at	31.1	24.4	72.0	51.6	45.1
370	PA0340_at	173.9	149.7	213.5	169.0	164.5
371	PA0341_lgt_at	160.3	195.5	128.4	119.5	159.5
372	PA0342_thyA_at	709.2	505.6	602.0	641.2	633.7
373	PA0343_at	50.7	42.3	35.1	35.6	48.5
374	PA0344_at	93.7	86.1	139.7	87.1	108.6
375	PA0345_at	58.4	51.7	144.6	133.2	119.3
376	PA0346_at	34.4	65.7	67.1	64.7	70.7
377	PA0347_glpQ_at	43.1	24.4	86.4	54.5	65.8
378	PA0348_at	76.1	28.5	76.7	52.0	33.9
379	PA0349_at	11.7	10.3	57.3	28.1	23.1
380	PA0350_folA_at	152.7	102.2	108.3	154.9	163.5
381	PA0351_at	140.8	175.8	130.3	153.2	165.1
382	PA0352_at	253.3	269.2	127.8	226.0	194.4
383	PA0353_ilvD_at	171.3	256.0	228.3	251.7	221.3
384	PA0354_at	399.0	296.4	582.4	430.9	408.1
385	PA0355_pfpI_at	33.6	23.1	70.5	60.7	49.5
386	PA0356_at	224.6	152.7	127.2	149.4	162.6
387	PA0357_mutM_at	173.8	157.1	48.2	98.8	119.0
388	PA0358_at	256.4	348.6	347.6	347.4	388.7
389	PA0359_at	293.3	289.7	176.7	195.6	254.1
390	PA0360_at	102.3	96.8	85.3	89.0	100.5
391	PA0361_at	107.7	105.4	89.4	79.9	84.9
392	PA0362_fdx1_at	460.7	580.2	527.7	604.5	594.7
393	PA0363_coaD_at	297.7	428.2	373.8	330.5	380.7
394	PA0364_at	23.4	57.1	61.6	67.5	52.1
395	PA0365_at	160.5	157.9	184.7	138.2	177.1
396	PA0366_at	87.9	78.0	82.0	101.8	92.0
397	PA0367_at	88.3	76.3	96.8	85.4	81.8
398	PA0368_at	107.6	71.2	185.3	141.3	109.6
399	PA0369_at	278.0	283.0	129.1	167.5	180.9
400	PA0370_at	542.1	480.8	653.1	635.9	542.9
401	PA0371_at	799.4	462.3	245.8	365.6	445.0
402	PA0372_at	785.3	838.3	404.3	638.8	601.8
403	PA0373_ftsY_at	670.0	555.7	621.9	525.4	540.0
404	PA0374_ftsE_at	880.0	870.0	570.6	491.9	677.1
405	PA0375_ftsX_at	606.0	584.2	1058.5	968.7	862.8
406	PA0376_rpoH_at	1306.0	1348.8	1404.7	1456.1	1377.8
407	PA0377_at	174.7	212.4	186.6	184.3	173.7
408	PA0378_at	52.0	66.2	89.6	95.7	77.9
409	PA0379_at	70.5	118.6	244.3	167.8	198.1
410	PA0380_i_at	356.9	563.0	602.8	722.1	640.2
411	PA0381_thiG_at	705.6	770.0	426.6	542.1	595.6
412	PA0382_micA_at	416.7	359.7	456.9	446.9	441.4
413	PA0383_at	25.5	34.2	74.6	43.6	40.2
414	PA0384_at	77.0	93.9	67.8	69.9	71.1
415	PA0385_at	133.5	115.4	75.5	90.5	100.9
416	PA0386_at	273.1	258.4	296.6	263.5	228.4
417	PA0387_at	771.7	588.5	700.9	616.7	591.7
418	PA0388_at	469.0	554.1	346.3	401.0	442.0
419	PA0389_at	440.3	503.9	265.9	300.2	282.6
420	PA0390_metX_at	562.2	611.6	375.6	456.5	457.7
421	PA0391_at	148.8	99.3	125.9	130.8	159.3
422	PA0392_at	602.7	590.7	437.9	536.2	469.3
423	PA0393_proC_at	644.2	480.0	599.0	568.7	512.7
424	PA0394_at	762.3	765.2	1222.7	885.9	767.9
425	PA0395_pilT_at	330.9	348.1	367.4	321.6	319.2
426	PA0396_pilU_at	150.8	143.0	221.5	284.5	276.4
427	PA0397_at	19.5	19.1	30.2	64.2	49.1
428	PA0398_at	100.7	145.6	94.9	70.5	139.7
429	PA0399_at	782.3	888.2	586.1	635.8	651.2
430	PA0400_at	711.1	772.2	923.5	671.7	748.8

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

431	PA0401_at	296.6	350.5	175.9	209.5	232.0
432	PA0402_pyrB_at	582.6	696.0	701.9	726.8	764.9
433	PA0403_pyrR_at	231.7	271.8	274.8	229.5	246.9
434	PA0404_i_at	647.1	610.9	920.1	751.9	597.1
435	PA0405_at	753.2	584.8	377.6	435.5	529.8
436	PA0406_at	521.0	515.0	453.6	468.3	420.8
437	PA0407_gshB_at	220.6	291.9	289.0	207.3	298.3
438	PA0408_pilG_at	717.9	958.5	370.4	596.5	648.5
439	PA0409_pilH_at	1201.7	1181.6	1760.2	1442.0	1446.0
440	PA0410_pilI_at	231.0	279.2	256.4	318.8	290.6
441	PA0411_pilJ_at	554.1	540.7	454.0	559.1	583.9
442	PA0412_pilK_at	156.3	133.2	241.8	206.3	230.5
443	PA0413_at	310.8	385.6	577.6	507.0	504.5
444	PA0414_at	179.3	221.6	161.7	153.0	199.5
445	PA0415_at	224.0	190.8	311.3	279.1	238.0
446	PA0416_at	67.0	68.1	50.7	59.4	98.8
447	PA0417_at	43.8	56.9	99.5	47.6	94.0
448	PA0418_at	90.6	58.9	80.2	48.2	69.3
449	PA0419_at	214.8	226.0	295.0	249.7	268.3
450	PA0420_bioA_at	422.4	368.5	273.5	392.6	305.3
451	PA0421_at	583.5	465.0	423.5	438.4	525.5
452	PA0422_at	297.2	246.3	227.1	349.8	347.3
453	PA0423_at	172.4	338.3	130.8	125.2	117.7
454	PA0424_mexR_at	73.1	174.0	166.5	159.5	198.3
455	PA0425_mexA_at	1257.0	1183.0	1816.1	1581.5	1385.9
456	PA0426_mexB_at	995.2	884.0	1196.1	1238.2	1217.2
457	PA0427_oprM_at	1216.0	1119.0	1017.4	1067.1	885.6
458	PA0428_at	444.7	562.6	775.4	816.1	780.5
459	PA0429_at	384.0	424.2	367.2	362.3	375.0
460	PA0430_metF_at	410.0	430.7	358.0	381.7	419.2
461	PA0431_at	787.0	815.5	962.6	788.7	820.9
462	PA0432_sahH_at	1277.2	1277.2	1726.3	2105.3	1492.7
463	PA0433_at	26.2	49.5	154.3	124.5	115.5
464	PA0434_at	74.3	49.7	85.0	74.3	57.0
465	PA0435_at	5.6	10.8	42.7	20.4	29.4
466	PA0436_at	219.8	285.7	236.4	285.1	229.1
467	PA0437_codA_at	431.2	404.0	357.8	486.3	402.2
468	PA0438_codB_at	159.8	143.6	267.0	207.0	194.7
469	PA0439_at	6.4	7.0	4.4	5.8	22.2
470	PA0440_at	4.0	3.3	14.4	20.4	4.7
471	PA0441_at	37.3	14.6	60.8	8.9	34.0
472	PA0442_r_at	0.3	0.0	1.2	0.0	0.1
473	PA0443_at	10.9	15.3	18.6	2.8	37.1
474	PA0444_at	29.5	22.7	39.6	45.1	37.4
475	PA0445_s_at	153.3	268.8	139.4	140.7	174.4
476	PA0446_at	2004.6	2199.7	860.7	1207.5	1202.0
477	PA0447_gcdH_at	4685.9	3189.4	2968.6	3522.8	2925.9
478	PA0448_at	69.5	77.7	71.3	60.3	73.3
479	PA0449_at	350.6	448.8	196.9	252.3	305.5
480	PA0450_at	7.8	12.8	26.4	34.1	29.9
481	PA0451_at	21.3	32.9	55.3	39.4	28.9
482	PA0452_at	2.6	11.7	7.6	23.3	22.8
483	PA0453_at	41.1	34.2	29.7	15.3	43.1
484	PA0454_at	103.7	92.8	117.1	98.5	115.4
485	PA0455_dbpA_at	187.8	162.1	155.0	225.6	201.0
486	PA0456_at	2047.2	1981.6	1851.8	1953.2	2210.3
487	PA0457_at	196.8	158.7	186.0	160.5	152.5
488	PA0458_at	75.3	85.1	110.6	106.7	91.0
489	PA0459_at	29.7	29.8	68.3	50.5	53.2
490	PA0460_at	87.4	85.9	132.0	84.5	98.6
491	PA0461_at	233.9	306.3	191.0	241.1	212.2
492	PA0462_at	79.2	68.0	142.3	161.1	124.7
493	PA0463_creB_at	131.1	141.4	108.6	128.1	137.0
494	PA0464_creC_at	143.6	149.7	271.8	168.3	168.6
495	PA0465_creD_at	22.4	14.4	49.1	5.1	30.3
496	PA0466_at	21.0	22.5	37.8	19.3	45.7
497	PA0467_at	266.1	306.0	230.5	297.5	325.6
498	PA0468_at	84.1	105.3	119.7	119.6	118.2
499	PA0469_at	130.4	118.1	159.2	165.2	176.8
500	PA0470_at	33.0	21.8	63.6	45.6	62.8
501	PA0471_at	8.0	22.8	94.5	92.5	77.1
502	PA0472_at	2.9	19.9	87.1	75.0	64.1
503	PA0473_at	66.9	107.7	105.4	96.6	102.9

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

504	PA0474_at	5.4	2.4	5.6	4.0	9.3
505	PA0475_at	41.9	23.4	56.2	36.2	45.9
506	PA0476_at	2.8	19.5	12.8	5.0	16.5
507	PA0477_at	30.0	37.4	32.9	49.3	54.3
508	PA0478_at	22.5	39.5	65.4	64.2	47.2
509	PA0479_at	31.2	27.6	22.5	3.7	46.9
510	PA0480_at	2.1	2.2	7.7	2.7	17.4
511	PA0481_at	103.8	84.9	110.5	110.0	101.2
512	PA0482_glcB_at	659.9	566.5	643.1	590.3	681.9
513	PA0483_at	5.1	24.0	31.3	47.0	32.9
514	PA0484_at	19.3	36.2	86.5	50.9	59.5
515	PA0485_at	194.7	193.8	139.1	118.0	153.7
516	PA0486_at	139.0	113.7	170.4	141.5	124.8
517	PA0487_at	57.6	135.3	68.3	102.6	94.9
518	PA0488_at	54.7	49.2	85.9	51.2	81.5
519	PA0489_at	18.6	8.1	28.3	7.8	31.4
520	PA0490_at	32.4	65.3	53.7	37.6	47.2
521	PA0491_at	45.9	43.5	42.3	71.4	53.8
522	PA0492_at	122.1	141.4	106.2	110.1	148.8
523	PA0493_at	88.8	149.6	125.3	99.7	149.3
524	PA0494_at	119.4	143.1	181.1	213.5	257.2
525	PA0495_at	212.3	190.5	385.0	322.0	400.9
526	PA0496_at	58.8	69.5	118.0	168.9	127.6
527	PA0497_at	15.6	17.1	24.2	21.1	33.4
528	PA0498_at	0.8	14.7	6.4	2.2	13.5
529	PA0499_at	12.6	16.8	82.4	15.5	27.0
530	PA0500_bioB_at	1589.5	1891.1	657.2	927.6	1000.3
531	PA0501_bioF_at	611.0	489.2	457.8	519.2	428.4
532	PA0502_at	401.4	341.9	452.3	429.4	377.6
533	PA0503_at	266.5	220.9	273.1	264.6	256.6
534	PA0504_bioD_at	194.4	194.1	148.6	203.3	171.7
535	PA0505_at	296.4	309.9	179.5	188.5	205.1
536	PA0506_at	276.8	334.6	200.1	228.0	237.1
537	PA0507_at	51.1	39.8	47.5	50.4	55.9
538	PA0508_at	48.6	50.9	63.9	72.2	71.2
539	PA0509_nirN_at	30.3	28.3	66.0	51.6	63.9
540	PA0510_at	9.8	8.6	28.5	30.5	18.5
541	PA0511_nirJ_at	24.4	25.5	51.9	34.2	37.0
542	PA0512_at	1.5	6.4	10.7	14.2	19.3
543	PA0513_at	28.7	4.5	58.3	26.0	23.4
544	PA0514_nirL_at	3.3	4.9	8.9	6.5	16.7
545	PA0515_at	18.3	26.6	42.4	21.7	38.8
546	PA0516_nirF_at	42.9	31.0	16.1	25.2	27.2
547	PA0517_nirC_at	11.1	10.6	35.4	9.4	30.5
548	PA0518_nirM_at	26.8	42.2	49.7	57.4	57.2
549	PA0519_nirS_at	28.0	26.9	42.0	39.8	48.1
550	PA0520_nirQ_at	43.3	47.2	48.9	30.7	45.9
551	PA0521_at	38.7	11.8	30.7	25.1	29.0
552	PA0522_r_at	225.9	164.4	491.0	362.3	302.3
553	PA0523_norC_at	23.1	13.8	21.3	36.8	26.7
554	PA0524_norB_at	1.1	3.1	17.5	3.7	5.4
555	PA0525_at	6.7	11.6	43.8	19.9	25.9
556	PA0526_at	15.4	9.3	52.0	32.1	15.2
557	PA0527_dnr_at	24.4	30.7	30.3	22.0	18.6
558	PA0528_at	11.0	30.3	38.2	23.0	37.6
559	PA0529_at	9.6	26.2	34.4	31.9	43.3
560	PA0530_at	14.2	35.0	45.6	18.1	41.1
561	PA0531_at	15.1	4.2	8.5	8.8	21.3
562	PA0532_at	3.8	20.9	46.1	28.9	49.5
563	PA0533_at	48.2	61.2	48.9	41.4	57.5
564	PA0534_at	60.3	142.8	85.2	58.8	75.2
565	PA0535_at	50.7	96.2	69.4	54.9	74.1
566	PA0536_at	181.0	153.5	210.3	303.3	232.4
567	PA0537_at	473.0	462.9	410.1	562.0	551.7
568	PA0538_dsB_at	68.7	96.2	120.2	94.9	118.5
569	PA0539_at	15.2	15.7	8.8	9.0	20.1
570	PA0540_at	25.8	23.7	30.2	12.6	35.5
571	PA0541_at	182.3	246.7	245.4	221.5	227.8
572	PA0542_at	202.9	305.2	193.2	204.4	241.9
573	PA0543_at	28.9	24.7	67.0	37.0	32.8
574	PA0544_at	44.6	67.1	162.9	128.7	120.5
575	PA0545_at	37.1	32.8	68.9	47.5	47.4
576	PA0546_metK_at	2334.9	2227.1	1650.0	2267.8	2184.8

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

577	PA0547_at	678.8	872.8	878.2	827.8	886.6
578	PA0548_tktA_at	951.9	982.6	653.7	853.6	895.7
579	PA0549_at	310.9	268.0	366.6	303.9	271.8
580	PA0550_at	46.3	42.0	52.6	52.8	30.4
581	PA0551_epd_at	486.9	435.7	467.6	538.6	492.3
582	PA0552_pgk_at	517.1	558.6	385.9	474.4	522.6
583	PA0553_at	535.0	459.1	665.8	723.0	645.0
584	PA0554_at	777.8	935.7	758.4	598.3	809.7
585	PA0555_fda_at	1870.3	1961.2	1644.6	1699.7	1686.5
586	PA0556_at	55.7	51.6	103.1	177.1	87.7
587	PA0557_at	1.1	14.3	32.5	6.1	26.7
588	PA0558_at	35.9	42.8	55.8	57.8	49.6
589	PA0559_at	152.2	193.7	138.6	177.9	191.2
590	PA0560_at	98.1	89.5	121.4	81.7	94.7
591	PA0561_at	3.6	38.2	33.6	33.9	25.0
592	PA0562_at	163.8	229.8	275.6	280.6	261.7
593	PA0563_at	883.5	994.3	779.7	776.5	731.7
594	PA0564_at	52.1	64.2	80.8	67.2	95.5
595	PA0565_at	11.2	53.3	45.8	42.4	46.4
596	PA0566_at	91.1	82.4	108.1	86.8	99.5
597	PA0567_i_at	3.0	19.5	18.6	18.4	26.9
598	PA0568_at	52.4	73.2	101.2	100.3	89.3
599	PA0569_at	70.0	126.4	123.4	142.2	113.3
600	PA0570_at	103.4	79.0	214.7	121.0	112.4
601	PA0571_at	92.7	105.0	162.9	108.4	126.7
602	PA0572_at	71.2	81.9	51.5	80.0	82.0
603	PA0573_at	25.6	13.8	4.5	17.3	30.0
604	PA0574_at	139.9	156.2	138.4	139.1	166.7
605	PA0575_at	3.0	2.4	26.6	32.9	10.7
606	PA0576_rpoD_at	3932.4	2666.2	2913.2	3232.0	2970.9
607	PA0577_dnaG_at	339.0	374.4	506.7	402.7	470.7
608	PA0578_at	1297.1	1371.4	1840.4	2073.7	1686.2
609	PA0579_rpsU_at	2742.7	3009.0	1801.3	2225.7	2358.2
610	PA0580_gcp_at	232.0	210.2	333.8	279.6	308.2
611	PA0581_i_at	63.6	82.4	117.5	96.5	89.3
612	PA0582_folB_at	73.4	192.5	111.3	140.3	215.4
613	PA0583_at	66.3	73.3	102.6	73.2	109.9
614	PA0584_cca_at	36.5	53.0	64.4	52.2	46.8
615	PA0585_at	28.4	9.3	25.7	9.9	14.9
616	PA0586_at	39.5	101.2	71.0	61.0	81.3
617	PA0587_at	47.4	43.8	60.7	43.1	62.4
618	PA0588_at	198.8	280.6	268.0	173.3	253.7
619	PA0589_at	357.4	326.3	220.7	222.9	214.0
620	PA0590_apaH_at	441.0	421.9	483.2	363.0	461.9
621	PA0591_at	467.3	411.8	498.0	489.1	458.6
622	PA0592_ksgA_at	570.9	434.5	400.2	640.1	457.0
623	PA0593_pdxA_at	598.7	606.3	813.9	627.5	520.2
624	PA0594_surA_at	1443.0	1269.0	1098.2	1160.3	1104.7
625	PA0595_ostA_at	3026.3	2044.9	2555.3	2416.4	2076.2
626	PA0596_at	336.7	393.5	292.6	340.3	357.5
627	PA0597_at	72.9	95.0	126.2	134.9	132.9
628	PA0598_at	216.4	213.3	295.8	366.8	258.9
629	PA0599_at	47.5	100.5	51.5	79.8	104.3
630	PA0600_at	47.4	64.4	68.0	41.5	47.6
631	PA0601_at	112.6	117.4	86.6	79.4	104.3
632	PA0602_at	24.2	52.8	59.4	44.3	56.4
633	PA0603_at	192.1	444.3	706.6	550.5	593.1
634	PA0604_at	118.1	301.3	261.6	296.6	254.3
635	PA0605_at	88.8	272.4	326.0	304.2	381.0
636	PA0606_at	68.9	109.6	103.4	127.2	145.0
637	PA0607_rpe_at	227.5	254.5	284.9	217.5	292.4
638	PA0608_at	738.1	607.9	764.2	784.6	664.3
639	PA0609_trpE_at	248.4	369.1	293.4	338.8	366.9
640	PA0610_prtN_at	92.4	101.3	68.0	75.6	56.1
641	PA0611_prtR_at	172.7	170.9	270.7	234.2	177.1
642	PA0612_i_at	166.0	112.5	115.3	118.6	87.7
643	PA0613_at	5.7	35.1	20.8	11.7	16.6
644	PA0614_at	62.1	78.9	216.7	135.7	130.1
645	PA0615_at	47.8	74.0	158.3	81.4	107.7
646	PA0616_at	57.5	104.1	230.5	154.7	134.2
647	PA0617_at	28.5	71.5	120.8	112.5	84.4
648	PA0618_at	79.1	121.0	177.8	140.6	147.9
649	PA0619_at	105.8	173.8	243.0	179.0	202.0

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

650	PA0620_at	59.2	92.4	186.4	182.1	124.2
651	PA0621_at	150.9	278.4	454.5	342.2	285.3
652	PA0622_at	184.7	228.5	338.1	303.9	293.6
653	PA0623_at	146.1	257.0	346.6	325.3	261.3
654	PA0624_at	52.4	82.7	148.7	75.6	108.2
655	PA0625_at	47.1	41.2	87.7	76.1	59.7
656	PA0626_at	54.4	84.8	82.3	65.5	82.9
657	PA0627_at	53.8	102.3	106.4	84.2	102.8
658	PA0628_at	26.5	57.1	74.4	75.0	67.8
659	PA0629_at	48.2	35.8	44.1	61.8	75.5
660	PA0630_at	69.0	56.2	136.8	99.3	112.0
661	PA0631_at	15.3	30.9	69.5	64.0	61.4
662	PA0632_at	49.2	55.8	74.1	69.4	50.3
663	PA0633_at	137.0	183.1	258.2	232.6	250.4
664	PA0634_at	50.1	58.4	81.3	58.6	56.3
665	PA0635_at	54.0	69.0	64.1	114.0	79.9
666	PA0636_at	96.6	149.9	324.6	233.9	213.2
667	PA0637_at	44.4	78.5	76.2	64.2	68.6
668	PA0638_at	49.3	64.4	79.0	96.0	78.7
669	PA0639_at	17.6	42.4	110.9	115.6	59.4
670	PA0640_at	17.4	36.1	53.3	42.2	34.4
671	PA0641_at	35.7	20.3	12.5	39.0	44.2
672	PA0642_at	2.0	8.7	28.6	6.6	8.7
673	PA0643_at	43.0	59.0	60.5	73.2	57.7
674	PA0644_at	31.6	96.5	24.7	30.8	61.0
675	PA0645_at	44.8	55.3	53.8	38.3	55.3
676	PA0646_at	43.1	29.8	69.7	74.7	57.4
677	PA0647_at	10.3	31.3	38.2	58.4	35.0
678	PA0648_at	36.8	95.3	46.2	55.2	70.8
679	PA0649_trpG_at	446.1	399.7	507.1	501.3	524.7
680	PA0650_trpD_at	359.3	515.0	498.3	471.9	507.2
681	PA0651_trpC_at	356.2	344.2	396.7	295.9	309.7
682	PA0652_vfr_at	777.1	1109.5	937.1	726.8	818.6
683	PA0653_at	202.6	234.9	120.2	121.2	134.7
684	PA0654_speD_at	1055.8	1586.1	1176.7	1640.6	1743.7
685	PA0655_at	291.5	222.0	143.3	165.5	210.0
686	PA0656_at	44.4	57.0	80.4	64.3	78.6
687	PA0657_at	84.0	74.3	95.9	125.0	125.3
688	PA0658_at	264.1	284.5	368.3	324.1	269.6
689	PA0659_at	526.5	491.1	862.5	600.1	487.8
690	PA0660_at	235.5	156.6	158.0	153.0	191.0
691	PA0661_at	358.6	395.5	450.4	431.7	495.2
692	PA0662_argC_at	306.4	287.3	301.1	345.1	371.2
693	PA0663_at	294.0	313.1	359.5	275.4	387.8
694	PA0664_at	245.5	243.3	234.4	297.2	287.0
695	PA0665_at	209.1	258.8	423.6	486.9	393.0
696	PA0666_at	182.4	175.4	157.3	210.7	160.3
697	PA0667_at	713.8	758.7	531.8	612.9	597.2
698	PA0668_tyrZ_at	276.2	440.1	485.8	469.2	466.9
699	PA0669_at	31.9	35.1	70.8	59.7	47.5
700	PA0670_at	13.6	28.0	45.7	43.0	52.5
701	PA0671_at	40.7	33.7	11.4	33.7	34.1
702	PA0672_at	6.9	35.5	101.5	81.9	61.5
703	PA0673_at	14.2	12.8	65.8	61.2	46.0
704	PA0674_at	6.1	10.2	52.8	24.2	32.3
705	PA0675_at	23.0	23.7	59.5	25.9	36.0
706	PA0676_at	56.7	24.5	59.5	14.0	63.7
707	PA0677_at	6.1	3.6	14.6	7.0	28.0
708	PA0678_i_at	14.1	0.9	3.3	3.4	19.9
709	PA0679_at	6.3	22.3	53.7	35.3	31.2
710	PA0680_at	6.0	9.2	32.8	3.1	28.3
711	PA0681_at	2.5	14.3	28.1	11.7	39.3
712	PA0682_at	46.3	19.5	20.4	16.9	41.8
713	PA0683_at	10.1	8.8	37.2	6.7	16.4
714	PA0684_at	18.9	21.5	58.0	35.3	50.0
715	PA0685_at	25.2	4.7	23.3	21.1	17.7
716	PA0686_at	10.5	16.0	36.6	52.2	22.7
717	PA0687_at	12.1	22.1	51.6	12.4	25.1
718	PA0688_at	3.3	11.2	23.7	26.5	33.3
719	PA0689_at	41.6	34.4	78.0	36.2	53.2
720	PA0690_at	12.9	2.4	4.9	1.7	5.4
721	PA0691_at	3.3	8.3	28.2	8.4	29.3
722	PA0692_at	15.7	12.7	44.0	7.2	26.5

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

723	PA0693_exbB2_at	20.6	16.9	16.5	22.2	31.1
724	PA0694_exbD2_at	115.8	52.0	120.5	57.0	63.5
725	PA0695_at	7.7	1.8	26.0	7.7	11.0
726	PA0696_at	1.3	1.7	5.1	4.5	18.1
727	PA0697_at	12.9	10.4	27.2	15.7	32.4
728	PA0698_at	8.4	14.2	32.7	8.7	21.2
729	PA0699_at	43.2	24.3	44.6	71.7	45.1
730	PA0700_at	39.1	35.8	55.0	22.6	54.4
731	PA0701_at	26.8	3.7	35.7	24.0	24.7
732	PA0702_at	4.0	22.3	30.6	3.7	32.0
733	PA0703_at	62.5	42.2	94.2	70.9	66.3
734	PA0704_at	70.8	91.2	14.6	54.0	46.5
735	PA0705_at	898.3	713.7	488.9	644.4	556.1
736	PA0706_cat_at	228.9	314.0	222.3	223.6	223.5
737	PA0707_toxR_at	69.8	41.4	96.1	46.4	57.3
738	PA0708_at	70.8	109.9	72.5	103.6	136.0
739	PA0709_at	41.5	24.4	48.5	24.6	42.7
740	PA0710_gloA2_at	29.6	20.2	58.0	10.3	30.4
741	PA0711_at	33.6	3.4	57.8	26.5	32.8
742	PA0712_at	73.8	65.3	55.3	76.8	57.1
743	PA0713_at	33.3	19.9	59.7	28.0	45.9
744	PA0714_at	3.0	4.7	27.8	3.7	13.0
745	PA0715_at	21.2	35.2	69.8	38.7	51.1
746	PA0716_at	17.3	9.7	27.2	13.0	8.9
747	PA0717_at	11.0	30.2	43.1	28.2	52.0
748	PA0718_at	12.8	10.3	48.7	26.3	37.1
749	PA0719_at	15.3	19.1	12.8	8.5	28.5
750	PA0720_at	64.0	56.0	62.3	75.2	88.0
751	PA0721_r_at	21.6	24.1	61.9	45.2	27.2
752	PA0722_at	86.5	99.0	90.5	37.9	79.0
753	PA0723_coaB_at	111.9	63.3	66.6	74.3	79.4
754	PA0724_at	21.6	10.4	4.1	4.7	32.7
755	PA0725_at	18.5	12.5	11.0	17.4	7.9
756	PA0726_at	26.6	20.0	51.1	30.9	46.3
757	PA0727_at	36.8	24.8	39.8	35.3	34.6
758	PA0728_at	3.4	12.5	41.8	7.7	41.0
759	PA0729_at	113.8	267.7	269.5	211.1	249.9
760	PA0730_at	708.6	1072.4	521.2	491.9	653.0
761	PA0731_at	105.3	118.7	94.9	76.2	99.0
762	PA0732_at	83.9	90.3	73.5	58.6	68.6
763	PA0733_at	184.9	156.7	255.3	189.6	164.1
764	PA0734_i_at	392.8	298.7	373.5	306.2	259.7
765	PA0735_at	192.3	182.6	107.3	158.5	192.9
766	PA0736_at	63.8	77.8	105.2	98.6	137.4
767	PA0737_at	34.3	31.2	27.7	18.7	24.9
768	PA0738_at	2.2	17.8	29.4	14.4	29.0
769	PA0739_at	89.0	55.9	58.7	75.4	69.5
770	PA0740_at	13.8	20.2	5.9	8.0	23.6
771	PA0741_at	76.2	42.7	54.0	39.8	30.6
772	PA0742_at	109.2	44.5	98.0	54.0	82.6
773	PA0743_at	12.3	41.6	40.4	27.3	44.1
774	PA0744_at	149.9	225.5	497.7	575.4	405.8
775	PA0745_at	331.9	528.7	708.3	698.8	706.1
776	PA0746_at	92.8	97.6	157.7	97.7	141.2
777	PA0747_at	44.2	118.0	116.0	155.9	104.2
778	PA0748_at	12.1	4.0	4.3	30.9	18.9
779	PA0749_at	79.5	103.1	166.5	131.6	125.1
780	PA0750_ung_at	227.4	267.3	163.2	181.4	222.6
781	PA0751_at	158.8	181.6	87.4	50.0	72.3
782	PA0752_at	221.1	317.3	133.4	131.0	86.9
783	PA0753_at	146.6	159.4	73.3	68.2	56.5
784	PA0754_at	216.9	312.5	74.0	82.8	92.8
785	PA0755_at	500.1	298.1	114.1	87.3	129.7
786	PA0756_at	114.5	143.4	216.6	229.3	173.9
787	PA0757_at	132.1	185.7	285.2	270.5	198.9
788	PA0758_at	399.7	305.1	133.0	193.4	223.2
789	PA0759_at	485.0	290.2	312.9	301.8	421.9
790	PA0760_at	178.5	331.4	217.6	181.5	196.9
791	PA0761_nadB_at	334.2	372.9	326.4	381.8	413.2
792	PA0762_algU_at	1437.3	1360.2	1714.8	1988.4	1817.7
793	PA0763_mucA_at	946.2	1081.4	1556.3	1433.2	1291.1
794	PA0764_mucB_at	394.4	427.7	488.5	508.2	461.1
795	PA0765_mucC_at	519.4	586.8	738.4	570.9	582.9

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

796	PA0766_mucD_at	574.9	830.7	735.9	1048.4	974.1
797	PA0767_lepA_at	893.7	1160.3	638.8	840.1	973.2
798	PA0768_lepB_at	1305.1	1400.4	1842.5	1564.2	1277.0
799	PA0769_at	613.7	1012.4	823.3	1015.4	964.3
800	PA0770_rnc_at	880.6	850.2	939.4	924.4	1188.2
801	PA0771_era_at	751.3	1322.4	1050.5	1063.6	936.3
802	PA0772_recO_at	71.4	120.3	166.5	134.9	124.1
803	PA0773_pdxJ_at	136.2	197.6	255.0	259.9	262.7
804	PA0774_at	128.9	204.7	190.4	179.9	228.2
805	PA0775_at	249.7	355.0	254.7	310.3	329.8
806	PA0776_at	21.5	16.7	35.0	22.4	30.5
807	PA0777_at	94.3	65.9	126.7	111.2	99.3
808	PA0778_at	332.3	246.9	266.2	257.4	262.5
809	PA0779_at	859.1	841.2	182.6	203.2	197.1
810	PA0780_at	123.8	125.1	145.1	124.4	120.6
811	PA0781_at	60.0	60.5	184.4	116.4	109.2
812	PA0782_putA_at	106.0	200.8	211.2	226.6	230.8
813	PA0783_putP_at	160.1	214.9	358.4	390.3	400.2
814	PA0784_at	110.9	128.9	110.8	112.3	159.3
815	PA0785_at	52.0	18.0	51.3	48.4	44.6
816	PA0786_at	16.5	8.1	30.2	10.2	31.7
817	PA0787_at	67.6	99.4	121.0	121.7	131.8
818	PA0788_at	70.2	38.3	90.6	38.3	63.9
819	PA0789_at	732.3	694.2	689.6	561.7	937.5
820	PA0790_at	18.1	16.0	21.8	8.9	16.2
821	PA0791_at	73.6	109.8	79.5	110.5	134.4
822	PA0792_prpD_at	67.9	109.5	281.6	201.6	171.3
823	PA0793_at	406.8	521.9	823.6	910.1	787.8
824	PA0794_at	298.9	476.1	738.9	626.7	598.3
825	PA0795_prpC_at	1289.7	1674.0	1359.2	1440.2	1618.4
826	PA0796_prpB_at	840.6	735.3	691.0	936.7	956.2
827	PA0797_at	316.8	291.3	521.2	380.2	447.8
828	PA0798_at	13.4	14.1	28.9	38.6	36.6
829	PA0799_at	97.9	118.1	92.2	112.9	119.9
830	PA0800_at	21.6	18.7	56.9	40.9	47.0
831	PA0801_at	2.6	38.7	251.4	145.1	112.5
832	PA0802_i_at	2.9	19.8	69.9	63.8	91.8
833	PA0803_at	4.6	19.4	25.9	46.0	39.1
834	PA0804_at	97.3	115.3	185.4	142.1	108.0
835	PA0805_at	317.5	597.5	305.1	327.4	336.2
836	PA0806_i_at	21.8	55.4	71.6	36.3	62.9
837	PA0807_at	50.0	46.0	48.8	8.9	41.3
838	PA0808_at	4.9	10.3	20.8	18.2	21.8
839	PA0809_at	17.5	15.5	41.1	24.3	22.2
840	PA0810_at	53.3	48.9	92.5	70.6	64.8
841	PA0811_at	9.0	12.0	8.0	15.9	17.6
842	PA0812_at	48.2	20.8	47.0	38.7	39.9
843	PA0813_at	43.7	42.0	89.4	80.3	63.0
844	PA0814_i_at	3.3	35.1	67.3	56.2	53.6
845	PA0815_at	29.8	34.3	44.3	30.7	52.3
846	PA0816_at	32.3	37.8	50.9	67.6	55.8
847	PA0817_at	43.9	54.8	63.3	64.9	73.3
848	PA0818_at	51.6	46.9	37.2	59.8	54.2
849	PA0819_f_at	43.2	44.0	51.1	60.7	56.0
850	PA0820_at	105.7	189.0	178.6	140.4	184.2
851	PA0821_at	73.5	84.3	100.4	93.1	101.4
852	PA0822_at	25.4	41.2	55.7	26.9	41.2
853	PA0823_at	2.3	17.9	36.3	4.4	32.5
854	PA0824_at	13.0	17.1	38.7	49.4	34.4
855	PA0825_at	2.0	9.1	35.2	24.8	16.9
856	PA0826_at	60.4	89.3	89.5	73.6	77.3
857	PA0827_at	103.8	144.2	127.8	103.8	135.4
858	PA0828_at	25.0	22.6	64.5	44.3	44.9
859	PA0829_at	26.4	14.1	34.9	27.8	22.1
860	PA0830_at	102.0	139.8	68.0	61.1	93.2
861	PA0831_oruR_at	309.4	197.7	446.4	332.0	308.5
862	PA0832_at	318.1	295.6	288.1	382.1	371.4
863	PA0833_at	1880.1	1380.0	856.1	1074.7	1041.0
864	PA0834_at	114.7	160.1	218.6	189.3	154.3
865	PA0835_pta_at	198.0	196.4	157.1	174.2	220.2
866	PA0836_at	203.3	186.5	171.3	222.0	199.3
867	PA0837_slyD_at	1026.4	771.5	629.2	858.6	733.3
868	PA0838_at	288.3	375.2	276.0	289.0	405.4

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

869	PA0839_at	63.4	140.1	73.2	41.4	71.3
870	PA0840_at	71.9	109.7	77.9	64.5	96.2
871	PA0841_at	106.6	102.7	138.3	127.6	158.5
872	PA0842_at	26.3	11.3	49.8	6.2	35.2
873	PA0843_plcR_at	28.8	18.9	25.0	27.9	41.3
874	PA0844_plcH_at	9.9	2.1	16.0	2.5	14.6
875	PA0845_at	7.0	4.7	37.5	7.4	29.1
876	PA0846_at	72.4	88.7	97.0	83.2	109.9
877	PA0847_at	9.2	30.9	11.4	8.4	49.0
878	PA0848_at	108.5	286.8	276.2	364.3	395.2
879	PA0849_trxB2_at	94.1	254.8	425.1	333.7	285.6
880	PA0850_at	70.2	50.5	25.5	43.3	49.3
881	PA0851_at	93.4	138.6	163.7	130.9	99.2
882	PA0852_cpbD_at	381.8	588.4	393.5	485.6	616.7
883	PA0853_at	272.1	233.6	312.1	254.6	236.5
884	PA0854_fumC2_at	347.2	247.6	222.4	241.8	232.4
885	PA0855_at	450.4	528.8	357.5	430.8	400.0
886	PA0856_at	2272.4	2226.4	1005.1	1532.4	1360.4
887	PA0857_bolA_at	824.6	642.0	449.9	529.2	515.0
888	PA0858_at	453.0	544.6	364.2	385.4	467.7
889	PA0859_at	137.9	120.7	234.5	223.4	207.1
890	PA0860_at	167.9	176.9	259.8	234.3	200.7
891	PA0861_at	69.1	78.5	83.9	86.0	63.4
892	PA0862_at	416.4	538.8	281.9	230.7	242.3
893	PA0863_at	10.1	10.9	3.6	24.1	32.9
894	PA0864_at	60.2	37.5	99.5	69.7	75.3
895	PA0865_hpd_at	4898.3	3447.6	1876.9	2368.8	2441.1
896	PA0866_aroP2_at	1351.6	1125.4	1519.2	1543.9	1511.4
897	PA0867_at	477.3	473.2	239.6	444.6	597.5
898	PA0868_at	96.8	161.9	118.3	96.9	141.3
899	PA0869_pbpG_at	477.5	543.5	557.9	559.5	539.3
900	PA0870_phhC_at	3257.9	3028.7	4136.8	3818.0	4152.5
901	PA0871_phhB_at	4326.4	3685.8	3061.3	3123.7	3094.6
902	PA0872_phhA_at	3854.8	2819.0	5462.1	4369.8	3934.7
903	PA0873_phhR_at	75.6	46.8	110.4	45.0	65.6
904	PA0874_at	8.8	19.1	25.8	23.9	30.3
905	PA0875_at	48.8	20.5	60.2	50.2	61.9
906	PA0876_at	249.3	252.6	200.3	248.7	257.9
907	PA0877_at	38.3	61.3	79.7	59.0	71.0
908	PA0878_at	9.5	23.4	29.9	28.3	34.6
909	PA0879_at	5.1	3.1	2.6	2.2	13.3
910	PA0880_at	12.9	14.2	18.8	9.1	20.7
911	PA0881_at	27.5	32.5	52.5	28.4	38.7
912	PA0882_at	14.8	23.5	22.4	37.0	23.6
913	PA0883_at	14.9	10.2	11.8	16.8	24.5
914	PA0884_at	7.4	13.3	38.0	4.8	23.8
915	PA0885_at	1.5	1.1	2.7	7.7	5.1
916	PA0886_at	3.4	11.5	22.8	3.6	30.7
917	PA0887_acsA_at	3702.0	1090.0	1332.7	1395.9	1473.3
918	PA0888_aotJ_at	1872.9	1955.5	1436.7	1923.0	2029.9
919	PA0889_aotQ_at	575.1	601.8	1000.6	968.6	851.9
920	PA0890_aotM_at	899.9	776.2	1153.5	1164.9	979.9
921	PA0891_at	1014.0	897.0	842.6	837.7	812.4
922	PA0892_aotP_at	1644.9	1293.5	2023.5	1855.0	1750.8
923	PA0893_argR_at	628.7	611.0	807.7	727.6	620.5
924	PA0894_at	26.7	33.2	48.7	35.1	39.8
925	PA0895_aruC_at	2471.6	1336.1	1091.9	1335.7	1431.0
926	PA0896_aruF_at	1403.7	1083.9	320.0	547.2	568.3
927	PA0897_aruG_at	1152.4	785.1	748.1	682.5	565.5
928	PA0898_aruD_at	1368.2	1066.6	764.6	819.7	766.9
929	PA0899_aruB_at	2171.7	1711.9	1197.4	1202.5	1166.9
930	PA0900_at	5046.7	3200.6	2400.7	2779.8	2465.2
931	PA0901_aruE_at	1188.9	891.0	748.1	618.6	713.1
932	PA0902_at	262.2	178.8	264.7	255.7	187.5
933	PA0903_alaS_at	832.9	584.3	1053.3	901.3	815.9
934	PA0904_lysC_at	1151.4	1277.3	1389.9	1632.3	1358.5
935	PA0905_csrA_at	658.2	791.1	369.5	378.8	453.5
936	PA0906_at	79.5	120.9	72.3	61.2	90.6
937	PA0907_at	44.2	31.4	37.4	51.8	36.9
938	PA0908_at	12.4	17.0	14.1	8.1	15.9
939	PA0909_i_at	7.9	14.5	22.5	8.3	15.6
940	PA0910_at	2.0	13.8	36.4	25.2	31.5
941	PA0911_at	16.3	34.2	62.1	30.1	47.0

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

942	PA0912_at	43.8	40.4	105.0	45.2	48.8
943	PA0913_mgtE_at	524.6	640.8	716.7	894.4	807.0
944	PA0914_at	99.2	97.2	126.3	129.1	133.0
945	PA0915_at	440.5	477.5	319.7	389.9	394.2
946	PA0916_at	780.5	1040.4	377.5	508.3	576.9
947	PA0917_kup_at	202.1	249.7	285.4	363.8	261.9
948	PA0918_at	205.1	229.8	331.3	260.1	236.3
949	PA0919_at	270.8	240.1	239.0	195.0	211.1
950	PA0920_at	197.5	265.8	266.6	196.8	155.6
951	PA0921_at	103.9	267.4	247.2	199.1	279.0
952	PA0922_at	172.1	227.8	209.2	203.1	233.4
953	PA0923_dinP_at	96.0	114.2	195.8	170.5	168.5
954	PA0924_at	128.1	100.0	171.8	144.3	113.6
955	PA0925_at	464.0	414.0	271.1	252.1	243.6
956	PA0926_at	564.5	538.0	648.4	537.3	463.4
957	PA0927_ldhA_at	350.6	237.5	193.1	197.3	215.4
958	PA0928_at	173.9	188.1	307.4	269.5	221.9
959	PA0929_at	15.7	14.6	64.1	56.0	108.7
960	PA0930_at	56.9	23.5	60.0	90.0	85.8
961	PA0931_at	15.0	6.9	7.7	5.0	32.5
962	PA0932_cysM_at	938.6	811.7	1410.9	990.5	867.6
963	PA0933_ygcA_at	481.9	434.2	675.1	605.5	556.7
964	PA0934_relA_at	527.1	596.7	655.3	631.6	707.8
965	PA0935_at	301.1	251.6	369.7	369.3	337.1
966	PA0936_at	207.8	299.7	244.5	284.4	246.5
967	PA0937_at	1063.8	918.4	1226.0	1068.3	1031.2
968	PA0938_at	405.6	995.7	687.6	637.5	705.6
969	PA0939_at	10.9	8.9	24.6	1.6	13.1
970	PA0940_at	41.3	30.1	60.7	56.6	63.7
971	PA0941_at	9.8	24.9	36.2	28.8	30.4
972	PA0942_at	64.1	60.6	112.3	79.0	102.1
973	PA0943_at	1472.0	1324.6	1378.3	1378.7	1412.0
974	PA0944_purN_at	748.2	809.4	724.1	747.8	729.5
975	PA0945_purM_at	931.9	889.6	978.3	976.8	984.6
976	PA0946_at	271.2	215.9	214.3	207.0	287.6
977	PA0947_at	427.5	342.5	577.6	519.5	475.8
978	PA0948_at	132.0	219.1	305.7	297.1	256.0
979	PA0949_wrbA_at	498.0	619.5	497.5	607.9	546.7
980	PA0950_at	537.3	603.7	391.2	749.2	716.3
981	PA0951_at	50.1	53.7	79.4	60.3	61.2
982	PA0952_at	59.5	50.7	37.6	25.7	48.6
983	PA0953_at	93.5	118.5	106.2	115.8	111.5
984	PA0954_at	28.6	68.1	50.0	72.3	59.1
985	PA0955_at	856.8	830.3	805.5	763.8	678.2
986	PA0956_proS_at	1651.3	1396.2	1320.3	1548.9	1424.2
987	PA0957_at	27.2	46.8	35.1	61.4	38.5
988	PA0958_oprD_at	4713.8	2726.3	3258.5	3140.2	2892.8
989	PA0959_at	289.2	422.7	260.2	325.3	313.7
990	PA0960_at	318.2	467.3	290.1	317.9	358.3
991	PA0961_at	158.3	275.1	257.5	313.2	314.8
992	PA0962_at	720.8	635.3	663.4	696.9	675.5
993	PA0963_aspS_at	1460.4	1265.1	1257.5	1559.1	1475.1
994	PA0964_at	1058.7	1226.6	1053.6	1179.3	1241.3
995	PA0965_ruvC_at	1212.4	1159.0	1107.8	1209.0	1240.6
996	PA0966_ruvA_at	574.2	773.9	942.8	833.5	793.5
997	PA0967_ruvB_at	506.9	416.8	583.4	504.2	574.8
998	PA0968_at	483.5	671.9	1546.3	1088.0	1074.6
999	PA0969_tolQ_at	954.4	1058.7	1653.4	1428.1	1424.7
1000	PA0970_tolR_at	820.2	1040.1	1121.6	1053.7	1344.2
1001	PA0971_tolA_at	775.5	1065.6	1874.2	1479.6	1158.6
1002	PA0972_tolB_at	1379.0	1742.4	1225.7	1604.8	1754.2
1003	PA0973_oprL_at	3821.6	2828.1	4321.3	3857.3	3350.5
1004	PA0974_at	2235.6	1649.6	1407.5	1747.2	1700.1
1005	PA0975_at	193.5	362.3	203.7	256.2	247.8
1006	PA0976_at	109.2	286.1	166.7	142.5	163.6
1007	PA0977_at	2.2	4.1	22.8	16.8	15.8
1008	PA0978_s_at	27.3	65.4	39.5	52.6	80.1
1009	PA0979_s_at	55.4	59.9	37.1	34.3	47.3
1010	PA0980_at	16.9	19.7	22.6	17.2	25.5
1011	PA0981_at	29.1	12.1	21.3	17.0	31.2
1012	PA0982_at	44.6	71.7	64.2	55.9	74.7
1013	PA0983_at	37.7	52.6	36.1	40.4	45.6
1014	PA0984_at	0.7	5.4	8.4	9.8	7.1

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1015	PA0985_at	5.5	22.8	3.9	3.2	18.9
1016	PA0986_i_at	8.6	0.3	16.7	2.6	4.2
1017	PA0987_at	19.6	4.3	30.8	6.9	18.7
1018	PA0988_at	84.6	50.0	89.9	95.4	68.9
1019	PA0989_at	74.9	75.5	49.4	64.5	64.1
1020	PA0990_at	5.0	16.7	28.5	22.3	28.3
1021	PA0991_at	31.3	23.6	29.2	23.9	20.9
1022	PA0992_at	51.8	65.8	92.6	82.1	94.9
1023	PA0993_at	1.7	0.8	13.8	11.8	25.0
1024	PA0994_at	26.0	26.4	75.9	22.2	27.4
1025	PA0995_ogt_at	66.5	45.8	50.6	64.9	60.6
1026	PA0996_at	2092.7	1760.6	1121.4	1174.1	1257.7
1027	PA0997_at	5380.7	2818.5	2465.6	2447.7	2234.5
1028	PA0998_at	3285.5	2222.1	2427.8	2448.9	1863.6
1029	PA0999_fabH1_at	4535.2	2750.0	3395.3	2980.4	2746.5
1030	PA1000_at	1891.4	1596.2	1491.5	1288.9	1239.2
1031	PA1001_phnA_at	1372.0	1636.0	1210.5	1256.6	1162.9
1032	PA1002_phnB_at	937.6	979.6	644.9	676.4	625.0
1033	PA1003_at	247.1	394.8	442.6	385.4	394.7
1034	PA1004_nadA_at	1026.5	1052.4	966.8	1044.5	1024.9
1035	PA1005_at	338.2	344.8	245.6	308.9	298.0
1036	PA1006_at	135.9	146.0	199.8	246.4	252.2
1037	PA1007_at	53.1	71.2	90.6	85.7	93.5
1038	PA1008_bcp_at	1732.6	1106.2	758.4	1017.4	1151.2
1039	PA1009_at	1303.3	1035.9	664.9	760.6	849.2
1040	PA1010_dapA_at	1670.6	1187.6	1276.3	1356.5	1319.0
1041	PA1011_at	1681.4	1135.1	1466.4	1464.1	1479.1
1042	PA1012_at	300.9	396.6	256.6	350.3	306.1
1043	PA1013_purC_at	921.2	881.4	836.0	990.8	1092.9
1044	PA1014_at	242.3	226.5	331.4	246.2	279.5
1045	PA1015_at	103.1	167.3	142.5	162.7	115.2
1046	PA1016_at	92.2	108.9	117.2	94.4	112.6
1047	PA1017_pauA_at	46.0	36.9	52.3	52.9	58.0
1048	PA1018_at	34.4	43.5	79.8	53.7	60.6
1049	PA1019_mucK_at	1.7	13.9	25.8	13.9	20.9
1050	PA1020_at	54.2	48.8	66.6	62.9	60.9
1051	PA1021_at	31.7	20.5	64.7	23.8	45.9
1052	PA1022_at	103.4	144.0	125.1	100.0	93.1
1053	PA1023_at	50.9	84.5	71.7	51.1	58.0
1054	PA1024_at	57.9	78.5	89.8	100.6	72.2
1055	PA1025_at	11.1	13.8	20.4	23.7	20.8
1056	PA1026_at	114.9	158.4	126.0	157.3	156.2
1057	PA1027_at	64.0	46.8	89.1	84.1	77.6
1058	PA1028_at	46.2	45.4	72.8	53.6	52.0
1059	PA1029_at	162.2	150.2	262.9	142.0	166.0
1060	PA1030_at	97.1	114.6	118.4	116.4	108.7
1061	PA1031_at	196.3	202.3	261.8	243.7	203.9
1062	PA1032_at	292.7	282.8	215.6	208.6	218.7
1063	PA1033_at	175.6	236.8	186.8	224.5	221.6
1064	PA1034_at	36.6	100.5	67.8	86.8	65.2
1065	PA1035_at	66.3	145.6	131.9	136.9	131.3
1066	PA1036_at	74.4	79.6	104.8	105.0	114.2
1067	PA1037_at	101.3	129.9	117.5	127.4	153.1
1068	PA1038_at	90.1	122.5	140.0	85.0	88.5
1069	PA1039_at	205.9	195.4	201.2	182.1	216.2
1070	PA1040_at	190.1	210.3	190.2	235.2	201.9
1071	PA1041_at	86.9	74.9	129.8	132.8	112.6
1072	PA1042_at	102.4	124.1	62.2	113.1	111.9
1073	PA1043_at	217.2	221.5	276.6	301.8	298.6
1074	PA1044_at	55.1	80.0	114.8	106.5	86.2
1075	PA1045_at	379.6	275.6	214.1	298.2	301.3
1076	PA1046_at	83.5	98.6	139.3	114.3	116.4
1077	PA1047_at	425.1	351.6	411.2	463.0	420.7
1078	PA1048_at	900.1	904.4	810.6	850.3	805.5
1079	PA1049_pdxH_at	236.8	239.8	160.9	271.8	291.3
1080	PA1050_at	47.4	70.0	116.9	104.4	113.4
1081	PA1051_at	79.2	17.5	32.9	35.5	40.5
1082	PA1052_at	10.1	4.3	23.4	18.5	23.3
1083	PA1053_at	2542.5	2263.2	3138.4	2947.0	2462.9
1084	PA1054_at	91.4	105.8	190.4	100.2	121.0
1085	PA1055_at	110.9	135.1	191.8	153.1	155.3
1086	PA1056_at	67.9	87.7	102.4	105.8	157.9
1087	PA1057_at	161.2	164.2	142.1	193.2	226.2

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1088	PA1058_at	177.3	232.0	208.5	154.1	173.8
1089	PA1059_at	61.5	122.4	176.0	169.5	172.5
1090	PA1060_at	180.5	153.4	163.0	114.8	138.3
1091	PA1061_at	488.0	438.5	653.4	531.7	580.5
1092	PA1062_at	269.7	280.9	468.6	361.1	328.9
1093	PA1063_at	157.0	231.3	164.9	151.7	190.4
1094	PA1064_at	265.8	286.6	352.5	330.7	362.2
1095	PA1065_at	62.6	45.3	38.3	46.6	70.8
1096	PA1066_at	2.4	2.9	6.2	9.7	17.1
1097	PA1067_at	39.5	20.7	34.6	21.9	31.5
1098	PA1068_at	409.1	269.3	323.7	388.5	383.4
1099	PA1069_at	163.4	239.3	176.6	248.0	241.0
1100	PA1070_braG_at	390.3	371.0	270.5	348.4	369.6
1101	PA1071_braF_at	1245.0	976.5	1221.4	964.0	1076.4
1102	PA1072_braE_at	431.1	354.5	343.9	370.5	404.8
1103	PA1073_braD_at	558.0	580.1	393.7	382.0	489.1
1104	PA1074_braC_at	1563.6	1344.9	1246.0	1646.8	1701.6
1105	PA1075_at	189.0	181.8	192.1	226.1	235.1
1106	PA1076_at	77.9	154.9	97.4	125.6	153.9
1107	PA1077_flgB_at	501.3	419.6	487.4	470.2	367.3
1108	PA1078_flgC_at	565.1	750.0	406.1	558.3	601.2
1109	PA1079_flgD_at	790.7	535.2	406.8	469.6	473.9
1110	PA1080_flgE_at	1438.0	1223.8	1356.5	1391.1	1113.5
1111	PA1081_flgF_at	376.5	429.0	325.4	379.7	385.2
1112	PA1082_flgG_at	717.5	840.5	466.3	578.0	594.1
1113	PA1083_flgH_at	403.2	418.6	276.5	396.8	399.4
1114	PA1084_flgI_at	299.1	286.5	279.1	338.4	360.6
1115	PA1085_flgJ_at	415.8	324.7	495.3	423.7	372.5
1116	PA1086_flgK_at	349.6	337.4	679.2	551.5	478.8
1117	PA1087_flgL_at	623.8	491.0	998.7	867.4	598.3
1118	PA1088_at	239.7	315.7	319.1	274.5	312.6
1119	PA1089_at	207.9	206.6	261.7	226.2	321.1
1120	PA1090_at	180.1	168.5	196.9	265.0	254.6
1121	PA1091_at	217.4	213.1	302.1	264.6	222.9
1122	PA1092_fliC_at	7363.4	3875.0	3811.7	4395.8	3843.2
1123	PA1093_at	1470.9	1758.8	1259.9	1507.3	1484.0
1124	PA1094_fliD_at	995.7	1482.6	627.7	845.0	1038.4
1125	PA1095_at	1166.8	1445.2	987.5	1126.7	1165.9
1126	PA1096_at	1791.0	1796.8	579.6	852.2	968.6
1127	PA1097_fleQ_at	418.6	368.3	658.1	320.6	436.7
1128	PA1098_fleS_at	216.9	190.5	301.8	344.5	311.1
1129	PA1099_fleR_at	268.7	229.9	330.2	280.4	255.8
1130	PA1100_fliE_at	251.9	313.0	275.6	337.6	355.2
1131	PA1101_fliF_at	443.4	420.3	539.6	503.0	508.8
1132	PA1102_fliG_at	1095.8	1110.6	893.9	830.8	1034.0
1133	PA1103_at	647.4	653.4	679.9	506.1	474.5
1134	PA1104_fliI_at	139.4	132.9	288.0	287.8	224.4
1135	PA1105_fliJ_at	124.0	77.6	142.5	116.2	138.6
1136	PA1106_at	18.7	53.7	44.2	62.9	44.3
1137	PA1107_at	29.2	11.0	26.2	13.7	21.6
1138	PA1108_at	16.5	4.3	18.6	11.7	38.0
1139	PA1109_at	2.1	2.5	8.8	3.6	3.1
1140	PA1110_at	75.2	52.6	82.5	61.7	64.1
1141	PA1111_at	17.9	18.7	75.4	21.0	31.8
1142	PA1112_at	37.1	54.2	52.4	58.4	75.5
1143	PA1113_at	46.1	41.3	29.8	28.6	45.9
1144	PA1114_at	89.5	120.8	113.4	113.0	78.4
1145	PA1115_at	210.7	160.2	119.5	114.7	134.2
1146	PA1116_at	212.5	322.4	217.0	267.9	288.7
1147	PA1117_at	137.0	238.2	152.8	168.5	171.3
1148	PA1118_at	24.3	33.5	63.1	51.6	37.9
1149	PA1119_at	279.1	273.3	271.1	264.9	288.6
1150	PA1120_at	57.0	82.8	79.9	79.3	90.6
1151	PA1121_at	94.9	93.3	110.9	164.2	93.1
1152	PA1122_at	127.1	185.5	79.5	138.5	128.7
1153	PA1123_at	55.0	55.9	56.3	36.2	77.4
1154	PA1124_dgt_at	71.1	79.5	83.8	72.2	80.5
1155	PA1125_at	62.5	69.5	119.2	131.6	77.1
1156	PA1126_at	217.1	220.9	205.4	232.2	254.9
1157	PA1127_at	65.8	58.2	106.9	99.6	80.7
1158	PA1128_at	62.0	74.8	122.3	92.4	82.7
1159	PA1129_at	40.3	30.7	46.9	32.9	40.5
1160	PA1130_at	27.7	62.9	64.2	38.8	50.3

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1161	PA1131_at	61.6	55.0	92.7	55.1	71.9
1162	PA1132_at	334.8	374.0	365.3	386.9	318.6
1163	PA1133_at	29.2	15.3	40.2	27.7	36.5
1164	PA1134_at	68.8	36.9	88.3	51.8	55.8
1165	PA1135_at	64.9	50.3	31.9	48.7	44.4
1166	PA1136_at	17.9	17.7	45.5	43.2	42.8
1167	PA1137_at	12.5	29.5	41.8	32.0	35.2
1168	PA1138_at	34.2	59.7	45.4	36.1	57.3
1169	PA1139_at	45.3	66.4	74.2	63.9	68.9
1170	PA1140_at	107.9	120.2	105.9	92.8	101.6
1171	PA1141_at	112.0	88.1	124.6	100.3	125.1
1172	PA1142_at	103.4	114.9	63.1	74.7	101.4
1173	PA1143_at	45.6	26.1	33.0	22.1	28.6
1174	PA1144_at	15.1	6.7	35.0	28.8	16.8
1175	PA1145_at	42.2	48.6	69.5	55.9	77.5
1176	PA1146_at	23.4	14.8	50.5	47.3	48.8
1177	PA1147_at	3.5	9.9	52.7	52.9	43.8
1178	PA1148_toxA_at	29.4	39.3	67.5	48.2	46.5
1179	PA1149_at	79.0	73.5	161.7	157.9	121.1
1180	PA1150_pys2_at	129.2	82.9	119.7	114.1	114.2
1181	PA1151_imm2_at	132.1	280.0	152.5	149.7	177.7
1182	PA1152_at	22.0	48.6	65.6	51.5	32.8
1183	PA1153_at	64.0	49.7	130.1	84.4	68.2
1184	PA1154_at	58.0	20.0	39.9	27.8	35.2
1185	PA1155_nrdB_at	1876.0	2001.6	2000.6	2010.3	1721.5
1186	PA1156_nrdA_at	1296.2	1309.7	929.2	997.7	1056.6
1187	PA1157_at	285.7	211.4	239.9	263.6	303.8
1188	PA1158_at	107.4	99.3	66.3	105.5	81.9
1189	PA1159_at	1927.4	2203.5	1415.0	1801.1	1985.0
1190	PA1160_at	285.4	380.9	483.9	443.3	378.3
1191	PA1161_rrmA_at	245.6	282.4	212.6	245.0	208.1
1192	PA1162_dapE_at	587.3	497.1	405.3	423.6	482.1
1193	PA1163_at	60.8	48.6	78.8	81.6	49.8
1194	PA1164_at	219.3	240.5	159.7	252.6	228.9
1195	PA1165_at	80.7	94.6	201.0	178.9	93.7
1196	PA1166_at	6.8	22.0	13.6	9.5	33.7
1197	PA1167_at	70.7	90.2	159.9	110.5	95.0
1198	PA1168_at	18.5	71.0	115.6	82.5	93.2
1199	PA1169_at	31.7	24.6	7.4	32.7	34.3
1200	PA1170_at	204.1	142.2	151.8	114.5	127.9
1201	PA1171_at	115.7	138.7	85.0	121.0	120.3
1202	PA1172_napC_at	23.9	41.0	81.5	71.4	57.9
1203	PA1173_napB_at	25.9	26.0	37.8	36.4	28.0
1204	PA1174_napA_at	29.0	31.7	55.7	60.1	70.1
1205	PA1175_napD_at	28.1	47.6	83.5	72.6	73.2
1206	PA1176_napF_at	0.6	20.6	20.4	21.8	40.1
1207	PA1177_napE_at	21.0	13.6	13.8	9.3	10.2
1208	PA1178_oprH_at	410.5	1819.1	481.7	468.7	577.4
1209	PA1179_phoP_at	119.1	239.8	205.1	212.4	256.4
1210	PA1180_phoQ_at	88.5	219.6	185.4	195.2	182.1
1211	PA1181_at	152.1	152.9	181.5	156.2	198.4
1212	PA1182_at	108.7	114.6	115.5	132.5	106.9
1213	PA1183_dctA_at	2.1	2.6	36.4	6.1	25.2
1214	PA1184_at	63.9	27.2	59.6	65.3	35.8
1215	PA1185_at	5.7	17.3	73.8	31.7	27.2
1216	PA1186_at	41.7	19.8	44.1	58.5	19.6
1217	PA1187_at	51.9	37.5	65.1	33.1	46.7
1218	PA1188_at	15.4	25.3	76.0	27.3	51.4
1219	PA1189_at	149.5	111.8	127.5	119.5	118.7
1220	PA1190_at	48.4	38.2	32.2	27.0	51.1
1221	PA1191_at	39.4	27.9	48.8	46.6	62.7
1222	PA1192_at	788.8	734.7	557.2	648.8	666.5
1223	PA1193_at	362.3	401.2	418.4	394.1	323.1
1224	PA1194_at	31.7	23.4	68.9	28.0	50.6
1225	PA1195_at	7.9	26.3	38.0	23.4	28.6
1226	PA1196_at	18.0	3.4	41.1	6.8	19.8
1227	PA1197_at	52.0	58.1	68.2	46.1	64.2
1228	PA1198_at	756.5	905.3	1292.5	1712.8	1457.6
1229	PA1199_at	591.4	537.6	493.1	555.1	504.4
1230	PA1200_at	124.5	144.9	147.4	126.1	140.4
1231	PA1201_at	124.4	145.6	110.5	142.1	124.3
1232	PA1202_at	41.7	178.6	72.2	92.4	111.3
1233	PA1203_at	144.1	217.6	122.1	134.0	138.6

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1234	PA1204_at	13.4	30.3	36.2	59.5	40.4
1235	PA1205_at	72.8	78.3	96.8	81.8	80.2
1236	PA1206_at	415.7	405.1	402.9	404.4	408.1
1237	PA1207_kefB_at	122.6	158.1	127.6	108.4	83.2
1238	PA1208_at	30.4	27.2	64.1	37.5	56.2
1239	PA1209_at	91.9	62.8	71.1	85.1	81.3
1240	PA1210_at	10.1	10.6	11.4	12.1	31.0
1241	PA1211_at	5.6	3.8	27.9	5.3	38.6
1242	PA1212_at	30.6	21.5	56.0	37.1	27.0
1243	PA1213_at	27.7	37.6	78.6	60.3	52.1
1244	PA1214_at	24.0	39.2	33.5	47.8	50.9
1245	PA1215_at	6.5	17.4	57.7	15.2	20.5
1246	PA1216_at	46.9	108.5	30.8	76.3	79.3
1247	PA1217_at	7.8	49.5	67.2	60.4	72.1
1248	PA1218_at	49.9	34.4	49.1	44.5	50.2
1249	PA1219_at	54.4	37.6	64.4	38.7	58.4
1250	PA1220_at	37.3	24.4	56.8	30.1	33.7
1251	PA1221_at	36.2	55.5	84.0	89.2	69.9
1252	PA1222_at	255.0	272.7	267.0	196.0	212.5
1253	PA1223_at	18.9	14.7	54.6	10.6	33.5
1254	PA1224_at	46.7	59.1	135.1	83.3	121.7
1255	PA1225_at	8.5	24.2	29.7	8.7	29.1
1256	PA1226_at	59.3	50.8	117.8	95.6	83.6
1257	PA1227_at	37.4	47.0	66.0	42.9	57.8
1258	PA1228_at	314.6	299.0	535.9	536.0	500.0
1259	PA1229_at	33.9	40.7	57.5	53.4	65.8
1260	PA1230_at	3.6	0.5	7.1	15.2	31.1
1261	PA1231_at	20.2	6.8	85.5	61.5	23.3
1262	PA1232_at	6.3	15.1	17.5	15.7	34.8
1263	PA1233_at	42.6	46.5	63.2	54.5	64.4
1264	PA1234_at	116.2	108.6	62.5	69.3	74.7
1265	PA1235_at	35.2	28.9	77.9	67.3	54.3
1266	PA1236_at	27.4	3.5	7.1	3.7	18.5
1267	PA1237_at	47.5	24.1	89.4	73.4	69.0
1268	PA1238_at	6.0	11.4	5.5	6.7	7.6
1269	PA1239_at	19.8	18.3	26.3	19.2	17.8
1270	PA1240_at	37.3	7.7	13.2	5.6	18.3
1271	PA1241_at	57.9	62.3	97.8	104.0	98.5
1272	PA1242_at	5.8	16.6	23.6	9.4	29.9
1273	PA1243_at	97.6	155.3	177.5	132.3	148.0
1274	PA1244_at	1288.7	1132.3	681.6	943.9	1095.9
1275	PA1245_at	180.3	279.0	434.2	313.8	351.2
1276	PA1246_aprD_at	119.5	142.6	119.8	141.8	151.6
1277	PA1247_aprE_at	260.6	253.3	371.9	320.7	269.8
1278	PA1248_aprF_at	132.6	147.3	173.1	140.4	148.6
1279	PA1249_aprA_at	56.0	106.7	80.1	69.6	93.9
1280	PA1250_aprI_at	187.7	295.9	199.3	244.1	279.3
1281	PA1251_at	32.4	30.0	51.6	41.4	51.4
1282	PA1252_at	29.4	58.4	116.3	93.9	61.0
1283	PA1253_at	30.1	22.4	48.8	51.4	42.8
1284	PA1254_at	36.1	14.5	36.5	3.5	35.8
1285	PA1255_at	52.0	22.2	70.5	50.2	35.6
1286	PA1256_at	7.9	13.0	34.6	33.7	30.9
1287	PA1257_at	1.4	4.9	29.2	23.7	19.6
1288	PA1258_at	14.5	2.4	35.5	22.6	33.3
1289	PA1259_at	1.9	2.9	7.9	5.6	16.9
1290	PA1260_at	15.6	10.3	28.3	7.1	12.5
1291	PA1261_at	55.8	59.8	48.6	45.0	42.1
1292	PA1262_at	2.0	4.9	34.0	9.1	19.9
1293	PA1263_at	110.2	117.2	73.1	79.5	121.8
1294	PA1264_at	34.1	29.7	37.0	37.5	21.4
1295	PA1265_at	16.1	31.3	70.3	62.2	44.7
1296	PA1266_at	4.1	13.5	29.1	17.5	20.5
1297	PA1267_at	3.2	4.7	12.7	7.7	18.6
1298	PA1268_at	8.4	34.6	57.0	16.9	39.7
1299	PA1269_at	231.0	273.6	143.1	203.6	181.2
1300	PA1270_at	3.2	16.7	63.5	45.1	28.6
1301	PA1271_at	323.3	360.9	502.0	555.8	552.2
1302	PA1272_cob0_at	611.2	651.4	825.3	824.5	847.8
1303	PA1273_cobB_at	298.7	323.9	303.1	293.6	259.2
1304	PA1274_at	327.6	316.8	350.1	352.6	303.9
1305	PA1275_cobD_at	133.8	179.2	179.3	202.6	201.8
1306	PA1276_cobC_at	175.7	185.0	295.5	259.2	237.7

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1307	PA1277_cobQ_at	166.9	152.2	250.0	227.0	270.9
1308	PA1278_cobP_at	267.8	318.9	473.4	375.8	371.7
1309	PA1279_cobU_at	159.5	142.4	188.3	176.2	250.0
1310	PA1280_at	188.3	188.7	272.2	234.4	202.1
1311	PA1281_cobV_at	84.0	132.6	210.1	180.2	185.3
1312	PA1282_at	19.0	12.5	35.0	23.4	21.8
1313	PA1283_at	40.7	63.9	55.6	78.9	71.4
1314	PA1284_at	38.1	12.8	8.0	4.0	27.2
1315	PA1285_at	52.0	67.3	126.0	102.0	105.0
1316	PA1286_at	7.7	27.3	47.5	33.9	50.5
1317	PA1287_at	94.5	94.9	74.7	124.5	83.4
1318	PA1288_at	3889.2	3048.1	2464.8	2703.7	2505.8
1319	PA1289_at	49.6	39.1	34.3	35.1	70.2
1320	PA1290_at	67.4	56.4	76.9	96.2	61.0
1321	PA1291_at	31.1	33.6	73.1	62.2	62.6
1322	PA1292_at	223.9	250.6	327.7	212.5	223.5
1323	PA1293_at	362.1	317.9	371.5	396.1	359.1
1324	PA1294_rnd_at	418.1	357.7	350.9	441.2	356.1
1325	PA1295_at	166.8	231.6	174.6	187.2	188.8
1326	PA1296_at	270.5	341.1	189.5	224.0	241.4
1327	PA1297_at	42.5	50.6	42.9	55.4	45.9
1328	PA1298_i_at	6.7	15.5	16.2	8.3	17.0
1329	PA1299_at	152.7	204.1	125.2	188.7	199.6
1330	PA1300_at	71.5	66.1	131.6	102.6	107.1
1331	PA1301_at	37.5	49.6	115.9	88.7	93.0
1332	PA1302_at	22.7	35.3	56.0	36.9	46.6
1333	PA1303_at	99.6	53.2	73.0	52.7	63.2
1334	PA1304_at	116.9	161.8	111.6	95.9	117.0
1335	PA1305_at	608.5	482.6	501.1	496.8	468.4
1336	PA1306_at	320.3	388.6	154.1	147.5	171.9
1337	PA1307_at	305.4	334.0	318.9	277.9	341.2
1338	PA1308_at	150.3	204.7	184.7	216.8	227.4
1339	PA1309_at	26.6	47.0	63.1	41.2	59.2
1340	PA1310_phnW_at	47.0	5.8	24.8	6.2	7.9
1341	PA1311_phnX_at	3.9	16.2	7.6	27.1	20.8
1342	PA1312_at	37.5	25.9	25.1	18.4	33.2
1343	PA1313_at	5.4	4.6	32.6	21.6	30.3
1344	PA1314_at	48.7	49.7	112.7	71.6	69.7
1345	PA1315_at	26.1	71.2	100.9	102.0	88.6
1346	PA1316_at	8.4	11.2	46.4	31.1	26.8
1347	PA1317_cyoA_at	184.0	259.2	181.2	200.1	194.1
1348	PA1318_cyoB_at	115.3	124.7	70.6	51.2	77.8
1349	PA1319_cyoC_at	30.0	50.0	76.5	59.4	75.2
1350	PA1320_cyoD_at	35.0	21.4	44.1	47.3	34.5
1351	PA1321_cyoE_at	22.5	24.2	116.7	62.6	71.0
1352	PA1322_at	5.4	12.9	6.9	21.4	33.0
1353	PA1323_at	50.3	122.9	99.0	87.1	80.2
1354	PA1324_at	89.3	129.4	77.2	94.6	91.4
1355	PA1325_at	5.8	21.7	59.9	61.4	37.4
1356	PA1326_ilvA2_at	77.3	90.4	100.1	114.8	118.4
1357	PA1327_at	14.5	40.4	11.9	22.5	45.6
1358	PA1328_at	3.8	9.4	19.1	32.3	29.0
1359	PA1329_at	31.6	26.1	90.4	30.7	33.9
1360	PA1330_at	43.0	75.1	80.7	70.0	65.6
1361	PA1331_at	90.5	108.8	164.9	141.4	111.4
1362	PA1332_at	22.3	22.2	35.6	29.6	31.4
1363	PA1333_r_at	399.5	227.4	175.8	206.1	239.6
1364	PA1334_at	30.8	30.6	15.2	26.7	44.5
1365	PA1335_at	113.9	63.3	95.5	126.9	101.5
1366	PA1336_at	563.6	194.0	160.4	168.5	177.4
1367	PA1337_ansB_at	1291.8	499.6	505.4	429.6	449.3
1368	PA1338_ggt_at	1404.8	241.5	327.0	254.1	292.5
1369	PA1339_at	2114.7	429.2	343.4	367.3	400.2
1370	PA1340_at	1308.0	137.5	284.5	170.5	192.3
1371	PA1341_at	1577.1	171.0	196.2	205.6	238.7
1372	PA1342_at	6569.6	1351.0	1407.5	1497.1	1456.0
1373	PA1343_at	50.8	142.8	121.5	76.7	77.6
1374	PA1344_at	5.8	76.1	43.2	62.4	51.9
1375	PA1345_at	2.1	20.0	9.5	10.7	20.3
1376	PA1346_at	4.6	9.0	22.5	14.1	33.7
1377	PA1347_at	22.1	16.5	34.4	17.9	18.6
1378	PA1348_at	31.2	35.7	75.8	76.1	36.5
1379	PA1349_at	14.0	25.0	28.6	34.7	14.3

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1380	PA1350_at	39.8	22.4	39.1	18.3	39.2
1381	PA1351_at	26.0	7.2	51.0	36.9	43.1
1382	PA1352_at	8.7	18.8	60.0	34.9	39.9
1383	PA1353_at	4.9	19.8	25.0	30.4	34.2
1384	PA1354_at	32.8	42.7	62.5	78.3	66.5
1385	PA1355_at	4.3	2.3	9.1	2.7	18.7
1386	PA1356_at	5.7	20.4	60.5	34.8	49.7
1387	PA1357_at	64.7	70.5	92.4	76.0	96.0
1388	PA1358_at	38.6	33.4	50.4	46.4	24.7
1389	PA1359_at	28.9	73.4	95.6	60.1	80.3
1390	PA1360_at	39.9	36.7	86.0	22.0	37.1
1391	PA1361_at	45.9	44.0	80.2	69.8	75.4
1392	PA1362_i_at	42.6	61.3	48.5	46.5	64.3
1393	PA1363_at	38.2	45.4	74.3	55.0	92.1
1394	PA1364_at	17.1	29.0	71.2	56.7	71.7
1395	PA1365_at	61.9	72.3	69.2	81.0	87.0
1396	PA1366_at	74.7	118.5	145.9	109.6	128.9
1397	PA1367_at	62.3	47.1	109.3	95.8	79.6
1398	PA1368_at	13.2	43.7	32.7	56.7	38.6
1399	PA1369_at	15.5	23.3	24.8	21.9	21.3
1400	PA1370_at	32.5	44.0	57.5	71.7	82.9
1401	PA1371_at	36.7	48.6	37.2	45.1	30.9
1402	PA1372_at	67.1	93.5	92.6	72.5	68.1
1403	PA1373_fabF2_at	102.4	96.8	150.3	120.2	128.6
1404	PA1374_at	35.3	44.6	88.0	62.2	78.5
1405	PA1375_pdxB_at	264.4	250.4	247.4	297.6	280.1
1406	PA1376_aceK_at	225.4	193.1	206.5	173.4	222.5
1407	PA1377_at	165.5	186.1	183.9	229.9	162.0
1408	PA1378_at	43.5	49.5	50.2	43.2	46.6
1409	PA1379_at	28.2	16.7	13.7	17.6	17.5
1410	PA1380_at	15.2	3.9	27.8	7.8	54.6
1411	PA1381_at	14.4	12.6	21.8	4.6	21.2
1412	PA1382_at	22.4	54.0	23.7	33.4	37.9
1413	PA1383_at	51.0	84.2	88.8	102.7	109.9
1414	PA1384_galE_at	8.2	10.7	11.1	6.8	22.1
1415	PA1385_at	6.9	11.8	66.0	17.9	24.2
1416	PA1386_at	13.3	24.4	23.7	20.7	22.2
1417	PA1387_at	10.0	41.7	42.4	52.9	55.9
1418	PA1388_at	21.7	21.6	75.4	38.2	54.3
1419	PA1389_at	12.6	20.9	58.5	37.9	44.3
1420	PA1390_at	34.7	37.2	30.4	14.1	22.7
1421	PA1391_at	8.1	17.5	41.3	23.2	40.1
1422	PA1392_at	9.0	17.7	5.0	24.3	28.7
1423	PA1393_cysC_at	8.7	19.4	22.9	19.0	26.5
1424	PA1394_at	85.6	33.7	98.7	80.0	90.6
1425	PA1395_at	55.9	67.8	86.9	70.6	90.4
1426	PA1396_at	109.7	98.3	145.6	119.8	83.5
1427	PA1397_at	77.0	94.9	92.2	106.5	127.3
1428	PA1398_at	84.8	74.9	59.3	90.5	80.4
1429	PA1399_at	70.0	35.8	86.4	65.7	59.7
1430	PA1400_at	35.0	14.8	44.0	32.0	43.3
1431	PA1401_at	61.1	53.2	113.0	47.9	65.2
1432	PA1402_at	17.3	42.1	34.6	39.9	61.2
1433	PA1403_at	27.9	26.1	38.4	45.5	31.6
1434	PA1404_at	63.9	105.2	56.4	92.0	76.0
1435	PA1405_at	67.3	69.5	89.8	77.4	79.7
1436	PA1406_at	30.5	14.7	35.8	7.9	31.2
1437	PA1407_at	86.1	108.3	192.7	152.7	145.6
1438	PA1408_at	35.2	36.4	70.1	49.4	39.6
1439	PA1409_aphA_at	64.3	81.6	137.9	120.5	115.9
1440	PA1410_at	51.5	142.2	126.9	119.6	153.8
1441	PA1411_at	25.7	63.1	95.5	93.8	80.5
1442	PA1412_at	43.6	16.9	17.5	39.9	31.5
1443	PA1413_at	35.2	65.7	103.0	75.7	77.0
1444	PA1414_at	38.1	90.6	139.5	90.4	102.9
1445	PA1415_at	16.9	30.7	89.8	68.1	43.8
1446	PA1416_at	23.3	17.9	52.3	27.6	27.4
1447	PA1417_at	65.8	66.2	72.2	33.4	56.4
1448	PA1418_at	19.9	40.9	96.2	59.3	67.2
1449	PA1419_at	6.4	7.1	17.0	4.8	14.3
1450	PA1420_at	35.5	22.1	46.3	18.7	33.8
1451	PA1421_speB2_at	44.0	34.2	41.1	49.7	41.7
1452	PA1422_at	128.9	105.9	93.8	144.0	144.3

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1453	PA1423_at	185.8	151.6	169.3	145.2	142.1
1454	PA1424_at	37.9	29.3	53.1	48.4	41.9
1455	PA1425_at	44.6	57.8	98.4	41.9	48.1
1456	PA1426_at	44.9	24.6	31.9	24.9	31.7
1457	PA1427_at	14.1	79.4	22.3	46.8	40.4
1458	PA1428_at	13.4	13.5	10.3	7.0	19.7
1459	PA1429_at	18.1	21.4	56.1	47.6	43.1
1460	PA1430_lasR_at	213.8	196.8	399.4	306.1	250.0
1461	PA1431_rsaL_at	1088.9	1545.2	1538.4	1637.8	1541.2
1462	PA1432_lasI_at	379.1	673.0	400.7	369.2	468.9
1463	PA1433_at	113.3	89.0	125.8	126.0	104.3
1464	PA1434_at	25.6	46.2	87.0	80.6	63.5
1465	PA1435_at	37.6	33.2	68.4	37.0	42.6
1466	PA1436_at	32.6	12.7	39.0	34.8	36.9
1467	PA1437_at	78.4	71.2	80.7	98.6	63.1
1468	PA1438_at	74.2	56.5	80.3	92.8	73.3
1469	PA1439_at	121.2	198.1	201.0	194.1	183.4
1470	PA1440_at	1450.9	1187.3	906.8	1364.0	1344.7
1471	PA1441_at	570.0	426.8	658.7	671.9	611.0
1472	PA1442_at	585.5	751.3	949.7	744.6	707.3
1473	PA1443_fliM_at	616.9	612.2	501.1	587.4	690.0
1474	PA1444_fliN_at	275.2	239.2	238.8	309.2	269.8
1475	PA1445_fliO_at	267.2	264.2	122.3	197.9	215.6
1476	PA1446_fliP_at	239.2	223.1	334.4	251.6	272.8
1477	PA1447_fliQ_at	184.2	234.5	291.2	230.3	234.9
1478	PA1448_fliR_at	72.6	67.8	91.5	66.2	72.8
1479	PA1449_flhB_at	64.8	51.3	160.8	71.6	61.4
1480	PA1450_at	38.9	40.1	109.7	73.3	78.4
1481	PA1451_at	55.8	112.2	96.1	90.3	73.6
1482	PA1452_flhA_at	134.9	158.7	145.8	171.7	149.2
1483	PA1453_flhF_at	493.2	309.7	318.7	326.7	344.6
1484	PA1454_at	691.8	732.6	848.5	920.7	826.0
1485	PA1455_fliA_at	721.4	1025.9	958.0	781.2	704.4
1486	PA1456_cheY_at	858.8	1063.9	653.6	821.7	929.9
1487	PA1457_cheZ_at	890.3	864.9	810.5	847.0	829.2
1488	PA1458_at	525.6	618.6	749.6	699.0	643.6
1489	PA1459_at	882.3	755.8	970.7	1081.3	1036.4
1490	PA1460_at	327.4	322.2	199.5	197.6	249.3
1491	PA1461_at	182.7	174.5	278.1	217.3	240.0
1492	PA1462_at	476.4	522.5	450.3	519.1	486.7
1493	PA1463_at	441.1	342.8	508.7	568.5	426.0
1494	PA1464_at	1676.1	1676.7	1217.8	1328.3	1305.4
1495	PA1465_at	331.8	431.2	133.3	321.4	311.8
1496	PA1466_at	36.8	28.1	51.8	39.6	54.4
1497	PA1467_at	81.0	68.4	129.5	88.9	99.3
1498	PA1468_at	19.8	31.0	41.3	38.3	37.0
1499	PA1469_at	44.2	33.9	47.4	48.1	49.9
1500	PA1470_at	38.9	23.3	89.9	73.8	69.5
1501	PA1471_at	115.9	140.2	103.0	108.3	113.9
1502	PA1472_at	41.4	57.4	105.0	100.2	104.6
1503	PA1473_at	197.7	173.7	144.9	143.3	126.0
1504	PA1474_at	221.6	326.8	191.3	188.0	212.2
1505	PA1475_ccmA_at	205.6	257.0	401.2	340.1	344.4
1506	PA1476_ccmB_at	127.5	185.1	199.8	212.4	220.2
1507	PA1477_ccmC_at	174.6	157.2	201.2	176.5	179.8
1508	PA1478_at	454.7	421.4	486.0	508.5	503.1
1509	PA1479_ccmE_at	874.3	924.4	730.2	811.6	784.4
1510	PA1480_ccmF_at	324.4	374.3	475.5	482.2	457.2
1511	PA1481_ccmG_at	247.6	317.2	325.6	292.9	255.7
1512	PA1482_ccmH_at	704.6	696.9	599.2	664.4	757.8
1513	PA1483_cycH_at	325.8	343.9	628.2	488.0	443.5
1514	PA1484_at	34.8	41.3	69.6	46.5	60.5
1515	PA1485_at	25.4	33.5	42.6	20.4	44.6
1516	PA1486_at	61.8	29.4	83.5	47.5	49.2
1517	PA1487_at	66.3	62.7	91.9	99.9	68.7
1518	PA1488_at	31.3	42.0	149.8	99.7	91.1
1519	PA1489_at	50.8	54.0	101.7	87.5	56.5
1520	PA1490_at	79.0	81.6	45.3	57.2	71.2
1521	PA1491_at	23.0	32.2	49.3	32.4	33.0
1522	PA1492_at	34.7	41.3	39.5	55.6	55.3
1523	PA1493_cysP_at	1166.3	1649.8	1348.8	1329.9	1376.4
1524	PA1494_at	574.1	473.2	522.6	445.3	432.1
1525	PA1495_at	124.5	120.0	93.6	140.5	128.2

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1526	PA1496_at	26.2	33.4	39.6	33.9	47.9
1527	PA1497_at	35.1	18.5	47.0	39.3	26.7
1528	PA1498_pykF_at	23.0	14.9	32.8	18.3	26.4
1529	PA1499_at	30.0	57.4	61.5	64.3	73.6
1530	PA1500_at	18.5	32.3	31.1	32.4	38.5
1531	PA1501_at	9.4	21.6	6.8	19.7	21.1
1532	PA1502_gcl_at	23.6	25.2	25.7	27.7	29.9
1533	PA1503_at	4.9	18.7	30.5	5.9	18.2
1534	PA1504_at	721.2	667.3	480.7	491.5	545.2
1535	PA1505_moaA2_at	206.1	216.9	101.4	150.4	172.2
1536	PA1506_at	51.0	51.1	74.6	65.7	63.2
1537	PA1507_at	4.9	23.6	51.4	33.5	60.2
1538	PA1508_at	31.8	60.4	125.4	90.8	71.7
1539	PA1509_at	56.4	69.7	101.3	94.8	83.1
1540	PA1510_at	39.6	22.0	26.2	28.0	13.3
1541	PA1511_at	80.7	68.8	52.5	53.0	70.1
1542	PA1513_at	74.0	77.4	86.2	70.9	74.1
1543	PA1514_at	90.7	62.8	34.4	55.2	62.6
1544	PA1515_alc_at	74.7	66.2	48.3	54.2	71.4
1545	PA1516_at	66.5	82.9	67.7	60.7	46.8
1546	PA1517_at	144.9	143.6	125.5	134.7	156.6
1547	PA1518_at	100.5	72.8	28.9	75.7	60.6
1548	PA1519_at	2.2	3.0	12.0	5.9	14.5
1549	PA1520_at	334.1	395.3	245.1	291.5	303.9
1550	PA1521_at	16.2	73.8	95.5	91.0	66.7
1551	PA1522_at	80.9	59.0	98.2	72.5	95.5
1552	PA1523_xdhB_at	42.3	39.3	31.5	17.7	39.4
1553	PA1524_xdhA_at	5.0	35.0	69.8	43.3	55.0
1554	PA1525_at	29.4	44.8	39.9	30.0	61.1
1555	PA1526_at	492.1	443.1	338.9	254.6	286.6
1556	PA1527_at	607.3	599.2	632.6	649.5	563.9
1557	PA1528_zipA_at	1790.2	1834.1	1436.4	1407.8	1335.6
1558	PA1529_lig_at	320.0	279.6	410.9	401.9	412.5
1559	PA1530_at	257.6	317.1	217.7	295.2	233.2
1560	PA1531_at	37.2	33.3	9.4	26.8	18.7
1561	PA1532_dnaX_at	986.8	764.9	1199.9	1085.4	1005.5
1562	PA1533_at	1400.1	1608.0	1397.4	1331.0	1354.9
1563	PA1534_recR_at	183.5	225.0	191.8	260.8	215.2
1564	PA1535_at	45.8	60.4	110.4	56.3	80.9
1565	PA1536_at	54.0	53.1	35.8	50.2	38.4
1566	PA1537_at	4.0	5.1	23.6	5.7	15.1
1567	PA1538_at	28.0	26.9	59.9	44.1	54.2
1568	PA1539_at	56.0	102.8	97.6	80.6	85.3
1569	PA1540_at	74.1	81.9	51.3	31.9	25.2
1570	PA1541_at	244.3	166.7	71.3	55.5	58.0
1571	PA1542_at	74.7	98.1	46.3	39.9	47.3
1572	PA1543_apt_at	265.9	318.2	251.0	412.2	353.6
1573	PA1544_anr_at	731.5	557.7	1347.7	1113.3	948.4
1574	PA1545_at	173.7	269.1	259.1	312.4	256.7
1575	PA1546_hemN_at	28.4	59.5	47.2	59.2	70.9
1576	PA1547_at	98.0	82.4	131.0	118.4	104.0
1577	PA1548_at	94.5	117.6	108.1	88.9	77.4
1578	PA1549_at	86.6	94.5	175.9	165.6	121.7
1579	PA1550_at	296.9	432.1	391.8	411.8	386.2
1580	PA1551_at	182.1	191.8	370.4	293.7	260.4
1581	PA1552_at	1422.9	1771.5	1276.9	1752.8	1654.0
1582	PA1553_at	2685.6	2316.1	5100.2	4090.8	3516.2
1583	PA1554_at	3693.0	2819.7	5358.6	5544.9	4439.2
1584	PA1555_at	83.8	58.3	169.2	113.7	181.4
1585	PA1556_at	77.9	58.6	107.3	70.6	115.8
1586	PA1557_at	43.4	59.2	53.2	26.8	61.4
1587	PA1558_at	85.2	60.8	66.0	47.9	75.9
1588	PA1559_at	383.8	692.3	797.2	838.2	638.2
1589	PA1560_at	201.6	395.3	244.7	291.7	237.1
1590	PA1561_aer_at	907.9	900.7	500.8	485.9	594.5
1591	PA1562_acnA_at	93.9	110.4	53.5	70.0	60.3
1592	PA1563_at	189.6	206.4	250.7	218.9	245.7
1593	PA1564_at	291.3	330.4	276.8	209.8	310.0
1594	PA1565_at	33.4	36.4	46.8	25.3	34.9
1595	PA1566_at	52.7	39.1	47.4	36.5	37.3
1596	PA1567_at	6.3	17.5	38.4	11.1	31.0
1597	PA1568_at	32.5	13.9	18.8	36.3	32.7
1598	PA1569_at	3.9	4.7	7.6	11.5	14.3

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1599	PA1570_at	71.8	46.3	79.1	52.1	75.3
1600	PA1571_at	63.7	84.2	58.9	77.3	59.9
1601	PA1572_at	111.1	112.0	110.3	110.1	106.2
1602	PA1573_at	87.2	89.4	183.2	120.0	107.0
1603	PA1574_at	327.5	590.3	206.3	365.7	415.7
1604	PA1575_at	32.5	46.5	76.0	84.5	62.3
1605	PA1576_at	36.0	56.7	92.1	77.2	76.8
1606	PA1577_at	82.2	108.3	117.2	90.4	119.8
1607	PA1578_at	6.1	30.1	100.9	75.9	71.9
1608	PA1579_at	748.4	939.3	720.1	807.8	918.8
1609	PA1580_gltA_at	5934.0	3172.0	3111.8	3397.2	3425.5
1610	PA1581_sdhC_at	4281.4	3056.8	2870.9	2876.3	2693.1
1611	PA1582_sdhD_at	5835.3	2546.4	3974.8	3238.3	2801.7
1612	PA1583_sdhA_at	5161.6	2512.7	3334.9	2861.0	2508.3
1613	PA1584_sdhB_at	3894.5	2714.3	3410.0	2896.8	2925.4
1614	PA1585_sucA_at	2779.5	1431.0	1625.3	1629.5	1498.1
1615	PA1586_sucB_at	5778.0	2996.1	4110.0	4763.6	3982.0
1616	PA1587_lpdG_at	2101.3	1743.2	2087.6	1811.5	1721.8
1617	PA1588_sucC_at	14015.8	4609.9	6221.1	7728.9	5442.6
1618	PA1589_sucD_at	11229.3	4782.0	8770.6	6744.2	5780.3
1619	PA1590_braB_at	145.0	259.0	203.8	251.3	227.3
1620	PA1591_at	204.1	137.4	363.5	254.7	221.5
1621	PA1592_i_at	3146.0	2659.0	2423.8	2449.6	2172.1
1622	PA1593_at	255.5	253.4	231.9	233.4	273.3
1623	PA1594_at	143.7	106.9	200.4	227.2	200.2
1624	PA1595_at	70.4	92.3	159.5	95.8	90.4
1625	PA1596_htpG_at	3255.4	2200.2	833.6	896.2	794.0
1626	PA1597_at	72.6	76.9	27.1	55.5	48.3
1627	PA1598_at	24.4	4.8	4.5	30.3	13.5
1628	PA1599_at	27.6	37.8	74.4	27.5	51.4
1629	PA1600_at	55.8	57.1	102.5	72.8	66.5
1630	PA1601_at	47.0	46.9	41.2	40.3	50.2
1631	PA1602_at	73.1	53.5	77.7	73.8	70.5
1632	PA1603_at	152.2	96.9	88.6	78.6	81.9
1633	PA1604_at	78.9	92.3	203.8	133.2	114.6
1634	PA1605_at	42.4	38.0	58.4	41.0	59.5
1635	PA1606_at	61.5	80.5	91.6	66.3	85.5
1636	PA1607_at	101.3	110.8	105.5	131.1	119.6
1637	PA1608_at	203.1	274.5	127.6	191.1	197.8
1638	PA1609_fabB_at	1411.3	1071.5	1334.0	1317.0	1295.9
1639	PA1610_fabA_at	3551.6	2322.0	2695.4	2160.6	2053.8
1640	PA1611_at	199.9	224.8	325.4	208.9	165.6
1641	PA1612_at	192.9	227.3	280.1	215.5	184.1
1642	PA1613_at	217.9	181.1	219.9	182.6	194.8
1643	PA1614_gpsA_at	718.7	711.3	378.7	520.0	505.6
1644	PA1615_at	264.3	266.3	184.9	243.9	239.8
1645	PA1616_at	349.0	251.4	285.6	430.8	312.5
1646	PA1617_at	64.8	69.4	84.9	63.7	76.8
1647	PA1618_at	126.7	129.7	178.7	191.8	179.7
1648	PA1619_at	80.1	101.5	168.6	131.2	96.6
1649	PA1620_at	28.1	29.3	83.6	53.2	66.0
1650	PA1621_at	157.7	162.2	234.7	218.7	207.2
1651	PA1622_at	88.7	90.1	160.5	149.5	129.5
1652	PA1623_at	198.5	226.0	148.3	182.9	254.5
1653	PA1624_at	114.4	127.5	143.1	141.2	131.0
1654	PA1625_at	10.7	43.8	87.1	50.3	45.5
1655	PA1626_at	82.9	51.0	87.0	90.5	82.8
1656	PA1627_at	92.8	57.5	100.7	110.8	97.0
1657	PA1628_at	44.2	43.7	58.3	52.9	63.6
1658	PA1629_at	84.0	68.0	84.7	50.1	76.1
1659	PA1630_at	55.0	82.4	96.0	79.2	65.8
1660	PA1631_at	51.6	17.8	24.6	26.5	20.1
1661	PA1632_kdpF_at	1.8	5.6	20.2	18.9	17.6
1662	PA1633_kdpA_at	56.2	26.8	80.9	65.4	60.9
1663	PA1634_kdpB_at	52.1	37.6	67.0	47.6	72.7
1664	PA1635_kdpC_at	26.5	7.9	30.5	6.9	16.4
1665	PA1636_kdpD_at	47.6	52.6	72.5	71.8	57.8
1666	PA1637_kdpE_at	40.5	26.7	11.1	13.9	45.5
1667	PA1638_at	167.2	122.1	123.7	156.4	140.7
1668	PA1639_at	128.1	115.9	178.3	190.5	196.3
1669	PA1640_at	235.2	200.4	202.8	234.8	230.1
1670	PA1641_at	57.5	63.2	75.6	100.4	81.9
1671	PA1642_selD_at	181.1	291.0	182.8	231.4	210.6

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1672	PA1643_at	136.0	123.5	117.2	153.1	132.6
1673	PA1644_at	161.3	159.6	115.3	175.2	142.6
1674	PA1645_at	62.5	107.5	98.0	85.7	105.4
1675	PA1646_at	5.3	28.2	71.8	20.7	48.9
1676	PA1647_at	59.4	36.5	67.9	54.1	57.5
1677	PA1648_at	19.1	42.3	37.4	21.3	28.9
1678	PA1649_at	25.5	40.4	44.8	43.0	28.8
1679	PA1650_at	1.3	30.1	43.3	35.8	49.7
1680	PA1651_at	189.9	216.7	246.9	266.0	270.1
1681	PA1652_at	55.8	34.8	67.0	49.8	90.5
1682	PA1653_at	66.7	64.5	68.1	88.7	126.9
1683	PA1654_at	404.5	353.3	419.1	430.7	404.8
1684	PA1655_at	154.4	233.1	222.4	264.2	208.9
1685	PA1656_at	121.8	151.3	231.6	124.5	160.0
1686	PA1657_at	273.5	327.5	169.5	171.0	187.2
1687	PA1658_at	261.5	275.1	90.5	134.2	139.1
1688	PA1659_at	173.8	172.2	117.7	125.9	108.4
1689	PA1660_at	54.2	74.6	78.1	49.0	69.0
1690	PA1661_at	30.9	90.2	85.6	97.0	107.8
1691	PA1662_at	73.7	74.8	88.1	53.5	72.1
1692	PA1663_at	147.5	137.3	179.7	159.7	134.7
1693	PA1664_at	122.4	156.2	427.1	237.6	264.8
1694	PA1665_at	100.1	155.0	122.5	138.7	128.8
1695	PA1666_at	132.9	173.4	139.2	132.1	157.6
1696	PA1667_at	187.6	304.6	175.1	129.9	203.8
1697	PA1668_at	107.4	154.1	179.6	137.9	144.1
1698	PA1669_at	106.8	184.7	136.9	120.4	139.2
1699	PA1670_stp1_at	93.4	75.2	117.9	89.9	50.5
1700	PA1671_stk1_at	22.4	56.5	55.5	57.9	44.4
1701	PA1672_at	20.7	37.8	55.4	55.9	78.3
1702	PA1673_at	19.7	35.9	29.0	27.9	53.5
1703	PA1674_folE2_at	388.8	528.5	296.0	453.4	473.3
1704	PA1675_at	301.2	303.7	459.1	422.8	383.0
1705	PA1676_at	174.7	105.9	183.0	181.2	153.3
1706	PA1677_at	784.8	466.5	591.8	559.6	563.3
1707	PA1678_at	210.9	245.7	211.0	231.6	244.9
1708	PA1679_at	253.6	228.3	204.5	204.0	145.5
1709	PA1680_at	48.0	45.0	84.4	59.9	46.3
1710	PA1681_aroC_at	637.0	479.1	605.8	602.8	577.1
1711	PA1682_at	114.9	93.4	113.8	79.6	99.4
1712	PA1683_at	137.0	185.6	227.5	204.2	230.2
1713	PA1684_at	405.0	379.3	231.4	312.3	345.2
1714	PA1685_masA_at	143.0	179.3	238.7	215.1	236.1
1715	PA1686_alkA_at	147.8	114.1	209.7	185.1	156.4
1716	PA1687_speE_at	240.6	370.2	158.4	192.9	244.3
1717	PA1688_at	528.4	485.1	769.7	658.8	649.4
1718	PA1689_at	499.3	629.5	544.5	673.7	730.3
1719	PA1690_pscU_at	23.5	26.8	38.9	19.2	27.0
1720	PA1691_pscT_at	57.9	42.4	27.6	30.8	29.4
1721	PA1692_at	206.0	143.9	157.1	106.3	105.1
1722	PA1693_pscR_at	139.3	80.5	83.3	80.7	62.0
1723	PA1694_pscQ_at	266.9	110.5	68.4	58.9	85.3
1724	PA1695_pscP_at	130.7	88.6	53.4	47.0	42.7
1725	PA1696_pscO_at	113.1	72.1	41.9	43.9	30.6
1726	PA1697_at	204.8	120.8	157.8	109.7	106.6
1727	PA1698_popN_at	75.9	56.1	55.6	70.0	56.4
1728	PA1699_at	33.6	28.2	39.2	31.7	44.7
1729	PA1700_at	105.1	70.9	92.8	61.6	74.2
1730	PA1701_at	118.9	98.7	77.3	58.0	87.7
1731	PA1702_i_at	28.2	32.3	47.1	19.5	38.5
1732	PA1703_pcrD_at	133.2	61.0	131.2	73.0	84.7
1733	PA1704_pcrR_at	50.5	27.2	41.8	43.9	33.8
1734	PA1705_pcrG_i_at	100.6	79.0	83.5	50.7	43.5
1735	PA1706_pcrV_at	76.0	42.4	6.1	33.8	31.1
1736	PA1707_pcrH_at	142.2	83.1	88.4	49.6	58.8
1737	PA1708_popB_at	285.9	162.3	103.5	135.5	117.0
1738	PA1709_popD_at	169.6	91.8	132.6	87.1	86.5
1739	PA1710_exsC_at	365.6	208.1	101.9	120.9	144.6
1740	PA1711_at	336.7	174.6	434.9	277.2	234.0
1741	PA1712_exsB_at	107.6	110.2	97.7	98.0	69.7
1742	PA1713_exsA_at	161.2	69.8	84.2	86.5	87.7
1743	PA1714_at	311.7	252.6	170.6	169.7	162.5
1744	PA1715_pscB_at	48.2	46.2	38.2	34.1	29.4

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1745	PA1716_pscC_at	178.1	133.4	159.2	194.6	129.5
1746	PA1717_pscD_at	87.0	74.1	86.5	64.7	71.6
1747	PA1718_pscE_at	253.1	175.9	119.4	116.6	141.2
1748	PA1719_pscF_at	254.3	151.4	83.3	118.3	95.0
1749	PA1720_pscG_at	131.7	62.4	40.2	91.3	71.8
1750	PA1721_pscH_at	61.4	54.9	79.8	59.4	46.9
1751	PA1722_pscI_at	221.2	129.9	191.5	127.9	131.8
1752	PA1723_pscJ_at	78.2	83.2	100.4	79.4	69.5
1753	PA1724_pscK_at	40.7	42.9	48.4	51.9	40.6
1754	PA1725_pscL_at	52.1	25.1	86.1	49.6	35.4
1755	PA1726_bglX_at	957.0	735.9	912.1	863.6	782.9
1756	PA1727_at	243.3	271.5	199.7	212.1	230.6
1757	PA1728_at	48.8	72.3	72.9	64.5	91.7
1758	PA1729_at	100.0	103.7	177.4	124.2	94.8
1759	PA1730_at	38.8	45.2	54.7	70.3	49.4
1760	PA1731_at	55.9	32.0	64.1	48.3	53.4
1761	PA1732_at	66.3	62.2	84.2	60.0	73.5
1762	PA1733_at	79.9	73.4	85.2	61.3	83.9
1763	PA1734_at	61.4	42.8	97.0	105.4	90.3
1764	PA1735_at	31.3	35.6	48.1	62.7	45.9
1765	PA1736_at	34.3	57.1	87.6	48.0	55.9
1766	PA1737_at	83.7	60.6	95.4	90.4	105.7
1767	PA1738_at	67.8	33.8	44.0	58.2	49.5
1768	PA1739_at	48.9	36.2	33.4	44.4	37.3
1769	PA1740_at	19.5	8.5	33.7	5.0	14.6
1770	PA1741_at	151.3	154.6	132.1	175.2	164.4
1771	PA1742_at	652.4	729.3	406.2	372.9	377.1
1772	PA1743_at	7.8	14.0	24.0	16.4	17.7
1773	PA1744_at	56.0	16.8	103.1	36.7	28.0
1774	PA1745_at	22.3	39.2	62.7	46.2	61.1
1775	PA1746_at	102.6	102.9	64.3	55.9	62.3
1776	PA1747_at	49.6	73.9	41.0	67.9	50.2
1777	PA1748_at	177.3	170.8	169.1	251.4	159.9
1778	PA1749_at	224.3	237.9	172.4	199.4	195.5
1779	PA1750_at	1140.5	1207.0	459.0	643.0	777.7
1780	PA1751_at	62.4	65.1	154.3	103.6	111.4
1781	PA1752_at	254.1	235.0	314.2	302.0	265.9
1782	PA1753_at	126.3	155.2	190.4	155.3	151.6
1783	PA1754_cysB_at	755.2	964.9	388.2	563.9	645.8
1784	PA1755_at	102.1	92.7	64.8	131.1	104.8
1785	PA1756_cysH_at	293.4	557.7	413.3	580.8	599.5
1786	PA1757_thrH_at	547.0	461.6	520.8	575.8	557.9
1787	PA1758_pabB_at	144.0	114.5	132.9	117.6	124.4
1788	PA1759_at	205.4	224.3	268.5	259.7	256.9
1789	PA1760_at	156.1	148.4	258.0	194.6	207.4
1790	PA1761_at	336.1	356.4	359.8	342.1	369.0
1791	PA1762_at	51.3	75.4	74.1	76.0	82.3
1792	PA1763_at	70.2	98.0	85.2	113.8	88.9
1793	PA1764_at	23.5	23.9	46.3	34.2	38.1
1794	PA1765_at	31.6	46.9	29.6	32.6	41.2
1795	PA1766_at	623.8	621.9	508.8	573.5	657.0
1796	PA1767_at	917.3	953.6	625.4	706.8	761.2
1797	PA1768_at	1623.4	1499.8	1771.7	1549.7	1503.4
1798	PA1769_at	438.5	451.4	222.1	305.4	337.0
1799	PA1770_ppsA_at	1748.8	1510.2	967.1	1659.9	1674.3
1800	PA1771_at	254.5	202.1	351.1	263.8	261.1
1801	PA1772_at	360.7	537.5	297.1	463.3	457.4
1802	PA1773_at	163.2	148.7	385.1	282.0	246.8
1803	PA1774_at	376.8	505.6	288.6	284.3	341.9
1804	PA1775_at	597.4	730.3	810.8	562.2	550.0
1805	PA1776_at	1566.6	1799.0	3325.8	2561.5	2437.4
1806	PA1777_oprF_at	5033.6	2630.9	3369.1	3440.7	3584.9
1807	PA1778_cobA_at	2.9	4.7	20.3	33.6	31.9
1808	PA1779_at	13.2	8.4	11.8	6.8	16.5
1809	PA1780_nirD_at	1.4	18.1	26.6	27.1	39.4
1810	PA1781_nirB_at	22.8	2.9	37.6	24.4	35.5
1811	PA1782_at	24.2	28.1	116.8	67.3	49.2
1812	PA1783_nasA_at	26.0	10.1	12.3	6.6	18.3
1813	PA1784_at	74.1	86.7	104.5	63.9	56.1
1814	PA1785_at	5.7	7.4	11.1	29.6	23.4
1815	PA1786_at	48.3	56.9	90.2	66.1	93.2
1816	PA1787_acnB_at	4488.7	2803.5	3660.0	3344.8	2931.6
1817	PA1788_at	76.5	126.6	143.9	163.2	145.8

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1818	PA1789_at	123.2	153.5	34.1	94.2	94.2
1819	PA1790_at	106.1	159.5	142.1	132.2	175.9
1820	PA1791_at	666.8	608.3	325.5	409.9	414.0
1821	PA1792_at	489.6	441.0	560.7	545.9	460.9
1822	PA1793_ppiB_at	1534.8	1683.2	2088.6	2087.4	1890.6
1823	PA1794_glnS_at	1044.4	892.7	967.3	974.1	984.9
1824	PA1795_cysS_at	1054.5	1029.1	1107.0	1014.4	975.9
1825	PA1796_fold_at	1113.4	878.9	1193.5	1097.2	960.7
1826	PA1797_at	256.1	241.3	115.3	101.8	115.4
1827	PA1798_at	362.3	301.2	274.1	275.2	264.9
1828	PA1799_at	576.3	400.7	567.6	519.7	548.8
1829	PA1800_tig_at	2292.7	2194.8	2930.4	3169.6	2445.8
1830	PA1801_clpP_at	2259.6	1613.8	1689.2	1845.9	1682.2
1831	PA1802_clpX_at	1456.2	1480.2	1174.4	1132.1	1477.5
1832	PA1803_lon_at	1640.6	1472.2	669.4	736.1	697.3
1833	PA1804_hupB_at	1929.8	1751.2	2577.3	2141.1	1956.0
1834	PA1805_ppiD_at	1117.5	1302.0	1037.7	1250.7	1201.8
1835	PA1806_fabI_at	309.4	219.5	436.5	309.0	280.7
1836	PA1807_at	218.3	261.4	172.8	189.6	181.1
1837	PA1808_at	299.9	259.8	326.2	284.6	277.5
1838	PA1809_at	230.7	224.4	303.3	242.9	255.5
1839	PA1810_at	142.2	80.7	108.5	80.1	101.8
1840	PA1811_at	168.5	148.5	228.6	180.5	170.2
1841	PA1812_mltD_at	1246.9	1250.0	1577.8	1512.6	1314.0
1842	PA1813_at	310.9	331.9	357.7	301.1	303.7
1843	PA1814_at	289.0	236.2	342.7	319.0	302.7
1844	PA1815_rnhA_at	453.8	438.4	544.0	606.1	531.7
1845	PA1816_dnaQ_at	385.4	367.6	325.9	297.8	388.0
1846	PA1817_at	15.7	31.9	24.8	36.8	29.7
1847	PA1818_at	2095.0	1128.2	1221.5	1026.9	1254.1
1848	PA1819_at	219.1	169.8	201.2	119.8	120.5
1849	PA1820_nhaB_at	65.2	47.8	66.9	66.2	86.6
1850	PA1821_at	516.2	374.0	454.9	514.0	562.0
1851	PA1822_at	383.0	274.4	379.3	340.6	367.4
1852	PA1823_at	342.5	249.5	358.0	309.5	336.2
1853	PA1824_at	43.1	84.3	140.1	111.6	123.7
1854	PA1825_at	33.8	42.3	70.8	77.2	85.1
1855	PA1826_at	19.0	21.4	28.8	7.8	19.6
1856	PA1827_at	54.0	32.9	73.4	55.4	45.2
1857	PA1828_at	187.2	184.5	73.4	93.5	145.0
1858	PA1829_at	182.1	181.3	113.6	138.2	129.3
1859	PA1830_at	384.7	578.3	209.2	265.0	360.9
1860	PA1831_at	53.0	82.9	74.0	105.8	100.2
1861	PA1832_at	245.7	264.9	240.7	256.1	314.5
1862	PA1833_at	265.9	168.7	227.1	211.7	260.2
1863	PA1834_at	53.5	66.1	84.0	65.0	78.3
1864	PA1835_at	49.2	63.0	53.5	79.1	63.0
1865	PA1836_at	16.7	39.4	50.7	40.2	50.9
1866	PA1837_at	1203.7	1741.3	1284.1	1429.1	1431.0
1867	PA1838_cysI_at	1667.2	2333.4	2803.9	2962.7	2477.5
1868	PA1839_at	152.5	183.9	149.3	183.2	163.6
1869	PA1840_at	283.1	276.2	231.7	254.5	293.4
1870	PA1841_at	106.1	120.2	69.5	83.7	69.1
1871	PA1842_at	196.7	148.6	99.2	129.5	164.5
1872	PA1843_methH_at	277.5	253.7	344.8	305.3	235.5
1873	PA1844_at	58.5	42.2	63.3	50.1	44.1
1874	PA1845_at	93.8	126.2	67.3	92.3	91.2
1875	PA1846_cti_at	177.9	137.0	195.6	204.2	219.1
1876	PA1847_at	1017.7	991.7	495.5	667.5	617.9
1877	PA1848_at	2.2	16.0	6.2	13.5	19.4
1878	PA1849_at	36.8	26.1	12.2	12.8	47.2
1879	PA1850_at	58.0	43.2	66.1	83.0	58.1
1880	PA1851_at	30.7	27.3	35.3	31.2	33.5
1881	PA1852_at	991.6	897.2	1125.5	1299.8	1082.1
1882	PA1853_at	142.0	116.2	206.5	193.6	215.3
1883	PA1854_at	46.5	45.3	69.7	47.1	59.4
1884	PA1855_r_at	46.7	14.8	33.4	29.3	36.6
1885	PA1856_at	9.0	14.5	13.5	24.5	30.3
1886	PA1857_at	434.5	303.1	412.6	438.5	453.7
1887	PA1858_str_at	85.0	78.7	116.8	104.8	93.3
1888	PA1859_at	74.7	63.7	50.3	46.4	80.8
1889	PA1860_at	65.9	16.8	118.2	70.3	52.6
1890	PA1861_modC_at	113.4	95.3	109.8	103.4	92.8

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1891	PA1862_modB_at	137.4	134.4	141.9	152.3	160.0
1892	PA1863_modA_at	148.2	120.8	69.0	78.0	95.8
1893	PA1864_at	21.0	14.3	40.9	43.0	24.5
1894	PA1865_at	82.7	93.9	75.2	92.2	83.1
1895	PA1866_at	64.2	78.5	116.6	72.4	84.8
1896	PA1867_at	5.4	25.2	51.2	23.7	30.1
1897	PA1868_xqhA_at	31.0	42.0	74.5	51.0	58.8
1898	PA1869_at	590.7	856.0	565.7	549.5	560.1
1899	PA1870_at	31.0	24.3	41.8	43.7	37.1
1900	PA1871_lasA_at	43.9	62.6	98.9	90.4	89.6
1901	PA1872_at	69.2	81.1	86.1	74.3	99.1
1902	PA1873_at	48.0	39.0	70.6	43.9	49.5
1903	PA1874_at	51.4	60.7	74.1	45.8	65.2
1904	PA1875_at	8.5	46.5	31.3	21.5	39.6
1905	PA1876_at	31.7	24.6	52.3	7.9	38.9
1906	PA1877_at	33.7	30.3	53.3	35.4	36.7
1907	PA1878_at	71.4	76.2	76.3	60.5	58.4
1908	PA1879_at	30.3	64.9	106.7	110.1	90.7
1909	PA1880_at	92.3	85.8	100.3	86.2	74.7
1910	PA1881_at	49.9	65.8	82.7	79.4	99.0
1911	PA1882_at	46.7	52.3	47.7	41.5	54.5
1912	PA1883_at	31.1	24.4	61.6	26.9	39.1
1913	PA1884_at	33.4	41.9	47.6	49.3	42.5
1914	PA1885_at	54.3	38.7	67.8	39.0	50.4
1915	PA1886_polB_at	50.0	57.8	72.2	72.9	94.7
1916	PA1887_at	5.4	21.5	4.0	25.8	10.2
1917	PA1888_at	45.6	38.5	62.1	59.3	55.9
1918	PA1889_at	66.4	71.2	61.5	58.2	88.0
1919	PA1890_at	138.6	127.4	261.4	181.9	181.7
1920	PA1891_at	84.2	91.9	154.2	121.3	111.5
1921	PA1892_at	104.2	280.4	267.4	270.8	293.4
1922	PA1893_at	237.7	605.8	563.3	730.7	645.6
1923	PA1894_at	545.1	1151.2	1127.7	1207.3	1206.3
1924	PA1895_at	516.6	957.0	887.6	786.9	892.6
1925	PA1896_at	301.5	642.1	566.4	618.0	655.7
1926	PA1897_at	597.5	1047.7	1346.5	1363.6	1151.5
1927	PA1898_at	139.1	118.8	87.6	105.5	131.4
1928	PA4210_s_at	5.5	33.6	32.8	35.7	41.8
1929	PA4211_g_at	46.2	241.4	145.3	156.3	209.0
1930	PA1901_s_at	37.0	176.2	327.8	252.7	290.9
1931	PA1902_s_at	22.6	71.3	15.2	51.2	61.4
1932	PA1903_s_at	58.7	135.6	130.6	167.6	140.2
1933	PA1904_s_at	23.6	103.5	77.4	59.8	62.0
1934	PA1905_s_at	53.3	232.7	166.7	134.3	173.1
1935	PA1906_at	33.8	34.7	55.0	33.4	60.2
1936	PA1907_at	28.5	17.9	28.6	16.4	27.6
1937	PA1908_at	5.9	6.0	14.8	35.2	16.5
1938	PA1909_at	38.6	10.7	11.8	16.7	23.2
1939	PA1910_at	3.1	23.7	55.5	32.4	56.9
1940	PA1911_at	21.5	30.4	109.6	80.7	63.7
1941	PA1912_at	83.3	85.5	120.2	131.4	96.3
1942	PA1913_at	263.8	290.7	301.9	302.9	219.2
1943	PA1914_at	3.4	3.1	7.9	3.4	17.6
1944	PA1915_at	63.2	35.7	74.7	20.3	30.9
1945	PA1916_at	2.9	13.6	35.4	29.4	44.4
1946	PA1917_at	5.6	11.4	19.9	21.6	16.7
1947	PA1918_at	28.4	18.2	35.5	36.8	28.5
1948	PA1919_at	18.5	3.5	29.6	21.9	17.6
1949	PA1920_at	29.2	22.1	62.5	35.7	35.6
1950	PA1921_at	25.1	2.5	19.4	12.1	17.4
1951	PA1922_at	26.0	17.8	25.7	19.0	23.5
1952	PA1923_at	47.5	28.1	41.2	28.8	38.6
1953	PA1924_at	6.0	14.5	12.0	6.5	39.9
1954	PA1925_at	9.2	18.8	15.4	15.3	27.5
1955	PA1926_at	202.6	250.5	221.6	267.2	260.8
1956	PA1927_metE_at	29.5	21.5	5.2	19.6	19.4
1957	PA1928_rimJ_at	66.7	99.8	154.8	138.7	122.4
1958	PA1929_i_at	48.0	50.1	112.4	71.9	86.6
1959	PA1930_at	21.2	42.0	52.5	35.5	34.8
1960	PA1931_at	14.1	11.8	60.5	19.0	21.2
1961	PA1932_at	5.0	19.4	50.6	47.6	52.5
1962	PA1933_at	14.1	15.5	24.3	39.5	20.4
1963	PA1934_at	41.4	41.6	73.9	83.9	74.5

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1964	PA1935_at	42.0	39.4	70.5	54.1	69.0
1965	PA1936_at	24.6	26.9	37.1	5.6	28.5
1966	PA1939_at	256.3	267.4	299.3	269.7	270.2
1967	PA1940_at	305.9	259.4	302.3	241.0	268.9
1968	PA1941_at	388.6	330.5	318.3	257.0	247.0
1969	PA1942_at	101.6	163.5	41.8	39.5	47.6
1970	PA1943_at	122.6	134.0	150.6	100.3	99.6
1971	PA1944_at	46.8	75.5	97.5	79.5	74.7
1972	PA1945_at	38.3	39.9	46.8	42.1	55.1
1973	PA1946_rbsB_at	49.8	80.1	72.4	78.9	87.0
1974	PA1947_rbsA_at	38.2	34.8	60.8	40.9	52.6
1975	PA1948_rbsC_at	36.1	59.5	44.3	74.2	57.4
1976	PA1949_rbsR_at	198.4	193.5	326.6	232.1	212.0
1977	PA1950_rbsK_at	166.4	186.0	187.2	200.7	182.6
1978	PA1951_at	2.3	7.1	1.9	3.0	17.6
1979	PA1952_at	27.9	21.4	35.7	24.1	25.4
1980	PA1953_at	3.7	1.9	5.5	4.1	3.5
1981	PA1954_at	3.4	19.3	33.0	34.6	34.4
1982	PA1955_at	2.9	4.4	22.6	1.8	12.0
1983	PA1956_at	29.4	16.0	45.1	10.7	30.0
1984	PA1957_at	54.0	63.9	69.8	109.0	77.5
1985	PA1958_at	133.0	119.4	204.0	154.9	158.7
1986	PA1959_bacA_at	248.5	190.9	158.7	137.1	241.1
1987	PA1960_at	68.1	59.7	99.0	100.2	74.4
1988	PA1961_at	14.8	33.0	64.4	51.5	51.8
1989	PA1962_at	2.5	30.8	19.0	23.5	30.3
1990	PA1963_at	141.3	161.9	27.8	79.2	114.7
1991	PA1964_at	393.8	400.2	441.3	411.2	371.0
1992	PA1965_at	74.3	92.7	138.0	108.8	113.5
1993	PA1966_at	109.2	116.2	154.9	131.6	129.6
1994	PA1967_at	84.1	82.6	70.3	119.9	96.8
1995	PA1968_at	90.9	117.2	135.0	117.4	97.8
1996	PA1969_at	165.8	221.0	168.1	210.1	226.1
1997	PA1970_at	15.4	36.7	52.1	39.6	43.3
1998	PA1971_braZ_at	59.8	48.8	38.3	54.4	67.1
1999	PA1972_at	3.7	1.2	6.6	2.9	17.7
2000	PA1973_pqqF_at	85.9	35.4	64.5	78.8	67.8
2001	PA1974_at	31.3	13.2	13.7	17.8	27.7
2002	PA1975_at	18.8	31.5	33.5	21.1	34.9
2003	PA1976_at	32.5	15.3	51.2	43.7	33.7
2004	PA1977_at	45.3	34.2	46.6	11.9	39.0
2005	PA1978_at	289.2	109.3	173.4	129.0	158.2
2006	PA1979_at	14.6	3.6	15.2	12.1	8.4
2007	PA1980_at	11.1	3.8	26.2	7.2	16.4
2008	PA1981_at	5.1	3.3	32.1	7.1	32.1
2009	PA1982_exaA_at	12.6	17.1	5.0	8.2	19.1
2010	PA1983_exaB_at	3.6	1.3	34.5	7.5	15.9
2011	PA1984_s_at	3835.5	2976.7	2642.7	2948.7	2862.6
2012	PA1985_pqqA_at	70.1	35.6	48.6	41.0	50.9
2013	PA1986_pqqB_at	122.0	62.8	110.0	81.0	103.1
2014	PA1987_pqqC_at	137.1	68.8	116.6	54.9	73.9
2015	PA1988_pqqD_at	100.1	99.0	84.1	89.1	106.7
2016	PA1989_pqqE_at	152.8	68.4	92.9	61.6	78.6
2017	PA1990_at	44.9	23.2	48.2	44.2	50.9
2018	PA1991_at	86.6	76.7	92.8	114.5	110.1
2019	PA1992_at	80.2	57.2	73.8	49.8	74.1
2020	PA1993_at	31.7	30.5	22.7	64.3	28.9
2021	PA1994_at	67.0	81.8	66.3	49.5	72.8
2022	PA1995_i_at	150.8	150.6	311.4	285.8	285.4
2023	PA1996_ppiC1_at	156.1	174.0	141.7	223.0	157.2
2024	PA1997_at	87.0	67.4	87.3	81.9	88.3
2025	PA1998_at	50.0	65.1	59.7	52.4	57.4
2026	PA1999_at	4590.8	3416.7	2854.2	4006.2	3512.2
2027	PA2000_at	4208.8	2598.2	3957.1	3388.0	2976.5
2028	PA2001_atoB_at	2787.0	2290.2	2523.4	2668.1	2131.3
2029	PA2002_at	361.0	207.3	289.7	274.8	328.4
2030	PA2003_bdHA_at	69.6	87.8	244.4	199.6	142.4
2031	PA2004_at	33.1	38.8	82.8	48.1	90.3
2032	PA2005_at	93.7	95.4	102.1	71.5	97.1
2033	PA2006_at	337.5	321.1	520.5	509.0	514.3
2034	PA2007_maiA_i_at	1155.5	968.2	626.1	869.3	885.3
2035	PA2008_fahA_at	3513.4	2115.0	3606.2	3089.8	2801.6
2036	PA2009_hmgA_at	2334.0	1647.0	1841.5	1709.0	1540.4

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2037	PA2010_at	131.6	96.6	81.9	68.0	87.7
2038	PA2011_at	481.9	547.0	864.8	852.6	995.8
2039	PA2012_at	363.3	421.4	1085.6	714.2	827.6
2040	PA2013_at	607.7	642.7	946.5	966.3	976.5
2041	PA2014_at	757.6	908.0	2013.0	1684.2	1583.3
2042	PA2015_at	2429.2	2448.8	3688.3	3277.1	3118.1
2043	PA2016_at	1080.7	1356.2	980.5	1113.9	1424.9
2044	PA2017_at	44.0	48.6	54.5	58.5	35.3
2045	PA2018_at	161.1	133.9	101.5	88.2	98.3
2046	PA2019_at	166.7	217.6	304.4	237.2	252.7
2047	PA2020_at	120.5	127.4	187.1	170.9	172.4
2048	PA2021_at	30.3	23.9	40.1	24.4	31.3
2049	PA2022_at	40.5	26.0	48.8	25.6	35.5
2050	PA2023_galU_at	1182.2	1366.4	1226.8	1194.9	1252.8
2051	PA2024_at	34.8	42.4	29.2	31.7	32.4
2052	PA2025_gor_at	199.8	237.2	210.5	239.9	342.2
2053	PA2026_at	30.7	37.7	63.9	35.0	57.1
2054	PA2027_at	45.2	45.5	36.6	31.5	59.7
2055	PA2028_at	48.4	51.5	56.5	63.5	55.4
2056	PA2029_i_at	78.7	97.6	77.8	60.8	72.8
2057	PA2030_at	56.5	88.5	105.7	91.3	100.2
2058	PA2031_i_at	153.6	180.2	323.8	386.5	346.0
2059	PA2032_at	44.3	56.9	19.1	42.0	29.0
2060	PA2033_at	18.4	35.6	67.8	46.1	65.9
2061	PA2034_at	3.1	13.5	25.7	26.4	34.0
2062	PA2035_at	48.2	34.7	37.3	33.7	30.0
2063	PA2036_at	9.8	16.2	33.4	28.5	3.0
2064	PA2037_at	35.7	56.6	57.8	41.7	53.3
2065	PA2038_at	137.3	128.5	108.0	122.6	140.4
2066	PA2039_at	129.7	140.0	122.5	105.3	106.1
2067	PA2041_at	257.0	278.4	138.2	170.9	168.6
2068	PA2042_at	703.8	756.2	609.0	731.0	747.8
2069	PA2043_at	17.5	50.8	74.1	56.5	53.8
2070	PA2044_at	154.7	206.1	294.8	273.9	249.0
2071	PA2045_at	435.9	446.1	339.5	279.4	317.3
2072	PA2046_at	15.7	1.4	17.7	5.9	16.6
2073	PA2047_at	46.6	69.9	64.8	78.1	65.4
2074	PA2048_at	25.7	18.7	42.0	35.0	29.5
2075	PA2049_at	125.1	74.7	142.0	109.1	102.2
2076	PA2050_at	6.6	62.9	42.8	43.3	46.5
2077	PA2051_at	8.8	18.2	39.2	21.8	30.0
2078	PA2052_cynS_at	65.8	49.4	55.6	58.2	40.4
2079	PA2053_cynT_at	37.4	18.0	36.7	42.5	34.3
2080	PA2054_cynR_at	48.5	28.4	56.3	42.0	32.9
2081	PA2055_at	20.3	21.9	30.6	22.8	31.4
2082	PA2056_at	26.3	20.7	38.4	32.1	28.2
2083	PA2057_at	8.8	3.7	3.6	2.7	6.5
2084	PA2058_at	6.0	3.4	22.5	20.1	21.3
2085	PA2059_at	43.1	15.8	33.4	32.7	18.1
2086	PA2060_at	34.8	12.2	14.9	11.4	40.8
2087	PA2061_at	11.8	2.6	11.6	4.8	13.2
2088	PA2062_at	97.6	146.7	185.9	184.9	171.8
2089	PA2063_at	135.4	151.8	176.5	167.0	151.1
2090	PA2064_pcoB_at	3.3	27.7	54.5	56.2	31.3
2091	PA2065_pcoA_at	3.5	16.1	35.9	21.3	21.7
2092	PA2066_at	12.4	74.9	160.3	104.9	91.9
2093	PA2067_at	51.3	76.2	131.4	99.9	85.7
2094	PA2068_at	23.2	27.7	49.5	32.5	44.4
2095	PA2069_at	69.3	68.8	158.0	77.3	82.2
2096	PA2070_at	2.2	1.1	24.5	4.5	21.1
2097	PA2071_fusA2_at	58.7	64.9	76.6	83.8	59.0
2098	PA2072_at	25.1	12.4	34.8	20.8	24.6
2099	PA2073_at	10.9	1.3	31.7	9.9	19.8
2100	PA2074_at	29.2	29.0	70.0	35.3	64.8
2101	PA2075_at	18.6	8.0	22.8	50.1	58.6
2102	PA2076_at	163.5	222.1	163.0	161.2	215.3
2103	PA2077_at	21.2	9.9	39.0	21.5	25.4
2104	PA2078_at	4.9	13.8	35.4	4.7	25.5
2105	PA2079_at	54.0	109.5	48.5	69.0	70.2
2106	PA2080_at	529.6	737.8	557.8	611.4	603.5
2107	PA2081_at	248.2	343.2	333.7	326.0	372.0
2108	PA2082_at	51.3	74.6	53.2	54.0	51.2
2109	PA2083_at	74.0	131.3	70.7	100.0	119.6

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2110	PA2084_at	26.0	32.2	68.0	45.0	45.8
2111	PA2085_at	19.4	25.1	42.0	30.4	33.0
2112	PA2086_at	38.9	36.5	46.1	31.6	41.7
2113	PA2087_at	5.0	20.6	46.9	25.2	20.0
2114	PA2088_at	4.0	3.7	5.5	5.4	4.9
2115	PA2089_at	34.1	32.9	58.5	42.4	33.7
2116	PA2090_at	33.0	24.0	42.1	37.6	26.2
2117	PA2091_at	5.7	12.4	15.7	6.9	24.4
2118	PA2092_at	6.2	10.4	57.5	30.8	29.0
2119	PA2093_at	32.5	24.5	61.3	40.0	44.7
2120	PA2094_at	66.0	32.2	56.8	54.4	48.0
2121	PA2095_at	39.6	21.7	40.3	20.8	27.5
2122	PA2096_at	14.6	27.4	14.7	10.4	19.5
2123	PA2097_at	38.1	22.2	32.5	27.2	25.3
2124	PA2098_at	6.6	24.0	85.5	60.8	49.2
2125	PA2099_at	9.9	16.9	56.8	7.8	30.7
2126	PA2100_at	58.5	37.9	53.4	40.8	38.3
2127	PA2101_at	20.6	13.7	6.1	5.7	21.9
2128	PA2102_at	40.6	25.7	16.6	22.4	28.1
2129	PA2103_at	63.9	81.3	89.2	98.0	88.7
2130	PA2104_at	53.5	67.9	75.3	64.2	81.0
2131	PA2105_at	87.4	83.9	101.1	82.2	76.3
2132	PA2106_at	5.4	59.5	44.3	53.7	67.5
2133	PA2107_at	52.3	43.1	113.4	85.5	68.2
2134	PA2108_at	4.8	26.6	58.8	47.4	37.6
2135	PA2109_at	1625.1	1232.2	1424.3	1424.6	1266.9
2136	PA2110_at	3301.0	2051.0	3488.9	3467.6	2655.7
2137	PA2111_at	6114.2	3919.7	2844.2	3612.9	3079.6
2138	PA2112_at	7537.4	4103.2	6505.4	5111.2	4462.7
2139	PA2113_at	5836.4	2992.5	5384.0	4412.2	3863.8
2140	PA2114_at	3220.2	1901.3	3237.0	2888.0	2532.4
2141	PA2115_at	131.6	146.1	206.5	202.1	208.9
2142	PA2116_at	848.8	687.1	839.7	963.9	1038.5
2143	PA2117_at	109.3	150.2	113.3	93.1	127.9
2144	PA2118_ada_at	63.7	55.6	60.2	74.4	61.7
2145	PA2119_at	3.0	15.0	24.9	15.6	22.8
2146	PA2120_at	15.0	16.1	45.6	23.1	26.3
2147	PA2121_at	47.2	31.1	37.9	56.1	42.5
2148	PA2122_at	139.3	144.2	71.8	63.0	87.6
2149	PA2123_at	161.9	114.8	82.0	110.2	95.7
2150	PA2124_at	15.2	16.4	40.7	14.6	20.9
2151	PA2125_at	25.4	25.9	69.4	44.0	34.3
2152	PA2126_at	55.6	73.6	120.4	90.9	75.7
2153	PA2127_at	91.9	123.6	233.0	132.8	159.1
2154	PA2128_at	87.7	60.1	85.4	75.5	62.9
2155	PA2129_at	11.9	17.0	35.3	28.1	18.7
2156	PA2130_at	13.1	21.9	11.5	26.7	18.8
2157	PA2131_at	2.8	17.5	52.2	56.1	25.4
2158	PA2132_at	22.5	20.0	40.7	28.3	48.0
2159	PA2133_at	3.0	2.5	2.6	4.7	7.7
2160	PA2134_at	58.6	55.8	85.7	71.9	43.7
2161	PA2135_at	44.7	11.1	25.6	23.6	24.5
2162	PA2136_at	5.7	1.9	5.6	4.4	8.6
2163	PA2137_at	3.5	11.2	22.0	5.0	23.7
2164	PA2138_at	4.7	13.4	42.8	29.3	33.2
2165	PA2139_r_at	1.4	1.0	13.5	1.8	16.7
2166	PA2140_at	2.9	15.0	25.6	18.2	20.9
2167	PA2141_at	13.4	2.6	21.9	4.4	9.8
2168	PA2142_at	19.5	11.0	48.2	31.8	24.4
2169	PA2143_at	4.8	1.5	6.6	2.3	11.7
2170	PA2144_glgP_at	7.3	11.8	30.9	28.7	25.6
2171	PA2145_at	22.1	24.5	50.1	34.6	31.1
2172	PA2146_i_at	43.4	23.5	36.8	24.2	33.9
2173	PA2147_katE_at	7.3	4.0	6.4	14.6	6.0
2174	PA2148_at	14.0	15.2	45.3	14.9	31.7
2175	PA2149_at	38.1	24.6	82.0	73.2	52.3
2176	PA2150_at	1.3	6.0	28.8	13.8	33.8
2177	PA2151_at	1.8	1.8	3.1	3.2	12.1
2178	PA2152_at	25.3	27.9	40.2	80.4	44.7
2179	PA2153_glgB_at	3.5	20.2	4.5	7.8	18.7
2180	PA2154_at	2.6	11.5	33.6	4.2	19.3
2181	PA2155_at	3.4	12.1	15.9	2.4	2.9
2182	PA2156_at	0.9	1.6	4.2	8.4	9.9

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2183	PA2157_at	39.7	21.7	38.3	27.7	35.4
2184	PA2158_at	8.6	5.9	33.3	15.3	22.1
2185	PA2159_at	21.6	23.4	37.3	29.0	30.2
2186	PA2160_at	35.8	31.9	24.0	21.9	32.8
2187	PA2161_at	7.4	3.6	2.5	7.1	1.9
2188	PA2162_at	1.7	17.1	34.1	25.4	40.6
2189	PA2163_at	19.4	25.0	38.4	35.5	31.9
2190	PA2164_at	36.6	22.4	33.1	40.9	36.3
2191	PA2165_at	15.4	19.2	11.5	18.9	27.1
2192	PA2166_at	34.0	24.0	28.9	40.0	40.0
2193	PA2167_at	6.3	2.2	32.0	12.9	17.0
2194	PA2168_at	25.9	23.9	63.3	41.6	54.9
2195	PA2169_at	6.0	33.9	51.6	38.5	31.5
2196	PA2170_at	15.7	10.4	19.1	18.1	19.8
2197	PA2171_at	19.3	17.5	19.1	29.0	21.5
2198	PA2172_at	22.5	20.2	54.6	27.9	30.4
2199	PA2173_at	27.0	18.6	36.0	22.9	28.3
2200	PA2174_at	17.2	22.5	47.8	27.3	34.0
2201	PA2175_at	38.1	28.7	37.6	35.7	27.4
2202	PA2176_at	28.8	1.8	8.2	5.9	17.2
2203	PA2177_at	39.6	53.0	73.8	74.8	57.9
2204	PA2178_at	5.7	22.6	18.4	30.2	29.2
2205	PA2179_at	4.3	1.2	13.6	2.9	5.6
2206	PA2180_at	13.6	28.0	59.9	29.9	27.6
2207	PA2181_at	16.7	10.3	37.4	7.9	17.4
2208	PA2182_at	19.2	18.5	18.8	13.7	14.9
2209	PA2183_at	33.1	1.6	1.5	1.7	13.1
2210	PA2184_at	12.9	21.6	47.3	35.4	44.2
2211	PA2185_at	2.1	4.6	32.2	14.2	13.4
2212	PA2186_r_at	30.2	49.8	87.3	61.5	70.7
2213	PA2187_at	4.3	3.3	11.9	19.1	23.1
2214	PA2188_at	1.5	11.3	23.3	19.2	17.1
2215	PA2189_at	26.2	16.6	33.5	25.3	16.0
2216	PA2190_at	5.8	20.2	5.2	3.8	14.4
2217	PA2191_exoY_at	28.2	25.9	19.3	10.8	32.4
2218	PA2192_at	6.1	1.8	4.5	20.2	24.3
2219	PA2193_hcnA_at	380.9	957.1	286.8	403.2	550.0
2220	PA2194_hcnB_at	629.5	680.0	669.2	609.2	789.6
2221	PA2195_hcnC_at	164.8	454.4	397.6	389.4	358.5
2222	PA2196_at	59.2	71.7	85.5	63.8	46.9
2223	PA2197_at	148.8	86.1	152.5	147.6	135.0
2224	PA2198_at	72.6	74.6	97.5	72.1	99.9
2225	PA2199_at	88.0	147.7	154.7	149.9	143.4
2226	PA2200_at	66.4	45.3	71.0	30.8	42.4
2227	PA2201_at	100.8	68.7	71.2	90.3	113.1
2228	PA2202_at	93.4	253.0	185.8	188.9	145.9
2229	PA2203_at	118.3	351.6	272.4	311.8	301.4
2230	PA2204_at	739.0	2171.7	1882.9	2252.6	1861.1
2231	PA2205_at	48.6	65.8	47.5	17.2	68.7
2232	PA2206_at	59.8	59.1	57.7	46.3	46.7
2233	PA2207_at	1.5	13.7	29.1	26.9	31.2
2234	PA2208_at	11.1	2.3	18.3	3.9	25.5
2235	PA2209_at	5.9	10.2	29.6	29.0	20.9
2236	PA2210_at	36.4	31.8	78.1	40.7	58.8
2237	PA2211_at	8.1	17.5	32.9	33.2	28.7
2238	PA2212_at	8.5	48.1	115.3	88.5	86.8
2239	PA2213_at	17.3	9.0	19.8	4.2	15.7
2240	PA2214_at	9.0	1.8	25.7	14.8	34.7
2241	PA2215_at	3.9	11.4	20.7	4.8	36.3
2242	PA2216_at	42.6	40.0	81.7	56.9	43.9
2243	PA2217_at	7.9	14.9	4.3	22.7	17.9
2244	PA2218_at	73.4	46.6	55.5	51.1	64.2
2245	PA2219_opdE_at	30.5	12.7	58.5	44.3	41.3
2246	PA2220_at	51.1	64.2	53.0	56.1	76.7
2247	PA2221_at	12.0	15.6	5.3	3.6	6.0
2248	PA2222_at	40.5	23.0	43.0	20.2	39.6
2249	PA2223_at	55.1	58.8	45.5	29.0	36.6
2250	PA2224_at	11.6	3.3	12.5	6.4	13.5
2251	PA2225_at	9.7	20.6	44.9	45.7	34.5
2252	PA2226_at	14.8	30.4	30.1	24.1	20.9
2253	PA2227_at	12.6	20.0	33.7	21.7	26.3
2254	PA2228_at	2.1	6.0	15.3	22.5	10.7
2255	PA2229_at	108.2	127.6	122.2	114.9	125.2

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2256	PA2230_at	176.5	135.4	158.0	148.3	152.4
2257	PA2231_at	498.6	582.9	463.1	453.1	438.0
2258	PA2232_at	648.8	464.8	421.4	520.1	560.9
2259	PA2233_at	482.7	438.6	348.3	405.8	348.5
2260	PA2234_at	1168.6	792.0	906.7	1198.6	1117.5
2261	PA2235_at	760.2	647.1	802.5	783.6	753.6
2262	PA2236_at	468.0	520.5	440.5	560.0	516.2
2263	PA2237_at	281.1	348.2	483.5	382.0	373.3
2264	PA2238_at	269.5	236.1	183.8	198.6	190.7
2265	PA2239_at	220.7	224.7	213.7	236.9	230.3
2266	PA2240_at	160.8	149.7	219.4	197.0	206.8
2267	PA2241_at	62.9	60.3	107.2	101.6	101.6
2268	PA2242_at	338.5	251.7	312.7	284.6	303.6
2269	PA2243_at	65.2	43.5	68.2	60.5	66.4
2270	PA2244_at	2.4	15.2	7.0	8.5	28.9
2271	PA2245_at	9.2	9.1	17.3	6.3	11.3
2272	PA2246_bkdR_at	63.5	43.8	34.5	73.1	71.3
2273	PA2247_bkdA1_at	3983.6	2402.4	2920.9	2880.8	2890.4
2274	PA2248_bkdA2_at	2570.4	1801.8	2632.7	2659.9	2105.6
2275	PA2249_bkdB_at	1939.2	1860.3	1320.2	1723.3	1596.9
2276	PA2250_lpdV_at	1355.2	1587.3	1879.6	1993.8	1720.9
2277	PA2251_at	34.5	30.4	37.2	29.3	51.5
2278	PA2252_at	131.3	235.1	311.2	283.4	296.9
2279	PA2253_ansA_at	149.7	185.8	317.1	308.1	293.6
2280	PA2254_pvcA_at	39.0	11.5	48.3	5.9	23.2
2281	PA2255_pvcB_at	4.4	10.2	16.7	13.2	23.6
2282	PA2256_pvcC_at	32.6	22.3	40.7	36.2	25.6
2283	PA2257_pvcD_at	17.3	10.9	47.7	17.3	38.9
2284	PA2258_ptxR_at	7.2	9.6	15.8	6.1	14.8
2285	PA2259_ptxS_at	490.1	557.8	322.8	343.4	373.8
2286	PA2260_at	290.0	263.7	333.4	334.4	286.5
2287	PA2261_at	98.8	102.2	93.8	107.1	107.1
2288	PA2262_at	92.1	100.9	92.6	94.3	116.6
2289	PA2263_at	240.5	201.0	298.1	233.2	165.1
2290	PA2264_at	198.6	331.3	195.4	235.9	231.8
2291	PA2265_at	277.3	468.5	244.5	308.6	301.1
2292	PA2266_at	127.8	242.9	445.6	202.8	215.8
2293	PA2267_at	121.5	55.9	152.4	172.3	112.3
2294	PA2268_at	59.6	35.7	33.7	49.1	45.0
2295	PA2269_at	23.7	43.7	85.9	96.5	65.6
2296	PA2270_at	348.7	274.0	285.4	342.5	285.9
2297	PA2271_i_at	140.4	126.2	170.8	127.9	114.5
2298	PA2272_pbpC_at	74.3	78.1	70.7	39.4	55.9
2299	PA2273_at	27.7	54.1	38.3	42.5	55.6
2300	PA2274_at	84.3	53.6	109.0	92.8	74.4
2301	PA2275_at	15.1	20.7	40.4	11.1	34.1
2302	PA2276_at	5.4	24.3	41.2	24.3	40.7
2303	PA2277_arsR_at	58.4	54.8	103.5	78.0	46.7
2304	PA2278_arsB_at	47.2	33.1	88.8	72.0	69.8
2305	PA2279_arsC_at	104.0	73.6	100.2	74.2	76.7
2306	PA2280_at	41.8	25.5	54.4	48.4	59.6
2307	PA2281_at	91.4	93.5	139.3	125.7	115.3
2308	PA2282_at	20.6	30.9	52.1	74.4	40.0
2309	PA2283_at	18.0	5.2	13.4	8.4	27.7
2310	PA2284_at	3.6	18.0	35.7	3.8	30.3
2311	PA2285_at	44.6	70.2	52.2	75.9	70.1
2312	PA2286_at	39.2	40.4	87.8	63.6	83.2
2313	PA2287_at	21.4	35.8	17.5	24.7	34.5
2314	PA2288_r_at	92.6	60.0	48.1	46.0	22.1
2315	PA2289_at	66.7	98.3	60.1	75.5	72.1
2316	PA2290_gcd_at	644.6	374.9	381.7	529.9	491.1
2317	PA3186_oprB_s_at	2091.7	2167.2	1835.7	1936.2	2084.9
2318	PA2292_at	29.1	18.0	35.3	42.9	40.6
2319	PA2293_at	4.6	6.8	19.3	5.1	15.6
2320	PA2294_at	6.6	48.6	53.6	31.7	58.0
2321	PA2295_at	1.9	26.5	42.0	29.4	22.5
2322	PA2296_at	22.0	26.1	33.1	22.3	38.3
2323	PA2297_at	89.2	78.1	103.8	79.6	89.4
2324	PA2298_at	51.6	78.0	153.4	109.6	101.3
2325	PA2299_at	46.0	47.8	59.8	66.5	64.0
2326	PA2300_chiC_at	42.2	57.8	103.0	61.5	67.8
2327	PA2301_at	99.1	128.3	219.4	168.9	165.4
2328	PA2302_at	136.9	117.0	123.2	115.3	129.6

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2329	PA2303_at	121.0	117.0	82.8	82.8	86.1
2330	PA2304_at	215.9	199.6	247.1	278.6	201.3
2331	PA2305_at	306.8	220.0	342.7	301.2	274.9
2332	PA2306_at	260.7	276.3	304.6	361.8	378.5
2333	PA2307_at	1.6	14.0	25.6	30.8	23.3
2334	PA2308_at	15.3	19.5	70.7	25.3	15.5
2335	PA2309_at	12.6	32.8	42.6	20.7	36.1
2336	PA2310_at	5.9	34.9	39.8	29.8	44.9
2337	PA2311_r_at	128.3	249.3	115.6	155.7	149.3
2338	PA2312_at	16.7	79.8	102.4	100.4	80.2
2339	PA2313_at	4.1	25.1	15.4	24.2	18.2
2340	PA2314_at	35.8	4.3	41.2	18.3	20.1
2341	PA2315_at	27.5	9.1	47.7	28.8	40.8
2342	PA2316_at	45.1	37.8	59.9	41.7	34.6
2343	PA2317_at	57.4	43.9	51.4	45.5	35.1
2344	PA2318_at	55.5	52.9	19.7	47.8	32.0
2345	PA2320_gntR_at	453.0	346.3	224.9	249.8	387.3
2346	PA2321_at	3944.4	1766.9	864.4	1185.7	1336.9
2347	PA2322_at	2948.7	1505.2	1153.4	1237.4	1380.4
2348	PA2323_at	2284.2	1351.3	1444.1	1351.4	1203.0
2349	PA2324_at	45.1	25.1	4.2	33.7	31.8
2350	PA2325_at	41.6	39.7	62.9	54.2	34.2
2351	PA2326_at	9.3	20.0	38.1	40.2	30.7
2352	PA2327_at	43.4	27.0	112.7	67.4	74.4
2353	PA2328_at	79.3	95.7	121.4	109.6	131.9
2354	PA2329_at	47.7	89.1	215.9	163.3	143.3
2355	PA2330_at	33.8	99.2	205.3	206.5	195.5
2356	PA2331_at	87.6	218.5	498.3	481.4	430.3
2357	PA2332_at	80.6	101.4	133.1	123.6	108.3
2358	PA2333_at	36.3	31.5	96.3	67.4	70.2
2359	PA2334_at	22.1	77.0	112.5	115.0	83.9
2360	PA2335_at	23.6	12.2	4.7	3.1	13.0
2361	PA2336_at	6.1	23.6	58.6	11.6	35.0
2362	PA2337_mtlR_at	28.8	50.9	27.3	36.5	33.8
2363	PA2338_at	36.8	36.6	58.1	53.4	42.7
2364	PA2339_at	25.4	20.2	52.0	35.9	34.1
2365	PA2340_at	31.6	11.2	28.6	23.7	30.2
2366	PA2341_at	31.6	34.3	59.2	53.1	57.3
2367	PA2342_mtlD_at	28.8	20.5	36.4	33.3	33.7
2368	PA2343_mtlY_at	5.2	17.1	52.1	28.6	27.1
2369	PA2344_mtlZ_at	116.3	89.5	127.8	134.9	120.8
2370	PA2345_at	78.7	79.4	109.7	108.7	94.5
2371	PA2346_at	7.0	12.4	13.7	7.8	19.7
2372	PA2347_at	8.2	33.7	19.3	29.1	40.0
2373	PA2348_at	29.4	12.7	11.5	7.7	26.9
2374	PA2349_at	50.4	41.7	87.3	56.1	50.9
2375	PA2350_at	10.5	22.0	39.9	10.3	43.9
2376	PA2351_at	14.6	25.3	66.4	41.8	31.5
2377	PA2352_at	97.0	94.7	96.0	154.8	104.1
2378	PA2353_at	45.5	47.1	55.1	35.2	36.5
2379	PA2354_at	10.8	29.6	39.0	42.5	32.8
2380	PA2355_at	8.0	17.9	12.0	9.4	43.1
2381	PA2356_msuD_at	19.6	19.6	29.1	7.8	22.0
2382	PA2357_msuE_at	42.3	14.5	23.2	18.9	26.1
2383	PA2358_at	296.5	441.1	162.2	134.7	196.2
2384	PA2359_at	6.9	127.5	96.7	65.0	74.8
2385	PA2360_at	49.1	59.2	92.6	64.5	60.6
2386	PA2361_at	14.6	29.6	19.3	15.0	29.1
2387	PA2362_at	11.0	18.9	34.5	17.0	21.8
2388	PA2363_at	37.9	22.6	66.7	45.6	56.4
2389	PA2364_at	29.5	34.1	30.9	70.3	46.0
2390	PA2365_at	67.9	66.6	117.8	88.7	80.6
2391	PA2366_at	27.0	82.4	112.9	102.5	110.8
2392	PA2367_at	34.0	52.9	83.6	41.9	52.0
2393	PA2368_i_at	39.7	51.2	151.8	72.2	81.5
2394	PA2369_at	10.7	20.7	84.5	73.1	25.1
2395	PA2370_at	30.7	20.8	50.4	30.3	28.6
2396	PA2371_at	6.0	29.4	71.8	27.1	11.6
2397	PA2372_at	15.6	16.8	13.3	7.2	6.6
2398	PA2373_at	8.5	66.7	45.5	43.7	62.4
2399	PA2374_at	2.7	22.8	3.1	51.4	26.6
2400	PA2375_i_at	15.4	44.3	44.6	32.9	52.9
2401	PA2376_at	22.5	23.2	53.7	29.2	33.5

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2402	PA2377_at	3.8	22.0	29.3	46.1	34.7
2403	PA2378_at	282.5	227.5	232.6	212.4	215.6
2404	PA2379_at	218.4	241.4	132.4	169.6	179.7
2405	PA2380_at	91.6	105.1	131.4	96.5	101.5
2406	PA2381_at	101.4	111.8	124.7	125.3	157.2
2407	PA2382_lldA_at	64.9	35.6	51.7	48.2	45.4
2408	PA2383_at	84.9	86.7	124.2	114.2	107.3
2409	PA2384_at	107.4	131.2	207.9	195.2	213.2
2410	PA2385_at	222.6	169.2	88.9	93.8	64.1
2411	PA2386_pvdA_at	360.8	219.4	135.7	114.4	82.1
2412	PA2387_at	24.7	48.3	51.3	87.1	90.4
2413	PA2388_at	217.1	289.4	454.7	487.9	408.5
2414	PA2389_at	600.4	315.2	205.5	258.8	245.3
2415	PA2390_at	367.6	169.5	174.3	227.3	172.8
2416	PA2391_at	287.6	102.9	116.4	181.3	144.1
2417	PA2392_at	202.7	49.9	58.0	39.5	51.3
2418	PA2393_at	601.7	178.7	65.2	55.0	57.9
2419	PA2394_at	856.7	229.9	106.3	108.5	105.4
2420	PA2395_at	917.4	214.6	92.7	84.4	102.3
2421	PA2396_at	598.0	334.0	68.3	77.9	54.8
2422	PA2397_pvdE_at	416.4	154.0	23.5	37.3	41.7
2423	PA2398_fpvA_at	584.6	356.6	598.0	777.6	831.5
2424	PA2399_pvdD_at	455.0	248.3	39.3	62.2	59.7
2425	PA2400_at	735.9	208.4	23.7	34.8	27.7
2426	PA2401_at	394.7	212.9	13.4	26.9	35.9
2427	PA2402_at	762.8	201.6	59.7	52.4	66.2
2428	PA2403_at	181.4	391.7	434.0	539.7	540.9
2429	PA2404_at	137.5	287.0	611.2	628.3	624.6
2430	PA2405_at	100.0	265.4	406.0	467.5	438.8
2431	PA2406_at	144.9	223.2	136.4	233.2	236.7
2432	PA2407_at	195.0	452.2	692.4	776.7	699.1
2433	PA2408_at	43.7	85.3	267.0	298.1	341.5
2434	PA2409_at	53.5	169.5	635.7	418.9	448.4
2435	PA2410_at	62.3	105.7	299.6	253.7	220.1
2436	PA2411_at	752.0	238.6	40.2	62.7	54.4
2437	PA2412_at	816.3	312.1	75.8	89.8	83.6
2438	PA2413_at	881.6	183.0	48.5	61.4	56.6
2439	PA2414_at	24.4	11.4	60.8	28.0	19.8
2440	PA2415_at	41.0	31.6	60.1	41.9	63.8
2441	PA2416_treA_at	64.9	44.0	56.1	60.0	41.2
2442	PA2417_at	23.7	25.2	40.8	17.8	33.3
2443	PA2418_at	6.2	18.7	36.0	8.7	21.5
2444	PA2419_at	1.7	3.6	7.2	3.5	24.3
2445	PA2420_at	5.1	5.3	17.7	4.3	4.4
2446	PA2421_at	11.4	21.1	9.5	29.0	48.6
2447	PA2422_at	31.7	23.1	15.8	18.3	18.5
2448	PA2423_at	145.6	288.9	92.2	138.3	164.7
2449	PA2424_at	412.1	84.3	21.6	20.0	29.9
2450	PA2425_at	99.3	31.1	25.1	28.2	33.6
2451	PA2426_pvdS_at	29.3	22.9	46.9	57.1	48.9
2452	PA2427_at	83.6	31.5	42.9	30.3	23.5
2453	PA2428_at	65.7	67.3	66.9	39.4	52.8
2454	PA2429_at	10.0	11.4	50.9	40.0	31.0
2455	PA2430_at	24.8	20.8	44.6	34.5	43.5
2456	PA2431_at	7.1	26.0	33.9	31.1	23.9
2457	PA2432_at	36.9	73.5	13.3	18.0	44.0
2458	PA2433_at	46.7	45.1	47.9	35.5	35.5
2459	PA2434_at	62.5	37.5	70.9	43.5	58.8
2460	PA2435_at	26.7	18.9	65.3	43.9	53.5
2461	PA2436_at	117.8	79.2	147.1	113.3	95.0
2462	PA2437_at	43.1	28.5	77.8	50.8	63.3
2463	PA2438_at	29.4	17.4	43.6	34.8	32.6
2464	PA2439_at	16.1	1.2	20.0	4.2	4.4
2465	PA2440_at	63.1	78.5	85.0	63.7	83.3
2466	PA2441_at	8.2	137.5	89.1	70.7	85.6
2467	PA2442_gcvT2_at	845.1	902.5	903.2	963.9	893.1
2468	PA2443_sdaA_at	1215.6	1214.1	1616.4	1331.2	1211.6
2469	PA2444_glyA2_at	1709.7	1468.2	1146.5	1406.2	1370.2
2470	PA2445_gcvP2_at	5304.5	3035.4	2788.0	3058.1	2940.9
2471	PA2446_gcvH2_at	4688.8	2401.8	2838.3	2631.0	2349.7
2472	PA2447_at	28.7	30.8	75.5	39.6	53.4
2473	PA2448_at	65.1	46.5	66.3	87.5	60.7
2474	PA2449_at	120.4	100.1	63.9	101.4	103.3

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2475	PA2450_at	288.3	203.8	112.3	171.0	178.3
2476	PA2451_at	297.0	104.4	54.9	38.5	38.6
2477	PA2452_at	570.2	96.9	49.1	26.3	43.0
2478	PA2453_at	689.7	779.2	536.1	570.7	647.2
2479	PA2454_at	120.2	120.5	106.6	133.1	116.8
2480	PA2455_at	203.0	168.9	149.2	133.1	143.8
2481	PA2456_at	94.1	114.1	81.0	86.3	84.7
2482	PA2457_at	109.9	98.8	101.5	76.4	66.5
2483	PA2458_at	28.9	14.8	20.0	23.7	29.1
2484	PA2459_at	49.0	143.5	102.8	73.8	80.2
2485	PA2460_i_at	151.3	297.6	349.9	235.4	262.2
2486	PA2461_at	43.6	56.2	82.3	59.7	78.9
2487	PA2462_at	204.7	346.8	321.2	345.8	374.2
2488	PA2464_at	358.5	304.0	211.2	212.5	239.3
2489	PA2465_at	4.4	1.0	3.3	2.7	15.1
2490	PA2466_at	3.7	26.1	24.8	28.6	24.5
2491	PA2467_at	20.7	24.1	118.0	73.5	69.2
2492	PA2468_at	2.6	14.1	100.5	41.8	37.6
2493	PA2469_at	9.8	36.4	60.2	49.6	39.2
2494	PA2470_gtdA_at	47.8	29.6	32.3	30.3	36.2
2495	PA2471_at	15.2	17.1	40.6	7.2	25.4
2496	PA2472_at	14.4	0.8	7.2	10.4	10.7
2497	PA2473_at	23.6	10.1	6.7	5.3	26.2
2498	PA2474_at	3.2	3.2	25.5	5.2	21.9
2499	PA2475_at	54.4	26.9	58.3	44.1	44.2
2500	PA2476_dsbG_at	256.4	260.2	340.5	287.6	292.1
2501	PA2477_at	50.3	69.0	67.0	75.3	71.8
2502	PA2478_at	31.8	50.8	28.6	49.0	54.7
2503	PA2479_at	68.6	73.1	85.1	57.3	71.8
2504	PA2480_at	24.9	23.7	44.6	24.6	33.6
2505	PA2481_at	156.2	106.5	87.8	72.5	71.6
2506	PA2482_at	179.0	132.9	150.0	84.5	96.6
2507	PA2483_at	101.4	112.1	157.8	99.8	115.3
2508	PA2484_at	111.3	104.5	119.8	87.0	128.2
2509	PA2485_at	19.4	50.0	13.9	18.2	28.9
2510	PA2486_at	15.5	26.7	22.8	19.6	18.3
2511	PA2487_i_at	32.6	28.9	17.8	22.7	39.1
2512	PA2488_at	58.0	39.1	73.7	98.5	61.0
2513	PA2489_at	63.3	26.5	81.7	83.1	47.2
2514	PA2490_at	52.7	55.8	73.7	54.9	56.6
2515	PA2491_at	123.5	125.3	109.7	128.5	142.9
2516	PA2492_mexT_at	90.1	123.0	92.0	119.7	109.6
2517	PA2493_mexE_at	6.0	14.2	30.3	24.8	41.0
2518	PA2494_mexF_at	4.1	2.4	26.2	5.1	17.4
2519	PA2495_oprN_at	55.8	17.9	34.8	24.4	28.5
2520	PA2496_at	19.2	41.3	54.8	50.1	52.3
2521	PA2497_at	47.8	44.1	37.2	42.2	28.4
2522	PA2498_at	61.9	39.1	68.0	113.1	67.1
2523	PA2499_at	12.5	9.6	36.6	4.8	10.0
2524	PA2500_at	28.1	19.9	33.9	23.9	29.9
2525	PA2501_at	88.5	126.4	95.4	92.9	87.5
2526	PA2502_at	93.5	110.5	118.1	121.1	131.9
2527	PA2503_at	212.9	145.8	215.4	212.9	211.5
2528	PA2504_at	43.9	40.2	36.6	50.9	45.8
2529	PA2505_at	15.3	16.5	46.3	14.6	31.8
2530	PA2506_at	32.2	29.0	21.7	62.3	25.0
2531	PA2507_catA_at	5.2	14.9	61.3	29.5	18.9
2532	PA2508_catC_at	24.8	17.4	46.3	17.1	35.5
2533	PA2509_catB_at	18.5	2.8	16.5	5.5	8.0
2534	PA2510_catR_at	99.1	57.0	88.8	57.8	65.0
2535	PA2511_at	16.2	8.5	55.8	20.4	45.1
2536	PA2512_antA_at	2.8	1.6	7.6	3.6	2.5
2537	PA2513_antB_at	13.8	23.0	21.9	31.2	34.9
2538	PA2514_antC_at	16.3	8.3	9.4	11.5	11.0
2539	PA2515_xylL_at	5.6	3.9	24.4	11.0	25.9
2540	PA2516_xylZ_at	13.6	1.5	8.8	22.3	6.7
2541	PA2517_xylY_at	27.0	18.6	15.4	29.9	32.1
2542	PA2518_xylX_at	12.5	3.1	26.5	5.8	9.5
2543	PA2519_xylS_at	56.9	37.6	47.8	41.3	38.6
2544	PA2520_czcA_at	8.8	13.1	50.9	21.0	32.9
2545	PA2521_czcB_at	36.7	27.5	39.3	35.5	37.1
2546	PA2522_czcC_at	1.3	3.9	22.4	5.6	14.5
2547	PA2523_at	47.4	32.1	48.0	41.6	44.8

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2548	PA2524_at	51.2	70.0	89.9	81.7	63.8
2549	PA2525_at	136.0	110.6	112.3	103.5	107.4
2550	PA2526_at	119.7	163.6	113.3	135.2	120.7
2551	PA2527_at	135.9	93.6	127.4	130.6	114.8
2552	PA2528_at	249.9	296.0	264.3	240.7	249.4
2553	PA2529_at	177.5	203.9	159.2	190.7	194.0
2554	PA2530_at	267.4	293.3	292.0	255.4	267.7
2555	PA2531_at	19.8	47.1	52.2	51.2	57.2
2556	PA2532_tpx_at	366.7	421.6	419.2	466.4	670.7
2557	PA2533_at	222.8	222.5	330.2	343.6	389.9
2558	PA2534_at	40.3	23.1	34.9	30.4	36.6
2559	PA2535_at	11.2	35.5	65.4	44.1	43.8
2560	PA2536_at	110.6	124.2	122.0	128.6	138.2
2561	PA2537_at	215.0	210.0	175.2	200.3	234.8
2562	PA2538_at	185.9	129.7	210.1	184.7	171.2
2563	PA2539_at	40.7	35.8	54.3	44.9	39.0
2564	PA2540_at	216.1	146.4	203.1	186.5	203.3
2565	PA2541_at	136.6	145.4	168.3	164.2	130.2
2566	PA2542_at	47.8	72.2	86.4	85.5	90.4
2567	PA2543_at	34.7	46.2	90.6	98.3	90.4
2568	PA2544_at	45.8	42.5	52.9	35.5	62.6
2569	PA2545_xthA_at	358.4	297.8	317.7	399.1	372.1
2570	PA2546_at	28.8	36.1	33.6	34.5	45.5
2571	PA2547_at	29.8	28.8	8.7	24.2	35.4
2572	PA2548_at	24.4	21.3	57.3	22.4	38.3
2573	PA2549_at	31.5	47.8	55.3	66.2	59.6
2574	PA2550_at	39.6	77.9	124.4	88.7	122.6
2575	PA2551_at	157.3	204.3	145.3	191.4	231.2
2576	PA2552_at	228.3	558.9	907.0	1009.1	1001.8
2577	PA2553_at	377.8	720.5	1147.5	1432.5	1333.2
2578	PA2554_at	323.5	543.7	1074.8	845.4	815.1
2579	PA2555_at	112.5	189.3	261.3	260.0	221.0
2580	PA2556_at	33.9	38.3	78.6	88.2	93.3
2581	PA2557_at	72.5	106.5	164.0	197.0	234.9
2582	PA2558_at	46.8	61.3	41.9	32.2	69.5
2583	PA2559_at	141.8	206.0	194.1	235.6	257.4
2584	PA2560_at	156.0	213.9	114.0	111.8	106.4
2585	PA2561_at	128.7	175.4	111.4	112.9	131.9
2586	PA2562_at	201.2	245.2	152.4	154.5	109.1
2587	PA2563_at	40.7	33.5	48.4	37.2	34.4
2588	PA2564_at	13.5	14.6	30.5	6.5	16.2
2589	PA2565_at	42.3	63.7	113.9	91.1	88.8
2590	PA2566_at	5.7	13.2	30.3	2.6	19.4
2591	PA2567_at	124.0	103.0	77.5	82.3	61.8
2592	PA2568_at	41.9	70.8	69.3	49.3	64.1
2593	PA2569_at	26.0	28.0	47.1	50.7	35.2
2594	PA2570_pa1L_at	17.5	14.8	25.3	17.9	19.5
2595	PA2571_at	4.2	18.0	9.6	7.8	20.7
2596	PA2572_at	10.3	38.7	47.2	63.4	49.1
2597	PA2573_at	22.8	33.9	52.7	25.2	27.3
2598	PA2574_at	3.4	28.3	28.5	17.0	28.2
2599	PA2575_at	174.0	204.1	260.1	224.3	256.8
2600	PA2576_at	24.2	30.4	76.9	44.8	54.8
2601	PA2577_at	12.5	71.9	59.5	45.9	73.5
2602	PA2578_at	17.0	41.2	38.2	34.6	22.4
2603	PA2579_at	286.8	247.3	112.4	136.2	135.9
2604	PA2580_at	72.9	68.2	66.2	55.1	66.0
2605	PA2581_at	229.9	234.1	159.5	187.7	161.1
2606	PA2582_at	383.2	497.5	510.0	430.2	484.8
2607	PA2583_at	44.5	89.0	130.5	102.1	94.5
2608	PA2584_pgsA_at	386.2	443.1	622.4	540.4	486.5
2609	PA2585_uvrC_at	290.5	286.2	220.7	227.0	224.4
2610	PA2586_gacA_at	711.9	823.9	576.8	599.0	671.7
2611	PA2587_at	311.3	357.0	519.5	470.5	519.4
2612	PA2588_at	121.5	122.9	112.7	137.8	165.4
2613	PA2589_at	43.2	48.2	14.1	18.4	37.3
2614	PA2590_at	30.5	21.5	46.5	37.8	34.9
2615	PA2591_at	197.2	178.2	170.8	200.1	172.9
2616	PA2592_at	236.2	399.0	279.4	272.7	297.9
2617	PA2593_at	50.8	151.5	92.5	118.1	121.8
2618	PA2594_at	47.9	109.4	117.5	146.2	116.5
2619	PA2595_at	34.2	56.7	59.2	52.4	46.1
2620	PA2596_at	35.7	13.4	32.7	21.1	52.6

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2621	PA2597_at	149.0	126.9	172.5	181.3	146.2
2622	PA2598_at	44.5	82.3	77.9	77.7	74.7
2623	PA2599_at	30.9	92.3	76.3	93.8	76.3
2624	PA2600_at	28.8	45.9	62.4	44.3	43.7
2625	PA2601_at	46.3	54.0	66.4	63.1	62.1
2626	PA2602_at	63.9	52.0	68.7	61.3	55.5
2627	PA2603_at	56.5	92.6	47.9	62.5	64.7
2628	PA2604_at	298.7	423.9	475.5	332.2	410.0
2629	PA2605_at	173.9	111.6	97.7	129.8	166.7
2630	PA2606_at	339.4	416.8	238.2	261.0	301.2
2631	PA2607_at	147.0	169.7	252.5	208.7	189.1
2632	PA2608_at	139.4	182.1	241.4	192.9	212.6
2633	PA2609_at	180.2	146.2	110.7	129.0	114.6
2634	PA2610_at	3.3	30.0	70.2	34.0	32.6
2635	PA2611_cysG_at	137.9	118.7	161.8	167.4	142.5
2636	PA2612_serS_at	1459.4	1400.7	1380.7	1290.5	1328.8
2637	PA2613_at	355.7	391.8	509.1	472.9	415.0
2638	PA2614_lolA_at	767.0	762.1	695.1	709.0	708.4
2639	PA2615_ftsK_at	601.6	384.5	677.6	596.6	551.7
2640	PA2616_trxB1_at	1080.1	909.2	460.4	624.0	746.2
2641	PA2617_aat_at	228.1	190.6	238.3	181.1	169.0
2642	PA2618_at	121.8	155.2	41.8	58.6	94.7
2643	PA2619_infA_at	1445.6	2037.3	520.2	712.1	896.3
2644	PA2620_clpA_at	584.1	675.6	399.4	527.1	517.0
2645	PA2621_at	682.5	917.9	515.7	532.7	576.3
2646	PA2622_cspD_at	148.2	349.8	192.2	221.5	255.6
2647	PA2623_icd_at	1511.7	1443.0	1360.8	1269.0	1553.2
2648	PA2624_idh_at	4196.3	2312.8	1944.1	2017.8	2199.1
2649	PA2625_at	447.7	296.1	314.8	282.3	316.1
2650	PA2626_trmU_at	1169.2	775.9	1405.2	1210.5	1012.3
2651	PA2627_at	813.0	652.6	460.1	533.5	561.7
2652	PA2628_at	93.0	69.7	88.4	94.7	75.5
2653	PA2629_purB_at	899.4	977.7	1117.8	1085.5	1115.7
2654	PA2630_at	282.0	363.5	318.4	296.4	327.3
2655	PA2631_at	336.9	504.7	342.4	466.3	475.1
2656	PA2632_at	131.1	164.5	144.2	113.3	141.7
2657	PA2633_at	164.0	174.9	93.9	111.6	136.2
2658	PA2634_at	966.1	1007.3	641.8	590.4	680.6
2659	PA2635_at	49.5	25.2	44.2	38.3	41.8
2660	PA2636_at	25.0	28.9	41.0	47.2	40.8
2661	PA2637_nuoA_at	910.8	700.1	752.0	713.9	989.6
2662	PA2638_nuoB_at	1317.3	1265.0	1415.7	1408.1	1206.0
2663	PA2639_nuoD_at	1852.0	1572.1	678.0	999.2	1016.5
2664	PA2640_nuoE_at	2182.0	1970.5	1101.7	1397.6	1403.6
2665	PA2641_nuoF_at	1085.1	1188.2	1395.7	1232.4	1090.9
2666	PA2642_nuoG_at	1419.3	1202.3	1547.2	1557.6	1352.3
2667	PA2643_nuoH_at	1560.7	1170.8	1539.6	1162.9	1113.3
2668	PA2644_nuoI_at	1013.0	1018.1	904.8	952.5	964.7
2669	PA2645_nuoJ_at	938.2	921.9	1042.3	911.1	1010.5
2670	PA2646_nuoK_at	1355.2	1075.2	1922.9	1543.9	1472.2
2671	PA2647_nuoL_at	963.5	810.8	1176.9	1020.9	1077.4
2672	PA2648_nuoM_at	1032.6	978.8	705.2	760.9	760.6
2673	PA2649_nuoN_at	693.0	569.7	485.6	492.5	580.1
2674	PA2650_at	78.9	65.3	87.4	86.1	70.1
2675	PA2651_at	68.8	90.2	138.4	82.2	93.2
2676	PA2652_at	240.6	323.6	195.8	234.1	254.5
2677	PA2653_at	58.5	86.7	103.7	129.1	135.0
2678	PA2654_at	240.1	200.4	147.6	172.7	213.1
2679	PA2655_i_at	24.2	28.6	74.4	42.6	50.6
2680	PA2656_at	44.9	80.3	123.8	103.7	98.4
2681	PA2657_at	124.6	104.5	163.9	172.7	144.2
2682	PA2658_at	160.9	229.2	177.0	225.1	197.4
2683	PA2659_at	188.2	354.4	128.3	151.7	194.5
2684	PA2660_at	191.4	162.2	356.5	246.1	239.2
2685	PA2661_at	140.1	183.9	181.7	170.6	151.6
2686	PA2662_at	22.6	24.0	44.7	34.1	39.6
2687	PA2663_at	21.7	19.2	36.1	25.1	17.9
2688	PA2664_fhp_at	4.9	7.9	5.5	19.1	20.3
2689	PA2665_at	90.5	91.5	50.8	69.4	88.0
2690	PA2666_at	353.7	386.4	182.2	259.6	289.3
2691	PA2667_at	734.8	1319.1	377.5	450.6	519.4
2692	PA2668_at	53.1	62.5	38.5	42.0	50.6
2693	PA2669_at	20.6	18.2	23.6	11.2	25.1

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2694	PA2670_at	24.5	9.3	2.0	3.5	20.3
2695	PA2671_at	33.2	12.9	16.2	27.3	22.8
2696	PA2672_at	12.9	13.0	28.7	33.7	35.1
2697	PA2673_at	1.0	10.3	38.6	35.4	21.0
2698	PA2674_at	33.5	10.5	21.1	26.9	21.8
2699	PA2675_at	42.8	24.7	46.5	44.0	33.1
2700	PA2676_at	24.9	21.4	48.5	10.4	18.5
2701	PA2677_at	5.5	3.6	28.9	6.7	28.6
2702	PA2678_at	26.5	18.4	38.8	27.1	16.0
2703	PA2679_at	35.5	36.0	78.2	55.2	54.1
2704	PA2680_at	8.1	15.4	4.9	2.2	3.5
2705	PA2681_at	35.0	30.9	47.0	46.8	39.2
2706	PA2682_at	95.1	111.0	108.6	97.2	80.4
2707	PA2683_at	111.1	80.9	106.5	98.2	92.8
2708	PA2684_at	213.2	166.3	213.5	157.7	176.4
2709	PA2685_at	209.2	182.1	159.7	158.0	180.2
2710	PA2686_pfeR_at	10.9	20.6	32.6	21.5	34.7
2711	PA2687_pfeS_at	18.5	8.8	49.8	45.5	31.9
2712	PA2688_pfeA_at	17.4	6.3	20.8	20.0	18.8
2713	PA2689_at	4.8	2.2	39.2	13.8	29.9
2714	PA2691_at	63.8	27.6	55.2	57.3	40.5
2715	PA2692_at	126.1	170.7	212.5	130.7	124.1
2716	PA2693_at	32.0	28.5	40.7	13.2	28.7
2717	PA2694_at	32.2	34.3	86.7	78.8	55.2
2718	PA2695_at	48.5	62.9	86.7	49.0	91.4
2719	PA2696_at	4.2	18.2	32.9	5.9	29.2
2720	PA2697_at	37.7	24.6	68.4	38.8	35.5
2721	PA2698_at	32.3	106.0	85.6	81.8	74.8
2722	PA2699_at	22.5	4.0	5.4	32.5	32.4
2723	PA2700_at	66.1	24.4	47.7	19.4	23.0
2724	PA2701_at	1.5	4.5	20.9	18.9	24.0
2725	PA2702_at	114.3	115.6	134.0	100.5	93.4
2726	PA2703_at	71.5	59.3	99.3	72.3	68.0
2727	PA2704_at	43.0	14.0	14.1	28.6	41.3
2728	PA2705_at	65.7	98.5	118.1	119.0	130.7
2729	PA2706_at	117.8	238.8	224.9	196.1	202.0
2730	PA2707_at	230.4	402.8	180.0	271.4	283.8
2731	PA2708_at	15.1	13.8	35.3	6.6	22.7
2732	PA2709_cysK_at	342.5	378.2	335.9	411.0	384.6
2733	PA2710_at	120.4	93.4	172.8	98.7	97.0
2734	PA2711_at	136.2	169.0	262.4	177.1	190.7
2735	PA2712_at	233.5	113.2	172.7	158.4	140.9
2736	PA2713_at	56.1	43.1	55.1	71.6	45.9
2737	PA2714_at	60.2	33.2	36.2	34.3	46.9
2738	PA2715_at	11.3	6.8	31.6	3.0	8.4
2739	PA2716_at	9.4	1.9	41.4	8.4	3.6
2740	PA2717_cpo_at	28.6	4.2	24.0	14.9	27.6
2741	PA2718_at	55.0	60.0	59.2	69.7	74.2
2742	PA2719_at	32.7	4.3	43.2	18.8	29.2
2743	PA2720_at	63.8	62.0	128.8	92.4	91.2
2744	PA2721_at	15.0	6.2	27.8	8.5	23.1
2745	PA2722_at	4.6	13.1	11.0	20.6	20.1
2746	PA2723_at	74.8	63.5	59.0	62.9	61.3
2747	PA2724_r_at	112.9	109.9	184.0	135.6	145.2
2748	PA2725_at	157.2	186.7	87.1	140.0	126.3
2749	PA2726_at	78.4	107.5	92.3	101.6	83.5
2750	PA2727_at	127.0	141.0	311.4	224.6	202.9
2751	PA2728_at	163.0	167.9	221.0	168.7	207.6
2752	PA2729_at	150.2	166.3	221.7	235.1	153.7
2753	PA2730_at	231.5	324.5	342.3	362.2	308.3
2754	PA2731_at	265.3	354.2	196.3	286.2	352.7
2755	PA2732_at	188.1	331.8	175.1	233.8	230.5
2756	PA2733_at	469.7	599.5	726.9	608.7	715.0
2757	PA2734_at	404.0	492.2	453.5	445.4	385.4
2758	PA2735_at	577.7	767.2	569.0	675.4	698.3
2759	PA2736_at	450.3	516.7	441.0	522.9	505.1
2760	PA2737_at	972.0	968.2	617.1	662.3	705.5
2761	PA2738_himA_at	1917.2	2307.0	1483.7	1348.8	1463.7
2762	PA2739_pheT_at	819.5	884.1	761.8	842.3	848.0
2763	PA2740_pheS_at	1044.8	1135.9	1315.4	1365.1	1309.2
2764	PA2741_rplT_at	916.0	1043.7	1575.9	1415.3	1366.9
2765	PA2742_rpmI_at	5772.2	4613.0	5598.1	5441.7	4239.8
2766	PA2743_infC_at	4083.7	2950.1	4898.0	4552.7	3724.1

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2767	PA2744_thrS_at	1630.3	1279.9	1166.5	1274.1	1319.3
2768	PA2745_at	61.0	74.5	126.7	69.1	90.0
2769	PA2746_at	16.1	10.9	20.0	9.7	10.8
2770	PA2747_at	45.1	43.8	43.5	53.0	49.9
2771	PA2748_at	43.6	52.1	71.5	44.5	60.6
2772	PA2749_endA_at	75.7	99.8	100.7	144.8	144.1
2773	PA2750_at	84.7	71.0	129.8	86.1	114.4
2774	PA2751_at	20.0	27.9	34.0	32.0	39.6
2775	PA2752_at	42.3	17.0	40.0	38.3	24.3
2776	PA2753_at	3.2	7.4	18.5	17.6	17.8
2777	PA2754_at	62.5	39.7	19.4	24.8	34.0
2778	PA2755_eco_at	290.1	262.9	236.6	267.8	294.7
2779	PA2756_at	52.1	106.4	102.5	116.0	97.8
2780	PA2757_at	23.2	24.6	59.4	33.2	36.0
2781	PA2758_at	62.6	29.8	52.4	62.7	49.2
2782	PA2759_at	23.5	14.0	13.1	22.6	23.7
2783	PA2760_at	2715.6	4172.8	1811.8	2121.4	2484.9
2784	PA2761_at	74.9	200.4	162.7	219.9	229.7
2785	PA2762_at	6.8	29.1	29.0	23.7	34.7
2786	PA2763_at	14.1	48.7	34.8	31.8	43.4
2787	PA2764_at	43.0	59.1	46.5	47.6	38.4
2788	PA2765_at	394.7	413.3	417.4	401.4	449.3
2789	PA2766_at	45.8	19.2	57.5	58.6	45.3
2790	PA2767_at	24.1	17.5	23.3	17.3	25.4
2791	PA2768_at	21.2	19.3	18.6	6.9	51.9
2792	PA2769_at	37.2	91.8	58.7	94.8	93.6
2793	PA2770_at	183.9	309.0	429.7	422.1	399.8
2794	PA2771_at	31.4	33.7	57.4	45.4	65.4
2795	PA2772_at	26.5	21.8	46.7	33.3	39.9
2796	PA2773_at	39.4	37.9	72.2	51.3	27.1
2797	PA2774_at	142.3	119.3	202.7	192.3	189.4
2798	PA2775_at	139.4	111.4	136.0	143.0	139.4
2799	PA2776_at	739.1	687.2	390.8	387.0	438.2
2800	PA2777_at	44.0	43.8	48.8	25.8	34.9
2801	PA2778_at	41.8	34.9	38.8	81.4	58.7
2802	PA2779_at	176.3	147.7	139.5	107.4	133.3
2803	PA2780_at	34.2	25.9	44.1	23.4	44.7
2804	PA2781_at	51.0	47.7	74.8	77.0	43.0
2805	PA2782_at	24.6	40.7	17.0	29.4	24.8
2806	PA2783_at	32.6	33.5	89.0	83.9	48.3
2807	PA2784_at	30.9	31.2	84.8	60.0	47.7
2808	PA2785_at	24.9	13.2	10.3	8.8	22.7
2809	PA2786_at	34.1	52.6	60.2	53.6	46.3
2810	PA2787_cpg2_at	14.0	16.4	19.4	5.8	6.9
2811	PA2788_at	54.7	66.2	94.1	75.2	86.2
2812	PA2789_at	47.5	39.6	34.7	26.2	33.1
2813	PA2790_at	25.8	46.9	50.6	30.5	31.4
2814	PA2791_at	44.1	33.8	41.9	17.7	20.1
2815	PA2792_at	76.3	122.6	91.7	68.8	100.1
2816	PA2793_at	241.1	213.6	134.4	163.8	171.4
2817	PA2794_at	18.4	25.6	34.6	26.4	29.2
2818	PA2795_at	130.4	97.0	134.3	120.5	94.6
2819	PA2796_tal_at	215.9	337.6	195.2	204.8	235.3
2820	PA2797_at	311.9	292.5	208.5	213.6	250.8
2821	PA2798_at	527.4	518.8	437.1	492.3	541.4
2822	PA2799_at	29.6	39.0	44.8	7.4	43.4
2823	PA2800_at	799.4	940.9	648.4	698.8	756.2
2824	PA2801_at	83.3	92.7	168.3	137.1	196.1
2825	PA2802_at	167.5	156.4	162.3	140.8	136.5
2826	PA2803_at	23.6	14.5	55.4	35.5	21.6
2827	PA2804_at	6.8	6.8	9.2	6.8	5.9
2828	PA2805_at	170.2	330.5	122.7	123.5	151.3
2829	PA2806_at	53.2	79.0	49.2	75.1	69.7
2830	PA2807_at	4.3	4.7	63.8	34.5	30.1
2831	PA2808_i_at	3.7	13.0	13.0	8.9	24.9
2832	PA2809_at	42.3	56.0	56.2	77.6	61.9
2833	PA2810_at	52.4	38.0	65.9	60.4	51.2
2834	PA2811_at	94.6	131.8	142.3	142.5	125.6
2835	PA2812_at	384.3	451.0	189.1	249.2	269.5
2836	PA2813_at	99.8	147.9	156.1	139.6	120.7
2837	PA2814_at	7.2	10.6	14.1	5.1	17.2
2838	PA2815_at	52.3	41.3	71.6	42.3	45.0
2839	PA2816_i_at	54.4	48.2	67.8	59.7	50.7

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2840	PA2817_at	231.9	251.7	297.6	246.8	259.6
2841	PA2818_at	56.6	46.4	25.2	32.5	43.2
2842	PA2819_at	34.6	9.5	15.3	9.8	10.5
2843	PA2820_at	152.0	215.9	236.6	217.5	215.9
2844	PA2821_at	59.6	90.1	84.3	54.3	74.4
2845	PA2822_at	93.1	98.3	144.2	120.2	95.4
2846	PA2823_at	286.0	355.2	162.8	245.7	316.1
2847	PA2824_at	79.8	54.1	79.7	42.6	68.2
2848	PA2825_at	30.8	32.1	43.7	42.5	50.2
2849	PA2826_at	109.1	108.0	133.6	144.0	117.9
2850	PA2827_at	166.0	144.5	127.6	110.5	142.9
2851	PA2828_at	496.3	573.2	412.0	418.2	417.1
2852	PA2829_at	214.3	222.3	211.4	175.3	173.0
2853	PA2830_htpX_at	579.0	483.8	265.4	414.8	470.0
2854	PA2831_at	205.5	197.0	169.9	253.6	181.0
2855	PA2832_tpm_at	29.7	37.9	67.5	52.0	45.9
2856	PA2833_i_at	6.1	28.0	11.7	3.1	17.6
2857	PA2834_at	64.1	59.5	76.3	87.9	52.0
2858	PA2835_at	3.3	14.5	25.1	10.0	27.7
2859	PA2836_at	3.6	17.8	7.0	20.4	15.6
2860	PA2837_at	26.0	15.9	35.3	33.0	19.7
2861	PA2838_at	12.2	20.7	41.7	7.7	33.8
2862	PA2839_at	58.2	15.9	22.5	27.7	22.2
2863	PA2840_at	504.3	461.3	600.4	598.4	496.5
2864	PA2841_at	16.9	50.1	59.5	70.5	68.4
2865	PA2842_at	35.5	52.4	69.7	69.1	49.3
2866	PA2843_at	351.6	249.8	433.6	282.5	290.2
2867	PA2844_at	25.6	24.8	15.7	22.7	37.1
2868	PA2845_at	13.2	10.4	19.3	18.2	23.5
2869	PA2846_at	27.0	32.4	38.0	20.2	30.8
2870	PA2847_at	20.7	5.7	11.7	14.5	10.9
2871	PA2848_at	45.1	55.2	77.6	70.5	52.9
2872	PA2849_at	162.8	165.0	119.4	165.7	127.0
2873	PA2850_ohr_at	229.7	316.8	190.0	205.5	194.3
2874	PA2851_efp_at	1487.6	1624.2	1650.8	1490.8	1467.4
2875	PA2852_at	64.6	55.1	47.6	39.9	55.3
2876	PA2853_oprI_at	7877.8	4153.1	7917.9	5856.8	5041.5
2877	PA2854_at	592.2	672.6	398.2	566.5	487.4
2878	PA2855_at	310.7	249.4	469.8	509.4	460.7
2879	PA2856_tesA_at	69.4	55.7	89.9	87.1	154.0
2880	PA2857_at	72.7	60.0	55.6	79.8	79.3
2881	PA2858_at	110.6	106.0	123.4	139.3	116.2
2882	PA2859_greB_at	117.8	168.4	115.8	123.1	141.0
2883	PA2860_at	142.7	194.7	173.8	173.6	163.1
2884	PA2861_ligT_at	3.1	9.9	35.8	6.5	30.5
2885	PA2862_lipA_at	70.3	80.5	71.4	105.5	134.5
2886	PA2863_lipH_at	12.0	20.6	50.6	48.6	38.2
2887	PA2864_at	42.6	45.4	43.4	44.5	35.6
2888	PA2865_at	84.4	85.8	83.7	84.5	98.2
2889	PA2866_mttC_at	279.0	259.2	306.2	269.8	250.8
2890	PA2867_at	486.3	466.6	281.1	318.7	371.2
2891	PA2868_i_at	74.3	84.2	44.8	104.0	70.4
2892	PA2869_at	41.1	30.3	72.5	41.7	39.7
2893	PA2870_at	77.4	46.6	120.9	78.8	53.3
2894	PA2871_at	59.9	67.1	97.7	79.6	110.9
2895	PA2872_at	64.9	77.0	75.6	56.7	77.2
2896	PA2873_at	19.2	13.3	23.0	12.2	15.8
2897	PA2874_at	25.4	42.4	52.8	53.8	41.1
2898	PA2875_at	84.7	67.4	103.8	101.4	102.1
2899	PA2876_pyrF_at	263.0	441.8	198.6	262.1	298.4
2900	PA2877_at	8.2	74.8	92.9	66.9	75.1
2901	PA2878_at	28.8	24.2	48.6	39.0	37.3
2902	PA2879_at	66.3	77.0	82.0	72.2	67.2
2903	PA2880_at	29.9	30.5	30.5	24.3	40.5
2904	PA2881_at	28.2	13.1	38.0	21.5	22.7
2905	PA2882_at	65.4	27.0	40.8	30.4	32.1
2906	PA2883_at	66.9	83.9	64.4	65.1	68.5
2907	PA2884_at	68.8	84.9	137.7	80.1	78.9
2908	PA2885_at	100.6	112.6	85.0	82.4	92.7
2909	PA2886_at	50.3	36.2	77.8	49.3	49.5
2910	PA2887_at	37.3	39.9	47.4	48.8	51.6
2911	PA2888_at	38.6	28.7	49.3	43.4	51.3
2912	PA2889_at	39.7	42.8	82.9	51.0	53.9

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2913	PA2890_at	35.2	33.6	94.2	87.8	59.3
2914	PA2891_at	29.8	9.4	43.8	37.9	14.9
2915	PA2892_at	35.1	33.7	44.1	34.5	41.7
2916	PA2893_at	44.7	52.5	49.5	63.1	29.4
2917	PA2894_at	164.7	187.8	265.5	263.6	238.8
2918	PA2895_at	113.2	120.5	140.7	145.3	94.5
2919	PA2896_at	141.4	117.1	153.6	152.7	125.4
2920	PA2897_at	206.6	220.3	312.9	206.2	213.8
2921	PA2898_at	6.4	13.8	47.6	30.4	26.4
2922	PA2899_at	70.6	89.0	90.0	80.2	77.1
2923	PA2900_at	151.6	173.9	127.0	151.6	146.2
2924	PA2901_at	291.9	412.8	629.6	473.3	425.2
2925	PA2902_at	135.5	118.9	139.1	155.4	176.8
2926	PA2903_cobJ_at	37.8	49.7	82.9	83.3	86.2
2927	PA2904_cobI_at	138.0	182.9	263.4	286.3	208.0
2928	PA2905_cobH_at	135.6	125.2	173.9	155.5	167.9
2929	PA2906_at	300.0	256.0	434.3	418.4	382.1
2930	PA2907_cobL_at	185.5	138.6	195.1	164.0	174.7
2931	PA2908_cbiD_at	122.9	123.3	161.7	146.2	128.1
2932	PA2909_i_at	43.3	45.9	87.2	70.1	57.8
2933	PA2910_at	8.6	25.3	60.4	33.1	40.8
2934	PA2911_at	51.4	94.3	91.8	122.0	119.6
2935	PA2912_at	73.0	80.5	121.1	136.7	134.3
2936	PA2913_at	21.6	47.3	41.9	47.4	50.1
2937	PA2914_at	18.0	27.7	37.9	45.8	45.0
2938	PA2915_at	70.1	76.9	69.1	67.2	89.6
2939	PA2916_at	25.5	20.6	43.4	25.5	36.1
2940	PA2917_at	20.3	46.8	45.4	22.4	27.8
2941	PA2918_at	124.8	157.6	117.7	106.6	119.4
2942	PA2919_at	10.2	8.0	9.7	10.4	9.5
2943	PA2920_at	69.7	43.9	43.2	49.4	51.9
2944	PA2921_at	56.9	61.9	76.5	86.2	104.3
2945	PA2922_at	5.7	20.7	23.4	12.4	35.5
2946	PA2923_hisJ_at	19.6	22.8	35.0	10.5	39.4
2947	PA2924_hisQ_at	11.4	3.1	31.6	5.8	11.9
2948	PA2925_hisM_at	33.4	20.3	3.3	6.1	27.2
2949	PA2926_hisP_at	11.0	11.4	39.2	25.2	39.9
2950	PA2927_at	17.1	16.5	38.4	2.6	28.3
2951	PA2928_at	57.7	42.7	96.9	67.0	59.2
2952	PA2929_at	26.0	39.5	42.8	16.5	36.6
2953	PA2930_at	74.6	86.1	42.6	83.6	91.2
2954	PA2931_at	36.9	55.6	82.2	80.0	69.9
2955	PA2932_morB_at	3.3	27.8	54.0	38.3	39.6
2956	PA2933_at	10.1	28.1	31.2	5.6	19.8
2957	PA2934_at	39.9	25.6	64.7	52.5	37.3
2958	PA2935_at	6.9	3.3	25.1	2.1	11.1
2959	PA2936_at	5.3	9.0	35.5	24.5	18.2
2960	PA2937_at	27.7	23.6	22.6	4.0	21.3
2961	PA2938_at	14.3	14.7	35.0	22.8	21.8
2962	PA2939_at	5.6	53.3	53.6	65.4	40.2
2963	PA2940_at	5.6	7.0	18.6	22.0	36.3
2964	PA2941_at	36.7	29.5	61.7	58.3	52.2
2965	PA2942_at	160.5	149.7	283.3	193.3	208.9
2966	PA2943_at	139.5	228.4	199.7	197.7	226.3
2967	PA2944_cobN_at	126.8	149.7	221.8	202.0	206.7
2968	PA2945_at	356.6	509.8	546.8	593.4	579.3
2969	PA2946_at	454.7	465.4	748.1	1009.7	856.9
2970	PA2947_i_at	166.2	146.5	59.8	113.3	107.5
2971	PA2948_cobM_at	141.3	147.7	83.1	131.3	107.9
2972	PA2949_at	67.9	75.6	67.4	76.0	86.8
2973	PA2950_at	749.8	1022.3	871.9	931.8	1212.0
2974	PA2951_etfA_at	2174.4	1419.5	1508.7	1850.2	1872.0
2975	PA2952_etfB_at	1658.3	1810.9	2406.4	1954.1	2355.9
2976	PA2953_at	881.5	1079.8	626.8	954.1	952.8
2977	PA2954_at	104.9	98.5	87.5	85.7	109.0
2978	PA2955_at	64.9	92.2	59.8	79.6	77.9
2979	PA2956_at	57.3	64.8	162.0	128.7	119.0
2980	PA2957_at	437.2	562.0	574.8	655.1	684.6
2981	PA2958_at	44.4	42.1	56.7	50.8	39.6
2982	PA2959_at	415.9	392.1	379.9	399.2	452.6
2983	PA2960_pilZ_at	326.7	423.9	220.1	246.6	289.8
2984	PA2961_holB_at	153.4	157.7	375.4	290.1	250.3
2985	PA2962_tmk_at	205.8	191.8	523.0	443.5	354.2

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2986	PA2963_at	270.1	285.2	282.3	214.7	219.9
2987	PA2964_pabC_at	315.6	367.0	686.8	651.8	630.5
2988	PA2965_fabF1_at	934.2	823.7	1103.6	986.2	905.4
2989	PA2966_acpP_at	3215.0	2893.6	2393.8	2347.0	2694.2
2990	PA2967_fabG_at	1118.6	871.8	1430.2	1217.5	1026.2
2991	PA2968_fabD_at	539.6	488.3	755.5	818.6	823.6
2992	PA2969_plsX_at	115.7	88.5	222.5	203.8	173.1
2993	PA2970_rpmF_at	1437.6	1958.0	1121.0	1232.5	1290.3
2994	PA2971_at	1921.8	2015.5	1612.5	2168.3	2233.5
2995	PA2972_at	100.7	118.5	95.0	139.5	141.4
2996	PA2973_at	510.9	451.7	728.3	532.4	465.8
2997	PA2974_at	147.4	182.4	252.8	215.4	215.3
2998	PA2975_rluC_at	235.1	270.5	292.7	342.0	232.7
2999	PA2976_rne_at	2065.2	2179.8	2754.0	3168.9	2332.0
3000	PA2977_murB_at	108.5	148.2	140.6	141.3	133.9
3001	PA2978_ptpA_at	201.5	318.5	222.1	276.9	295.9
3002	PA2979_kdsB_at	616.6	415.4	358.1	353.4	384.8
3003	PA2980_at	503.9	576.8	378.9	393.8	464.0
3004	PA2981_lpxK_at	79.5	80.9	118.7	105.3	99.5
3005	PA2982_at	143.6	117.9	216.3	195.5	128.7
3006	PA2983_at	352.0	371.7	240.1	299.5	355.0
3007	PA2984_at	18.7	20.7	65.6	52.0	42.7
3008	PA2985_at	98.2	101.3	120.6	116.3	131.6
3009	PA2986_at	192.5	234.2	108.7	174.1	166.1
3010	PA2987_at	367.0	391.6	389.8	409.7	413.4
3011	PA2988_at	213.9	157.7	284.5	279.1	147.2
3012	PA2989_at	27.8	66.4	87.7	69.5	67.1
3013	PA2990_at	185.9	163.8	173.6	185.9	167.3
3014	PA2991_sth_at	812.4	550.8	352.9	409.0	467.2
3015	PA2992_at	297.4	479.9	236.6	193.8	325.0
3016	PA2993_at	399.1	296.3	277.2	287.4	284.1
3017	PA2994_nqrF_at	297.7	324.5	419.4	377.8	419.6
3018	PA2995_nqrE_at	417.3	465.2	425.3	443.0	426.5
3019	PA2996_nqrD_at	322.6	352.4	568.1	503.6	457.4
3020	PA2997_nqrC_at	147.0	147.0	158.1	175.0	173.3
3021	PA2998_nqrB_at	364.5	308.4	425.1	417.0	365.9
3022	PA2999_nqrA_at	399.5	374.9	587.5	561.8	488.9
3023	PA3000_aroP1_at	56.4	69.3	85.3	85.0	108.5
3024	PA3001_at	2742.9	2234.2	1776.0	1810.5	1848.0
3025	PA3002_mfd_at	351.3	315.5	240.5	286.3	256.1
3026	PA3003_at	251.2	416.4	191.2	270.9	296.1
3027	PA3004_at	161.9	178.0	71.1	117.3	98.7
3028	PA3005_at	213.1	228.3	140.5	161.7	181.1
3029	PA3006_at	96.2	155.5	133.6	142.3	145.6
3030	PA3007_lexA_at	344.2	360.2	337.5	301.5	304.0
3031	PA3008_at	89.9	130.3	87.6	125.2	115.7
3032	PA3009_at	828.6	955.7	344.2	445.5	405.6
3033	PA3010_at	231.4	309.3	310.4	235.7	293.1
3034	PA3011_topA_at	514.6	636.0	948.8	846.0	574.3
3035	PA3012_at	69.5	104.3	125.5	96.7	126.3
3036	PA3013_foaB_at	276.9	272.2	250.9	282.0	283.2
3037	PA3014_faoA_at	502.9	596.1	266.1	360.2	399.2
3038	PA3015_at	118.8	87.9	139.4	99.2	100.1
3039	PA3016_at	58.9	31.8	50.4	19.3	35.4
3040	PA3017_at	149.9	154.4	219.6	209.6	147.4
3041	PA3018_at	49.8	21.0	69.9	59.7	47.3
3042	PA3019_at	135.9	171.1	173.5	170.7	219.2
3043	PA3020_at	173.2	147.2	174.7	169.6	154.8
3044	PA3021_at	626.9	743.2	748.4	492.1	455.7
3045	PA3022_at	198.4	190.4	167.4	177.7	194.8
3046	PA3023_at	10.6	31.7	67.3	31.5	39.5
3047	PA3024_at	37.7	34.8	49.0	30.0	30.6
3048	PA3025_at	31.1	39.8	96.9	60.5	58.6
3049	PA3026_at	55.5	58.0	122.9	95.4	101.1
3050	PA3027_at	152.4	159.8	180.5	184.4	189.8
3051	PA3028_moeA2_at	82.0	90.8	121.4	114.7	111.4
3052	PA3029_moab2_at	453.0	419.3	256.8	314.4	441.1
3053	PA3030_at	79.7	59.1	137.7	72.7	61.7
3054	PA3031_at	338.5	948.6	266.5	424.5	515.4
3055	PA3032_at	38.7	33.0	34.0	65.3	38.5
3056	PA3033_at	161.1	214.3	149.0	135.6	187.3
3057	PA3034_at	113.5	154.4	55.7	99.2	108.2
3058	PA3035_at	181.5	132.3	155.9	143.3	148.1

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3059	PA3036_at	27.0	37.0	37.2	11.8	31.7
3060	PA3037_at	32.8	36.0	23.9	54.4	48.0
3061	PA3038_at	1281.6	832.6	595.5	631.3	787.9
3062	PA3039_at	26.1	25.1	50.0	30.2	35.7
3063	PA3040_at	180.0	241.8	206.4	258.1	276.8
3064	PA3041_at	77.2	137.3	123.0	114.0	134.9
3065	PA3042_at	56.0	52.6	73.6	41.5	62.9
3066	PA3043_at	46.1	72.5	93.5	92.6	76.7
3067	PA3044_at	11.3	22.5	53.6	42.4	45.4
3068	PA3045_at	18.2	12.1	24.8	4.0	17.7
3069	PA3046_at	469.3	506.5	399.1	426.8	461.1
3070	PA3047_at	214.0	204.4	240.8	239.1	239.4
3071	PA3048_at	66.3	94.4	117.5	121.6	128.6
3072	PA3049_rmf_at	47.6	73.9	17.2	40.6	36.5
3073	PA3050_pyrD_at	392.5	514.0	621.0	432.1	498.9
3074	PA3051_at	7.2	54.5	18.5	23.7	40.8
3075	PA3052_at	131.6	157.2	123.2	124.3	146.5
3076	PA3053_at	95.7	119.3	118.7	100.1	100.1
3077	PA3054_at	42.7	77.9	97.8	97.6	81.1
3078	PA3055_at	253.7	306.4	407.5	403.9	334.5
3079	PA3056_at	103.0	119.4	112.0	79.5	134.5
3080	PA3057_at	32.8	27.7	20.5	21.1	24.0
3081	PA3058_at	49.1	31.5	86.4	48.4	51.3
3082	PA3059_at	44.8	49.0	78.9	106.7	67.7
3083	PA3060_at	43.1	29.3	66.4	76.9	53.5
3084	PA3061_at	35.5	53.8	74.1	95.2	84.3
3085	PA3062_at	30.9	24.4	71.9	71.5	44.6
3086	PA3063_at	19.8	25.1	70.2	9.4	41.3
3087	PA3064_at	5.6	8.0	11.6	5.6	15.1
3088	PA3065_at	17.8	11.0	14.9	5.3	27.3
3089	PA3066_at	20.3	39.8	24.8	33.0	40.7
3090	PA3067_at	97.7	75.1	132.8	77.5	80.1
3091	PA3068_at	3559.1	2603.4	3305.9	3044.1	2562.1
3092	PA3069_at	19.2	43.4	110.0	49.8	56.2
3093	PA3070_at	295.8	390.2	251.8	230.9	271.1
3094	PA3071_at	328.1	240.6	227.4	298.6	278.4
3095	PA3072_at	146.9	132.5	181.0	185.6	140.0
3096	PA3073_at	88.9	92.4	108.8	139.9	76.8
3097	PA3074_at	132.2	136.8	99.3	152.6	119.3
3098	PA3075_at	132.1	75.3	107.5	105.2	107.8
3099	PA3076_at	78.0	111.0	149.6	93.6	109.9
3100	PA3077_at	151.4	133.9	147.8	126.8	78.4
3101	PA3078_at	101.2	132.5	87.5	101.2	115.7
3102	PA3079_at	93.3	106.2	97.3	81.9	102.2
3103	PA3080_at	158.0	148.7	184.6	164.6	189.9
3104	PA3081_at	234.3	248.1	253.7	316.8	296.7
3105	PA3082_at	331.2	294.3	276.1	447.2	413.5
3106	PA3083_pepN_at	190.5	265.0	117.9	187.4	161.0
3107	PA3084_at	207.1	212.3	193.7	189.1	209.0
3108	PA3085_at	303.2	361.4	209.8	198.8	181.0
3109	PA3086_at	58.3	73.6	158.7	94.4	93.0
3110	PA3087_at	119.9	78.0	78.5	91.2	93.5
3111	PA3088_at	206.3	262.6	146.6	188.8	154.9
3112	PA3089_at	24.2	39.9	48.7	7.6	37.5
3113	PA3090_at	12.0	10.2	3.4	20.2	24.0
3114	PA3091_at	51.5	57.1	83.5	65.7	69.2
3115	PA3092_fadH1_at	48.0	76.4	60.8	63.7	65.2
3116	PA3093_at	103.8	130.2	233.0	295.2	246.0
3117	PA3094_at	128.4	96.4	117.8	84.9	123.4
3118	PA3095_xcpZ_at	80.6	56.1	110.0	69.7	80.7
3119	PA3096_xcpY_at	102.9	149.7	285.2	212.3	182.0
3120	PA3097_xcpX_at	51.0	85.0	73.8	88.6	115.5
3121	PA3098_xcpW_at	101.4	190.1	182.2	176.6	168.4
3122	PA3099_xcpV_at	193.6	204.4	397.1	331.5	264.8
3123	PA3100_xcpU_at	118.4	149.7	210.0	160.4	172.0
3124	PA3101_xcpT_at	244.5	379.9	490.1	452.1	387.2
3125	PA3102_xcpS_at	175.2	118.3	113.9	116.1	136.3
3126	PA3103_xcpR_at	166.3	227.5	243.6	227.9	216.3
3127	PA3104_xcpP_at	659.8	820.6	402.4	344.5	538.2
3128	PA3105_xcpQ_at	594.2	586.0	551.6	536.8	553.3
3129	PA3106_at	274.6	288.7	344.1	304.9	320.0
3130	PA3107_metZ_at	946.3	735.1	749.2	843.7	805.9
3131	PA3108_purF_at	720.2	642.8	601.5	762.4	844.2

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3132	PA3109_at	240.3	217.8	186.6	192.9	199.1
3133	PA3110_at	478.3	490.1	700.6	646.2	610.4
3134	PA3111_folC_at	475.5	412.5	696.8	625.0	596.3
3135	PA3112_accD_at	473.2	392.3	473.5	509.1	490.1
3136	PA3113_trpF_at	375.3	399.7	708.7	576.8	548.1
3137	PA3114_truA_at	261.2	194.8	235.4	246.1	251.5
3138	PA3115_at	952.2	1222.5	963.1	1023.3	876.4
3139	PA3116_at	295.6	315.5	370.5	403.5	410.8
3140	PA3117_asd_at	462.8	428.3	548.7	573.0	629.3
3141	PA3118_leuB_at	124.6	169.7	159.2	160.6	131.7
3142	PA3119_at	68.8	47.8	108.9	64.2	77.7
3143	PA3120_leuD_at	86.4	81.9	69.1	61.6	80.7
3144	PA3121_leuC_at	89.6	88.0	67.2	61.8	53.9
3145	PA3122_at	100.8	91.9	28.1	47.7	51.9
3146	PA3123_at	87.7	167.0	133.9	104.3	145.2
3147	PA3124_at	68.3	102.0	140.9	125.6	119.7
3148	PA3125_at	2.7	19.9	32.1	20.7	19.9
3149	PA3126_ibpA_at	107.6	178.5	34.6	44.2	51.9
3150	PA3127_at	61.1	56.1	84.3	79.4	77.0
3151	PA3128_at	35.6	58.6	85.2	69.2	65.3
3152	PA3129_at	185.3	146.7	322.4	270.7	242.7
3153	PA3130_at	104.6	96.9	124.5	137.4	125.9
3154	PA3131_at	112.6	138.0	148.0	108.9	145.6
3155	PA3132_at	56.5	39.9	87.8	60.8	68.0
3156	PA3133_at	32.7	35.7	37.4	47.2	82.9
3157	PA3134_gltX_at	756.2	719.9	756.3	814.5	771.3
3158	PA3135_at	100.9	81.2	36.5	65.3	72.5
3159	PA3136_at	67.4	36.9	44.7	41.7	44.7
3160	PA3137_at	5.5	19.4	55.6	26.4	18.6
3161	PA3138_uvrB_at	144.1	119.6	144.0	213.6	115.0
3162	PA3139_at	3396.7	1874.1	2866.6	2118.3	2106.7
3163	PA3140_at	12.0	12.9	14.6	18.3	9.5
3164	PA3141_wbpM_g_at	346.2	505.2	403.5	330.2	381.6
3165	PA3142_i_at	45.7	144.3	164.6	137.3	148.5
3166	PA3143_at	84.1	154.2	79.9	66.5	104.0
3167	PA3144_f_at	97.2	160.5	101.2	107.9	108.7
3168	PA3145_wbpL_at	190.5	312.1	316.0	259.0	342.4
3169	PA3146_wbpK_at	517.9	717.1	774.5	614.0	682.4
3170	PA3147_wbpJ_at	467.7	863.4	560.3	498.0	663.9
3171	PA3148_wbpI_at	227.4	337.1	629.2	421.6	379.7
3172	PA3149_wbpH_at	246.2	364.8	581.7	359.2	375.2
3173	PA3150_wbpG_at	166.0	333.5	221.1	182.0	236.8
3174	PA3151_hisF2_at	223.2	501.5	738.3	574.1	535.6
3175	PA3152_hisH2_at	206.9	484.7	288.2	300.0	384.6
3176	PA3153_wzx_at	40.7	80.1	76.5	48.5	66.6
3177	PA3154_wzy_at	50.5	78.4	156.4	72.1	97.0
3178	PA3155_wbpE_at	432.9	648.4	348.8	340.5	448.2
3179	PA3156_wbpD_at	357.9	377.2	275.0	307.7	418.2
3180	PA3157_at	106.8	198.8	115.8	82.0	124.9
3181	PA3158_wbpB_at	662.6	773.2	1120.2	787.2	814.3
3182	PA3159_wbpA_at	1004.3	945.2	1236.9	975.9	892.1
3183	PA3160_wzz_at	163.4	305.9	262.9	207.4	226.8
3184	PA3161_himD_at	233.7	300.2	290.8	321.7	342.1
3185	PA3162_rpsA_at	3979.2	2417.1	4457.1	3258.3	3387.6
3186	PA3163_cmK_at	424.8	396.4	559.9	470.5	405.2
3187	PA3164_at	536.3	486.0	608.7	510.9	477.7
3188	PA3165_hisC2_at	309.0	282.3	258.6	311.7	290.0
3189	PA3166_pheA_at	563.8	624.1	557.7	773.3	492.0
3190	PA3167_serC_at	841.3	795.2	573.6	495.8	577.4
3191	PA3168_gyrA_at	914.3	864.0	1005.0	976.3	1054.7
3192	PA3169_at	482.6	408.6	642.6	665.7	602.6
3193	PA3170_at	455.3	358.9	214.1	312.0	279.0
3194	PA3171_ubiG_at	473.2	415.4	524.1	492.0	431.5
3195	PA3172_at	575.8	513.0	466.7	463.5	484.1
3196	PA3173_at	319.1	382.7	292.1	358.2	367.2
3197	PA3174_at	24.7	43.5	42.0	37.5	37.7
3198	PA3175_at	29.1	26.9	58.3	54.3	46.7
3199	PA3176_gltS_at	32.2	17.2	33.4	26.9	23.8
3200	PA3177_at	115.8	139.6	209.3	205.4	195.7
3201	PA3178_at	70.6	67.0	126.5	137.4	77.8
3202	PA3179_at	383.2	542.0	437.6	453.3	521.4
3203	PA3180_at	4.4	34.8	35.6	46.4	30.9
3204	PA3181_at	1643.5	1162.7	1680.7	1643.3	1414.0

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3205	PA3182_at	4221.2	2676.8	4518.1	3261.4	3175.4
3206	PA3183_zwf_at	4081.6	2657.5	3993.6	3704.4	2902.8
3207	PA3184_at	139.8	108.0	182.7	187.2	167.8
3208	PA3185_at	185.4	136.1	259.8	211.9	221.5
3209	PA3187_at	2015.3	1557.0	2597.1	2856.7	2196.4
3210	PA3188_at	1344.3	1420.2	1474.2	1268.0	1549.8
3211	PA3189_at	975.3	682.9	935.6	966.9	1041.4
3212	PA3190_at	3449.6	1789.2	3776.9	3331.9	3160.0
3213	PA3191_at	235.6	236.7	227.3	207.3	231.6
3214	PA3192_gltR_at	438.4	542.8	479.0	515.4	557.1
3215	PA3193_glk_at	743.5	569.7	620.8	637.5	669.5
3216	PA3194_edd_at	1275.5	1038.9	1001.5	968.2	969.8
3217	PA3195_gapA_at	2518.4	1907.8	2067.6	2193.5	2047.1
3218	PA3196_at	130.2	112.5	89.1	118.5	115.9
3219	PA3197_at	201.9	279.8	217.4	213.1	219.4
3220	PA3198_at	83.8	150.9	166.0	120.3	113.8
3221	PA3199_at	136.5	221.6	114.7	150.7	191.6
3222	PA3200_at	94.7	101.7	82.4	97.7	116.1
3223	PA3201_at	304.3	395.0	516.3	346.7	304.0
3224	PA3202_at	589.6	678.6	581.6	575.8	716.9
3225	PA3203_at	447.6	413.1	433.9	454.7	435.0
3226	PA3204_at	326.6	354.5	378.3	381.8	354.2
3227	PA3205_at	397.9	696.8	591.6	487.9	396.4
3228	PA3206_at	86.9	67.1	78.0	59.1	85.7
3229	PA3207_at	42.5	83.0	86.0	70.5	88.9
3230	PA3208_at	186.6	220.7	135.8	200.5	246.7
3231	PA3209_at	130.0	153.9	270.7	254.5	199.1
3232	PA3210_trkH_at	164.3	194.8	105.5	115.0	152.2
3233	PA3211_at	158.6	176.7	193.0	167.7	203.4
3234	PA3212_at	348.6	214.8	357.2	373.9	283.5
3235	PA3213_at	329.0	311.3	257.0	299.2	230.2
3236	PA3214_at	187.5	182.9	246.2	239.8	191.8
3237	PA3215_at	66.2	75.4	34.3	38.2	65.5
3238	PA3216_at	22.1	17.2	41.1	24.7	33.2
3239	PA3217_at	157.6	173.9	176.2	191.6	180.4
3240	PA3218_at	2.2	12.5	6.0	5.1	29.2
3241	PA3219_at	35.4	20.0	28.2	55.1	29.9
3242	PA3220_at	146.0	139.7	107.6	140.6	140.1
3243	PA3221_csaA_at	429.4	290.4	110.2	156.5	169.4
3244	PA3222_at	209.3	143.2	120.4	140.3	107.3
3245	PA3223_acpD_at	29.6	27.8	47.2	33.4	25.4
3246	PA3224_at	104.2	132.9	77.0	74.1	122.6
3247	PA3225_at	169.6	191.1	159.7	175.2	172.8
3248	PA3226_at	150.3	132.5	170.2	147.4	158.6
3249	PA3227_ppiA_at	1010.4	637.5	635.0	775.0	802.7
3250	PA3228_at	178.3	163.2	128.7	160.0	128.7
3251	PA3229_at	29.1	27.6	41.5	41.6	31.0
3252	PA3230_at	45.1	57.1	57.4	60.1	60.9
3253	PA3231_at	20.1	10.6	13.8	16.1	20.2
3254	PA3232_at	115.5	64.8	92.3	89.9	79.4
3255	PA3233_at	110.9	52.6	119.4	80.2	107.0
3256	PA3234_at	394.2	151.2	203.1	223.5	285.3
3257	PA3235_at	279.0	145.8	189.5	183.0	262.7
3258	PA3236_at	35.1	33.3	41.0	32.0	38.8
3259	PA3237_at	5.0	5.9	11.6	19.1	10.1
3260	PA3238_at	182.8	152.4	150.0	222.7	207.9
3261	PA3239_at	271.5	255.8	231.2	266.9	254.1
3262	PA3240_at	51.7	41.8	77.4	63.0	68.2
3263	PA3241_at	57.4	50.0	81.1	104.9	85.1
3264	PA3242_at	85.5	101.8	113.1	105.2	114.4
3265	PA3243_minC_at	342.4	334.2	270.6	315.5	279.8
3266	PA3244_minD_at	965.0	880.2	1319.8	1368.8	1048.4
3267	PA3245_minE_at	561.5	814.4	533.2	579.0	598.0
3268	PA3246_rluA_at	545.9	501.1	615.4	589.7	496.3
3269	PA3247_at	266.9	300.2	166.2	218.9	162.7
3270	PA3248_at	51.2	54.3	68.2	55.3	50.8
3271	PA3249_at	2.6	1.1	3.0	3.0	4.1
3272	PA3250_at	92.9	114.8	53.7	79.6	100.6
3273	PA3251_at	43.2	45.1	72.9	68.8	49.5
3274	PA3252_at	22.1	23.6	17.6	4.7	24.3
3275	PA3253_at	28.6	21.3	23.8	25.0	42.0
3276	PA3254_at	29.1	32.6	63.0	46.0	46.8
3277	PA3255_at	133.5	104.0	138.1	123.9	124.4

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3278	PA3256_at	44.6	56.2	86.4	91.7	108.2
3279	PA3257_prc_at	1136.6	912.5	810.0	672.9	648.5
3280	PA3258_at	62.7	84.9	95.2	76.1	73.5
3281	PA3259_at	127.8	123.3	208.3	190.9	164.0
3282	PA3260_at	161.9	211.2	202.3	218.7	261.9
3283	PA3261_at	49.8	41.1	39.2	50.7	51.7
3284	PA3262_at	1357.7	1332.3	692.9	1053.3	1168.0
3285	PA3263_at	423.3	465.4	397.1	515.6	465.1
3286	PA3264_at	81.5	52.0	57.6	47.9	72.4
3287	PA3265_at	50.1	60.3	47.3	53.7	64.7
3288	PA3266_capB_at	135.3	141.1	146.4	152.0	160.9
3289	PA3267_at	131.8	115.1	180.2	159.2	141.3
3290	PA3268_at	77.3	54.3	167.9	172.0	169.9
3291	PA3269_at	51.5	83.8	37.3	51.4	56.5
3292	PA3270_at	368.7	255.0	283.4	315.2	383.6
3293	PA3271_at	191.0	74.4	84.0	88.2	84.8
3294	PA3272_at	74.0	76.5	80.2	80.0	61.5
3295	PA3273_at	3.3	2.8	52.2	4.1	12.8
3296	PA3274_at	3.5	15.1	11.9	4.2	11.0
3297	PA3275_at	41.0	46.9	141.6	112.2	73.9
3298	PA3276_at	95.1	121.2	120.3	90.9	121.3
3299	PA3277_at	16.8	41.7	56.7	31.7	33.7
3300	PA3278_at	2.7	8.5	29.4	21.5	21.9
3301	PA3279_oprP_at	24.5	9.7	27.9	29.5	16.7
3302	PA3280_oprO_at	12.9	31.9	24.3	5.6	19.6
3303	PA3281_at	15.3	15.3	41.8	12.1	16.2
3304	PA3282_at	52.7	6.3	40.0	14.8	23.6
3305	PA3283_at	28.3	33.6	46.3	34.9	30.8
3306	PA3284_at	77.7	102.9	90.6	79.3	89.8
3307	PA3285_at	164.5	264.0	281.3	270.0	311.5
3308	PA3286_at	463.6	505.2	352.6	453.5	472.3
3309	PA3287_at	54.5	64.3	49.8	70.5	65.1
3310	PA3288_at	42.6	44.3	59.7	59.1	39.5
3311	PA3289_at	32.2	40.6	39.9	8.4	35.4
3312	PA3290_at	84.5	84.6	88.1	98.3	83.0
3313	PA3291_at	25.2	46.3	16.1	23.3	22.2
3314	PA3292_at	26.8	18.0	52.5	33.8	20.6
3315	PA3293_at	50.2	42.6	48.1	56.2	58.7
3316	PA3294_s_at	110.8	96.1	117.2	89.2	97.6
3317	PA3295_at	134.2	188.9	81.6	120.6	150.7
3318	PA3296_phoA_at	84.3	36.2	73.7	45.2	42.3
3319	PA3297_at	233.1	256.0	143.0	189.8	171.4
3320	PA3298_at	40.5	49.1	93.6	70.4	57.1
3321	PA3299_fadD1_at	584.2	430.1	611.8	540.1	602.3
3322	PA3300_fadD2_at	77.1	80.0	106.2	76.6	96.1
3323	PA3301_at	356.1	259.5	218.6	288.7	306.7
3324	PA3302_at	208.6	230.3	189.1	218.5	253.3
3325	PA3303_at	31.6	25.1	44.6	46.5	34.8
3326	PA3304_at	78.6	76.3	74.9	63.3	66.8
3327	PA3305_at	69.4	68.0	95.6	83.7	48.3
3328	PA3306_at	168.9	205.8	231.7	217.3	198.4
3329	PA3307_r_at	140.2	117.3	221.8	173.7	115.7
3330	PA3308_hepA_at	550.1	466.6	522.6	575.5	627.1
3331	PA3309_at	24.8	54.1	73.8	57.9	49.3
3332	PA3310_at	363.1	391.2	188.6	228.1	297.4
3333	PA3311_at	7.5	3.7	10.5	4.0	29.6
3334	PA3312_at	74.0	50.0	186.8	130.4	124.8
3335	PA3313_at	880.7	720.5	543.8	903.9	853.1
3336	PA3314_at	368.2	379.1	579.4	540.4	516.2
3337	PA3315_at	81.8	68.3	158.2	88.2	92.1
3338	PA3316_at	113.3	50.9	91.9	66.8	80.0
3339	PA3317_at	145.6	115.1	139.6	129.7	125.0
3340	PA3318_at	49.8	39.6	53.4	43.5	43.6
3341	PA3319_plcN_at	3.2	18.4	31.9	27.0	16.6
3342	PA3320_at	1.1	6.0	6.2	2.2	11.1
3343	PA3321_at	66.8	49.9	96.1	107.2	98.4
3344	PA3322_at	144.1	124.4	150.4	125.6	151.1
3345	PA3323_at	56.7	49.3	49.5	36.1	48.3
3346	PA3324_at	26.9	16.1	45.9	6.7	15.5
3347	PA3325_at	59.3	24.2	59.0	29.9	52.7
3348	PA3326_at	656.1	916.6	993.5	971.7	876.0
3349	PA3327_at	170.2	248.8	384.4	383.2	295.6
3350	PA3328_at	100.3	313.8	212.9	217.8	195.8

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3351	PA3329_at	136.4	344.7	191.1	207.4	163.9
3352	PA3330_at	135.1	441.7	147.8	174.7	197.0
3353	PA3331_at	276.5	832.7	373.1	421.3	457.8
3354	PA3332_at	274.0	551.3	359.2	403.8	372.3
3355	PA3333_fabH2_at	119.9	336.0	185.7	200.1	207.8
3356	PA3334_at	89.8	242.1	216.3	161.3	181.4
3357	PA3335_at	46.0	101.9	73.0	90.9	89.2
3358	PA3336_at	28.3	62.8	13.9	51.5	46.5
3359	PA3337_rfaD_at	2.6	16.2	10.2	4.4	33.0
3360	PA3338_at	53.7	53.2	49.6	39.4	42.6
3361	PA3339_at	100.2	87.6	92.4	94.1	92.9
3362	PA3340_at	215.0	221.3	192.7	199.0	259.5
3363	PA3341_at	126.7	156.6	142.1	194.1	145.4
3364	PA3342_at	56.9	34.5	21.0	41.3	28.2
3365	PA3343_at	8.2	44.0	59.0	56.4	57.6
3366	PA3344_recQ_at	204.1	155.9	277.3	261.1	205.9
3367	PA3345_at	158.1	177.3	271.7	249.4	206.9
3368	PA3346_at	41.3	49.3	55.6	34.1	48.1
3369	PA3347_at	140.4	158.4	71.2	113.4	114.8
3370	PA3348_at	317.5	326.5	418.8	381.7	411.2
3371	PA3349_at	547.6	537.8	567.4	564.1	522.9
3372	PA3350_at	123.7	109.6	132.1	101.1	146.9
3373	PA3351_at	3174.9	2329.5	1644.0	1889.3	1862.9
3374	PA3352_at	974.5	800.9	778.5	818.4	749.8
3375	PA3353_at	403.2	356.4	428.2	340.5	312.2
3376	PA3354_at	54.7	62.3	85.3	78.0	87.4
3377	PA3355_at	90.9	67.3	122.4	86.4	77.7
3378	PA3356_at	846.8	1032.5	562.3	440.3	537.1
3379	PA3357_dsdA_at	288.5	223.3	149.1	184.3	209.6
3380	PA3358_at	33.5	35.6	132.2	89.0	54.0
3381	PA3359_at	4.4	2.6	18.3	7.8	2.5
3382	PA3360_at	4.5	5.6	29.3	8.1	5.6
3383	PA3361_at	64.1	105.3	95.9	56.5	78.6
3384	PA3362_at	37.7	19.8	81.5	37.2	28.0
3385	PA3363_amiR_at	46.7	91.3	67.5	58.1	77.9
3386	PA3364_amiC_at	56.5	39.3	61.5	69.7	58.2
3387	PA3365_at	39.7	80.6	90.8	84.4	109.8
3388	PA3366_amiE_at	45.1	95.7	125.3	96.0	96.1
3389	PA3367_at	19.9	19.4	33.2	25.6	28.4
3390	PA3368_at	27.7	26.2	34.8	41.3	30.6
3391	PA3369_at	65.0	63.3	60.8	70.1	56.2
3392	PA3370_at	16.7	33.8	46.3	32.3	16.3
3393	PA3371_at	12.5	38.2	49.4	49.8	54.0
3394	PA3372_at	74.4	56.3	82.1	72.1	52.6
3395	PA3373_at	120.4	99.0	159.4	155.9	96.4
3396	PA3374_at	5.6	25.9	22.0	26.7	29.6
3397	PA3375_at	27.0	14.8	81.2	41.3	32.8
3398	PA3376_at	3.0	4.6	26.1	4.6	3.4
3399	PA3377_at	46.7	23.5	61.6	25.8	31.3
3400	PA3378_at	26.1	22.0	36.4	28.3	25.6
3401	PA3379_at	4.2	5.0	8.5	5.1	16.2
3402	PA3380_at	22.7	2.6	7.5	21.3	8.6
3403	PA3381_at	50.2	34.9	57.0	45.0	46.3
3404	PA3382_phnE_at	2.0	1.5	2.9	4.0	9.6
3405	PA3383_at	6.5	18.0	7.0	7.5	17.2
3406	PA3384_phnC_at	19.2	25.7	35.6	20.5	26.2
3407	PA3385_at	1521.2	1457.0	919.6	1155.9	1189.6
3408	PA3386_at	12.7	19.1	16.9	28.6	33.6
3409	PA3387_rhlG_at	35.7	45.9	81.4	58.4	40.0
3410	PA3388_at	198.0	151.4	190.8	222.9	194.4
3411	PA3389_at	33.1	22.5	74.7	21.7	47.8
3412	PA3390_at	34.5	27.5	57.1	25.6	23.9
3413	PA3391_nosR_at	23.3	7.5	9.7	6.8	18.0
3414	PA3392_nosZ_at	5.8	9.9	22.9	20.0	35.3
3415	PA3393_nosD_at	4.9	17.9	63.5	50.7	31.4
3416	PA3394_nosF_at	4.5	11.1	31.2	15.6	30.2
3417	PA3395_nosY_at	4.3	7.3	20.6	9.0	24.1
3418	PA3396_nosL_at	19.9	31.2	55.6	28.5	55.1
3419	PA3397_fpr_at	354.8	589.9	356.2	586.7	641.7
3420	PA3398_at	80.7	72.6	93.3	76.3	100.6
3421	PA3399_at	20.3	48.4	74.5	57.0	61.5
3422	PA3400_at	51.1	45.3	65.2	55.8	65.9
3423	PA3401_at	93.8	84.1	75.2	56.1	64.2

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3424	PA3402_at	62.6	95.3	68.1	93.9	97.9
3425	PA3403_at	162.3	137.6	202.4	166.1	160.4
3426	PA3404_at	8.4	22.3	51.5	64.3	37.4
3427	PA3405_hasE_at	4.4	17.4	18.4	34.5	26.4
3428	PA3406_hasD_at	14.1	28.4	27.1	22.0	48.8
3429	PA3407_hasAp_at	1.9	4.4	3.6	3.1	4.7
3430	PA3408_hasR_at	9.3	20.5	50.0	23.9	47.1
3431	PA3409_at	24.6	26.7	53.3	32.6	41.3
3432	PA3410_at	55.0	51.5	105.4	75.9	91.5
3433	PA3411_r_at	59.8	52.3	86.7	51.3	51.9
3434	PA3412_at	15.7	9.5	29.2	4.3	26.9
3435	PA3413_at	99.3	193.7	275.5	206.9	172.6
3436	PA3414_at	38.8	28.6	54.6	26.6	44.6
3437	PA3415_at	49.7	20.1	84.7	33.1	36.4
3438	PA3416_at	4.5	2.8	8.3	5.2	22.6
3439	PA3417_at	5.5	18.7	39.4	33.9	30.1
3440	PA3418_ldh_at	46.7	46.9	69.3	38.7	65.1
3441	PA3419_at	54.8	65.8	107.6	61.2	78.4
3442	PA3420_at	13.5	19.9	44.0	33.7	39.7
3443	PA3421_at	43.2	9.3	26.9	5.8	12.5
3444	PA3422_at	16.7	2.3	48.1	18.7	15.6
3445	PA3423_at	51.4	73.9	73.0	65.3	66.2
3446	PA3424_at	40.3	22.3	32.5	44.9	29.0
3447	PA3425_at	30.6	36.6	61.3	56.4	77.6
3448	PA3426_at	37.7	39.8	59.1	52.1	52.2
3449	PA3427_at	2.2	22.1	3.2	8.2	25.3
3450	PA3428_at	8.5	2.8	29.0	30.0	17.9
3451	PA3429_at	37.9	13.0	66.2	16.8	35.5
3452	PA3430_at	4.0	25.8	20.8	12.9	23.0
3453	PA3431_at	8.9	24.9	72.9	56.5	72.9
3454	PA3432_i_at	33.8	28.6	55.9	29.6	38.4
3455	PA3433_at	24.5	38.5	25.0	46.7	42.1
3456	PA3435_at	444.1	348.4	355.2	419.7	450.4
3457	PA3436_at	221.1	165.9	76.2	110.5	67.1
3458	PA3437_at	234.7	220.7	234.5	224.8	199.9
3459	PA3438_folE1_at	171.6	217.0	96.9	119.8	119.2
3460	PA3439_folX_at	470.4	512.2	100.5	196.5	240.0
3461	PA3440_at	1690.8	1391.4	1175.1	1237.9	1280.6
3462	PA3441_at	43.6	58.3	34.1	46.3	40.5
3463	PA3442_at	5.6	56.1	27.1	34.0	68.2
3464	PA3443_at	7.4	63.3	70.2	50.0	51.4
3465	PA3444_at	22.3	88.0	36.3	26.4	41.5
3466	PA3445_at	19.6	138.8	74.0	59.1	50.8
3467	PA3446_at	53.5	419.1	172.0	284.0	230.1
3468	PA3447_at	22.3	12.0	20.3	21.1	14.4
3469	PA3448_at	26.4	10.1	12.8	16.8	12.1
3470	PA3449_at	24.4	7.7	33.1	3.1	23.1
3471	PA3450_at	199.1	725.3	436.7	594.7	485.9
3472	PA3451_at	1.7	22.1	2.8	4.7	17.8
3473	PA3452_mqoA_at	581.3	416.6	402.9	545.3	457.7
3474	PA3453_at	252.3	260.8	312.0	343.9	330.7
3475	PA3454_at	25.3	37.6	11.9	48.3	36.2
3476	PA3455_at	141.5	144.8	102.2	102.1	126.3
3477	PA3456_at	156.5	127.0	112.1	135.7	118.1
3478	PA3457_at	7.7	35.7	74.6	58.9	47.1
3479	PA3458_at	62.2	47.8	78.4	57.8	69.5
3480	PA3459_at	35.8	34.3	10.4	41.8	40.8
3481	PA3460_at	18.5	13.6	19.6	19.6	27.8
3482	PA3461_at	3.2	13.7	40.1	18.0	37.0
3483	PA3462_at	42.8	23.5	28.4	14.3	36.7
3484	PA3463_at	167.2	212.7	237.4	228.4	259.3
3485	PA3464_at	35.0	21.5	45.0	53.4	34.7
3486	PA3465_at	24.2	10.4	19.1	5.3	25.1
3487	PA3466_at	226.1	215.9	247.9	266.6	271.2
3488	PA3467_at	3.0	1.6	35.4	8.0	4.4
3489	PA3468_at	174.7	161.8	178.1	158.5	156.9
3490	PA3469_at	106.5	104.3	83.8	107.6	109.3
3491	PA3470_i_at	101.4	86.7	79.7	89.4	90.1
3492	PA3471_at	243.8	250.0	156.5	187.3	219.0
3493	PA3472_at	73.7	75.0	38.8	52.2	70.3
3494	PA3473_at	55.2	62.4	75.3	89.8	97.0
3495	PA3474_at	91.9	62.6	126.6	75.1	86.6
3496	PA3475_pheC_at	99.7	155.1	153.9	151.9	149.9

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3497	PA3476_rhlL_at	394.8	537.7	466.3	556.6	643.0
3498	PA3477_rhlR_at	318.2	383.2	545.0	516.1	527.8
3499	PA3478_rhlB_at	67.5	79.3	113.4	120.2	97.5
3500	PA3479_rhlA_at	42.6	152.7	136.3	133.7	195.8
3501	PA3480_at	809.4	700.2	382.0	512.5	507.5
3502	PA3481_at	363.8	411.2	646.9	433.0	485.7
3503	PA3482_metG_at	1172.6	1175.2	1160.5	1294.3	1235.2
3504	PA3483_at	357.5	261.9	234.9	309.1	207.0
3505	PA3484_at	291.2	317.3	206.9	185.3	154.6
3506	PA3485_r_at	186.1	147.2	233.9	249.9	173.9
3507	PA3486_at	77.7	44.8	46.8	50.3	57.2
3508	PA3487_at	70.0	111.9	109.5	86.2	71.0
3509	PA3488_at	192.5	152.4	291.4	169.0	209.3
3510	PA3489_at	155.6	133.5	164.3	155.2	171.3
3511	PA3490_at	141.2	108.1	180.3	204.3	136.6
3512	PA3491_at	380.7	364.9	573.1	481.3	380.6
3513	PA3492_at	63.8	73.9	154.0	121.7	112.0
3514	PA3493_at	81.5	84.6	138.9	109.9	80.9
3515	PA3494_at	100.2	71.9	128.8	95.2	102.9
3516	PA3495_nth_at	89.6	213.0	150.6	141.2	147.9
3517	PA3496_at	191.9	385.7	165.8	138.0	136.0
3518	PA3497_at	61.3	23.2	86.0	29.5	44.4
3519	PA3498_at	7.6	11.3	47.3	47.5	16.4
3520	PA3499_at	72.8	98.1	68.4	72.7	71.6
3521	PA3500_at	69.4	84.2	77.6	115.0	87.5
3522	PA3501_at	27.8	80.8	94.8	65.4	81.8
3523	PA3502_at	43.0	79.9	65.0	48.5	47.9
3524	PA3503_at	26.6	41.3	55.4	56.7	72.6
3525	PA3504_at	61.1	28.7	51.2	34.6	41.9
3526	PA3505_at	64.9	46.3	83.9	46.1	65.0
3527	PA3506_at	6.7	15.6	21.5	32.2	45.4
3528	PA3507_at	8.5	52.7	57.6	5.6	37.5
3529	PA3508_at	39.6	33.5	50.8	48.7	39.4
3530	PA3509_at	25.1	48.5	38.8	41.6	52.9
3531	PA3510_at	50.0	60.8	78.4	77.2	65.7
3532	PA3511_at	95.9	52.1	64.2	67.6	40.9
3533	PA3512_at	5.8	22.6	14.1	13.6	36.8
3534	PA3513_at	1.8	8.9	12.3	6.6	13.7
3535	PA3514_at	33.7	23.8	47.4	37.3	44.8
3536	PA3515_at	9.5	16.3	22.5	40.2	27.7
3537	PA3516_at	2.9	26.0	142.2	84.1	74.0
3538	PA3517_at	54.5	40.1	146.4	101.4	70.7
3539	PA3518_at	7.8	15.2	54.9	27.0	29.3
3540	PA3519_at	20.9	30.5	133.1	85.3	83.6
3541	PA3520_at	6.2	26.9	27.7	16.0	29.3
3542	PA3521_at	4.8	3.8	6.6	12.9	6.7
3543	PA3522_at	16.6	14.8	29.8	22.8	20.9
3544	PA3523_at	2.6	9.3	26.9	27.1	39.0
3545	PA3524_gloA1_at	620.3	667.4	462.2	609.7	574.9
3546	PA3525_argG_at	849.8	978.6	904.2	997.7	977.8
3547	PA3526_at	234.5	215.7	93.0	229.4	175.2
3548	PA3527_pyrC_at	585.4	616.6	286.8	335.3	399.3
3549	PA3528_rnt_at	681.2	768.1	393.7	547.1	502.9
3550	PA3529_at	1513.9	1088.7	927.3	1159.7	1304.6
3551	PA3530_at	10.5	27.3	60.1	66.4	76.8
3552	PA3531_bfrB_at	5712.8	2282.0	185.2	196.2	219.9
3553	PA3532_at	54.9	65.1	55.3	44.5	67.7
3554	PA3533_at	751.9	1076.4	607.1	927.3	829.2
3555	PA3534_at	53.7	49.2	48.9	13.8	53.0
3556	PA3535_at	345.2	335.0	430.3	487.8	397.8
3557	PA3536_at	73.1	103.2	168.5	106.2	112.1
3558	PA3537_argF_at	176.3	174.5	321.1	308.6	258.7
3559	PA3538_at	199.6	226.7	303.8	226.7	208.1
3560	PA3539_at	137.0	145.1	126.7	145.4	133.1
3561	PA3540_algD_at	5.5	24.0	45.5	24.7	25.8
3562	PA3541_at	2.3	11.5	3.3	21.7	20.7
3563	PA3542_at	28.7	41.8	56.7	28.1	37.2
3564	PA3543_algK_at	2.7	1.0	2.6	2.9	1.6
3565	PA3544_algE_at	32.0	13.1	26.5	15.0	24.2
3566	PA3545_algG_at	52.0	14.7	30.2	13.7	26.3
3567	PA3546_algX_at	12.1	30.6	56.1	39.5	60.6
3568	PA3547_algL_at	32.3	11.9	36.3	44.6	27.7
3569	PA3548_algI_at	15.9	9.4	16.8	10.7	11.3

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3570	PA3549_algJ_at	58.9	27.3	80.8	48.1	39.3
3571	PA3550_algF_at	25.8	37.7	44.2	60.6	28.5
3572	PA3551_algA_at	65.5	53.6	50.7	58.9	43.5
3573	PA3552_at	208.4	518.4	250.2	330.9	296.5
3574	PA3553_at	122.2	269.0	158.7	172.6	141.4
3575	PA3554_at	283.3	524.6	270.6	328.8	305.7
3576	PA3555_at	67.8	105.3	76.7	82.1	93.4
3577	PA3556_at	108.7	185.3	114.3	117.1	137.6
3578	PA3557_at	29.4	57.4	84.7	53.2	48.8
3579	PA3558_at	78.7	210.8	183.4	139.6	158.5
3580	PA3559_at	144.7	337.7	118.9	140.8	133.5
3581	PA3560_fruA_at	246.0	168.2	364.6	271.0	266.4
3582	PA3561_fruK_at	902.4	787.8	1000.2	699.0	830.2
3583	PA3562_at	566.9	448.9	472.0	563.1	527.1
3584	PA3563_fruR_at	411.2	489.3	325.6	311.6	326.2
3585	PA3564_at	26.7	47.0	66.7	67.3	50.7
3586	PA3565_at	51.7	41.5	50.8	93.1	59.3
3587	PA3566_at	256.3	349.9	319.8	245.7	307.3
3588	PA3567_at	161.2	201.6	207.5	183.5	225.1
3589	PA3568_at	40.6	20.3	46.2	43.6	36.5
3590	PA3569_mmsB_at	24.7	31.9	37.7	56.7	54.0
3591	PA3570_mmsA_at	67.3	69.9	113.7	108.3	120.4
3592	PA3571_mmsR_at	27.1	47.8	47.1	29.5	70.6
3593	PA3572_at	16.5	31.5	40.4	19.4	31.0
3594	PA3573_at	39.6	34.9	35.2	40.2	42.5
3595	PA3574_at	78.8	102.4	99.9	108.5	103.2
3596	PA3575_at	100.6	83.9	94.8	87.1	112.1
3597	PA3576_at	56.2	83.2	87.1	60.5	71.3
3598	PA3577_i_at	89.5	129.6	75.8	69.1	75.4
3599	PA3578_at	66.5	79.0	96.3	94.6	110.2
3600	PA3579_at	94.4	90.2	76.9	90.6	74.0
3601	PA3580_at	145.7	106.1	109.2	131.2	128.1
3602	PA3581_glpF_at	238.5	109.2	170.5	91.0	70.2
3603	PA3582_glpK_at	329.6	236.7	158.8	157.3	205.2
3604	PA3583_glpR_at	358.1	230.6	310.5	317.1	249.3
3605	PA3584_glpD_at	416.6	138.9	171.2	73.6	82.1
3606	PA3585_glpM_at	117.7	120.3	34.4	55.3	85.7
3607	PA3586_at	3.0	8.8	27.6	9.0	29.7
3608	PA3587_metR_at	105.0	122.0	114.4	120.2	110.4
3609	PA3588_at	10.2	14.3	50.0	24.9	17.6
3610	PA3589_at	5.6	3.9	2.8	3.0	15.4
3611	PA3590_at	23.4	21.6	27.8	5.4	36.5
3612	PA3591_at	1.8	9.1	37.9	15.1	24.1
3613	PA3592_at	36.4	35.9	30.6	25.4	28.6
3614	PA3593_at	22.6	27.5	39.3	30.3	21.9
3615	PA3594_at	46.9	49.0	63.6	49.5	51.4
3616	PA3595_at	19.1	10.8	7.2	18.6	18.4
3617	PA3596_at	6.7	27.9	28.6	17.3	31.6
3618	PA3597_at	15.3	8.9	12.1	32.7	22.4
3619	PA3598_at	12.2	26.2	66.2	15.0	42.6
3620	PA3599_at	79.6	55.1	44.6	51.0	60.1
3621	PA3600_at	2.4	2.9	10.6	4.9	28.4
3622	PA3601_at	14.6	35.6	91.8	56.1	58.0
3623	PA3602_at	208.8	320.6	238.0	180.8	167.8
3624	PA3603_dgkA_at	268.9	251.2	325.6	260.5	245.0
3625	PA3604_at	584.4	511.5	664.0	684.6	683.6
3626	PA3605_at	78.9	76.8	56.6	61.7	70.7
3627	PA3606_at	113.4	93.6	158.8	154.3	133.0
3628	PA3607_potA_at	150.4	188.9	289.1	243.0	266.5
3629	PA3608_potB_at	73.4	110.4	91.1	125.0	131.5
3630	PA3609_potC_at	125.4	143.8	267.3	244.7	183.8
3631	PA3610_potD_at	203.3	176.3	163.6	165.0	152.5
3632	PA3611_at	482.6	632.0	330.3	421.2	541.4
3633	PA3612_at	244.6	300.2	206.8	240.1	284.1
3634	PA3613_at	12.8	26.4	41.1	24.4	44.6
3635	PA3614_at	141.4	80.8	80.4	84.4	77.4
3636	PA3615_at	137.1	113.0	105.5	111.7	108.7
3637	PA3616_at	141.3	122.0	189.6	189.2	198.6
3638	PA3617_recA_at	670.1	611.6	638.5	597.6	637.5
3639	PA3618_at	154.8	159.9	208.3	218.7	237.0
3640	PA3619_at	31.0	12.0	33.6	25.2	7.7
3641	PA3620_mutS_at	595.9	391.5	329.2	332.1	327.2
3642	PA3621_fdxA_at	614.3	1161.5	380.3	706.4	788.6

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3643	PA3622_rpoS_at	1131.7	1036.8	808.7	913.5	974.0
3644	PA3623_at	178.1	156.0	187.5	168.0	166.3
3645	PA3624_pcm_at	502.1	507.4	613.5	634.5	561.2
3646	PA3625_surE_at	1086.0	773.9	1075.0	1066.2	1049.1
3647	PA3626_at	199.5	200.4	206.3	212.6	199.4
3648	PA3627_at	283.4	262.3	158.0	239.1	245.2
3649	PA3628_at	163.0	123.2	204.3	179.3	216.9
3650	PA3629_adhC_at	128.3	202.2	136.9	212.9	196.4
3651	PA3630_at	27.1	16.8	39.1	26.9	28.1
3652	PA3631_at	151.5	144.7	286.3	330.9	242.7
3653	PA3632_at	242.4	278.3	222.6	256.7	281.1
3654	PA3633_at	330.7	310.2	269.3	321.2	323.3
3655	PA3634_at	683.1	1065.5	628.7	719.0	675.5
3656	PA3635_eno_at	1479.8	1271.1	1367.6	1551.3	1353.6
3657	PA3636_kdsA_at	603.8	690.1	445.6	460.7	446.7
3658	PA3637_pyrG_at	2120.4	1442.5	1371.5	1609.8	1280.2
3659	PA3638_at	128.1	222.8	266.3	256.8	281.9
3660	PA3639_accA_at	544.9	436.1	460.9	465.1	559.7
3661	PA3640_dnaE_at	574.0	637.1	468.6	570.9	491.4
3662	PA3641_at	366.8	475.2	522.6	518.6	675.5
3663	PA3642_rnhB_at	184.9	293.8	589.5	480.9	484.1
3664	PA3643_lpxB_at	458.9	421.9	774.9	575.9	608.3
3665	PA3644_lpxA_at	1281.4	1265.4	1012.9	1091.8	1022.7
3666	PA3645_fabZ_at	1853.3	1518.2	1426.1	1539.4	1628.5
3667	PA3646_lpxD_at	1819.0	1427.6	1659.5	1585.4	1422.0
3668	PA3647_at	2071.1	1699.9	2306.8	2337.6	1932.7
3669	PA3648_at	1190.9	1129.8	834.3	866.3	842.4
3670	PA3649_at	161.1	186.6	181.3	208.5	199.8
3671	PA3650_dxr_at	226.2	255.1	509.6	471.1	405.5
3672	PA3651_cdsA_at	220.3	239.1	282.7	259.1	293.2
3673	PA3652_uppS_at	746.6	507.6	662.5	799.1	781.3
3674	PA3653_frr_at	1512.7	1989.5	2957.8	2458.8	2332.4
3675	PA3654_pyrH_at	1606.1	1061.2	2038.2	1739.6	1602.0
3676	PA3655_tsf_at	1758.3	1607.2	3290.5	2530.6	2229.0
3677	PA3656_rpsB_at	5974.5	3590.0	4051.8	4392.5	4051.7
3678	PA3657_map_at	1024.6	1007.4	774.5	798.4	996.7
3679	PA3658_glnD_at	191.7	187.6	194.0	163.0	167.3
3680	PA3659_at	317.7	348.3	469.3	424.6	374.2
3681	PA3660_at	67.6	47.1	77.9	82.9	73.7
3682	PA3661_at	75.7	50.2	64.6	74.0	73.1
3683	PA3662_at	200.5	293.1	261.2	312.2	307.8
3684	PA3663_at	51.2	70.7	98.6	73.9	99.7
3685	PA3664_at	381.6	401.0	325.6	562.9	472.5
3686	PA3665_at	361.9	299.7	699.4	622.0	518.6
3687	PA3666_dapD_at	689.0	588.8	811.3	674.7	607.4
3688	PA3667_at	151.1	116.6	150.6	115.3	139.6
3689	PA3668_at	91.7	84.3	103.0	78.0	88.4
3690	PA3669_at	6.5	28.0	34.6	20.0	28.1
3691	PA3670_at	92.3	87.4	92.1	111.2	100.1
3692	PA3671_at	50.6	34.8	83.3	66.8	70.4
3693	PA3672_at	93.3	97.0	100.3	107.7	108.0
3694	PA3673_plsB_at	318.0	319.4	249.2	251.0	264.3
3695	PA3674_at	272.4	271.0	205.8	272.4	255.0
3696	PA3675_at	267.6	249.4	190.8	197.7	260.5
3697	PA3676_at	107.1	207.5	666.8	492.4	532.1
3698	PA3677_at	65.5	89.8	239.4	187.8	188.5
3699	PA3678_at	107.2	136.8	168.7	149.3	161.7
3700	PA3679_at	75.2	88.8	121.2	86.0	81.0
3701	PA3680_at	66.2	99.8	34.4	88.5	65.3
3702	PA3681_at	6.0	32.0	33.2	33.5	25.1
3703	PA3682_at	1.8	23.4	39.7	24.6	26.0
3704	PA3683_at	111.3	124.1	147.9	154.6	168.8
3705	PA3684_i_at	125.3	190.0	288.5	195.6	224.9
3706	PA3685_at	115.1	85.7	172.7	115.1	151.2
3707	PA3686_adk_at	570.2	641.1	532.8	637.6	646.6
3708	PA3687_ppc_at	101.2	124.4	157.0	143.7	162.7
3709	PA3688_at	45.6	44.5	51.6	56.2	42.8
3710	PA3689_at	95.1	107.3	124.1	106.5	113.8
3711	PA3690_at	109.1	180.9	128.8	154.9	143.5
3712	PA3691_at	129.8	194.6	115.1	117.8	117.8
3713	PA3692_at	64.9	84.5	62.3	63.3	76.8
3714	PA3693_at	82.3	81.7	98.0	104.7	73.4
3715	PA3694_at	171.1	207.2	182.6	152.2	191.4

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3716	PA3695_at	117.1	125.2	170.9	170.5	155.3
3717	PA3696_at	76.6	87.7	106.8	70.3	81.7
3718	PA3697_at	266.3	251.0	368.5	303.8	270.9
3719	PA3698_at	101.2	116.5	95.1	116.7	102.8
3720	PA3699_at	148.4	116.6	135.2	135.3	186.3
3721	PA3700_lyssS_at	1687.7	1431.5	993.1	1410.1	1305.7
3722	PA3701_prfB_at	1265.1	961.2	1050.3	1044.4	1066.7
3723	PA3702_at	112.1	136.6	200.8	147.5	150.6
3724	PA3703_at	135.5	135.3	211.3	131.6	130.1
3725	PA3704_at	122.6	108.0	134.7	133.3	122.1
3726	PA3705_at	201.0	152.0	204.6	184.3	169.0
3727	PA3706_at	59.2	54.2	50.5	56.5	58.4
3728	PA3707_at	65.4	32.4	97.2	64.7	83.3
3729	PA3708_at	182.7	149.0	111.2	102.4	119.2
3730	PA3709_at	24.9	13.0	5.0	7.9	6.7
3731	PA3710_at	20.4	34.9	60.6	24.3	62.7
3732	PA3711_at	61.9	28.9	26.7	37.4	37.7
3733	PA3712_at	96.5	157.1	248.1	175.0	187.0
3734	PA3713_at	73.8	59.4	45.9	45.6	70.5
3735	PA3714_at	38.1	44.4	69.5	65.1	68.6
3736	PA3715_at	30.3	42.0	34.8	44.5	40.1
3737	PA3716_at	512.6	370.0	486.4	432.3	374.4
3738	PA3717_at	193.4	208.9	109.0	151.2	191.0
3739	PA3718_at	18.7	18.2	39.0	18.1	40.1
3740	PA3719_at	5.8	42.3	103.0	93.3	85.5
3741	PA3720_at	13.8	17.4	57.0	28.2	55.2
3742	PA3721_at	7.5	36.6	71.8	46.4	53.0
3743	PA3722_at	540.6	504.7	275.7	367.5	377.9
3744	PA3723_at	52.6	107.7	157.1	130.2	142.9
3745	PA3724_lasB_at	353.7	741.3	437.1	576.4	687.3
3746	PA3725_recJ_at	198.8	184.1	211.2	226.2	265.7
3747	PA3726_at	182.3	179.5	240.1	200.7	203.8
3748	PA3727_at	60.4	119.6	109.4	103.9	81.0
3749	PA3728_at	107.6	120.8	132.9	138.1	111.7
3750	PA3729_at	457.8	443.8	375.8	398.6	347.1
3751	PA3730_at	157.7	120.6	120.0	121.0	124.6
3752	PA3731_at	452.3	565.9	537.0	505.2	464.7
3753	PA3732_at	392.5	362.5	418.3	435.6	354.9
3754	PA3733_at	9.5	48.9	4.2	19.5	41.4
3755	PA3734_at	41.2	25.5	19.7	28.0	38.8
3756	PA3735_thrC_at	576.8	657.3	627.1	584.8	478.3
3757	PA3736_hom_at	1479.3	1009.6	1559.0	1523.9	1305.0
3758	PA3737_dsbC_at	500.9	634.5	363.4	448.7	470.2
3759	PA3738_xerD_at	146.1	108.4	126.8	122.3	115.5
3760	PA3739_at	28.8	47.3	90.1	55.6	74.1
3761	PA3740_at	101.8	162.0	129.4	106.1	112.5
3762	PA3741_at	109.1	131.3	88.6	106.5	82.8
3763	PA3742_rplS_at	2040.7	2010.1	1419.0	1894.7	2019.6
3764	PA3743_trmD_at	2067.5	2274.2	2956.7	2907.0	2766.8
3765	PA3744_rimM_at	2639.2	1966.7	3013.3	2700.3	2467.4
3766	PA3745_rpsP_at	2938.6	2442.7	3912.3	4134.5	3294.6
3767	PA3746_ffh_at	682.6	527.2	555.2	496.6	458.2
3768	PA3747_at	506.1	386.0	548.7	523.5	490.0
3769	PA3748_at	339.2	285.4	410.1	438.7	376.4
3770	PA3749_at	25.9	13.2	14.2	19.7	24.0
3771	PA3750_at	58.6	55.8	77.6	93.1	87.9
3772	PA3751_purT_at	135.4	95.2	215.5	184.2	173.0
3773	PA3752_at	253.2	275.0	353.8	365.9	334.5
3774	PA3753_at	348.9	447.9	418.2	313.0	312.5
3775	PA3754_at	222.9	187.9	213.3	193.3	175.8
3776	PA3755_at	162.7	129.6	166.5	166.1	152.9
3777	PA3756_at	526.2	603.2	412.9	505.8	549.9
3778	PA3757_at	71.4	91.7	91.1	100.2	120.2
3779	PA3758_at	121.6	103.2	46.8	73.7	128.9
3780	PA3759_at	101.9	78.1	104.2	119.8	109.2
3781	PA3760_at	87.6	59.3	66.0	45.0	59.3
3782	PA3761_at	37.8	22.6	74.4	45.9	37.5
3783	PA3762_at	20.9	33.8	37.3	21.2	30.7
3784	PA3763_purL_at	693.6	696.9	786.9	826.3	737.5
3785	PA3764_at	238.8	239.7	275.0	222.5	279.9
3786	PA3765_at	32.1	30.6	47.1	35.0	43.6
3787	PA3766_at	227.1	142.9	143.3	81.1	114.7
3788	PA3767_at	34.9	92.4	128.8	199.0	200.6

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3789	PA3768_at	141.9	203.0	587.6	479.9	415.2
3790	PA3769_guaA_at	927.3	809.7	788.1	1011.9	867.1
3791	PA3770_guaB_at	1399.3	1000.6	1109.7	1564.2	1266.8
3792	PA3771_at	2.7	6.1	22.3	7.9	10.2
3793	PA3772_at	21.1	13.7	26.3	24.1	32.3
3794	PA3773_at	4.7	8.3	10.0	12.5	32.4
3795	PA3774_at	43.7	18.0	19.2	27.5	21.6
3796	PA3775_at	9.1	1.2	15.7	4.9	18.9
3797	PA3776_at	49.6	31.5	36.2	31.1	34.7
3798	PA3777_xseA_at	112.9	140.8	136.3	182.1	142.5
3799	PA3778_at	70.7	93.9	84.3	82.8	63.4
3800	PA3779_at	138.4	131.4	94.7	97.5	93.0
3801	PA3780_at	53.2	33.9	57.7	33.0	48.6
3802	PA3781_at	54.3	53.8	44.7	60.7	50.4
3803	PA3782_at	64.6	46.2	70.8	83.5	57.3
3804	PA3783_at	52.8	26.8	47.4	37.5	56.3
3805	PA3784_at	68.3	58.5	119.2	83.3	87.2
3806	PA3785_at	51.7	68.0	132.1	89.9	107.1
3807	PA3786_at	13.6	56.2	101.1	92.4	107.6
3808	PA3787_at	109.6	157.8	155.0	152.7	190.5
3809	PA3788_at	73.6	59.0	103.7	100.1	73.5
3810	PA3789_at	10.4	2.3	3.6	2.2	8.3
3811	PA3790_oprC_at	4.8	26.0	32.1	44.2	21.3
3812	PA3791_at	51.0	47.7	77.0	49.8	52.8
3813	PA3792_leuA_at	468.7	446.4	580.3	492.3	596.9
3814	PA3793_at	153.7	158.7	297.4	211.3	202.2
3815	PA3794_at	132.6	132.1	236.8	192.1	198.0
3816	PA3795_at	136.0	221.2	97.3	98.4	101.9
3817	PA3796_at	125.3	137.0	187.9	143.1	163.1
3818	PA3797_at	266.5	273.5	330.5	343.3	240.4
3819	PA3798_at	195.1	215.4	268.8	347.1	266.4
3820	PA3799_at	635.4	677.8	515.6	526.7	520.5
3821	PA3800_at	706.2	908.3	1205.0	1045.8	1038.7
3822	PA3801_at	1455.6	1272.9	1177.2	1392.0	1199.6
3823	PA3802_hisS_at	728.8	733.1	881.6	793.7	907.0
3824	PA3803_at	1220.1	1190.9	1641.2	1301.4	1290.7
3825	PA3804_at	933.8	836.3	533.5	577.4	637.4
3826	PA3805_pilF_at	393.5	361.5	339.4	306.5	364.8
3827	PA3806_at	1720.8	1912.4	1345.3	1295.3	1388.0
3828	PA3807_ndk_at	1938.0	2146.2	2677.3	2623.1	2111.3
3829	PA3808_at	287.3	412.7	294.4	411.8	334.1
3830	PA3809_fdx2_at	651.8	509.4	591.9	758.6	739.0
3831	PA3810_hscA_at	294.1	298.1	334.7	300.2	327.9
3832	PA3811_hscB_at	684.2	650.5	688.8	764.8	776.4
3833	PA3812_iscA_at	1841.7	1755.8	2039.1	1790.3	1732.7
3834	PA3813_iscU_at	1100.2	1147.0	1279.3	1312.2	1295.1
3835	PA3814_iscS_at	2260.6	1926.6	1614.5	1839.9	1848.6
3836	PA3815_at	1419.7	1435.1	1541.5	1396.6	1460.5
3837	PA3816_cysE_at	520.6	380.6	466.3	452.0	428.6
3838	PA3817_at	280.5	426.5	204.3	262.3	232.3
3839	PA3818_at	604.6	662.8	749.0	757.5	712.2
3840	PA3819_at	399.6	389.7	192.2	292.7	357.7
3841	PA3820_secF_at	385.0	411.6	550.1	533.6	527.8
3842	PA3821_secD_at	992.5	1010.1	1066.8	927.1	1196.9
3843	PA3822_at	933.6	1052.6	2069.1	1629.8	1670.5
3844	PA3823_tgt_at	365.2	304.2	220.7	358.4	345.3
3845	PA3824_queA_at	484.5	417.4	417.8	432.8	417.2
3846	PA3825_at	23.4	15.9	29.6	12.5	37.6
3847	PA3826_at	41.4	55.5	73.6	50.3	63.0
3848	PA3827_at	279.1	258.1	309.3	337.7	371.6
3849	PA3828_at	500.2	458.1	658.6	630.6	586.3
3850	PA3829_at	0.9	13.6	46.0	32.8	17.6
3851	PA3830_at	24.1	19.0	56.0	33.3	38.8
3852	PA3831_pepA_at	498.4	513.8	591.2	564.7	594.2
3853	PA3832_holC_at	304.3	311.1	361.0	268.2	280.1
3854	PA3833_at	678.7	832.6	338.3	391.2	410.8
3855	PA3834_valS_at	1276.3	1169.5	816.2	772.2	944.2
3856	PA3835_at	41.2	59.6	48.6	46.3	44.3
3857	PA3836_at	556.0	506.5	469.7	384.2	434.5
3858	PA3837_at	251.7	206.8	340.1	385.3	334.0
3859	PA3838_at	264.7	235.2	260.9	279.9	297.5
3860	PA3839_at	3.0	4.3	7.3	8.1	33.1
3861	PA3840_at	71.5	75.1	161.8	116.2	88.5

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3862	PA3841_exoS_at	38.3	48.3	49.9	41.3	32.9
3863	PA3842_at	133.0	71.0	72.9	39.5	52.3
3864	PA3843_at	42.9	9.9	17.3	14.9	25.2
3865	PA3844_at	49.6	42.1	111.3	95.7	90.7
3866	PA3845_at	53.9	59.5	153.1	113.2	85.6
3867	PA3846_at	57.0	63.3	69.8	48.1	74.3
3868	PA3847_at	42.5	38.5	88.5	94.7	70.4
3869	PA3848_at	106.3	88.9	87.0	117.6	97.6
3870	PA3849_at	230.6	344.3	301.4	271.4	337.0
3871	PA3850_at	261.7	261.1	347.8	278.4	244.7
3872	PA3851_at	23.8	49.7	65.5	56.5	62.3
3873	PA3852_at	115.6	136.7	134.0	98.4	98.9
3874	PA3853_at	92.4	126.2	190.8	135.1	136.5
3875	PA3854_at	150.6	166.1	283.0	269.2	238.9
3876	PA3855_at	63.4	59.4	73.0	84.9	79.3
3877	PA3856_at	65.0	80.4	77.4	42.6	78.3
3878	PA3857_at	339.3	293.9	469.3	349.2	276.4
3879	PA3858_at	105.5	108.8	52.1	97.1	98.4
3880	PA3859_at	140.5	121.1	87.5	111.2	156.5
3881	PA3860_at	53.5	50.8	106.5	80.9	84.5
3882	PA3861_rhlB_at	529.1	706.9	493.7	553.9	573.8
3883	PA3862_at	204.6	139.1	191.8	206.6	193.5
3884	PA3863_at	73.8	90.2	104.0	81.8	75.4
3885	PA3864_at	105.4	112.5	137.3	130.5	140.3
3886	PA3865_at	65.5	120.5	78.2	86.8	97.3
3887	PA3866_at	40.9	39.3	4.3	13.0	43.1
3888	PA3867_at	20.4	25.4	97.4	41.4	89.7
3889	PA3868_at	48.8	20.1	52.2	18.9	29.1
3890	PA3869_at	37.6	24.0	52.6	51.1	40.2
3891	PA3870_moaA1_at	9.3	14.8	31.0	20.2	18.2
3892	PA3871_at	18.6	28.4	49.4	16.4	32.7
3893	PA3872_narI_at	58.6	25.2	71.2	24.8	62.3
3894	PA3873_narJ_at	56.7	17.7	18.5	27.8	26.9
3895	PA3874_narH_at	9.2	21.1	43.5	22.8	26.3
3896	PA3875_narG_at	2.3	5.0	20.5	15.5	16.4
3897	PA3876_narK2_at	3.7	9.9	37.1	31.4	20.9
3898	PA3877_narK1_at	17.3	3.7	13.6	5.1	7.4
3899	PA3878_narX_at	99.0	61.7	86.9	85.1	88.9
3900	PA3879_narL_at	75.8	79.2	76.5	76.5	76.3
3901	PA3880_at	46.7	38.1	70.3	46.9	76.9
3902	PA3881_at	94.8	81.7	67.7	110.8	114.5
3903	PA3882_at	62.2	57.2	95.0	89.9	89.9
3904	PA3883_at	52.0	99.0	106.5	88.8	68.1
3905	PA3884_at	23.7	27.8	55.0	45.4	32.5
3906	PA3885_at	59.7	63.7	9.5	60.9	44.6
3907	PA3886_at	71.5	78.8	185.1	114.7	103.2
3908	PA3887_nhaP_at	53.1	59.0	76.7	67.4	70.1
3909	PA3888_at	14.1	10.9	30.7	26.6	23.1
3910	PA3889_at	42.3	22.4	56.1	58.6	53.3
3911	PA3890_at	4.7	5.5	21.5	16.7	25.7
3912	PA3891_at	19.0	31.7	28.9	80.8	55.7
3913	PA3892_at	86.7	65.8	68.7	65.4	57.8
3914	PA3893_at	77.5	61.4	104.0	59.2	65.1
3915	PA3894_at	97.0	133.6	67.0	57.9	85.6
3916	PA3895_at	187.4	135.9	301.2	213.6	150.9
3917	PA3896_at	137.8	137.8	195.8	120.5	187.6
3918	PA3897_at	3.6	2.2	5.2	6.1	5.8
3919	PA3898_at	173.2	138.2	135.4	130.9	122.1
3920	PA3899_at	29.4	16.8	37.2	68.3	33.1
3921	PA3900_at	12.5	26.7	66.9	37.7	42.1
3922	PA3901_fecA_at	681.6	271.8	85.1	72.9	103.9
3923	PA3902_at	100.4	109.0	205.7	133.5	119.1
3924	PA3903_prfC_at	931.7	955.6	705.5	728.2	761.7
3925	PA3904_i_at	2128.2	1316.0	2592.6	2321.9	1774.2
3926	PA3905_at	262.8	355.9	280.1	291.5	276.6
3927	PA3906_at	662.6	652.7	917.4	1079.5	870.9
3928	PA3907_at	905.7	804.6	921.1	849.4	789.0
3929	PA3908_at	544.3	498.4	377.1	411.6	456.0
3930	PA3909_at	21.8	19.0	52.2	35.6	46.2
3931	PA3910_at	36.4	14.6	27.8	9.8	36.2
3932	PA3911_at	52.3	54.4	76.7	59.3	77.0
3933	PA3912_at	7.3	14.4	26.3	37.0	19.9
3934	PA3913_at	8.1	5.1	36.9	19.9	31.3

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3935	PA3914_moeA1_at	3.0	1.2	14.1	3.6	7.0
3936	PA3915_moaB1_at	40.5	34.4	67.7	36.6	34.7
3937	PA3916_moaE_at	140.6	130.3	208.9	124.7	129.5
3938	PA3917_moaD_at	190.7	147.3	194.8	203.8	191.2
3939	PA3918_moaC_at	181.7	201.7	235.9	280.5	275.3
3940	PA3919_at	79.9	136.1	55.8	52.9	78.0
3941	PA3920_at	74.8	53.4	177.1	82.4	49.2
3942	PA3921_at	84.2	51.4	115.5	68.5	70.7
3943	PA3922_at	200.0	250.6	309.4	339.1	314.8
3944	PA3923_at	257.1	236.8	297.0	332.8	335.5
3945	PA3924_at	81.9	103.6	138.0	118.0	154.5
3946	PA3925_at	118.7	138.0	221.3	174.4	182.8
3947	PA3926_at	26.0	19.9	11.2	11.6	32.8
3948	PA3927_at	12.8	27.4	30.2	39.1	39.6
3949	PA3928_r_at	16.0	14.0	103.8	94.3	62.8
3950	PA3929_cioB_at	30.0	21.1	64.3	44.1	54.3
3951	PA3930_cioA_at	43.9	65.9	71.7	159.2	130.7
3952	PA3931_at	348.1	1737.3	1393.1	1379.4	1112.7
3953	PA3932_at	25.6	135.8	135.4	129.0	124.0
3954	PA3933_at	38.1	9.7	34.1	24.4	23.0
3955	PA3934_at	156.8	115.3	196.1	219.7	159.7
3956	PA3935_tauD_at	79.4	202.0	123.0	107.7	76.7
3957	PA3936_at	21.5	127.8	82.2	81.2	83.0
3958	PA3937_at	59.6	136.9	74.4	57.5	60.0
3959	PA3938_at	72.6	351.8	130.2	163.1	119.8
3960	PA3939_at	9.9	37.6	101.7	55.4	51.5
3961	PA3940_at	2028.3	1814.3	1118.7	1512.2	1705.7
3962	PA3941_at	160.7	152.4	140.5	152.7	165.7
3963	PA3942_tesB_at	380.6	273.9	232.2	239.4	302.6
3964	PA3943_at	88.2	90.9	113.6	130.2	100.1
3965	PA3944_at	73.4	58.1	95.7	97.6	132.7
3966	PA3945_at	31.3	58.8	66.1	49.2	76.6
3967	PA3946_at	5.0	20.6	55.4	33.7	41.4
3968	PA3947_at	20.8	20.4	34.5	29.9	44.0
3969	PA3948_at	133.8	153.7	85.7	108.2	102.8
3970	PA3949_at	120.2	166.1	204.8	156.9	150.9
3971	PA3950_at	262.4	235.8	246.2	273.4	209.4
3972	PA3951_at	148.4	152.0	125.8	133.4	126.5
3973	PA3952_at	197.8	191.6	93.6	83.0	96.2
3974	PA3953_at	34.5	21.5	45.1	44.7	40.6
3975	PA3954_at	15.2	18.7	23.5	27.7	30.1
3976	PA3955_at	91.3	93.7	86.8	102.5	113.4
3977	PA3956_at	19.6	28.7	52.2	57.2	52.5
3978	PA3957_at	1.6	2.3	11.5	19.4	5.4
3979	PA3958_at	108.1	135.1	136.8	109.4	114.0
3980	PA3959_at	132.5	91.0	101.3	87.0	83.6
3981	PA3960_at	92.2	60.6	41.8	49.8	93.3
3982	PA3961_at	109.7	97.9	144.1	149.3	140.2
3983	PA3962_at	175.6	193.7	133.7	185.3	198.5
3984	PA3963_at	40.0	33.7	50.1	49.1	42.1
3985	PA3964_at	30.0	18.8	43.5	19.9	36.3
3986	PA3965_at	163.0	158.1	120.5	94.2	128.1
3987	PA3966_at	199.9	298.8	344.9	296.4	256.2
3988	PA3967_at	138.0	204.3	220.8	214.7	175.4
3989	PA3968_at	75.9	97.4	179.4	142.0	128.6
3990	PA3969_at	112.6	109.1	91.3	83.0	129.0
3991	PA3970_amn_at	184.8	203.3	126.8	176.7	177.7
3992	PA3971_at	43.9	35.2	49.9	45.9	53.2
3993	PA3972_at	81.6	116.3	71.4	79.3	85.7
3994	PA3973_at	55.3	91.5	39.9	70.3	78.7
3995	PA3974_at	60.8	48.5	52.2	53.8	51.6
3996	PA3975_thiD_at	574.9	480.4	671.6	662.9	558.2
3997	PA3976_thiE_at	732.5	544.2	740.9	728.8	640.0
3998	PA3977_hemL_at	1136.8	979.7	946.7	1193.2	1042.2
3999	PA3978_at	539.6	507.2	542.7	649.9	583.0
4000	PA3979_at	130.5	136.9	75.3	114.9	137.6
4001	PA3980_at	641.9	694.5	878.0	831.6	856.9
4002	PA3981_at	914.1	791.1	651.5	747.7	758.0
4003	PA3982_at	727.1	770.2	1182.5	909.5	792.0
4004	PA3983_at	115.3	107.1	170.6	87.5	98.0
4005	PA3984_lnt_at	155.5	134.1	207.5	206.6	211.7
4006	PA3985_at	36.2	47.0	55.5	38.7	57.8
4007	PA3986_at	45.8	27.5	39.9	36.6	34.7

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4008	PA3987_leuS_at	1711.9	1397.9	819.1	1154.2	1140.5
4009	PA3988_at	1896.2	1559.0	775.4	683.8	1249.3
4010	PA3989_holA_at	582.9	526.3	327.3	466.9	497.6
4011	PA3990_at	294.1	413.5	138.8	127.6	154.9
4012	PA3991_at	1.1	13.1	33.0	29.2	26.4
4013	PA3992_at	178.0	170.2	169.8	169.1	153.4
4014	PA3994_at	5.3	6.8	15.3	24.4	36.5
4015	PA3995_at	4.7	19.9	42.4	57.7	28.4
4016	PA3996_lipA_at	486.2	466.8	445.7	490.9	451.5
4017	PA3997_lipB_at	450.5	414.8	621.3	568.8	431.3
4018	PA3998_at	853.0	842.3	667.6	669.5	702.1
4019	PA3999_dacC_at	1478.6	1426.4	1519.8	1472.5	1379.2
4020	PA4000_at	379.7	356.2	306.0	328.4	331.7
4021	PA4001_mltB2_at	508.2	485.9	430.6	413.2	425.7
4022	PA4002_rodA_at	161.8	184.3	201.4	242.9	248.5
4023	PA4003_pbpA_at	363.5	278.7	379.0	350.8	348.1
4024	PA4004_at	617.9	640.6	623.7	671.9	605.9
4025	PA4005_at	536.2	589.2	457.5	463.6	498.0
4026	PA4006_at	676.3	842.1	616.8	647.5	667.3
4027	PA4007_proA_at	637.5	612.4	548.8	717.6	642.9
4028	PA4008_at	19.2	22.1	48.7	37.4	35.0
4029	PA4009_at	16.3	15.9	16.2	13.9	21.1
4030	PA4010_at	209.5	242.5	288.2	199.5	229.2
4031	PA4011_at	197.6	160.4	209.2	226.6	200.7
4032	PA4012_at	69.5	151.7	123.2	145.5	163.5
4033	PA4013_at	75.8	94.1	95.6	90.8	110.5
4034	PA4014_at	214.7	186.0	249.9	276.5	326.3
4035	PA4015_at	303.8	413.3	481.8	402.0	428.6
4036	PA4016_at	44.6	36.8	70.6	49.8	34.8
4037	PA4017_at	133.2	99.2	193.8	179.2	152.3
4038	PA4018_r_at	86.6	65.9	104.6	112.6	85.9
4039	PA4019_at	192.7	197.4	261.0	249.2	248.0
4040	PA4020_mpl_at	452.8	384.6	367.3	443.6	418.9
4041	PA4021_at	72.4	61.7	108.4	88.2	72.2
4042	PA4023_at	349.8	437.8	729.5	697.3	525.9
4043	PA4024_eutB_at	646.9	834.0	356.0	519.1	637.4
4044	PA4025_r_at	394.6	464.0	501.8	519.0	492.0
4045	PA4026_at	106.4	126.4	104.6	106.4	94.9
4046	PA4027_at	121.7	92.0	143.6	130.6	107.8
4047	PA4028_i_at	55.7	29.7	39.9	38.6	72.4
4048	PA4029_at	284.4	278.2	230.8	244.7	281.4
4049	PA4030_at	382.6	308.8	347.3	341.6	341.6
4050	PA4031_ppa_at	1525.1	1344.3	930.0	1291.0	1418.0
4051	PA4032_at	144.3	128.3	214.8	158.2	123.1
4052	PA4033_at	17.2	22.7	3.2	15.6	20.3
4053	PA4034_aqpZ_at	15.2	16.3	13.9	20.5	27.4
4054	PA4035_at	191.1	174.9	183.2	156.2	208.2
4055	PA4036_at	58.5	47.3	24.0	60.1	58.1
4056	PA4037_at	20.5	25.1	53.3	45.2	36.2
4057	PA4038_at	6.3	11.5	21.3	20.3	37.2
4058	PA4039_at	21.6	17.9	36.8	41.6	30.7
4059	PA4040_at	60.9	50.0	57.0	52.0	57.1
4060	PA4041_at	2.4	4.9	24.1	10.1	25.4
4061	PA4042_xseB_at	753.8	719.6	463.5	693.9	734.4
4062	PA4043_ispA_at	564.1	393.8	681.0	546.1	483.0
4063	PA4044_dxs_at	322.0	399.1	472.2	403.9	415.0
4064	PA4045_at	110.5	97.9	119.0	161.3	158.3
4065	PA4046_at	127.0	156.7	188.6	141.8	149.1
4066	PA4047_ribA_at	457.3	350.5	454.8	549.9	470.7
4067	PA4048_at	53.0	53.9	93.2	102.4	89.5
4068	PA4049_at	131.6	164.5	233.6	182.7	251.8
4069	PA4050_pgpA_at	171.4	199.0	333.8	273.5	261.8
4070	PA4051_thiL_at	350.8	302.5	671.3	540.0	491.7
4071	PA4052_nusB_at	919.7	941.3	693.0	909.9	872.1
4072	PA4053_ribE_at	1350.7	1194.2	1084.0	1213.9	1283.6
4073	PA4054_ribB_at	1280.4	1261.8	940.1	1123.2	1056.2
4074	PA4055_ribC_at	452.6	405.0	606.3	562.0	555.9
4075	PA4056_ribD_at	263.0	285.9	390.1	443.3	425.1
4076	PA4057_at	529.8	452.5	612.4	646.4	649.1
4077	PA4058_at	247.6	192.4	375.5	330.4	373.6
4078	PA4059_at	631.9	513.9	764.6	696.5	575.6
4079	PA4060_at	425.4	379.5	282.4	367.0	356.4
4080	PA4061_at	936.8	743.5	717.5	673.8	608.4

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4081	PA4062_at	34.4	42.7	32.8	38.8	24.4
4082	PA4063_at	124.1	91.3	105.7	103.1	83.2
4083	PA4064_at	49.6	29.1	40.6	61.0	33.7
4084	PA4065_at	41.0	54.9	86.0	69.3	65.7
4085	PA4066_at	53.7	75.4	57.5	61.3	55.3
4086	PA4067_oprG_at	148.3	118.1	208.1	154.9	192.2
4087	PA4068_at	190.9	242.8	250.4	216.3	159.1
4088	PA4069_at	310.0	290.9	290.5	381.3	322.0
4089	PA4070_at	3.0	1.8	7.4	13.4	17.4
4090	PA4071_at	2.2	1.3	4.0	4.5	7.0
4091	PA4072_at	22.9	11.8	5.5	4.3	10.8
4092	PA4073_at	54.4	50.6	83.1	31.6	65.1
4093	PA4074_at	2.7	13.6	28.6	5.7	9.5
4094	PA4075_at	53.9	37.3	68.7	62.6	57.4
4095	PA4076_at	84.2	73.8	86.5	101.7	66.4
4096	PA4077_at	42.0	42.5	88.1	72.8	70.2
4097	PA4078_at	32.4	15.8	39.7	18.9	23.8
4098	PA4079_at	123.9	114.3	216.0	189.2	169.2
4099	PA4080_at	71.3	103.8	60.4	46.2	62.2
4100	PA4081_at	13.3	10.6	50.9	33.2	28.6
4101	PA4082_at	20.9	9.4	3.9	10.9	28.0
4102	PA4083_at	13.3	19.2	36.2	31.2	44.8
4103	PA4084_at	2.8	0.8	3.5	3.6	1.9
4104	PA4085_at	2.3	7.9	3.2	3.2	15.1
4105	PA4086_at	27.7	39.0	34.5	38.5	62.9
4106	PA4087_at	8.5	18.8	53.4	24.4	38.8
4107	PA4088_at	3.9	2.6	42.6	9.5	19.0
4108	PA4089_at	9.1	1.3	6.1	6.2	22.1
4109	PA4090_at	81.1	152.2	223.4	255.1	229.5
4110	PA4091_hpaA_at	14.9	12.6	23.6	40.9	25.7
4111	PA4092_hpaC_at	7.2	5.1	12.7	18.4	17.4
4112	PA4093_at	21.9	28.4	20.6	21.4	30.3
4113	PA4094_at	89.1	71.7	79.0	81.6	80.8
4114	PA4095_at	40.8	25.3	47.0	46.3	36.4
4115	PA4096_at	17.2	10.4	17.7	15.1	16.8
4116	PA4097_at	26.4	6.5	50.6	32.7	30.3
4117	PA4098_at	35.6	15.9	38.4	56.0	34.5
4118	PA4099_at	2.4	2.8	35.8	8.6	20.0
4119	PA4100_at	38.7	6.2	12.6	7.3	22.6
4120	PA4101_at	71.6	55.8	94.8	70.9	87.3
4121	PA4102_at	78.4	60.7	133.7	101.7	123.4
4122	PA4103_at	6.5	10.3	5.6	3.8	19.1
4123	PA4104_at	32.3	32.3	47.6	40.4	53.0
4124	PA4105_at	5.3	3.8	21.2	8.8	15.4
4125	PA4106_at	17.1	12.1	39.4	18.1	33.2
4126	PA4107_at	27.1	25.7	19.6	15.1	35.2
4127	PA4108_at	43.3	33.3	53.2	47.8	45.5
4128	PA4109_ampR_at	67.8	69.8	124.0	112.2	113.6
4129	PA4110_ampC_at	59.5	51.6	62.8	46.8	66.2
4130	PA4111_i_at	126.5	143.0	175.5	160.5	138.0
4131	PA4112_at	25.3	49.6	79.4	57.3	41.3
4132	PA4113_at	67.7	81.8	121.8	95.8	88.8
4133	PA4114_at	111.4	97.1	76.1	101.7	103.1
4134	PA4115_at	133.5	202.4	189.4	154.4	152.2
4135	PA4116_at	598.1	494.8	614.3	374.9	385.3
4136	PA4117_at	296.8	360.8	211.6	273.8	264.2
4137	PA4118_at	111.4	104.0	74.4	108.3	94.2
4138	PA4119_aph_at	53.8	69.9	14.6	68.1	56.1
4139	PA4120_at	32.7	23.8	65.7	45.7	40.3
4140	PA4121_at	55.6	32.3	47.5	53.2	56.1
4141	PA4122_at	35.8	37.5	49.8	29.7	41.2
4142	PA4123_hpcC_at	36.2	29.0	61.8	48.0	43.9
4143	PA4124_hpcB_at	34.6	42.1	41.3	23.6	30.7
4144	PA4125_hpcD_at	34.5	29.0	47.1	37.5	51.5
4145	PA4126_at	14.9	13.0	77.4	25.7	42.7
4146	PA4127_hpcG_at	6.2	12.8	25.2	20.6	20.3
4147	PA4128_at	10.0	38.1	14.5	75.9	32.3
4148	PA4129_at	48.7	65.5	167.9	116.1	126.3
4149	PA4130_at	129.8	217.4	246.3	337.1	255.3
4150	PA4131_at	192.6	458.4	887.7	913.1	951.7
4151	PA4132_at	98.4	137.5	369.7	301.2	244.0
4152	PA4133_at	54.7	111.7	165.5	219.5	212.1
4153	PA4134_i_at	6.1	15.1	57.3	71.3	59.3

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4154	PA4135_at	123.4	168.8	217.5	176.3	279.3
4155	PA4136_at	7.2	21.6	40.6	40.1	40.6
4156	PA4137_at	1.3	2.0	5.1	3.4	16.5
4157	PA4138_tyrS_at	74.3	109.4	117.1	146.9	186.7
4158	PA4139_at	89.5	154.0	100.3	89.7	64.1
4159	PA4140_at	52.5	58.6	110.0	66.3	66.7
4160	PA4141_at	173.1	332.2	178.7	147.6	237.5
4161	PA4142_at	72.5	86.5	55.1	49.5	62.1
4162	PA4143_at	58.3	55.7	79.1	59.9	55.0
4163	PA4144_at	37.1	63.8	59.0	7.0	59.2
4164	PA4145_at	46.4	55.5	52.2	19.4	35.7
4165	PA4146_at	26.1	30.1	62.7	40.2	46.5
4166	PA4147_acoR_at	27.6	16.4	53.2	65.2	24.6
4167	PA4148_at	3.4	7.9	13.8	2.4	12.4
4168	PA4149_at	23.0	19.5	42.6	45.7	22.3
4169	PA4150_at	28.5	22.4	39.7	6.0	38.1
4170	PA4151_acoB_at	3.5	15.7	15.3	12.9	19.4
4171	PA4152_at	11.5	17.2	58.9	31.8	33.2
4172	PA4153_at	5.0	16.8	41.2	23.7	34.7
4173	PA4154_at	23.5	32.8	86.0	72.1	58.1
4174	PA4155_at	25.1	5.5	32.2	24.3	34.0
4175	PA4156_at	24.4	20.1	34.6	17.2	37.2
4176	PA4157_at	41.2	92.4	50.6	58.5	74.0
4177	PA4158_fepC_at	11.6	1.3	41.5	10.9	18.8
4178	PA4159_fepB_at	7.7	12.1	46.2	25.8	20.2
4179	PA4160_fepD_at	5.5	9.5	6.8	11.8	20.1
4180	PA4161_fepG_at	6.7	12.1	8.7	3.6	28.2
4181	PA4162_at	68.8	65.0	104.9	90.7	90.5
4182	PA4163_at	439.5	330.2	521.1	567.1	429.2
4183	PA4164_at	158.9	195.2	245.7	242.7	209.5
4184	PA4165_at	26.6	24.0	51.0	39.1	50.8
4185	PA4166_at	33.2	12.1	31.8	8.6	22.6
4186	PA4167_at	2.5	2.4	16.3	4.9	18.0
4187	PA4168_at	24.4	6.2	22.0	31.5	35.3
4188	PA4169_at	3.3	33.1	24.0	26.6	34.1
4189	PA4170_at	16.0	20.5	24.5	5.2	21.8
4190	PA4171_at	18.0	31.2	54.2	43.1	77.3
4191	PA4172_at	22.9	11.5	12.0	16.9	47.3
4192	PA4173_at	33.9	15.5	34.3	24.8	24.5
4193	PA4174_at	42.2	39.0	63.3	47.7	50.4
4194	PA4175_at	210.4	274.0	210.7	337.0	287.0
4195	PA4176_ppiC2_at	206.6	271.1	347.1	300.9	280.0
4196	PA4177_at	25.7	20.2	17.6	3.2	32.0
4197	PA4178_at	37.0	36.0	31.1	41.1	29.5
4198	PA4179_at	103.6	52.0	56.8	19.2	54.3
4199	PA4180_at	136.1	119.2	147.6	148.9	183.8
4200	PA4181_at	145.8	122.1	147.4	144.7	120.7
4201	PA4182_at	120.5	84.3	206.6	116.3	150.1
4202	PA4183_at	52.5	44.4	46.4	89.2	40.3
4203	PA4184_at	55.7	68.1	113.3	142.7	122.3
4204	PA4185_at	144.1	146.4	128.2	106.4	151.7
4205	PA4186_at	50.2	19.0	32.7	46.2	36.2
4206	PA4187_at	11.3	13.1	20.3	19.8	31.1
4207	PA4188_at	28.3	31.5	23.3	16.1	32.6
4208	PA4189_at	2.2	2.1	4.1	5.7	6.1
4209	PA4190_at	120.7	139.5	153.5	168.7	208.7
4210	PA4191_at	42.2	95.1	131.4	99.7	87.2
4211	PA4192_at	24.1	190.8	160.3	176.8	147.0
4212	PA4193_at	35.6	211.0	152.5	191.0	169.5
4213	PA4194_at	34.1	345.7	166.5	236.1	196.8
4214	PA4195_at	141.0	655.5	353.0	419.0	429.7
4215	PA4196_at	90.1	108.0	70.2	104.2	93.0
4216	PA4197_at	61.6	56.1	48.4	58.3	79.0
4217	PA4198_at	95.2	96.5	91.3	101.5	146.4
4218	PA4199_at	161.2	119.7	219.1	159.8	159.1
4219	PA4200_at	89.7	76.2	54.5	91.5	82.7
4220	PA4201_ddlA_at	45.6	39.3	75.9	53.1	80.2
4221	PA4202_at	34.3	41.0	49.7	65.0	96.3
4222	PA4203_at	46.7	42.0	77.2	47.2	61.0
4223	PA4204_at	49.5	63.7	67.6	88.3	77.8
4224	PA4205_at	88.8	115.8	58.3	87.2	74.7
4225	PA4206_at	242.4	235.2	191.6	173.5	266.2
4226	PA4207_at	161.6	120.2	172.8	142.1	145.9

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4227	PA4208_at	152.9	179.4	168.4	184.2	158.9
4228	PA4209_at	5.7	92.1	57.3	101.9	104.9
4229	PA4217_at	42.7	105.5	96.4	80.7	97.5
4230	PA4218_at	3.3	4.3	60.7	32.7	49.3
4231	PA4219_at	1.7	1.5	49.4	25.1	12.2
4232	PA4220_i_at	18.2	1.4	100.6	72.2	69.4
4233	PA4221_fptA_at	6.4	12.7	104.3	81.3	82.4
4234	PA4222_at	3.8	2.9	62.7	42.4	50.2
4235	PA4223_at	31.8	17.3	84.4	49.4	55.8
4236	PA4224_at	38.7	13.2	97.0	82.8	89.1
4237	PA4225_pchF_at	1.8	1.2	26.8	31.5	19.8
4238	PA4226_pchE_at	9.0	12.9	99.7	58.6	54.6
4239	PA4227_pchR_at	3.9	21.2	70.9	78.9	58.0
4240	PA4228_pchD_at	27.1	21.5	116.7	123.7	81.9
4241	PA4229_pchC_at	27.4	20.7	143.1	159.8	144.4
4242	PA4230_pchB_at	19.8	8.7	72.3	56.4	68.3
4243	PA4231_pchA_at	4.0	1.3	52.6	39.3	56.0
4244	PA4232_ssb_at	1734.5	1375.9	1431.8	1521.6	1368.1
4245	PA4233_at	240.5	223.5	284.4	237.6	298.9
4246	PA4234_uvrA_at	633.9	671.7	811.6	650.3	610.9
4247	PA4235_bfrA_at	367.8	394.5	236.8	293.0	297.1
4248	PA4236_katA_at	149.8	284.5	227.4	277.8	270.3
4249	PA4237_rplQ_at	3924.2	2902.0	3917.6	3572.6	3344.9
4250	PA4238_rpoA_at	10056.0	4671.5	8012.7	6776.4	5333.3
4251	PA4239_rpsD_at	4824.8	2942.5	4458.4	4261.4	3564.9
4252	PA4240_rpsK_at	8433.9	4212.1	6926.6	8647.9	4808.3
4253	PA4241_rpsM_at	7080.8	4166.3	5141.9	4997.7	4549.5
4254	PA4242_rpmJ_at	10393.3	4098.0	4072.2	6015.4	5279.3
4255	PA4243_secY_at	6525.2	3259.2	2160.5	2398.4	2869.5
4256	PA4244_rplO_at	6597.1	3364.8	8203.8	6459.7	5072.5
4257	PA4245_rpmD_at	9936.0	3794.5	4362.2	4439.9	4319.5
4258	PA4246_rpsE_at	9927.9	4197.1	7081.6	6036.3	4986.3
4259	PA4247_rplR_at	7539.0	4383.2	6456.9	6728.6	5166.0
4260	PA4248_rplF_at	7902.6	3444.1	6116.3	5479.9	4451.1
4261	PA4249_rpsH_at	10683.2	4225.8	9053.6	7308.2	5459.9
4262	PA4250_rpsN_at	4783.2	3119.1	7483.3	5471.7	4186.6
4263	PA4251_rplE_at	13122.7	4664.0	11872.9	9475.1	6517.9
4264	PA4252_rplX_at	7773.1	3746.2	5807.8	4886.8	3903.2
4265	PA4253_rplN_at	10083.7	3965.0	7897.2	5804.2	4970.5
4266	PA4254_rpsQ_at	14769.1	5098.2	11338.1	9474.5	6628.2
4267	PA4255_rpmC_at	2413.8	1753.2	2086.6	2285.9	2030.6
4268	PA4256_rplP_at	6674.0	3337.0	10487.4	6030.6	4543.8
4269	PA4257_rpsC_at	7882.0	3486.2	6343.9	5035.7	3925.7
4270	PA4258_rplV_at	10006.3	4517.9	10924.0	8802.5	6071.9
4271	PA4259_rpsS_at	9733.9	4270.9	9828.9	6414.4	5701.5
4272	PA4260_rplB_at	10651.9	4247.7	12709.7	8480.0	5634.7
4273	PA4261_rplW_at	9702.4	4584.0	10224.9	7440.2	5626.0
4274	PA4262_rplD_at	9040.9	3983.4	7329.2	5862.3	5116.0
4275	PA4263_rplC_at	11576.1	4241.7	9590.0	7246.5	5300.3
4276	PA4264_rpsJ_at	9123.7	4721.8	8316.1	6263.5	5349.9
4277	PA4265_tufA_s_at	4567.0	3380.6	3038.4	3683.4	3479.2
4278	PA4266_fusA1_at	5576.7	2775.8	6257.0	4752.1	4032.6
4279	PA4267_rpsG_at	13015.8	4507.0	10873.1	7217.4	5182.6
4280	PA4268_rpsL_at	5633.6	2985.7	4540.1	3600.6	3015.8
4281	PA4269_rpoC_at	6143.4	2550.3	6488.2	5274.1	3988.4
4282	PA4270_rpoB_at	2700.7	1830.5	2451.0	2509.4	2143.3
4283	PA4271_rplL_at	10643.6	4802.3	10184.0	6923.5	5983.5
4284	PA4272_rplJ_at	13146.7	4866.2	10032.3	8599.2	6237.9
4285	PA4273_rplA_at	7629.4	3553.4	8029.5	6374.2	4799.5
4286	PA4274_rplK_at	13411.0	4333.7	11395.1	7834.0	5578.8
4287	PA4275_nusG_at	1171.0	1645.5	1929.4	1750.6	1575.2
4288	PA4276_secE_at	2582.4	2340.8	4418.3	3490.9	2951.3
4289	PA4278_at	128.2	179.7	165.7	141.4	161.6
4290	PA4279_at	252.8	329.1	415.8	264.0	295.3
4291	PA4280_birA_at	449.0	345.1	411.9	390.9	466.3
4292	PA4281_sbcD_at	175.6	134.9	144.0	161.7	163.0
4293	PA4282_at	156.9	100.3	134.1	128.7	122.9
4294	PA4283_recD_at	99.2	84.1	104.5	120.2	101.3
4295	PA4284_recB_at	277.8	232.7	401.2	341.5	289.0
4296	PA4285_recC_at	108.0	151.0	132.7	186.5	170.1
4297	PA4286_at	243.0	196.8	320.8	294.3	261.1
4298	PA4287_at	2.8	10.5	4.6	6.2	30.6
4299	PA4288_at	35.8	31.4	28.2	26.8	24.1

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4300	PA4289_at	56.5	28.4	100.4	49.2	61.4
4301	PA4290_at	513.3	149.5	195.1	181.2	224.9
4302	PA4291_at	168.3	151.7	400.9	234.7	214.7
4303	PA4292_at	605.9	673.5	518.1	498.3	552.9
4304	PA4293_at	22.5	7.1	5.2	4.7	18.6
4305	PA4294_at	15.0	27.0	25.7	20.8	34.7
4306	PA4295_at	0.9	14.9	30.8	2.4	18.7
4307	PA4296_at	215.9	213.8	144.6	185.9	200.3
4308	PA4297_at	2.1	2.9	4.6	3.8	14.3
4309	PA4298_at	4.4	13.7	42.3	28.5	35.9
4310	PA4299_at	29.4	31.0	90.0	40.3	58.2
4311	PA4300_at	35.7	19.1	62.4	43.5	40.3
4312	PA4301_at	30.6	22.9	69.8	34.3	56.1
4313	PA4302_at	7.5	19.4	14.5	21.1	23.3
4314	PA4303_at	32.4	22.4	47.2	42.8	48.2
4315	PA4304_at	12.8	18.6	5.4	51.3	33.3
4316	PA4305_at	29.7	30.1	41.8	49.1	42.6
4317	PA4306_at	15.7	28.0	31.0	26.7	33.5
4318	PA4307_pctC_at	149.4	87.6	97.2	117.9	109.0
4319	PA4308_at	73.3	84.6	107.1	138.4	109.9
4320	PA4309_pctA_at	279.6	305.6	199.8	244.2	255.8
4321	PA4310_pctB_at	1272.5	775.2	702.3	720.8	880.0
4322	PA4311_at	41.8	40.8	74.5	59.7	50.5
4323	PA4312_at	158.6	183.7	169.8	132.0	175.8
4324	PA4313_at	46.6	79.3	71.4	67.1	73.3
4325	PA4314_purU1_at	607.3	503.5	568.2	551.3	694.5
4326	PA4315_mvaT_at	4843.4	4175.3	3602.2	3622.7	3080.6
4327	PA4316_sbcB_at	116.5	158.5	207.5	123.2	189.9
4328	PA4317_at	1501.8	993.6	1167.5	1182.5	1088.8
4329	PA4318_at	344.2	261.5	431.3	375.1	267.6
4330	PA4319_at	299.5	198.9	224.3	186.0	180.3
4331	PA4320_at	224.2	174.5	224.3	213.1	174.4
4332	PA4321_at	581.9	382.1	480.6	492.0	409.5
4333	PA4322_at	414.8	316.8	354.5	376.3	341.7
4334	PA4323_at	348.5	210.5	403.1	356.0	331.8
4335	PA4324_at	96.0	155.4	97.5	131.4	158.1
4336	PA4325_at	138.5	228.8	188.3	204.4	228.0
4337	PA4326_at	66.4	97.6	73.3	107.7	114.8
4338	PA4327_at	55.1	77.9	103.6	89.7	77.0
4339	PA4328_at	46.2	33.3	42.0	52.2	42.9
4340	PA4329_pykA_at	1404.7	933.0	864.4	951.0	999.4
4341	PA4330_at	9.2	69.0	103.0	85.0	95.2
4342	PA4331_at	169.1	158.9	229.4	196.8	207.6
4343	PA4332_at	139.4	123.8	126.5	131.8	123.5
4344	PA4333_at	1770.6	1672.4	1265.4	1636.8	1553.9
4345	PA4334_at	38.1	67.3	106.2	51.7	74.1
4346	PA4335_at	24.4	57.6	55.5	49.4	80.6
4347	PA4336_at	224.7	238.1	260.5	211.7	243.1
4348	PA4337_at	32.2	36.9	73.9	38.4	55.6
4349	PA4338_at	41.3	36.0	21.5	42.9	44.7
4350	PA4339_at	71.0	82.2	107.0	69.5	74.2
4351	PA4340_at	145.7	141.5	110.3	136.9	112.7
4352	PA4341_at	4.0	8.7	42.7	4.4	13.6
4353	PA4342_at	19.6	26.0	78.0	69.8	40.0
4354	PA4343_at	13.1	1.5	18.9	7.4	12.4
4355	PA4344_at	32.0	15.1	62.3	38.3	38.2
4356	PA4345_at	3.8	23.5	8.7	51.8	31.7
4357	PA4346_at	1.4	1.5	13.5	7.5	9.4
4358	PA4347_at	35.2	40.7	27.3	46.4	50.8
4359	PA4348_at	22.9	25.1	52.7	32.4	33.9
4360	PA4349_at	48.1	53.6	82.9	58.1	61.9
4361	PA4350_at	42.7	15.1	38.6	34.7	36.4
4362	PA4351_at	33.6	14.3	57.8	33.9	28.1
4363	PA4352_at	54.9	112.6	111.6	125.3	146.6
4364	PA4353_at	127.3	72.1	146.2	96.6	101.7
4365	PA4354_at	113.8	82.1	71.5	79.5	91.4
4366	PA4355_at	91.8	105.0	134.0	116.2	105.8
4367	PA4356_xenB_at	163.6	111.7	87.4	99.2	106.7
4368	PA4357_r_at	98.2	40.6	12.5	14.2	43.9
4369	PA4358_at	31.1	35.9	47.7	50.3	51.7
4370	PA4359_i_at	32.1	48.1	174.7	55.4	50.8
4371	PA4360_at	1858.5	1368.0	1025.8	997.0	1035.9
4372	PA4361_at	60.1	44.3	58.4	28.6	50.2

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4373	PA4362_at	16.2	28.6	42.8	33.4	37.0
4374	PA4363_iciA_at	25.1	26.1	39.6	35.7	37.2
4375	PA4364_at	33.4	21.9	54.5	52.2	44.5
4376	PA4365_at	27.7	22.8	44.7	38.7	51.0
4377	PA4366_sodB_at	2235.5	2637.1	2650.6	2693.2	2651.8
4378	PA4367_at	152.5	130.6	55.4	80.0	111.0
4379	PA4368_at	52.7	56.7	106.4	93.6	82.9
4380	PA4369_at	59.1	73.2	98.7	90.6	74.2
4381	PA4370_at	334.4	1060.9	2775.2	2787.7	2343.7
4382	PA4371_at	9.0	117.1	459.2	395.1	353.6
4383	PA4372_at	156.1	240.8	992.8	877.3	716.7
4384	PA4373_at	109.6	135.9	238.3	283.3	268.1
4385	PA4374_at	239.3	156.4	153.5	169.8	194.9
4386	PA4375_at	88.3	111.2	53.0	73.0	69.7
4387	PA4376_pncB2_at	172.3	184.4	285.0	273.0	247.2
4388	PA4377_at	84.4	96.8	115.4	92.3	103.9
4389	PA4378_inaA_at	80.4	73.4	99.4	99.5	86.6
4390	PA4379_at	120.5	208.4	167.8	204.9	202.2
4391	PA4380_at	115.9	85.3	171.7	83.0	94.5
4392	PA4381_at	206.6	173.6	148.8	140.7	211.7
4393	PA4382_at	37.9	19.0	30.4	41.3	38.3
4394	PA4383_at	54.4	33.4	60.3	55.1	61.8
4395	PA4384_at	8.3	68.2	154.3	135.7	127.1
4396	PA4385_groEL_at	4636.2	3252.4	2720.0	2084.3	1979.9
4397	PA4386_groES_at	11447.7	4248.9	5637.6	4434.6	4088.0
4398	PA4387_at	234.5	165.8	81.3	117.5	134.4
4399	PA4388_at	103.7	119.4	182.3	156.0	169.8
4400	PA4389_at	154.3	231.6	146.7	221.6	214.4
4401	PA4390_at	124.5	153.6	109.6	156.9	149.2
4402	PA4391_at	81.4	80.0	117.7	71.7	92.1
4403	PA4392_at	49.5	64.5	39.0	36.0	52.9
4404	PA4393_at	119.4	128.8	123.5	81.7	101.1
4405	PA4394_at	119.4	172.1	127.7	140.4	137.0
4406	PA4395_at	923.0	929.5	552.3	744.9	805.6
4407	PA4396_at	87.9	93.9	86.6	80.6	112.2
4408	PA4397_panE_at	87.5	81.8	119.5	96.4	96.9
4409	PA4398_at	93.9	103.5	163.1	108.7	127.9
4410	PA4399_at	138.7	119.6	137.4	141.5	135.7
4411	PA4400_at	122.4	137.9	118.1	168.1	181.8
4412	PA4401_at	178.5	170.9	192.5	209.8	256.6
4413	PA4402_argJ_at	482.5	526.8	622.1	608.4	497.7
4414	PA4403_secA_at	1481.7	1652.1	725.4	997.4	983.2
4415	PA4404_at	149.7	154.5	271.1	303.1	222.6
4416	PA4405_at	54.4	73.9	42.7	53.7	60.6
4417	PA4406_lpxC_at	969.6	1339.8	1153.0	1251.4	1386.6
4418	PA4407_ftsZ_at	2543.2	2218.8	2092.1	2451.6	2411.2
4419	PA4408_ftsA_at	510.3	700.7	527.6	520.4	540.4
4420	PA4409_ftsQ_at	1448.9	1161.6	1016.0	1002.6	1056.1
4421	PA4410_ddlB_at	652.8	703.9	669.6	677.8	668.0
4422	PA4411_murC_at	1135.7	1025.4	793.3	798.7	888.4
4423	PA4412_murG_at	730.0	531.8	1437.9	866.3	850.5
4424	PA4413_ftsW_at	609.8	548.1	671.1	687.2	634.9
4425	PA4414_murD_at	544.8	483.4	565.5	556.9	527.9
4426	PA4415_mraY_at	708.2	631.4	985.5	940.9	879.6
4427	PA4416_murF_at	692.4	638.6	888.1	1215.1	881.6
4428	PA4417_murE_at	594.1	632.3	649.4	696.0	641.5
4429	PA4418_ftsI_at	454.5	619.1	395.4	456.5	369.3
4430	PA4419_ftsL_at	287.0	362.3	320.3	275.6	315.0
4431	PA4420_at	505.5	568.5	844.7	736.1	641.9
4432	PA4421_at	738.7	1108.8	797.0	776.9	918.2
4433	PA4422_at	179.8	193.6	345.3	300.8	271.0
4434	PA4423_at	1058.2	1089.3	634.3	935.1	875.9
4435	PA4424_at	843.2	843.6	1148.5	974.8	823.1
4436	PA4425_at	1236.3	1254.8	1181.1	1202.4	1186.4
4437	PA4426_at	763.5	916.8	426.2	620.6	701.3
4438	PA4427_sspB_at	257.2	295.3	340.1	361.7	340.0
4439	PA4428_sspA_at	503.8	559.5	610.2	649.3	665.7
4440	PA4429_at	915.7	936.7	1968.4	1627.4	1520.4
4441	PA4430_at	1814.2	1529.4	1962.4	1913.5	1931.4
4442	PA4431_at	3197.0	2351.4	5762.1	4460.6	3840.9
4443	PA4432_rpsI_at	848.8	1176.9	1602.5	1595.8	1492.3
4444	PA4433_rplM_at	8165.3	3585.0	3625.3	4478.3	4201.6
4445	PA4434_at	194.1	207.3	167.6	183.1	204.4

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4446	PA4435_at	30.1	32.5	39.1	36.5	42.3
4447	PA4436_at	226.7	140.0	209.3	205.8	149.1
4448	PA4437_at	104.4	91.9	172.5	105.4	138.1
4449	PA4438_at	373.2	433.7	590.3	612.9	582.1
4450	PA4439_trpS_at	649.9	537.1	621.5	612.9	543.7
4451	PA4440_at	184.5	232.3	209.7	206.1	257.6
4452	PA4441_at	2127.0	1690.7	2205.7	1802.5	1814.5
4453	PA4442_cysN_at	542.2	1171.4	931.0	1073.7	1103.4
4454	PA4443_cysD_at	1122.2	2395.3	2340.7	2571.1	2297.9
4455	PA4444_mltB1_at	140.9	180.8	232.0	203.1	245.3
4456	PA4445_at	130.8	129.4	126.1	136.8	161.8
4457	PA4446_algW_at	313.6	356.4	204.5	271.2	341.9
4458	PA4447_hisC1_at	312.0	467.6	331.1	357.1	404.4
4459	PA4448_hisD_at	260.7	218.6	200.1	270.0	266.5
4460	PA4449_hisG_at	1231.0	1247.0	1155.4	958.8	1137.1
4461	PA4450_murA_at	1941.2	1705.3	1756.8	1853.7	1707.2
4462	PA4451_at	1566.4	1293.9	1001.3	1317.6	1435.0
4463	PA4452_at	321.0	303.6	361.2	322.9	353.1
4464	PA4453_at	920.1	1044.9	1036.0	1027.2	1002.7
4465	PA4454_at	563.8	648.2	487.2	562.5	505.9
4466	PA4455_at	317.4	369.5	633.2	373.9	453.4
4467	PA4456_at	253.9	368.4	393.8	359.9	369.8
4468	PA4457_at	942.7	909.2	576.0	731.1	772.1
4469	PA4458_at	756.3	541.9	545.8	592.7	683.4
4470	PA4459_at	1340.8	1413.4	576.9	663.4	895.1
4471	PA4460_at	2609.2	2126.3	1628.8	1906.2	1628.2
4472	PA4461_at	1646.4	1571.5	863.4	931.4	1020.9
4473	PA4462_rpoN_at	800.5	715.0	351.9	511.6	618.0
4474	PA4463_at	1221.0	1153.9	1057.5	1283.0	957.5
4475	PA4464_ptsN_at	1509.0	1578.7	2076.3	1524.5	1525.7
4476	PA4465_at	1189.1	942.9	899.3	841.6	890.2
4477	PA4466_at	969.6	844.8	620.1	712.7	688.7
4478	PA4467_at	39.3	15.7	55.9	46.1	40.2
4479	PA4468_sodM_at	9.6	23.3	58.1	63.5	50.9
4480	PA4469_at	14.5	29.5	67.5	59.7	85.4
4481	PA4470_fumC1_at	31.0	27.2	53.5	46.7	62.6
4482	PA4471_at	4.3	16.9	52.6	38.2	32.2
4483	PA4472_pmbA_at	116.4	86.3	92.8	118.5	98.9
4484	PA4473_at	700.1	774.5	461.6	496.1	491.8
4485	PA4474_at	191.4	201.0	199.4	167.2	266.1
4486	PA4475_at	158.7	149.0	150.6	164.0	181.2
4487	PA4476_at	135.2	103.7	129.7	139.4	181.4
4488	PA4477_cafA_at	193.1	253.1	226.2	232.2	206.8
4489	PA4478_at	217.0	232.9	232.8	189.1	212.2
4490	PA4479_mreD_at	772.0	650.3	1200.2	937.0	809.1
4491	PA4480_mreC_at	1571.6	1452.6	1402.1	1331.3	1268.1
4492	PA4481_mreB_at	1664.6	1533.3	1779.9	1841.3	1713.6
4493	PA4482_gatC_at	554.1	793.7	1305.0	1059.4	1000.1
4494	PA4483_gatA_at	1241.1	1381.2	991.6	1209.4	1194.6
4495	PA4484_gatB_at	1053.6	939.5	1063.5	1164.7	993.0
4496	PA4485_at	87.0	63.2	65.6	59.8	80.6
4497	PA4486_at	109.0	98.2	182.3	145.7	118.1
4498	PA4487_at	145.2	132.8	124.4	188.3	191.6
4499	PA4488_at	130.4	99.3	160.0	106.9	119.6
4500	PA4489_at	394.2	334.0	294.7	357.5	295.1
4501	PA4490_at	551.3	443.5	637.6	585.3	575.4
4502	PA4491_at	362.5	324.0	394.9	332.2	356.5
4503	PA4492_at	813.5	619.6	445.4	555.8	557.2
4504	PA4493_at	216.8	261.8	188.2	272.7	235.5
4505	PA4494_at	49.5	96.4	113.9	118.4	127.1
4506	PA4495_at	321.4	368.3	462.7	325.8	401.7
4507	PA4496_at	431.0	439.0	516.9	707.3	596.4
4508	PA4497_at	160.3	197.5	139.7	130.7	137.6
4509	PA4498_at	466.5	258.8	261.3	265.1	298.1
4510	PA4499_at	343.2	200.2	226.1	208.9	206.8
4511	PA4500_at	7992.6	3770.4	4745.7	3895.9	3807.3
4512	PA4501_at	6275.4	2448.2	3236.6	2782.6	2505.2
4513	PA4502_at	4843.2	2768.6	3689.1	3426.1	2926.3
4514	PA4503_at	3565.2	2027.2	2739.2	2018.6	2003.6
4515	PA4504_at	3844.8	2303.8	3229.1	2818.7	2431.6
4516	PA4505_at	2797.3	2084.0	1418.3	1276.5	1500.0
4517	PA4506_at	4095.7	3022.0	3756.0	3079.3	2670.2
4518	PA4507_at	58.7	145.4	115.1	90.5	86.6

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4519	PA4508_at	61.8	66.5	109.1	81.9	61.8
4520	PA4509_at	19.6	32.9	72.9	68.6	58.6
4521	PA4510_at	51.3	62.7	124.6	111.0	62.7
4522	PA4511_at	98.8	86.9	157.5	169.1	132.8
4523	PA4512_at	256.4	225.1	167.7	186.4	196.6
4524	PA4513_at	8.1	33.2	84.7	79.3	96.2
4525	PA4514_at	49.5	15.7	74.4	87.2	86.1
4526	PA4515_at	61.3	87.9	297.7	328.6	307.2
4527	PA4516_at	51.9	66.4	188.3	184.0	161.5
4528	PA4517_at	144.1	92.7	105.6	90.9	109.0
4529	PA4518_at	30.2	75.6	89.1	48.8	103.9
4530	PA4519_at	237.6	682.7	442.6	512.5	768.2
4531	PA4520_at	57.1	114.7	130.2	123.1	139.8
4532	PA4521_at	85.3	77.9	143.3	115.5	119.0
4533	PA4522_ampD_at	75.9	95.8	70.8	93.1	79.9
4534	PA4523_at	88.5	68.4	106.2	141.7	112.7
4535	PA4524_nadC_at	114.5	124.1	104.1	134.1	121.6
4536	PA4525_pilA_at	492.9	703.8	407.2	463.7	694.0
4537	PA4526_pilB_at	203.8	246.4	230.8	221.8	207.6
4538	PA4527_pilC_at	136.8	170.8	88.8	103.6	119.1
4539	PA4528_pilD_at	124.3	130.5	224.6	171.1	202.7
4540	PA4529_at	384.0	250.7	267.3	278.0	286.2
4541	PA4530_at	176.4	191.2	270.5	227.6	205.5
4542	PA4531_at	25.8	52.1	68.2	30.0	68.7
4543	PA4532_at	83.9	145.5	161.2	156.2	160.0
4544	PA4533_at	70.7	75.1	122.2	119.9	113.5
4545	PA4534_at	81.4	96.2	77.6	52.2	84.8
4546	PA4535_at	134.3	245.8	115.1	151.2	139.7
4547	PA4536_at	125.2	206.7	203.7	212.8	216.8
4548	PA4537_at	184.5	329.2	282.6	254.3	279.4
4549	PA4538_ndh_at	343.5	289.0	375.2	343.2	306.4
4550	PA4539_at	72.4	79.5	41.7	49.2	67.5
4551	PA4540_at	3.7	4.8	7.9	4.3	22.4
4552	PA4541_at	30.8	23.0	59.9	50.5	55.4
4553	PA4542_clpB_at	321.2	289.1	76.0	114.0	108.2
4554	PA4543_at	99.6	106.8	112.6	114.5	140.7
4555	PA4544_rluD_at	462.3	591.2	393.3	366.5	416.6
4556	PA4545_comL_at	1238.2	1142.9	844.8	912.8	958.3
4557	PA4546_pilS_at	282.7	301.2	139.6	180.0	232.7
4558	PA4547_pilR_at	294.8	293.1	213.7	255.5	282.3
4559	PA4548_at	220.0	140.8	322.4	258.5	234.7
4560	PA4549_fimT_at	14.0	3.0	26.3	7.6	6.4
4561	PA4550_fimU_at	56.5	81.0	60.4	50.0	74.3
4562	PA4551_pilV_at	67.7	117.0	172.8	104.7	104.6
4563	PA4552_pilW_at	99.4	185.0	100.2	104.8	94.3
4564	PA4553_pilX_at	84.2	63.0	14.5	39.0	54.4
4565	PA4554_pilY1_at	106.2	112.1	74.3	83.7	84.2
4566	PA4555_pilY2_at	70.2	97.4	45.0	53.8	80.3
4567	PA4556_pilE_at	141.0	169.5	148.7	96.2	146.4
4568	PA4557_lytB_at	357.1	465.8	330.2	389.8	377.1
4569	PA4558_at	1636.1	1688.7	1136.0	1420.9	1515.3
4570	PA4559_lspA_at	562.1	550.3	516.6	471.3	492.5
4571	PA4560_ileS_at	529.4	517.1	746.1	773.1	770.0
4572	PA4561_ribF_at	697.5	480.8	742.5	771.0	693.4
4573	PA4562_at	172.6	171.5	222.2	222.9	222.7
4574	PA4563_rpsT_at	4512.8	4194.4	3401.4	3990.9	3796.8
4575	PA4564_at	150.5	164.7	154.0	197.4	185.6
4576	PA4565_proB_at	846.7	867.1	803.5	776.1	787.9
4577	PA4566_obg_at	700.4	767.6	749.0	792.9	817.4
4578	PA4567_rpmA_at	3642.5	2119.4	2834.0	3948.9	3227.9
4579	PA4568_rplU_at	11068.9	4319.3	7749.0	7114.7	5358.0
4580	PA4569_ispB_at	946.2	802.3	1210.2	1097.5	957.7
4581	PA4570_at	53.8	56.8	105.8	60.5	85.8
4582	PA4571_at	52.6	26.8	56.0	42.3	34.4
4583	PA4572_fklB_at	540.5	599.1	647.6	739.5	820.3
4584	PA4573_at	70.5	76.4	110.8	108.4	81.9
4585	PA4574_at	179.1	224.0	252.8	262.2	279.3
4586	PA4575_at	73.8	68.6	98.0	71.1	84.3
4587	PA4576_at	312.8	290.8	394.6	348.0	345.8
4588	PA4577_at	1.9	13.2	16.7	20.2	42.2
4589	PA4578_at	3598.3	2546.6	3044.5	2973.0	2709.1
4590	PA4579_at	156.8	139.7	196.2	154.2	148.3
4591	PA4580_at	99.9	117.8	165.0	154.1	124.2

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4592	PA4581_rtcR_at	72.6	74.4	56.6	68.7	74.6
4593	PA4582_at	81.0	79.6	117.7	160.4	105.6
4594	PA4583_at	92.9	119.4	133.1	185.6	156.3
4595	PA4584_at	52.7	47.7	113.9	85.6	116.4
4596	PA4585_rtcA_at	55.8	62.3	135.9	122.3	126.6
4597	PA4586_at	2.6	20.8	79.9	21.9	52.7
4598	PA4587_ccpR_at	34.7	50.1	41.2	27.6	59.0
4599	PA4588_gdhA_at	48.7	50.6	90.6	95.4	107.1
4600	PA4589_at	53.6	53.3	86.5	65.8	59.2
4601	PA4590_pra_at	95.4	142.8	103.4	93.2	126.4
4602	PA4591_at	50.4	63.0	92.1	93.1	72.5
4603	PA4592_at	102.8	97.9	159.2	156.1	139.9
4604	PA4593_at	40.5	64.2	78.4	49.3	52.6
4605	PA4594_at	45.0	60.1	88.6	63.1	85.5
4606	PA4595_at	1083.2	850.8	939.7	1093.3	1130.7
4607	PA4596_at	75.3	95.1	111.2	87.7	73.7
4608	PA4597_oprJ_at	78.1	69.9	155.6	166.0	140.0
4609	PA4598_mexD_at	47.3	62.6	64.2	43.0	57.9
4610	PA4599_mexC_at	35.9	45.7	33.1	24.2	47.8
4611	PA4600_nfxB_at	148.4	190.5	121.3	121.6	114.9
4612	PA4601_at	157.8	182.1	187.1	182.6	189.9
4613	PA4602_glyA3_at	2196.8	1855.7	1023.4	1590.2	1714.5
4614	PA4603_at	35.4	40.3	47.1	51.6	61.0
4615	PA4604_at	263.6	182.4	179.2	245.9	250.9
4616	PA4605_at	444.5	403.6	196.6	279.9	330.7
4617	PA4606_at	1166.5	713.7	1084.4	843.0	1064.8
4618	PA4607_at	181.3	438.7	249.0	391.6	354.3
4619	PA4608_at	93.0	109.8	164.8	118.0	123.5
4620	PA4609_radA_at	82.3	95.0	140.0	110.3	143.0
4621	PA4610_at	10.0	2.8	45.5	36.0	40.6
4622	PA4611_at	47.0	145.8	75.8	79.0	76.9
4623	PA4612_at	38.0	53.2	58.9	52.0	51.6
4624	PA4613_katB_at	51.4	103.4	92.7	66.7	116.5
4625	PA4614_mscL_at	131.8	250.7	194.6	185.7	224.9
4626	PA4615_at	80.6	101.0	129.8	134.2	103.7
4627	PA4616_at	84.1	82.0	110.3	90.5	90.7
4628	PA4617_at	90.0	99.3	120.2	141.4	146.8
4629	PA4618_at	71.1	61.1	75.0	50.6	71.1
4630	PA4619_at	84.6	116.7	77.6	91.0	88.0
4631	PA4620_at	150.7	176.8	90.8	143.1	156.2
4632	PA4621_at	52.9	65.0	77.3	74.1	71.5
4633	PA4622_at	47.2	51.1	62.4	63.4	51.2
4634	PA4623_r_at	88.5	47.5	71.7	53.2	67.6
4635	PA4624_at	65.7	95.7	137.8	114.2	105.0
4636	PA4625_at	399.6	410.6	234.1	292.2	318.5
4637	PA4626_hprA_at	253.8	152.5	194.6	250.5	183.6
4638	PA4627_at	385.9	347.9	462.9	401.9	393.2
4639	PA4628_lytP_at	131.1	171.0	163.5	149.1	176.2
4640	PA4629_at	83.5	71.3	95.6	97.5	92.6
4641	PA4630_at	15.0	34.2	4.7	23.2	39.1
4642	PA4631_at	294.4	230.5	216.2	209.2	264.2
4643	PA4632_at	1373.9	1127.3	1129.2	1286.2	1276.9
4644	PA4633_at	538.3	486.7	309.2	307.5	455.1
4645	PA4634_at	38.1	70.2	100.9	82.6	99.8
4646	PA4635_at	2.1	2.5	3.9	7.3	15.9
4647	PA4636_at	907.8	658.9	575.9	574.3	636.9
4648	PA4637_i_at	26.9	31.5	41.5	41.2	24.7
4649	PA4638_at	58.2	74.7	56.4	53.2	49.0
4650	PA4639_at	751.8	484.4	447.3	826.5	806.5
4651	PA4640_mqoB_at	1175.4	984.5	1836.2	1686.1	1560.3
4652	PA4641_at	43.3	106.1	161.9	79.9	90.5
4653	PA4642_at	208.1	348.0	170.9	276.1	308.3
4654	PA4643_at	225.4	262.1	196.8	190.8	224.5
4655	PA4644_at	130.5	124.8	80.8	112.9	94.0
4656	PA4645_at	487.3	555.7	541.7	692.3	624.1
4657	PA4646_upp_at	805.4	743.7	959.5	918.2	880.7
4658	PA4647_uraA_at	373.5	349.4	263.2	359.0	346.3
4659	PA4648_at	57.8	81.8	79.4	64.0	77.3
4660	PA4649_at	69.9	37.3	50.0	30.1	67.5
4661	PA4650_at	6.7	10.2	52.3	16.7	28.5
4662	PA4651_at	18.2	23.8	54.5	24.0	29.9
4663	PA4652_at	6.1	1.9	42.5	6.9	5.4
4664	PA4653_at	23.0	11.7	21.8	24.4	16.5

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4665	PA4654_at	4.1	9.7	19.8	8.0	27.6
4666	PA4655_hemH_at	561.4	448.9	341.0	531.9	494.0
4667	PA4656_at	131.2	118.3	55.7	85.9	140.6
4668	PA4657_at	164.5	148.5	118.6	125.5	105.2
4669	PA4658_at	190.7	211.8	161.4	127.0	129.6
4670	PA4659_at	97.0	89.2	57.3	56.2	55.8
4671	PA4660_phr_at	239.3	193.1	196.5	128.4	125.0
4672	PA4661_at	907.2	1169.1	870.3	1195.7	1242.5
4673	PA4662_murI_at	342.4	265.9	522.5	361.7	374.2
4674	PA4663_moeB_at	302.7	286.2	208.8	417.0	285.0
4675	PA4664_hemK_at	509.4	459.9	459.1	541.5	564.2
4676	PA4665_prfA_at	743.4	663.2	989.6	896.0	826.9
4677	PA4666_hemA_at	420.5	381.0	505.6	443.4	492.0
4678	PA4667_at	604.7	594.7	609.9	578.5	604.6
4679	PA4668_at	400.7	373.5	691.7	570.4	467.4
4680	PA4669_ipk_at	384.8	440.5	288.2	320.5	356.2
4681	PA4670_prs_at	2578.4	2049.4	3674.4	3283.1	2639.6
4682	PA4671_at	6915.5	3389.0	4063.1	3767.8	3641.3
4683	PA4672_at	1104.0	1032.8	1497.6	1432.9	1444.1
4684	PA4673_at	494.2	724.5	1219.3	959.9	945.4
4685	PA4674_at	5.2	29.7	28.4	8.3	23.5
4686	PA4675_at	34.4	121.7	647.7	581.5	623.4
4687	PA4676_at	374.1	293.9	229.5	355.1	371.9
4688	PA4677_at	218.7	260.0	297.2	264.4	302.4
4689	PA4678_rimI_at	139.8	211.0	102.8	156.8	148.3
4690	PA4679_at	244.3	193.5	427.7	308.7	275.4
4691	PA4680_at	2.8	31.6	58.3	13.4	36.1
4692	PA4681_at	45.0	49.8	54.2	39.0	48.6
4693	PA4682_at	44.7	88.3	69.9	86.7	86.6
4694	PA4683_at	27.9	6.2	8.0	16.6	32.1
4695	PA4684_at	590.6	629.9	392.6	508.0	458.8
4696	PA4685_at	512.2	542.2	441.4	516.9	517.2
4697	PA4686_at	1055.6	1003.1	666.5	809.4	869.0
4698	PA4687_hitA_at	110.9	317.2	384.4	442.8	459.0
4699	PA4688_hitB_at	47.8	96.2	267.9	243.4	230.0
4700	PA4689_at	119.4	98.7	99.5	80.7	119.2
4701	PA4690_at	175.9	231.4	102.1	144.1	162.4
4702	PA4691_at	38.6	24.7	100.0	48.3	61.5
4703	PA4692_at	51.5	49.8	107.6	66.1	89.5
4704	PA4693_pssA_at	197.9	199.0	225.3	204.8	227.5
4705	PA4694_ilvC_at	1005.4	1304.8	1198.3	1399.8	1344.4
4706	PA4695_ilvH_at	1224.4	1190.0	984.6	847.4	957.2
4707	PA4696_ilvI_at	504.6	545.2	520.6	500.9	521.6
4708	PA4697_at	362.6	441.5	428.3	318.6	325.3
4709	PA4698_at	319.0	372.0	298.6	305.0	358.8
4710	PA4699_at	214.4	274.7	286.7	307.8	253.9
4711	PA4700_mrcB_at	407.4	366.6	482.8	459.4	346.3
4712	PA4701_at	473.6	566.5	530.4	630.4	552.5
4713	PA4702_at	34.2	56.4	55.7	50.2	64.2
4714	PA4703_at	27.9	36.6	38.9	43.7	47.7
4715	PA4704_at	82.5	81.2	94.1	71.4	88.4
4716	PA4705_at	32.1	77.4	79.4	108.2	93.2
4717	PA4706_at	57.6	61.2	107.5	87.7	121.3
4718	PA4707_at	56.0	32.8	91.6	61.1	54.7
4719	PA4708_at	80.3	74.9	129.2	146.8	108.0
4720	PA4709_at	60.6	54.8	91.5	108.9	73.1
4721	PA4710_at	11.9	33.4	77.8	48.2	63.4
4722	PA4711_at	139.3	104.8	83.0	126.5	136.4
4723	PA4712_at	79.0	67.0	62.6	83.1	88.1
4724	PA4713_at	6.9	26.9	7.4	46.6	27.9
4725	PA4714_at	79.7	111.7	94.8	83.1	104.6
4726	PA4715_at	186.0	202.7	135.1	157.6	188.6
4727	PA4716_at	81.9	52.8	75.1	67.0	48.3
4728	PA4717_at	153.0	168.5	137.1	137.0	157.5
4729	PA4718_at	103.2	56.4	117.5	82.1	95.9
4730	PA4719_at	252.5	354.6	266.2	253.0	304.7
4731	PA4720_trmA_at	553.9	442.8	608.9	597.5	472.8
4732	PA4721_at	74.7	80.2	192.1	145.5	123.3
4733	PA4722_at	207.3	260.0	492.2	308.4	357.2
4734	PA4723_dksA_at	1873.0	1677.7	1320.3	1639.1	1546.5
4735	PA4724_at	136.0	152.8	108.6	103.1	93.1
4736	PA4725_at	115.6	112.5	68.1	115.3	99.9
4737	PA4726_at	496.1	503.5	361.3	410.0	437.7

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4738	PA4727_pcnB_at	629.3	598.1	850.5	628.4	573.6
4739	PA4728_folk_at	348.8	303.2	217.9	211.2	294.4
4740	PA4729_panB_at	930.1	839.8	797.6	852.7	769.7
4741	PA4730_panC_at	797.9	752.1	596.2	712.5	654.4
4742	PA4731_panD_at	552.9	778.7	357.4	444.3	516.0
4743	PA4732_pgi_at	545.5	510.2	465.9	680.4	500.1
4744	PA4733_acsB_at	180.2	200.5	171.6	146.4	184.3
4745	PA4734_at	226.9	219.5	162.2	203.6	220.2
4746	PA4735_at	200.4	240.8	248.7	236.1	202.7
4747	PA4736_at	157.2	189.7	135.7	146.2	185.1
4748	PA4737_at	85.8	162.1	143.6	118.7	141.3
4749	PA4738_at	94.9	41.4	49.5	38.5	69.4
4750	PA4739_at	34.2	44.9	61.1	68.6	83.5
4751	PA4740_pnp_at	1277.7	1639.7	1159.5	1333.1	1364.8
4752	PA4741_rps0_at	2428.3	2011.1	2116.9	2202.3	2164.5
4753	PA4742_truB_at	667.6	832.5	905.7	920.5	923.4
4754	PA4743_rbfA_at	1047.4	1230.1	926.3	929.0	1063.0
4755	PA4744_infB_at	1347.8	1531.3	1715.6	1908.4	1720.0
4756	PA4745_nusA_at	2032.9	2220.4	2969.3	2864.1	2446.2
4757	PA4746_at	1148.3	1194.8	917.8	994.2	1073.4
4758	PA4747_secG_at	1181.5	1223.5	757.9	909.6	961.6
4759	PA4748_tpiA_at	1137.0	1203.8	1668.1	1947.6	1796.2
4760	PA4749_glmM_at	475.1	473.7	523.1	446.3	474.1
4761	PA4750_folP_at	369.3	370.0	295.1	342.4	392.9
4762	PA4751_ftsH_at	1270.7	1042.9	860.8	887.9	907.4
4763	PA4752_ftsJ_at	188.3	206.5	144.8	131.3	125.1
4764	PA4753_at	447.7	480.6	424.1	370.6	455.4
4765	PA4754_at	195.3	250.2	528.3	336.4	348.0
4766	PA4755_greA_at	348.1	514.7	266.6	386.9	449.9
4767	PA4756_carB_at	989.9	956.9	1024.8	1004.9	1074.1
4768	PA4757_at	599.7	673.7	735.7	679.9	739.5
4769	PA4758_carA_at	673.2	710.5	702.0	701.4	653.5
4770	PA4759_dapB_at	503.6	697.3	88.3	106.5	168.4
4771	PA4760_dnaJ_at	981.5	980.6	219.7	231.2	278.0
4772	PA4761_dnaK_at	2816.1	1985.3	356.8	524.3	523.8
4773	PA4762_grpE_at	5322.3	2926.1	978.1	1006.7	1105.8
4774	PA4763_recN_at	247.2	228.4	201.4	220.9	219.1
4775	PA4764_fur_at	511.7	757.4	484.3	554.8	676.5
4776	PA4765_omlA_at	1847.6	1318.4	1278.7	1468.6	1283.5
4777	PA4766_at	54.5	56.6	138.1	74.1	76.4
4778	PA4767_at	125.9	176.3	235.8	274.0	228.5
4779	PA4768_smpB_at	198.1	343.0	140.7	252.6	189.3
4780	PA4769_at	222.3	195.6	308.8	267.0	285.1
4781	PA4770_lldP_at	28.9	28.8	58.8	45.0	47.6
4782	PA4771_lldD_at	64.9	26.3	31.0	41.4	50.3
4783	PA4772_at	16.6	17.0	46.4	8.9	51.8
4784	PA4773_at	320.3	560.1	329.5	333.0	328.4
4785	PA4774_at	114.4	311.5	222.4	248.7	188.6
4786	PA4775_at	126.7	245.1	334.9	221.7	230.4
4787	PA4776_at	185.3	394.6	295.1	268.1	253.0
4788	PA4777_at	70.7	118.9	113.5	92.9	112.4
4789	PA4778_at	845.6	737.3	506.9	674.2	648.9
4790	PA4779_at	52.6	23.4	41.6	30.8	15.8
4791	PA4780_at	133.7	196.4	280.3	227.1	232.8
4792	PA4781_at	27.7	37.2	45.8	43.3	61.4
4793	PA4782_at	116.6	330.1	154.9	144.3	160.7
4794	PA4783_at	43.3	57.9	85.7	65.0	75.6
4795	PA4784_at	124.6	147.7	134.9	102.1	137.0
4796	PA4785_at	22.5	14.1	34.5	24.2	36.3
4797	PA4786_at	32.5	38.3	81.7	62.4	61.9
4798	PA4787_at	142.1	144.0	253.2	189.4	168.1
4799	PA4788_at	32.3	48.8	79.5	49.8	78.3
4800	PA4789_at	179.8	205.0	234.1	243.9	238.1
4801	PA4790_at	96.0	89.6	188.4	170.1	139.8
4802	PA4791_at	113.4	163.6	136.2	162.2	194.1
4803	PA4792_at	114.8	94.6	115.4	123.5	97.8
4804	PA4793_at	475.5	550.5	284.3	402.8	354.9
4805	PA4794_at	218.2	186.8	151.5	144.5	143.3
4806	PA4795_at	176.1	269.5	283.3	200.7	216.8
4807	PA4796_at	94.5	108.8	118.5	95.8	101.0
4808	PA4798_at	75.7	71.5	80.7	61.5	69.4
4809	PA4799_at	28.3	19.4	36.7	28.7	21.0
4810	PA4800_at	31.4	40.3	47.6	55.5	58.0

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4811	PA4801_at	77.3	92.1	59.4	75.2	80.9
4812	PA4802_at	69.6	76.6	116.0	103.4	97.3
4813	PA4803_at	83.2	73.1	95.5	90.9	69.4
4814	PA4804_at	42.6	36.5	42.6	55.8	41.3
4815	PA4805_at	31.1	20.1	18.2	5.6	22.9
4816	PA4806_at	28.6	57.2	65.0	32.5	28.7
4817	PA4807_selB_at	165.0	111.1	127.2	115.4	142.1
4818	PA4808_selA_at	213.3	169.8	138.6	178.9	185.8
4819	PA4809_fdhE_at	108.4	57.0	99.8	116.4	101.2
4820	PA4810_fdnI_at	131.7	128.7	100.4	116.7	88.9
4821	PA4811_fdnH_at	168.5	118.2	118.9	128.6	103.9
4822	PA4812_fdnG_at	219.8	265.9	255.4	236.0	251.7
4823	PA4813_lipC_at	2.8	10.3	9.4	18.1	15.0
4824	PA4814_fadhH2_at	24.8	20.6	31.4	25.6	20.8
4825	PA4815_at	61.9	69.8	71.8	74.0	61.5
4826	PA4816_at	57.5	68.5	76.3	87.0	77.5
4827	PA4817_at	103.8	141.3	111.8	101.9	118.7
4828	PA4818_at	4.5	15.0	31.8	43.8	43.0
4829	PA4819_at	8.0	26.5	65.7	41.5	42.5
4830	PA4820_at	15.9	8.3	36.4	17.2	18.2
4831	PA4821_at	58.3	56.6	61.0	89.1	79.5
4832	PA4822_at	21.5	10.7	40.4	10.6	32.8
4833	PA4823_at	4.5	12.7	52.7	13.7	24.6
4834	PA4824_at	3.7	15.7	36.8	10.0	41.6
4835	PA4825_mgtA_at	11.3	13.4	33.3	20.0	40.3
4836	PA4826_at	44.4	54.0	56.5	96.7	105.0
4837	PA4827_at	12.8	43.6	36.4	46.5	38.9
4838	PA4828_at	24.9	36.1	6.4	28.7	41.2
4839	PA4829_lpd3_at	32.9	34.8	19.0	28.6	29.7
4840	PA4830_at	59.1	41.6	84.9	77.3	55.1
4841	PA4831_at	53.7	69.9	127.7	114.3	74.8
4842	PA4832_at	16.7	19.9	51.9	30.8	41.9
4843	PA4833_at	31.8	56.3	36.8	30.2	50.6
4844	PA4834_at	1.4	6.8	8.0	6.1	31.5
4845	PA4835_at	9.7	10.2	39.1	37.8	33.9
4846	PA4836_at	31.0	24.2	67.4	71.9	29.9
4847	PA4837_at	49.2	41.2	113.7	48.7	114.2
4848	PA4838_at	40.2	32.7	75.1	65.7	65.1
4849	PA4839_speA_at	1133.7	1306.3	1241.8	1003.5	983.9
4850	PA4840_at	161.6	324.7	124.8	229.5	273.4
4851	PA4841_at	231.7	184.9	188.3	198.0	209.1
4852	PA4842_at	567.7	699.2	374.2	413.6	467.5
4853	PA4843_at	764.3	492.6	325.4	401.0	338.1
4854	PA4844_at	81.7	57.4	56.8	50.9	53.2
4855	PA4845_dipZ_at	126.4	105.5	106.2	102.4	152.4
4856	PA4846_aroQ1_at	1405.9	1449.8	946.7	1031.1	1190.2
4857	PA4847_accB_at	2904.1	2810.3	4370.1	3308.8	2813.6
4858	PA4848_accC_at	1980.3	1663.3	2118.0	2427.5	2095.6
4859	PA4849_at	70.0	52.2	191.8	111.5	111.2
4860	PA4850_prmA_at	728.2	622.7	532.4	541.9	560.7
4861	PA4851_at	488.2	365.6	530.7	432.3	476.0
4862	PA4852_at	878.4	1087.8	1297.9	1348.9	1129.3
4863	PA4853_fis_at	1774.8	1792.9	1144.5	1191.7	1145.0
4864	PA4854_purH_at	561.2	688.8	589.1	551.5	589.7
4865	PA4855_purD_at	755.6	657.4	460.9	664.2	728.3
4866	PA4856_at	566.0	459.4	423.4	391.5	387.3
4867	PA4857_at	39.7	41.5	35.7	49.8	45.9
4868	PA4858_at	5.1	24.5	31.3	8.7	20.1
4869	PA4859_at	32.7	56.6	84.4	65.2	88.3
4870	PA4860_at	12.8	21.2	42.1	17.2	54.8
4871	PA4861_at	6.2	16.8	54.9	45.4	53.4
4872	PA4862_at	25.8	18.9	53.6	50.3	42.3
4873	PA4863_at	213.9	179.7	120.9	169.9	181.2
4874	PA4864_ureD_at	87.4	69.8	75.2	56.0	69.1
4875	PA4865_ureA_at	214.8	199.8	292.6	229.9	235.3
4876	PA4866_at	154.2	111.6	122.0	134.4	145.2
4877	PA4867_ureB_at	106.0	96.1	19.6	66.9	75.7
4878	PA4868_ureC_at	126.3	98.2	95.0	60.4	100.4
4879	PA4869_at	110.9	117.3	104.3	149.5	135.9
4880	PA4870_at	168.7	206.5	92.2	98.6	103.4
4881	PA4871_at	2.5	18.4	33.4	18.5	15.6
4882	PA4872_at	297.9	241.2	354.9	315.6	361.3
4883	PA4873_at	112.1	122.8	138.1	142.0	170.3

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4884	PA4874_at	137.4	175.3	166.1	191.1	167.3
4885	PA4875_at	57.5	56.1	33.8	29.9	42.8
4886	PA4876_osmE_at	66.4	116.6	103.1	79.2	90.8
4887	PA4877_at	22.4	43.2	44.8	31.4	47.5
4888	PA4878_at	67.5	114.3	151.7	108.4	125.6
4889	PA4879_at	42.4	39.7	66.4	49.6	50.8
4890	PA4880_at	80.9	82.9	51.5	48.7	61.8
4891	PA4881_at	53.3	35.2	44.3	38.3	48.2
4892	PA4882_at	12.2	9.7	8.7	3.9	21.5
4893	PA4883_at	3.2	1.7	17.8	5.4	24.6
4894	PA4884_at	27.7	9.5	54.1	38.0	47.1
4895	PA4885_irlR_at	49.7	73.4	46.5	61.9	79.2
4896	PA4886_at	2.2	14.8	37.8	20.8	34.7
4897	PA4887_at	130.9	81.5	188.5	148.2	226.2
4898	PA4888_at	104.6	108.1	147.0	122.3	116.2
4899	PA4889_at	100.4	70.9	122.1	96.8	107.7
4900	PA4890_at	176.1	143.4	158.9	159.4	157.6
4901	PA4891_ureE_at	30.4	19.1	13.4	11.7	52.2
4902	PA4892_ureF_at	68.4	50.9	100.8	71.3	68.8
4903	PA4893_ureG_at	116.6	119.4	111.3	78.8	99.7
4904	PA4894_i_at	40.3	39.8	54.0	40.8	56.8
4905	PA4895_at	18.6	15.9	44.9	26.2	28.8
4906	PA4896_at	21.7	41.1	66.1	68.3	63.7
4907	PA4897_at	25.8	28.2	94.2	56.2	42.3
4908	PA4898_at	2.8	2.2	47.2	4.1	31.4
4909	PA4899_at	7.3	9.3	7.2	29.5	34.2
4910	PA4900_at	30.5	27.2	66.3	56.0	37.4
4911	PA4901_mdIC_at	4.3	11.8	21.8	18.3	26.6
4912	PA4902_at	58.0	58.4	42.0	67.3	68.7
4913	PA4903_at	8.9	11.2	45.6	32.4	31.3
4914	PA4904_vanA_at	45.7	25.5	35.2	35.3	45.0
4915	PA4905_vanB_at	23.7	1.9	21.9	17.7	18.5
4916	PA4906_at	102.7	143.7	147.7	155.6	124.2
4917	PA4907_at	512.1	547.9	694.1	622.1	554.0
4918	PA4908_at	25.9	21.8	59.0	43.6	59.9
4919	PA4909_at	7.3	8.1	9.5	14.7	23.4
4920	PA4910_at	35.9	22.9	38.8	37.2	36.5
4921	PA4911_at	1.8	9.6	10.2	9.0	30.2
4922	PA4912_at	15.2	11.0	22.6	8.7	28.2
4923	PA4913_at	59.5	52.7	60.5	65.0	59.3
4924	PA4914_at	27.2	34.8	74.6	44.8	66.3
4925	PA4915_at	13.3	85.2	51.3	45.8	89.9
4926	PA4916_at	93.0	138.2	85.3	86.2	131.1
4927	PA4917_at	80.9	143.2	142.1	118.6	114.4
4928	PA4918_at	303.2	219.1	192.5	253.3	226.3
4929	PA4919_pncB1_at	502.4	400.4	256.3	284.4	284.3
4930	PA4920_nadE_at	1022.0	919.4	587.8	720.8	631.5
4931	PA4921_at	76.5	57.1	90.3	93.0	95.1
4932	PA4922_azuD_at	1817.8	2136.1	1540.5	2002.3	2038.6
4933	PA4923_at	137.1	194.7	151.0	236.3	279.8
4934	PA4924_at	73.8	86.8	97.0	84.5	89.8
4935	PA4925_at	4.2	31.3	78.0	34.0	37.0
4936	PA4926_at	4.9	23.8	74.6	38.0	44.4
4937	PA4927_at	41.4	28.8	22.1	16.4	28.5
4938	PA4928_at	316.5	322.6	321.7	439.2	333.7
4939	PA4929_at	51.5	32.3	59.4	40.2	65.4
4940	PA4930_alr_at	129.3	107.3	172.2	134.3	167.2
4941	PA4931_dnaB_at	488.5	565.8	295.4	445.4	486.8
4942	PA4932_rplI_at	2375.9	2065.3	9649.9	5747.4	4344.0
4943	PA4933_at	2116.7	1971.3	5926.0	3464.2	3046.4
4944	PA4934_rpsR_at	5217.1	2951.5	5187.9	4926.6	4288.1
4945	PA4935_rpsF_at	4991.5	3459.2	3945.5	4078.8	3644.4
4946	PA4936_at	221.5	395.3	322.1	374.3	354.2
4947	PA4937_rnr_at	769.9	827.1	1052.5	830.6	789.2
4948	PA4938_purA_at	867.1	1073.6	1116.9	1319.6	1074.8
4949	PA4939_at	442.0	372.6	338.9	370.1	370.7
4950	PA4940_at	616.9	526.9	698.0	634.7	651.3
4951	PA4941_hflC_at	1427.8	1090.7	911.3	990.3	986.2
4952	PA4942_hflK_at	1181.4	1116.9	813.7	968.4	957.8
4953	PA4943_at	1188.3	1097.0	1230.1	1088.8	1025.4
4954	PA4944_at	2723.2	2651.9	1486.7	1629.6	1875.6
4955	PA4945_miaA_at	214.6	202.8	171.1	202.5	174.8
4956	PA4946_mutL_at	384.4	380.1	262.8	280.8	312.9

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4957	PA4947_amiB_at	709.3	608.8	602.4	630.1	640.0
4958	PA4948_at	178.2	201.5	315.9	295.4	288.7
4959	PA4949_at	159.0	163.6	133.3	124.7	164.1
4960	PA4950_at	121.5	128.7	131.9	122.1	125.8
4961	PA4951_orn_at	327.8	359.4	419.3	488.9	526.8
4962	PA4952_at	310.0	319.4	301.9	288.6	308.9
4963	PA4953_motB_at	410.2	526.5	249.6	274.2	315.4
4964	PA4954_motA_at	176.6	163.1	292.1	191.2	170.2
4965	PA4955_at	266.1	213.3	228.6	234.4	237.3
4966	PA4956_rhdA_at	397.7	331.8	365.2	398.0	352.2
4967	PA4957_psd_at	623.2	533.4	459.3	479.0	530.4
4968	PA4958_at	179.3	120.7	252.7	271.7	240.7
4969	PA4959_at	272.1	242.7	396.1	266.2	270.8
4970	PA4960_at	301.8	274.0	333.4	310.9	369.3
4971	PA4961_at	371.0	380.1	369.4	388.0	349.8
4972	PA4962_at	56.4	51.5	119.6	95.5	73.6
4973	PA4963_at	246.7	345.3	241.2	298.6	306.5
4974	PA4964_parC_at	256.6	251.1	293.3	311.6	326.4
4975	PA4965_at	241.8	387.1	261.3	264.3	266.4
4976	PA4966_at	211.5	230.5	309.9	279.3	287.7
4977	PA4967_parE_at	238.3	272.6	244.4	277.5	301.2
4978	PA4968_at	249.2	213.1	233.6	195.0	190.9
4979	PA4969_at	108.0	99.1	136.8	84.3	106.5
4980	PA4970_at	402.5	451.8	219.9	249.2	258.1
4981	PA4971_at	252.2	266.5	121.6	129.1	141.3
4982	PA4972_at	218.8	259.8	187.4	155.0	174.9
4983	PA4973_thiC_at	70.8	96.5	101.8	132.7	129.8
4984	PA4974_at	900.9	773.8	555.8	776.8	798.9
4985	PA4975_at	25.8	41.9	36.9	26.6	47.2
4986	PA4976_aspC_at	72.5	94.2	86.3	106.1	83.7
4987	PA4977_at	66.0	76.7	64.7	87.4	84.7
4988	PA4978_at	46.4	53.7	103.0	58.0	83.9
4989	PA4979_at	45.8	38.2	86.4	44.7	58.6
4990	PA4980_at	71.3	110.7	110.9	81.6	109.1
4991	PA4981_at	1.6	22.3	69.2	33.4	48.4
4992	PA4982_at	46.9	47.0	89.4	47.6	54.0
4993	PA4983_at	80.1	71.3	97.9	84.6	78.6
4994	PA4984_at	69.4	48.4	42.9	68.2	51.2
4995	PA4985_at	45.4	33.7	42.7	31.9	46.6
4996	PA4986_at	2.0	14.4	31.9	9.5	22.9
4997	PA4987_at	68.1	89.3	56.3	81.3	105.3
4998	PA4988_waaA_at	100.1	99.5	186.4	103.9	120.8
4999	PA4989_at	12.8	25.9	83.5	56.9	68.0
5000	PA4990_at	65.1	40.8	52.3	38.6	52.0
5001	PA4991_at	210.2	205.1	376.3	276.0	248.6
5002	PA4992_at	181.3	156.6	375.4	167.6	218.1
5003	PA4993_at	64.5	102.0	64.1	69.1	68.2
5004	PA4994_at	63.8	44.2	62.8	57.7	60.7
5005	PA4995_at	20.2	15.4	16.1	20.9	23.3
5006	PA4996_rfaE_at	351.0	410.8	637.8	595.5	549.3
5007	PA4997_msbA_at	677.6	545.3	724.0	614.4	566.2
5008	PA4998_at	627.6	557.7	552.4	540.6	499.5
5009	PA4999_at	118.8	100.3	155.1	114.1	124.2
5010	PA5000_at	228.6	385.5	123.6	186.0	205.9
5011	PA5001_at	256.3	278.2	321.8	279.8	359.6
5012	PA5002_at	199.3	241.3	234.4	251.0	308.6
5013	PA5003_at	294.5	326.5	446.9	388.7	422.3
5014	PA5004_at	319.5	334.8	373.8	403.8	409.5
5015	PA5005_at	872.8	826.2	790.9	865.9	891.0
5016	PA5006_at	117.2	108.6	221.6	192.6	156.6
5017	PA5007_at	185.5	223.8	175.5	219.3	235.4
5018	PA5008_at	326.4	352.8	345.9	354.1	458.4
5019	PA5009_waaP_at	427.6	338.8	351.8	374.7	328.5
5020	PA5010_waaG_at	349.9	437.7	370.5	379.5	377.4
5021	PA5011_waaC_at	521.2	556.7	568.5	606.3	586.6
5022	PA5012_waaF_at	581.1	712.4	538.6	557.6	771.1
5023	PA5013_ilvE_at	1363.9	1321.8	1197.6	1366.8	1389.0
5024	PA5014_glnE_at	227.3	165.1	227.7	167.5	222.4
5025	PA5015_aceE_at	1112.2	922.0	1537.1	1287.2	1202.0
5026	PA5016_aceF_at	863.5	785.1	608.4	777.6	709.3
5027	PA5017_at	325.7	311.9	181.3	183.3	220.2
5028	PA5018_msrA_at	337.1	279.8	390.7	390.8	358.2
5029	PA5019_at	155.9	292.9	311.4	338.6	361.8

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

5030	PA5020_at	42.2	55.4	37.3	33.3	37.7
5031	PA5021_at	90.9	91.0	197.8	160.3	131.8
5032	PA5022_at	327.5	399.3	200.7	240.4	225.9
5033	PA5023_at	40.5	120.3	99.6	114.6	115.3
5034	PA5024_at	239.7	820.4	630.8	852.4	708.0
5035	PA5025_metY_at	166.5	139.4	143.9	156.0	149.6
5036	PA5026_at	61.7	71.0	157.7	79.3	64.4
5037	PA5027_at	3.0	23.9	36.5	27.9	37.9
5038	PA5028_at	408.9	513.0	359.3	359.9	374.7
5039	PA5029_at	77.4	105.2	81.5	63.2	107.4
5040	PA5030_at	62.9	57.4	62.8	83.2	54.6
5041	PA5031_at	36.5	24.9	47.1	60.2	35.2
5042	PA5032_at	21.8	12.4	46.2	23.7	25.9
5043	PA5033_at	66.7	57.0	52.4	86.4	63.7
5044	PA5034_hemE_at	66.4	136.4	121.3	109.2	124.3
5045	PA5035_gltD_at	172.3	207.4	229.1	273.8	305.3
5046	PA5036_gltB_at	223.7	363.7	441.2	331.1	400.9
5047	PA5037_at	581.9	512.8	623.3	774.6	642.9
5048	PA5038_aroB_at	195.3	321.6	137.8	179.2	190.8
5049	PA5039_aroK_at	446.2	599.0	526.2	580.3	549.3
5050	PA5040_pilQ_at	574.5	588.1	402.8	659.0	598.2
5051	PA5041_pilP_at	464.0	687.1	523.7	608.5	602.5
5052	PA5042_pilO_at	486.7	641.2	446.8	469.5	486.9
5053	PA5043_pilN_at	502.9	666.8	519.2	576.9	546.3
5054	PA5044_pilM_at	645.4	976.7	1111.7	1040.5	1005.9
5055	PA5045_ponA_at	289.5	321.0	267.1	246.8	345.5
5056	PA5046_at	1825.3	1897.4	3069.1	2788.5	2369.1
5057	PA5047_at	238.9	303.4	488.1	440.1	424.0
5058	PA5048_at	412.4	503.7	415.5	432.8	422.2
5059	PA5049_rpmE_at	613.3	1607.2	249.8	527.4	552.5
5060	PA5050_priA_at	202.0	192.1	145.5	173.1	135.7
5061	PA5051_argS_at	548.5	634.7	425.4	486.9	500.1
5062	PA5052_at	766.8	894.5	669.6	858.8	872.3
5063	PA5053_hslV_at	1019.7	1125.0	426.5	377.4	414.5
5064	PA5054_hslU_at	4197.1	2904.1	556.8	674.7	670.7
5065	PA5055_at	711.9	531.9	188.2	147.7	166.7
5066	PA5056_phaC1_at	181.7	285.0	178.7	188.3	226.0
5067	PA5057_phaD_at	107.5	95.6	52.2	83.9	78.7
5068	PA5058_phaC2_at	44.8	67.3	77.6	63.9	61.4
5069	PA5059_at	6.3	23.5	7.0	23.9	37.9
5070	PA5060_phaF_at	522.6	769.5	662.9	616.0	554.2
5071	PA5061_at	124.3	199.5	132.7	149.6	164.9
5072	PA5062_at	263.1	245.3	286.9	250.5	233.9
5073	PA5063_ubiE_at	763.0	659.5	604.1	633.6	709.0
5074	PA5064_at	844.3	898.0	360.6	471.9	680.7
5075	PA5065_at	505.6	489.5	559.8	434.9	460.6
5076	PA5066_hisI_at	806.2	910.2	1052.0	882.6	814.3
5077	PA5067_hisE_at	876.9	933.9	1315.6	992.4	981.0
5078	PA5068_tatA_at	616.6	820.9	596.1	640.1	716.3
5079	PA5069_tatB_at	789.8	1076.5	690.8	686.2	654.8
5080	PA5070_tatC_at	531.4	398.2	301.5	345.4	333.6
5081	PA5071_at	136.3	115.9	229.0	205.6	160.7
5082	PA5072_at	264.1	266.4	268.5	345.4	324.5
5083	PA5073_at	122.6	131.5	123.4	139.2	137.5
5084	PA5074_at	234.2	302.5	375.4	379.0	368.6
5085	PA5075_at	556.7	589.0	886.0	704.5	608.4
5086	PA5076_at	252.3	447.3	307.9	406.5	395.0
5087	PA5077_mdoH_at	374.3	318.1	342.0	409.8	377.8
5088	PA5078_at	1330.5	1266.7	1135.6	1260.8	1261.3
5089	PA5079_at	362.8	326.7	319.1	335.1	406.2
5090	PA5080_at	461.9	461.3	398.8	473.6	418.9
5091	PA5081_at	29.1	36.7	87.5	64.0	83.8
5092	PA5082_at	52.2	43.3	96.3	60.4	81.7
5093	PA5083_at	26.1	33.5	46.9	20.5	31.3
5094	PA5084_at	25.8	14.7	12.9	7.2	19.5
5095	PA5085_at	122.6	83.3	102.7	79.9	72.2
5096	PA5086_at	22.9	41.0	71.7	56.6	68.6
5097	PA5087_at	13.9	25.8	34.1	22.9	21.8
5098	PA5088_at	19.1	19.7	25.3	11.9	18.6
5099	PA5089_at	18.8	43.2	59.9	36.8	57.8
5100	PA5090_at	49.5	58.5	62.8	94.0	66.6
5101	PA5091_hutG_at	94.7	122.7	168.2	119.7	101.7
5102	PA5092_hutI_at	12.1	27.0	41.8	37.6	41.7

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5103	PA5093_at	8.3	22.2	62.7	38.6	33.6
5104	PA5094_at	47.4	74.8	76.4	72.2	72.3
5105	PA5095_at	34.9	48.1	126.7	98.5	69.0
5106	PA5096_at	49.4	39.4	72.7	60.5	48.4
5107	PA5097_at	4.3	10.7	20.6	26.4	33.8
5108	PA5098_hutH_at	1.6	19.1	25.6	31.3	37.4
5109	PA5099_at	12.7	40.4	19.4	6.2	21.5
5110	PA5100_hutU_at	66.8	301.8	71.7	57.6	66.2
5111	PA5101_at	57.7	93.1	87.5	85.1	95.0
5112	PA5102_at	18.8	31.0	59.4	41.6	22.7
5113	PA5103_at	47.3	173.9	175.0	160.8	170.2
5114	PA5104_at	96.6	82.6	75.0	61.4	80.1
5115	PA5105_hutC_at	151.3	167.9	107.5	132.2	114.3
5116	PA5106_at	53.3	179.4	73.0	66.1	59.5
5117	PA5107_blc_at	82.4	133.9	139.8	130.3	178.5
5118	PA5108_at	180.8	193.4	203.2	159.5	197.1
5119	PA5109_at	318.2	292.8	271.2	271.1	248.0
5120	PA5110_fbp_at	1178.2	1012.9	609.9	695.0	796.2
5121	PA5111_gloA3_at	375.0	250.4	327.6	356.3	361.3
5122	PA5112_estA_at	697.8	594.1	864.4	768.3	800.2
5123	PA5113_at	235.2	201.5	254.8	254.5	226.6
5124	PA5114_at	120.9	93.4	200.4	166.2	129.1
5125	PA5115_at	43.6	32.8	30.7	32.0	38.4
5126	PA5116_at	27.5	36.8	54.1	37.0	59.0
5127	PA5117_typA_at	889.4	1016.3	1001.7	980.5	984.0
5128	PA5118_thiI_at	509.7	785.6	731.6	807.0	709.7
5129	PA5119_glnA_at	6104.0	2764.3	2569.4	2345.0	1971.9
5130	PA5120_at	152.3	127.7	133.1	123.1	121.5
5131	PA5121_at	103.6	112.8	68.0	94.7	110.7
5132	PA5122_at	159.9	187.7	92.1	119.5	143.7
5133	PA5123_at	84.1	135.0	244.3	172.5	146.6
5134	PA5124_ntrB_at	206.7	111.5	107.9	103.2	90.3
5135	PA5125_ntrC_at	227.2	126.3	88.4	108.2	124.2
5136	PA5126_at	76.3	75.0	115.2	86.5	100.4
5137	PA5127_at	59.3	71.4	54.1	47.0	84.6
5138	PA5128_secB_at	1561.7	1714.1	1263.1	1515.2	1604.7
5139	PA5129_grx_at	2832.1	2086.9	2021.0	2115.5	2003.8
5140	PA5130_at	1246.6	1449.0	1383.4	1036.3	1353.3
5141	PA5131_pgm_at	878.5	568.5	943.6	819.4	839.7
5142	PA5132_at	206.5	137.7	237.9	151.4	170.8
5143	PA5133_at	614.3	555.3	915.2	648.9	646.6
5144	PA5134_at	776.5	731.2	577.0	630.4	667.0
5145	PA5135_at	529.2	473.1	335.9	331.8	311.1
5146	PA5136_at	248.9	214.7	265.7	238.7	228.3
5147	PA5137_at	33.7	63.4	76.9	70.9	74.0
5148	PA5138_at	95.3	146.9	130.1	145.8	186.0
5149	PA5139_at	205.5	285.7	217.7	284.2	322.6
5150	PA5140_hisF1_at	533.2	611.7	636.2	595.0	596.6
5151	PA5141_hisA_at	534.0	528.0	445.7	451.9	434.4
5152	PA5142_hisH1_at	724.7	668.5	924.9	995.4	854.8
5153	PA5143_hisB_at	731.1	770.7	446.7	531.2	637.1
5154	PA5144_i_at	27.6	5.2	29.8	31.2	15.6
5155	PA5145_at	70.0	74.6	83.0	92.3	100.6
5156	PA5146_at	241.7	320.7	270.2	343.2	332.6
5157	PA5147_mutY_at	575.3	366.7	408.3	387.5	419.4
5158	PA5148_at	1706.4	1784.4	1293.6	1341.2	1221.2
5159	PA5149_at	176.4	91.6	122.2	109.0	109.5
5160	PA5150_at	38.5	31.4	27.1	21.2	18.9
5161	PA5151_at	78.9	85.7	76.4	104.1	89.1
5162	PA5152_at	1466.5	984.9	1001.0	965.6	1005.6
5163	PA5153_at	1979.4	1786.0	1309.8	1358.3	1427.4
5164	PA5154_at	556.7	413.3	357.8	364.6	465.2
5165	PA5155_at	299.2	301.6	138.6	158.2	208.4
5166	PA5156_at	221.3	138.0	93.5	107.5	158.4
5167	PA5157_at	61.8	49.4	102.6	71.3	84.3
5168	PA5158_at	56.2	52.1	59.5	89.6	65.9
5169	PA5159_at	54.8	52.9	44.8	45.3	38.3
5170	PA5160_at	39.0	46.1	83.2	72.7	53.3
5171	PA5161_rmlB_at	733.7	658.8	531.7	585.7	697.7
5172	PA5162_rmlD_at	818.7	673.9	656.5	648.8	684.7
5173	PA5163_rmlA_at	1474.5	1029.3	1202.5	1165.2	1214.1
5174	PA5164_rmlC_at	577.0	783.3	748.7	627.0	682.4
5175	PA5165_at	190.4	135.6	193.1	149.3	129.7

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5176	PA5166_at	262.6	239.4	192.1	216.8	239.9
5177	PA5167_at	149.2	135.8	164.8	127.9	174.3
5178	PA5168_at	39.6	34.0	95.0	63.4	65.3
5179	PA5169_at	53.7	34.9	64.3	46.7	59.4
5180	PA5170_arcD_at	54.5	46.5	38.8	34.4	64.5
5181	PA5171_arcA_at	326.0	461.3	258.6	229.2	348.6
5182	PA5172_arcB_at	462.0	703.7	390.4	334.4	560.8
5183	PA5173_arcC_at	125.3	189.7	261.6	197.2	215.9
5184	PA5174_at	831.6	796.9	693.3	692.1	736.5
5185	PA5175_cysQ_at	89.1	101.6	133.6	114.5	106.5
5186	PA5176_at	187.2	214.0	164.4	223.6	221.3
5187	PA5177_at	181.5	206.8	171.7	174.1	129.0
5188	PA5178_at	302.5	495.8	366.0	492.9	446.6
5189	PA5179_at	71.9	62.9	80.8	58.8	68.1
5190	PA5180_at	105.8	142.8	56.7	48.3	67.5
5191	PA5181_at	109.2	85.7	63.1	78.5	62.6
5192	PA5182_at	1078.8	814.5	827.7	871.1	874.0
5193	PA5183_at	337.4	264.2	215.1	195.1	272.0
5194	PA5184_at	163.0	186.0	192.0	186.9	195.2
5195	PA5185_at	27.7	52.3	52.9	33.2	44.4
5196	PA5186_at	51.9	65.6	46.6	58.1	75.5
5197	PA5187_at	68.4	72.2	69.7	63.3	70.5
5198	PA5188_at	1.3	35.0	13.5	6.3	28.5
5199	PA5189_at	22.6	30.4	50.6	14.1	30.5
5200	PA5190_at	109.3	142.5	161.6	148.7	146.2
5201	PA5191_at	72.8	79.5	61.5	89.3	77.0
5202	PA5192_pckA_at	1514.3	1561.8	1885.2	1849.4	1817.8
5203	PA5193_yrfI_at	387.1	482.8	563.9	519.5	490.7
5204	PA5194_at	304.3	343.6	174.7	268.4	306.6
5205	PA5195_at	110.9	109.8	83.4	133.1	121.5
5206	PA5196_at	88.5	144.0	186.3	176.6	139.0
5207	PA5197_rimK_at	104.0	128.9	118.7	104.8	106.3
5208	PA5198_at	194.3	102.2	147.3	115.0	132.1
5209	PA5199_envZ_at	196.2	269.9	171.3	249.5	212.7
5210	PA5200_ompR_at	385.9	386.4	537.3	610.1	580.3
5211	PA5201_at	907.9	592.1	608.6	669.6	717.0
5212	PA5202_at	279.0	288.6	189.4	193.5	220.0
5213	PA5203_gshA_at	422.6	380.2	195.3	263.8	229.0
5214	PA5204_argA_at	254.5	188.0	213.5	183.3	263.5
5215	PA5205_at	57.5	80.9	82.2	93.9	56.4
5216	PA5206_argE_at	109.2	147.8	104.0	89.5	107.3
5217	PA5207_at	11.7	11.6	15.4	12.4	12.6
5218	PA5208_at	33.9	62.0	44.5	61.1	43.1
5219	PA5209_at	188.0	187.7	222.2	162.3	156.5
5220	PA5210_at	157.1	239.5	150.7	202.8	168.9
5221	PA5211_at	30.9	65.1	59.3	47.4	72.4
5222	PA5212_i_at	475.6	478.7	292.6	261.8	387.1
5223	PA5213_gcvP1_at	78.1	55.0	122.9	78.3	65.8
5224	PA5214_gcvH1_at	535.4	565.4	367.8	498.0	532.4
5225	PA5215_gcvT1_at	384.0	529.0	301.6	555.1	421.4
5226	PA5216_at	42.0	46.4	74.6	126.6	114.4
5227	PA5217_at	64.2	149.9	397.4	459.3	453.7
5228	PA5218_at	40.2	41.6	22.6	46.1	30.2
5229	PA5219_at	72.3	46.3	126.2	64.1	64.2
5230	PA5220_at	93.6	163.8	225.3	261.7	201.4
5231	PA5221_at	188.5	154.3	104.4	165.1	153.5
5232	PA5222_at	225.8	284.0	464.2	408.1	367.5
5233	PA5223_ubiH_at	299.6	197.9	164.9	275.4	231.7
5234	PA5224_pepP_at	368.3	455.2	332.8	387.8	469.0
5235	PA5225_at	404.2	325.6	427.1	421.7	471.5
5236	PA5226_at	401.1	452.2	405.7	241.6	277.7
5237	PA5227_at	408.6	411.6	306.9	305.5	295.1
5238	PA5228_at	101.4	115.1	249.2	164.7	126.4
5239	PA5229_at	127.1	89.7	94.7	123.1	103.2
5240	PA5230_at	100.7	118.0	85.9	87.9	104.1
5241	PA5231_at	92.6	250.9	230.9	214.1	208.7
5242	PA5232_at	200.7	284.6	365.2	357.3	258.0
5243	PA5233_at	216.0	241.6	112.9	161.0	174.3
5244	PA5234_at	106.9	121.8	119.2	128.2	133.4
5245	PA5235_glpT_at	290.3	215.8	135.2	186.4	227.0
5246	PA5236_at	203.4	237.7	421.6	291.7	260.3
5247	PA5237_at	328.5	234.5	330.4	268.5	277.1
5248	PA5238_at	4.7	29.7	79.3	23.7	41.2

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5249	PA5239_rho_at	1492.9	1042.5	998.4	908.4	939.4
5250	PA5240_trxA_at	785.0	822.1	698.0	811.1	895.4
5251	PA5241_ppx_at	291.7	364.7	266.1	380.8	427.3
5252	PA5242_ppk_at	605.8	589.1	308.5	447.3	506.9
5253	PA5243_hemB_at	304.2	338.0	375.5	330.0	333.6
5254	PA5244_at	123.2	114.5	170.1	101.6	122.9
5255	PA5245_at	472.6	441.6	441.2	467.7	362.8
5256	PA5246_at	63.3	76.3	58.5	66.7	72.8
5257	PA5247_at	123.7	149.5	206.4	182.4	190.3
5258	PA5248_at	13.4	81.9	117.0	104.1	90.9
5259	PA5249_at	65.4	54.3	12.7	16.1	38.3
5260	PA5250_at	263.0	338.1	144.7	248.1	250.8
5261	PA5251_at	270.0	259.6	278.7	256.7	295.9
5262	PA5252_at	424.6	472.0	615.3	598.1	541.1
5263	PA5253_algP_at	3824.6	3224.1	3239.4	2868.3	2572.9
5264	PA5254_at	57.3	86.3	75.1	72.3	75.3
5265	PA5255_algQ_at	471.9	665.8	544.2	573.9	570.2
5266	PA5256_dsbH_at	89.9	97.1	93.6	114.9	134.1
5267	PA5257_at	130.7	135.7	179.3	156.1	129.2
5268	PA5258_at	195.2	162.5	183.0	238.2	226.4
5269	PA5259_hemD_at	108.6	131.2	120.7	143.9	161.8
5270	PA5260_hemC_at	284.3	210.7	333.0	407.9	311.3
5271	PA5261_algR_at	76.7	117.3	142.4	77.1	144.6
5272	PA5262_algZ_at	71.4	90.5	162.0	116.3	111.9
5273	PA5263_argH_at	988.7	846.2	680.4	900.7	868.5
5274	PA5264_at	23.2	33.2	17.8	27.6	35.6
5275	PA5265_at	2.4	10.9	6.1	16.1	17.1
5276	PA5266_at	25.3	20.9	39.7	44.8	37.9
5277	PA5268_corA_at	162.2	165.6	148.4	148.7	154.7
5278	PA5269_at	131.4	140.1	132.7	106.6	108.3
5279	PA5270_at	173.6	174.3	141.5	153.6	131.3
5280	PA5271_at	152.4	211.7	145.3	108.5	120.9
5281	PA5272_cyaA_at	50.8	80.2	92.2	78.6	75.3
5282	PA5273_at	89.9	82.7	107.3	100.6	91.1
5283	PA5274_rnk_at	1156.3	1135.9	1882.4	1452.6	1433.7
5284	PA5275_at	39.3	66.5	88.1	110.0	96.3
5285	PA5276_lppL_i_at	1315.4	1821.2	1087.8	1189.5	1351.7
5286	PA5277_lytA_at	684.5	738.0	626.3	659.3	690.8
5287	PA5278_dapF_at	432.7	432.2	301.4	390.4	444.7
5288	PA5279_at	713.9	648.5	898.0	1021.8	918.6
5289	PA5280_sss_at	193.3	161.7	204.5	148.9	189.1
5290	PA5281_at	154.4	155.9	121.4	123.0	158.2
5291	PA5282_at	42.7	14.7	42.3	33.3	44.4
5292	PA5283_at	62.4	42.1	48.5	52.5	62.1
5293	PA5284_at	34.1	24.1	27.1	39.1	26.5
5294	PA5285_at	3393.9	2604.3	2424.7	2972.4	2556.2
5295	PA5286_at	631.7	627.9	668.6	748.5	819.2
5296	PA5287_amtB_at	33.9	53.1	88.1	79.1	88.4
5297	PA5288_glnK_at	629.9	977.7	694.0	754.3	827.7
5298	PA5289_at	626.1	380.7	581.5	487.2	536.3
5299	PA5290_at	73.1	62.1	79.6	91.4	81.1
5300	PA5291_at	26.7	30.5	40.9	53.7	29.6
5301	PA5292_at	34.9	46.8	62.8	40.7	38.3
5302	PA5293_at	33.9	39.9	82.5	61.3	91.6
5303	PA5294_at	11.2	6.4	12.9	9.5	35.1
5304	PA5295_at	188.6	184.7	209.7	200.9	253.2
5305	PA5296_rep_at	220.8	286.0	172.6	177.3	178.9
5306	PA5297_poxB_at	28.2	39.5	93.0	36.7	49.4
5307	PA5298_at	850.6	967.0	254.7	441.4	533.3
5308	PA5299_at	85.0	68.4	141.4	104.3	75.6
5309	PA5300_cycB_at	660.8	810.7	1010.2	1128.9	1073.9
5310	PA5301_at	1679.6	1721.4	999.3	1163.5	1362.8
5311	PA5302_dadX_at	272.5	308.1	254.9	206.0	242.9
5312	PA5303_at	564.8	494.5	341.7	434.5	401.4
5313	PA5304_dadA_at	686.3	514.0	429.9	447.8	427.7
5314	PA5305_at	113.1	147.2	219.9	257.6	265.1
5315	PA5306_at	397.0	563.9	301.2	301.9	360.2
5316	PA5307_at	65.1	42.2	80.1	76.6	65.9
5317	PA5308_lrp_at	165.8	246.4	270.6	192.4	197.0
5318	PA5309_at	184.6	230.4	224.6	181.0	162.7
5319	PA5310_at	68.9	101.0	91.9	66.5	127.5
5320	PA5311_at	35.4	40.5	30.0	40.1	28.9
5321	PA5312_at	2032.6	1653.1	799.9	843.7	912.9

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

5322	PA5313_at	631.0	677.6	165.2	237.8	289.2
5323	PA5314_at	158.0	253.1	96.0	88.7	95.0
5324	PA5315_rpmG_at	330.8	1056.6	453.5	507.5	582.8
5325	PA5316_rpmB_at	5771.2	3707.9	3973.6	4494.8	4175.4
5326	PA5317_at	126.9	150.3	117.5	81.9	120.8
5327	PA5318_at	35.1	58.1	40.3	50.6	70.7
5328	PA5319_radC_at	83.7	60.4	134.2	88.3	92.4
5329	PA5320_dfp_at	1494.8	1320.6	823.1	1160.8	1051.2
5330	PA5321_dut_at	487.0	575.9	276.9	412.9	414.0
5331	PA5322_algC_at	943.2	843.3	976.2	836.2	769.0
5332	PA5323_argB_at	430.2	732.0	433.5	461.7	518.5
5333	PA5324_at	94.2	107.4	65.6	100.2	108.3
5334	PA5325_at	0.8	7.1	7.4	4.6	26.9
5335	PA5326_at	12.4	9.9	29.9	31.7	19.1
5336	PA5327_at	24.6	40.9	101.9	66.0	63.0
5337	PA5328_at	22.0	16.7	4.7	12.7	21.3
5338	PA5329_at	92.9	175.3	88.6	95.3	110.5
5339	PA5330_at	223.4	428.9	247.4	343.6	342.8
5340	PA5331_pyrE_at	456.4	447.9	478.9	470.0	517.1
5341	PA5332_crc_at	823.9	1015.4	727.3	878.1	828.4
5342	PA5333_at	113.1	159.6	190.2	161.2	202.4
5343	PA5334_rph_at	493.9	411.8	531.4	609.4	524.7
5344	PA5335_at	693.6	533.9	352.2	533.4	555.3
5345	PA5336_gmk_at	670.4	664.9	591.9	596.4	540.8
5346	PA5337_rpoZ_at	1361.3	1493.9	738.6	1112.7	1266.1
5347	PA5338_spoT_at	993.9	847.6	1140.3	898.4	807.6
5348	PA5339_at	1253.2	1965.1	1242.2	1302.2	1452.0
5349	PA5340_at	548.9	745.7	656.7	677.4	678.9
5350	PA5341_at	7.8	26.5	55.2	29.7	36.7
5351	PA5342_at	43.2	41.3	92.4	94.2	89.8
5352	PA5343_at	90.7	103.7	105.6	158.6	115.5
5353	PA5344_at	552.9	444.7	446.3	502.8	493.7
5354	PA5345_recG_at	262.9	239.0	223.4	220.2	205.3
5355	PA5346_at	328.1	369.9	290.0	315.8	328.5
5356	PA5347_at	163.9	179.5	136.2	173.9	217.4
5357	PA5348_at	3438.6	2114.9	1891.2	2001.0	2189.1
5358	PA5349_at	229.6	170.2	235.5	181.6	211.6
5359	PA5350_r_at	718.9	590.1	901.5	773.7	724.2
5360	PA5351_at	450.1	895.6	814.5	650.8	673.0
5361	PA5352_at	56.7	39.9	68.7	52.9	64.3
5362	PA5353_glcF_at	24.0	12.5	44.0	33.4	23.8
5363	PA5354_glcE_at	7.3	16.4	8.7	41.8	11.2
5364	PA5355_glcD_at	31.5	46.2	71.3	57.4	56.3
5365	PA5356_glcC_at	165.6	170.6	205.4	156.8	175.3
5366	PA5357_at	113.4	67.3	123.6	83.5	100.5
5367	PA5358_ubiA_at	157.8	147.3	121.9	114.6	145.9
5368	PA5359_at	27.5	66.4	56.9	58.6	35.2
5369	PA5360_phoB_at	409.1	347.3	192.8	229.0	288.0
5370	PA5361_phoR_at	110.6	103.7	74.0	80.0	59.8
5371	PA5362_at	489.1	365.3	266.2	310.2	345.6
5372	PA5363_at	64.6	98.9	169.6	120.2	130.5
5373	PA5364_at	229.4	350.4	254.1	323.4	295.1
5374	PA5365_phoU_at	479.7	339.7	194.4	189.6	226.4
5375	PA5366_pstB_at	712.2	460.8	285.1	306.0	389.0
5376	PA5367_pstA_at	518.1	376.6	231.6	288.4	326.0
5377	PA5368_pstC_at	514.4	246.2	262.0	271.5	247.7
5378	PA5369_at	1627.2	984.8	442.3	465.0	509.0
5379	PA5370_at	159.8	176.7	173.1	166.2	178.5
5380	PA5371_at	146.5	148.2	175.0	167.6	157.0
5381	PA5372_betA_at	35.9	41.9	69.4	50.4	48.2
5382	PA5373_betB_at	273.8	173.7	257.8	224.8	270.2
5383	PA5374_betI_at	234.6	256.4	172.8	159.2	245.6
5384	PA5375_betT1_at	69.3	50.5	66.4	41.4	58.8
5385	PA5376_at	68.1	57.7	49.5	50.6	57.6
5386	PA5377_at	158.3	158.4	243.6	180.5	183.4
5387	PA5378_at	65.3	87.1	71.4	63.3	84.0
5388	PA5379_sdaB_at	48.7	33.9	87.5	41.3	67.9
5389	PA5380_at	333.7	284.7	293.1	270.3	381.2
5390	PA5381_at	5.5	25.0	29.3	27.9	45.1
5391	PA5382_at	77.2	43.2	92.8	72.6	66.6
5392	PA5383_at	4.0	9.1	25.6	30.4	32.4
5393	PA5384_at	3.5	4.1	46.8	33.7	32.3
5394	PA5385_at	42.2	19.6	45.1	34.7	44.8

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5395	PA5386_at	24.8	5.5	31.4	27.5	51.3
5396	PA5387_at	27.2	20.1	78.8	36.4	33.9
5397	PA5388_at	28.0	17.8	50.4	23.5	45.4
5398	PA5389_at	58.7	56.3	49.0	83.4	88.7
5399	PA5390_at	11.4	13.8	33.6	36.3	31.4
5400	PA5391_at	21.9	24.9	39.9	21.8	24.6
5401	PA5392_at	26.9	13.0	35.1	11.9	34.0
5402	PA5393_at	5.3	27.4	38.4	43.8	36.2
5403	PA5394_cls_at	61.2	85.7	72.3	63.9	82.3
5404	PA5395_at	19.0	22.4	30.9	26.5	26.3
5405	PA5396_at	40.3	67.0	35.8	43.8	38.0
5406	PA5397_at	15.0	35.3	54.2	34.7	47.4
5407	PA5398_at	41.4	32.3	58.7	34.7	31.7
5408	PA5399_at	29.7	9.7	27.0	13.4	22.2
5409	PA5400_at	51.6	5.5	12.1	9.4	21.7
5410	PA5401_at	1.7	10.3	37.9	48.1	34.0
5411	PA5402_at	47.3	32.3	15.8	20.0	53.4
5412	PA5403_at	54.9	91.4	85.4	77.4	77.4
5413	PA5404_at	64.5	44.9	77.5	38.3	50.0
5414	PA5405_i_at	46.3	27.3	95.5	51.1	54.0
5415	PA5406_at	156.5	233.4	246.4	255.1	225.4
5416	PA5407_at	88.8	133.0	115.3	169.4	189.2
5417	PA5408_at	95.9	174.6	179.3	139.9	112.5
5418	PA5409_at	27.1	35.4	29.5	34.3	38.0
5419	PA5410_at	24.4	43.6	61.9	31.7	52.5
5420	PA5411_at	42.8	34.4	51.2	51.4	45.4
5421	PA5412_at	101.7	53.2	209.9	115.0	95.9
5422	PA5413_ltaA_at	494.3	375.2	361.6	313.6	377.5
5423	PA5414_at	955.1	1111.4	857.8	847.7	823.5
5424	PA5415_glyA1_s_at	3277.7	2406.4	2996.6	2609.2	2212.4
5425	PA5416_soxB_at	15.1	24.8	49.0	31.1	36.3
5426	PA5417_soxD_at	16.8	29.8	40.2	15.2	26.0
5427	PA5418_soxA_at	53.7	15.2	30.6	34.5	41.2
5428	PA5419_soxG_at	72.8	68.1	64.3	57.3	60.4
5429	PA5420_purU2_at	18.5	34.7	44.9	39.2	44.3
5430	PA5421_fdhA_at	17.7	42.9	57.3	51.7	50.6
5431	PA5422_at	155.1	192.1	81.0	125.1	161.4
5432	PA5423_at	311.3	307.2	310.4	404.2	341.5
5433	PA5424_at	158.9	261.3	196.7	204.8	218.4
5434	PA5425_purK_at	399.7	501.5	315.8	402.6	479.8
5435	PA5426_purE_at	1263.6	859.9	726.7	1192.2	1064.1
5436	PA5427_adhA_at	6.6	4.3	10.7	10.3	5.3
5437	PA5428_at	66.1	63.9	118.0	129.6	113.2
5438	PA5429_aspA_at	1258.0	1107.3	1650.8	1641.1	1739.0
5439	PA5430_at	141.2	139.5	159.2	160.6	162.4
5440	PA5431_at	37.4	48.2	43.7	18.2	38.1
5441	PA5432_at	119.0	137.3	171.0	101.7	133.8
5442	PA5433_at	35.3	53.4	49.3	46.0	61.7
5443	PA5434_mtr_at	146.4	169.7	138.4	157.9	120.5
5444	PA5435_at	1828.5	1404.8	567.0	967.8	1143.0
5445	PA5436_at	4837.4	3147.7	1337.9	1937.2	1859.8
5446	PA5437_at	230.1	225.9	118.7	121.8	147.9
5447	PA5438_at	567.8	460.4	403.7	348.7	280.0
5448	PA5439_at	42.4	65.4	155.3	135.6	72.6
5449	PA5440_at	34.3	36.9	54.3	58.1	68.9
5450	PA5441_at	346.5	273.3	343.3	336.4	350.8
5451	PA5442_at	59.2	31.1	112.5	69.8	66.7
5452	PA5443_uvrD_at	247.9	253.4	420.9	368.1	318.9
5453	PA5444_at	22.7	27.6	48.1	46.8	47.9
5454	PA5445_at	1276.4	404.4	374.2	410.7	517.6
5455	PA5446_i_at	2872.4	2917.1	2045.9	2151.2	2303.9
5456	PA5447_wbpZ_at	134.5	179.6	220.3	209.8	179.9
5457	PA5448_wbpY_at	99.0	185.3	288.1	217.5	232.4
5458	PA5449_wbpX_at	237.2	222.2	245.8	200.8	250.6
5459	PA5450_wzt_at	221.6	316.7	287.4	365.5	377.6
5460	PA5451_wzm_at	193.1	232.9	187.4	165.8	202.4
5461	PA5452_wbpW_at	186.5	177.3	190.4	204.9	224.7
5462	PA5453_gmd_at	431.8	469.0	415.9	577.8	541.5
5463	PA5454_rmd_at	192.6	304.2	164.8	161.8	198.8
5464	PA5455_at	279.2	298.5	535.3	299.4	267.9
5465	PA5456_at	292.5	291.7	263.0	290.6	294.8
5466	PA5457_at	171.5	173.6	322.0	252.2	235.6
5467	PA5458_at	137.2	171.5	285.8	202.0	234.9

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5468	PA5459_at	241.4	266.8	407.6	262.5	285.1
5469	PA5460_at	27.9	44.4	27.1	67.5	56.5
5470	PA5461_at	1231.2	889.1	625.0	839.0	973.6
5471	PA5462_at	531.8	425.4	542.5	565.6	536.6
5472	PA5463_at	282.3	325.0	352.7	337.1	428.3
5473	PA5464_at	194.8	203.5	223.9	203.3	221.6
5474	PA5465_at	56.1	86.6	76.2	58.5	101.2
5475	PA5466_at	59.0	59.1	110.5	69.0	90.5
5476	PA5467_at	52.9	59.6	42.4	37.1	53.0
5477	PA5468_at	53.3	61.7	57.0	37.3	35.8
5478	PA5469_at	25.2	37.0	54.6	30.7	44.0
5479	PA5470_at	72.6	76.5	67.5	109.4	74.6
5480	PA5471_at	102.6	122.8	157.8	158.6	166.5
5481	PA5472_at	275.5	325.5	282.3	316.3	353.0
5482	PA5473_at	51.5	31.5	56.7	44.0	43.2
5483	PA5474_at	138.1	109.9	159.6	170.6	131.1
5484	PA5475_at	19.4	23.4	42.6	29.9	35.0
5485	PA5476_cita_at	36.2	26.1	35.6	37.5	48.2
5486	PA5477_at	89.7	84.0	113.4	103.5	111.5
5487	PA5478_at	134.6	132.3	206.3	175.4	217.8
5488	PA5479_gltP_at	128.0	265.7	276.1	343.0	373.3
5489	PA5480_at	3.6	1.6	2.9	3.1	6.9
5490	PA5481_at	22.8	13.8	57.3	27.2	34.0
5491	PA5482_at	22.6	9.6	14.7	1.3	22.9
5492	PA5483_algB_at	165.6	229.3	184.1	192.8	217.3
5493	PA5484_at	115.1	105.9	103.8	75.7	97.5
5494	PA5485_at	190.6	129.0	163.7	168.5	169.0
5495	PA5486_at	70.4	59.5	89.9	92.6	87.2
5496	PA5487_at	322.1	375.2	315.1	478.5	387.5
5497	PA5488_at	622.9	578.6	477.9	488.2	494.3
5498	PA5489_dsBA_at	707.2	846.0	944.6	844.7	1062.9
5499	PA5490_cc4_at	2259.2	1860.3	1548.8	2022.6	1948.9
5500	PA5491_at	989.0	1150.0	1444.2	1555.8	1318.8
5501	PA5492_at	657.9	759.8	602.0	608.3	635.9
5502	PA5493_pola_at	335.8	344.8	281.2	284.4	323.5
5503	PA5494_at	374.8	539.7	152.7	256.7	307.7
5504	PA5495_thrB_at	539.5	481.0	384.4	327.6	419.3
5505	PA5496_at	40.6	62.5	61.9	83.9	59.1
5506	PA5497_at	65.1	65.4	58.1	80.8	52.9
5507	PA5498_at	153.0	110.5	175.7	178.9	185.6
5508	PA5499_np20_at	281.6	297.8	253.2	330.9	319.8
5509	PA5500_znuC_at	257.3	200.3	167.4	207.7	235.7
5510	PA5501_znuB_at	112.5	101.1	132.0	150.5	132.4
5511	PA5502_at	150.8	157.3	316.6	305.4	235.6
5512	PA5503_at	453.8	578.1	543.7	543.7	564.7
5513	PA5504_at	514.6	645.1	739.5	695.2	714.2
5514	PA5505_at	1080.7	1247.6	991.1	1054.3	1176.4
5515	PA5506_at	237.6	224.6	168.7	228.1	248.9
5516	PA5507_at	636.0	437.2	462.8	372.3	462.0
5517	PA5508_at	422.1	321.2	283.1	274.3	285.9
5518	PA5509_at	254.4	183.5	174.6	195.5	199.7
5519	PA5510_at	48.5	43.5	87.1	63.0	69.6
5520	PA5511_at	63.0	126.9	135.9	145.3	165.0
5521	PA5512_at	123.3	137.0	157.9	95.1	107.5
5522	PA5513_at	158.9	151.8	230.2	220.7	170.3
5523	PA5514_at	16.0	39.4	46.0	55.6	51.0
5524	PA5515_at	197.7	154.9	131.0	144.8	141.3
5525	PA5516_pdxY_at	222.8	179.2	197.0	220.3	193.2
5526	PA5517_at	30.4	62.9	99.3	82.6	94.4
5527	PA5518_at	69.2	45.3	111.2	86.6	84.0
5528	PA5519_at	340.7	365.1	177.8	232.8	254.4
5529	PA5520_at	55.9	44.2	44.1	40.7	33.9
5530	PA5521_at	280.8	291.6	182.8	129.9	131.4
5531	PA5522_at	205.5	161.8	106.8	93.3	102.2
5532	PA5523_at	262.5	228.7	176.5	163.4	166.7
5533	PA5524_at	114.7	168.7	95.9	82.3	93.0
5534	PA5525_at	97.2	90.0	75.6	69.1	81.4
5535	PA5526_at	60.8	161.7	47.5	81.3	110.6
5536	PA5527_at	180.0	222.8	263.9	305.0	262.7
5537	PA5528_at	713.3	581.4	608.9	633.7	608.7
5538	PA5529_at	61.9	114.2	139.6	84.7	95.8
5539	PA5530_at	24.0	13.1	27.2	7.3	19.2
5540	PA5531_tonB_at	80.2	183.9	681.2	586.9	522.4

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5541	PA5532_at	46.5	20.4	38.1	21.9	39.1
5542	PA5533_at	72.5	156.2	76.2	93.7	128.5
5543	PA5534_at	8.9	6.0	39.3	9.1	20.6
5544	PA5535_at	27.8	30.0	62.1	53.6	45.0
5545	PA5536_at	20.3	8.0	38.4	3.3	25.8
5546	PA5537_at	44.3	23.3	45.3	34.1	42.6
5547	PA5538_amiA_at	2.8	2.4	34.3	7.6	23.3
5548	PA5539_at	30.1	15.3	11.5	22.4	34.0
5549	PA5540_at	34.0	21.5	40.6	36.8	48.7
5550	PA5541_at	2.9	27.0	68.1	51.4	51.3
5551	PA5542_at	25.6	25.1	71.4	55.3	48.9
5552	PA5543_at	42.4	52.9	121.2	84.5	89.9
5553	PA5544_at	51.6	51.9	92.1	121.0	79.0
5554	PA5545_at	102.3	182.2	366.6	278.1	241.5
5555	PA5546_at	111.9	161.9	163.0	235.8	210.5
5556	PA5547_at	75.9	88.8	73.5	62.0	72.2
5557	PA5548_at	19.9	29.7	49.9	47.6	47.6
5558	PA5549_glmS_at	205.7	234.5	255.3	221.7	271.9
5559	PA5550_at	215.9	235.8	223.0	284.1	273.3
5560	PA5551_at	262.9	287.8	223.4	197.9	255.4
5561	PA5552_glmU_at	775.1	785.8	810.0	802.1	762.2
5562	PA5553_atpC_at	797.6	901.3	1151.8	1189.4	1136.6
5563	PA5554_atpD_at	1692.2	2105.4	2739.6	2357.9	2189.2
5564	PA5555_atpG_at	6731.3	4000.6	8359.9	6525.1	4930.7
5565	PA5556_atpA_at	5965.3	3049.2	6071.0	6556.4	4916.9
5566	PA5557_atpH_at	7065.4	3547.5	7714.5	6570.4	4784.0
5567	PA5558_atpF_at	8699.0	4484.4	11872.4	9202.9	6304.9
5568	PA5559_atpE_at	5026.1	3454.8	9517.3	5932.9	4873.6
5569	PA5560_atpB_at	1942.5	2260.9	2559.5	3088.8	2959.0
5570	PA5561_atpI_at	224.4	395.3	586.2	521.9	476.8
5571	PA5562_spo0J_at	589.6	615.2	792.3	849.4	740.3
5572	PA5563_soj_at	1063.7	1058.4	862.8	816.2	1006.5
5573	PA5564_gidB_at	764.8	848.8	1319.3	1011.0	1062.7
5574	PA5565_gidA_at	973.9	844.7	932.5	1036.7	989.1
5575	PA5566_at	4.8	15.4	34.3	19.5	28.0
5576	PA5567_at	154.9	201.4	274.7	314.1	283.2
5577	PA5568_at	1369.3	1149.3	3116.4	2160.9	1938.0
5578	PA5569_rnpA_at	6065.2	3315.4	5056.4	4746.2	4115.0
5579	PA5570_rpmH_at	2756.8	2097.3	1859.8	2069.7	2019.7
5580	ig_53521_56546_at	11.7	14.0	36.4	23.3	22.0
5581	ig_64729_65339_at	3.4	12.0	37.4	49.0	38.3
5582	ig_65479_66303_at	0.8	1.0	6.0	5.1	6.5
5583	ig_68616_69272_at	82.1	92.5	82.9	88.4	101.4
5584	ig_188448_189120_at	187.6	147.5	165.9	225.0	223.9
5585	ig_223454_224101_at	21.8	25.7	54.7	40.1	31.0
5586	ig_297561_299081_at	2.0	10.3	24.7	9.7	18.9
5587	ig_326671_327284_at	101.4	134.0	109.7	52.2	78.4
5588	ig_517462_518083_at	2.8	11.0	7.3	3.1	29.8
5589	ig_545644_546334_at	14.6	11.3	6.2	2.3	10.0
5590	ig_629884_630527_at	2.1	21.9	28.8	24.1	25.2
5591	ig_721556_727608_s_at	6766.1	3339.0	6624.8	4864.9	4016.0
5592	ig_773696_774416_at	60.4	38.6	53.1	52.2	61.9
5593	ig_785174_785969_at	5.3	5.6	27.2	21.5	20.0
5594	ig_788253_789144_at	14.9	24.6	47.9	45.3	21.6
5595	ig_863300_864095_at	99.6	84.0	130.2	142.8	129.3
5596	ig_884172_884799_at	17.5	24.8	27.4	21.9	34.9
5597	ig_901046_901934_at	12.5	8.6	30.2	13.3	18.1
5598	ig_991198_991830_at	342.4	556.7	500.7	531.5	546.5
5599	ig_1046911_1047549_at	41.9	72.1	49.1	35.5	38.6
5600	ig_1063544_1064555_at	9.7	41.7	49.3	34.6	31.8
5601	ig_1087095_1087843_at	37.8	53.4	89.0	61.2	60.9
5602	ig_1117390_1118158_at	95.6	119.9	139.6	142.8	149.7
5603	ig_1204781_1205771_at	36.4	58.6	94.5	56.8	62.9
5604	ig_1246788_1247932_at	19.0	27.0	44.6	25.3	37.8
5605	ig_1254309_1255042_at	3.6	18.6	12.7	13.5	24.9
5606	ig_1324109_1324793_at	1.9	9.1	3.4	4.6	2.6
5607	ig_1348401_1349416_at	50.1	66.7	61.4	49.0	42.9
5608	ig_1427453_1428080_at	27.1	61.5	50.9	35.9	39.6
5609	ig_1489095_1489815_at	8.2	45.2	37.2	17.8	51.6
5610	ig_1553675_1554415_at	20.9	39.1	3.9	7.3	40.8
5611	ig_1637696_1638379_at	13.7	4.6	4.4	14.6	8.0
5612	ig_1802453_1803626_at	23.9	17.4	30.0	28.0	22.7
5613	ig_1947041_1948502_at	92.3	119.8	165.4	163.5	152.9

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

5614	ig_1996806_1997509_at	27.7	29.1	28.6	33.9	19.8
5615	ig_2068728_2069490_at	24.4	37.3	91.5	78.5	63.1
5616	ig_2116265_2117030_at	1.8	20.4	23.1	18.6	15.0
5617	ig_2164548_2165213_at	20.6	7.8	25.0	7.4	11.5
5618	ig_2226144_2226879_at	8.5	6.4	2.4	18.0	15.1
5619	ig_2239267_2240302_at	5.6	2.9	24.9	26.8	10.7
5620	ig_2243603_2244492_at	1.8	14.9	30.6	23.5	25.5
5621	ig_2250595_2251275_at	4.7	15.4	8.9	15.1	22.9
5622	ig_2281578_2282480_at	2.6	11.4	19.7	25.2	26.6
5623	ig_2341640_2342493_at	22.5	37.1	24.8	26.7	31.6
5624	ig_2450765_2451707_at	14.8	2.2	8.4	6.1	8.3
5625	ig_2557964_2558918_s_at	121.3	200.2	181.3	130.9	206.7
5626	ig_2568284_2568929_at	16.6	3.0	4.1	6.5	10.6
5627	ig_2721530_2722174_at	8.5	2.3	1.8	4.5	11.0
5628	ig_2737193_2737881_at	2.9	7.2	29.6	17.4	15.2
5629	ig_2893827_2894451_at	11.4	52.6	33.1	29.8	56.2
5630	ig_2901558_2902217_at	23.8	3.1	36.0	15.1	17.9
5631	ig_2905549_2906165_at	3.4	16.3	47.4	23.1	13.5
5632	ig_2918211_2918966_at	10.2	31.3	65.0	22.8	47.1
5633	ig_2922568_2923366_at	1.7	7.8	20.1	2.2	10.4
5634	ig_2927920_2928538_at	3.1	1.0	3.1	2.3	1.8
5635	ig_3051348_3051956_at	12.3	10.8	2.4	17.4	20.6
5636	ig_3087490_3088659_at	33.7	57.4	81.9	68.4	45.4
5637	ig_3112150_3112877_at	6.9	33.1	58.6	41.5	55.2
5638	ig_3115632_3116653_at	2.9	17.9	22.6	10.7	25.3
5639	ig_3122585_3123598_at	4.5	35.8	10.8	40.3	29.8
5640	ig_3129070_3129728_at	19.0	19.6	17.8	28.1	29.6
5641	ig_3206252_3206914_at	43.9	66.2	91.4	40.5	75.8
5642	ig_3265210_3265847_at	34.1	41.9	29.9	53.5	51.8
5643	ig_3475169_3475955_at	14.9	13.7	18.1	14.8	14.5
5644	ig_3514564_3515415_at	3.9	8.7	27.9	21.4	25.0
5645	ig_3526677_3527428_at	82.8	116.7	62.7	57.4	74.1
5646	ig_3545073_3545880_at	84.7	127.8	78.7	70.5	79.1
5647	ig_3546926_3547688_at	27.8	68.8	21.7	39.0	38.2
5648	ig_3648915_3649704_at	27.3	29.2	42.7	31.8	42.1
5649	ig_3677080_3677719_at	13.5	15.3	57.5	17.2	21.0
5650	ig_3705160_3705889_at	12.3	16.7	33.1	19.1	31.4
5651	ig_3961922_3962824_at	1.0	0.3	2.7	1.7	9.6
5652	ig_4240578_4241341_at	81.3	75.5	97.2	52.6	93.2
5653	ig_4294604_4297249_at	10.6	10.3	8.0	10.0	12.3
5654	ig_4320819_4321433_at	74.9	88.3	115.2	72.8	67.4
5655	ig_4326394_4327696_at	19.8	13.6	24.9	17.2	18.8
5656	ig_4448217_4448892_at	36.0	38.9	40.4	9.0	34.7
5657	ig_4509996_4510970_at	1.9	9.9	17.9	14.9	21.5
5658	ig_4559649_4560294_at	33.5	46.6	40.1	19.5	36.4
5659	ig_4584530_4585148_at	3.0	5.2	6.5	2.7	17.5
5660	ig_4629184_4629943_at	1.2	4.1	7.1	13.6	14.5
5661	ig_4705304_4705955_at	27.8	15.3	59.0	29.9	30.7
5662	ig_4713098_4713795_at	16.9	19.3	11.0	12.3	17.5
5663	ig_727608_721556_s_at	73.2	16.6	23.4	24.8	29.5
5664	ig_4888194_4889111_at	8.4	20.5	25.5	15.5	32.6
5665	ig_4956028_4956733_at	16.2	9.9	44.2	21.6	21.6
5666	ig_5086695_5087407_at	5.9	8.5	23.7	13.6	17.1
5667	ig_5130767_5131427_at	66.4	109.6	76.6	91.5	118.6
5668	ig_5207621_5208463_at	2106.7	1760.8	917.9	1194.2	1455.9
5669	ig_5242558_5243177_at	24.5	60.2	43.2	35.9	43.4
5670	ig_5308424_5309325_at	1148.2	1128.4	790.1	607.9	668.4
5671	ig_5457716_5458499_i_at	24.2	1.3	28.2	2.1	10.8
5672	ig_5513111_5513731_at	7.6	1.8	17.1	0.8	3.6
5673	ig_5541409_5542072_at	109.7	166.5	217.7	187.7	194.6
5674	ig_5563286_5563964_at	286.1	289.4	184.9	185.1	236.2
5675	ig_5774806_5775619_at	18.6	18.6	37.5	17.3	29.1
5676	ig_5820113_5820909_at	2.5	0.7	2.1	1.4	9.5
5677	ig_5991130_5992382_at	599.1	712.5	505.9	520.4	474.7
5678	ig_6090705_6092045_at	18.1	9.2	20.7	11.8	14.1
5679	ig_6125079_6125795_at	5.6	26.3	18.2	13.1	36.8
5680	ig_56546_53521_at	6.8	6.5	15.9	5.7	18.5
5681	ig_65339_64729_at	190.4	188.5	309.5	201.7	194.6
5682	ig_66303_65479_at	20.7	49.1	30.0	14.4	19.9
5683	ig_69272_68616_at	33.6	59.7	53.7	56.4	58.6
5684	ig_189120_188448_at	11.8	14.4	45.8	22.3	55.6
5685	ig_224101_223454_at	11.2	9.6	7.3	20.2	6.4
5686	ig_299081_297561_at	11.3	17.7	28.2	21.8	24.5

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

5687	ig_327284_326671_at	31.0	51.7	53.1	43.3	45.9
5688	ig_518083_517462_at	11.4	15.5	57.2	35.2	41.5
5689	ig_546334_545644_at	71.3	88.1	22.6	34.8	47.5
5690	ig_630527_629884_at	92.3	111.0	68.3	77.9	90.4
5691	ig_774416_773696_at	24.9	14.0	24.8	4.8	28.2
5692	ig_785969_785174_at	5.7	30.0	26.5	24.0	16.9
5693	ig_789144_788253_at	83.4	176.8	67.4	46.3	73.5
5694	ig_864095_863300_at	34.9	31.0	25.3	35.3	50.0
5695	ig_884799_884172_at	16.0	8.0	25.1	8.5	22.6
5696	ig_901934_901046_at	104.8	288.8	246.0	172.4	165.9
5697	ig_991830_991198_at	1.9	8.6	14.0	11.1	18.2
5698	ig_1047549_1046911_at	149.1	204.7	164.7	175.8	197.5
5699	ig_1064555_1063544_at	8.1	12.7	16.9	7.3	8.9
5700	ig_1087843_1087095_at	150.7	234.2	197.9	187.3	229.0
5701	ig_1118158_1117390_at	16.2	27.2	47.9	27.9	43.1
5702	ig_1205771_1204781_at	201.5	263.8	166.4	162.4	180.9
5703	ig_1247932_1246788_at	0.4	5.2	2.3	0.8	5.2
5704	ig_1255042_1254309_at	135.9	275.4	166.1	271.2	267.3
5705	ig_1324793_1324109_at	38.6	20.0	25.5	16.3	21.5
5706	ig_1349416_1348401_at	72.7	111.1	69.6	64.3	95.5
5707	ig_1428080_1427453_at	26.5	9.0	13.1	9.4	13.9
5708	ig_1489815_1489095_at	38.1	54.9	91.6	63.0	54.4
5709	ig_1554415_1553675_at	29.4	54.3	107.9	77.1	77.4
5710	ig_1638379_1637696_at	1.6	16.2	10.1	3.0	15.4
5711	ig_1803626_1802453_at	23.7	15.1	11.9	6.1	13.3
5712	ig_1948502_1947041_at	35.7	42.1	60.6	49.4	42.8
5713	ig_1997509_1996806_at	7.4	38.9	44.9	35.5	55.3
5714	ig_2069490_2068728_at	32.4	30.2	74.0	47.5	48.3
5715	ig_2117030_2116265_at	40.8	23.0	34.3	55.2	37.8
5716	ig_2165213_2164548_at	70.6	39.0	106.1	54.8	45.2
5717	ig_2226879_2226144_at	22.9	5.4	19.2	10.9	17.4
5718	ig_2240302_2239267_at	20.8	26.9	24.1	29.1	17.3
5719	ig_2244492_2243603_at	128.5	97.3	128.5	151.8	119.3
5720	ig_2251275_2250595_at	17.0	6.4	43.0	27.2	23.3
5721	ig_2282480_2281578_at	16.5	20.4	5.5	3.7	17.6
5722	ig_2342493_2341640_at	101.8	107.6	105.6	107.4	81.1
5723	ig_2451707_2450765_at	2.5	5.3	11.2	9.1	13.0
5724	ig_2558918_2557964_s_at	79.0	76.1	86.8	53.1	89.2
5725	ig_2568929_2568284_at	1.9	8.7	24.5	15.4	10.7
5726	ig_2722174_2721530_at	1.6	5.5	4.8	3.5	16.5
5727	ig_2737881_2737193_at	3.8	0.7	30.0	18.5	10.6
5728	ig_2894451_2893827_at	135.3	137.8	156.2	84.4	128.1
5729	ig_2902217_2901558_at	2.3	4.3	28.4	1.5	17.9
5730	ig_2906165_2905549_at	99.0	48.0	126.0	80.5	60.5
5731	ig_2918966_2918211_at	88.7	163.6	97.4	109.4	95.6
5732	ig_2923366_2922568_at	61.5	49.6	64.6	60.9	28.2
5733	ig_2928538_2927920_at	11.7	1.3	23.1	2.5	16.3
5734	ig_3051956_3051348_at	2.8	1.0	16.9	4.1	12.6
5735	ig_3088659_3087490_at	23.6	23.9	31.5	19.5	30.3
5736	ig_3112877_3112150_at	31.5	30.0	27.5	8.4	40.4
5737	ig_3116653_3115632_at	28.4	25.2	54.0	33.6	41.7
5738	ig_3123598_3122585_at	37.3	75.8	78.4	59.0	50.9
5739	ig_3129728_3129070_at	56.4	113.8	100.2	105.1	95.0
5740	ig_3206914_3206252_at	2.2	3.4	22.7	0.7	14.2
5741	ig_3265847_3265210_at	34.8	18.3	32.7	18.9	31.8
5742	ig_3475955_3475169_at	29.5	95.1	78.0	72.3	68.5
5743	ig_3515415_3514564_at	68.8	73.1	55.7	76.5	92.4
5744	ig_3527428_3526677_at	45.6	55.6	64.5	99.2	68.3
5745	ig_3545880_3545073_at	294.5	448.5	435.6	293.5	384.5
5746	ig_3547688_3546926_at	94.3	172.3	124.8	143.0	193.3
5747	ig_3649704_3648915_at	16.5	40.4	76.5	86.2	50.7
5748	ig_3677719_3677080_at	79.1	61.8	73.2	60.1	58.8
5749	ig_3705889_3705160_at	65.8	93.5	92.7	103.5	98.7
5750	ig_3874653_3873835_r_at	4.4	5.5	62.2	7.6	6.3
5751	ig_3962824_3961922_at	1.0	0.2	10.0	4.3	1.1
5752	ig_4241341_4240578_at	20.5	36.0	43.6	46.8	41.6
5753	ig_4297249_4294604_at	8.7	8.4	21.9	17.5	15.7
5754	ig_4321433_4320819_at	20.1	31.8	51.1	51.4	42.3
5755	ig_4327696_4326394_at	15.5	24.9	37.8	15.7	30.2
5756	ig_4448892_4448217_at	53.0	62.1	45.0	42.3	68.1
5757	ig_4510970_4509996_at	5.9	8.3	7.0	15.4	15.3
5758	ig_4560294_4559649_at	0.8	1.9	15.2	0.7	9.2
5759	ig_4585148_4584530_at	14.5	7.7	34.8	29.9	21.3

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

5760	ig_4629943_4629184_at	1.6	0.8	11.1	2.3	2.8
5761	ig_4705955_4705304_at	6.5	11.1	34.4	22.9	24.2
5762	ig_4713795_4713098_at	12.7	17.0	12.9	19.1	14.6
5763	ig_4889111_4888194_at	127.3	82.2	101.6	115.6	111.0
5764	ig_4956733_4956028_at	4301.3	4191.7	2742.4	5846.1	4568.1
5765	ig_5087407_5086695_at	91.9	92.4	98.4	121.1	110.0
5766	ig_5131427_5130767_at	21.9	15.8	50.7	25.7	27.2
5767	ig_5208463_5207621_at	12.6	60.6	61.6	43.7	47.2
5768	ig_5243177_5242558_at	33.2	44.9	35.7	51.4	51.5
5769	ig_5309325_5308424_at	24.3	34.1	37.1	37.0	42.4
5770	ig_5458499_5457716_at	3.9	2.7	28.1	5.5	13.2
5771	ig_5513731_5513111_at	22.2	7.6	23.5	17.9	18.7
5772	ig_5542072_5541409_at	33.5	54.5	39.5	44.0	59.0
5773	ig_5563964_5563286_at	42.6	114.2	65.1	58.7	62.4
5774	ig_5775619_5774806_at	8.8	24.8	44.1	39.0	48.1
5775	ig_5820909_5820113_at	20.8	14.3	22.5	21.8	32.2
5776	ig_5992382_5991130_at	49.8	92.1	61.1	60.4	58.3
5777	ig_6092045_6090705_at	16.3	29.3	42.0	44.3	47.5
5778	ig_6125795_6125079_at	335.5	228.3	233.4	237.5	253.3
5779	Pae_AF291700cnds_at	9.9	2.3	2.8	19.9	2.2
5780	Pae_AF191564cnds1_at	1.8	2.0	5.0	2.7	1.3
5781	Pae_AF191564cnds4_at	2.0	1.9	10.3	4.2	2.4
5782	Pae_AF140629cnds1_at	9.5	0.4	11.4	5.2	2.6
5783	Pae_AF140629cnds2_at	21.2	7.1	0.9	0.8	6.6
5784	Pae_AF133699cnds2_at	13.6	10.9	31.8	9.1	17.5
5785	Pae_AF133699cnds3_at	1.8	0.0	0.1	0.3	0.0
5786	Pae_AF133699cnds4_at	1.9	0.9	5.4	1.5	1.1
5787	Pae_AF133697cnds_at	2.5	0.7	0.7	0.4	0.3
5788	Pae_AF147795cnds2_at	2.4	0.3	1.2	7.0	0.1
5789	Pae_AF147795cnds3_at	1.1	0.4	0.9	6.6	0.4
5790	Pae_AF147795cnds4_at	3.0	0.3	4.2	0.8	0.3
5791	Pae_AF147795cnds5_at	2.2	0.2	11.4	1.9	0.7
5792	Pae_AF147795cnds6_at	1.9	0.2	0.4	2.7	0.6
5793	Pae_AF147795cnds7_at	0.4	0.5	1.4	5.9	3.3
5794	Pae_AF147795cnds8_at	1.2	3.3	1.5	7.0	7.7
5795	Pae_AF147795cnds9_at	5.7	0.4	8.3	7.1	1.1
5796	Pae_AF147795cnds10_at	1.0	0.1	12.2	6.0	0.7
5797	Pae_AF147795cnds11_at	0.4	0.2	1.2	0.4	0.4
5798	Pae_AF043558cnds_at	17.2	0.4	13.0	1.7	0.6
5799	Pae_AF080442cnds1_at	0.9	9.9	2.3	16.0	2.9
5800	Pae_AF080442cnds2_at	1.6	6.8	16.6	1.6	5.4
5801	Pae_M21651cnds_at	6.7	0.9	2.6	11.0	5.9
5802	Pae_M21652cnds_at	2.6	0.7	13.8	6.8	4.8
5803	Pae_L07945cnds_at	16.9	3.7	12.7	13.3	4.2
5804	Pae_L37109cnds1_at	1.8	0.6	2.1	8.4	0.9
5805	Pae_L37109cnds2_at	1.1	0.2	20.4	0.9	1.7
5806	Pae_AF027291cnds_at	18.8	9.9	29.1	35.2	7.0
5807	Pae_M57501cnds_g_at	13.4	8.4	22.0	13.4	7.9
5808	Pae_U97065cnds3_at	5.4	9.2	20.2	3.1	7.1
5809	Pae_U85514cnds_at	30.5	3.8	36.2	14.7	8.4
5810	Pae_L06157cnds2_at	4.0	1.4	2.3	1.4	1.5
5811	Pae_J05162cnds_at	7.4	0.1	0.5	6.3	0.1
5812	Pae_M14849cnds_at	5.5	0.3	11.3	0.9	2.3
5813	Pae_M14850cnds_at	14.5	0.4	4.5	0.3	2.9
5814	Pae_M98270cnds1_at	10.6	0.8	0.9	6.9	1.1
5815	Pae_M98270cnds2_at	2.3	6.3	34.8	13.0	5.0
5816	Pae_M98270cnds3_at	17.5	0.3	7.0	1.2	0.6
5817	Pae_M29695cnds1_at	20.0	5.9	7.6	1.5	6.5
5818	Pae_M29695cnds2_at	2.4	1.8	15.9	6.2	1.8
5819	Pae_L06161cnds_at	1.7	1.0	1.8	2.5	2.7
5820	Pae_L06160cnds_at	11.7	3.8	16.8	14.6	1.4
5821	Pae_AF035937cnds3_at	2.1	1.0	18.2	1.8	1.2
5822	Pae_AF035937cnds4_at	1.4	4.5	5.9	2.8	0.8
5823	Pae_AF035937cnds5_at	9.0	1.8	2.7	3.4	0.5
5824	Pae_AF035937cnds6_at	0.8	0.5	3.6	2.0	7.6
5825	Pae_AF035937cnds7_at	0.8	2.1	2.0	4.6	0.5
5826	Pae_AF035937cnds8_at	3.7	0.6	4.3	4.8	2.2
5827	Pae_AF035937cnds9_at	8.3	0.5	1.4	0.8	3.0
5828	Pae_AF035937cnds10_at	6.4	2.5	2.9	6.1	1.1
5829	Pae_AF035937cnds11_at	20.2	9.5	16.1	14.7	7.6
5830	Pae_AF035937cnds12_at	16.7	2.1	12.9	10.9	2.6
5831	Pae_AF035937cnds13_at	1.3	0.8	2.1	4.0	3.8
5832	Pae_L81176cnds3_at	37.7	23.9	59.9	47.3	23.4

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

5833	Pae_L81176cnds4_at	25.9	13.9	37.8	18.4	13.4
5834	Pae_L81176cnds5_at	2.4	3.5	22.1	14.6	3.2
5835	Pae_L81176cnds6_at	5.9	2.1	14.1	7.4	1.1
5836	Pae_AF241171cnds1_r_at	3.1	1.5	4.1	2.6	1.4
5837	Pae_AF241171cnds4_at	45.9	8.2	41.8	34.5	26.2
5838	Pae_AF241171cnds5_at	8.8	10.9	14.3	24.1	6.0
5839	Pae_AF241171cnds6_at	3.6	10.3	12.8	13.5	15.0
5840	Pae_AF241171cnds7_at	26.8	10.1	16.4	12.1	8.8
5841	Pae_AF241171cnds8_at	19.1	14.0	9.8	4.9	2.9
5842	Pae_AF241171cnds9_at	1.7	2.1	36.0	11.1	10.5
5843	Pae_AF241171cnds10_at	5.4	1.4	3.4	5.6	2.4
5844	Pae_AF241171cnds11_at	4.0	1.9	15.3	12.9	6.0
5845	Pae_AF241171cnds12_at	11.6	1.3	5.6	9.4	1.2
5846	Pae_AF241171cnds13_at	10.6	1.3	2.6	5.3	0.7
5847	Pae_AF241171cnds14_at	1.7	1.1	4.0	3.7	2.0
5848	Pae_AF241171cnds15_at	29.1	7.3	60.8	33.2	27.7
5849	Pae_AF241171cnds16_at	17.7	11.3	25.3	34.0	8.7
5850	Pae_AF241171cnds17_at	2.2	0.8	1.1	3.4	2.6
5851	Pae_AF241171cnds18_at	16.3	9.0	9.3	29.9	11.7
5852	Pae_AF241171cnds19_at	4.6	8.1	17.8	27.2	20.2
5853	Pae_AF241171cnds20_at	11.0	14.9	18.4	15.3	6.7
5854	Pae_AF241171cnds21_at	1.1	1.5	10.2	2.0	8.9
5855	Pae_AF241171cnds22_at	0.8	1.5	24.1	13.3	2.3
5856	Pae_AF241171cnds23_at	0.7	0.6	3.9	1.0	0.7
5857	Pae_AF241171cnds24_at	1.1	0.7	3.5	1.7	0.6
5858	Pae_AF241171cnds25_at	3.8	13.8	33.4	5.0	10.0
5859	Pae_AF241171cnds26_at	18.8	15.3	36.1	23.4	10.2
5860	Pae_AF241171cnds27_at	20.1	14.2	7.0	5.4	2.4
5861	Pae_AF241171cnds28_at	0.9	0.8	18.5	3.9	8.3
5862	Pae_AF241171cnds29_at	14.2	2.9	10.1	9.9	1.6
5863	Pae_AF241171cnds30_at	3.4	1.1	4.0	19.5	3.8
5864	Pae_AF241171cnds31_at	2.0	0.3	1.8	1.8	0.7
5865	Pae_AF241171cnds34_at	0.7	6.2	3.5	19.2	6.1
5866	Pae_AF241171cnds35_at	12.0	8.3	19.1	7.3	11.8
5867	Pae_AF241171cnds36_at	0.8	0.2	0.4	2.0	0.4
5868	Pae_AF241171cnds39_at	27.8	19.4	28.9	5.6	21.1
5869	Pae_AF241171cnds40_at	12.3	7.9	9.0	26.8	8.2
5870	Pae_AF241171cnds41_at	8.1	1.7	8.0	6.4	4.6
5871	Pae_AF241171cnds42_at	2.0	2.7	3.1	2.6	1.4
5872	Pae_AF241171cnds43_s_at	13.8	2.1	11.2	0.2	0.3
5873	Pae_AF241171cnds44_r_at	6.2	0.8	9.7	4.7	1.4
5874	Pae_AF241171cnds45_at	14.1	3.9	9.4	12.9	1.1
5875	Pae_AF241171cnds47_at	0.6	0.5	1.9	1.5	0.4
5876	Pae_AF241171cnds48_at	1.3	3.2	3.3	2.6	1.5
5877	Pae_AF241171cnds49_i_at	0.3	0.2	2.2	1.3	2.1
5878	Pae_AF241171cnds50_i_at	20.1	0.3	13.7	9.2	2.2
5879	Pae_AF241171cnds51_at	1.3	0.2	1.1	5.2	0.6
5880	Pae_tRNA_Ala_f_at	547.8	1531.6	585.3	1002.1	996.5
5881	Pae_tRNA_Arg_s_at	591.6	807.7	368.8	495.1	507.3
5882	Pae_tRNA_Asn_s_at	278.0	498.2	370.6	475.6	581.9
5883	Pae_tRNA_Gln_s_at	1086.1	1524.3	2596.4	1728.8	1984.8
5884	Pae_tRNA_His_f_at	224.8	446.4	80.8	179.3	224.2
5885	Pae_tRNA_Ile_f_at	707.9	1785.8	438.1	769.7	921.2
5886	Pae_tRNA_Leu_s_at	357.0	887.2	538.1	624.0	706.6
5887	Pae_tRNA_Lys_f_at	148.6	422.9	63.4	156.2	228.4
5888	Pae_tRNA_Met_s_at	24.6	25.1	24.8	16.1	19.7
5889	Pae_tRNA_Phe_f_at	268.6	492.6	383.0	399.9	422.4
5890	Pae_tRNA_Pro_f_at	10.2	47.2	21.6	32.7	38.8
5891	Pae_tRNA_Ser_f_at	128.5	166.5	194.7	168.9	111.4
5892	Pae_tRNA_Thr_s_at	25.1	44.1	40.7	35.4	24.9
5893	Pae_5SrRNA_s_at	1214.7	2739.1	1728.9	2219.3	1989.6
5894	Pae_23SrRNA_s_at	40698.3	5057.6	22000.6	13513.2	7543.5
5895	Pae_16SrRNA_s_at	35965.7	4858.3	20286.1	11687.1	6813.5
5896	Pae_tRNA_Cys_i_at	95.8	189.1	155.5	215.5	226.4
5897	Pae_tRNA_Gly_s_at	1539.3	1699.7	2269.2	2133.2	2296.5
5898	Pae_tRNA_Trp_f_at	2067.2	2064.1	2702.9	3310.4	2981.1
5899	Pae_tRNA_Tyr_s_at	131.4	295.3	729.7	715.1	564.6
5900	Pae_tRNA_Val_f_at	2070.1	2305.9	2459.1	2658.4	2241.1

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

Nr.	Probe Set Name	Array Number for H ₂ O ₂ -treated samples				
		6	7	8	9	10
1	AFFX-YEL002C_WPB1_at	49.2	81.9	25.2	16.0	17.2
2	AFFX-YEL018W_at	150.7	434.5	62.6	104.0	94.4
3	AFFX-YEL024W_RIP1_at	529.6	1212.2	248.0	291.0	268.9
4	AFFX-YFL039C_ACT1_at	3.5	1.7	1.6	0.8	7.1
5	AFFX-YER148W_SPT15_at	218.5	489.4	143.6	202.1	220.9
6	AFFX-YER022W_SRB4_at	8.8	0.1	0.3	0.4	0.1
7	AFFX-Athal_GAPDH_at	32.5	131.5	26.3	25.6	21.1
8	AFFX-Athal_ubq_at	22.8	1.0	1.3	3.9	5.8
9	AFFX-Athal_actin_at	1.9	1.7	0.4	0.3	1.1
10	AFFX-Bsubtilis_dapB_at	127.4	338.1	84.4	112.8	92.1
11	AFFX-Bsubtilis_lys_at	204.4	682.4	236.9	286.6	238.8
12	AFFX-Bsubtilis_pheB_at	1405.6	2981.1	675.1	1107.8	1024.9
13	AFFX-Bsubtilis_thrC_at	497.6	990.0	341.9	317.7	320.7
14	AFFX-Bsubtilis_trpD_at	133.7	305.8	122.6	166.7	125.7
15	Pae_flgK_at	2.9	6.1	4.9	3.5	3.5
16	Pae_flgL_at	4.0	2.9	3.2	1.9	1.7
17	Pae_orfA_vioA_at	18.1	7.8	7.1	17.8	16.7
18	Pae_orfB_at	58.2	18.6	39.8	13.7	11.9
19	Pae_orfC_at	12.8	6.9	12.9	13.3	8.1
20	Pae_orfD_at	23.0	7.7	7.0	3.8	5.3
21	Pae_orfE_at	13.7	14.4	8.8	2.1	7.4
22	Pae_orfF_at	70.3	31.7	13.3	22.4	10.1
23	Pae_orfG_at	3.5	9.4	12.6	14.2	13.3
24	Pae_orfH_at	42.5	2.5	6.6	2.6	28.2
25	Pae_orfI_at	10.2	15.9	4.3	17.7	17.4
26	Pae_orfJ_at	30.6	8.7	10.0	3.7	5.5
27	Pae_orfK_at	11.9	1.3	4.9	0.4	0.8
28	Pae_orfL_at	5.7	3.6	4.9	3.3	15.0
29	Pae_orfM_at	30.1	3.7	1.8	12.1	0.8
30	Pae_orfN_at	11.4	3.7	5.8	14.0	2.2
31	PA0001_dnaA_at	640.6	491.5	857.3	927.4	907.2
32	PA0002_dnaN_at	1308.9	1039.6	1496.9	1532.2	1633.6
33	PA0003_recF_at	625.0	652.2	528.6	446.7	519.1
34	PA0004_gyrB_at	583.2	707.8	510.3	586.7	622.3
35	PA0005_at	238.8	148.5	258.7	226.9	258.4
36	PA0006_at	185.3	120.2	315.7	290.9	257.6
37	PA0007_at	127.9	109.3	165.5	203.0	160.0
38	PA0008_glyS_at	131.9	344.7	171.6	149.2	177.2
39	PA0009_glyQ_at	112.1	136.0	293.7	215.1	222.6
40	PA0010_tag_at	17.7	22.9	38.8	45.5	53.3
41	PA0011_at	155.8	99.3	220.6	197.0	172.5
42	PA0012_at	146.2	157.4	133.5	132.5	142.4
43	PA0013_at	41.5	2.4	2.9	20.1	1.8
44	PA0014_at	9.3	26.9	14.2	33.7	20.8
45	PA0015_at	119.4	208.5	176.3	184.2	191.4
46	PA0016_trkA_at	162.1	93.1	182.4	135.2	139.7
47	PA0017_at	222.0	146.6	178.9	187.1	160.5
48	PA0018_fmt_at	358.3	302.5	304.0	355.0	348.0
49	PA0019_def_at	1986.7	2921.4	1301.6	1192.8	1314.7
50	PA0020_at	441.9	278.0	550.2	420.2	466.4
51	PA0021_at	9.6	34.7	27.8	32.9	26.1
52	PA0022_at	11.8	44.1	53.7	63.2	64.7
53	PA0023_qor_at	107.2	79.7	227.1	262.3	233.2
54	PA0024_hemF_at	209.0	152.3	178.2	205.5	216.5
55	PA0025_aroE_at	91.1	55.8	90.2	75.0	72.2
56	PA0026_at	466.3	236.9	387.0	368.9	359.0
57	PA0027_at	71.6	64.6	108.1	110.1	87.2
58	PA0028_at	84.6	97.5	80.1	125.7	75.4
59	PA0029_at	82.6	58.4	92.9	70.9	65.3
60	PA0030_at	8.8	7.5	37.3	54.3	36.8
61	PA0031_betC_at	57.0	32.6	57.0	36.0	15.9
62	PA0032_at	106.3	75.9	120.2	148.5	107.9
63	PA0033_at	224.6	56.4	78.7	96.4	73.7
64	PA0034_at	128.2	128.5	114.2	132.0	161.6
65	PA0035_trpA_at	261.7	291.5	363.9	334.6	343.6
66	PA0036_trpB_at	628.7	477.1	588.5	654.6	693.7
67	PA0037_trpI_at	122.5	54.4	41.7	66.2	57.9
68	PA0038_at	460.5	411.4	345.2	526.6	525.0
69	PA0039_at	950.3	1129.0	667.0	690.2	680.8

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

70	PA0040_s_at	149.1	123.6	292.7	306.1	187.5
71	PA0041_at	57.0	165.5	59.8	64.9	79.3
72	PA0042_at	219.4	181.5	270.5	264.9	247.6
73	PA0043_at	92.1	58.0	129.5	130.2	94.6
74	PA0044_exoT_at	328.8	194.6	109.8	126.6	149.3
75	PA0045_at	270.3	222.2	227.9	227.5	178.7
76	PA0046_at	184.9	201.4	111.7	131.5	110.6
77	PA0047_at	75.1	142.9	55.8	73.8	58.5
78	PA0048_at	185.4	301.9	201.3	197.1	219.6
79	PA0049_at	297.6	369.1	993.2	865.0	919.5
80	PA0050_r_at	111.6	195.3	129.3	146.7	106.7
81	PA0051_at	34.7	39.0	37.1	52.3	34.4
82	PA0052_at	15.0	97.9	168.9	201.1	186.8
83	PA0053_at	194.6	158.0	200.7	254.0	250.2
84	PA0054_at	158.5	64.8	248.1	174.8	153.8
85	PA0055_at	828.3	523.5	1232.9	1111.3	1301.9
86	PA0056_at	23.2	25.4	37.8	30.9	29.1
87	PA0057_at	32.8	51.4	53.2	53.3	42.2
88	PA0058_at	53.4	52.1	72.2	47.3	28.0
89	PA0059_osmC_at	176.5	67.1	92.9	119.0	94.0
90	PA0060_at	306.6	336.7	280.5	382.3	361.8
91	PA0061_at	98.9	79.3	70.5	67.4	83.9
92	PA0062_at	10.1	28.5	26.6	35.6	37.1
93	PA0063_at	264.5	201.1	263.3	272.5	271.6
94	PA0064_at	121.2	133.0	191.9	177.0	184.7
95	PA0065_at	373.5	252.7	348.9	325.4	374.6
96	PA0066_at	276.2	146.3	376.3	386.8	525.6
97	PA0067_prLC_at	3251.3	2179.4	3284.2	3179.9	3728.0
98	PA0068_at	1838.5	1725.6	1954.8	1777.9	1572.8
99	PA0069_at	332.5	292.7	183.3	235.7	214.8
100	PA0070_at	2486.4	2656.3	2010.3	2168.9	1985.0
101	PA0071_at	136.6	194.2	147.5	149.7	121.7
102	PA0072_at	102.7	126.5	61.0	69.7	79.0
103	PA0073_at	393.1	464.9	340.9	361.4	305.3
104	PA0074_ppkA_at	284.0	622.3	286.1	278.0	275.9
105	PA0075_at	459.5	843.3	463.2	501.0	530.4
106	PA0076_at	178.5	329.2	198.2	225.7	197.6
107	PA0077_at	215.6	357.4	188.5	193.7	151.4
108	PA0078_at	286.4	373.5	170.7	174.8	151.5
109	PA0079_at	445.8	445.0	257.7	320.7	250.7
110	PA0080_at	269.1	150.8	202.3	196.3	194.0
111	PA0081_at	662.3	504.3	497.8	550.3	574.8
112	PA0082_at	518.8	256.3	565.2	535.8	570.5
113	PA0083_at	1786.1	1415.6	1272.5	1381.6	1414.7
114	PA0084_at	665.1	767.0	677.0	710.6	755.1
115	PA0085_at	794.4	1414.5	533.1	672.2	604.6
116	PA0086_at	180.5	298.8	173.2	197.9	126.1
117	PA0087_at	121.5	142.5	66.9	112.2	70.5
118	PA0088_at	36.7	182.6	79.0	76.0	81.5
119	PA0089_at	164.1	191.8	52.0	83.9	84.6
120	PA0090_at	242.3	965.0	253.3	262.2	259.5
121	PA0091_at	113.0	480.7	156.0	148.4	150.6
122	PA0092_at	225.5	124.9	157.2	192.4	164.5
123	PA0093_at	496.0	200.8	479.0	373.2	356.7
124	PA0094_at	1501.7	932.2	871.9	768.9	970.8
125	PA0095_at	455.4	419.5	343.4	352.7	300.8
126	PA0096_at	179.3	90.8	87.6	113.8	68.9
127	PA0097_at	116.0	98.8	87.9	121.7	81.8
128	PA0098_at	89.2	63.7	63.0	69.4	46.2
129	PA0099_at	88.8	93.2	42.6	60.2	48.9
130	PA0100_at	144.2	399.3	224.1	193.0	237.7
131	PA0101_at	274.5	196.2	146.4	178.9	141.5
132	PA0102_at	565.3	642.1	476.5	515.4	579.2
133	PA0103_at	125.3	83.0	85.6	107.6	89.0
134	PA0104_at	24.5	72.5	43.0	74.1	57.4
135	PA0105_coxB_at	42.1	87.4	236.7	315.6	260.7
136	PA0106_coxA_at	56.4	61.2	190.2	244.2	201.7
137	PA0107_at	56.1	37.4	138.0	189.5	118.9
138	PA0108_coIII_at	35.5	56.7	125.2	166.2	117.9
139	PA0109_at	57.7	54.2	107.4	142.3	133.1
140	PA0110_at	70.1	39.6	62.8	100.8	61.8
141	PA0111_at	8.7	30.4	9.7	38.5	7.1
142	PA0112_at	69.5	51.9	69.9	57.1	43.1

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

143	PA0113_at	66.5	99.8	64.2	71.8	51.9
144	PA0114_at	350.0	183.3	272.8	313.5	235.4
145	PA0115_at	129.8	66.7	163.7	136.9	128.0
146	PA0116_at	127.3	101.9	147.1	178.3	208.1
147	PA0117_at	163.1	98.8	202.7	189.0	175.9
148	PA0118_at	107.0	38.5	62.3	70.2	60.0
149	PA0119_at	482.6	467.6	409.7	351.5	392.3
150	PA0120_at	641.7	531.1	305.3	335.8	380.4
151	PA0121_at	479.9	192.0	323.3	363.2	327.9
152	PA0122_at	606.3	1020.8	683.0	779.6	676.3
153	PA0123_at	185.3	97.1	167.0	163.8	128.0
154	PA0124_at	438.3	313.2	351.3	356.6	427.9
155	PA0125_at	696.4	423.0	360.6	400.7	518.5
156	PA0126_at	214.8	556.5	179.0	162.2	137.2
157	PA0127_at	178.1	126.2	120.7	91.1	123.5
158	PA0128_at	62.7	93.8	116.2	78.3	72.6
159	PA0129_gabP_at	112.1	85.9	104.1	109.9	82.6
160	PA0130_at	250.1	355.6	329.2	326.8	311.8
161	PA0131_at	224.5	642.1	280.4	329.6	305.0
162	PA0132_at	279.0	1582.6	687.6	841.2	778.1
163	PA0133_at	242.1	152.1	208.8	202.7	246.0
164	PA0134_at	271.4	148.0	136.8	181.0	170.5
165	PA0135_at	6.5	31.4	27.4	67.8	38.4
166	PA0136_at	16.6	18.1	16.4	48.3	51.6
167	PA0137_at	32.3	25.3	36.4	47.3	34.7
168	PA0138_at	8.8	37.0	59.6	30.6	36.8
169	PA0139_ahpC_at	40411.2	13926.7	10474.7	10458.0	12423.3
170	PA0140_ahpF_at	6574.6	3414.4	5049.2	4613.0	4663.0
171	PA0141_at	142.9	343.7	202.4	149.2	125.0
172	PA0142_at	47.5	41.0	60.0	72.4	74.2
173	PA0143_at	293.6	180.8	386.6	319.0	341.4
174	PA0144_at	11.6	62.1	199.8	192.1	178.0
175	PA0145_i_at	8.6	46.1	102.7	80.9	80.0
176	PA0146_at	46.5	61.5	46.8	57.2	59.2
177	PA0147_at	250.6	171.0	231.4	265.5	260.9
178	PA0148_at	38.2	47.5	164.0	170.1	163.0
179	PA0149_at	506.6	297.4	291.4	330.1	306.7
180	PA0150_at	263.7	150.9	180.5	198.4	172.7
181	PA0151_at	110.3	109.8	85.2	90.5	74.1
182	PA0152_pcaQ_at	63.1	68.9	83.2	92.1	95.2
183	PA0153_pcaH_at	147.6	90.5	109.4	110.0	122.8
184	PA0154_pcaG_at	174.3	129.2	87.7	104.3	104.9
185	PA0155_pcaR_at	166.0	140.6	194.7	194.8	232.3
186	PA0156_at	94.9	116.6	138.1	161.0	183.6
187	PA0157_at	154.8	122.8	79.5	71.8	95.8
188	PA0158_at	3.9	122.7	55.4	53.9	72.0
189	PA0159_at	117.6	235.1	274.5	220.0	277.0
190	PA0160_at	287.3	586.6	473.3	433.7	511.1
191	PA0161_at	77.0	117.8	76.6	83.0	92.0
192	PA0162_at	169.3	181.9	137.1	146.7	104.6
193	PA0163_at	93.5	40.8	79.6	91.4	42.1
194	PA0164_at	41.8	22.5	17.0	48.0	38.1
195	PA0165_at	106.2	289.4	107.6	136.2	118.4
196	PA0166_at	12.8	24.5	6.1	19.6	11.0
197	PA0167_at	239.2	145.5	463.0	431.1	468.7
198	PA0168_at	38.8	85.9	196.0	198.7	159.5
199	PA0169_at	30.8	239.5	52.4	49.5	36.2
200	PA0170_at	68.4	153.0	99.3	83.3	72.2
201	PA0171_at	27.7	212.4	101.9	86.6	98.5
202	PA0172_at	117.7	108.8	99.0	92.3	83.5
203	PA0173_at	12.8	4.8	5.5	11.9	32.2
204	PA0174_at	9.4	4.8	33.5	39.9	31.7
205	PA0175_at	58.3	54.2	38.5	68.8	46.4
206	PA0176_at	160.5	160.2	283.3	254.3	207.6
207	PA0177_at	41.6	46.0	87.5	92.2	73.0
208	PA0178_at	206.7	113.5	390.5	339.3	278.2
209	PA0179_at	970.2	771.6	1272.3	1596.1	1625.1
210	PA0180_at	227.3	179.1	382.3	348.2	350.1
211	PA0181_at	300.1	177.8	255.0	260.8	296.1
212	PA0182_at	91.3	56.3	64.8	83.0	105.9
213	PA0183_atsA_at	145.1	48.0	62.7	76.6	54.5
214	PA0184_at	119.2	8.5	11.5	4.9	15.8
215	PA0185_at	284.5	55.1	56.3	64.3	64.0

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

216	PA0186_at	130.4	17.8	17.9	18.6	23.4
217	PA0187_at	54.6	32.8	45.7	39.3	20.8
218	PA0188_at	32.2	20.0	26.4	50.2	35.1
219	PA0189_at	97.4	39.8	35.7	40.0	29.3
220	PA0190_at	4.3	15.1	21.1	23.6	10.3
221	PA0191_at	411.4	16.3	24.7	37.5	29.2
222	PA0192_at	265.2	98.6	54.1	38.7	41.1
223	PA0193_at	177.0	82.0	38.9	49.3	55.9
224	PA0194_at	191.4	82.1	30.5	61.1	56.9
225	PA0195_pntA_at	237.7	130.6	409.2	368.4	373.4
226	PA0196_pntB_at	93.4	37.3	157.5	131.0	87.9
227	PA0197_at	169.8	50.7	41.6	62.7	39.0
228	PA0198_exbB1_at	220.3	26.3	33.4	31.9	32.4
229	PA0199_exbD1_at	284.4	57.4	38.3	41.0	35.3
230	PA0200_i_at	153.0	142.8	78.9	123.0	102.1
231	PA0201_at	4762.9	208.0	7.0	23.5	211.6
232	PA0202_at	73.6	51.2	8.6	30.1	36.3
233	PA0203_at	11.0	12.4	20.0	28.7	20.5
234	PA0204_at	53.3	11.9	4.3	23.7	7.3
235	PA0205_at	8.0	88.7	59.5	81.3	47.4
236	PA0206_at	12.5	28.3	70.7	74.1	58.8
237	PA0207_at	188.3	107.6	237.3	203.9	155.9
238	PA0208_mdcA_at	8.5	55.8	83.5	66.4	73.0
239	PA0209_at	55.0	26.1	48.9	68.5	47.4
240	PA0210_mdcC_at	7.1	2.2	33.6	37.8	24.5
241	PA0211_mdcD_at	67.8	27.8	47.1	18.8	26.6
242	PA0212_mdcE_at	12.0	14.1	5.8	24.8	26.1
243	PA0213_at	9.2	17.7	16.8	15.6	10.9
244	PA0214_at	31.4	35.5	9.4	26.1	9.0
245	PA0215_at	95.0	68.8	68.7	79.2	73.1
246	PA0216_at	40.1	30.6	38.5	80.4	66.5
247	PA0217_at	61.8	42.4	80.2	81.1	50.6
248	PA0218_at	190.6	99.6	164.0	147.0	135.1
249	PA0219_at	15.4	8.7	31.2	72.7	53.5
250	PA0220_at	20.8	28.7	49.6	36.6	35.6
251	PA0221_at	81.4	35.1	29.6	40.1	40.1
252	PA0222_at	14.8	8.1	13.4	2.8	2.3
253	PA0223_at	106.6	68.0	37.9	44.6	48.4
254	PA0224_at	123.4	105.2	89.2	105.9	126.6
255	PA0225_at	147.5	147.4	298.2	246.1	258.0
256	PA0226_at	74.4	67.1	96.8	82.2	58.3
257	PA0227_at	123.3	64.1	90.5	73.9	46.4
258	PA0228_pcaF_at	23.2	32.3	37.4	41.2	36.9
259	PA0229_pcaT_at	104.5	41.8	35.4	52.4	35.5
260	PA0230_pcaB_at	288.2	116.9	237.7	327.9	321.2
261	PA0231_pcaD_at	182.0	149.3	238.1	208.0	197.6
262	PA0232_pcaC_at	122.8	110.2	135.7	117.1	162.6
263	PA0233_at	44.8	32.3	122.9	80.8	106.8
264	PA0234_at	58.5	52.9	34.6	45.0	24.4
265	PA0235_pcaK_at	127.1	88.0	72.3	51.4	46.1
266	PA0236_at	87.2	45.2	84.9	96.2	112.4
267	PA0237_at	74.5	60.0	84.4	75.9	46.5
268	PA0238_at	72.1	47.7	62.8	51.3	35.7
269	PA0239_at	62.0	41.3	56.5	95.1	68.8
270	PA0240_at	72.8	33.9	32.8	16.2	2.1
271	PA0241_at	79.7	35.3	43.6	53.1	32.7
272	PA0242_at	14.7	21.7	65.7	67.0	48.2
273	PA0243_at	78.5	10.8	84.9	48.4	63.6
274	PA0244_at	35.4	26.1	36.2	37.7	48.3
275	PA0245_aroQ2_at	134.3	87.9	42.9	60.0	60.0
276	PA0246_at	63.4	43.5	84.1	66.7	57.6
277	PA0247_pobA_at	56.4	31.1	42.4	71.5	42.2
278	PA0248_at	174.5	62.2	117.5	158.2	158.6
279	PA0249_at	526.5	335.8	699.6	576.5	534.2
280	PA0250_at	4243.8	3105.9	3672.2	3469.5	3639.7
281	PA0251_at	5.3	50.0	37.3	48.7	21.9
282	PA0252_at	80.1	21.3	55.0	45.0	56.4
283	PA0253_at	104.5	80.2	113.3	124.9	107.1
284	PA0254_at	82.3	70.5	58.2	76.4	66.2
285	PA0255_at	144.9	126.3	231.0	203.4	242.3
286	PA0256_at	88.2	68.2	67.7	78.3	65.9
287	PA0257_at	81.1	115.5	63.8	89.2	70.5
288	PA0258_at	191.7	257.4	158.8	187.4	210.1

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

289	PA0259_at	303.2	326.4	275.8	340.6	319.6
290	PA0260_at	177.1	203.8	165.7	268.7	221.8
291	PA0261_at	130.4	114.7	136.3	153.0	129.2
292	PA0262_at	105.2	66.3	70.9	86.6	78.0
293	PA0263_hpcC_s_at	230.4	214.1	109.1	154.8	111.9
294	PA0264_at	57.4	116.3	108.9	98.7	57.3
295	PA0265_gabD_at	1194.7	1318.6	1726.3	1762.9	1958.6
296	PA0266_gabT_at	868.4	2464.8	930.6	969.5	1083.4
297	PA0267_at	95.2	88.1	118.2	101.5	89.7
298	PA0268_at	144.2	104.0	93.0	124.9	105.3
299	PA0269_at	265.3	277.5	283.6	344.5	343.6
300	PA0270_at	252.4	250.3	377.8	353.3	360.1
301	PA0271_at	180.2	107.3	196.0	166.6	211.0
302	PA0272_at	68.3	67.7	57.8	69.9	44.0
303	PA0273_at	17.2	19.5	24.8	28.0	16.3
304	PA0274_at	50.2	32.7	76.8	87.8	68.8
305	PA0275_at	268.4	180.8	261.5	292.0	313.1
306	PA0276_at	256.8	155.6	182.0	146.2	109.3
307	PA0277_at	40.0	119.4	158.3	158.5	138.2
308	PA0278_at	105.7	84.6	282.2	258.0	173.1
309	PA0279_at	45.9	41.9	126.1	146.0	150.5
310	PA0280_cysA_at	458.8	71.2	61.2	61.9	86.6
311	PA0281_cysW_at	939.1	115.5	35.4	64.6	81.2
312	PA0282_cysT_at	868.2	73.0	38.0	82.2	108.3
313	PA0283_sbp_at	3487.4	130.3	106.9	55.5	288.0
314	PA0284_at	14035.4	400.3	158.9	118.4	951.2
315	PA0285_at	111.8	71.1	107.3	116.3	117.3
316	PA0286_at	417.9	182.7	505.1	409.4	434.1
317	PA0287_at	10.7	20.9	4.0	16.9	4.7
318	PA0288_speB1_at	73.8	26.4	5.2	33.4	17.0
319	PA0289_at	247.9	216.7	268.5	339.6	248.0
320	PA0290_at	122.7	50.3	72.3	112.8	94.0
321	PA0291_oprE_at	2916.7	767.0	469.2	438.6	639.9
322	PA0292_at	491.0	568.6	1052.7	716.1	663.7
323	PA0293_at	50.1	165.4	161.8	145.9	161.1
324	PA0294_at	204.7	90.7	165.6	177.0	170.9
325	PA0295_at	102.5	48.6	81.0	76.0	55.4
326	PA0296_s_at	4424.2	2864.6	4103.1	3403.6	3679.2
327	PA0297_at	827.7	407.2	1022.6	924.7	990.5
328	PA0298_at	1633.4	1495.7	1591.2	1284.4	1298.6
329	PA0299_at	2899.1	3590.8	1782.2	1969.0	2017.3
330	PA0300_potF2_at	1748.1	2945.7	1599.2	1673.7	1658.5
331	PA0301_potF3_at	249.0	317.0	302.1	285.6	273.7
332	PA0302_potG_at	122.9	468.6	186.5	202.3	217.4
333	PA0303_potH_at	153.1	476.8	186.9	188.2	184.3
334	PA0304_potI_at	84.3	256.9	51.1	58.4	54.5
335	PA0305_at	187.6	152.6	140.4	108.5	127.6
336	PA0306_at	123.5	75.8	74.3	100.9	89.6
337	PA0307_at	74.2	32.0	55.6	47.8	54.5
338	PA0308_at	107.8	91.4	205.9	194.9	196.5
339	PA0309_at	210.4	166.4	342.1	261.8	280.2
340	PA0310_at	246.1	227.6	176.4	209.3	182.9
341	PA0311_at	13.0	79.2	89.4	72.3	64.7
342	PA0312_at	470.6	200.7	638.8	684.7	627.4
343	PA0313_at	82.1	46.9	120.1	111.0	77.4
344	PA0314_at	164.0	107.6	285.1	261.5	297.7
345	PA0315_at	339.9	333.8	457.3	469.2	467.3
346	PA0316_serA_at	215.1	190.6	342.5	267.4	334.9
347	PA0317_at	460.1	256.7	666.2	543.0	579.8
348	PA0318_at	357.3	284.5	399.1	471.9	413.1
349	PA0319_at	249.4	146.7	189.5	186.0	159.5
350	PA0320_at	165.4	237.8	98.6	62.9	75.3
351	PA0321_at	45.0	44.5	68.4	65.5	55.0
352	PA0322_at	7.8	35.8	47.8	31.8	51.1
353	PA0323_at	35.8	28.2	34.6	33.9	35.6
354	PA0324_at	10.5	7.4	10.9	39.1	16.7
355	PA0325_at	11.1	46.5	67.9	59.1	66.0
356	PA0326_at	117.9	146.5	95.5	92.9	108.9
357	PA0327_at	28.7	59.1	63.7	65.8	50.8
358	PA0328_at	70.7	138.7	97.4	70.9	61.2
359	PA0329_at	497.4	339.2	428.0	486.9	506.7
360	PA0330_rpiA_at	242.2	205.2	426.2	344.7	330.0
361	PA0331_ilvA1_at	165.1	113.0	297.4	289.4	261.0

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

362	PA0332_at	178.5	114.2	181.2	232.2	184.8
363	PA0333_at	148.2	52.9	75.8	81.0	55.8
364	PA0334_at	140.6	73.3	111.6	91.1	90.3
365	PA0335_at	400.9	285.6	793.1	779.3	856.5
366	PA0336_at	3905.3	2789.5	2947.9	3037.2	3238.7
367	PA0337_ptsP_at	1023.4	1118.2	900.7	1078.0	903.0
368	PA0338_at	60.9	94.2	59.0	57.4	35.2
369	PA0339_at	110.6	33.9	102.3	118.7	139.4
370	PA0340_at	82.5	63.5	95.0	93.4	108.6
371	PA0341_lgt_at	51.2	66.6	62.3	73.3	53.5
372	PA0342_thyA_at	226.9	194.9	452.9	353.8	385.5
373	PA0343_at	80.0	74.3	95.2	106.8	99.8
374	PA0344_at	171.2	112.3	140.2	142.7	113.6
375	PA0345_at	149.3	103.3	215.3	290.1	273.4
376	PA0346_at	37.4	76.8	66.9	63.9	47.4
377	PA0347_glpQ_at	140.2	52.4	79.2	113.2	63.5
378	PA0348_at	50.3	67.2	70.7	68.9	53.1
379	PA0349_at	72.3	18.7	30.3	16.4	21.0
380	PA0350_folA_at	35.6	35.7	107.6	75.9	75.7
381	PA0351_at	318.1	309.7	295.3	306.7	377.5
382	PA0352_at	109.2	82.7	57.0	66.4	62.8
383	PA0353_ilvD_at	443.6	416.5	397.8	311.5	357.6
384	PA0354_at	78.9	62.9	91.7	101.4	73.0
385	PA0355_pfpI_at	216.1	88.8	60.7	86.5	96.4
386	PA0356_at	93.9	64.2	96.6	93.5	109.5
387	PA0357_mutM_at	116.6	82.9	155.9	138.3	138.9
388	PA0358_at	105.8	98.2	141.7	130.6	138.6
389	PA0359_at	317.3	236.2	402.8	341.2	414.2
390	PA0360_at	359.0	215.8	528.6	448.5	373.3
391	PA0361_at	133.7	60.6	90.3	111.6	123.0
392	PA0362_fdx1_at	1030.9	759.2	743.5	894.0	970.3
393	PA0363_coaD_at	252.9	117.9	408.4	377.1	437.3
394	PA0364_at	51.8	58.0	62.4	59.4	35.1
395	PA0365_at	251.8	121.0	266.3	265.8	269.7
396	PA0366_at	183.6	118.5	252.9	191.3	224.9
397	PA0367_at	164.5	95.1	251.6	256.4	296.9
398	PA0368_at	129.3	141.5	271.3	169.9	165.3
399	PA0369_at	197.6	354.7	129.1	109.4	91.1
400	PA0370_at	228.4	473.3	256.5	230.7	214.4
401	PA0371_at	218.4	393.8	279.3	203.5	184.8
402	PA0372_at	452.8	368.6	736.7	680.4	724.6
403	PA0373_ftsY_at	538.5	385.1	813.3	819.3	784.2
404	PA0374_ftsE_at	736.7	568.0	869.6	615.0	639.9
405	PA0375_ftsX_at	605.7	627.9	654.1	761.8	670.8
406	PA0376_rpoH_at	1912.6	1629.0	2230.1	2143.9	2340.0
407	PA0377_at	111.6	149.2	110.9	139.4	121.5
408	PA0378_at	57.4	45.0	49.3	63.6	51.3
409	PA0379_at	151.9	61.7	202.9	245.5	232.7
410	PA0380_i_at	148.5	64.1	191.8	202.5	285.7
411	PA0381_thiG_at	91.6	95.3	164.6	131.5	125.1
412	PA0382_micA_at	6.2	54.7	58.1	51.4	66.9
413	PA0383_at	7.6	44.1	31.0	24.9	24.1
414	PA0384_at	122.4	89.3	147.8	106.1	111.1
415	PA0385_at	47.8	38.6	63.6	54.7	60.6
416	PA0386_at	145.5	75.4	98.4	86.7	87.3
417	PA0387_at	330.5	395.1	323.7	388.9	383.4
418	PA0388_at	231.7	342.0	207.2	198.0	192.7
419	PA0389_at	60.3	82.4	140.1	96.6	113.3
420	PA0390_metX_at	79.1	96.9	199.2	155.8	188.8
421	PA0391_at	138.4	123.7	66.2	89.4	68.7
422	PA0392_at	277.0	316.1	368.3	351.4	309.7
423	PA0393_procA_at	358.7	288.4	457.9	491.2	485.5
424	PA0394_at	583.2	461.6	1149.6	1011.0	1162.7
425	PA0395_pilT_at	246.3	128.1	335.7	257.2	291.9
426	PA0396_pilU_at	118.1	119.6	222.2	346.9	269.5
427	PA0397_at	88.5	48.9	60.6	71.1	68.7
428	PA0398_at	212.1	212.1	329.2	303.4	334.9
429	PA0399_at	624.0	622.8	507.0	411.5	501.5
430	PA0400_at	381.2	627.4	287.3	342.3	352.8
431	PA0401_at	202.7	222.3	177.4	161.4	151.2
432	PA0402_pyrB_at	460.9	336.2	627.6	615.5	651.5
433	PA0403_pyrR_at	389.6	332.8	394.5	403.9	464.9
434	PA0404_i_at	1629.1	1440.0	1412.8	1828.8	1756.3

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

435	PA0405_at	1622.2	1112.6	1237.8	1321.6	1426.3
436	PA0406_at	136.3	75.3	323.4	193.8	241.9
437	PA0407_gshB_at	351.6	276.3	490.1	554.4	521.6
438	PA0408_pilG_at	1015.5	804.7	1068.7	1111.7	1461.8
439	PA0409_pilH_at	1048.1	597.2	1985.7	1829.3	2063.4
440	PA0410_pilI_at	121.6	45.4	300.4	238.4	226.0
441	PA0411_pilJ_at	115.6	334.4	272.4	225.3	214.5
442	PA0412_pilK_at	122.6	103.1	101.7	77.3	93.0
443	PA0413_at	337.1	978.5	305.4	318.9	318.3
444	PA0414_at	225.0	499.8	227.8	243.6	217.7
445	PA0415_at	422.7	270.7	337.7	295.9	293.8
446	PA0416_at	96.0	136.1	67.2	141.8	71.8
447	PA0417_at	53.9	50.8	18.8	69.2	47.6
448	PA0418_at	96.3	17.2	66.0	49.6	39.2
449	PA0419_at	105.1	92.0	139.4	135.6	118.3
450	PA0420_bioA_at	236.6	118.8	299.6	279.8	281.2
451	PA0421_at	211.1	152.0	307.1	357.9	327.3
452	PA0422_at	278.8	124.3	923.9	903.0	1039.3
453	PA0423_at	215.5	323.6	182.1	139.7	161.9
454	PA0424_mexR_at	256.4	304.7	340.2	310.0	255.7
455	PA0425_mexA_at	428.5	353.1	802.2	738.4	731.4
456	PA0426_mexB_at	306.7	546.6	484.9	409.8	466.3
457	PA0427_oprM_at	557.2	1596.7	520.0	414.3	499.9
458	PA0428_at	354.1	531.5	397.7	359.1	385.3
459	PA0429_at	249.7	253.3	239.1	207.2	230.4
460	PA0430_metF_at	131.3	182.9	102.0	83.2	62.0
461	PA0431_at	274.0	405.6	367.0	332.8	286.7
462	PA0432_sahH_at	576.6	855.1	1052.9	947.1	843.5
463	PA0433_at	68.6	32.6	94.4	109.2	84.1
464	PA0434_at	146.5	102.5	83.8	78.9	67.3
465	PA0435_at	64.5	8.3	41.6	54.2	25.5
466	PA0436_at	468.9	344.5	599.3	807.4	753.5
467	PA0437_codA_at	102.8	148.2	43.1	81.9	65.8
468	PA0438_codB_at	112.3	18.0	66.2	65.6	40.6
469	PA0439_at	25.1	7.0	18.0	20.1	15.3
470	PA0440_at	4.4	5.9	7.4	30.1	17.0
471	PA0441_at	153.5	88.0	128.1	142.0	160.7
472	PA0442_r_at	0.3	3.3	0.0	5.7	0.0
473	PA0443_at	24.9	9.2	33.5	47.5	20.9
474	PA0444_at	62.9	13.7	54.3	57.2	69.5
475	PA0445_s_at	120.4	151.6	122.6	147.6	141.9
476	PA0446_at	58.6	604.4	248.0	293.7	287.3
477	PA0447_gcdH_at	515.8	1743.1	880.2	1008.5	1252.7
478	PA0448_at	116.2	51.7	145.1	114.7	115.2
479	PA0449_at	9922.9	6741.8	4300.5	4488.7	4455.1
480	PA0450_at	41.1	28.8	15.0	40.0	32.4
481	PA0451_at	119.0	96.7	111.8	121.0	106.1
482	PA0452_at	90.4	41.2	41.1	63.6	53.3
483	PA0453_at	23.6	70.5	28.1	44.8	46.2
484	PA0454_at	125.8	136.8	185.8	196.9	222.1
485	PA0455_dbpA_at	226.6	174.7	230.2	229.4	228.4
486	PA0456_at	1449.7	1853.6	1657.9	1675.8	1712.4
487	PA0457_at	170.6	137.6	171.7	165.1	176.7
488	PA0458_at	108.7	87.1	188.7	136.6	147.1
489	PA0459_at	91.3	65.1	77.5	86.1	82.4
490	PA0460_at	98.6	117.1	152.0	199.3	205.3
491	PA0461_at	223.4	180.7	358.5	339.9	344.0
492	PA0462_at	329.7	238.5	332.5	377.4	319.7
493	PA0463_creB_at	185.2	152.4	206.8	247.3	302.5
494	PA0464_creC_at	88.3	62.2	160.0	183.4	112.6
495	PA0465_creD_at	29.1	22.1	24.7	36.3	30.8
496	PA0466_at	68.1	33.7	35.5	43.2	45.8
497	PA0467_at	399.6	497.9	522.3	584.3	561.5
498	PA0468_at	375.3	277.4	389.5	436.3	477.1
499	PA0469_at	366.6	292.7	549.2	460.7	536.7
500	PA0470_at	107.4	92.3	99.6	146.9	115.7
501	PA0471_at	933.9	466.3	687.0	738.0	727.4
502	PA0472_at	802.4	463.9	468.2	456.5	494.4
503	PA0473_at	143.8	193.3	418.6	288.4	385.3
504	PA0474_at	12.2	10.5	2.1	15.5	13.5
505	PA0475_at	30.2	18.5	88.7	70.2	111.9
506	PA0476_at	58.9	60.2	5.9	49.4	55.8
507	PA0477_at	156.3	79.9	93.5	104.5	94.6

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

508	PA0478_at	77.0	45.1	76.1	69.8	93.5
509	PA0479_at	131.5	67.0	197.2	230.0	216.1
510	PA0480_at	5.5	2.7	6.8	5.8	14.2
511	PA0481_at	74.0	72.7	72.5	92.7	64.0
512	PA0482_glcB_at	118.7	215.1	255.8	258.3	255.0
513	PA0483_at	53.8	33.1	85.0	107.6	76.1
514	PA0484_at	119.3	94.5	198.3	201.4	121.9
515	PA0485_at	153.4	91.1	164.5	181.1	167.3
516	PA0486_at	262.6	158.3	324.4	273.9	302.3
517	PA0487_at	224.9	207.0	333.1	267.7	288.8
518	PA0488_at	115.0	52.7	139.4	121.0	141.2
519	PA0489_at	55.5	29.2	50.4	75.7	61.8
520	PA0490_at	175.6	192.7	199.3	217.4	166.0
521	PA0491_at	36.0	71.4	48.1	68.5	92.8
522	PA0492_at	886.3	1423.6	2478.3	2127.6	2353.6
523	PA0493_at	582.7	817.7	1581.1	1408.5	1336.3
524	PA0494_at	535.2	580.5	1411.1	1199.4	1112.8
525	PA0495_at	655.7	490.3	1457.6	1306.7	1087.6
526	PA0496_at	119.3	112.2	303.0	294.5	211.0
527	PA0497_at	69.4	35.9	27.3	45.0	51.9
528	PA0498_at	40.1	66.3	32.4	59.0	60.1
529	PA0499_at	210.1	98.1	112.6	112.0	97.1
530	PA0500_bioB_at	2802.4	2169.2	2022.8	1712.6	1884.3
531	PA0501_bioF_at	335.6	230.3	306.3	288.1	284.5
532	PA0502_at	142.2	131.3	176.2	188.2	147.5
533	PA0503_at	95.2	82.0	82.9	105.2	143.0
534	PA0504_bioD_at	125.3	102.0	88.7	81.1	75.6
535	PA0505_at	1449.6	2288.4	894.3	1103.0	1123.2
536	PA0506_at	852.2	1015.3	1291.6	669.5	785.4
537	PA0507_at	141.5	74.2	380.5	142.9	90.6
538	PA0508_at	73.2	44.8	59.2	66.4	59.4
539	PA0509_nirN_at	124.1	104.9	113.1	95.8	82.0
540	PA0510_at	55.6	72.1	53.0	44.6	59.8
541	PA0511_nirJ_at	116.9	105.6	98.4	65.6	77.5
542	PA0512_at	12.7	45.5	24.7	43.4	23.3
543	PA0513_at	10.0	62.1	25.8	38.5	33.8
544	PA0514_nirL_at	7.4	88.6	7.5	26.7	40.0
545	PA0515_at	9.7	245.8	50.4	67.2	8.7
546	PA0516_nirF_at	49.2	80.5	40.7	40.8	38.6
547	PA0517_nirC_at	8.6	171.1	18.7	22.4	15.9
548	PA0518_nirM_at	34.0	152.7	63.1	53.7	44.3
549	PA0519_nirS_at	39.6	124.1	27.5	37.7	12.9
550	PA0520_nirQ_at	191.1	101.8	130.1	90.3	85.1
551	PA0521_at	61.5	11.3	26.3	38.8	32.4
552	PA0522_r_at	185.1	292.7	335.8	272.2	222.6
553	PA0523_norC_at	12.4	22.0	15.3	20.4	37.2
554	PA0524_norB_at	9.9	5.3	17.9	21.5	13.3
555	PA0525_at	7.3	22.1	28.7	23.6	22.4
556	PA0526_at	83.4	50.5	39.8	35.9	34.5
557	PA0527_dnr_at	62.9	91.1	32.4	33.6	31.5
558	PA0528_at	17.9	34.3	51.0	25.0	52.3
559	PA0529_at	83.6	103.2	85.5	122.2	102.4
560	PA0530_at	35.0	53.7	47.1	65.7	40.2
561	PA0531_at	79.6	20.2	49.6	41.6	14.0
562	PA0532_at	100.9	76.2	52.4	57.6	76.5
563	PA0533_at	4.6	29.4	56.8	50.2	68.1
564	PA0534_at	111.9	94.8	47.0	69.6	56.6
565	PA0535_at	93.4	72.5	61.1	46.9	65.1
566	PA0536_at	175.2	322.5	295.6	255.4	257.1
567	PA0537_at	1107.3	560.1	891.4	991.9	1062.7
568	PA0538_dsbB_at	46.3	81.1	198.2	230.2	181.7
569	PA0539_at	118.2	50.6	18.9	19.4	41.0
570	PA0540_at	23.0	15.9	52.9	61.9	43.7
571	PA0541_at	46.7	75.4	128.6	125.7	92.0
572	PA0542_at	85.8	169.2	192.6	183.0	186.1
573	PA0543_at	125.1	40.3	62.5	59.7	66.6
574	PA0544_at	161.4	68.3	315.2	278.2	267.2
575	PA0545_at	86.1	64.2	71.0	84.9	60.5
576	PA0546_metK_at	408.9	940.3	303.2	278.9	323.4
577	PA0547_at	105.2	113.6	126.7	121.8	109.1
578	PA0548_tktA_at	178.4	259.0	282.2	282.1	290.5
579	PA0549_at	135.8	145.4	92.6	78.9	79.6
580	PA0550_at	51.1	27.6	53.2	63.1	50.9

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

581	PA0551_epd_at	169.1	114.6	363.6	296.4	333.6
582	PA0552_pgk_at	50.7	180.1	79.6	143.6	83.3
583	PA0553_at	254.0	192.3	217.7	309.1	309.3
584	PA0554_at	252.3	300.8	394.7	330.0	250.0
585	PA0555_fda_at	521.7	816.7	858.7	800.7	924.7
586	PA0556_at	36.3	44.7	8.0	39.2	32.5
587	PA0557_at	6.0	5.9	6.9	24.8	3.1
588	PA0558_at	41.9	31.3	153.2	137.6	115.2
589	PA0559_at	97.5	63.7	66.4	73.1	72.2
590	PA0560_at	118.8	40.1	113.0	121.6	87.5
591	PA0561_at	65.0	39.2	60.0	47.0	36.1
592	PA0562_at	149.5	183.8	321.2	329.1	326.4
593	PA0563_at	2133.2	1982.9	1740.3	1737.7	1790.6
594	PA0564_at	154.1	75.5	136.7	157.3	116.1
595	PA0565_at	332.3	310.4	136.2	351.5	135.8
596	PA0566_at	437.2	293.0	399.8	444.2	443.9
597	PA0567_i_at	161.8	75.4	57.3	109.5	93.4
598	PA0568_at	87.7	90.5	108.1	105.3	114.0
599	PA0569_at	121.3	102.5	156.9	152.6	133.9
600	PA0570_at	172.1	144.5	229.7	159.7	176.9
601	PA0571_at	248.0	134.7	193.9	264.7	343.8
602	PA0572_at	33.7	78.3	81.6	86.0	87.9
603	PA0573_at	9.2	16.9	32.5	37.2	34.0
604	PA0574_at	343.5	203.7	387.0	359.9	372.8
605	PA0575_at	69.9	16.6	22.7	11.0	9.8
606	PA0576_rpoD_at	1118.3	1061.3	1004.8	932.9	961.8
607	PA0577_dnaG_at	370.6	252.5	297.9	381.8	366.1
608	PA0578_at	127.9	123.1	299.0	173.8	218.1
609	PA0579_rpsU_at	338.8	260.4	529.8	399.0	472.8
610	PA0580_gcp_at	163.6	93.1	118.4	88.4	103.6
611	PA0581_i_at	364.7	156.8	192.8	255.1	273.0
612	PA0582_folB_at	15.7	42.5	50.2	46.0	46.9
613	PA0583_at	16.8	38.7	56.4	56.8	42.6
614	PA0584_cca_at	111.7	99.0	126.5	155.5	146.4
615	PA0585_at	46.1	4.5	28.4	29.1	13.5
616	PA0586_at	235.9	201.3	222.9	336.3	249.0
617	PA0587_at	115.1	94.1	302.8	377.8	330.0
618	PA0588_at	1403.4	1261.5	2404.7	2017.6	2060.5
619	PA0589_at	417.7	331.7	413.5	447.2	389.1
620	PA0590_apah_at	691.9	643.7	1041.3	1016.6	1250.1
621	PA0591_at	844.1	594.1	1020.7	1016.7	1038.1
622	PA0592_ksgA_at	181.3	177.8	325.4	292.3	375.5
623	PA0593_pdxA_at	104.1	481.4	139.7	145.3	150.3
624	PA0594_surA_at	258.4	853.9	275.8	246.1	291.8
625	PA0595_ostA_at	572.3	490.2	1098.4	933.5	927.2
626	PA0596_at	643.3	958.0	496.8	593.9	582.7
627	PA0597_at	215.8	211.2	190.2	227.1	209.2
628	PA0598_at	302.2	423.1	363.2	437.8	440.3
629	PA0599_at	476.8	256.6	294.7	278.6	321.8
630	PA0600_at	85.0	16.1	14.3	31.8	29.0
631	PA0601_at	160.2	195.7	200.9	204.9	225.3
632	PA0602_at	14.1	67.3	36.7	53.4	45.3
633	PA0603_at	111.9	228.9	183.1	215.1	192.2
634	PA0604_at	12.6	124.1	85.8	89.2	94.1
635	PA0605_at	6.6	80.6	17.8	42.8	35.8
636	PA0606_at	51.0	45.3	50.8	36.7	31.1
637	PA0607_rpe_at	96.1	56.5	73.1	113.5	75.3
638	PA0608_at	216.4	248.2	300.0	265.5	272.1
639	PA0609_trpE_at	98.2	109.2	412.7	540.7	458.4
640	PA0610_prtN_at	531.8	413.0	267.1	282.1	325.5
641	PA0611_prtR_at	594.2	259.0	473.7	575.4	601.4
642	PA0612_i_at	405.9	170.9	166.7	124.9	122.8
643	PA0613_at	126.2	55.3	28.3	35.1	39.6
644	PA0614_at	27.6	67.3	70.5	109.9	93.2
645	PA0615_at	86.7	122.6	123.0	143.9	146.8
646	PA0616_at	144.3	141.1	138.4	168.5	158.1
647	PA0617_at	10.5	58.3	42.0	74.1	55.1
648	PA0618_at	105.1	117.5	112.3	112.1	97.5
649	PA0619_at	122.3	174.8	153.4	138.5	135.2
650	PA0620_at	24.7	122.2	102.2	148.3	108.6
651	PA0621_at	201.0	369.3	306.5	377.5	482.5
652	PA0622_at	123.2	290.4	224.8	297.9	313.1
653	PA0623_at	196.9	226.8	217.6	207.7	272.9

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

654	PA0624_at	62.2	96.4	169.9	103.6	110.2
655	PA0625_at	96.4	60.2	53.6	45.1	30.5
656	PA0626_at	93.7	116.7	72.6	85.6	73.5
657	PA0627_at	57.8	96.9	70.9	76.7	78.2
658	PA0628_at	11.6	42.4	45.7	69.9	54.2
659	PA0629_at	24.2	40.8	35.7	47.4	56.2
660	PA0630_at	41.4	44.6	62.6	77.1	66.2
661	PA0631_at	14.7	18.5	30.0	49.7	48.4
662	PA0632_at	8.7	47.0	42.8	53.6	38.3
663	PA0633_at	179.0	244.8	197.4	246.7	238.1
664	PA0634_at	18.1	47.0	46.8	47.7	50.4
665	PA0635_at	24.6	43.6	51.6	54.5	46.0
666	PA0636_at	113.1	172.4	134.0	184.2	151.6
667	PA0637_at	11.9	86.1	45.7	51.4	70.6
668	PA0638_at	29.9	64.5	41.0	73.4	67.2
669	PA0639_at	42.3	62.6	60.2	83.3	77.9
670	PA0640_at	47.2	24.2	35.0	42.6	26.6
671	PA0641_at	37.7	14.0	14.5	16.1	38.1
672	PA0642_at	5.1	15.1	9.8	22.1	17.6
673	PA0643_at	64.1	95.8	45.7	68.6	72.9
674	PA0644_at	113.0	116.8	76.6	88.4	83.3
675	PA0645_at	87.6	94.7	67.6	64.3	60.1
676	PA0646_at	72.3	39.0	56.3	57.2	70.4
677	PA0647_at	71.5	84.7	100.4	91.7	87.0
678	PA0648_at	291.7	319.5	193.5	238.5	258.1
679	PA0649_trpG_at	476.1	279.0	1242.7	1395.4	1263.5
680	PA0650_trpD_at	359.9	358.6	799.6	857.6	883.4
681	PA0651_trpC_at	182.1	193.6	331.9	412.9	520.4
682	PA0652_vfr_at	915.3	736.1	1074.3	947.5	1055.2
683	PA0653_at	110.9	86.8	161.2	142.4	135.1
684	PA0654_speD_at	144.2	124.8	184.6	130.7	158.3
685	PA0655_at	433.8	242.5	443.7	370.9	470.5
686	PA0656_at	186.7	209.6	274.8	334.4	296.7
687	PA0657_at	182.4	125.0	302.9	288.4	276.9
688	PA0658_at	231.8	124.9	260.9	259.8	248.9
689	PA0659_at	262.4	272.1	571.4	514.9	624.5
690	PA0660_at	260.4	142.7	338.7	345.3	374.8
691	PA0661_at	527.1	479.8	1101.5	1076.5	1113.0
692	PA0662_argC_at	40.5	79.3	175.2	148.3	157.8
693	PA0663_at	64.5	92.8	189.1	81.4	158.8
694	PA0664_at	213.1	160.6	171.2	167.7	186.7
695	PA0665_at	823.7	546.7	973.1	1226.6	1365.7
696	PA0666_at	23.6	50.3	31.0	51.7	39.3
697	PA0667_at	197.1	164.8	249.2	221.7	168.7
698	PA0668_tyrZ_at	74.9	162.2	288.6	296.4	263.1
699	PA0669_at	167.4	106.6	96.6	119.7	91.6
700	PA0670_at	587.0	151.0	186.9	192.9	171.7
701	PA0671_at	1241.8	624.9	556.5	490.5	417.1
702	PA0672_at	935.9	609.3	887.8	646.0	668.9
703	PA0673_at	101.7	60.2	135.9	127.8	141.5
704	PA0674_at	87.3	22.8	62.5	66.1	71.5
705	PA0675_at	42.8	47.2	52.6	48.1	46.6
706	PA0676_at	18.5	16.4	24.8	32.8	18.0
707	PA0677_at	8.2	6.4	10.4	28.0	16.4
708	PA0678_i_at	9.6	10.0	25.2	4.1	23.6
709	PA0679_at	111.9	42.7	42.6	64.9	49.8
710	PA0680_at	35.3	20.6	21.2	32.1	20.1
711	PA0681_at	12.1	26.5	2.9	7.5	15.7
712	PA0682_at	84.0	26.7	22.8	41.1	30.6
713	PA0683_at	59.4	20.2	11.4	6.9	12.2
714	PA0684_at	22.9	29.1	19.8	25.0	16.8
715	PA0685_at	13.1	13.9	10.1	30.7	3.8
716	PA0686_at	49.4	29.4	19.6	28.3	10.9
717	PA0687_at	87.9	4.9	13.9	21.8	12.8
718	PA0688_at	4.3	2.0	18.0	23.6	21.9
719	PA0689_at	119.9	108.3	119.3	130.8	106.6
720	PA0690_at	4.9	18.6	7.1	29.7	15.4
721	PA0691_at	4.4	12.4	17.8	20.8	7.5
722	PA0692_at	27.2	34.5	25.5	19.9	21.6
723	PA0693_exbB2_at	14.9	31.1	9.5	18.3	16.2
724	PA0694_exbD2_at	204.2	91.5	83.4	61.0	79.1
725	PA0695_at	8.9	7.9	4.1	38.3	5.8
726	PA0696_at	20.1	2.0	4.2	2.2	1.1

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

727	PA0697_at	11.1	10.0	17.5	26.9	1.5
728	PA0698_at	7.4	26.6	21.6	42.3	26.3
729	PA0699_at	69.6	37.4	40.7	60.6	56.0
730	PA0700_at	53.1	17.8	77.1	34.0	46.2
731	PA0701_at	8.7	18.5	6.0	30.4	13.5
732	PA0702_at	53.6	4.3	14.8	16.1	4.3
733	PA0703_at	6.5	27.4	40.5	57.8	32.3
734	PA0704_at	25.7	52.1	90.1	74.0	55.2
735	PA0705_at	335.4	218.8	623.6	549.0	572.4
736	PA0706_cat_at	150.2	74.7	218.7	185.6	176.5
737	PA0707_toxR_at	24.7	22.0	76.1	57.9	38.8
738	PA0708_at	157.6	105.7	243.5	236.0	245.8
739	PA0709_at	50.0	54.7	40.9	45.7	36.8
740	PA0710_gloA2_at	49.3	32.8	14.1	55.5	40.0
741	PA0711_at	17.1	21.2	29.0	23.7	27.3
742	PA0712_at	161.5	60.1	120.3	121.8	148.9
743	PA0713_at	131.8	160.5	102.1	122.9	123.6
744	PA0714_at	14.9	17.6	15.0	9.5	16.3
745	PA0715_at	95.3	120.6	131.5	229.7	214.3
746	PA0716_at	28.8	29.3	28.6	37.3	44.9
747	PA0717_at	16.9	45.9	56.0	72.6	64.0
748	PA0718_at	70.0	15.6	21.1	46.8	43.7
749	PA0719_at	4.5	10.2	16.5	26.1	17.8
750	PA0720_at	60.1	90.2	54.1	80.1	46.5
751	PA0721_r_at	114.2	57.8	46.4	24.3	26.7
752	PA0722_at	83.7	132.1	82.7	86.5	95.9
753	PA0723_coaB_at	95.5	91.3	59.1	84.3	78.8
754	PA0724_at	48.8	33.8	19.6	30.0	16.6
755	PA0725_at	22.2	22.2	11.6	17.6	6.6
756	PA0726_at	13.5	24.5	52.6	43.0	41.8
757	PA0727_at	84.9	70.2	59.7	68.7	68.2
758	PA0728_at	11.0	29.0	54.9	49.1	60.8
759	PA0729_at	1479.3	1503.3	1319.6	1609.6	1712.7
760	PA0730_at	176.5	252.1	193.6	210.5	193.8
761	PA0731_at	147.0	136.4	172.0	169.2	226.2
762	PA0732_at	265.2	256.0	179.7	226.0	259.3
763	PA0733_at	93.1	81.8	126.1	142.4	133.6
764	PA0734_i_at	106.5	43.5	202.0	190.7	201.2
765	PA0735_at	90.3	94.5	143.3	122.1	150.0
766	PA0736_at	90.6	36.4	118.5	123.9	121.2
767	PA0737_at	94.6	64.9	53.8	67.4	81.6
768	PA0738_at	38.1	33.2	50.1	49.9	35.1
769	PA0739_at	246.8	212.3	179.4	193.8	190.3
770	PA0740_at	23.2	11.9	27.4	4.9	6.2
771	PA0741_at	71.4	64.6	37.3	45.2	30.7
772	PA0742_at	4.9	32.9	36.5	52.7	49.0
773	PA0743_at	122.0	82.4	180.7	146.4	141.9
774	PA0744_at	312.4	293.3	340.3	433.0	429.7
775	PA0745_at	680.5	850.2	1076.9	895.1	953.3
776	PA0746_at	136.3	143.1	206.8	227.3	229.4
777	PA0747_at	142.7	269.4	329.5	324.0	373.1
778	PA0748_at	63.0	7.0	38.2	54.2	45.8
779	PA0749_at	94.2	67.5	203.1	177.6	154.0
780	PA0750_ung_at	29.7	115.5	104.1	82.9	118.6
781	PA0751_at	105.0	171.0	50.4	53.6	40.1
782	PA0752_at	114.9	287.6	71.7	69.5	61.5
783	PA0753_at	97.9	125.6	42.7	50.5	48.2
784	PA0754_at	297.8	512.6	111.7	110.1	109.6
785	PA0755_at	209.0	267.9	140.7	162.9	112.7
786	PA0756_at	73.0	42.1	153.4	118.3	98.1
787	PA0757_at	57.3	66.9	74.8	93.0	59.9
788	PA0758_at	148.9	117.6	153.7	164.5	155.7
789	PA0759_at	461.2	278.2	956.4	678.5	661.1
790	PA0760_at	92.6	136.6	101.0	86.6	101.0
791	PA0761_nadB_at	871.0	1031.8	656.9	776.3	756.8
792	PA0762_algU_at	3627.1	2158.5	2794.5	2938.0	2951.1
793	PA0763_mucA_at	2051.3	1552.4	1803.7	2225.1	2283.8
794	PA0764_mucB_at	610.5	464.9	549.1	611.1	595.0
795	PA0765_mucC_at	510.4	487.0	508.4	676.5	570.8
796	PA0766_mucD_at	333.4	559.7	569.4	543.6	528.2
797	PA0767_lepA_at	184.6	254.4	205.6	186.0	183.5
798	PA0768_lepB_at	322.1	796.6	395.6	385.3	334.3
799	PA0769_at	280.7	440.9	479.7	525.7	502.0

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

800	PA0770_rnc_at	311.0	394.7	368.7	479.1	545.7
801	PA0771_era_at	156.7	607.0	264.3	385.8	372.8
802	PA0772_rec0_at	78.6	68.4	76.1	75.7	95.5
803	PA0773_pdxJ_at	105.8	130.1	178.6	129.3	107.2
804	PA0774_at	84.5	66.9	46.3	71.2	40.8
805	PA0775_at	72.7	33.9	62.9	60.2	54.6
806	PA0776_at	16.3	27.9	27.2	58.9	33.0
807	PA0777_at	64.1	42.9	93.6	127.8	132.7
808	PA0778_at	133.6	115.8	209.6	212.8	200.0
809	PA0779_at	211.8	175.4	220.9	227.9	189.1
810	PA0780_at	112.1	84.5	137.5	135.5	158.9
811	PA0781_at	115.0	98.9	88.9	105.8	51.0
812	PA0782_putA_at	173.6	197.0	192.5	200.4	193.5
813	PA0783_putP_at	89.1	134.0	119.4	113.6	112.5
814	PA0784_at	471.6	416.7	483.6	636.5	682.4
815	PA0785_at	29.1	31.6	51.1	55.0	64.9
816	PA0786_at	54.5	12.1	30.9	32.9	18.1
817	PA0787_at	110.9	88.9	163.4	149.5	114.8
818	PA0788_at	130.1	135.8	97.5	120.8	98.9
819	PA0789_at	258.7	1060.8	244.3	287.8	255.3
820	PA0790_at	24.5	25.1	19.4	31.6	14.7
821	PA0791_at	355.3	297.6	334.4	297.6	309.9
822	PA0792_prpD_at	124.9	185.5	159.6	123.2	177.3
823	PA0793_at	131.0	282.5	183.9	203.2	154.9
824	PA0794_at	94.3	382.2	196.4	143.3	144.6
825	PA0795_prpC_at	344.9	1616.3	691.2	681.9	651.6
826	PA0796_prpB_at	140.7	260.3	604.2	570.2	535.1
827	PA0797_at	195.7	133.3	916.1	952.3	914.6
828	PA0798_at	10.4	13.7	46.5	40.9	54.9
829	PA0799_at	23.1	49.7	37.1	46.6	53.5
830	PA0800_at	132.7	33.3	57.2	45.1	35.3
831	PA0801_at	170.0	66.7	135.1	82.1	57.2
832	PA0802_i_at	52.7	16.5	47.1	53.8	38.3
833	PA0803_at	79.1	33.7	65.0	39.0	69.8
834	PA0804_at	301.8	237.4	286.5	276.1	298.4
835	PA0805_at	1903.4	1783.6	981.3	1002.0	1227.8
836	PA0806_i_at	87.3	67.1	73.0	90.6	73.3
837	PA0807_at	38.7	91.6	45.7	74.2	54.5
838	PA0808_at	78.4	40.6	38.5	41.2	33.9
839	PA0809_at	62.6	47.0	21.8	45.8	31.3
840	PA0810_at	150.1	125.0	206.0	219.6	195.5
841	PA0811_at	48.6	13.6	41.3	32.3	20.8
842	PA0812_at	65.8	41.1	39.9	38.1	28.5
843	PA0813_at	118.4	51.0	60.0	75.5	69.5
844	PA0814_i_at	85.1	68.5	68.6	66.0	74.8
845	PA0815_at	248.4	243.1	183.2	252.9	208.2
846	PA0816_at	145.7	122.2	168.2	160.1	153.0
847	PA0817_at	90.8	79.6	100.9	114.0	105.5
848	PA0818_at	30.1	58.5	79.6	78.4	73.1
849	PA0819_f_at	172.7	83.4	73.8	72.8	90.1
850	PA0820_at	436.8	339.5	780.0	749.1	661.5
851	PA0821_at	301.2	260.1	249.3	273.6	259.4
852	PA0822_at	113.2	111.9	70.5	79.1	68.2
853	PA0823_at	46.9	32.6	24.2	63.0	49.1
854	PA0824_at	20.2	36.8	58.0	102.1	42.1
855	PA0825_at	85.3	37.0	65.8	59.6	60.4
856	PA0826_at	584.2	640.9	667.1	669.7	787.1
857	PA0827_at	46.5	73.7	167.2	150.9	194.1
858	PA0828_at	61.3	39.8	59.9	43.7	50.9
859	PA0829_at	8.2	20.6	41.1	33.7	22.3
860	PA0830_at	567.7	939.1	475.4	338.3	427.5
861	PA0831_oruR_at	416.2	199.3	528.5	559.7	629.2
862	PA0832_at	308.6	183.2	454.8	390.4	427.7
863	PA0833_at	2154.0	1542.2	1451.9	1448.1	1413.1
864	PA0834_at	43.0	56.5	19.3	31.9	38.6
865	PA0835_pta_at	251.8	416.9	428.1	419.6	454.3
866	PA0836_at	920.2	893.4	899.0	1138.8	1153.9
867	PA0837_slyD_at	301.9	189.7	631.9	525.6	521.2
868	PA0838_at	370.7	525.4	941.6	685.4	745.8
869	PA0839_at	141.6	132.9	488.4	144.2	115.5
870	PA0840_at	128.4	155.5	547.0	179.0	149.5
871	PA0841_at	279.3	252.5	543.9	412.3	419.0
872	PA0842_at	11.2	58.0	39.5	39.5	18.6

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

873	PA0843_plcR_at	65.3	44.8	39.3	59.8	47.5
874	PA0844_plcH_at	30.0	8.1	5.7	9.4	15.2
875	PA0845_at	5.3	4.0	17.1	27.7	27.6
876	PA0846_at	136.5	48.5	224.5	208.0	211.7
877	PA0847_at	12.3	14.3	68.6	87.5	81.1
878	PA0848_at	7428.6	2810.9	5838.5	5761.6	6438.4
879	PA0849_trxB2_at	3265.3	1838.0	4685.7	4996.8	4572.8
880	PA0850_at	15.2	35.1	43.4	60.6	55.8
881	PA0851_at	214.5	108.0	144.3	108.5	138.6
882	PA0852_cpbD_at	130.9	287.0	202.3	183.8	195.2
883	PA0853_at	287.1	228.6	297.3	303.7	259.7
884	PA0854_fumC2_at	413.1	232.2	320.2	259.1	300.4
885	PA0855_at	570.5	382.2	603.8	518.8	619.2
886	PA0856_at	1099.0	800.7	1588.5	1556.4	1565.8
887	PA0857_boIA_at	283.7	192.2	454.5	391.9	467.9
888	PA0858_at	139.9	149.7	217.0	156.8	168.0
889	PA0859_at	105.9	66.4	106.1	107.0	102.4
890	PA0860_at	115.3	124.6	79.4	98.5	97.7
891	PA0861_at	118.2	131.8	139.9	175.2	173.0
892	PA0862_at	2509.9	2891.2	2112.0	1850.3	2135.7
893	PA0863_at	4.3	26.0	35.5	28.8	37.6
894	PA0864_at	145.6	55.5	99.3	121.1	97.4
895	PA0865_hpd_at	3410.3	7348.6	4781.4	4267.8	5038.4
896	PA0866_aroP2_at	226.5	591.4	1587.1	1337.8	1362.4
897	PA0867_at	219.5	418.9	459.1	344.8	308.9
898	PA0868_at	218.5	107.4	128.0	125.9	86.7
899	PA0869_pbpG_at	726.8	938.0	803.3	932.9	984.1
900	PA0870_phhC_at	3792.2	3441.4	5139.8	4600.8	4938.1
901	PA0871_phhB_at	4947.8	7459.7	4697.2	4346.8	4231.3
902	PA0872_phhA_at	10879.3	9248.3	7787.3	8213.2	8744.4
903	PA0873_phhR_at	174.9	52.9	120.5	146.1	134.0
904	PA0874_at	81.5	64.9	69.8	49.6	57.8
905	PA0875_at	131.7	55.2	21.9	42.0	28.1
906	PA0876_at	646.5	682.0	664.6	571.1	659.7
907	PA0877_at	168.9	157.2	165.6	120.1	118.2
908	PA0878_at	89.5	32.3	42.9	58.9	46.4
909	PA0879_at	5.8	3.4	6.4	18.7	3.9
910	PA0880_at	11.1	32.0	23.9	43.8	13.5
911	PA0881_at	59.1	7.6	30.0	49.4	37.4
912	PA0882_at	89.2	8.2	23.7	45.4	20.0
913	PA0883_at	12.4	6.6	10.5	20.1	15.0
914	PA0884_at	8.9	28.8	22.2	37.5	31.2
915	PA0885_at	45.3	1.9	2.1	16.5	4.7
916	PA0886_at	12.6	21.1	10.8	17.0	14.7
917	PA0887_acsA_at	1868.9	3637.9	1687.7	1962.0	2140.9
918	PA0888_aotJ_at	113.7	338.5	336.5	425.3	410.5
919	PA0889_aotQ_at	56.6	56.3	41.1	61.4	53.4
920	PA0890_aotM_at	135.0	194.8	98.5	122.9	129.9
921	PA0891_at	237.2	357.8	128.2	105.7	98.1
922	PA0892_aotP_at	148.9	626.4	228.0	235.4	230.5
923	PA0893_argR_at	174.1	707.8	210.5	303.7	241.3
924	PA0894_at	113.9	69.7	69.0	62.1	88.4
925	PA0895_aruC_at	4527.8	3116.9	3527.0	4056.5	4086.3
926	PA0896_aruF_at	556.7	699.6	595.4	668.5	666.7
927	PA0897_aruG_at	500.8	649.2	461.2	482.6	430.4
928	PA0898_aruD_at	534.7	546.4	237.1	322.2	265.2
929	PA0899_aruB_at	577.5	1808.0	283.2	349.9	354.5
930	PA0900_at	2382.0	4562.3	2394.6	2072.6	2311.1
931	PA0901_aruE_at	571.5	845.4	463.4	496.2	535.4
932	PA0902_at	216.5	122.9	324.4	275.3	296.9
933	PA0903_alaS_at	296.3	268.2	448.5	368.5	396.1
934	PA0904_lysC_at	278.3	572.2	435.2	409.4	423.1
935	PA0905_csrA_at	760.2	962.5	408.4	483.8	522.2
936	PA0906_at	948.8	792.4	529.6	651.2	786.7
937	PA0907_at	90.0	101.3	122.3	154.9	162.7
938	PA0908_at	8.1	18.7	8.0	18.8	2.4
939	PA0909_i_at	6.3	33.6	27.4	39.3	35.9
940	PA0910_at	77.8	24.2	11.7	36.8	28.9
941	PA0911_at	47.9	36.2	33.1	40.2	54.2
942	PA0912_at	18.9	63.1	92.6	72.5	73.9
943	PA0913_mgtE_at	463.7	479.0	446.1	470.7	463.5
944	PA0914_at	7.8	34.2	38.2	27.1	14.8
945	PA0915_at	10.6	51.1	32.4	26.6	30.0

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

946	PA0916_at	92.7	98.6	79.9	75.5	45.2
947	PA0917_kup_at	104.7	108.5	102.6	127.0	91.6
948	PA0918_at	418.2	461.4	448.9	439.2	492.6
949	PA0919_at	195.1	206.6	134.4	125.7	77.9
950	PA0920_at	120.7	91.9	91.5	107.4	62.1
951	PA0921_at	217.0	272.6	225.5	134.7	153.6
952	PA0922_at	3850.4	2454.7	1879.9	2337.8	2029.5
953	PA0923_dinP_at	636.3	254.8	487.5	492.8	431.0
954	PA0924_at	80.1	99.9	86.6	79.1	95.1
955	PA0925_at	183.2	142.9	193.7	154.3	156.3
956	PA0926_at	159.1	179.9	201.5	206.8	220.4
957	PA0927_ldhA_at	98.4	135.2	48.9	49.8	41.4
958	PA0928_at	149.2	117.2	119.1	128.9	106.0
959	PA0929_at	174.4	55.3	367.2	244.0	359.5
960	PA0930_at	61.6	64.8	104.4	92.8	113.6
961	PA0931_at	92.1	38.2	50.8	56.4	31.8
962	PA0932_cysM_at	363.0	247.8	1012.8	849.2	809.1
963	PA0933_ygcA_at	233.7	163.7	288.8	263.9	240.2
964	PA0934_relA_at	326.7	527.9	437.0	463.9	403.1
965	PA0935_at	214.4	198.5	348.9	375.8	415.4
966	PA0936_at	268.4	229.0	313.9	272.1	301.3
967	PA0937_at	374.1	203.7	918.0	790.3	905.4
968	PA0938_at	411.0	366.3	559.5	504.1	399.7
969	PA0939_at	6.4	19.5	13.7	22.6	23.8
970	PA0940_at	97.9	60.9	63.0	104.7	100.3
971	PA0941_at	103.1	45.1	45.8	64.6	60.1
972	PA0942_at	334.9	373.7	217.8	315.4	309.6
973	PA0943_at	944.5	684.0	1233.1	1493.8	1573.7
974	PA0944_purN_at	75.6	182.8	137.9	143.8	153.7
975	PA0945_purM_at	60.6	100.5	206.8	128.7	159.1
976	PA0946_at	190.7	64.7	470.6	336.0	382.6
977	PA0947_at	123.9	76.1	331.2	301.9	263.6
978	PA0948_at	157.7	66.4	195.6	251.7	181.5
979	PA0949_wrbA_at	521.6	302.5	680.8	602.2	642.9
980	PA0950_at	555.7	318.2	774.2	809.0	849.7
981	PA0951_at	77.3	47.3	99.8	102.7	63.1
982	PA0952_at	68.5	66.7	65.5	69.6	57.0
983	PA0953_at	180.4	91.5	290.9	224.7	203.4
984	PA0954_at	17.7	57.4	127.5	110.2	74.9
985	PA0955_at	201.8	204.7	240.3	231.3	262.3
986	PA0956_proS_at	416.8	308.0	840.9	700.4	770.8
987	PA0957_at	9.2	57.9	61.8	57.6	50.2
988	PA0958 oprD_at	4896.0	5142.1	3781.9	3946.6	4107.6
989	PA0959_at	279.0	190.3	316.8	386.3	363.4
990	PA0960_at	211.2	205.2	298.9	358.4	410.1
991	PA0961_at	214.9	111.3	422.2	360.1	411.0
992	PA0962_at	22718.9	9958.8	9720.4	9359.4	10167.2
993	PA0963_aspS_at	559.0	489.6	760.2	786.2	675.2
994	PA0964_at	427.8	695.5	540.6	445.6	591.8
995	PA0965_ruvC_at	907.2	988.5	961.7	923.0	914.9
996	PA0966_ruvA_at	519.1	522.1	588.6	576.7	514.5
997	PA0967_ruvB_at	341.8	300.4	327.2	362.9	321.1
998	PA0968_at	424.2	417.3	559.6	546.8	470.2
999	PA0969_tolQ_at	779.5	701.7	858.7	813.5	761.9
1000	PA0970_tolR_at	793.4	543.0	589.0	533.3	524.1
1001	PA0971_tolA_at	589.6	883.4	642.4	568.8	600.7
1002	PA0972_tolB_at	1250.9	1996.1	1221.6	1166.7	1330.2
1003	PA0973 oprL_at	1694.6	3278.4	1914.2	1813.0	1867.5
1004	PA0974_at	846.8	1170.1	975.8	1004.4	960.9
1005	PA0975_at	95.3	98.8	89.3	108.2	92.2
1006	PA0976_at	100.9	182.4	93.5	117.7	110.0
1007	PA0977_at	15.2	14.6	9.0	27.2	2.2
1008	PA0978_s_at	101.8	93.2	110.6	132.3	135.1
1009	PA0979_s_at	123.9	176.9	91.0	101.0	116.5
1010	PA0980_at	37.6	47.3	35.9	53.9	72.4
1011	PA0981_at	59.1	29.8	26.2	33.6	46.0
1012	PA0982_at	245.4	139.9	158.4	215.1	219.4
1013	PA0983_at	203.9	368.4	167.1	244.9	292.8
1014	PA0984_at	15.8	5.5	31.8	30.7	27.4
1015	PA0985_at	74.3	43.3	7.4	27.0	3.9
1016	PA0986_i_at	3.4	0.9	4.4	4.4	7.9
1017	PA0987_at	40.6	10.8	12.2	31.0	14.9
1018	PA0988_at	122.9	61.3	153.7	145.5	142.0

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1019	PA0989_at	80.4	56.0	73.4	66.9	69.8
1020	PA0990_at	77.1	33.8	94.6	133.1	124.6
1021	PA0991_at	35.3	44.0	46.2	51.7	41.1
1022	PA0992_at	147.0	160.8	121.4	121.1	134.6
1023	PA0993_at	19.5	25.9	12.4	25.6	13.7
1024	PA0994_at	41.5	84.8	63.7	82.5	55.2
1025	PA0995_ogt_at	216.0	315.7	175.8	161.9	135.4
1026	PA0996_at	546.6	891.7	910.0	874.8	1021.4
1027	PA0997_at	741.6	2357.2	933.3	942.2	969.2
1028	PA0998_at	576.4	2309.9	555.3	614.2	683.4
1029	PA0999_fabH1_at	1199.8	3704.1	1275.5	1424.7	1477.0
1030	PA1000_at	504.3	2248.8	678.1	675.1	716.1
1031	PA1001_phnA_at	463.6	2164.6	1078.4	947.2	962.4
1032	PA1002_phnB_at	405.0	1486.9	661.0	639.7	638.5
1033	PA1003_at	238.7	259.7	260.2	247.7	244.1
1034	PA1004_nadA_at	702.0	651.1	538.3	533.6	513.6
1035	PA1005_at	400.1	275.8	625.9	597.9	550.7
1036	PA1006_at	67.1	32.0	140.8	116.8	145.6
1037	PA1007_at	60.2	25.5	29.1	51.4	23.8
1038	PA1008_bcp_at	412.0	260.7	818.4	609.5	797.4
1039	PA1009_at	758.5	265.8	910.5	940.7	1143.3
1040	PA1010_dapA_at	625.0	294.8	1094.0	946.1	1004.7
1041	PA1011_at	268.8	467.7	369.3	321.9	337.7
1042	PA1012_at	62.3	135.1	121.7	85.3	93.6
1043	PA1013_purC_at	200.8	414.3	289.0	283.8	301.3
1044	PA1014_at	56.4	68.0	182.5	177.3	159.1
1045	PA1015_at	209.8	229.6	201.4	210.6	208.5
1046	PA1016_at	106.5	60.2	99.5	64.0	69.4
1047	PA1017_pauA_at	42.3	54.2	18.7	37.5	20.8
1048	PA1018_at	53.4	29.3	21.9	20.8	10.1
1049	PA1019_mucK_at	27.4	20.9	5.1	17.7	13.1
1050	PA1020_at	70.4	75.3	93.4	101.3	98.4
1051	PA1021_at	93.2	51.2	69.5	74.0	62.8
1052	PA1022_at	127.3	167.3	137.9	123.5	168.5
1053	PA1023_at	33.1	92.2	61.4	63.3	57.3
1054	PA1024_at	59.1	116.6	73.0	99.5	41.7
1055	PA1025_at	8.1	15.7	23.2	31.3	25.8
1056	PA1026_at	55.7	100.2	67.6	71.8	89.0
1057	PA1027_at	69.0	80.1	124.5	159.2	151.4
1058	PA1028_at	104.3	61.3	70.0	62.5	65.4
1059	PA1029_at	725.7	342.8	473.3	545.2	528.8
1060	PA1030_at	276.6	239.7	253.1	259.1	263.6
1061	PA1031_at	313.2	145.0	236.5	211.0	207.0
1062	PA1032_at	115.8	82.8	69.3	72.3	66.3
1063	PA1033_at	234.2	183.6	315.5	316.1	367.3
1064	PA1034_at	73.6	117.7	116.0	136.8	155.8
1065	PA1035_at	917.6	1199.8	661.8	628.1	696.0
1066	PA1036_at	161.3	77.8	208.8	265.6	248.6
1067	PA1037_at	56.4	36.8	70.1	65.4	58.3
1068	PA1038_at	194.9	129.0	181.5	187.9	181.3
1069	PA1039_at	555.7	289.9	475.3	574.5	556.8
1070	PA1040_at	429.3	343.8	653.5	666.6	735.0
1071	PA1041_at	280.5	207.3	658.9	772.1	706.9
1072	PA1042_at	60.8	35.9	93.9	102.6	60.2
1073	PA1043_at	113.9	77.8	154.5	200.9	178.2
1074	PA1044_at	119.0	53.6	183.7	175.5	143.9
1075	PA1045_at	201.7	95.7	254.4	195.8	207.4
1076	PA1046_at	26.1	137.3	30.2	82.7	55.2
1077	PA1047_at	225.1	214.8	376.3	338.4	303.6
1078	PA1048_at	801.4	1099.4	538.1	583.5	586.0
1079	PA1049_pdxH_at	312.5	157.6	429.8	391.9	378.1
1080	PA1050_at	53.9	114.9	138.7	113.7	112.4
1081	PA1051_at	1145.1	371.9	123.8	117.6	139.8
1082	PA1052_at	174.5	48.4	35.7	44.5	55.9
1083	PA1053_at	3983.1	3033.9	4097.5	2960.5	3941.8
1084	PA1054_at	282.3	191.8	213.8	242.5	217.7
1085	PA1055_at	303.1	224.3	317.6	331.7	262.4
1086	PA1056_at	273.1	178.3	150.3	242.5	223.4
1087	PA1057_at	383.1	286.0	215.7	262.9	264.3
1088	PA1058_at	415.9	330.1	186.5	258.3	208.9
1089	PA1059_at	217.2	152.4	147.5	204.4	177.6
1090	PA1060_at	333.4	224.8	216.1	272.8	266.8
1091	PA1061_at	365.9	384.1	576.3	624.6	571.6

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1092	PA1062_at	203.9	334.6	296.3	351.2	328.0
1093	PA1063_at	169.2	244.3	164.2	203.8	154.0
1094	PA1064_at	181.5	117.2	429.7	372.5	403.0
1095	PA1065_at	59.0	78.2	128.8	103.9	120.0
1096	PA1066_at	44.6	34.7	38.8	38.0	26.8
1097	PA1067_at	42.0	35.5	56.0	43.9	59.0
1098	PA1068_at	183.5	134.0	208.9	223.5	176.9
1099	PA1069_at	129.3	186.1	134.5	129.6	169.8
1100	PA1070_braG_at	232.8	460.3	149.8	145.7	163.7
1101	PA1071_braF_at	631.7	1280.7	540.0	522.1	539.7
1102	PA1072_braE_at	212.6	230.9	197.6	235.4	198.4
1103	PA1073_braD_at	441.3	400.4	442.6	391.3	409.1
1104	PA1074_braC_at	2870.5	2656.1	2361.9	2502.7	2218.8
1105	PA1075_at	504.4	334.0	475.2	521.7	535.0
1106	PA1076_at	210.2	247.5	218.7	242.5	215.0
1107	PA1077_flgB_at	1204.4	1437.6	1302.1	1301.0	1618.5
1108	PA1078_flgC_at	1185.1	1917.0	1334.1	1381.4	1455.9
1109	PA1079_flgD_at	1117.2	1156.6	1373.9	1182.6	1197.3
1110	PA1080_flgE_at	2091.5	2832.8	2469.2	2452.1	2430.2
1111	PA1081_flgF_at	1061.6	1350.5	919.3	833.7	888.6
1112	PA1082_flgG_at	1754.9	2497.1	1891.3	1712.7	1906.2
1113	PA1083_flgH_at	584.0	857.7	741.9	789.8	809.9
1114	PA1084_flgI_at	443.5	526.2	686.4	604.0	490.0
1115	PA1085_flgJ_at	540.6	447.1	469.3	520.2	398.3
1116	PA1086_flgK_at	440.8	490.0	304.4	534.0	438.9
1117	PA1087_flgL_at	756.8	759.4	703.1	862.8	835.7
1118	PA1088_at	306.6	296.1	342.5	345.3	262.8
1119	PA1089_at	174.9	190.7	193.0	210.0	201.1
1120	PA1090_at	105.3	143.3	225.4	231.8	169.7
1121	PA1091_at	161.6	327.5	176.3	238.5	210.0
1122	PA1092_fliC_at	14464.1	10913.5	8173.9	7618.7	8538.1
1123	PA1093_at	1989.0	1835.8	2404.1	2058.5	2385.7
1124	PA1094_fliD_at	1841.1	1546.7	1939.6	2136.5	2147.1
1125	PA1095_at	3075.5	3896.6	3259.8	3555.8	4034.2
1126	PA1096_at	4874.1	5413.5	3059.9	3080.3	3551.7
1127	PA1097_fleQ_at	1493.0	1144.4	1293.4	1607.7	1665.2
1128	PA1098_fleS_at	315.4	251.1	713.1	679.7	711.8
1129	PA1099_fleR_at	311.9	210.9	490.2	513.2	503.9
1130	PA1100_fliE_at	477.6	297.7	776.6	802.0	788.8
1131	PA1101_fliF_at	390.6	304.6	770.0	756.9	711.4
1132	PA1102_fliG_at	1134.1	1087.2	1412.9	1358.0	1361.4
1133	PA1103_at	478.3	761.0	615.7	497.1	422.6
1134	PA1104_fliI_at	151.9	135.9	174.6	200.4	193.7
1135	PA1105_fliJ_at	105.5	64.2	81.9	114.5	133.7
1136	PA1106_at	206.6	161.1	205.6	137.7	192.7
1137	PA1107_at	12.4	25.1	8.3	40.8	32.6
1138	PA1108_at	32.5	8.0	9.8	11.0	8.8
1139	PA1109_at	8.3	8.1	4.1	3.6	18.4
1140	PA1110_at	31.7	65.2	90.0	108.6	87.9
1141	PA1111_at	107.6	55.4	67.0	85.1	78.5
1142	PA1112_at	60.8	88.6	160.9	186.3	187.7
1143	PA1113_at	46.2	20.8	22.8	28.3	4.1
1144	PA1114_at	111.0	151.8	134.6	192.1	131.3
1145	PA1115_at	432.8	332.4	292.9	362.6	279.3
1146	PA1116_at	41.8	146.7	75.0	68.5	66.2
1147	PA1117_at	98.5	67.1	125.1	113.0	126.0
1148	PA1118_at	46.1	109.3	80.9	105.8	119.9
1149	PA1119_at	244.3	381.2	262.1	289.6	333.0
1150	PA1120_at	53.7	39.2	73.4	70.5	74.7
1151	PA1121_at	180.5	64.4	197.9	123.2	140.3
1152	PA1122_at	667.1	797.2	711.6	766.8	767.3
1153	PA1123_at	14.6	36.1	64.9	44.8	53.5
1154	PA1124_dgt_at	282.6	144.8	276.0	274.4	266.5
1155	PA1125_at	151.2	144.2	141.2	163.5	194.6
1156	PA1126_at	57.7	72.0	139.9	125.0	115.3
1157	PA1127_at	120.4	87.6	152.2	153.6	151.4
1158	PA1128_at	88.4	67.7	134.1	142.8	127.4
1159	PA1129_at	111.1	20.1	25.5	34.8	36.2
1160	PA1130_at	100.4	79.1	52.5	92.7	105.9
1161	PA1131_at	121.8	36.0	57.7	73.6	64.4
1162	PA1132_at	147.4	137.9	204.0	226.3	199.2
1163	PA1133_at	63.4	31.4	34.0	50.2	49.5
1164	PA1134_at	136.9	66.4	76.3	53.4	59.1

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1165	PA1135_at	220.8	154.8	230.5	254.7	253.5
1166	PA1136_at	103.0	36.2	78.2	78.6	92.6
1167	PA1137_at	97.5	63.0	62.9	67.3	73.0
1168	PA1138_at	155.6	119.3	140.1	137.0	152.5
1169	PA1139_at	133.4	118.0	126.7	132.5	132.3
1170	PA1140_at	179.1	147.5	169.5	123.5	130.3
1171	PA1141_at	95.6	108.3	133.1	73.3	139.2
1172	PA1142_at	55.5	42.4	164.2	72.8	119.9
1173	PA1143_at	73.1	28.9	44.9	39.3	24.3
1174	PA1144_at	55.4	15.3	18.6	33.0	8.4
1175	PA1145_at	98.2	25.6	53.6	44.7	62.5
1176	PA1146_at	109.8	19.4	30.3	37.0	43.9
1177	PA1147_at	100.7	28.7	76.5	60.5	38.2
1178	PA1148_toxA_at	31.6	65.5	31.4	37.1	46.6
1179	PA1149_at	204.4	158.3	193.2	234.5	226.9
1180	PA1150_pys2_at	252.3	196.5	187.9	182.0	195.6
1181	PA1151_imm2_at	307.8	519.6	284.1	392.9	435.8
1182	PA1152_at	61.2	33.3	44.4	41.3	48.1
1183	PA1153_at	84.3	64.0	101.7	99.8	103.0
1184	PA1154_at	74.4	26.3	29.6	38.0	14.2
1185	PA1155_nrdB_at	493.6	1702.9	242.8	302.2	331.7
1186	PA1156_nrdA_at	279.0	283.0	321.1	253.4	270.1
1187	PA1157_at	99.7	77.2	165.8	125.9	113.6
1188	PA1158_at	40.6	31.7	40.3	27.0	27.9
1189	PA1159_at	949.1	1632.4	1369.0	1479.8	1549.9
1190	PA1160_at	738.6	624.8	491.0	641.9	627.7
1191	PA1161_rrmA_at	101.3	84.1	75.1	58.8	57.3
1192	PA1162_dapE_at	266.0	160.6	244.7	220.9	219.8
1193	PA1163_at	68.2	42.1	37.2	44.5	32.3
1194	PA1164_at	299.3	226.9	331.4	261.2	327.5
1195	PA1165_at	82.4	150.0	200.0	185.7	161.1
1196	PA1166_at	91.7	42.4	68.6	71.5	100.2
1197	PA1167_at	223.2	168.3	245.7	220.8	194.2
1198	PA1168_at	51.7	107.2	134.1	139.1	178.4
1199	PA1169_at	36.1	24.7	9.8	40.5	40.9
1200	PA1170_at	86.9	21.3	46.8	56.4	49.6
1201	PA1171_at	216.0	116.9	257.1	210.8	175.6
1202	PA1172_napC_at	67.1	56.8	30.0	53.6	40.5
1203	PA1173_napB_at	12.0	49.3	36.5	41.6	34.4
1204	PA1174_napA_at	38.0	63.2	155.5	148.5	97.7
1205	PA1175_napD_at	154.0	86.7	224.0	266.6	224.3
1206	PA1176_napF_at	124.3	50.9	202.9	231.3	242.8
1207	PA1177_napE_at	46.7	39.7	75.5	106.0	109.2
1208	PA1178_oprH_at	1321.8	1954.7	2224.5	556.4	1325.6
1209	PA1179_phoP_at	212.7	332.4	397.5	233.4	357.4
1210	PA1180_phoQ_at	140.7	106.4	193.0	110.3	133.0
1211	PA1181_at	58.8	70.9	81.5	86.4	80.2
1212	PA1182_at	57.7	62.8	117.6	124.7	103.8
1213	PA1183_dctA_at	25.8	7.6	15.5	40.5	44.8
1214	PA1184_at	13.4	46.5	83.6	63.3	64.0
1215	PA1185_at	9.5	26.3	38.0	36.8	31.4
1216	PA1186_at	26.2	10.2	35.8	37.7	44.5
1217	PA1187_at	121.5	57.7	94.6	57.7	74.6
1218	PA1188_at	84.7	48.5	96.0	56.9	69.3
1219	PA1189_at	76.0	47.7	93.0	83.5	79.5
1220	PA1190_at	133.1	386.5	489.5	615.7	685.0
1221	PA1191_at	146.0	116.9	96.6	103.4	86.1
1222	PA1192_at	180.4	109.7	298.3	295.3	268.5
1223	PA1193_at	113.5	127.3	168.0	134.6	161.6
1224	PA1194_at	10.5	14.6	30.8	24.5	29.2
1225	PA1195_at	67.4	53.5	21.0	46.3	42.1
1226	PA1196_at	4.6	36.3	7.7	37.2	44.8
1227	PA1197_at	95.1	72.8	91.4	92.0	101.8
1228	PA1198_at	126.7	127.6	247.4	263.4	293.3
1229	PA1199_at	156.9	254.5	144.6	130.1	100.0
1230	PA1200_at	84.4	111.0	40.1	52.7	48.4
1231	PA1201_at	119.6	130.5	218.9	205.0	224.4
1232	PA1202_at	95.8	196.0	143.8	142.2	185.3
1233	PA1203_at	221.5	221.4	279.5	249.1	277.7
1234	PA1204_at	100.2	22.3	83.8	92.0	93.6
1235	PA1205_at	82.4	79.0	126.7	115.7	120.6
1236	PA1206_at	196.6	139.2	302.7	280.9	349.2
1237	PA1207_kefB_at	102.1	30.2	49.7	46.3	51.4

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1238	PA1208_at	49.6	51.0	70.8	59.9	37.2
1239	PA1209_at	295.9	308.5	182.9	274.0	290.5
1240	PA1210_at	110.9	740.4	235.1	202.1	217.0
1241	PA1211_at	9.2	20.0	24.5	50.2	42.3
1242	PA1212_at	39.6	17.6	22.5	31.6	19.9
1243	PA1213_at	36.9	38.9	9.3	36.4	44.3
1244	PA1214_at	50.3	46.9	46.8	45.7	24.5
1245	PA1215_at	17.2	18.4	5.4	23.1	8.4
1246	PA1216_at	82.9	87.7	60.1	47.9	56.1
1247	PA1217_at	50.8	41.9	59.9	51.5	60.3
1248	PA1218_at	88.8	56.8	6.1	36.6	24.1
1249	PA1219_at	46.9	38.3	55.0	54.1	31.6
1250	PA1220_at	6.7	3.1	39.8	25.1	25.7
1251	PA1221_at	37.5	39.8	89.7	69.2	59.1
1252	PA1222_at	133.3	106.8	155.8	138.7	142.8
1253	PA1223_at	106.8	77.6	132.1	118.2	150.5
1254	PA1224_at	136.5	61.5	87.1	133.2	117.0
1255	PA1225_at	48.4	51.9	19.9	52.3	32.1
1256	PA1226_at	239.7	73.0	180.2	209.1	176.3
1257	PA1227_at	45.9	39.2	84.8	86.9	69.4
1258	PA1228_at	118.3	143.4	114.5	149.3	117.8
1259	PA1229_at	252.7	194.0	296.8	324.1	305.2
1260	PA1230_at	123.5	82.4	161.1	123.6	95.3
1261	PA1231_at	83.6	20.9	101.4	82.2	37.9
1262	PA1232_at	50.7	32.8	29.7	54.0	31.6
1263	PA1233_at	25.5	32.9	66.3	85.6	46.4
1264	PA1234_at	23.4	52.2	58.0	76.7	86.3
1265	PA1235_at	59.7	59.5	142.7	137.2	131.7
1266	PA1236_at	24.9	5.5	11.1	14.5	20.6
1267	PA1237_at	106.5	56.8	65.7	69.7	47.8
1268	PA1238_at	20.8	7.4	4.0	9.8	19.3
1269	PA1239_at	8.6	3.5	3.8	35.7	26.3
1270	PA1240_at	7.9	3.1	38.2	39.4	32.8
1271	PA1241_at	120.6	37.2	100.0	138.1	127.6
1272	PA1242_at	13.9	19.0	17.4	24.6	17.7
1273	PA1243_at	137.1	88.5	75.4	79.3	79.3
1274	PA1244_at	945.0	1389.2	885.1	936.0	1073.9
1275	PA1245_at	453.8	150.6	472.9	437.3	611.7
1276	PA1246_aprD_at	105.9	47.9	100.8	91.2	127.6
1277	PA1247_aprE_at	220.2	139.4	117.5	131.0	146.9
1278	PA1248_aprF_at	126.3	72.4	44.9	70.2	65.2
1279	PA1249_aprA_at	122.5	81.6	89.5	96.7	96.1
1280	PA1250_aprI_at	105.4	137.3	248.7	236.3	223.5
1281	PA1251_at	62.0	32.1	10.8	23.8	19.2
1282	PA1252_at	80.6	71.9	87.9	87.8	95.8
1283	PA1253_at	23.1	28.3	45.5	55.0	33.3
1284	PA1254_at	79.6	46.4	16.2	32.0	22.0
1285	PA1255_at	108.1	45.7	46.3	49.6	44.6
1286	PA1256_at	69.2	40.1	67.3	73.2	55.5
1287	PA1257_at	10.1	30.1	6.9	9.3	19.7
1288	PA1258_at	13.1	30.7	29.5	39.3	27.9
1289	PA1259_at	16.0	7.2	33.2	42.2	36.6
1290	PA1260_at	43.0	100.7	64.5	74.1	85.5
1291	PA1261_at	79.8	20.9	92.2	81.1	93.8
1292	PA1262_at	23.1	5.0	40.4	46.5	3.9
1293	PA1263_at	169.7	96.2	136.5	171.0	143.3
1294	PA1264_at	70.9	58.8	66.8	58.7	68.7
1295	PA1265_at	49.7	49.9	62.5	63.9	56.0
1296	PA1266_at	51.8	20.2	16.5	33.3	28.1
1297	PA1267_at	12.3	9.4	12.7	45.1	8.5
1298	PA1268_at	48.1	44.1	75.1	81.2	60.3
1299	PA1269_at	970.9	755.7	736.1	655.9	640.0
1300	PA1270_at	12.0	46.6	44.0	14.5	29.0
1301	PA1271_at	78.4	121.0	92.6	83.9	60.7
1302	PA1272_cob0_at	201.5	354.8	230.5	261.1	222.6
1303	PA1273_cobB_at	44.1	96.0	51.5	35.7	69.5
1304	PA1274_at	86.1	218.6	101.0	63.3	81.2
1305	PA1275_cobD_at	6.4	163.9	63.6	51.2	77.0
1306	PA1276_cobC_at	103.4	262.7	95.7	108.0	112.9
1307	PA1277_cobQ_at	98.5	287.0	169.1	134.0	112.2
1308	PA1278_cobP_at	215.3	606.1	305.3	296.3	335.2
1309	PA1279_cobU_at	117.7	291.2	234.1	276.8	201.4
1310	PA1280_at	173.1	362.5	246.6	230.3	273.8

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1311	PA1281_cobV_at	100.0	209.4	153.0	199.9	118.6
1312	PA1282_at	5.9	35.1	19.0	27.7	25.8
1313	PA1283_at	195.2	159.0	167.3	214.2	181.8
1314	PA1284_at	86.3	9.4	35.8	29.9	25.0
1315	PA1285_at	145.3	101.1	232.2	301.6	294.5
1316	PA1286_at	60.8	4.4	55.3	49.1	32.2
1317	PA1287_at	151.5	134.6	189.5	193.2	214.2
1318	PA1288_at	1977.6	5217.3	2014.8	1746.4	1730.7
1319	PA1289_at	179.0	401.3	582.9	632.1	635.9
1320	PA1290_at	243.3	316.4	260.3	191.9	190.9
1321	PA1291_at	84.3	67.1	81.6	92.4	103.6
1322	PA1292_at	301.3	247.7	390.9	320.6	438.7
1323	PA1293_at	100.8	95.7	251.5	189.1	265.4
1324	PA1294_rnd_at	211.3	163.8	263.4	229.1	255.8
1325	PA1295_at	100.8	40.9	91.6	72.6	90.4
1326	PA1296_at	510.4	729.5	475.6	479.5	543.0
1327	PA1297_at	105.7	81.1	73.5	83.8	81.6
1328	PA1298_i_at	55.2	35.2	36.9	46.7	34.7
1329	PA1299_at	47.0	60.6	47.6	45.6	39.9
1330	PA1300_at	719.0	397.6	601.5	575.2	525.4
1331	PA1301_at	433.8	245.2	409.6	473.2	448.7
1332	PA1302_at	174.7	112.7	136.5	114.7	93.0
1333	PA1303_at	3.5	28.3	9.4	6.4	8.3
1334	PA1304_at	91.4	37.8	80.3	79.6	56.5
1335	PA1305_at	282.4	232.7	502.4	462.1	478.5
1336	PA1306_at	473.4	530.4	388.0	397.2	440.8
1337	PA1307_at	680.2	611.0	663.5	621.2	602.4
1338	PA1308_at	332.2	361.1	395.9	409.4	390.4
1339	PA1309_at	123.7	41.0	114.2	101.1	75.3
1340	PA1310_phnW_at	137.1	95.7	96.8	115.4	101.0
1341	PA1311_phnX_at	51.5	47.5	23.5	70.5	57.4
1342	PA1312_at	38.0	26.1	52.2	54.2	42.3
1343	PA1313_at	8.8	5.2	26.8	32.8	4.0
1344	PA1314_at	75.7	62.9	103.7	95.2	84.0
1345	PA1315_at	55.7	46.8	117.2	140.0	102.7
1346	PA1316_at	113.2	88.4	81.4	94.9	69.7
1347	PA1317_cyoA_at	198.2	147.1	79.0	81.9	73.7
1348	PA1318_cyoB_at	88.5	144.1	81.9	33.5	45.5
1349	PA1319_cyoC_at	79.4	54.9	24.7	31.7	36.1
1350	PA1320_cyoD_at	60.2	44.7	22.5	29.6	22.0
1351	PA1321_cyoE_at	91.5	44.9	35.5	58.5	42.2
1352	PA1322_at	76.1	54.4	33.0	59.2	37.2
1353	PA1323_at	455.0	326.3	203.7	303.7	329.8
1354	PA1324_at	411.9	347.9	265.7	301.8	289.0
1355	PA1325_at	8.4	11.4	15.9	42.3	45.4
1356	PA1326_ilvA2_at	89.1	69.1	100.0	87.7	78.7
1357	PA1327_at	16.9	67.0	62.1	63.8	81.2
1358	PA1328_at	86.3	67.5	50.8	70.3	83.4
1359	PA1329_at	45.6	41.7	41.5	37.8	36.3
1360	PA1330_at	69.9	84.7	56.7	95.0	70.6
1361	PA1331_at	205.2	85.3	395.9	412.9	324.8
1362	PA1332_at	17.7	44.6	30.4	56.2	23.4
1363	PA1333_r_at	522.5	658.8	368.7	349.5	352.3
1364	PA1334_at	65.9	17.6	33.1	39.7	23.1
1365	PA1335_at	93.0	257.1	37.9	53.6	53.5
1366	PA1336_at	172.8	620.2	146.7	110.0	118.8
1367	PA1337_ansB_at	371.5	2113.1	157.0	192.0	155.8
1368	PA1338_ggt_at	175.3	1110.5	94.8	125.6	96.5
1369	PA1339_at	419.7	1555.1	227.9	240.2	240.2
1370	PA1340_at	142.2	471.4	165.2	141.1	106.2
1371	PA1341_at	190.8	480.2	226.4	192.1	192.6
1372	PA1342_at	1697.5	4387.9	1777.3	2047.8	2182.8
1373	PA1343_at	14.1	102.5	215.9	86.1	93.5
1374	PA1344_at	11.2	9.2	119.6	49.7	98.5
1375	PA1345_at	47.2	34.1	21.2	35.3	25.1
1376	PA1346_at	35.4	4.0	15.3	35.2	30.5
1377	PA1347_at	65.5	51.1	55.1	64.6	28.7
1378	PA1348_at	181.3	327.4	203.0	321.5	290.0
1379	PA1349_at	49.4	46.9	54.6	44.1	39.6
1380	PA1350_at	75.4	71.8	57.3	59.3	63.9
1381	PA1351_at	61.7	13.5	26.6	41.2	15.7
1382	PA1352_at	110.9	20.4	39.4	62.3	39.0
1383	PA1353_at	13.9	36.9	40.2	41.2	29.6

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1384	PA1354_at	100.1	51.7	56.5	86.1	105.9
1385	PA1355_at	4.4	2.2	31.4	25.4	20.5
1386	PA1356_at	52.1	13.9	34.7	62.4	35.5
1387	PA1357_at	58.2	39.2	107.7	72.5	73.1
1388	PA1358_at	101.3	54.6	94.7	95.9	82.1
1389	PA1359_at	150.7	88.3	104.5	132.0	128.3
1390	PA1360_at	75.2	25.2	24.6	41.7	53.7
1391	PA1361_at	89.9	26.8	40.6	31.9	38.9
1392	PA1362_i_at	261.9	276.0	149.6	160.8	128.5
1393	PA1363_at	187.3	90.9	115.3	112.9	106.6
1394	PA1364_at	103.9	44.6	67.3	52.5	39.5
1395	PA1365_at	103.8	31.5	103.9	92.2	89.1
1396	PA1366_at	384.4	386.6	426.4	412.4	406.7
1397	PA1367_at	26.6	31.3	43.0	61.1	49.8
1398	PA1368_at	125.2	97.4	78.1	79.9	57.4
1399	PA1369_at	46.8	43.6	73.2	50.0	58.4
1400	PA1370_at	105.0	42.0	131.2	130.8	117.7
1401	PA1371_at	18.3	82.8	39.4	48.8	49.8
1402	PA1372_at	146.3	167.3	121.1	111.5	94.7
1403	PA1373_fabF2_at	191.7	119.1	92.3	119.7	127.2
1404	PA1374_at	89.8	43.2	85.4	75.3	64.4
1405	PA1375_pdxB_at	125.4	154.3	218.6	211.0	195.6
1406	PA1376_aceK_at	653.1	555.5	981.1	870.9	1026.3
1407	PA1377_at	483.1	322.4	699.5	628.6	667.0
1408	PA1378_at	130.9	86.9	124.8	173.6	139.5
1409	PA1379_at	16.8	29.4	35.7	46.6	28.2
1410	PA1380_at	19.6	26.6	51.5	63.2	56.3
1411	PA1381_at	104.5	16.3	39.2	22.9	23.6
1412	PA1382_at	267.5	312.3	145.9	159.6	136.0
1413	PA1383_at	111.2	107.0	116.4	125.9	116.8
1414	PA1384_galE_at	58.6	19.8	26.1	33.1	20.0
1415	PA1385_at	50.6	26.6	44.8	22.0	40.3
1416	PA1386_at	113.9	46.0	43.2	53.2	46.3
1417	PA1387_at	98.6	83.8	65.4	92.2	91.8
1418	PA1388_at	50.8	48.2	63.2	62.1	63.4
1419	PA1389_at	43.8	37.6	48.2	54.0	47.2
1420	PA1390_at	17.2	32.9	48.6	55.3	30.8
1421	PA1391_at	50.8	29.8	18.8	33.1	37.4
1422	PA1392_at	57.3	40.2	42.8	39.2	36.4
1423	PA1393_cysC_at	10.3	43.6	56.7	48.1	67.9
1424	PA1394_at	33.5	32.9	58.3	82.9	92.3
1425	PA1395_at	63.2	22.3	63.7	67.0	56.9
1426	PA1396_at	85.5	71.2	104.9	74.8	70.9
1427	PA1397_at	84.9	56.8	81.7	103.8	97.3
1428	PA1398_at	7.8	33.7	85.2	103.3	85.9
1429	PA1399_at	85.3	70.0	120.4	88.1	49.6
1430	PA1400_at	36.9	40.2	25.2	47.4	27.5
1431	PA1401_at	204.4	132.8	172.5	167.4	178.6
1432	PA1402_at	114.8	84.5	66.6	95.0	100.3
1433	PA1403_at	22.5	14.8	71.4	83.8	68.1
1434	PA1404_at	115.8	133.3	82.3	66.2	80.6
1435	PA1405_at	234.7	161.7	145.1	141.0	160.9
1436	PA1406_at	141.0	89.0	64.9	81.8	87.1
1437	PA1407_at	71.3	56.9	57.0	52.4	64.2
1438	PA1408_at	170.6	95.2	93.6	91.3	97.9
1439	PA1409_aphA_at	89.8	71.4	95.8	90.2	108.8
1440	PA1410_at	76.2	87.6	141.3	102.8	89.7
1441	PA1411_at	91.8	59.3	130.9	97.3	105.6
1442	PA1412_at	48.8	16.0	33.4	28.2	24.0
1443	PA1413_at	151.6	125.3	150.5	198.4	163.2
1444	PA1414_at	658.5	1401.8	636.7	596.0	748.9
1445	PA1415_at	51.0	69.2	94.7	76.5	45.7
1446	PA1416_at	64.9	30.7	20.8	38.0	20.3
1447	PA1417_at	415.0	98.0	91.4	67.4	73.3
1448	PA1418_at	984.0	164.0	84.8	84.0	47.7
1449	PA1419_at	625.5	104.3	9.2	23.0	23.3
1450	PA1420_at	1508.0	396.2	79.5	67.7	57.5
1451	PA1421_speB2_at	2082.3	551.1	80.2	84.6	75.9
1452	PA1422_at	77.5	50.5	52.0	72.9	46.3
1453	PA1423_at	262.9	197.7	290.0	244.0	252.6
1454	PA1424_at	117.1	31.9	67.9	91.5	85.9
1455	PA1425_at	127.6	60.5	113.6	140.6	95.2
1456	PA1426_at	12.1	8.7	22.2	54.7	44.7

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1457	PA1427_at	29.3	31.2	32.8	57.0	34.7
1458	PA1428_at	10.4	2.1	4.3	5.4	5.5
1459	PA1429_at	65.4	91.9	66.9	64.3	54.9
1460	PA1430_lasR_at	566.8	425.4	711.1	682.0	646.5
1461	PA1431_rsaL_at	5684.2	3861.0	4035.5	4970.0	5482.0
1462	PA1432_lasI_at	998.3	1237.5	784.2	787.0	794.8
1463	PA1433_at	43.6	85.7	95.3	65.2	78.1
1464	PA1434_at	28.0	44.2	111.9	77.4	107.8
1465	PA1435_at	91.4	52.1	58.1	75.5	34.7
1466	PA1436_at	67.6	41.9	28.7	23.3	38.4
1467	PA1437_at	181.7	177.8	167.9	131.3	169.3
1468	PA1438_at	85.4	92.6	95.9	104.5	115.9
1469	PA1439_at	150.6	83.0	140.7	177.5	146.5
1470	PA1440_at	1613.0	975.2	2312.0	2167.1	2209.0
1471	PA1441_at	828.5	932.3	1401.5	1096.4	1259.0
1472	PA1442_at	668.2	607.0	891.3	903.5	1008.1
1473	PA1443_fliM_at	477.8	607.2	704.2	779.0	754.1
1474	PA1444_fliN_at	188.4	237.3	239.4	267.3	245.9
1475	PA1445_fliO_at	96.6	214.4	139.6	154.4	154.9
1476	PA1446_fliP_at	227.9	178.6	126.0	146.7	183.5
1477	PA1447_fliQ_at	131.1	215.3	159.5	183.1	111.8
1478	PA1448_fliR_at	105.5	84.3	75.9	60.7	38.5
1479	PA1449_flhB_at	132.5	59.8	51.9	48.5	35.5
1480	PA1450_at	55.9	30.8	114.6	106.8	105.8
1481	PA1451_at	61.1	109.4	107.0	87.5	85.1
1482	PA1452_flhA_at	152.4	151.8	209.4	235.9	211.0
1483	PA1453_flhF_at	872.0	715.4	923.9	763.1	729.5
1484	PA1454_at	1793.5	1487.8	1638.1	1762.9	1719.8
1485	PA1455_fliA_at	1257.0	1308.7	1234.3	1241.6	1232.8
1486	PA1456_cheY_at	1035.3	767.5	1185.1	1111.1	1118.2
1487	PA1457_cheZ_at	533.6	501.8	883.7	906.0	760.3
1488	PA1458_at	355.2	347.7	597.9	550.3	529.8
1489	PA1459_at	437.3	696.0	624.1	648.4	579.1
1490	PA1460_at	197.9	289.0	159.1	154.0	135.5
1491	PA1461_at	117.7	162.0	95.9	114.3	93.6
1492	PA1462_at	522.2	646.4	641.4	658.5	751.0
1493	PA1463_at	953.8	715.4	1144.8	1276.8	1193.3
1494	PA1464_at	2668.2	3769.8	2766.8	2520.0	2533.5
1495	PA1465_at	571.4	706.9	487.3	536.5	467.9
1496	PA1466_at	715.9	528.3	588.2	614.5	598.0
1497	PA1467_at	180.2	111.6	162.1	139.0	153.8
1498	PA1468_at	54.9	30.4	67.4	67.6	46.1
1499	PA1469_at	113.8	49.5	138.8	133.9	116.1
1500	PA1470_at	102.2	70.3	100.6	111.2	98.5
1501	PA1471_at	132.5	142.5	156.5	194.8	176.1
1502	PA1472_at	126.0	43.8	74.1	99.5	90.8
1503	PA1473_at	272.0	234.3	357.4	312.8	272.5
1504	PA1474_at	578.0	486.5	613.3	716.7	745.4
1505	PA1475_ccmA_at	65.8	70.4	147.6	108.5	111.7
1506	PA1476_ccmB_at	5.7	37.5	49.2	53.8	39.1
1507	PA1477_ccmC_at	99.7	72.6	117.7	75.7	81.8
1508	PA1478_at	94.7	141.8	114.1	134.6	123.3
1509	PA1479_ccmE_at	248.5	494.9	266.7	230.7	234.6
1510	PA1480_ccmF_at	107.1	254.3	92.6	86.9	114.2
1511	PA1481_ccmG_at	65.2	290.0	69.9	90.8	66.0
1512	PA1482_ccmH_at	311.8	754.6	241.1	251.3	262.5
1513	PA1483_cycH_at	198.9	404.5	140.8	196.2	189.2
1514	PA1484_at	186.6	126.7	172.3	205.9	227.8
1515	PA1485_at	16.6	25.4	54.6	63.5	56.8
1516	PA1486_at	13.0	60.1	60.9	48.0	36.3
1517	PA1487_at	52.8	78.3	59.0	66.1	63.1
1518	PA1488_at	63.6	35.1	40.3	61.2	47.5
1519	PA1489_at	50.0	38.6	58.6	58.0	49.0
1520	PA1490_at	90.4	46.6	112.6	106.5	72.5
1521	PA1491_at	8.8	64.7	9.2	45.5	36.3
1522	PA1492_at	146.6	77.4	67.4	72.6	62.9
1523	PA1493_cysP_at	13931.0	1952.3	2025.2	1583.1	2689.9
1524	PA1494_at	330.1	289.1	455.7	435.8	391.6
1525	PA1495_at	112.4	93.9	111.9	94.9	69.0
1526	PA1496_at	5.6	18.2	27.3	39.8	26.3
1527	PA1497_at	42.2	27.3	27.5	33.6	15.5
1528	PA1498_pykF_at	35.3	23.7	26.9	10.2	2.8
1529	PA1499_at	95.5	40.2	35.6	59.6	42.4

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1530	PA1500_at	12.9	33.1	21.2	26.0	22.3
1531	PA1501_at	25.2	34.0	25.3	23.8	8.9
1532	PA1502_gcl_at	85.9	30.1	44.0	39.5	35.4
1533	PA1503_at	40.7	50.5	41.0	48.2	46.1
1534	PA1504_at	349.4	151.0	518.9	471.8	538.2
1535	PA1505_moaA2_at	1245.4	993.0	1105.1	1107.0	1157.6
1536	PA1506_at	210.8	109.8	151.7	168.8	124.0
1537	PA1507_at	36.5	35.3	27.0	38.8	35.1
1538	PA1508_at	100.1	104.8	137.0	160.4	181.5
1539	PA1509_at	145.4	224.7	291.4	286.8	321.0
1540	PA1510_at	20.6	53.3	43.5	29.2	41.5
1541	PA1511_at	112.1	94.9	109.9	89.9	98.3
1542	PA1513_at	251.9	187.5	141.5	123.3	177.5
1543	PA1514_at	241.7	174.6	131.1	153.7	153.5
1544	PA1515_alc_at	413.7	312.6	166.1	159.9	180.3
1545	PA1516_at	326.5	304.0	145.7	200.4	211.4
1546	PA1517_at	892.4	871.7	553.6	620.6	709.7
1547	PA1518_at	149.2	151.3	146.7	149.4	161.5
1548	PA1519_at	7.0	4.3	14.8	19.3	28.5
1549	PA1520_at	443.9	376.7	547.7	477.3	495.1
1550	PA1521_at	150.2	55.7	83.5	77.0	71.0
1551	PA1522_at	177.6	63.1	117.2	127.4	114.1
1552	PA1523_xdhB_at	167.8	116.9	108.3	116.1	130.1
1553	PA1524_xdhA_at	325.1	166.4	181.9	206.7	212.7
1554	PA1525_at	208.8	136.4	202.8	169.1	153.8
1555	PA1526_at	441.0	367.3	496.4	469.6	477.5
1556	PA1527_at	656.1	572.5	660.8	525.8	523.9
1557	PA1528_zipA_at	2045.4	2211.2	2032.2	1789.4	2160.1
1558	PA1529_lig_at	136.8	119.7	158.9	160.4	140.7
1559	PA1530_at	53.7	199.1	100.5	88.0	91.6
1560	PA1531_at	33.3	42.3	44.7	33.6	64.8
1561	PA1532_dnaX_at	321.5	236.7	751.4	838.9	859.4
1562	PA1533_at	1007.3	1466.8	1035.1	807.9	847.5
1563	PA1534_recR_at	83.6	80.7	63.4	98.2	107.9
1564	PA1535_at	128.7	167.2	127.8	145.3	165.6
1565	PA1536_at	48.5	8.3	61.3	55.1	71.0
1566	PA1537_at	21.3	29.5	41.1	97.8	51.5
1567	PA1538_at	189.2	100.0	160.7	125.0	132.0
1568	PA1539_at	252.9	357.4	242.8	271.1	196.7
1569	PA1540_at	1130.6	586.2	780.0	1139.5	1121.6
1570	PA1541_at	2417.5	1205.8	1836.5	1835.4	1695.7
1571	PA1542_at	348.4	614.1	284.0	186.8	186.4
1572	PA1543_apt_at	220.2	84.2	269.4	262.7	293.4
1573	PA1544_anr_at	846.6	403.9	1205.7	1283.9	1387.5
1574	PA1545_at	1089.6	1089.4	1152.0	1652.9	1699.0
1575	PA1546_hemN_at	56.6	308.8	96.8	82.5	70.8
1576	PA1547_at	169.1	97.6	128.7	106.1	112.7
1577	PA1548_at	164.3	168.0	122.4	113.8	112.8
1578	PA1549_at	111.5	114.3	118.2	143.5	126.2
1579	PA1550_at	376.0	372.4	230.8	299.0	314.4
1580	PA1551_at	152.9	150.8	157.1	219.2	159.1
1581	PA1552_at	358.5	1269.9	242.2	279.0	339.9
1582	PA1553_at	248.9	857.9	389.6	411.5	401.7
1583	PA1554_at	310.4	851.7	433.7	481.8	471.3
1584	PA1555_at	146.8	836.9	252.0	304.2	257.2
1585	PA1556_at	76.0	674.6	201.4	192.8	193.2
1586	PA1557_at	107.2	547.5	101.4	76.9	67.7
1587	PA1558_at	223.5	148.3	227.2	232.7	219.7
1588	PA1559_at	195.0	380.6	129.8	167.1	160.7
1589	PA1560_at	72.1	133.6	52.0	58.4	83.2
1590	PA1561_aer_at	3281.9	4044.9	2776.8	2454.9	2520.5
1591	PA1562_acnA_at	200.9	227.8	144.2	190.8	180.3
1592	PA1563_at	127.0	77.5	83.5	90.9	65.9
1593	PA1564_at	294.3	148.3	473.8	409.6	397.9
1594	PA1565_at	7.8	35.9	37.3	15.2	27.9
1595	PA1566_at	20.7	20.6	33.9	33.6	28.9
1596	PA1567_at	48.3	35.6	46.9	37.1	41.6
1597	PA1568_at	28.9	41.9	28.0	46.0	38.7
1598	PA1569_at	86.4	35.6	56.9	22.6	44.0
1599	PA1570_at	52.1	42.9	109.5	116.3	122.3
1600	PA1571_at	193.9	130.8	135.7	118.9	142.8
1601	PA1572_at	346.0	271.3	383.4	345.9	355.7
1602	PA1573_at	295.8	185.3	331.3	336.0	303.4

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1603	PA1574_at	52.2	163.7	94.4	89.5	103.6
1604	PA1575_at	63.1	89.8	131.6	166.6	149.2
1605	PA1576_at	43.2	46.9	157.4	179.2	165.0
1606	PA1577_at	70.4	42.6	59.5	58.7	40.6
1607	PA1578_at	7.0	52.0	87.7	82.5	56.4
1608	PA1579_at	929.5	1269.2	1141.2	1126.2	1182.5
1609	PA1580_gltA_at	874.0	2815.3	1458.5	1202.9	1139.1
1610	PA1581_sdhC_at	632.2	542.1	1200.4	1014.1	976.1
1611	PA1582_sdhD_at	629.4	481.4	1410.8	1109.9	1077.7
1612	PA1583_sdhA_at	539.2	983.8	771.3	562.0	580.2
1613	PA1584_sdhB_at	718.3	2425.4	734.8	605.0	618.0
1614	PA1585_sucA_at	626.1	1793.2	488.6	466.5	495.4
1615	PA1586_sucB_at	2016.5	5598.7	1317.4	1761.0	1778.3
1616	PA1587_lpdG_at	941.4	2308.1	718.8	872.8	849.7
1617	PA1588_sucC_at	2711.9	7208.7	2765.8	3144.4	2961.8
1618	PA1589_sucD_at	3667.6	8025.5	2992.4	3184.7	3107.0
1619	PA1590_braB_at	142.1	135.2	195.8	187.0	139.6
1620	PA1591_at	57.3	58.4	40.6	48.3	59.0
1621	PA1592_i_at	5648.4	4024.2	2518.5	3124.4	3551.5
1622	PA1593_at	148.2	43.3	120.8	115.2	134.5
1623	PA1594_at	115.6	52.2	98.2	106.9	105.8
1624	PA1595_at	14.2	9.1	15.2	25.8	16.2
1625	PA1596_htpG_at	667.6	481.7	411.7	460.9	479.4
1626	PA1597_at	83.2	31.8	7.4	38.4	24.5
1627	PA1598_at	10.8	6.5	10.3	12.1	14.2
1628	PA1599_at	58.2	8.3	55.2	38.3	41.4
1629	PA1600_at	87.9	75.9	33.9	36.2	31.1
1630	PA1601_at	44.6	62.3	32.1	38.0	25.4
1631	PA1602_at	101.3	66.1	94.7	60.5	81.0
1632	PA1603_at	312.8	284.6	201.3	212.4	236.7
1633	PA1604_at	461.6	416.8	338.0	342.7	366.9
1634	PA1605_at	153.2	129.4	141.4	123.5	91.2
1635	PA1606_at	98.5	42.5	68.9	71.6	57.7
1636	PA1607_at	637.0	556.2	432.2	453.4	485.8
1637	PA1608_at	223.5	179.1	269.0	288.5	249.7
1638	PA1609_fabB_at	453.3	423.1	691.6	591.5	705.9
1639	PA1610_fabA_at	776.2	592.8	1163.1	932.5	1111.0
1640	PA1611_at	116.4	244.3	120.3	113.6	124.8
1641	PA1612_at	144.8	150.5	87.8	124.6	95.7
1642	PA1613_at	134.9	81.2	143.9	112.5	123.3
1643	PA1614_gpsA_at	418.8	283.5	619.4	555.2	575.4
1644	PA1615_at	190.3	152.1	319.6	236.2	277.6
1645	PA1616_at	196.5	141.9	264.3	182.5	233.2
1646	PA1617_at	559.8	520.0	549.5	677.1	606.9
1647	PA1618_at	523.4	257.8	395.1	377.6	385.2
1648	PA1619_at	258.0	228.9	334.8	344.2	288.5
1649	PA1620_at	64.0	47.9	68.4	95.0	67.5
1650	PA1621_at	515.0	610.3	823.1	717.5	744.1
1651	PA1622_at	141.2	170.4	216.7	258.3	213.9
1652	PA1623_at	292.1	214.3	493.0	602.9	591.8
1653	PA1624_at	252.5	157.5	250.0	250.3	240.4
1654	PA1625_at	90.0	53.8	58.6	78.1	77.6
1655	PA1626_at	26.7	34.6	72.5	49.6	42.7
1656	PA1627_at	123.3	58.9	96.0	102.2	105.2
1657	PA1628_at	106.7	39.5	62.4	76.3	76.1
1658	PA1629_at	109.4	71.8	135.0	74.6	105.4
1659	PA1630_at	82.3	48.1	139.2	97.7	108.7
1660	PA1631_at	16.0	15.7	8.0	20.4	9.1
1661	PA1632_kdpF_at	8.5	11.7	22.7	20.8	8.4
1662	PA1633_kdpA_at	75.2	117.0	114.0	70.6	57.4
1663	PA1634_kdpB_at	128.6	73.2	25.9	73.4	52.8
1664	PA1635_kdpC_at	9.0	3.8	2.5	27.4	3.4
1665	PA1636_kdpD_at	18.5	9.8	50.7	49.2	52.1
1666	PA1637_kdpE_at	48.9	39.1	36.2	48.6	48.0
1667	PA1638_at	9.2	17.5	59.3	59.5	56.8
1668	PA1639_at	52.4	57.8	163.1	139.3	114.7
1669	PA1640_at	388.3	207.1	629.6	578.8	662.4
1670	PA1641_at	97.1	89.6	191.2	184.8	221.2
1671	PA1642_selD_at	203.1	222.8	377.2	371.5	350.8
1672	PA1643_at	164.6	115.3	135.9	145.0	146.7
1673	PA1644_at	189.3	106.5	212.9	195.2	202.1
1674	PA1645_at	201.3	191.0	300.5	296.8	259.1
1675	PA1646_at	49.8	36.6	27.4	55.6	50.0

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1676	PA1647_at	43.5	60.7	67.4	47.9	51.1
1677	PA1648_at	55.7	70.2	192.0	63.3	79.2
1678	PA1649_at	38.2	41.7	124.0	55.6	42.4
1679	PA1650_at	83.5	87.1	138.4	127.4	115.4
1680	PA1651_at	168.2	144.3	351.8	266.1	248.5
1681	PA1652_at	88.4	14.7	56.8	70.3	42.6
1682	PA1653_at	128.6	37.1	200.0	174.3	131.4
1683	PA1654_at	204.9	185.3	841.2	618.8	637.4
1684	PA1655_at	85.9	66.6	223.5	163.7	170.8
1685	PA1656_at	363.9	303.7	376.5	366.3	372.5
1686	PA1657_at	285.5	305.5	380.1	381.1	376.3
1687	PA1658_at	139.5	242.2	213.4	173.6	173.6
1688	PA1659_at	150.3	149.7	144.4	130.2	127.4
1689	PA1660_at	23.6	44.2	45.8	49.1	26.3
1690	PA1661_at	66.5	81.0	56.9	52.9	48.6
1691	PA1662_at	75.2	100.8	46.2	55.9	44.6
1692	PA1663_at	107.9	161.3	87.1	94.9	95.8
1693	PA1664_at	39.7	60.4	89.8	177.4	157.6
1694	PA1665_at	95.0	92.7	61.0	69.9	74.4
1695	PA1666_at	120.1	125.8	113.0	73.8	106.0
1696	PA1667_at	133.7	192.0	109.3	102.0	85.4
1697	PA1668_at	63.8	91.9	74.2	82.0	62.6
1698	PA1669_at	34.1	69.3	38.7	45.3	60.6
1699	PA1670_stp1_at	114.1	80.9	101.3	76.3	74.0
1700	PA1671_stk1_at	14.3	6.0	17.3	38.9	35.3
1701	PA1672_at	261.9	245.3	248.7	379.6	384.1
1702	PA1673_at	70.6	229.4	85.7	123.3	107.9
1703	PA1674_folE2_at	134.1	95.0	249.1	236.4	285.6
1704	PA1675_at	108.6	75.5	124.9	120.4	135.3
1705	PA1676_at	223.2	137.2	203.5	218.5	217.3
1706	PA1677_at	1503.0	1300.5	1176.0	1258.3	1502.2
1707	PA1678_at	86.5	69.6	114.4	86.6	78.5
1708	PA1679_at	412.0	314.3	468.8	505.3	560.8
1709	PA1680_at	202.4	116.6	130.5	145.7	123.7
1710	PA1681_aroC_at	125.7	153.5	443.3	428.9	356.3
1711	PA1682_at	36.8	5.5	9.2	34.0	17.3
1712	PA1683_at	118.3	204.4	139.0	148.7	169.7
1713	PA1684_at	299.3	382.1	412.6	388.9	421.2
1714	PA1685_masA_at	99.6	70.2	101.0	73.4	98.0
1715	PA1686_alkA_at	612.8	337.9	523.5	574.4	584.3
1716	PA1687_speE_at	105.6	56.7	30.5	29.8	28.7
1717	PA1688_at	91.6	126.7	142.2	142.2	130.8
1718	PA1689_at	108.8	344.1	116.1	91.1	73.4
1719	PA1690_pscU_at	4.9	55.7	16.3	23.4	21.6
1720	PA1691_pscT_at	48.9	55.8	33.6	29.8	30.5
1721	PA1692_at	168.1	213.5	153.0	157.9	139.1
1722	PA1693_pscR_at	170.5	119.4	110.5	96.4	126.7
1723	PA1694_pscQ_at	62.6	126.9	25.4	44.7	29.1
1724	PA1695_pscP_at	52.6	60.1	9.1	20.6	5.6
1725	PA1696_pscO_at	63.3	21.3	13.7	15.4	36.6
1726	PA1697_at	75.5	108.5	112.4	82.6	67.1
1727	PA1698_popN_at	10.3	41.7	62.9	46.2	39.8
1728	PA1699_at	6.7	3.4	3.2	27.4	22.5
1729	PA1700_at	73.7	57.6	35.8	59.5	51.8
1730	PA1701_at	62.9	34.5	38.8	55.5	33.9
1731	PA1702_i_at	38.9	19.2	9.9	9.4	19.5
1732	PA1703_pcrD_at	69.6	87.5	61.0	68.7	68.0
1733	PA1704_pcrR_at	26.5	48.3	33.1	42.0	26.7
1734	PA1705_pcrG_i_at	118.2	165.3	64.0	70.3	50.9
1735	PA1706_pcrV_at	103.7	148.5	26.5	42.9	42.9
1736	PA1707_pcrH_at	204.9	179.3	51.5	97.9	61.9
1737	PA1708_popB_at	293.3	328.6	101.3	129.6	115.7
1738	PA1709_popD_at	202.8	173.7	85.8	94.2	100.0
1739	PA1710_exsC_at	198.1	104.7	213.9	187.9	201.1
1740	PA1711_at	341.8	142.9	239.7	257.8	285.5
1741	PA1712_exsB_at	46.6	83.0	72.1	75.0	96.8
1742	PA1713_exsA_at	126.6	136.8	100.5	94.5	90.4
1743	PA1714_at	359.7	241.7	186.8	215.0	185.5
1744	PA1715_pscB_at	9.2	27.7	23.8	25.8	21.5
1745	PA1716_pscC_at	180.8	157.8	86.8	105.4	81.8
1746	PA1717_pscD_at	32.2	110.7	44.6	38.7	37.2
1747	PA1718_pscE_at	202.7	340.9	73.2	110.2	75.6
1748	PA1719_pscF_at	74.2	199.8	68.8	73.4	84.0

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1749	PA1720_pscG_at	133.1	94.9	50.3	52.7	43.4
1750	PA1721_pscH_at	156.0	118.2	71.4	72.8	34.4
1751	PA1722_pscI_at	250.2	302.4	103.1	133.3	122.7
1752	PA1723_pscJ_at	163.4	141.1	78.7	72.0	52.1
1753	PA1724_pscK_at	143.2	73.6	48.7	61.3	47.2
1754	PA1725_pscL_at	88.9	67.0	44.1	52.9	41.9
1755	PA1726_bglX_at	396.0	550.7	441.2	279.2	337.4
1756	PA1727_at	93.1	70.2	110.4	121.0	107.2
1757	PA1728_at	129.2	107.9	182.9	191.5	220.4
1758	PA1729_at	398.2	290.8	367.3	364.1	369.3
1759	PA1730_at	130.7	101.1	140.3	169.9	133.4
1760	PA1731_at	131.2	40.3	55.3	81.2	87.8
1761	PA1732_at	94.5	51.3	95.3	89.4	90.4
1762	PA1733_at	134.4	127.5	139.2	129.0	103.2
1763	PA1734_at	55.1	28.5	117.5	128.7	130.0
1764	PA1735_at	67.3	32.8	67.2	69.6	51.3
1765	PA1736_at	89.4	96.0	138.3	91.9	99.1
1766	PA1737_at	94.2	117.4	158.2	121.2	109.9
1767	PA1738_at	290.2	161.0	298.7	292.6	312.9
1768	PA1739_at	146.4	78.4	50.8	109.4	97.5
1769	PA1740_at	10.5	16.4	24.3	36.0	28.5
1770	PA1741_at	227.9	168.6	154.8	167.4	186.0
1771	PA1742_at	2360.2	2267.0	1892.5	1752.6	1779.9
1772	PA1743_at	7.3	26.4	15.3	24.8	9.4
1773	PA1744_at	128.5	49.3	38.0	46.2	57.5
1774	PA1745_at	79.5	153.9	173.1	188.3	188.6
1775	PA1746_at	72.7	137.0	114.5	134.5	93.9
1776	PA1747_at	153.9	132.4	51.8	53.0	60.3
1777	PA1748_at	50.4	87.3	115.7	99.7	94.0
1778	PA1749_at	608.9	562.5	527.0	497.1	565.4
1779	PA1750_at	309.9	337.4	652.7	453.6	520.9
1780	PA1751_at	202.5	157.1	341.4	281.7	290.1
1781	PA1752_at	397.9	254.0	571.6	570.5	532.6
1782	PA1753_at	387.7	344.8	380.0	441.0	436.8
1783	PA1754_cysB_at	1620.9	1227.9	1008.8	954.0	1119.8
1784	PA1755_at	119.2	71.1	107.8	65.8	118.6
1785	PA1756_cysH_at	664.8	296.6	266.7	221.0	522.1
1786	PA1757_thrH_at	124.7	92.6	105.3	103.7	100.4
1787	PA1758_pabB_at	105.5	65.6	182.5	166.4	153.0
1788	PA1759_at	1040.0	1162.4	1142.8	1155.5	1123.9
1789	PA1760_at	657.3	366.1	361.1	423.2	380.5
1790	PA1761_at	898.1	712.0	820.4	713.3	766.9
1791	PA1762_at	106.5	84.1	146.3	133.2	132.5
1792	PA1763_at	166.9	112.8	108.6	114.0	93.3
1793	PA1764_at	19.3	19.3	22.7	28.1	24.9
1794	PA1765_at	15.4	66.6	81.8	91.5	72.9
1795	PA1766_at	222.5	488.6	210.6	191.2	202.9
1796	PA1767_at	214.8	296.8	376.3	283.1	257.7
1797	PA1768_at	428.4	224.3	1079.3	916.5	992.0
1798	PA1769_at	841.6	725.7	593.4	581.9	620.6
1799	PA1770_ppsA_at	568.3	472.0	1045.5	774.4	1053.4
1800	PA1771_at	67.3	21.6	28.8	45.2	34.1
1801	PA1772_at	359.4	450.1	580.8	478.7	423.8
1802	PA1773_at	304.4	228.6	354.9	390.5	421.9
1803	PA1774_at	312.2	184.7	311.3	297.9	356.5
1804	PA1775_at	379.6	247.1	417.6	394.5	445.0
1805	PA1776_at	2050.2	2428.7	1821.3	2330.3	2450.7
1806	PA1777_oprF_at	4824.2	4736.4	2993.6	3580.0	3214.4
1807	PA1778_cobA_at	7.8	7.7	23.8	36.3	30.1
1808	PA1779_at	7.1	9.7	22.8	32.5	15.2
1809	PA1780_nirD_at	58.1	18.9	10.8	25.3	23.8
1810	PA1781_nirB_at	46.3	23.6	21.0	17.4	26.3
1811	PA1782_at	87.1	29.8	42.9	63.3	53.8
1812	PA1783_nasA_at	20.1	5.3	7.6	4.7	5.4
1813	PA1784_at	180.6	188.3	195.3	196.4	198.3
1814	PA1785_at	23.5	5.3	24.5	18.6	20.6
1815	PA1786_at	8.7	52.9	61.2	54.2	41.6
1816	PA1787_acnB_at	1525.7	3079.6	1385.8	1384.6	1418.2
1817	PA1788_at	78.5	43.8	169.0	143.5	203.7
1818	PA1789_at	246.8	319.0	409.5	291.0	387.4
1819	PA1790_at	10.6	20.7	53.9	39.0	51.7
1820	PA1791_at	202.3	161.3	203.9	116.9	114.5
1821	PA1792_at	263.2	295.7	272.3	184.5	298.8

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1822	PA1793_ppiB_at	1324.1	1521.9	1215.9	1320.0	1368.5
1823	PA1794_glnS_at	438.2	331.0	759.5	633.9	649.9
1824	PA1795_cysS_at	360.8	630.6	439.9	410.5	427.3
1825	PA1796_fold_at	327.0	210.0	714.6	627.1	622.8
1826	PA1797_at	59.4	68.0	58.6	69.6	61.0
1827	PA1798_at	115.5	91.9	147.8	141.6	132.2
1828	PA1799_at	294.4	220.7	598.6	531.0	615.2
1829	PA1800_tig_at	375.6	714.8	716.4	634.6	678.2
1830	PA1801_clpP_at	1164.3	934.3	1502.9	1413.6	1321.0
1831	PA1802_clpX_at	2075.2	1954.3	2114.1	2161.3	2358.1
1832	PA1803_lon_at	1391.5	1200.7	871.7	850.7	922.6
1833	PA1804_hupB_at	1716.4	2045.2	1640.2	1661.9	1651.4
1834	PA1805_ppiD_at	404.8	634.7	554.0	537.3	545.1
1835	PA1806_fabI_at	179.6	422.9	212.6	260.9	245.8
1836	PA1807_at	209.1	501.4	118.7	128.0	130.8
1837	PA1808_at	191.9	261.9	115.1	136.0	134.1
1838	PA1809_at	156.2	209.0	124.8	141.5	140.3
1839	PA1810_at	123.5	119.4	96.4	115.3	103.3
1840	PA1811_at	309.4	173.5	330.1	358.9	315.4
1841	PA1812_mltD_at	204.5	205.9	277.0	267.7	227.9
1842	PA1813_at	531.6	477.2	586.5	576.9	610.9
1843	PA1814_at	434.1	305.9	493.8	575.4	518.1
1844	PA1815_rnhA_at	228.2	152.2	227.2	320.9	333.8
1845	PA1816_dnaQ_at	191.4	167.2	207.8	222.6	166.6
1846	PA1817_at	123.9	138.9	139.9	141.2	147.9
1847	PA1818_at	2907.2	1980.7	3372.6	2903.1	2712.9
1848	PA1819_at	293.1	265.7	174.4	160.0	124.4
1849	PA1820_nhaB_at	56.0	58.8	105.8	80.0	121.5
1850	PA1821_at	186.2	113.1	451.3	440.3	455.0
1851	PA1822_at	133.9	85.0	148.2	141.3	97.0
1852	PA1823_at	133.5	301.0	127.1	143.4	137.4
1853	PA1824_at	11.1	6.0	33.0	9.4	17.0
1854	PA1825_at	16.8	20.8	56.7	52.7	38.6
1855	PA1826_at	108.5	56.5	62.6	62.7	64.9
1856	PA1827_at	76.1	98.1	104.8	93.5	88.8
1857	PA1828_at	95.1	164.4	364.6	116.7	131.5
1858	PA1829_at	254.4	134.1	723.8	229.5	253.5
1859	PA1830_at	223.3	550.2	211.9	164.8	161.6
1860	PA1831_at	109.7	51.7	164.5	95.1	93.7
1861	PA1832_at	212.3	173.2	417.0	412.2	462.1
1862	PA1833_at	329.4	186.7	479.7	348.3	366.8
1863	PA1834_at	97.0	63.6	124.1	73.6	73.8
1864	PA1835_at	111.6	65.2	98.5	87.7	95.6
1865	PA1836_at	54.6	62.8	155.9	154.4	117.4
1866	PA1837_at	451.6	356.9	163.9	146.2	276.1
1867	PA1838_cysI_at	680.0	259.1	155.5	175.6	382.2
1868	PA1839_at	24.6	76.2	80.6	28.6	53.8
1869	PA1840_at	133.4	122.0	227.1	255.4	238.8
1870	PA1841_at	92.2	59.5	88.7	81.4	79.3
1871	PA1842_at	173.9	253.2	81.6	111.8	96.2
1872	PA1843_methH_at	175.5	219.9	145.2	129.9	118.0
1873	PA1844_at	62.2	21.3	35.9	36.5	31.6
1874	PA1845_at	98.7	64.4	65.5	49.6	47.1
1875	PA1846_cti_at	77.2	104.4	67.3	82.6	106.1
1876	PA1847_at	3337.0	3085.5	1646.9	1811.3	1999.7
1877	PA1848_at	12.7	3.8	7.4	31.8	2.4
1878	PA1849_at	11.7	5.7	12.1	16.1	18.6
1879	PA1850_at	140.9	88.9	85.5	92.7	95.5
1880	PA1851_at	88.1	40.1	56.6	61.6	53.6
1881	PA1852_at	488.6	238.2	983.1	890.0	1196.1
1882	PA1853_at	53.2	52.7	85.8	90.1	88.9
1883	PA1854_at	61.2	33.4	79.8	41.5	38.8
1884	PA1855_r_at	27.0	20.6	24.8	20.1	18.8
1885	PA1856_at	16.7	31.2	15.8	17.3	25.5
1886	PA1857_at	122.4	100.2	268.6	234.2	218.6
1887	PA1858_str_at	203.5	84.8	164.0	190.4	150.3
1888	PA1859_at	205.9	76.6	162.8	150.5	183.2
1889	PA1860_at	139.2	60.1	150.9	160.0	109.6
1890	PA1861_modC_at	145.9	93.7	89.9	86.9	89.7
1891	PA1862_modB_at	115.7	88.7	107.4	150.1	133.7
1892	PA1863_modA_at	223.1	106.1	151.6	158.5	153.0
1893	PA1864_at	85.8	86.4	69.7	78.6	110.9
1894	PA1865_at	636.5	269.3	306.3	405.3	261.8

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1895	PA1866_at	221.7	126.0	121.7	114.5	108.3
1896	PA1867_at	80.8	3.5	23.5	24.3	6.6
1897	PA1868_xqhA_at	14.8	71.6	47.7	49.5	33.8
1898	PA1869_at	107.3	161.4	110.6	79.9	139.9
1899	PA1870_at	8.1	19.5	31.2	42.4	26.5
1900	PA1871_lasA_at	27.2	54.4	53.0	92.1	76.2
1901	PA1872_at	160.3	72.8	208.0	233.1	220.8
1902	PA1873_at	16.7	35.3	68.3	67.4	46.2
1903	PA1874_at	132.8	171.7	210.9	176.1	140.3
1904	PA1875_at	51.2	43.7	26.5	54.9	48.2
1905	PA1876_at	6.4	49.0	53.2	84.6	68.5
1906	PA1877_at	65.2	66.0	39.1	61.5	46.4
1907	PA1878_at	129.5	52.9	78.3	73.4	99.3
1908	PA1879_at	16.9	7.2	55.9	70.5	47.5
1909	PA1880_at	89.1	52.9	121.3	92.3	112.5
1910	PA1881_at	65.0	33.8	159.7	168.3	127.6
1911	PA1882_at	220.4	149.6	81.7	98.8	136.0
1912	PA1883_at	38.2	69.6	35.1	42.7	8.5
1913	PA1884_at	126.4	82.7	115.4	98.5	92.3
1914	PA1885_at	104.6	77.1	131.9	167.5	168.2
1915	PA1886_polB_at	152.6	69.8	140.6	152.9	155.3
1916	PA1887_at	88.3	20.0	5.8	42.8	22.9
1917	PA1888_at	32.0	46.4	85.8	118.0	127.1
1918	PA1889_at	56.5	80.6	61.0	87.1	80.0
1919	PA1890_at	287.1	140.2	362.2	362.2	361.8
1920	PA1891_at	119.0	62.8	89.8	60.1	49.3
1921	PA1892_at	9.8	155.1	147.7	110.0	108.0
1922	PA1893_at	39.1	380.3	217.1	189.3	231.1
1923	PA1894_at	226.5	814.7	458.3	513.7	510.9
1924	PA1895_at	134.8	480.2	393.5	345.1	347.5
1925	PA1896_at	269.5	449.6	517.1	477.2	481.6
1926	PA1897_at	395.1	898.9	1156.2	1179.3	1263.8
1927	PA1898_at	351.9	346.1	349.1	386.1	347.5
1928	PA4210_s_at	21.3	23.6	38.0	27.0	25.4
1929	PA4211_g_at	59.6	41.6	52.0	73.1	33.8
1930	PA1901_s_at	108.9	98.2	112.0	191.4	172.4
1931	PA1902_s_at	9.1	6.4	6.9	9.4	7.6
1932	PA1903_s_at	50.1	71.7	48.5	53.7	54.6
1933	PA1904_s_at	27.2	63.7	22.1	42.8	17.8
1934	PA1905_s_at	101.9	109.3	82.4	75.2	62.6
1935	PA1906_at	11.0	28.1	46.9	37.5	32.5
1936	PA1907_at	61.1	3.5	7.4	18.6	18.1
1937	PA1908_at	76.0	5.3	11.0	26.7	12.4
1938	PA1909_at	70.9	22.4	57.4	59.1	46.4
1939	PA1910_at	241.3	138.1	180.9	164.5	156.6
1940	PA1911_at	1636.2	985.9	947.8	895.8	857.6
1941	PA1912_at	2388.9	2028.7	641.3	644.8	538.5
1942	PA1913_at	130.7	117.9	226.2	240.7	223.4
1943	PA1914_at	43.4	17.1	4.7	38.1	10.1
1944	PA1915_at	207.7	119.0	124.1	123.6	101.1
1945	PA1916_at	25.6	7.7	22.8	7.3	24.2
1946	PA1917_at	10.9	34.8	25.9	3.0	23.4
1947	PA1918_at	93.4	32.8	10.0	18.0	18.9
1948	PA1919_at	22.3	11.6	4.1	22.7	3.0
1949	PA1920_at	143.6	54.7	42.4	62.8	38.9
1950	PA1921_at	8.0	2.9	3.6	24.6	24.2
1951	PA1922_at	63.5	5.3	18.7	11.3	4.6
1952	PA1923_at	21.5	18.5	30.0	43.4	30.4
1953	PA1924_at	9.5	20.4	9.6	25.0	31.1
1954	PA1925_at	16.5	29.2	38.5	33.6	28.4
1955	PA1926_at	50.9	101.2	63.8	73.7	66.0
1956	PA1927_metE_at	28.8	23.5	10.9	8.9	22.3
1957	PA1928_rimJ_at	223.9	167.3	268.0	175.3	183.4
1958	PA1929_i_at	37.3	47.1	111.4	88.8	130.6
1959	PA1930_at	20.0	102.0	134.4	160.2	163.3
1960	PA1931_at	16.5	29.8	49.8	47.2	55.3
1961	PA1932_at	70.1	45.7	39.9	48.7	41.8
1962	PA1933_at	8.2	62.4	35.3	42.7	15.2
1963	PA1934_at	121.7	94.3	138.2	145.3	150.0
1964	PA1935_at	173.1	71.8	109.9	217.0	173.6
1965	PA1936_at	65.0	35.8	61.7	55.7	41.0
1966	PA1939_at	317.8	269.6	586.2	572.6	497.7
1967	PA1940_at	191.5	91.5	142.1	144.9	130.0

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

1968	PA1941_at	421.1	343.9	629.5	529.1	480.2
1969	PA1942_at	666.1	897.3	511.3	366.0	236.9
1970	PA1943_at	358.5	219.8	440.0	440.4	348.6
1971	PA1944_at	202.2	161.9	166.8	212.3	205.9
1972	PA1945_at	76.2	67.0	97.5	77.2	99.4
1973	PA1946_rbsB_at	360.5	389.1	489.5	474.4	456.6
1974	PA1947_rbsA_at	215.5	146.4	219.7	194.8	167.7
1975	PA1948_rbsC_at	218.3	115.1	180.3	123.3	156.6
1976	PA1949_rbsR_at	557.0	436.5	476.9	468.1	421.4
1977	PA1950_rbsK_at	565.3	353.0	492.9	451.8	377.3
1978	PA1951_at	101.9	40.3	129.6	162.9	116.2
1979	PA1952_at	31.2	40.3	41.2	37.3	52.1
1980	PA1953_at	4.2	6.2	3.4	5.0	3.4
1981	PA1954_at	80.6	53.9	52.4	50.3	51.6
1982	PA1955_at	47.4	8.1	18.9	9.1	1.4
1983	PA1956_at	51.8	27.7	25.9	27.4	25.3
1984	PA1957_at	85.2	28.1	78.5	70.1	65.8
1985	PA1958_at	62.8	69.4	168.8	188.6	186.6
1986	PA1959_bacA_at	114.4	41.9	98.7	70.0	85.0
1987	PA1960_at	75.2	22.8	27.3	28.1	37.0
1988	PA1961_at	40.2	40.3	54.7	61.1	41.2
1989	PA1962_at	5.0	21.0	49.8	44.7	49.1
1990	PA1963_at	337.3	332.5	376.8	471.4	515.1
1991	PA1964_at	134.9	131.6	180.7	173.6	180.2
1992	PA1965_at	33.1	61.8	138.8	111.9	124.7
1993	PA1966_at	14.8	82.1	57.0	53.8	19.8
1994	PA1967_at	137.5	124.2	252.7	185.1	211.8
1995	PA1968_at	234.3	110.3	152.1	170.8	179.5
1996	PA1969_at	139.6	174.0	200.9	208.8	236.8
1997	PA1970_at	96.4	77.3	44.2	45.6	52.6
1998	PA1971_braZ_at	25.4	1.5	11.5	36.9	11.7
1999	PA1972_at	11.0	1.7	2.8	3.8	2.0
2000	PA1973_pqqF_at	71.0	33.8	52.9	66.9	59.6
2001	PA1974_at	62.4	38.0	6.0	27.0	34.1
2002	PA1975_at	54.3	32.2	38.1	50.6	58.7
2003	PA1976_at	8.8	29.5	17.0	52.1	35.0
2004	PA1977_at	131.7	50.9	60.3	66.1	55.8
2005	PA1978_at	318.4	367.5	293.8	286.5	345.6
2006	PA1979_at	4.1	1.6	11.1	12.2	14.8
2007	PA1980_at	27.4	7.3	8.8	32.8	11.0
2008	PA1981_at	12.7	10.9	56.6	13.6	14.3
2009	PA1982_exaA_at	12.6	8.0	6.5	8.2	8.8
2010	PA1983_exaB_at	9.6	5.6	2.3	3.1	3.7
2011	PA1984_s_at	2415.8	4541.6	3447.0	3479.8	3765.5
2012	PA1985_pqqA_at	43.2	61.8	59.0	62.5	67.9
2013	PA1986_pqqB_at	107.9	78.1	104.2	88.9	95.4
2014	PA1987_pqqC_at	102.2	74.7	76.5	87.9	72.2
2015	PA1988_pqqD_at	62.6	108.6	77.6	103.0	70.3
2016	PA1989_pqqE_at	154.4	91.3	59.9	44.9	71.7
2017	PA1990_at	51.6	58.3	50.9	52.6	35.6
2018	PA1991_at	243.0	149.6	284.8	323.4	337.9
2019	PA1992_at	98.6	138.7	118.3	131.2	101.1
2020	PA1993_at	54.3	39.2	51.1	30.1	48.3
2021	PA1994_at	139.0	111.6	100.7	105.0	118.4
2022	PA1995_i_at	418.2	261.7	756.2	526.1	557.3
2023	PA1996_ppiC1_at	187.2	161.4	278.7	310.9	331.8
2024	PA1997_at	426.2	525.6	273.7	358.0	266.8
2025	PA1998_at	174.3	83.1	90.1	107.2	100.0
2026	PA1999_at	659.5	5570.7	1881.7	3418.6	5346.3
2027	PA2000_at	604.4	2902.6	1724.6	2627.9	3185.1
2028	PA2001_atoB_at	295.3	1860.8	958.0	1501.6	1741.2
2029	PA2002_at	96.1	129.2	86.7	111.3	94.5
2030	PA2003_bdhA_at	141.5	111.9	136.4	163.0	180.9
2031	PA2004_at	13.6	7.2	37.1	85.4	59.6
2032	PA2005_at	35.0	138.0	36.0	86.0	52.6
2033	PA2006_at	100.7	487.0	383.8	421.4	377.4
2034	PA2007_maiA_i_at	300.1	2407.3	1341.7	1230.7	1355.2
2035	PA2008_fahA_at	708.5	5358.3	5323.1	4398.6	4615.0
2036	PA2009_hmgA_at	512.6	3885.1	4169.9	3862.0	4256.3
2037	PA2010_at	60.5	79.3	117.1	113.0	96.2
2038	PA2011_at	431.0	1065.0	517.2	422.9	473.0
2039	PA2012_at	320.6	721.2	231.6	372.3	388.1
2040	PA2013_at	785.6	976.2	666.3	656.3	705.3

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2041	PA2014_at	1103.5	1560.7	1308.4	1459.3	1353.8
2042	PA2015_at	7753.5	8099.0	6036.4	5670.6	5834.1
2043	PA2016_at	5125.0	4436.3	4737.3	4243.9	4731.6
2044	PA2017_at	233.0	171.0	95.9	134.7	135.7
2045	PA2018_at	51.6	75.4	54.5	24.7	32.2
2046	PA2019_at	14.8	70.5	60.2	52.6	51.8
2047	PA2020_at	106.1	116.7	82.7	101.9	112.0
2048	PA2021_at	144.6	103.8	46.5	95.8	75.1
2049	PA2022_at	83.8	54.9	49.7	51.3	33.4
2050	PA2023_galU_at	485.5	414.1	606.6	572.5	531.7
2051	PA2024_at	185.8	342.7	131.9	166.8	187.6
2052	PA2025_gor_at	1119.3	1183.2	886.2	1025.2	961.7
2053	PA2026_at	22.3	25.4	57.4	40.1	22.8
2054	PA2027_at	158.0	72.3	87.3	65.9	65.7
2055	PA2028_at	169.8	107.8	135.0	119.8	144.0
2056	PA2029_i_at	95.7	88.3	105.4	84.0	82.3
2057	PA2030_at	190.1	104.5	142.1	140.4	162.9
2058	PA2031_i_at	610.5	316.3	483.9	537.5	676.0
2059	PA2032_at	24.4	5.1	23.5	37.2	39.4
2060	PA2033_at	702.5	419.5	740.6	594.1	635.4
2061	PA2034_at	193.2	106.5	222.6	203.7	184.5
2062	PA2035_at	87.8	63.5	70.0	91.4	71.7
2063	PA2036_at	7.9	32.7	22.7	75.0	32.5
2064	PA2037_at	79.4	59.6	97.4	127.7	84.4
2065	PA2038_at	92.6	69.6	94.0	81.7	66.5
2066	PA2039_at	109.4	59.1	103.1	115.2	113.7
2067	PA2041_at	306.5	217.9	437.6	407.6	362.2
2068	PA2042_at	190.4	208.8	238.6	174.3	179.5
2069	PA2043_at	8.4	31.4	61.0	47.7	51.7
2070	PA2044_at	140.0	84.6	185.9	193.0	166.4
2071	PA2045_at	390.9	289.5	366.2	374.0	420.8
2072	PA2046_at	15.0	11.2	8.6	15.2	11.8
2073	PA2047_at	219.2	121.8	172.4	240.9	223.2
2074	PA2048_at	29.7	37.2	34.7	30.9	35.4
2075	PA2049_at	71.9	45.1	91.0	58.0	96.6
2076	PA2050_at	64.4	11.0	14.8	31.4	17.3
2077	PA2051_at	9.2	15.1	14.8	47.6	18.4
2078	PA2052_cynS_at	210.5	97.2	112.1	160.2	142.7
2079	PA2053_cynT_at	186.3	91.2	160.1	165.9	167.5
2080	PA2054_cynR_at	112.6	48.0	71.3	74.2	72.6
2081	PA2055_at	9.2	25.9	43.2	32.5	35.0
2082	PA2056_at	64.8	9.9	24.1	33.4	39.2
2083	PA2057_at	12.0	3.7	9.8	25.0	30.0
2084	PA2058_at	49.1	27.1	29.6	19.2	6.7
2085	PA2059_at	90.8	55.6	31.2	16.3	40.5
2086	PA2060_at	24.2	31.7	19.6	27.9	23.7
2087	PA2061_at	9.8	15.3	14.3	9.5	18.3
2088	PA2062_at	1481.7	222.2	151.6	131.9	248.5
2089	PA2063_at	130.7	52.8	79.0	75.7	64.6
2090	PA2064_pcoB_at	69.2	35.6	43.1	26.4	30.2
2091	PA2065_pcoA_at	7.6	31.5	8.4	6.6	22.3
2092	PA2066_at	110.3	71.4	88.8	62.7	62.3
2093	PA2067_at	118.2	56.8	74.7	77.2	92.7
2094	PA2068_at	20.1	3.6	4.9	18.8	6.6
2095	PA2069_at	18.0	43.3	22.5	37.5	40.2
2096	PA2070_at	14.9	2.9	2.6	2.7	5.9
2097	PA2071_fusA2_at	122.3	117.0	196.6	182.0	164.5
2098	PA2072_at	19.4	19.4	34.6	29.6	20.4
2099	PA2073_at	85.4	26.1	26.0	24.5	30.7
2100	PA2074_at	116.9	79.1	53.5	47.4	42.8
2101	PA2075_at	114.6	52.0	74.8	93.7	118.9
2102	PA2076_at	266.6	211.0	301.6	219.6	222.8
2103	PA2077_at	6.1	29.4	8.7	16.7	8.9
2104	PA2078_at	40.9	15.4	6.9	30.3	20.4
2105	PA2079_at	84.5	8.3	94.9	45.4	53.6
2106	PA2080_at	639.2	394.8	822.0	602.4	667.5
2107	PA2081_at	999.0	395.0	710.1	785.5	945.9
2108	PA2082_at	151.7	160.3	264.0	231.9	198.8
2109	PA2083_at	1033.5	85.6	111.5	115.3	201.2
2110	PA2084_at	146.1	34.5	56.5	46.0	49.3
2111	PA2085_at	115.8	38.1	31.3	23.9	37.9
2112	PA2086_at	66.6	29.1	37.8	52.6	33.4
2113	PA2087_at	23.8	12.2	26.3	21.3	8.7

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2114	PA2088_at	7.8	1.9	2.7	3.7	3.0
2115	PA2089_at	129.9	65.0	27.9	40.2	25.2
2116	PA2090_at	115.0	20.3	40.2	28.4	34.0
2117	PA2091_at	13.0	5.5	3.9	35.1	4.6
2118	PA2092_at	31.1	15.7	20.9	19.7	23.2
2119	PA2093_at	9.0	62.3	47.9	61.7	43.0
2120	PA2094_at	115.6	56.1	48.9	72.2	67.4
2121	PA2095_at	82.3	43.6	33.0	34.4	43.3
2122	PA2096_at	51.0	28.4	16.8	58.2	49.2
2123	PA2097_at	37.7	42.1	30.1	13.3	32.2
2124	PA2098_at	93.5	55.0	53.5	39.8	57.0
2125	PA2099_at	8.5	65.4	9.3	41.3	15.3
2126	PA2100_at	244.6	273.8	213.2	232.9	248.6
2127	PA2101_at	77.1	84.8	77.7	70.1	48.7
2128	PA2102_at	104.2	100.0	85.6	92.8	95.7
2129	PA2103_at	191.2	186.5	225.0	236.1	190.8
2130	PA2104_at	157.7	85.4	94.6	113.4	100.6
2131	PA2105_at	98.4	113.3	140.6	156.8	166.2
2132	PA2106_at	58.4	70.3	72.8	108.3	99.3
2133	PA2107_at	166.7	139.0	110.7	77.1	68.6
2134	PA2108_at	23.6	49.1	48.8	38.4	11.2
2135	PA2109_at	278.4	1166.1	307.5	350.1	347.5
2136	PA2110_at	1234.1	2600.3	1355.1	1253.0	1280.4
2137	PA2111_at	2901.3	4357.8	1526.7	1721.2	1696.4
2138	PA2112_at	3373.0	4547.7	2664.5	2607.9	2836.9
2139	PA2113_at	2548.9	2618.9	2970.1	2683.1	2412.2
2140	PA2114_at	1971.0	1854.2	2838.5	2816.9	2722.7
2141	PA2115_at	153.8	73.9	169.7	162.8	150.0
2142	PA2116_at	1122.6	703.2	2061.6	1916.6	1979.9
2143	PA2117_at	94.0	128.3	150.5	137.1	118.6
2144	PA2118_ada_at	59.8	101.9	87.7	81.8	60.1
2145	PA2119_at	35.5	46.8	21.3	36.3	6.0
2146	PA2120_at	73.6	48.9	87.8	100.0	106.4
2147	PA2121_at	205.3	143.4	260.3	324.4	283.5
2148	PA2122_at	434.8	292.8	258.3	204.1	204.3
2149	PA2123_at	343.4	382.3	247.2	280.7	259.6
2150	PA2124_at	9.2	5.3	22.3	21.9	12.4
2151	PA2125_at	7.7	32.2	29.9	35.5	24.5
2152	PA2126_at	144.6	214.8	186.4	126.0	120.5
2153	PA2127_at	374.6	508.2	726.5	648.5	593.1
2154	PA2128_at	51.5	54.6	51.1	69.6	79.2
2155	PA2129_at	8.0	6.1	19.0	14.7	12.0
2156	PA2130_at	113.9	4.6	17.7	20.5	14.8
2157	PA2131_at	44.5	24.5	15.5	35.6	4.7
2158	PA2132_at	14.4	44.7	29.0	40.6	16.8
2159	PA2133_at	5.3	5.4	2.3	3.8	2.6
2160	PA2134_at	162.0	58.7	90.2	54.4	58.5
2161	PA2135_at	18.3	22.1	31.2	15.2	19.9
2162	PA2136_at	4.7	14.6	2.5	4.7	4.8
2163	PA2137_at	8.9	2.9	7.5	26.5	32.0
2164	PA2138_at	55.7	29.6	31.0	30.0	19.6
2165	PA2139_r_at	3.5	12.1	5.9	6.7	11.5
2166	PA2140_at	39.5	8.0	7.5	16.0	4.4
2167	PA2141_at	36.0	2.6	16.9	7.9	7.7
2168	PA2142_at	88.0	27.0	36.2	29.5	31.9
2169	PA2143_at	43.8	21.9	18.9	32.3	9.2
2170	PA2144_glgP_at	21.6	21.5	16.2	35.4	32.2
2171	PA2145_at	141.6	80.9	115.0	151.8	144.3
2172	PA2146_i_at	51.7	54.4	53.3	44.6	32.9
2173	PA2147_katE_at	18.0	6.0	7.5	5.2	6.0
2174	PA2148_at	20.7	17.1	34.7	26.3	19.8
2175	PA2149_at	42.7	29.8	76.4	65.7	63.9
2176	PA2150_at	6.2	10.9	2.5	17.2	16.6
2177	PA2151_at	7.0	1.6	4.0	1.7	14.9
2178	PA2152_at	50.5	60.8	79.0	70.6	36.7
2179	PA2153_glgB_at	58.3	9.7	8.4	19.9	2.6
2180	PA2154_at	61.2	30.9	11.6	30.8	37.2
2181	PA2155_at	7.1	19.1	4.6	17.5	10.9
2182	PA2156_at	4.7	0.8	1.0	1.8	6.4
2183	PA2157_at	48.4	25.9	46.7	37.4	36.1
2184	PA2158_at	54.8	4.4	3.2	22.3	10.0
2185	PA2159_at	31.7	27.5	24.6	27.3	25.8
2186	PA2160_at	40.1	61.1	30.6	27.4	18.5

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2187	PA2161_at	11.0	1.6	1.7	26.0	4.7
2188	PA2162_at	82.7	25.6	34.0	41.6	36.6
2189	PA2163_at	80.4	32.6	40.2	27.7	19.4
2190	PA2164_at	70.9	23.3	27.1	33.7	15.5
2191	PA2165_at	70.2	42.5	26.1	36.3	51.0
2192	PA2166_at	83.9	76.2	45.6	53.5	87.1
2193	PA2167_at	57.0	22.5	4.9	3.9	2.6
2194	PA2168_at	110.1	48.9	51.4	63.9	34.4
2195	PA2169_at	90.3	53.2	34.7	29.6	50.2
2196	PA2170_at	9.2	30.3	23.5	22.5	20.8
2197	PA2171_at	15.1	19.8	14.9	22.3	20.2
2198	PA2172_at	28.6	35.5	17.0	19.3	17.9
2199	PA2173_at	31.8	21.4	20.1	23.4	11.7
2200	PA2174_at	63.6	67.9	85.0	116.4	123.2
2201	PA2175_at	52.3	47.1	38.5	49.4	34.5
2202	PA2176_at	53.2	53.2	37.3	46.5	54.4
2203	PA2177_at	73.4	80.8	100.9	110.6	94.1
2204	PA2178_at	21.2	4.5	10.5	13.5	3.9
2205	PA2179_at	30.0	8.8	25.6	4.4	4.3
2206	PA2180_at	79.2	31.3	34.8	37.5	36.6
2207	PA2181_at	130.4	57.5	36.9	32.0	6.6
2208	PA2182_at	74.2	43.7	37.8	53.6	36.5
2209	PA2183_at	19.1	18.9	17.2	27.9	27.2
2210	PA2184_at	67.6	22.9	43.9	52.3	44.3
2211	PA2185_at	9.4	27.0	4.5	19.8	35.4
2212	PA2186_r_at	14.2	94.8	100.1	66.5	54.2
2213	PA2187_at	21.2	22.0	34.9	35.4	10.5
2214	PA2188_at	41.4	25.6	38.4	34.5	7.8
2215	PA2189_at	94.0	48.8	57.7	36.1	30.9
2216	PA2190_at	9.3	27.6	36.9	52.3	3.2
2217	PA2191_exoY_at	48.5	30.3	23.8	29.6	21.8
2218	PA2192_at	55.9	8.0	25.1	38.9	20.1
2219	PA2193_hcnA_at	122.4	459.6	197.3	171.2	143.6
2220	PA2194_hcnB_at	66.0	389.1	124.5	156.7	138.4
2221	PA2195_hcnC_at	99.2	404.2	106.6	103.9	85.2
2222	PA2196_at	25.5	77.7	77.4	85.1	54.9
2223	PA2197_at	110.1	92.9	170.1	123.4	161.9
2224	PA2198_at	10.6	76.3	18.4	81.2	70.5
2225	PA2199_at	155.6	238.5	156.1	158.7	160.0
2226	PA2200_at	102.7	60.3	44.7	45.6	34.7
2227	PA2201_at	93.0	34.7	88.7	62.2	47.1
2228	PA2202_at	199.3	57.9	29.6	32.9	63.6
2229	PA2203_at	256.6	34.1	30.8	19.4	66.4
2230	PA2204_at	5892.4	820.5	317.2	326.7	1317.7
2231	PA2205_at	123.2	58.1	65.5	43.6	46.5
2232	PA2206_at	180.4	148.1	221.5	123.5	201.8
2233	PA2207_at	19.5	24.6	19.0	21.9	20.1
2234	PA2208_at	80.7	6.4	6.5	20.6	4.8
2235	PA2209_at	119.2	22.9	42.2	48.9	41.0
2236	PA2210_at	114.5	127.9	85.3	118.4	126.7
2237	PA2211_at	116.3	79.7	72.3	80.7	76.7
2238	PA2212_at	260.9	160.1	191.8	197.8	173.9
2239	PA2213_at	44.4	10.7	22.1	6.0	3.7
2240	PA2214_at	6.2	11.5	1.9	30.2	4.5
2241	PA2215_at	37.3	9.9	6.1	22.8	23.6
2242	PA2216_at	96.5	86.8	84.3	87.8	56.3
2243	PA2217_at	10.8	2.9	7.2	13.6	2.2
2244	PA2218_at	163.1	102.3	107.1	102.2	95.6
2245	PA2219_opdE_at	171.4	64.1	74.6	90.5	86.3
2246	PA2220_at	201.8	157.1	205.1	227.5	234.6
2247	PA2221_at	23.4	30.4	39.5	25.0	18.8
2248	PA2222_at	15.6	21.9	36.1	41.2	35.1
2249	PA2223_at	97.7	90.2	68.0	93.9	80.6
2250	PA2224_at	5.3	10.9	13.4	15.0	10.6
2251	PA2225_at	66.3	38.9	38.1	53.9	49.4
2252	PA2226_at	24.7	39.3	20.5	22.9	33.2
2253	PA2227_at	26.9	49.2	31.6	40.4	37.6
2254	PA2228_at	24.6	3.2	12.9	13.7	31.6
2255	PA2229_at	96.4	105.2	195.4	218.7	181.3
2256	PA2230_at	40.9	60.3	99.6	81.0	59.5
2257	PA2231_at	463.4	514.3	403.3	421.6	323.0
2258	PA2232_at	356.2	428.3	377.9	354.5	345.2
2259	PA2233_at	209.3	319.9	169.1	189.9	178.8

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2260	PA2234_at	542.9	464.3	425.5	434.4	357.9
2261	PA2235_at	371.9	660.1	333.1	301.3	275.8
2262	PA2236_at	313.8	738.9	209.8	246.5	238.2
2263	PA2237_at	174.4	450.5	174.7	240.8	218.3
2264	PA2238_at	345.5	459.4	172.5	184.7	191.5
2265	PA2239_at	272.0	390.6	230.1	202.3	193.1
2266	PA2240_at	199.0	266.1	170.2	219.8	208.7
2267	PA2241_at	150.3	157.9	81.3	118.3	90.6
2268	PA2242_at	258.6	286.3	274.1	302.5	273.1
2269	PA2243_at	117.8	97.5	40.1	64.5	75.1
2270	PA2244_at	8.7	25.2	23.5	24.0	20.9
2271	PA2245_at	35.5	12.2	8.2	13.8	2.2
2272	PA2246_bkdR_at	161.3	80.5	207.7	162.5	151.5
2273	PA2247_bkdA1_at	13612.7	8587.4	6722.4	6460.1	6733.3
2274	PA2248_bkdA2_at	7040.6	6107.1	4521.9	4779.1	4750.6
2275	PA2249_bkdB_at	4371.3	4658.3	3196.7	2834.6	2868.0
2276	PA2250_lpdV_at	2451.8	2809.3	2222.5	2626.3	2280.5
2277	PA2251_at	105.3	35.5	65.2	49.6	79.4
2278	PA2252_at	23.8	116.1	46.1	44.2	44.0
2279	PA2253_ansA_at	176.2	193.2	256.8	234.6	267.7
2280	PA2254_pvcA_at	24.5	25.1	13.5	18.3	4.3
2281	PA2255_pvcB_at	8.0	17.1	11.9	8.0	11.9
2282	PA2256_pvcC_at	39.3	20.6	26.2	37.1	37.1
2283	PA2257_pvcD_at	6.1	3.0	19.4	23.0	10.9
2284	PA2258_ptxR_at	38.7	2.4	8.4	21.3	21.1
2285	PA2259_ptxS_at	4517.0	4063.7	4191.8	3434.2	4045.5
2286	PA2260_at	2312.0	1915.6	3130.8	3028.2	3512.4
2287	PA2261_at	1139.8	520.9	1148.3	1275.8	1157.1
2288	PA2262_at	558.5	280.0	723.6	773.2	639.0
2289	PA2263_at	699.8	490.3	524.8	728.6	573.2
2290	PA2264_at	293.1	414.1	289.2	275.5	269.6
2291	PA2265_at	165.2	560.0	253.8	252.0	216.9
2292	PA2266_at	115.5	411.8	173.9	159.9	209.9
2293	PA2267_at	103.2	61.6	130.3	150.4	126.5
2294	PA2268_at	5.6	41.6	27.4	42.6	46.4
2295	PA2269_at	110.2	57.1	76.8	86.6	48.1
2296	PA2270_at	706.9	318.1	697.0	562.1	583.3
2297	PA2271_i_at	289.3	137.8	327.8	204.9	248.3
2298	PA2272_pbpC_at	70.5	67.7	97.2	61.4	93.8
2299	PA2273_at	189.2	152.4	179.4	137.3	137.9
2300	PA2274_at	162.5	161.1	156.0	112.3	175.2
2301	PA2275_at	84.3	30.3	10.7	36.4	22.5
2302	PA2276_at	66.3	8.5	60.2	84.3	60.1
2303	PA2277_arsR_at	106.4	75.1	108.3	80.5	83.8
2304	PA2278_arsB_at	57.3	35.6	36.8	71.1	46.3
2305	PA2279_arsC_at	5.8	32.2	35.3	39.3	30.1
2306	PA2280_at	11.8	32.7	8.6	23.1	37.7
2307	PA2281_at	43.7	28.7	101.9	78.5	64.9
2308	PA2282_at	134.7	122.1	53.6	55.7	71.9
2309	PA2283_at	17.9	5.3	7.2	12.1	23.4
2310	PA2284_at	18.1	8.4	4.8	25.2	4.2
2311	PA2285_at	127.6	67.3	61.5	68.5	55.1
2312	PA2286_at	104.4	92.0	77.6	59.0	52.4
2313	PA2287_at	86.2	167.8	90.4	43.9	37.2
2314	PA2288_r_at	2048.6	1023.3	1048.4	975.5	951.7
2315	PA2289_at	79.9	111.2	33.7	35.4	42.7
2316	PA2290_gcd_at	219.0	356.7	245.4	218.1	267.6
2317	PA3186_oprB_s_at	1150.9	4176.4	1243.7	1084.3	978.4
2318	PA2292_at	7.1	29.9	22.2	30.0	8.0
2319	PA2293_at	5.5	2.2	2.5	3.8	3.0
2320	PA2294_at	82.5	50.3	58.2	47.7	48.9
2321	PA2295_at	74.8	18.0	22.9	22.8	10.9
2322	PA2296_at	14.0	20.3	14.9	11.2	18.6
2323	PA2297_at	290.4	75.7	51.2	53.9	69.7
2324	PA2298_at	292.9	90.4	116.9	99.7	112.5
2325	PA2299_at	168.4	84.2	74.2	92.8	84.0
2326	PA2300_chiC_at	53.7	63.4	50.7	48.5	46.2
2327	PA2301_at	185.2	131.0	169.1	217.3	212.1
2328	PA2302_at	89.6	138.2	147.3	151.0	145.4
2329	PA2303_at	6.9	188.5	79.6	87.4	92.0
2330	PA2304_at	164.7	248.5	120.1	143.3	236.7
2331	PA2305_at	161.0	227.8	208.0	219.3	200.7
2332	PA2306_at	246.1	150.5	702.3	579.4	582.0

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2333	PA2307_at	135.8	17.9	5.2	31.7	18.2
2334	PA2308_at	86.3	36.4	56.5	3.9	22.7
2335	PA2309_at	236.1	30.0	20.5	23.9	23.6
2336	PA2310_at	400.7	32.2	4.3	17.7	20.8
2337	PA2311_r_at	1774.0	121.6	70.4	43.3	82.6
2338	PA2312_at	581.2	19.2	48.4	46.4	61.0
2339	PA2313_at	61.8	35.0	36.9	17.4	22.2
2340	PA2314_at	57.6	8.5	32.5	11.4	22.8
2341	PA2315_at	45.1	21.9	24.1	47.7	26.8
2342	PA2316_at	92.5	40.2	68.4	82.8	93.7
2343	PA2317_at	69.7	65.1	67.5	51.9	36.6
2344	PA2318_at	127.1	59.9	51.8	45.6	49.4
2345	PA2320_gntR_at	2660.1	1984.8	2217.5	2257.0	2267.0
2346	PA2321_at	4174.3	2644.3	4313.6	3717.1	4073.9
2347	PA2322_at	2313.7	2674.2	2803.0	2624.4	2542.1
2348	PA2323_at	469.8	1151.9	975.7	886.0	1030.7
2349	PA2324_at	88.3	21.1	24.1	26.1	16.3
2350	PA2325_at	82.0	67.9	56.2	39.6	46.9
2351	PA2326_at	51.0	20.6	26.3	11.0	35.5
2352	PA2327_at	98.1	16.0	54.1	71.9	39.0
2353	PA2328_at	146.8	91.0	41.7	55.4	77.3
2354	PA2329_at	107.8	43.2	46.8	59.2	53.1
2355	PA2330_at	213.8	51.7	59.8	80.0	141.3
2356	PA2331_at	418.5	75.9	126.4	134.5	296.2
2357	PA2332_at	364.6	207.5	192.9	232.2	276.9
2358	PA2333_at	134.5	33.5	53.5	51.9	69.5
2359	PA2334_at	232.6	29.7	37.0	38.7	60.6
2360	PA2335_at	16.0	16.9	2.8	2.3	2.9
2361	PA2336_at	7.7	22.1	21.5	21.7	8.6
2362	PA2337_mtLR_at	145.0	91.6	99.0	123.1	134.2
2363	PA2338_at	130.6	60.9	41.0	54.7	54.8
2364	PA2339_at	13.1	41.2	33.5	43.6	31.7
2365	PA2340_at	58.4	34.9	27.1	31.6	17.6
2366	PA2341_at	74.7	52.3	30.0	47.9	30.5
2367	PA2342_mtLD_at	45.5	25.1	14.2	27.1	20.6
2368	PA2343_mtLY_at	9.9	5.7	11.9	16.3	12.1
2369	PA2344_mtLZ_at	124.8	80.2	183.2	144.5	147.1
2370	PA2345_at	122.9	86.9	174.5	135.2	144.2
2371	PA2346_at	11.5	8.4	7.7	24.6	5.3
2372	PA2347_at	40.5	70.4	35.3	44.6	47.1
2373	PA2348_at	7.1	5.2	4.8	29.3	12.8
2374	PA2349_at	111.9	59.8	64.1	53.4	44.4
2375	PA2350_at	62.7	28.0	54.5	43.0	27.2
2376	PA2351_at	127.1	51.3	59.0	41.6	55.7
2377	PA2352_at	18.7	26.9	22.7	34.1	22.7
2378	PA2353_at	39.2	22.8	50.2	43.3	38.9
2379	PA2354_at	57.9	27.6	41.0	8.9	31.0
2380	PA2355_at	44.6	47.1	29.0	53.2	16.6
2381	PA2356_msuD_at	31.1	13.6	41.8	33.7	13.6
2382	PA2357_msuE_at	60.2	33.2	6.2	22.5	20.2
2383	PA2358_at	449.5	301.0	117.7	131.7	123.6
2384	PA2359_at	1176.3	19.8	6.6	32.8	49.5
2385	PA2360_at	14.7	77.7	72.5	78.7	76.2
2386	PA2361_at	57.2	34.1	20.5	33.6	20.5
2387	PA2362_at	13.8	40.9	58.9	78.0	51.9
2388	PA2363_at	98.4	56.9	109.8	121.8	129.4
2389	PA2364_at	196.5	198.1	256.3	291.6	260.2
2390	PA2365_at	212.9	204.0	338.4	262.4	336.7
2391	PA2366_at	113.8	152.2	229.1	294.7	235.2
2392	PA2367_at	37.8	50.3	86.1	69.4	58.3
2393	PA2368_i_at	98.4	73.1	147.1	119.1	93.0
2394	PA2369_at	13.3	40.2	26.9	33.6	22.3
2395	PA2370_at	12.7	22.2	17.4	33.4	31.0
2396	PA2371_at	37.4	64.3	65.8	39.0	30.0
2397	PA2372_at	52.3	44.8	29.9	45.7	51.5
2398	PA2373_at	151.1	80.4	138.3	115.9	110.0
2399	PA2374_at	79.7	27.9	38.0	41.0	40.6
2400	PA2375_i_at	191.8	114.5	123.7	127.1	140.2
2401	PA2376_at	55.2	45.9	36.6	51.3	36.8
2402	PA2377_at	99.6	65.0	18.5	86.9	32.7
2403	PA2378_at	137.6	224.9	224.3	242.5	220.8
2404	PA2379_at	199.8	267.1	354.4	266.8	336.9
2405	PA2380_at	183.7	199.8	299.2	244.7	299.7

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2406	PA2381_at	130.5	123.0	335.5	354.8	407.1
2407	PA2382_lldA_at	92.1	59.0	64.6	62.9	48.6
2408	PA2383_at	220.8	92.8	251.8	264.6	294.5
2409	PA2384_at	401.0	132.0	328.3	284.8	281.3
2410	PA2385_at	164.9	119.0	14.7	36.3	35.5
2411	PA2386_pvdA_at	378.4	131.1	85.3	67.7	83.4
2412	PA2387_at	48.7	64.5	63.6	79.4	97.8
2413	PA2388_at	365.7	437.2	317.0	341.5	361.4
2414	PA2389_at	211.5	169.0	117.1	109.1	138.3
2415	PA2390_at	152.0	134.3	93.7	73.6	81.3
2416	PA2391_at	206.9	244.6	64.2	81.1	48.7
2417	PA2392_at	34.9	62.6	11.2	29.2	26.6
2418	PA2393_at	114.4	80.9	27.4	27.5	24.6
2419	PA2394_at	147.2	177.1	59.3	54.4	29.2
2420	PA2395_at	202.1	163.3	24.1	37.7	6.0
2421	PA2396_at	330.4	391.5	79.5	79.8	71.4
2422	PA2397_pvdE_at	79.8	64.6	52.1	36.9	25.8
2423	PA2398_fpvA_at	831.9	612.4	793.0	604.6	629.9
2424	PA2399_pvdD_at	831.9	929.1	46.3	49.8	55.3
2425	PA2400_at	1746.2	1395.1	39.2	36.2	32.1
2426	PA2401_at	1340.4	1347.1	42.7	37.9	32.0
2427	PA2402_at	1580.2	1519.5	25.9	57.4	43.0
2428	PA2403_at	276.0	94.7	239.5	217.6	246.1
2429	PA2404_at	224.3	94.0	171.4	149.2	116.4
2430	PA2405_at	137.9	51.0	85.4	79.2	85.3
2431	PA2406_at	151.0	60.0	66.9	47.3	48.6
2432	PA2407_at	290.6	139.8	164.2	113.5	118.2
2433	PA2408_at	93.5	14.2	10.2	30.7	25.7
2434	PA2409_at	118.9	57.2	61.0	86.9	106.1
2435	PA2410_at	146.8	110.3	99.7	78.5	95.6
2436	PA2411_at	222.8	279.3	24.2	19.7	11.0
2437	PA2412_at	427.4	379.7	50.5	44.5	53.7
2438	PA2413_at	299.5	263.1	18.2	21.9	4.8
2439	PA2414_at	41.1	32.3	43.4	47.2	42.3
2440	PA2415_at	90.8	56.1	120.8	96.0	88.5
2441	PA2416_treA_at	107.3	86.8	84.0	60.8	59.8
2442	PA2417_at	122.9	59.7	133.0	165.0	199.8
2443	PA2418_at	57.7	23.6	32.6	31.3	10.1
2444	PA2419_at	64.6	48.5	4.7	10.0	3.7
2445	PA2420_at	6.4	5.7	8.2	13.8	5.0
2446	PA2421_at	54.8	28.9	31.7	64.6	28.2
2447	PA2422_at	83.6	65.6	57.0	36.7	40.5
2448	PA2423_at	527.9	398.1	441.3	488.3	521.5
2449	PA2424_at	857.8	544.7	37.3	14.8	4.7
2450	PA2425_at	112.7	26.2	35.8	41.0	25.7
2451	PA2426_pvdS_at	1107.7	430.1	617.2	296.9	396.0
2452	PA2427_at	121.4	58.3	37.9	16.7	9.0
2453	PA2428_at	130.8	46.0	36.2	69.3	61.5
2454	PA2429_at	107.2	51.7	30.6	29.4	23.1
2455	PA2430_at	46.4	57.2	70.9	37.6	38.9
2456	PA2431_at	5.3	32.6	43.5	43.2	24.1
2457	PA2432_at	93.7	148.1	113.5	129.5	122.1
2458	PA2433_at	167.5	159.5	118.9	109.6	127.5
2459	PA2434_at	122.9	55.5	45.8	48.2	54.8
2460	PA2435_at	60.3	98.5	75.7	65.8	62.5
2461	PA2436_at	129.1	75.3	96.7	96.1	101.5
2462	PA2437_at	94.3	93.3	61.1	49.1	49.1
2463	PA2438_at	7.6	8.3	17.2	26.6	11.3
2464	PA2439_at	13.4	1.7	29.1	6.8	10.3
2465	PA2440_at	93.9	43.6	61.7	53.7	56.3
2466	PA2441_at	9.7	75.2	16.6	25.9	29.1
2467	PA2442_gcvT2_at	173.7	682.0	232.1	203.5	275.0
2468	PA2443_sdaA_at	170.9	594.0	196.3	248.1	267.3
2469	PA2444_glyA2_at	68.9	636.1	117.6	136.3	152.6
2470	PA2445_gcvP2_at	458.6	2170.4	826.3	788.3	733.6
2471	PA2446_gcvH2_at	471.9	575.9	1099.7	1013.4	1098.5
2472	PA2447_at	12.3	50.7	76.8	77.8	84.8
2473	PA2448_at	14.7	73.7	98.7	65.6	85.7
2474	PA2449_at	10.0	39.3	48.0	47.6	40.1
2475	PA2450_at	372.1	197.8	261.9	256.2	246.3
2476	PA2451_at	269.7	264.3	57.0	47.6	73.5
2477	PA2452_at	204.8	383.1	49.8	51.8	61.0
2478	PA2453_at	257.0	345.9	176.9	214.6	210.9

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2479	PA2454_at	58.8	33.0	48.0	54.5	53.0
2480	PA2455_at	63.7	84.6	101.8	61.9	76.3
2481	PA2456_at	225.4	344.6	155.6	194.1	181.2
2482	PA2457_at	364.5	225.6	347.5	415.0	454.6
2483	PA2458_at	27.1	35.2	49.3	26.4	55.5
2484	PA2459_at	131.8	132.5	83.6	108.8	86.0
2485	PA2460_i_at	230.8	201.7	330.6	440.0	436.2
2486	PA2461_at	39.8	72.3	127.7	162.6	161.3
2487	PA2462_at	405.2	718.9	417.6	438.0	430.7
2488	PA2464_at	586.3	266.5	804.4	569.4	776.6
2489	PA2465_at	8.6	21.3	3.2	15.8	1.2
2490	PA2466_at	108.0	38.9	80.0	63.9	80.0
2491	PA2467_at	286.2	142.0	266.7	241.4	239.5
2492	PA2468_at	542.0	210.0	210.2	163.9	115.7
2493	PA2469_at	121.8	72.3	72.6	108.6	78.7
2494	PA2470_gtdA_at	10.1	8.9	59.5	28.4	38.7
2495	PA2471_at	18.4	24.3	7.9	33.9	32.7
2496	PA2472_at	7.7	4.3	4.9	2.8	3.4
2497	PA2473_at	8.4	5.2	8.7	16.4	4.5
2498	PA2474_at	10.0	15.2	18.7	11.3	8.3
2499	PA2475_at	87.7	50.2	58.1	66.9	65.6
2500	PA2476_dsbG_at	126.0	201.6	106.0	118.8	96.2
2501	PA2477_at	135.0	83.6	69.6	39.6	52.6
2502	PA2478_at	56.1	31.2	9.4	37.8	15.1
2503	PA2479_at	156.0	106.8	109.7	110.3	103.5
2504	PA2480_at	10.8	16.1	30.9	28.3	33.0
2505	PA2481_at	419.3	340.7	309.5	404.7	153.1
2506	PA2482_at	637.1	353.4	398.5	545.9	255.3
2507	PA2483_at	892.3	709.6	641.5	630.2	547.9
2508	PA2484_at	308.1	243.4	262.7	265.6	294.2
2509	PA2485_at	603.4	413.2	244.3	358.6	314.5
2510	PA2486_at	378.4	223.7	167.0	174.8	185.8
2511	PA2487_i_at	130.5	95.1	71.4	85.5	68.2
2512	PA2488_at	94.1	76.7	106.3	104.4	104.9
2513	PA2489_at	145.1	82.6	145.8	109.6	131.4
2514	PA2490_at	76.1	25.3	76.3	64.5	60.3
2515	PA2491_at	179.1	170.5	271.2	284.0	332.7
2516	PA2492_mexT_at	202.9	175.6	222.8	210.1	219.9
2517	PA2493_mexE_at	32.0	5.9	27.2	33.0	29.0
2518	PA2494_mexF_at	10.0	5.3	4.7	14.6	19.1
2519	PA2495_oprN_at	38.8	25.6	20.7	35.1	7.0
2520	PA2496_at	37.6	11.2	29.7	37.7	39.7
2521	PA2497_at	156.8	60.9	83.3	81.3	51.8
2522	PA2498_at	101.0	85.6	102.3	119.3	112.5
2523	PA2499_at	11.9	48.3	30.6	51.1	53.0
2524	PA2500_at	111.6	46.2	44.3	66.5	45.3
2525	PA2501_at	336.3	648.0	338.7	359.1	382.7
2526	PA2502_at	9.6	36.8	46.3	49.9	31.3
2527	PA2503_at	124.5	84.3	92.8	76.4	81.1
2528	PA2504_at	77.5	127.4	137.4	147.9	153.4
2529	PA2505_at	79.8	40.5	53.3	41.6	27.7
2530	PA2506_at	68.7	57.5	49.0	39.4	51.4
2531	PA2507_catA_at	4.2	31.6	50.0	44.9	42.2
2532	PA2508_catC_at	77.3	30.0	22.6	37.6	28.3
2533	PA2509_catB_at	52.5	26.9	4.8	2.3	9.5
2534	PA2510_catR_at	87.9	69.7	64.3	82.4	83.2
2535	PA2511_at	38.7	19.4	17.6	59.1	46.7
2536	PA2512_antA_at	5.8	8.3	4.3	13.7	6.4
2537	PA2513_antB_at	47.8	30.1	25.0	34.9	25.2
2538	PA2514_antC_at	43.3	16.3	5.6	25.6	2.4
2539	PA2515_xylL_at	37.7	20.9	42.1	25.4	41.1
2540	PA2516_xylZ_at	13.8	5.5	5.9	23.5	19.6
2541	PA2517_xylY_at	58.2	28.5	45.4	47.7	37.5
2542	PA2518_xylX_at	7.4	4.2	5.9	17.8	4.6
2543	PA2519_xylS_at	121.5	87.2	114.6	216.5	188.3
2544	PA2520_czcA_at	42.9	33.4	22.1	32.6	43.3
2545	PA2521_czcB_at	38.2	20.9	35.7	26.2	47.8
2546	PA2522_czcC_at	49.9	23.3	5.0	18.3	24.8
2547	PA2523_at	229.3	140.6	204.2	203.9	240.1
2548	PA2524_at	137.9	126.8	179.7	151.2	124.0
2549	PA2525_at	85.9	210.7	79.6	96.7	87.8
2550	PA2526_at	87.5	181.9	76.7	73.9	98.8
2551	PA2527_at	88.8	71.1	87.6	64.0	49.8

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2552	PA2528_at	141.1	128.0	171.2	176.3	159.3
2553	PA2529_at	100.9	72.6	200.5	145.6	252.2
2554	PA2530_at	184.1	249.0	181.6	155.6	136.1
2555	PA2531_at	117.5	52.5	45.4	54.2	61.0
2556	PA2532_tpx_at	305.1	224.2	724.1	582.7	576.3
2557	PA2533_at	92.4	69.6	160.5	112.2	106.5
2558	PA2534_at	69.0	20.6	54.3	50.7	40.4
2559	PA2535_at	18.1	43.0	33.9	43.4	25.4
2560	PA2536_at	82.3	61.0	54.0	60.9	57.9
2561	PA2537_at	134.8	156.0	134.3	158.4	156.9
2562	PA2538_at	253.1	139.4	112.1	111.4	116.5
2563	PA2539_at	37.5	37.6	28.0	27.7	17.5
2564	PA2540_at	191.2	182.1	203.7	223.4	195.5
2565	PA2541_at	164.1	109.2	301.7	299.8	312.7
2566	PA2542_at	21.1	54.4	45.8	59.5	51.1
2567	PA2543_at	162.0	53.5	91.0	133.1	124.9
2568	PA2544_at	58.7	21.3	93.3	100.3	57.0
2569	PA2545_xthA_at	151.3	117.5	235.9	202.4	237.6
2570	PA2546_at	50.8	42.9	37.3	42.9	45.5
2571	PA2547_at	9.1	6.9	47.2	35.3	45.1
2572	PA2548_at	7.6	10.0	10.8	19.2	31.9
2573	PA2549_at	107.8	63.8	38.4	57.9	49.6
2574	PA2550_at	85.8	104.6	380.3	162.0	99.4
2575	PA2551_at	291.3	370.8	477.2	307.3	358.6
2576	PA2552_at	843.3	921.7	1057.1	1304.8	1253.0
2577	PA2553_at	1044.8	1642.7	2131.2	2136.2	1976.2
2578	PA2554_at	1088.6	1575.8	1697.3	1673.2	1806.5
2579	PA2555_at	499.2	740.6	631.6	915.7	872.8
2580	PA2556_at	225.0	134.1	254.8	215.9	179.7
2581	PA2557_at	491.8	428.3	1126.7	1113.0	1206.6
2582	PA2558_at	7.1	41.1	37.7	42.6	44.3
2583	PA2559_at	510.2	361.9	696.0	769.4	806.7
2584	PA2560_at	581.5	777.8	503.6	510.3	564.7
2585	PA2561_at	101.5	83.9	73.2	60.9	42.3
2586	PA2562_at	481.5	396.9	394.9	410.3	420.1
2587	PA2563_at	53.1	5.1	40.0	27.2	21.7
2588	PA2564_at	81.7	22.4	7.3	35.6	41.3
2589	PA2565_at	120.3	73.0	95.7	129.6	131.3
2590	PA2566_at	26.2	22.1	26.1	28.5	29.8
2591	PA2567_at	264.6	228.2	178.5	223.1	192.0
2592	PA2568_at	153.1	74.2	123.5	119.1	114.8
2593	PA2569_at	90.6	121.6	89.7	83.2	84.2
2594	PA2570_pa1L_at	9.3	15.8	20.8	36.5	34.1
2595	PA2571_at	5.6	58.9	91.6	97.6	88.7
2596	PA2572_at	150.2	92.6	227.4	268.8	269.4
2597	PA2573_at	174.4	189.3	237.0	244.8	244.8
2598	PA2574_at	5.4	86.9	121.6	119.0	65.1
2599	PA2575_at	258.6	262.0	656.1	602.8	670.2
2600	PA2576_at	86.3	75.6	129.1	102.0	116.2
2601	PA2577_at	480.3	430.3	366.4	476.4	442.9
2602	PA2578_at	160.2	104.4	110.9	141.0	136.4
2603	PA2579_at	217.7	119.3	229.2	234.6	195.2
2604	PA2580_at	57.3	79.0	92.0	67.8	63.4
2605	PA2581_at	324.9	241.3	319.5	221.4	269.2
2606	PA2582_at	451.2	372.1	793.9	798.3	881.2
2607	PA2583_at	164.8	133.9	125.2	118.6	114.4
2608	PA2584_pgsA_at	311.4	217.0	526.5	544.1	504.0
2609	PA2585_uvrC_at	132.0	170.9	210.7	219.7	189.9
2610	PA2586_gacA_at	1116.9	1074.1	1083.1	1110.7	1028.2
2611	PA2587_at	159.1	253.1	556.3	495.3	473.2
2612	PA2588_at	251.2	214.5	242.7	321.5	385.6
2613	PA2589_at	91.5	55.7	46.0	39.3	27.7
2614	PA2590_at	51.5	39.4	43.6	38.1	34.7
2615	PA2591_at	336.4	223.7	276.2	329.9	331.2
2616	PA2592_at	206.6	224.4	343.9	332.7	437.4
2617	PA2593_at	26.0	10.4	20.4	36.5	35.4
2618	PA2594_at	486.3	49.7	43.1	63.8	133.8
2619	PA2595_at	192.2	44.7	38.5	43.9	78.3
2620	PA2596_at	304.7	21.2	35.6	28.6	80.2
2621	PA2597_at	1268.3	376.1	130.6	163.0	479.4
2622	PA2598_at	2007.4	308.3	85.9	81.1	271.8
2623	PA2599_at	2008.2	242.5	92.0	88.6	308.4
2624	PA2600_at	1775.7	135.7	74.8	67.9	186.2

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2625	PA2601_at	171.0	137.0	156.2	143.5	186.6
2626	PA2602_at	808.8	52.8	90.3	64.4	97.6
2627	PA2603_at	521.6	69.3	70.9	76.7	87.8
2628	PA2604_at	1307.3	964.5	1144.0	1348.7	1295.7
2629	PA2605_at	299.7	187.1	354.3	321.4	339.8
2630	PA2606_at	602.0	531.3	565.1	614.6	647.4
2631	PA2607_at	243.7	168.1	295.0	320.0	331.8
2632	PA2608_at	249.8	190.6	276.2	411.0	339.4
2633	PA2609_at	222.2	190.0	199.5	185.1	146.1
2634	PA2610_at	27.8	29.9	47.0	48.1	22.8
2635	PA2611_cysG_at	194.4	173.5	132.2	180.5	125.5
2636	PA2612_serS_at	1260.2	1443.6	1148.0	1162.2	1065.4
2637	PA2613_at	427.6	378.2	401.8	428.5	411.4
2638	PA2614_lolA_at	837.9	816.5	768.9	760.3	751.2
2639	PA2615_ftsK_at	1001.6	627.1	920.8	868.2	807.9
2640	PA2616_trxB1_at	1597.3	1074.7	1335.1	1186.0	1187.0
2641	PA2617_aat_at	204.0	139.5	172.8	201.9	175.7
2642	PA2618_at	271.8	337.6	153.4	148.4	161.4
2643	PA2619_infA_at	214.6	236.7	246.1	218.7	274.3
2644	PA2620_clpA_at	1278.6	1281.1	1088.6	1189.7	1208.2
2645	PA2621_at	1554.4	2200.3	1509.1	1419.6	1507.3
2646	PA2622_cspD_at	230.5	383.2	577.5	570.6	609.7
2647	PA2623_icd_at	458.8	959.8	920.6	892.9	892.7
2648	PA2624_idh_at	1140.7	2609.9	1437.4	1296.4	1292.8
2649	PA2625_at	66.2	175.5	79.1	84.0	113.7
2650	PA2626_trmU_at	434.1	376.0	707.3	622.4	614.8
2651	PA2627_at	220.1	270.6	292.8	231.7	267.3
2652	PA2628_at	88.0	95.3	49.2	43.4	33.7
2653	PA2629_purB_at	73.0	109.0	139.6	157.5	201.6
2654	PA2630_at	27.4	86.4	46.2	33.6	29.4
2655	PA2631_at	661.5	1258.1	741.2	968.5	1037.6
2656	PA2632_at	280.1	346.2	254.2	262.6	241.6
2657	PA2633_at	300.7	468.7	362.5	352.2	371.9
2658	PA2634_at	385.0	635.7	413.6	359.3	390.3
2659	PA2635_at	22.5	44.6	19.0	15.1	25.8
2660	PA2636_at	10.4	37.5	38.5	34.9	42.8
2661	PA2637_nuoA_at	87.4	63.0	314.7	416.2	285.2
2662	PA2638_nuoB_at	139.7	273.9	297.4	309.9	309.4
2663	PA2639_nuoD_at	133.9	534.9	128.7	102.9	113.2
2664	PA2640_nuoE_at	192.5	1307.9	181.4	174.0	178.7
2665	PA2641_nuoF_at	235.6	1118.0	249.6	216.7	243.6
2666	PA2642_nuoG_at	448.8	1446.9	473.7	381.8	499.3
2667	PA2643_nuoH_at	716.1	1557.7	549.1	507.6	543.5
2668	PA2644_nuoI_at	359.1	1591.4	371.9	415.8	489.2
2669	PA2645_nuoJ_at	330.9	931.5	367.1	397.0	392.8
2670	PA2646_nuoK_at	669.5	1226.7	748.1	788.9	816.6
2671	PA2647_nuoL_at	492.6	693.5	473.0	554.4	557.9
2672	PA2648_nuoM_at	560.5	1261.1	425.8	465.9	363.5
2673	PA2649_nuoN_at	406.2	822.0	331.5	346.8	328.9
2674	PA2650_at	85.5	54.2	42.1	35.7	45.1
2675	PA2651_at	88.7	79.5	254.5	149.7	193.0
2676	PA2652_at	192.2	169.8	301.5	341.2	350.5
2677	PA2653_at	48.5	13.5	16.6	36.8	33.1
2678	PA2654_at	339.9	251.9	509.3	513.7	490.3
2679	PA2655_i_at	88.1	25.1	6.3	30.2	18.1
2680	PA2656_at	79.1	45.1	69.2	54.0	50.4
2681	PA2657_at	97.0	60.9	154.9	144.7	154.0
2682	PA2658_at	240.6	167.5	287.0	243.4	222.6
2683	PA2659_at	341.9	287.1	267.5	244.4	282.7
2684	PA2660_at	16.2	51.7	91.9	86.4	108.8
2685	PA2661_at	7.2	33.4	49.2	42.5	40.7
2686	PA2662_at	65.2	52.7	41.4	55.1	36.0
2687	PA2663_at	98.9	34.8	63.9	42.6	47.9
2688	PA2664_fhp_at	37.0	44.2	37.2	29.0	63.1
2689	PA2665_at	306.0	253.7	189.0	206.6	244.9
2690	PA2666_at	108.4	86.5	153.4	194.0	172.3
2691	PA2667_at	1652.3	1977.4	1289.4	1352.6	1296.2
2692	PA2668_at	153.4	112.7	131.9	181.6	151.6
2693	PA2669_at	37.0	26.1	22.4	29.3	37.4
2694	PA2670_at	37.4	13.2	39.7	49.6	33.5
2695	PA2671_at	71.3	28.9	49.1	30.0	28.8
2696	PA2672_at	52.5	34.0	35.0	18.7	27.1
2697	PA2673_at	80.6	17.7	29.9	38.9	40.1

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2698	PA2674_at	63.8	18.9	32.1	24.6	9.9
2699	PA2675_at	103.2	62.9	59.0	42.0	54.8
2700	PA2676_at	9.5	4.8	12.8	32.2	10.5
2701	PA2677_at	51.3	3.8	4.9	32.0	7.1
2702	PA2678_at	14.2	38.4	23.8	34.4	26.5
2703	PA2679_at	50.2	70.1	66.4	72.7	56.7
2704	PA2680_at	42.3	11.3	4.0	25.7	12.6
2705	PA2681_at	46.7	34.2	80.1	57.1	61.8
2706	PA2682_at	84.9	36.6	133.2	95.7	107.9
2707	PA2683_at	82.3	82.8	47.9	66.4	68.9
2708	PA2684_at	84.6	146.8	83.1	95.7	78.0
2709	PA2685_at	202.4	109.0	181.4	240.5	151.6
2710	PA2686_pfeR_at	854.3	1050.6	238.1	198.8	217.4
2711	PA2687_pfeS_at	853.2	876.2	538.6	552.7	608.6
2712	PA2688_pfeA_at	132.1	58.4	53.6	56.8	53.2
2713	PA2689_at	38.3	10.1	29.2	52.7	15.1
2714	PA2691_at	47.2	66.0	66.5	68.4	58.9
2715	PA2692_at	321.0	141.1	317.0	252.9	239.6
2716	PA2693_at	62.0	41.7	101.0	74.0	95.3
2717	PA2694_at	22.4	41.6	47.3	52.9	40.8
2718	PA2695_at	67.1	21.1	65.1	65.4	44.6
2719	PA2696_at	66.8	45.8	62.9	63.5	59.7
2720	PA2697_at	65.9	26.6	51.2	45.2	38.9
2721	PA2698_at	53.9	79.2	78.3	88.9	73.6
2722	PA2699_at	43.4	16.8	17.8	48.0	30.0
2723	PA2700_at	11.3	46.5	53.5	40.3	48.2
2724	PA2701_at	56.6	9.0	9.5	5.0	17.8
2725	PA2702_at	173.2	92.2	157.6	168.6	151.4
2726	PA2703_at	82.1	38.2	96.1	84.9	85.4
2727	PA2704_at	13.4	41.7	33.7	21.1	14.5
2728	PA2705_at	135.9	107.7	133.4	223.4	163.2
2729	PA2706_at	363.6	332.7	498.9	466.0	434.6
2730	PA2707_at	800.0	974.9	918.7	828.7	837.9
2731	PA2708_at	15.6	33.9	37.8	41.2	44.5
2732	PA2709_cysK_at	619.4	334.7	902.9	845.8	874.1
2733	PA2710_at	109.7	73.1	149.7	219.9	193.3
2734	PA2711_at	274.0	249.5	403.4	344.9	325.5
2735	PA2712_at	148.8	131.8	194.3	164.0	146.2
2736	PA2713_at	149.2	106.1	148.6	166.8	203.7
2737	PA2714_at	60.6	27.2	22.9	27.9	27.5
2738	PA2715_at	4.2	12.0	1.3	0.6	17.5
2739	PA2716_at	34.5	12.0	21.8	7.1	34.0
2740	PA2717_cpo_at	15.4	34.3	45.1	46.4	45.6
2741	PA2718_at	227.4	90.9	359.7	316.4	324.5
2742	PA2719_at	14.4	25.7	50.6	42.7	48.5
2743	PA2720_at	27.2	22.6	126.7	89.9	69.3
2744	PA2721_at	75.1	20.8	38.5	15.8	49.7
2745	PA2722_at	12.3	14.4	25.3	45.0	38.0
2746	PA2723_at	373.7	335.2	284.2	347.4	371.9
2747	PA2724_r_at	296.0	144.9	244.0	229.4	210.8
2748	PA2725_at	419.3	328.6	376.5	298.8	244.1
2749	PA2726_at	255.9	192.2	166.9	161.4	148.4
2750	PA2727_at	254.7	165.6	115.1	228.6	155.5
2751	PA2728_at	142.2	370.8	157.8	163.4	174.1
2752	PA2729_at	192.6	370.7	156.1	173.5	176.9
2753	PA2730_at	356.8	559.0	431.5	511.5	397.2
2754	PA2731_at	326.3	502.0	422.6	516.8	533.0
2755	PA2732_at	145.9	431.9	191.7	188.0	264.6
2756	PA2733_at	351.5	735.7	294.9	418.3	369.0
2757	PA2734_at	391.3	481.5	272.1	247.5	258.6
2758	PA2735_at	221.3	298.5	372.7	444.0	443.6
2759	PA2736_at	502.3	275.2	636.2	616.5	582.8
2760	PA2737_at	2503.5	2458.7	1739.3	1518.0	1880.6
2761	PA2738_himA_at	4800.5	6527.8	3562.2	3425.3	3767.0
2762	PA2739_pheT_at	299.4	585.2	210.2	189.1	192.4
2763	PA2740_pheS_at	211.1	350.7	297.5	231.3	219.6
2764	PA2741_rplT_at	801.5	1056.4	722.2	752.6	733.3
2765	PA2742_rpmI_at	9556.3	9144.0	3700.5	3768.3	4120.3
2766	PA2743_infC_at	3448.6	4412.5	3668.3	4173.4	4208.8
2767	PA2744_thrS_at	270.3	316.8	462.4	353.1	418.7
2768	PA2745_at	15.5	63.5	83.8	83.2	66.4
2769	PA2746_at	60.3	67.2	25.0	38.3	27.2
2770	PA2747_at	114.3	91.2	102.9	108.6	105.2

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2771	PA2748_at	63.9	64.1	112.4	118.4	134.5
2772	PA2749_endA_at	89.4	48.0	42.5	36.8	50.3
2773	PA2750_at	20.0	14.1	77.0	59.4	68.1
2774	PA2751_at	98.7	70.6	86.8	67.6	55.7
2775	PA2752_at	44.7	35.3	28.5	17.8	7.7
2776	PA2753_at	57.5	35.1	27.8	18.8	36.5
2777	PA2754_at	345.3	249.9	174.6	218.4	210.8
2778	PA2755_eco_at	289.2	227.2	360.8	378.6	354.7
2779	PA2756_at	245.2	263.2	323.2	403.8	396.3
2780	PA2757_at	39.9	24.9	143.7	108.9	108.5
2781	PA2758_at	155.2	113.1	139.4	121.7	129.3
2782	PA2759_at	66.0	33.9	37.3	39.9	46.6
2783	PA2760_at	2034.8	4362.5	1538.4	1537.0	1402.9
2784	PA2761_at	189.6	61.2	130.7	110.0	141.9
2785	PA2762_at	45.0	48.6	65.4	57.5	35.1
2786	PA2763_at	72.8	37.0	22.4	29.3	16.0
2787	PA2764_at	23.7	41.4	45.1	55.6	59.9
2788	PA2765_at	66.5	148.4	142.9	153.9	158.5
2789	PA2766_at	69.1	47.8	135.8	94.0	104.2
2790	PA2767_at	16.0	51.2	38.4	40.5	30.8
2791	PA2768_at	7.8	6.4	47.7	24.7	36.0
2792	PA2769_at	7.2	23.7	28.0	23.0	27.4
2793	PA2770_at	50.8	71.6	62.9	66.9	92.1
2794	PA2771_at	61.8	80.9	91.6	102.9	83.8
2795	PA2772_at	44.0	18.6	14.5	25.7	30.1
2796	PA2773_at	22.6	27.8	39.0	30.6	29.4
2797	PA2774_at	98.3	66.8	142.9	158.4	136.9
2798	PA2775_at	104.9	64.5	130.2	126.1	143.0
2799	PA2776_at	1305.2	683.6	1050.0	1194.0	1139.7
2800	PA2777_at	84.7	65.4	80.5	68.3	64.0
2801	PA2778_at	85.7	59.0	95.6	99.7	99.3
2802	PA2779_at	256.0	394.7	272.4	354.0	278.5
2803	PA2780_at	90.9	59.9	93.9	77.7	76.6
2804	PA2781_at	47.9	98.6	131.3	87.5	97.5
2805	PA2782_at	42.1	39.1	45.9	36.2	34.2
2806	PA2783_at	64.4	70.9	75.2	63.2	58.0
2807	PA2784_at	62.5	31.6	42.3	57.1	42.6
2808	PA2785_at	16.8	30.1	35.0	32.3	20.8
2809	PA2786_at	145.9	30.2	29.1	41.8	70.2
2810	PA2787_cpg2_at	9.8	3.5	5.1	14.8	8.8
2811	PA2788_at	176.8	155.2	277.0	267.7	269.9
2812	PA2789_at	82.3	41.8	25.7	65.5	51.7
2813	PA2790_at	93.3	70.8	118.6	92.2	110.7
2814	PA2791_at	27.8	9.4	37.4	29.4	17.5
2815	PA2792_at	8.0	37.2	47.4	47.1	35.1
2816	PA2793_at	68.6	94.9	177.4	136.7	113.8
2817	PA2794_at	85.1	58.9	71.9	92.2	106.1
2818	PA2795_at	19.6	26.0	68.5	66.5	79.7
2819	PA2796_tal_at	371.0	209.6	539.8	531.0	537.2
2820	PA2797_at	277.6	281.5	261.6	265.9	284.9
2821	PA2798_at	282.4	191.0	332.4	321.7	323.8
2822	PA2799_at	69.2	94.5	109.4	84.6	88.9
2823	PA2800_at	266.4	329.8	499.9	419.8	443.3
2824	PA2801_at	74.2	54.1	113.6	68.1	72.6
2825	PA2802_at	251.3	132.0	235.9	254.0	246.5
2826	PA2803_at	16.9	13.8	37.7	29.5	23.7
2827	PA2804_at	12.0	9.8	12.5	24.6	7.2
2828	PA2805_at	828.6	1210.3	493.9	577.1	587.0
2829	PA2806_at	12.6	18.5	7.4	31.5	15.0
2830	PA2807_at	138.5	20.7	18.4	98.3	4.1
2831	PA2808_i_at	12.4	22.0	11.8	33.9	23.1
2832	PA2809_at	69.4	57.8	139.1	133.6	116.1
2833	PA2810_at	49.4	58.3	58.8	62.9	57.5
2834	PA2811_at	68.8	38.3	81.4	79.5	59.8
2835	PA2812_at	131.9	96.5	239.0	183.2	160.9
2836	PA2813_at	164.2	128.3	286.3	276.0	197.5
2837	PA2814_at	34.1	35.7	67.0	37.4	56.1
2838	PA2815_at	152.1	94.6	107.9	120.1	111.0
2839	PA2816_i_at	119.8	140.8	108.0	109.4	137.9
2840	PA2817_at	110.7	71.7	116.7	112.6	109.1
2841	PA2818_at	19.4	44.9	62.4	43.0	54.1
2842	PA2819_at	44.1	78.0	11.0	13.2	28.1
2843	PA2820_at	668.7	316.4	1130.8	1022.6	1152.4

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2844	PA2821_at	237.1	192.4	349.7	352.0	311.6
2845	PA2822_at	14.4	70.9	52.6	47.1	46.8
2846	PA2823_at	92.3	125.3	123.6	128.7	135.9
2847	PA2824_at	81.5	46.3	104.1	88.3	55.9
2848	PA2825_at	842.1	668.8	955.5	955.7	878.3
2849	PA2826_at	3658.5	2259.3	3487.4	3599.2	3614.4
2850	PA2827_at	1323.0	910.2	1153.0	1019.4	1100.5
2851	PA2828_at	115.7	146.6	180.8	162.8	157.1
2852	PA2829_at	7.7	25.6	55.8	29.5	38.2
2853	PA2830_htpX_at	608.6	333.2	698.2	762.0	807.5
2854	PA2831_at	78.8	66.8	105.2	97.8	137.7
2855	PA2832_tpm_at	83.6	44.3	100.0	94.1	84.2
2856	PA2833_i_at	18.3	57.2	41.0	50.5	44.5
2857	PA2834_at	210.0	125.5	139.7	64.0	90.3
2858	PA2835_at	13.2	31.4	11.1	16.1	24.5
2859	PA2836_at	67.3	19.4	25.0	20.4	12.2
2860	PA2837_at	48.1	32.4	27.6	24.0	14.7
2861	PA2838_at	6.0	44.8	20.6	32.2	31.9
2862	PA2839_at	109.8	82.5	103.4	103.5	84.3
2863	PA2840_at	319.1	287.9	130.5	133.7	116.0
2864	PA2841_at	53.5	54.9	41.1	104.8	90.8
2865	PA2842_at	55.9	52.6	56.6	46.9	48.8
2866	PA2843_at	1111.4	713.0	1862.6	1701.9	1472.5
2867	PA2844_at	64.9	56.7	70.0	57.3	48.1
2868	PA2845_at	132.1	127.3	53.6	69.5	58.5
2869	PA2846_at	176.5	112.3	102.7	112.5	78.6
2870	PA2847_at	10.8	16.4	24.1	26.9	25.3
2871	PA2848_at	209.9	182.6	169.5	156.1	145.9
2872	PA2849_at	3194.6	1991.6	2420.2	2522.4	2896.5
2873	PA2850_ohr_at	10410.5	4605.9	3867.7	4639.7	6161.0
2874	PA2851_efp_at	171.8	234.2	348.8	287.8	290.2
2875	PA2852_at	92.4	50.4	37.0	67.7	74.1
2876	PA2853_oprI_at	8738.5	8837.9	3943.8	4994.3	4521.0
2877	PA2854_at	895.5	1006.9	770.0	741.1	885.9
2878	PA2855_at	146.1	104.3	171.3	175.8	140.6
2879	PA2856_tesA_at	97.8	45.7	198.5	209.4	164.2
2880	PA2857_at	124.9	47.4	110.0	130.1	137.4
2881	PA2858_at	149.7	58.7	123.0	122.7	130.0
2882	PA2859_greB_at	70.1	92.1	87.4	92.6	83.1
2883	PA2860_at	185.3	94.9	100.0	109.2	160.5
2884	PA2861_ligT_at	73.1	50.5	18.7	24.3	29.8
2885	PA2862_lipA_at	28.4	76.6	136.7	69.5	114.3
2886	PA2863_lipH_at	3.2	6.4	2.2	29.0	20.2
2887	PA2864_at	78.3	54.3	64.9	61.5	72.6
2888	PA2865_at	50.7	33.8	47.8	74.5	61.6
2889	PA2866_mttC_at	172.6	139.9	304.3	224.6	238.7
2890	PA2867_at	610.7	515.5	824.6	706.3	801.3
2891	PA2868_i_at	2035.3	1853.1	1119.6	1048.6	1073.4
2892	PA2869_at	186.9	167.2	140.1	129.1	139.6
2893	PA2870_at	104.7	78.7	127.4	125.7	95.5
2894	PA2871_at	124.7	65.6	151.7	135.2	144.4
2895	PA2872_at	13.1	83.0	61.8	85.5	65.4
2896	PA2873_at	3.8	30.3	20.7	24.2	12.3
2897	PA2874_at	14.5	44.3	28.4	30.4	34.3
2898	PA2875_at	99.6	45.9	79.6	80.8	58.2
2899	PA2876_pyrF_at	79.5	47.7	127.4	73.1	104.2
2900	PA2877_at	83.9	54.0	120.6	110.2	110.3
2901	PA2878_at	84.5	53.5	32.3	41.0	42.2
2902	PA2879_at	282.2	277.4	237.4	246.4	329.9
2903	PA2880_at	96.0	32.2	43.8	40.0	33.5
2904	PA2881_at	67.7	9.6	29.9	34.0	26.1
2905	PA2882_at	56.9	24.5	22.1	34.6	32.7
2906	PA2883_at	509.2	417.5	359.9	431.2	480.3
2907	PA2884_at	153.0	139.1	287.9	207.3	203.7
2908	PA2885_at	278.8	300.7	421.6	459.2	481.9
2909	PA2886_at	32.6	45.5	76.5	66.9	70.1
2910	PA2887_at	66.8	49.7	77.6	52.3	41.3
2911	PA2888_at	32.5	38.3	31.6	42.5	40.6
2912	PA2889_at	94.9	68.6	33.1	49.5	47.1
2913	PA2890_at	10.8	44.7	69.5	45.5	37.2
2914	PA2891_at	29.5	6.0	29.8	23.0	16.6
2915	PA2892_at	41.2	75.7	42.5	40.6	42.5
2916	PA2893_at	73.9	28.7	75.2	53.6	49.1

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2917	PA2894_at	226.6	204.4	377.9	259.2	289.1
2918	PA2895_at	267.6	140.8	148.5	172.8	209.8
2919	PA2896_at	285.4	233.1	259.1	314.6	345.1
2920	PA2897_at	514.7	257.6	613.4	591.5	579.4
2921	PA2898_at	12.0	6.8	17.7	53.3	19.0
2922	PA2899_at	131.5	170.7	185.1	191.8	194.8
2923	PA2900_at	100.7	98.9	112.2	81.7	69.6
2924	PA2901_at	137.9	236.8	228.7	188.3	217.1
2925	PA2902_at	30.1	67.4	100.3	125.4	97.4
2926	PA2903_cobJ_at	8.8	8.4	34.2	38.1	26.4
2927	PA2904_cobI_at	43.4	111.3	70.9	85.1	84.5
2928	PA2905_cobH_at	49.8	56.4	57.4	32.9	54.7
2929	PA2906_at	123.4	120.3	231.8	161.7	192.1
2930	PA2907_cobL_at	56.2	54.9	95.8	60.3	68.8
2931	PA2908_cbiD_at	111.3	84.3	97.2	58.1	75.0
2932	PA2909_i_at	60.1	46.4	46.8	46.6	25.5
2933	PA2910_at	95.6	26.8	30.6	33.6	15.0
2934	PA2911_at	6.6	2.8	2.9	24.1	3.9
2935	PA2912_at	12.6	50.6	29.8	57.3	25.0
2936	PA2913_at	60.8	27.9	42.1	41.7	28.2
2937	PA2914_at	19.1	17.6	26.8	29.5	18.4
2938	PA2915_at	159.1	108.9	182.9	209.1	195.8
2939	PA2916_at	28.1	17.0	36.3	40.7	29.2
2940	PA2917_at	13.1	31.4	85.9	69.1	89.9
2941	PA2918_at	267.0	359.8	221.2	187.0	265.7
2942	PA2919_at	56.5	9.6	5.5	13.9	20.7
2943	PA2920_at	43.2	58.4	157.7	193.1	197.1
2944	PA2921_at	115.3	36.6	105.4	141.4	87.6
2945	PA2922_at	41.6	16.5	27.9	31.8	5.2
2946	PA2923_hisJ_at	61.8	44.4	18.4	32.4	23.6
2947	PA2924_hisQ_at	3.7	7.1	16.9	12.7	15.9
2948	PA2925_hisM_at	57.3	11.6	7.2	23.5	19.7
2949	PA2926_hisP_at	28.9	5.8	5.8	24.6	20.1
2950	PA2927_at	15.8	22.4	5.0	18.5	27.4
2951	PA2928_at	29.9	69.8	71.6	72.9	69.2
2952	PA2929_at	82.7	49.4	347.9	236.9	256.8
2953	PA2930_at	231.7	229.4	189.7	190.1	159.1
2954	PA2931_at	188.9	117.9	123.4	134.9	117.2
2955	PA2932_morB_at	22.8	45.5	38.7	48.0	43.3
2956	PA2933_at	8.1	32.3	7.7	25.4	30.9
2957	PA2934_at	51.1	59.8	53.7	49.8	24.5
2958	PA2935_at	7.1	1.2	10.3	14.7	3.9
2959	PA2936_at	65.8	14.3	24.6	17.7	25.5
2960	PA2937_at	172.5	133.3	100.4	110.9	182.2
2961	PA2938_at	8.1	48.8	29.2	41.4	43.0
2962	PA2939_at	44.0	26.9	37.7	35.4	42.1
2963	PA2940_at	43.4	50.6	52.4	57.4	69.6
2964	PA2941_at	68.7	47.8	44.3	78.8	42.2
2965	PA2942_at	111.2	77.5	240.6	202.1	192.7
2966	PA2943_at	454.2	131.3	594.6	582.9	499.4
2967	PA2944_cobN_at	62.3	81.5	22.6	22.6	64.4
2968	PA2945_at	17.2	98.0	129.7	127.1	144.9
2969	PA2946_at	342.8	213.9	616.0	613.3	789.2
2970	PA2947_i_at	54.3	49.6	72.2	52.7	54.5
2971	PA2948_cobM_at	109.1	86.9	98.5	83.5	73.9
2972	PA2949_at	108.7	53.6	90.8	104.2	89.9
2973	PA2950_at	170.1	230.6	210.7	247.5	271.2
2974	PA2951_etfA_at	826.1	1066.9	1297.1	973.3	990.6
2975	PA2952_etfB_at	1309.6	1538.2	1774.2	1552.1	1599.1
2976	PA2953_at	506.6	572.0	902.9	529.5	559.4
2977	PA2954_at	97.9	110.2	155.7	97.5	105.5
2978	PA2955_at	112.8	49.2	101.8	120.1	93.1
2979	PA2956_at	94.6	32.7	27.7	34.2	40.3
2980	PA2957_at	55.2	89.1	106.8	126.6	130.2
2981	PA2958_at	109.6	81.1	117.4	131.9	109.6
2982	PA2959_at	298.3	214.9	355.6	308.3	305.0
2983	PA2960_pilZ_at	195.6	212.8	309.1	280.3	330.4
2984	PA2961_holB_at	130.1	200.0	208.8	144.7	167.8
2985	PA2962_tmK_at	103.3	160.7	216.9	248.8	250.4
2986	PA2963_at	149.6	125.9	204.2	164.6	181.3
2987	PA2964_pabC_at	175.8	124.5	111.1	98.5	122.6
2988	PA2965_fabF1_at	238.4	281.9	314.7	322.8	289.1
2989	PA2966_acpP_at	1000.3	1243.0	1055.6	1207.8	1283.8

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

2990	PA2967_fabG_at	352.7	428.1	269.7	237.4	244.2
2991	PA2968_fabD_at	76.9	90.0	107.2	134.8	108.9
2992	PA2969_plsX_at	42.9	40.0	37.3	33.3	26.4
2993	PA2970_rpmF_at	398.0	638.9	197.9	166.8	171.9
2994	PA2971_at	547.5	605.2	492.6	366.5	427.9
2995	PA2972_at	25.1	44.0	79.3	89.7	92.0
2996	PA2973_at	172.4	230.2	231.9	224.1	208.6
2997	PA2974_at	88.8	92.8	157.5	143.9	121.3
2998	PA2975_rluC_at	199.7	188.4	270.1	237.4	211.7
2999	PA2976_rne_at	1620.7	2972.1	1452.6	1230.0	1250.0
3000	PA2977_murB_at	23.7	78.8	125.3	80.4	96.4
3001	PA2978_ptpA_at	85.9	155.1	176.2	168.8	139.8
3002	PA2979_kdsB_at	267.0	198.2	383.5	354.6	378.5
3003	PA2980_at	194.1	274.4	451.9	476.4	392.2
3004	PA2981_lpxK_at	72.7	67.5	43.5	45.3	38.8
3005	PA2982_at	104.3	63.0	104.2	72.4	83.5
3006	PA2983_at	65.8	91.8	144.5	109.4	107.6
3007	PA2984_at	64.5	20.3	70.3	71.0	44.7
3008	PA2985_at	215.5	131.6	231.6	265.6	274.7
3009	PA2986_at	67.0	66.0	52.0	39.3	41.2
3010	PA2987_at	111.5	242.0	153.0	141.3	136.6
3011	PA2988_at	78.7	69.8	114.4	134.8	114.8
3012	PA2989_at	137.8	139.6	119.4	127.9	169.8
3013	PA2990_at	314.1	256.5	417.9	327.0	360.5
3014	PA2991_sth_at	291.3	333.6	341.5	258.8	294.9
3015	PA2992_at	124.0	611.0	194.0	262.8	220.2
3016	PA2993_at	126.7	244.1	166.4	139.8	121.5
3017	PA2994_nqrF_at	165.6	220.7	98.3	100.2	118.5
3018	PA2995_nqrE_at	125.6	266.4	83.8	85.5	106.6
3019	PA2996_nqrD_at	85.7	197.9	75.1	86.4	74.1
3020	PA2997_nqrC_at	66.7	98.0	49.4	38.7	45.8
3021	PA2998_nqrB_at	111.6	196.9	131.0	97.3	89.1
3022	PA2999_nqrA_at	79.7	71.3	162.5	135.4	123.1
3023	PA3000_aroP1_at	68.7	31.1	35.6	24.3	23.0
3024	PA3001_at	498.5	367.7	727.2	583.3	595.5
3025	PA3002_mfd_at	259.0	287.1	316.8	295.6	305.2
3026	PA3003_at	143.9	261.7	165.0	132.4	140.9
3027	PA3004_at	138.2	181.7	122.0	94.5	93.6
3028	PA3005_at	167.9	105.1	221.2	229.0	219.4
3029	PA3006_at	725.3	1047.5	810.5	657.3	561.9
3030	PA3007_lexA_at	6486.0	4498.4	3836.0	3950.1	3795.4
3031	PA3008_at	2917.2	1063.4	1970.9	1596.5	1522.4
3032	PA3009_at	558.7	817.5	508.1	670.4	547.2
3033	PA3010_at	156.9	173.9	122.4	116.2	158.7
3034	PA3011_topA_at	174.8	210.6	225.3	213.9	236.5
3035	PA3012_at	87.5	73.0	152.4	153.5	131.3
3036	PA3013_foaB_at	110.4	282.8	197.8	147.4	145.8
3037	PA3014_faoA_at	338.2	440.8	737.9	353.9	324.3
3038	PA3015_at	181.3	227.7	302.1	238.2	253.6
3039	PA3016_at	34.2	35.4	39.6	39.1	39.3
3040	PA3017_at	533.9	656.3	560.9	548.4	622.0
3041	PA3018_at	21.8	69.7	23.1	32.9	31.8
3042	PA3019_at	44.4	69.3	42.6	53.6	51.7
3043	PA3020_at	261.2	179.1	214.8	244.6	212.5
3044	PA3021_at	588.4	858.8	622.4	561.3	602.1
3045	PA3022_at	237.9	219.1	391.1	484.5	488.5
3046	PA3023_at	49.0	42.4	60.8	65.6	58.9
3047	PA3024_at	52.2	36.9	11.0	16.5	15.5
3048	PA3025_at	15.9	66.9	64.0	47.8	28.7
3049	PA3026_at	97.3	39.6	47.7	81.1	96.7
3050	PA3027_at	106.2	104.0	223.9	203.5	248.2
3051	PA3028_moeA2_at	100.4	68.4	114.8	90.5	77.5
3052	PA3029_moab2_at	320.6	222.6	586.1	571.5	633.6
3053	PA3030_at	136.2	54.3	141.2	150.8	147.8
3054	PA3031_at	1344.0	1357.5	920.5	935.4	954.2
3055	PA3032_at	139.7	98.2	104.3	113.6	101.5
3056	PA3033_at	302.5	267.2	401.4	477.6	411.0
3057	PA3034_at	371.5	323.1	290.3	294.7	305.6
3058	PA3035_at	414.8	185.2	155.0	128.9	144.3
3059	PA3036_at	15.7	39.5	7.7	31.5	22.0
3060	PA3037_at	51.1	54.7	36.1	51.6	34.6
3061	PA3038_at	556.8	1640.2	1180.4	1023.1	1089.4
3062	PA3039_at	65.0	53.8	76.8	50.4	41.0

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3063	PA3040_at	715.6	362.1	655.0	855.3	823.4
3064	PA3041_at	353.2	194.5	320.1	331.0	303.4
3065	PA3042_at	140.7	62.0	162.5	181.1	199.5
3066	PA3043_at	95.0	74.7	141.3	192.5	200.0
3067	PA3044_at	146.5	50.0	70.2	67.2	62.4
3068	PA3045_at	87.4	39.4	25.0	34.8	26.5
3069	PA3046_at	120.8	254.1	180.0	210.2	194.2
3070	PA3047_at	289.2	178.3	187.6	208.3	190.5
3071	PA3048_at	132.4	71.2	77.6	73.5	84.7
3072	PA3049_rmf_at	456.1	544.3	417.3	464.8	531.0
3073	PA3050_pyrD_at	344.9	235.0	357.4	353.9	331.7
3074	PA3051_at	55.8	161.3	121.1	109.0	98.3
3075	PA3052_at	405.4	283.5	469.5	382.0	461.2
3076	PA3053_at	214.6	120.2	171.4	194.3	188.6
3077	PA3054_at	140.6	174.0	92.1	85.6	91.1
3078	PA3055_at	389.3	321.8	542.2	530.2	568.1
3079	PA3056_at	300.3	164.4	347.9	405.4	458.4
3080	PA3057_at	96.5	81.2	50.6	77.6	69.1
3081	PA3058_at	126.9	42.9	44.9	64.9	25.7
3082	PA3059_at	64.9	40.5	47.3	48.2	55.4
3083	PA3060_at	24.2	57.4	41.3	38.1	42.1
3084	PA3061_at	74.4	42.7	68.7	41.4	65.4
3085	PA3062_at	73.8	27.0	30.1	29.6	11.1
3086	PA3063_at	51.4	39.0	37.9	18.8	26.9
3087	PA3064_at	46.1	4.4	3.7	5.5	1.9
3088	PA3065_at	35.4	5.5	35.7	28.0	27.9
3089	PA3066_at	18.8	72.7	58.5	63.8	64.0
3090	PA3067_at	20.0	72.5	133.2	90.8	158.6
3091	PA3068_at	567.8	3330.9	875.3	898.0	1022.3
3092	PA3069_at	100.9	48.1	132.2	100.1	102.0
3093	PA3070_at	319.9	215.2	410.1	378.6	450.8
3094	PA3071_at	275.3	119.2	263.3	261.9	223.5
3095	PA3072_at	123.1	125.5	127.8	131.8	104.8
3096	PA3073_at	94.2	120.5	92.1	59.1	70.8
3097	PA3074_at	130.8	256.2	107.6	74.5	102.1
3098	PA3075_at	72.7	133.5	106.0	56.2	75.2
3099	PA3076_at	72.2	121.8	103.0	109.8	129.9
3100	PA3077_at	70.1	160.0	113.8	106.5	112.6
3101	PA3078_at	73.8	84.0	94.3	115.1	73.9
3102	PA3079_at	124.4	257.1	112.5	105.7	134.6
3103	PA3080_at	326.8	154.6	372.3	373.6	430.7
3104	PA3081_at	127.9	205.4	86.4	75.6	86.7
3105	PA3082_at	113.8	114.3	149.9	114.6	110.2
3106	PA3083_pepN_at	105.0	243.4	154.1	155.4	168.4
3107	PA3084_at	379.2	189.5	195.9	181.0	189.6
3108	PA3085_at	377.8	183.5	290.5	263.9	281.9
3109	PA3086_at	81.9	78.3	87.6	91.1	64.1
3110	PA3087_at	23.2	65.0	90.4	99.8	82.9
3111	PA3088_at	310.1	217.3	277.4	307.3	328.0
3112	PA3089_at	314.6	205.0	279.8	307.1	240.9
3113	PA3090_at	17.8	30.9	38.8	30.6	16.4
3114	PA3091_at	66.3	38.4	70.6	52.9	56.0
3115	PA3092_fadH1_at	78.1	46.7	68.2	66.2	62.6
3116	PA3093_at	158.4	92.6	192.2	199.1	181.5
3117	PA3094_at	102.5	97.4	150.4	74.8	73.4
3118	PA3095_xcpZ_at	110.5	98.9	89.8	75.9	88.8
3119	PA3096_xcpY_at	247.2	292.3	298.1	267.8	227.9
3120	PA3097_xcpX_at	88.8	118.6	101.7	99.6	73.4
3121	PA3098_xcpW_at	242.1	179.5	139.5	116.2	126.3
3122	PA3099_xcpV_at	261.3	169.0	251.4	207.4	192.7
3123	PA3100_xcpU_at	164.5	162.9	115.5	161.9	134.1
3124	PA3101_xcpT_at	358.6	396.5	369.0	409.2	381.9
3125	PA3102_xcpS_at	177.4	138.6	183.5	136.0	153.8
3126	PA3103_xcpR_at	449.6	402.8	472.5	473.7	494.9
3127	PA3104_xcpP_at	751.5	729.5	906.1	829.6	816.3
3128	PA3105_xcpQ_at	435.6	556.6	632.2	617.3	593.0
3129	PA3106_at	168.4	354.2	156.1	168.4	148.5
3130	PA3107_metZ_at	321.9	605.3	371.8	324.1	327.0
3131	PA3108_purF_at	260.9	392.8	303.9	374.2	369.8
3132	PA3109_at	146.9	129.1	207.8	177.8	171.6
3133	PA3110_at	401.7	631.0	545.4	506.3	558.3
3134	PA3111_folC_at	106.8	116.4	127.8	145.0	147.0
3135	PA3112_accD_at	12.3	119.9	194.0	138.4	155.9

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3136	PA3113_trpF_at	329.4	220.7	542.1	517.7	536.1
3137	PA3114_truA_at	158.2	121.4	143.4	133.1	104.5
3138	PA3115_at	1054.4	1697.7	1223.0	1003.6	1030.6
3139	PA3116_at	11.8	58.4	98.8	70.7	62.3
3140	PA3117_asd_at	122.1	80.3	208.3	247.4	191.6
3141	PA3118_leuB_at	152.0	165.7	203.9	204.9	174.7
3142	PA3119_at	111.6	64.5	157.0	76.4	91.7
3143	PA3120_leuD_at	115.8	125.1	96.0	112.7	107.6
3144	PA3121_leuC_at	170.3	161.1	132.9	150.0	137.4
3145	PA3122_at	69.7	51.3	108.9	95.8	44.7
3146	PA3123_at	368.2	341.3	468.9	481.1	426.6
3147	PA3124_at	351.2	279.7	426.0	438.9	442.7
3148	PA3125_at	84.6	76.5	68.5	73.2	74.1
3149	PA3126_ibpA_at	184.9	81.1	98.8	96.4	99.2
3150	PA3127_at	259.4	158.3	244.0	236.9	260.6
3151	PA3128_at	269.8	153.6	278.0	251.9	232.8
3152	PA3129_at	52.6	83.8	69.3	79.9	64.1
3153	PA3130_at	66.9	60.7	78.3	96.6	70.9
3154	PA3131_at	18.2	45.0	175.1	165.0	159.6
3155	PA3132_at	65.3	34.9	75.3	37.9	38.5
3156	PA3133_at	9.3	26.1	25.2	77.1	57.2
3157	PA3134_gltX_at	137.7	196.4	345.5	342.1	353.0
3158	PA3135_at	111.0	43.3	84.0	93.2	88.9
3159	PA3136_at	38.3	44.3	41.8	18.8	18.0
3160	PA3137_at	32.9	22.0	31.1	12.2	22.8
3161	PA3138_uvrB_at	185.1	143.6	242.7	180.9	227.4
3162	PA3139_at	376.1	461.4	735.4	617.0	666.9
3163	PA3140_at	7.1	9.6	18.7	16.0	10.6
3164	PA3141_wbpM_g_at	657.9	734.1	655.5	662.9	596.0
3165	PA3142_i_at	515.1	790.4	345.3	474.9	442.1
3166	PA3143_at	139.0	113.7	131.9	104.2	105.0
3167	PA3144_f_at	215.7	204.4	141.9	177.1	198.3
3168	PA3145_wbpL_at	224.2	282.3	246.5	324.2	216.8
3169	PA3146_wbpK_at	296.1	485.5	386.1	477.9	406.4
3170	PA3147_wbpJ_at	551.4	490.6	455.0	468.7	337.1
3171	PA3148_wbpI_at	214.6	241.4	207.7	295.0	204.2
3172	PA3149_wbpH_at	237.3	225.3	262.1	310.2	284.7
3173	PA3150_wbpG_at	159.2	261.9	186.6	241.4	198.6
3174	PA3151_hisF2_at	290.8	485.8	422.2	744.0	572.5
3175	PA3152_hisH2_at	266.8	563.7	352.7	354.6	375.4
3176	PA3153_wzx_at	76.9	55.6	41.4	69.0	61.5
3177	PA3154_wzy_at	12.6	53.0	55.5	71.5	34.1
3178	PA3155_wbpE_at	307.4	825.7	337.6	375.0	341.5
3179	PA3156_wbpD_at	271.4	387.8	283.8	328.6	329.4
3180	PA3157_at	92.6	99.2	113.4	98.5	102.3
3181	PA3158_wbpB_at	507.3	439.0	679.8	780.2	698.9
3182	PA3159_wbpA_at	952.3	850.5	1267.9	1203.2	1149.8
3183	PA3160_wzz_at	313.2	298.3	473.8	633.0	580.9
3184	PA3161_himD_at	1572.5	1579.6	1527.4	1780.5	1916.1
3185	PA3162_rpsA_at	461.8	728.1	564.4	431.2	469.7
3186	PA3163_cmk_at	124.4	262.0	105.0	87.7	99.8
3187	PA3164_at	225.7	321.0	222.6	190.6	164.8
3188	PA3165_hisC2_at	97.3	132.5	78.9	66.5	64.5
3189	PA3166_pheA_at	178.7	340.0	174.3	177.8	200.9
3190	PA3167_serC_at	268.3	450.5	234.9	162.1	157.3
3191	PA3168_gyrA_at	303.7	429.4	397.6	437.3	393.2
3192	PA3169_at	109.3	142.6	217.2	196.0	226.8
3193	PA3170_at	344.1	216.1	410.1	322.0	276.1
3194	PA3171_ubiG_at	151.5	147.8	264.5	226.3	230.4
3195	PA3172_at	176.0	229.0	214.1	185.7	176.2
3196	PA3173_at	122.9	125.9	93.3	100.5	96.4
3197	PA3174_at	132.1	68.1	53.0	28.4	37.8
3198	PA3175_at	45.9	51.9	61.5	61.2	53.8
3199	PA3176_gltS_at	56.8	19.9	37.6	27.2	29.0
3200	PA3177_at	310.9	370.4	591.4	565.3	526.7
3201	PA3178_at	79.8	74.5	95.4	93.8	100.0
3202	PA3179_at	62.3	104.4	79.3	60.3	61.6
3203	PA3180_at	55.9	32.6	31.7	44.7	31.6
3204	PA3181_at	391.8	707.8	1043.8	1263.2	1286.9
3205	PA3182_at	1190.7	2914.9	3245.3	3699.9	3652.4
3206	PA3183_zwf_at	1654.4	2885.7	4327.3	4513.7	4790.1
3207	PA3184_at	129.1	141.4	390.4	374.7	365.7
3208	PA3185_at	116.7	226.8	187.4	210.1	244.4

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3209	PA3187_at	864.7	2220.4	711.3	742.0	753.9
3210	PA3188_at	547.5	1140.8	506.4	389.3	289.7
3211	PA3189_at	365.2	690.5	374.4	415.7	319.3
3212	PA3190_at	1868.7	2149.8	3031.7	2763.1	2750.0
3213	PA3191_at	99.5	256.0	99.7	180.2	157.1
3214	PA3192_gltR_at	410.1	661.6	492.6	413.8	420.7
3215	PA3193_glk_at	250.2	435.4	501.3	530.0	539.8
3216	PA3194_edd_at	1507.3	1678.8	1847.2	1583.8	1863.3
3217	PA3195_gapA_at	4680.5	4804.0	6354.8	5946.8	6089.2
3218	PA3196_at	126.8	136.6	120.7	91.6	114.4
3219	PA3197_at	157.0	175.5	264.6	247.1	219.2
3220	PA3198_at	124.8	117.6	137.3	154.0	125.2
3221	PA3199_at	231.0	162.5	261.8	267.4	251.2
3222	PA3200_at	159.9	88.5	133.6	119.2	123.3
3223	PA3201_at	525.4	372.2	659.4	603.4	661.8
3224	PA3202_at	669.5	512.3	1059.7	974.5	957.5
3225	PA3203_at	267.0	269.5	446.5	371.9	410.4
3226	PA3204_at	240.6	224.9	308.2	294.1	325.4
3227	PA3205_at	763.3	1262.1	353.9	396.4	357.0
3228	PA3206_at	49.1	46.7	63.1	97.2	85.1
3229	PA3207_at	74.3	96.1	76.3	72.4	48.7
3230	PA3208_at	70.9	69.2	130.5	145.8	122.4
3231	PA3209_at	40.2	59.4	40.9	52.0	43.3
3232	PA3210_trkH_at	48.4	25.3	68.4	42.0	31.3
3233	PA3211_at	545.1	378.2	590.3	553.8	566.4
3234	PA3212_at	687.7	305.1	556.6	673.6	594.1
3235	PA3213_at	710.7	534.4	474.8	552.2	573.2
3236	PA3214_at	346.5	385.3	331.0	351.0	347.0
3237	PA3215_at	80.8	75.1	92.0	97.8	103.5
3238	PA3216_at	82.9	79.6	46.3	70.6	72.9
3239	PA3217_at	174.3	103.5	199.3	184.4	193.7
3240	PA3218_at	76.2	36.7	42.5	38.7	31.6
3241	PA3219_at	8.2	37.9	65.1	37.3	39.0
3242	PA3220_at	278.6	182.9	254.2	323.8	423.0
3243	PA3221_csaA_at	7.5	112.3	106.3	65.1	78.6
3244	PA3222_at	65.9	76.0	8.7	29.6	42.5
3245	PA3223_acpD_at	45.3	23.9	35.8	41.1	34.4
3246	PA3224_at	122.8	181.0	252.4	217.5	233.8
3247	PA3225_at	423.7	369.7	508.9	489.3	472.3
3248	PA3226_at	303.2	172.7	283.8	318.5	318.4
3249	PA3227_ppiA_at	984.9	774.4	1122.3	1042.6	1101.7
3250	PA3228_at	185.7	217.5	154.9	155.1	155.2
3251	PA3229_at	65.1	36.4	76.7	50.9	44.4
3252	PA3230_at	144.4	74.5	164.4	100.1	123.3
3253	PA3231_at	8.9	15.2	4.1	17.2	2.4
3254	PA3232_at	28.1	106.6	50.2	54.2	59.2
3255	PA3233_at	31.6	93.4	66.5	47.6	50.8
3256	PA3234_at	562.9	961.8	636.6	665.5	624.5
3257	PA3235_at	579.6	1175.6	660.2	906.0	949.9
3258	PA3236_at	84.0	41.7	24.4	35.6	42.9
3259	PA3237_at	4356.5	2093.1	1647.8	1822.5	2015.7
3260	PA3238_at	1140.1	670.9	1016.7	1014.7	959.5
3261	PA3239_at	950.4	797.0	1111.7	1037.8	904.9
3262	PA3240_at	244.2	646.0	303.6	408.1	366.4
3263	PA3241_at	103.8	33.7	102.9	74.3	69.6
3264	PA3242_at	56.0	27.0	48.1	54.3	51.7
3265	PA3243_minC_at	157.7	80.1	203.9	186.4	206.5
3266	PA3244_minD_at	310.5	262.6	597.8	536.4	639.8
3267	PA3245_minE_at	114.5	167.8	230.3	185.3	186.3
3268	PA3246_rluA_at	138.1	94.7	147.6	131.8	131.8
3269	PA3247_at	149.2	122.3	270.9	204.3	262.6
3270	PA3248_at	184.5	141.6	138.8	107.7	124.2
3271	PA3249_at	6.3	3.0	7.0	10.3	3.0
3272	PA3250_at	8.8	64.3	96.1	79.7	74.5
3273	PA3251_at	71.1	31.9	50.2	33.9	27.3
3274	PA3252_at	72.3	11.4	20.4	53.7	4.5
3275	PA3253_at	14.1	17.5	15.7	24.9	21.8
3276	PA3254_at	60.7	41.5	63.9	53.0	31.4
3277	PA3255_at	108.4	119.0	214.6	161.7	151.1
3278	PA3256_at	22.1	39.7	139.7	128.4	161.9
3279	PA3257_prc_at	1477.7	1385.3	1288.0	1158.1	1070.0
3280	PA3258_at	117.5	55.4	62.7	59.9	42.2
3281	PA3259_at	309.8	188.1	270.5	348.0	345.0

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3282	PA3260_at	423.2	314.8	599.5	700.6	619.5
3283	PA3261_at	123.1	61.4	61.7	77.4	62.6
3284	PA3262_at	407.8	397.2	877.3	783.7	799.2
3285	PA3263_at	146.0	169.4	287.4	204.7	191.4
3286	PA3264_at	10.9	43.2	72.3	68.5	65.2
3287	PA3265_at	51.6	44.5	50.7	50.2	43.5
3288	PA3266_capB_at	111.8	161.7	80.2	87.8	103.6
3289	PA3267_at	169.4	142.5	215.8	212.0	227.2
3290	PA3268_at	72.4	23.7	93.9	49.7	61.3
3291	PA3269_at	14.9	34.1	19.9	22.6	32.1
3292	PA3270_at	153.9	138.0	241.1	222.0	198.9
3293	PA3271_at	120.1	147.1	79.8	95.5	71.5
3294	PA3272_at	268.5	229.4	136.3	152.9	173.7
3295	PA3273_at	9.0	5.5	15.3	24.4	3.3
3296	PA3274_at	12.6	5.9	4.6	24.7	19.5
3297	PA3275_at	78.3	31.5	52.6	45.6	22.0
3298	PA3276_at	6.9	35.1	54.7	53.4	53.8
3299	PA3277_at	84.1	81.3	288.2	97.8	50.0
3300	PA3278_at	103.8	51.3	40.6	51.2	33.4
3301	PA3279_oprP_at	31.4	24.5	3.6	26.6	10.7
3302	PA3280_oprO_at	94.1	8.5	39.4	39.6	9.2
3303	PA3281_at	140.2	121.8	86.2	157.5	98.0
3304	PA3282_at	107.3	125.2	177.4	199.7	106.5
3305	PA3283_at	520.5	336.9	410.6	539.6	319.5
3306	PA3284_at	573.9	560.3	395.4	496.3	271.6
3307	PA3285_at	459.1	225.7	662.9	678.5	599.3
3308	PA3286_at	1181.1	651.4	1621.4	1304.0	1357.1
3309	PA3287_at	7998.5	4408.0	5361.9	5490.9	5735.8
3310	PA3288_at	184.0	215.9	289.8	230.2	225.2
3311	PA3289_at	179.9	118.3	188.1	167.3	169.3
3312	PA3290_at	163.2	136.2	120.9	137.1	119.5
3313	PA3291_at	8.3	33.3	32.5	19.6	17.6
3314	PA3292_at	30.5	11.0	29.9	26.7	14.9
3315	PA3293_at	50.9	36.8	43.7	33.7	20.5
3316	PA3294_s_at	100.4	65.4	59.5	60.5	63.3
3317	PA3295_at	104.7	85.2	163.8	138.7	135.0
3318	PA3296_phoA_at	104.4	37.5	34.2	36.0	30.3
3319	PA3297_at	81.6	157.8	106.2	92.3	94.9
3320	PA3298_at	67.7	40.7	35.4	60.0	34.6
3321	PA3299_fadD1_at	25.8	137.7	200.9	231.5	236.2
3322	PA3300_fadD2_at	156.6	125.3	199.0	141.8	145.7
3323	PA3301_at	247.3	144.5	354.8	267.4	268.8
3324	PA3302_at	153.8	181.1	165.6	161.7	166.1
3325	PA3303_at	82.7	45.6	42.8	55.7	49.8
3326	PA3304_at	149.8	112.9	101.1	95.8	89.1
3327	PA3305_at	129.8	76.8	83.9	113.6	116.9
3328	PA3306_at	1236.0	1067.8	885.2	1152.6	1292.5
3329	PA3307_r_at	552.0	684.1	331.0	368.2	389.3
3330	PA3308_hepA_at	137.8	129.3	114.1	90.8	61.4
3331	PA3309_at	43.6	356.5	79.9	100.6	108.1
3332	PA3310_at	11.9	158.9	70.3	58.7	62.5
3333	PA3311_at	10.4	15.1	38.9	68.6	56.0
3334	PA3312_at	99.5	81.1	97.0	89.6	102.4
3335	PA3313_at	59.5	102.9	213.7	175.4	161.6
3336	PA3314_at	27.0	79.4	97.3	110.1	76.6
3337	PA3315_at	60.2	44.3	5.3	12.5	7.8
3338	PA3316_at	13.4	29.0	9.0	38.2	19.0
3339	PA3317_at	182.6	167.2	182.1	193.4	225.5
3340	PA3318_at	134.1	85.2	37.0	85.6	43.2
3341	PA3319_plcN_at	79.2	38.0	43.5	23.6	48.2
3342	PA3320_at	48.0	30.2	19.1	25.9	18.4
3343	PA3321_at	203.8	103.6	176.7	157.0	153.3
3344	PA3322_at	175.2	60.7	201.7	170.3	189.3
3345	PA3323_at	123.0	90.0	89.6	83.4	80.4
3346	PA3324_at	22.0	40.0	34.5	29.9	17.0
3347	PA3325_at	40.9	48.0	40.7	43.8	27.4
3348	PA3326_at	550.4	552.7	1502.7	1389.7	1355.3
3349	PA3327_at	165.9	126.8	126.9	119.4	150.0
3350	PA3328_at	31.2	148.6	110.7	93.4	74.7
3351	PA3329_at	53.0	133.4	104.8	99.1	94.7
3352	PA3330_at	12.8	96.6	120.1	131.0	94.5
3353	PA3331_at	74.9	322.8	324.5	285.4	261.9
3354	PA3332_at	25.0	204.3	230.9	220.7	243.6

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3355	PA3333_fabH2_at	71.9	138.6	142.0	137.6	132.5
3356	PA3334_at	40.4	85.2	136.8	110.1	118.1
3357	PA3335_at	102.4	79.6	70.4	72.3	67.7
3358	PA3336_at	9.2	3.4	5.6	7.2	9.0
3359	PA3337_rfaD_at	8.6	25.0	35.3	33.3	18.4
3360	PA3338_at	90.3	91.0	85.2	77.8	113.3
3361	PA3339_at	96.1	68.4	63.7	51.5	49.6
3362	PA3340_at	171.3	150.2	305.7	296.3	317.7
3363	PA3341_at	290.7	233.5	223.3	247.1	200.2
3364	PA3342_at	103.0	80.4	105.4	135.5	115.0
3365	PA3343_at	262.9	142.4	187.2	241.1	204.7
3366	PA3344_recQ_at	118.6	84.6	117.5	107.6	163.1
3367	PA3345_at	172.3	115.8	235.1	278.2	312.7
3368	PA3346_at	47.4	39.9	63.0	91.0	77.5
3369	PA3347_at	285.3	413.2	324.8	283.0	311.1
3370	PA3348_at	718.2	564.1	1128.8	1141.1	1067.8
3371	PA3349_at	1334.3	1221.8	2067.5	2091.8	2159.2
3372	PA3350_at	273.0	321.6	412.7	310.7	306.0
3373	PA3351_at	7180.0	5579.3	5049.1	4693.8	5385.4
3374	PA3352_at	1842.3	1469.4	1984.2	1808.4	2084.4
3375	PA3353_at	741.8	623.7	767.6	675.8	704.8
3376	PA3354_at	195.6	124.2	149.8	183.3	155.5
3377	PA3355_at	73.0	55.9	184.3	130.7	132.6
3378	PA3356_at	1391.1	1640.8	1223.0	1132.8	1137.6
3379	PA3357_dsdA_at	174.2	112.5	220.5	163.6	168.6
3380	PA3358_at	71.1	36.1	33.5	32.8	12.2
3381	PA3359_at	4.6	3.2	4.6	11.8	3.5
3382	PA3360_at	12.9	6.6	4.8	8.3	4.5
3383	PA3361_at	126.4	149.0	237.0	216.4	188.7
3384	PA3362_at	78.8	67.8	49.0	74.9	52.1
3385	PA3363_amiR_at	108.9	91.3	118.0	119.1	108.4
3386	PA3364_amiC_at	166.0	70.2	105.7	164.2	145.7
3387	PA3365_at	86.6	119.0	329.5	332.5	320.7
3388	PA3366_amiE_at	262.8	292.6	379.4	372.4	370.3
3389	PA3367_at	12.0	21.5	56.6	53.0	43.6
3390	PA3368_at	95.3	44.6	50.8	49.7	47.3
3391	PA3369_at	224.8	224.4	208.8	271.9	247.2
3392	PA3370_at	62.7	50.0	95.7	95.1	116.2
3393	PA3371_at	89.4	64.7	138.7	134.5	137.6
3394	PA3372_at	131.8	23.2	58.9	39.1	35.2
3395	PA3373_at	174.6	103.9	188.5	164.2	154.4
3396	PA3374_at	30.6	41.6	45.6	45.4	33.3
3397	PA3375_at	79.3	42.4	56.5	27.2	29.6
3398	PA3376_at	6.1	4.6	3.7	1.9	3.4
3399	PA3377_at	75.0	46.6	25.9	32.4	15.1
3400	PA3378_at	48.2	17.4	21.5	24.6	12.2
3401	PA3379_at	12.6	27.1	6.0	22.8	3.8
3402	PA3380_at	10.8	5.6	3.1	5.3	3.9
3403	PA3381_at	52.1	54.2	37.0	54.4	30.9
3404	PA3382_phnE_at	11.7	2.3	2.6	3.0	1.8
3405	PA3383_at	47.9	11.0	22.0	28.3	5.5
3406	PA3384_phnC_at	67.9	22.1	23.1	40.9	17.2
3407	PA3385_at	4194.4	4363.0	3787.1	3036.3	3839.4
3408	PA3386_at	40.8	24.4	31.8	15.9	3.4
3409	PA3387_rhlG_at	31.4	47.3	112.3	62.2	56.3
3410	PA3388_at	76.6	68.6	144.9	105.0	83.5
3411	PA3389_at	55.3	27.0	34.1	49.4	29.5
3412	PA3390_at	80.1	43.0	41.4	27.3	25.3
3413	PA3391_nosR_at	30.5	25.4	5.4	3.6	3.1
3414	PA3392_nosZ_at	40.6	21.5	13.1	30.9	37.5
3415	PA3393_nosD_at	5.7	60.1	48.4	47.6	34.7
3416	PA3394_nosF_at	8.8	4.3	29.4	26.7	11.5
3417	PA3395_nosY_at	5.0	2.4	3.6	15.6	6.9
3418	PA3396_nosL_at	54.9	27.8	70.0	62.2	37.1
3419	PA3397_fpr_at	242.9	103.8	185.9	148.6	250.1
3420	PA3398_at	51.9	46.5	95.5	91.7	73.8
3421	PA3399_at	184.9	101.5	160.8	141.4	172.5
3422	PA3400_at	75.9	29.6	26.1	43.2	34.9
3423	PA3401_at	59.4	63.2	84.3	54.7	72.4
3424	PA3402_at	100.4	65.6	98.3	78.2	92.6
3425	PA3403_at	74.9	70.0	58.2	52.4	75.1
3426	PA3404_at	41.9	31.8	29.6	29.4	26.5
3427	PA3405_hasE_at	4.5	5.0	15.5	24.2	2.9

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3428	PA3406_hasD_at	59.5	30.5	38.0	33.2	20.3
3429	PA3407_hasAp_at	8.6	14.4	40.3	10.1	8.1
3430	PA3408_hasR_at	97.4	56.7	63.7	61.1	79.9
3431	PA3409_at	84.0	71.3	117.1	81.2	79.8
3432	PA3410_at	396.2	295.4	198.3	259.2	248.9
3433	PA3411_r_at	35.2	46.9	27.4	54.9	40.9
3434	PA3412_at	47.5	18.9	21.0	24.8	31.7
3435	PA3413_at	499.4	261.4	710.4	840.4	752.7
3436	PA3414_at	149.2	24.5	184.6	207.3	211.9
3437	PA3415_at	92.7	55.4	50.5	66.4	62.8
3438	PA3416_at	21.0	28.0	23.4	51.3	45.7
3439	PA3417_at	72.9	76.2	91.0	146.2	139.9
3440	PA3418_ldh_at	348.3	275.6	354.4	566.6	564.3
3441	PA3419_at	289.4	200.8	310.9	357.1	343.5
3442	PA3420_at	37.9	63.1	142.0	63.9	42.7
3443	PA3421_at	71.8	33.4	30.1	36.2	13.8
3444	PA3422_at	24.7	18.7	8.3	6.7	19.9
3445	PA3423_at	273.2	159.8	178.7	225.2	249.0
3446	PA3424_at	58.9	54.1	60.1	51.6	46.7
3447	PA3425_at	60.3	59.0	54.4	82.6	43.9
3448	PA3426_at	41.6	55.0	73.8	85.8	92.9
3449	PA3427_at	83.5	71.0	213.2	72.7	52.8
3450	PA3428_at	9.8	17.9	23.2	28.1	2.4
3451	PA3429_at	75.8	40.2	47.7	40.6	37.8
3452	PA3430_at	104.9	146.1	113.4	80.1	58.4
3453	PA3431_at	29.2	78.1	75.4	67.3	43.2
3454	PA3432_i_at	78.7	47.6	31.3	51.8	41.2
3455	PA3433_at	119.7	76.7	106.4	104.0	122.4
3456	PA3435_at	148.2	104.6	310.5	268.4	237.9
3457	PA3436_at	49.9	211.7	53.9	74.8	71.2
3458	PA3437_at	334.0	202.5	449.4	459.3	458.2
3459	PA3438_folE1_at	74.3	125.0	185.0	196.4	191.9
3460	PA3439_folX_at	372.0	326.5	520.9	346.4	373.9
3461	PA3440_at	1025.6	650.5	2178.9	1692.8	1920.8
3462	PA3441_at	333.0	64.1	21.8	30.9	39.1
3463	PA3442_at	1260.8	50.5	13.0	20.0	87.3
3464	PA3443_at	832.7	57.7	30.4	34.5	50.3
3465	PA3444_at	1848.4	71.4	9.3	24.5	65.1
3466	PA3445_at	2862.3	72.1	19.3	16.9	45.1
3467	PA3446_at	6961.9	88.5	27.4	29.7	142.9
3468	PA3447_at	18.6	5.5	14.0	10.0	20.2
3469	PA3448_at	56.3	16.9	7.7	9.2	15.1
3470	PA3449_at	83.4	5.8	6.8	7.5	1.4
3471	PA3450_at	9257.9	294.0	118.3	103.2	421.4
3472	PA3451_at	57.2	33.2	54.9	38.1	58.0
3473	PA3452_mqoA_at	354.5	518.0	130.2	135.0	167.8
3474	PA3453_at	90.4	74.5	117.6	96.6	95.8
3475	PA3454_at	40.3	20.3	128.6	71.5	36.2
3476	PA3455_at	343.0	272.0	256.7	233.7	265.1
3477	PA3456_at	98.0	75.1	145.0	77.8	90.7
3478	PA3457_at	5.4	3.7	44.6	33.8	28.0
3479	PA3458_at	201.2	188.2	166.3	196.4	173.2
3480	PA3459_at	339.4	203.2	192.8	323.4	273.9
3481	PA3460_at	207.2	98.7	132.7	245.7	159.9
3482	PA3461_at	60.0	32.8	62.2	90.8	66.5
3483	PA3462_at	12.8	6.7	25.5	26.5	15.5
3484	PA3463_at	164.3	133.5	133.6	149.9	131.1
3485	PA3464_at	51.5	5.0	46.0	39.8	48.0
3486	PA3465_at	20.6	33.5	60.5	90.2	89.6
3487	PA3466_at	221.6	160.6	328.5	347.3	252.6
3488	PA3467_at	7.5	21.8	4.1	18.8	15.3
3489	PA3468_at	87.3	104.0	64.5	94.1	66.4
3490	PA3469_at	115.3	85.2	99.2	91.1	114.3
3491	PA3470_i_at	32.8	61.6	73.4	68.1	76.3
3492	PA3471_at	313.6	280.6	361.3	293.0	325.5
3493	PA3472_at	73.2	39.4	94.8	62.9	70.1
3494	PA3473_at	34.9	39.1	42.2	30.1	34.3
3495	PA3474_at	64.4	35.6	56.7	49.3	28.7
3496	PA3475_pheC_at	109.6	54.0	136.0	155.5	100.2
3497	PA3476_rhlL_at	381.2	332.8	972.5	861.6	916.0
3498	PA3477_rhlR_at	283.8	164.7	581.8	602.2	639.1
3499	PA3478_rhlB_at	78.1	30.4	40.1	49.4	31.6
3500	PA3479_rhlA_at	62.3	49.5	76.6	59.8	74.2

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3501	PA3480_at	217.2	90.7	259.6	235.3	263.1
3502	PA3481_at	386.4	265.0	486.3	568.9	472.6
3503	PA3482_metG_at	679.8	523.3	1030.2	914.7	893.4
3504	PA3483_at	256.3	192.6	214.9	225.2	183.1
3505	PA3484_at	226.0	278.6	160.4	144.0	142.3
3506	PA3485_r_at	234.7	197.5	114.8	108.9	101.5
3507	PA3486_at	29.1	31.9	23.6	47.2	14.0
3508	PA3487_at	59.4	88.4	40.4	64.3	44.8
3509	PA3488_at	182.4	278.5	197.6	245.2	291.1
3510	PA3489_at	43.3	60.2	73.7	43.8	42.5
3511	PA3490_at	38.8	19.1	18.0	35.0	26.6
3512	PA3491_at	192.1	325.8	160.1	150.3	150.1
3513	PA3492_at	102.8	92.5	30.5	55.4	61.3
3514	PA3493_at	41.0	78.7	10.7	17.4	44.8
3515	PA3494_at	32.2	90.7	44.5	40.2	43.4
3516	PA3495_nth_at	55.4	364.1	147.2	121.7	116.9
3517	PA3496_at	1149.2	1169.2	430.7	369.4	519.5
3518	PA3497_at	89.4	75.0	50.8	39.1	50.3
3519	PA3498_at	52.7	16.5	10.4	18.9	4.9
3520	PA3499_at	68.7	93.9	71.6	67.2	54.8
3521	PA3500_at	83.0	105.1	114.1	92.7	90.7
3522	PA3501_at	7.6	76.9	25.7	50.5	52.9
3523	PA3502_at	14.1	57.1	35.3	42.8	17.6
3524	PA3503_at	14.6	68.4	34.7	54.5	35.8
3525	PA3504_at	26.2	27.5	29.6	43.5	11.4
3526	PA3505_at	119.0	100.1	56.5	64.9	31.0
3527	PA3506_at	7.8	44.9	2.4	22.3	4.2
3528	PA3507_at	40.6	14.9	7.3	3.1	2.9
3529	PA3508_at	10.5	51.8	31.3	24.9	26.4
3530	PA3509_at	39.0	59.9	8.9	38.3	13.5
3531	PA3510_at	71.7	92.2	46.2	32.7	31.8
3532	PA3511_at	9.8	78.9	52.6	46.3	44.5
3533	PA3512_at	6.1	9.4	8.5	1.4	32.4
3534	PA3513_at	5.1	10.8	18.9	18.6	16.7
3535	PA3514_at	109.5	47.1	30.4	66.4	64.0
3536	PA3515_at	19.5	25.9	28.9	181.8	31.9
3537	PA3516_at	10.2	40.8	12.5	1045.1	31.2
3538	PA3517_at	77.6	26.8	33.3	1354.7	33.2
3539	PA3518_at	8.0	27.9	23.8	1656.0	44.1
3540	PA3519_at	63.8	86.1	83.8	4087.2	77.4
3541	PA3520_at	122.6	66.1	52.6	577.4	44.8
3542	PA3521_at	88.1	2.4	4.7	115.6	3.3
3543	PA3522_at	26.7	20.5	9.4	98.8	14.9
3544	PA3523_at	11.8	2.9	3.8	575.7	4.5
3545	PA3524_gloA1_at	663.2	464.5	686.9	807.0	811.8
3546	PA3525_argG_at	293.1	203.1	472.3	442.7	515.6
3547	PA3526_at	916.5	621.0	829.7	917.6	957.6
3548	PA3527_pyrC_at	375.3	248.2	497.9	410.2	416.9
3549	PA3528_rnt_at	414.8	367.5	367.7	440.7	486.1
3550	PA3529_at	501.3	602.8	753.5	786.2	852.7
3551	PA3530_at	1511.3	1320.3	200.4	164.7	147.7
3552	PA3531_bfrB_at	266.7	802.5	222.4	297.7	312.9
3553	PA3532_at	37.9	28.5	25.1	35.8	46.5
3554	PA3533_at	815.9	897.8	1157.7	1146.1	1326.4
3555	PA3534_at	90.5	77.8	202.4	91.5	84.6
3556	PA3535_at	381.6	298.4	513.5	520.0	556.1
3557	PA3536_at	154.9	111.4	195.0	140.3	189.2
3558	PA3537_argF_at	131.2	62.3	136.0	131.9	138.5
3559	PA3538_at	191.2	190.0	336.8	320.6	302.9
3560	PA3539_at	341.6	140.3	416.3	349.0	467.4
3561	PA3540_algD_at	78.3	36.1	20.9	25.6	24.9
3562	PA3541_at	10.5	4.0	16.0	16.9	2.3
3563	PA3542_at	90.9	67.6	49.2	49.5	32.9
3564	PA3543_algK_at	6.6	3.9	5.8	3.5	2.1
3565	PA3544_algE_at	12.7	45.9	10.3	19.7	22.2
3566	PA3545_algG_at	11.0	5.1	13.6	29.8	6.0
3567	PA3546_algX_at	56.3	40.7	45.0	73.0	67.6
3568	PA3547_algL_at	8.5	19.2	34.6	16.7	11.4
3569	PA3548_algI_at	18.2	27.4	14.3	21.0	20.7
3570	PA3549_algJ_at	71.6	49.6	40.9	43.7	38.7
3571	PA3550_algF_at	37.2	37.7	25.4	21.6	34.3
3572	PA3551_algA_at	99.7	72.0	70.7	31.5	45.7
3573	PA3552_at	121.6	202.6	288.7	125.6	168.0

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3574	PA3553_at	24.1	88.3	146.0	47.8	71.2
3575	PA3554_at	174.7	362.9	161.0	102.5	185.8
3576	PA3555_at	75.8	80.0	23.8	35.5	10.4
3577	PA3556_at	38.9	198.9	64.9	53.0	74.2
3578	PA3557_at	28.7	86.7	31.2	52.9	42.3
3579	PA3558_at	98.5	235.2	116.1	143.5	158.3
3580	PA3559_at	166.2	313.9	140.1	132.4	119.8
3581	PA3560_fruA_at	83.8	360.8	128.6	187.5	214.7
3582	PA3561_fruK_at	333.0	1489.8	424.1	404.1	491.2
3583	PA3562_at	150.2	425.2	199.0	177.0	215.5
3584	PA3563_fruR_at	492.5	330.4	549.2	449.2	560.1
3585	PA3564_at	73.0	51.2	66.6	49.9	61.7
3586	PA3565_at	283.7	157.3	133.6	195.7	231.7
3587	PA3566_at	715.3	736.1	656.2	680.3	748.3
3588	PA3567_at	297.1	270.3	369.2	405.9	372.3
3589	PA3568_at	73.0	54.3	46.4	44.9	43.7
3590	PA3569_mmsB_at	10.7	52.5	47.5	49.2	42.8
3591	PA3570_mmsA_at	162.6	118.2	160.3	161.9	171.6
3592	PA3571_mmsR_at	160.6	96.0	209.1	178.2	206.9
3593	PA3572_at	74.0	102.1	69.3	65.9	83.8
3594	PA3573_at	5.0	9.5	14.4	94.6	10.6
3595	PA3574_at	64.5	117.2	108.8	115.7	122.9
3596	PA3575_at	161.1	57.0	102.4	131.8	132.3
3597	PA3576_at	244.7	133.5	171.1	227.4	222.6
3598	PA3577_i_at	274.8	380.7	200.4	259.7	236.1
3599	PA3578_at	112.3	68.5	193.4	187.6	166.0
3600	PA3579_at	101.7	75.2	111.3	70.2	77.0
3601	PA3580_at	264.6	190.8	346.3	267.0	288.8
3602	PA3581_glpF_at	1031.6	577.6	1486.0	1340.5	1419.5
3603	PA3582_glpK_at	1140.5	850.5	1811.3	1629.8	1427.5
3604	PA3583_glpR_at	424.4	224.2	315.1	343.1	273.7
3605	PA3584_glpD_at	3404.5	3101.7	1545.4	1345.4	1479.8
3606	PA3585_glpM_at	110.2	119.1	66.9	49.6	41.4
3607	PA3586_at	36.3	2.2	11.8	16.8	9.2
3608	PA3587_metR_at	276.3	145.6	158.9	199.2	248.1
3609	PA3588_at	58.4	16.0	6.6	32.4	18.3
3610	PA3589_at	4.7	4.8	3.4	4.7	1.5
3611	PA3590_at	28.5	25.2	45.1	41.3	3.5
3612	PA3591_at	6.3	9.6	17.0	18.8	22.3
3613	PA3592_at	66.2	32.2	27.4	30.5	38.2
3614	PA3593_at	14.4	26.2	58.0	38.9	39.3
3615	PA3594_at	171.0	154.5	138.3	134.7	160.4
3616	PA3595_at	89.8	28.5	33.3	36.6	21.8
3617	PA3596_at	26.2	45.2	17.2	66.6	80.6
3618	PA3597_at	11.2	5.5	8.1	8.4	24.8
3619	PA3598_at	93.2	64.5	57.5	66.8	56.0
3620	PA3599_at	54.6	69.8	112.1	76.7	128.9
3621	PA3600_at	141.7	252.2	111.9	112.8	106.4
3622	PA3601_at	340.1	469.8	206.8	185.7	199.6
3623	PA3602_at	251.9	169.2	417.9	212.7	283.3
3624	PA3603_dgkA_at	128.4	127.7	127.5	130.0	72.0
3625	PA3604_at	295.7	209.7	401.2	412.5	428.1
3626	PA3605_at	64.6	28.5	40.8	42.3	46.5
3627	PA3606_at	125.0	88.6	150.7	138.9	137.8
3628	PA3607_potA_at	34.9	80.8	45.8	59.3	51.8
3629	PA3608_potB_at	5.9	19.0	2.1	20.3	14.6
3630	PA3609_potC_at	38.5	48.2	37.7	42.5	28.7
3631	PA3610_potD_at	37.9	38.8	15.7	33.6	6.6
3632	PA3611_at	359.7	222.9	593.6	634.6	609.9
3633	PA3612_at	135.5	85.8	196.9	222.5	223.5
3634	PA3613_at	18.8	129.3	9.5	39.2	54.0
3635	PA3614_at	409.7	369.4	373.6	364.3	288.5
3636	PA3615_at	349.8	415.8	331.2	405.1	413.9
3637	PA3616_at	374.7	268.9	386.6	377.4	328.2
3638	PA3617_recA_at	3154.7	1545.7	2075.7	1998.2	1996.1
3639	PA3618_at	288.9	204.1	467.0	446.7	412.4
3640	PA3619_at	9.2	22.0	16.0	32.7	32.9
3641	PA3620_mutS_at	126.9	163.2	204.4	145.3	148.3
3642	PA3621_fdxA_at	169.8	412.7	246.0	169.5	156.4
3643	PA3622_rpoS_at	2139.3	2020.6	2692.5	2629.8	2912.2
3644	PA3623_at	211.2	126.8	188.9	132.5	153.1
3645	PA3624_pcm_at	691.6	470.0	729.9	459.5	485.0
3646	PA3625_surE_at	1015.6	539.5	1188.3	1175.1	1188.4

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3647	PA3626_at	57.2	65.4	176.6	154.8	123.2
3648	PA3627_at	259.0	147.9	242.2	237.8	280.6
3649	PA3628_at	138.7	83.4	242.2	235.0	165.8
3650	PA3629_adhC_at	280.5	155.6	279.3	361.9	353.6
3651	PA3630_at	96.3	49.1	67.0	114.6	109.2
3652	PA3631_at	133.7	91.8	125.0	141.5	152.5
3653	PA3632_at	103.9	128.4	171.8	131.5	131.9
3654	PA3633_at	249.7	167.3	193.9	235.1	228.1
3655	PA3634_at	787.3	1330.9	666.8	643.7	661.8
3656	PA3635_eno_at	160.2	354.2	179.6	190.3	190.9
3657	PA3636_kdsA_at	101.2	183.6	101.7	96.9	90.9
3658	PA3637_pyrG_at	243.0	278.1	480.0	432.3	395.3
3659	PA3638_at	82.6	84.9	15.1	73.3	52.0
3660	PA3639_accA_at	162.3	184.2	254.5	252.6	195.9
3661	PA3640_dnaE_at	231.6	468.1	283.1	219.6	247.7
3662	PA3641_at	121.7	172.2	56.0	79.9	48.2
3663	PA3642_rnhB_at	121.1	157.9	97.8	90.2	83.7
3664	PA3643_lpxB_at	137.6	206.6	159.0	144.2	155.3
3665	PA3644_lpxA_at	255.9	390.4	299.6	284.9	275.6
3666	PA3645_fabZ_at	293.5	362.9	402.9	443.7	421.1
3667	PA3646_lpxD_at	447.0	884.6	363.3	401.4	468.3
3668	PA3647_at	284.6	1195.5	485.4	557.5	555.8
3669	PA3648_at	244.1	329.0	258.3	257.6	234.1
3670	PA3649_at	254.6	324.3	171.3	205.9	196.1
3671	PA3650_dxr_at	182.7	255.9	135.6	132.4	141.8
3672	PA3651_cdsA_at	47.1	118.5	61.0	51.9	59.6
3673	PA3652_uppS_at	157.0	214.6	143.1	125.2	117.5
3674	PA3653_frr_at	319.1	1004.6	380.3	450.9	519.3
3675	PA3654_pyrH_at	132.4	289.9	214.2	195.0	195.8
3676	PA3655_tsf_at	726.6	1084.7	302.0	416.3	369.1
3677	PA3656_rpsB_at	5235.5	5693.6	2335.6	2235.8	2550.7
3678	PA3657_map_at	907.0	470.8	1130.9	1201.6	1223.3
3679	PA3658_glnD_at	93.5	74.2	70.7	84.4	83.5
3680	PA3659_at	138.1	243.8	195.3	168.5	195.9
3681	PA3660_at	92.1	85.4	167.8	162.5	131.0
3682	PA3661_at	218.3	96.3	115.3	105.1	125.6
3683	PA3662_at	2536.7	2414.3	1320.7	1610.6	1938.9
3684	PA3663_at	77.6	82.5	92.1	96.4	97.9
3685	PA3664_at	310.9	131.4	424.3	463.5	465.7
3686	PA3665_at	161.1	91.0	352.6	366.4	385.7
3687	PA3666_dapD_at	228.5	308.5	336.5	293.4	298.2
3688	PA3667_at	112.0	129.9	84.3	112.9	103.2
3689	PA3668_at	87.6	102.3	66.9	59.3	63.8
3690	PA3669_at	11.5	31.2	7.0	17.8	5.5
3691	PA3670_at	67.7	31.4	34.9	34.7	26.5
3692	PA3671_at	32.3	22.2	34.6	24.0	29.5
3693	PA3672_at	46.4	36.9	89.0	76.6	81.5
3694	PA3673_plsB_at	124.1	136.0	169.6	161.7	146.3
3695	PA3674_at	373.1	308.7	319.5	277.7	254.9
3696	PA3675_at	137.9	130.2	157.7	167.8	125.2
3697	PA3676_at	102.1	223.9	251.4	295.9	232.6
3698	PA3677_at	115.4	93.4	222.7	151.7	149.7
3699	PA3678_at	225.5	146.0	244.6	266.4	239.0
3700	PA3679_at	26.3	52.3	84.5	81.2	60.4
3701	PA3680_at	22.6	23.3	57.0	71.3	49.4
3702	PA3681_at	81.2	72.2	22.5	56.8	33.7
3703	PA3682_at	10.2	28.5	53.2	69.0	50.5
3704	PA3683_at	200.3	99.4	217.8	239.9	211.6
3705	PA3684_i_at	511.6	684.2	524.4	656.8	709.1
3706	PA3685_at	13.3	21.1	45.7	60.5	39.5
3707	PA3686_adk_at	96.5	127.5	237.0	202.7	232.1
3708	PA3687_ppc_at	407.2	314.0	555.6	586.0	545.4
3709	PA3688_at	91.9	78.9	140.3	157.7	154.2
3710	PA3689_at	494.4	380.0	378.3	419.6	445.8
3711	PA3690_at	924.2	256.4	275.0	371.1	304.4
3712	PA3691_at	1606.5	975.8	736.1	1016.5	945.3
3713	PA3692_at	617.3	320.8	196.2	383.3	278.8
3714	PA3693_at	77.9	42.3	104.9	50.3	66.0
3715	PA3694_at	48.8	85.2	120.5	88.7	109.1
3716	PA3695_at	89.1	70.9	102.3	107.7	88.3
3717	PA3696_at	12.4	71.9	73.8	68.7	66.5
3718	PA3697_at	259.6	136.4	406.2	392.6	403.8
3719	PA3698_at	228.3	137.9	293.4	434.2	338.7

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3720	PA3699_at	83.0	117.9	214.4	174.6	206.1
3721	PA3700_lyssS_at	270.2	441.8	283.4	224.5	213.9
3722	PA3701_prfB_at	166.3	235.2	329.3	314.0	336.6
3723	PA3702_at	174.8	252.6	143.6	157.9	160.4
3724	PA3703_at	143.0	214.6	227.4	245.7	176.0
3725	PA3704_at	99.9	210.1	82.7	106.2	76.1
3726	PA3705_at	187.3	185.3	98.7	142.8	116.9
3727	PA3706_at	82.6	66.7	38.0	59.5	45.5
3728	PA3707_at	79.3	44.0	67.3	85.5	66.2
3729	PA3708_at	131.6	171.2	181.4	180.6	155.2
3730	PA3709_at	20.4	33.5	41.8	57.0	36.1
3731	PA3710_at	18.1	71.1	172.4	257.9	268.3
3732	PA3711_at	174.6	33.4	98.3	66.4	74.6
3733	PA3712_at	280.4	219.6	415.4	502.0	574.8
3734	PA3713_at	5.2	22.6	8.1	9.8	7.7
3735	PA3714_at	87.6	58.2	78.8	72.9	53.8
3736	PA3715_at	80.2	61.6	100.8	116.7	58.5
3737	PA3716_at	98.0	238.6	114.3	128.6	112.9
3738	PA3717_at	74.2	59.8	92.3	120.0	135.7
3739	PA3718_at	9.4	23.4	16.2	24.8	10.5
3740	PA3719_at	46.7	48.8	68.4	92.8	65.1
3741	PA3720_at	101.2	39.0	86.9	128.6	53.0
3742	PA3721_at	53.9	19.7	21.8	36.0	20.6
3743	PA3722_at	205.4	172.3	329.8	291.5	336.1
3744	PA3723_at	204.7	346.9	618.8	492.1	419.1
3745	PA3724_lasB_at	70.5	184.0	263.0	242.7	292.7
3746	PA3725_recJ_at	101.5	73.0	88.7	88.4	67.7
3747	PA3726_at	63.7	75.2	89.2	79.6	85.7
3748	PA3727_at	132.5	416.1	95.1	70.4	116.7
3749	PA3728_at	93.9	236.6	85.0	81.8	84.9
3750	PA3729_at	482.5	645.3	275.4	295.7	337.3
3751	PA3730_at	202.9	114.5	186.6	134.2	136.3
3752	PA3731_at	1033.6	950.1	931.2	1086.3	1136.7
3753	PA3732_at	957.6	673.2	955.1	780.0	888.8
3754	PA3733_at	66.1	21.0	40.3	54.2	61.9
3755	PA3734_at	104.4	116.7	84.3	109.5	111.6
3756	PA3735_thrC_at	220.5	334.9	175.7	147.3	155.9
3757	PA3736_hom_at	253.0	257.7	446.7	367.8	406.9
3758	PA3737_dsbC_at	317.3	256.2	379.2	353.1	379.3
3759	PA3738_xerD_at	111.5	73.9	179.2	187.0	192.6
3760	PA3739_at	48.1	28.6	63.1	69.3	52.9
3761	PA3740_at	511.2	810.7	633.3	424.6	530.7
3762	PA3741_at	34.3	28.4	12.6	30.1	17.6
3763	PA3742_rplS_at	453.4	1105.0	256.4	247.9	273.7
3764	PA3743_trmD_at	325.1	402.0	308.2	257.7	253.2
3765	PA3744_rimM_at	425.2	460.5	334.0	326.4	375.9
3766	PA3745_rpsP_at	302.2	324.6	552.3	463.7	445.8
3767	PA3746_ffh_at	81.8	108.3	212.0	161.8	231.5
3768	PA3747_at	360.7	145.2	839.7	823.1	553.2
3769	PA3748_at	282.6	179.6	523.0	417.2	409.7
3770	PA3749_at	34.9	40.3	26.4	23.6	23.3
3771	PA3750_at	63.5	28.4	34.2	70.8	39.4
3772	PA3751_purT_at	143.9	137.1	189.3	158.2	132.8
3773	PA3752_at	285.3	193.6	389.7	498.5	414.4
3774	PA3753_at	699.0	721.5	859.0	682.3	658.2
3775	PA3754_at	694.9	402.5	673.0	690.0	678.1
3776	PA3755_at	395.2	208.5	463.4	550.9	575.2
3777	PA3756_at	1348.5	1155.2	1301.0	1239.0	1660.2
3778	PA3757_at	214.6	143.1	395.1	425.1	430.2
3779	PA3758_at	33.9	141.2	286.1	276.4	268.6
3780	PA3759_at	126.4	91.1	125.5	123.6	90.9
3781	PA3760_at	102.0	97.0	73.9	56.3	43.4
3782	PA3761_at	4.8	25.2	19.4	20.0	25.2
3783	PA3762_at	83.0	90.2	61.0	92.7	81.1
3784	PA3763_purL_at	259.3	168.6	336.6	257.8	249.0
3785	PA3764_at	257.2	156.8	305.6	324.8	338.8
3786	PA3765_at	11.3	34.0	43.0	55.8	45.1
3787	PA3766_at	18.8	74.5	52.8	56.0	45.8
3788	PA3767_at	167.2	126.3	173.8	203.2	180.5
3789	PA3768_at	394.8	231.5	692.2	562.6	595.4
3790	PA3769_guaA_at	174.6	369.8	137.0	148.9	163.5
3791	PA3770_guaB_at	124.3	213.3	298.2	258.8	282.1
3792	PA3771_at	60.4	47.7	9.4	59.4	36.9

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3793	PA3772_at	46.8	41.1	59.5	45.4	36.2
3794	PA3773_at	70.2	15.9	7.6	15.7	4.5
3795	PA3774_at	63.0	25.8	26.1	30.6	22.4
3796	PA3775_at	8.0	3.0	3.9	4.8	3.7
3797	PA3776_at	10.1	28.1	51.8	25.4	16.5
3798	PA3777_xseA_at	100.6	91.1	180.4	139.9	136.6
3799	PA3778_at	93.0	70.8	73.9	68.1	49.5
3800	PA3779_at	82.5	83.7	50.7	40.4	45.6
3801	PA3780_at	15.3	29.9	13.2	19.4	3.7
3802	PA3781_at	44.1	33.5	28.5	19.2	17.2
3803	PA3782_at	228.6	72.8	183.3	218.9	208.3
3804	PA3783_at	6.7	49.7	44.5	57.6	66.6
3805	PA3784_at	40.4	53.4	48.5	37.2	31.5
3806	PA3785_at	13.9	7.2	36.9	52.4	37.5
3807	PA3786_at	155.7	48.9	120.1	125.2	202.2
3808	PA3787_at	73.0	77.5	246.6	259.1	374.3
3809	PA3788_at	150.8	108.3	86.3	141.5	109.8
3810	PA3789_at	27.4	2.0	3.8	6.3	6.2
3811	PA3790_oprC_at	32.1	12.4	32.1	38.9	24.1
3812	PA3791_at	92.9	67.5	89.2	85.8	84.2
3813	PA3792_leuA_at	2174.1	1419.8	2151.9	1665.3	1808.8
3814	PA3793_at	191.9	136.4	276.3	270.2	339.6
3815	PA3794_at	126.7	82.9	154.5	206.3	177.2
3816	PA3795_at	254.3	191.9	225.7	192.7	227.3
3817	PA3796_at	115.3	164.4	158.6	167.0	149.5
3818	PA3797_at	389.1	476.0	353.5	457.2	455.8
3819	PA3798_at	17.8	68.1	162.9	154.6	147.1
3820	PA3799_at	233.7	358.2	252.6	230.0	229.6
3821	PA3800_at	337.1	811.3	452.5	386.9	374.4
3822	PA3801_at	444.0	1171.6	657.1	514.4	631.2
3823	PA3802_hisS_at	131.5	532.2	198.7	207.1	226.2
3824	PA3803_at	291.5	851.1	282.2	309.1	294.4
3825	PA3804_at	144.6	522.2	141.7	124.7	132.5
3826	PA3805_pilF_at	70.2	85.0	102.5	91.3	59.3
3827	PA3806_at	197.7	270.6	336.7	235.6	239.1
3828	PA3807_ndk_at	488.8	726.2	531.6	469.4	523.6
3829	PA3808_at	256.6	277.7	174.8	118.2	150.4
3830	PA3809_fdx2_at	533.4	532.0	210.1	255.8	188.6
3831	PA3810_hscA_at	208.7	109.2	80.5	110.1	69.2
3832	PA3811_hscB_at	582.4	326.5	382.0	415.9	368.9
3833	PA3812_iscA_at	1772.3	1361.3	1164.5	1171.6	994.6
3834	PA3813_iscU_at	1281.3	985.3	867.0	949.0	836.9
3835	PA3814_iscS_at	4175.6	2087.4	2283.1	2282.6	2170.3
3836	PA3815_at	4477.6	1306.2	2231.0	2239.6	2061.3
3837	PA3816_cysE_at	241.0	140.0	271.7	251.3	309.8
3838	PA3817_at	175.3	113.9	188.7	165.7	156.7
3839	PA3818_at	74.6	49.4	100.8	82.4	79.5
3840	PA3819_at	1719.7	937.3	1040.3	1062.5	1209.7
3841	PA3820_secF_at	118.8	343.4	75.6	87.6	117.7
3842	PA3821_secD_at	72.3	170.3	170.8	150.5	167.8
3843	PA3822_at	214.5	220.9	637.8	648.1	484.0
3844	PA3823_tgt_at	51.1	121.4	106.0	50.1	50.6
3845	PA3824_queA_at	164.9	75.8	141.9	98.0	95.3
3846	PA3825_at	10.2	13.6	12.2	25.7	5.6
3847	PA3826_at	21.7	28.5	58.2	48.3	34.1
3848	PA3827_at	14.4	58.9	132.7	132.5	109.8
3849	PA3828_at	132.2	105.0	333.9	335.6	253.5
3850	PA3829_at	4.3	23.7	39.9	18.8	41.2
3851	PA3830_at	13.6	15.7	116.2	101.9	84.9
3852	PA3831_pepA_at	296.5	233.6	553.2	518.7	526.4
3853	PA3832_holC_at	201.4	184.2	230.1	234.8	199.7
3854	PA3833_at	674.4	792.5	541.3	459.1	541.1
3855	PA3834_valS_at	219.3	518.9	274.7	214.3	249.9
3856	PA3835_at	18.3	52.0	54.1	51.6	63.6
3857	PA3836_at	355.3	734.8	561.2	524.0	532.1
3858	PA3837_at	195.3	162.5	208.1	195.9	218.8
3859	PA3838_at	222.3	281.5	191.7	193.8	171.6
3860	PA3839_at	107.8	26.0	68.9	52.5	41.4
3861	PA3840_at	18.5	64.4	51.8	42.5	40.7
3862	PA3841_exoS_at	181.7	193.4	102.9	100.2	105.5
3863	PA3842_at	203.5	94.9	63.5	84.1	91.0
3864	PA3843_at	65.4	27.7	24.1	20.4	18.6
3865	PA3844_at	252.7	132.4	279.3	232.7	195.1

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3866	PA3845_at	238.0	180.5	177.7	273.4	256.5
3867	PA3846_at	187.9	196.4	242.4	284.1	279.0
3868	PA3847_at	118.3	48.0	104.3	95.6	124.3
3869	PA3848_at	125.0	107.4	259.5	244.4	211.8
3870	PA3849_at	171.5	147.4	320.8	259.9	242.1
3871	PA3850_at	871.2	730.6	604.0	646.3	697.3
3872	PA3851_at	64.8	96.3	114.2	111.1	120.0
3873	PA3852_at	377.8	281.0	402.8	349.5	297.3
3874	PA3853_at	59.1	52.7	64.3	61.4	53.4
3875	PA3854_at	48.5	67.0	93.1	135.6	113.1
3876	PA3855_at	74.5	58.3	74.7	80.6	73.1
3877	PA3856_at	131.3	98.5	112.0	167.7	154.3
3878	PA3857_at	959.0	632.6	815.0	749.6	795.2
3879	PA3858_at	139.2	117.1	220.2	252.6	248.6
3880	PA3859_at	142.0	142.1	218.4	205.5	212.1
3881	PA3860_at	128.3	146.6	156.6	166.4	136.6
3882	PA3861_rhlB_at	310.5	316.0	540.8	475.4	459.2
3883	PA3862_at	165.6	95.1	259.5	265.9	272.6
3884	PA3863_at	145.0	55.3	102.1	96.7	65.0
3885	PA3864_at	101.1	60.1	57.5	81.3	60.4
3886	PA3865_at	266.9	206.7	278.4	214.1	219.9
3887	PA3866_at	54.4	47.0	30.0	61.4	44.4
3888	PA3867_at	57.7	94.3	166.2	143.1	134.0
3889	PA3868_at	52.8	67.0	50.0	75.7	33.9
3890	PA3869_at	42.6	66.2	51.3	48.7	46.0
3891	PA3870_moaA1_at	6.4	4.3	26.9	5.3	11.9
3892	PA3871_at	61.6	23.0	30.8	29.9	43.6
3893	PA3872_narI_at	79.5	48.3	59.2	54.6	58.4
3894	PA3873_narJ_at	76.5	20.6	25.3	33.7	19.3
3895	PA3874_narH_at	5.4	46.9	26.7	33.2	18.9
3896	PA3875_narG_at	16.5	17.0	3.6	17.1	22.7
3897	PA3876_narK2_at	23.5	32.3	21.5	37.7	8.4
3898	PA3877_narK1_at	26.5	29.2	7.4	3.9	2.1
3899	PA3878_narX_at	130.3	128.0	152.9	108.7	119.9
3900	PA3879_narL_at	174.9	211.7	216.5	155.4	135.6
3901	PA3880_at	96.3	111.6	90.9	100.2	73.1
3902	PA3881_at	291.1	223.4	294.4	442.0	477.7
3903	PA3882_at	143.8	122.2	214.5	270.6	218.3
3904	PA3883_at	82.5	71.4	77.8	59.2	52.8
3905	PA3884_at	11.8	13.4	28.7	23.5	25.8
3906	PA3885_at	34.5	54.7	11.8	20.1	26.5
3907	PA3886_at	124.1	61.4	162.0	149.0	213.4
3908	PA3887_nhaP_at	9.9	26.2	71.4	71.0	54.9
3909	PA3888_at	35.2	21.7	56.2	52.9	45.8
3910	PA3889_at	34.6	42.1	78.0	71.7	75.8
3911	PA3890_at	69.9	3.8	20.0	29.9	18.5
3912	PA3891_at	87.9	48.1	41.9	44.9	49.6
3913	PA3892_at	50.0	82.2	52.2	45.2	45.5
3914	PA3893_at	53.8	91.3	53.2	50.2	46.3
3915	PA3894_at	52.9	55.9	82.9	75.0	47.6
3916	PA3895_at	193.8	134.4	297.9	389.9	260.4
3917	PA3896_at	83.0	77.8	174.1	137.6	135.1
3918	PA3897_at	15.6	5.5	13.6	4.0	15.7
3919	PA3898_at	287.7	168.8	354.5	332.4	374.3
3920	PA3899_at	445.1	187.2	315.7	297.5	296.5
3921	PA3900_at	208.2	104.8	233.8	203.1	202.5
3922	PA3901_fecA_at	167.3	230.4	67.0	73.9	45.6
3923	PA3902_at	167.5	110.1	147.4	181.3	156.5
3924	PA3903_prfC_at	121.0	250.3	256.5	221.9	215.2
3925	PA3904_i_at	598.6	497.0	965.1	834.8	846.8
3926	PA3905_at	37.5	59.2	110.3	89.3	88.8
3927	PA3906_at	109.2	157.2	208.8	216.3	161.0
3928	PA3907_at	176.1	480.9	148.5	169.0	126.8
3929	PA3908_at	102.5	295.4	87.1	88.9	76.0
3930	PA3909_at	9.6	23.3	31.0	25.8	5.6
3931	PA3910_at	58.8	18.4	22.4	29.0	10.6
3932	PA3911_at	10.7	118.0	37.8	99.0	66.1
3933	PA3912_at	29.9	37.8	26.2	9.8	20.4
3934	PA3913_at	38.3	18.7	14.4	12.6	10.9
3935	PA3914_moeA1_at	10.3	3.1	2.8	5.8	7.2
3936	PA3915_moaB1_at	57.5	41.1	31.3	55.7	33.1
3937	PA3916_moaE_at	223.5	185.9	267.3	314.8	288.1
3938	PA3917_moaD_at	199.7	237.6	303.3	375.0	371.8

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

3939	PA3918_moac_at	389.5	379.7	470.7	546.0	672.3
3940	PA3919_at	1339.1	1389.7	1018.3	1624.8	1533.0
3941	PA3920_at	61.4	138.3	52.9	1484.0	34.3
3942	PA3921_at	167.5	87.4	124.1	111.6	103.3
3943	PA3922_at	75.3	259.1	181.8	151.5	249.1
3944	PA3923_at	78.4	216.8	248.8	278.3	351.3
3945	PA3924_at	97.9	92.3	71.9	90.0	111.8
3946	PA3925_at	85.0	120.3	107.8	95.4	85.7
3947	PA3926_at	95.8	35.8	27.5	36.9	18.1
3948	PA3927_at	197.7	59.1	80.7	98.7	130.4
3949	PA3928_r_at	91.2	51.6	68.5	78.7	61.1
3950	PA3929_cioB_at	92.9	60.7	57.2	66.1	53.8
3951	PA3930_cioA_at	157.3	69.5	179.1	171.1	201.0
3952	PA3931_at	11196.7	304.8	175.9	170.5	475.6
3953	PA3932_at	548.5	47.4	41.7	47.7	67.5
3954	PA3933_at	9.0	9.1	9.7	18.1	16.0
3955	PA3934_at	157.9	151.8	253.0	223.8	203.5
3956	PA3935_tauD_at	376.1	80.0	64.7	64.8	63.8
3957	PA3936_at	230.8	38.0	51.5	40.1	13.9
3958	PA3937_at	243.9	48.3	26.7	29.1	25.9
3959	PA3938_at	639.0	41.1	43.1	63.1	53.0
3960	PA3939_at	256.0	35.5	29.2	50.8	50.3
3961	PA3940_at	674.4	1022.9	668.5	631.9	807.6
3962	PA3941_at	214.0	164.7	199.0	185.5	153.9
3963	PA3942_tesB_at	469.4	364.2	470.6	354.7	410.5
3964	PA3943_at	207.1	164.1	162.6	171.8	169.4
3965	PA3944_at	221.3	143.8	241.5	295.4	279.5
3966	PA3945_at	492.3	517.9	560.7	694.0	648.9
3967	PA3946_at	26.9	48.3	72.3	78.9	61.4
3968	PA3947_at	66.3	32.1	56.6	64.4	53.3
3969	PA3948_at	256.3	128.0	176.4	167.6	157.1
3970	PA3949_at	72.2	81.9	174.1	142.1	140.3
3971	PA3950_at	201.4	171.6	260.4	281.1	257.7
3972	PA3951_at	296.4	165.0	203.6	162.8	186.4
3973	PA3952_at	230.1	122.7	186.2	181.3	173.1
3974	PA3953_at	10.6	7.5	47.4	68.1	70.8
3975	PA3954_at	4.9	44.0	31.8	22.7	22.4
3976	PA3955_at	90.4	43.1	120.6	83.1	74.5
3977	PA3956_at	39.6	35.1	42.9	56.4	44.8
3978	PA3957_at	34.8	20.5	6.5	37.9	24.7
3979	PA3958_at	24.8	64.7	146.4	106.2	113.4
3980	PA3959_at	61.9	29.0	53.1	62.5	62.2
3981	PA3960_at	47.3	49.9	72.8	66.5	40.6
3982	PA3961_at	158.5	125.0	171.4	162.6	152.4
3983	PA3962_at	320.7	116.5	198.5	163.0	193.0
3984	PA3963_at	5.3	13.3	47.7	39.9	51.2
3985	PA3964_at	37.6	16.4	23.5	38.4	21.1
3986	PA3965_at	193.3	166.5	183.3	153.4	157.4
3987	PA3966_at	214.5	116.2	218.9	260.0	302.6
3988	PA3967_at	12.4	44.4	52.5	61.3	45.4
3989	PA3968_at	133.8	76.9	79.2	80.7	66.3
3990	PA3969_at	350.3	252.2	413.8	456.0	447.6
3991	PA3970_amn_at	931.1	847.0	881.7	738.2	911.5
3992	PA3971_at	196.0	319.0	250.1	228.3	161.5
3993	PA3972_at	444.2	1034.0	794.6	727.6	776.3
3994	PA3973_at	529.7	1266.6	612.6	630.6	704.9
3995	PA3974_at	81.6	45.1	57.1	42.6	47.5
3996	PA3975_thiD_at	563.4	228.2	731.4	699.3	789.0
3997	PA3976_thiE_at	508.0	223.7	577.8	566.6	610.2
3998	PA3977_hemL_at	363.2	461.3	592.5	487.7	541.5
3999	PA3978_at	1372.0	1539.3	1193.3	1139.3	1189.1
4000	PA3979_at	63.7	74.8	51.4	44.8	40.5
4001	PA3980_at	137.5	104.7	251.2	222.5	217.7
4002	PA3981_at	3592.4	2208.0	2545.0	2436.5	2713.4
4003	PA3982_at	2772.8	1953.0	2323.1	2401.5	2402.9
4004	PA3983_at	236.4	229.7	276.5	347.0	360.5
4005	PA3984_lnt_at	5.1	31.7	77.2	102.0	92.9
4006	PA3985_at	45.8	49.3	64.9	63.3	53.3
4007	PA3986_at	124.4	122.8	131.9	141.9	117.1
4008	PA3987_leuS_at	521.8	740.6	846.9	699.3	734.8
4009	PA3988_at	301.1	528.9	531.2	473.0	533.7
4010	PA3989_holA_at	207.1	399.5	220.7	208.4	215.8
4011	PA3990_at	215.4	454.2	144.6	90.6	71.6

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4012	PA3991_at	54.3	16.3	2.4	19.3	11.8
4013	PA3992_at	88.6	50.1	116.0	119.6	71.8
4014	PA3994_at	53.1	16.9	10.2	28.8	40.3
4015	PA3995_at	83.3	93.0	106.0	91.7	93.0
4016	PA3996_lipA_at	244.3	363.4	293.0	263.5	268.0
4017	PA3997_lipB_at	273.3	249.9	275.3	282.9	241.0
4018	PA3998_at	546.2	621.5	512.4	574.2	593.4
4019	PA3999_dacC_at	806.3	1299.5	847.1	862.9	870.3
4020	PA4000_at	309.3	348.4	239.7	261.1	260.9
4021	PA4001_mltB2_at	222.6	356.3	339.7	277.5	300.3
4022	PA4002_rodA_at	120.1	148.5	107.6	110.5	85.7
4023	PA4003_pbpA_at	103.3	173.5	128.5	170.0	134.1
4024	PA4004_at	138.8	159.7	145.6	118.4	134.3
4025	PA4005_at	75.7	140.1	153.7	119.9	106.1
4026	PA4006_at	101.6	143.4	178.2	155.7	151.9
4027	PA4007_proA_at	234.6	159.0	274.4	257.5	275.3
4028	PA4008_at	12.5	32.2	23.6	48.4	50.8
4029	PA4009_at	36.7	45.0	29.9	49.9	50.9
4030	PA4010_at	281.0	183.5	334.7	289.4	312.2
4031	PA4011_at	144.8	161.8	290.3	193.8	190.0
4032	PA4012_at	122.7	175.4	200.3	220.7	234.7
4033	PA4013_at	136.8	106.5	116.0	68.9	122.6
4034	PA4014_at	74.7	132.1	380.4	313.4	282.8
4035	PA4015_at	708.9	590.5	1208.4	842.3	893.9
4036	PA4016_at	40.8	48.0	63.4	57.8	79.2
4037	PA4017_at	235.6	209.1	208.8	284.4	251.2
4038	PA4018_r_at	16.7	53.0	120.9	87.9	69.8
4039	PA4019_at	187.8	163.2	192.8	192.2	191.4
4040	PA4020_mpl_at	359.6	281.9	349.2	436.7	445.2
4041	PA4021_at	246.9	116.6	327.3	355.3	315.4
4042	PA4023_at	172.1	309.5	435.3	385.8	363.7
4043	PA4024_eutB_at	257.4	639.5	367.4	364.9	370.4
4044	PA4025_r_at	234.5	466.5	314.8	278.7	295.3
4045	PA4026_at	425.6	366.3	411.7	412.2	430.0
4046	PA4027_at	340.9	327.5	307.0	374.1	389.4
4047	PA4028_i_at	53.2	71.1	56.6	65.8	53.9
4048	PA4029_at	110.3	67.7	187.0	166.6	175.4
4049	PA4030_at	94.5	100.5	167.8	215.4	167.6
4050	PA4031_ppa_at	269.6	146.0	372.0	258.7	317.1
4051	PA4032_at	140.7	115.5	203.8	170.7	171.1
4052	PA4033_at	48.9	28.3	19.4	22.5	12.2
4053	PA4034_aqpZ_at	11.9	23.6	30.4	21.3	22.8
4054	PA4035_at	136.1	96.9	252.7	265.3	280.6
4055	PA4036_at	98.4	29.4	14.2	58.9	47.9
4056	PA4037_at	38.6	32.2	47.4	38.4	34.0
4057	PA4038_at	4.3	1.5	4.8	16.2	7.2
4058	PA4039_at	21.8	32.6	10.9	26.4	18.0
4059	PA4040_at	131.5	209.4	106.3	113.9	155.8
4060	PA4041_at	25.7	17.2	21.9	47.0	35.2
4061	PA4042_xseB_at	278.1	197.9	602.0	537.2	560.2
4062	PA4043_ispA_at	147.9	132.5	267.0	267.5	250.2
4063	PA4044_dxs_at	403.0	282.0	484.1	553.4	559.8
4064	PA4045_at	61.9	48.8	57.7	56.0	58.2
4065	PA4046_at	90.7	61.4	95.9	103.4	89.7
4066	PA4047_ribA_at	299.9	156.1	463.9	390.8	412.9
4067	PA4048_at	9.2	64.3	66.1	71.3	56.8
4068	PA4049_at	122.0	144.2	149.0	188.8	162.4
4069	PA4050_pgpA_at	76.6	113.2	147.6	107.4	107.1
4070	PA4051_thiL_at	44.3	84.1	138.2	127.1	123.7
4071	PA4052_nusB_at	271.2	335.1	374.1	305.9	318.3
4072	PA4053_ribE_at	385.6	353.7	547.2	490.0	543.6
4073	PA4054_ribB_at	228.8	368.0	168.5	151.1	187.2
4074	PA4055_ribC_at	18.2	62.8	113.8	78.1	101.6
4075	PA4056_ribD_at	383.5	274.3	485.3	490.6	477.3
4076	PA4057_at	555.9	312.9	965.5	838.4	889.4
4077	PA4058_at	99.7	64.8	255.0	265.1	252.0
4078	PA4059_at	171.4	126.4	308.6	321.7	290.5
4079	PA4060_at	106.2	85.7	145.6	182.6	137.3
4080	PA4061_at	664.4	355.4	650.7	663.4	715.4
4081	PA4062_at	6.1	19.0	12.1	32.3	28.5
4082	PA4063_at	9.5	72.9	131.4	126.5	117.5
4083	PA4064_at	51.4	15.7	65.1	33.8	62.8
4084	PA4065_at	20.3	40.3	75.2	69.5	90.9

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4085	PA4066_at	15.6	33.7	35.4	40.7	56.4
4086	PA4067_oprG_at	279.2	520.8	312.5	303.2	218.8
4087	PA4068_at	305.5	282.5	130.3	177.9	185.3
4088	PA4069_at	454.1	258.3	557.3	592.7	632.1
4089	PA4070_at	109.6	57.4	80.4	129.7	114.4
4090	PA4071_at	6.0	2.6	3.2	4.6	4.6
4091	PA4072_at	24.8	10.4	13.0	19.4	3.6
4092	PA4073_at	90.5	57.2	43.7	77.6	67.3
4093	PA4074_at	31.1	7.1	20.1	39.1	23.9
4094	PA4075_at	22.5	14.2	64.5	44.0	52.7
4095	PA4076_at	82.1	53.5	122.4	104.7	106.2
4096	PA4077_at	32.1	22.9	86.9	83.2	73.0
4097	PA4078_at	56.5	18.0	20.0	23.3	38.7
4098	PA4079_at	170.7	124.1	310.3	375.7	341.6
4099	PA4080_at	222.1	182.9	239.8	172.4	172.3
4100	PA4081_at	19.2	38.9	31.0	23.9	29.7
4101	PA4082_at	2.8	13.6	28.4	19.1	16.2
4102	PA4083_at	70.5	20.7	4.3	45.4	18.3
4103	PA4084_at	4.8	3.2	3.0	11.6	3.9
4104	PA4085_at	26.3	12.0	8.0	18.2	4.2
4105	PA4086_at	34.1	58.1	67.3	67.0	46.1
4106	PA4087_at	102.7	46.0	53.6	65.4	59.4
4107	PA4088_at	55.1	13.4	13.1	20.8	3.5
4108	PA4089_at	26.4	3.1	7.1	15.4	3.7
4109	PA4090_at	2328.9	1365.7	1226.0	1380.2	1409.4
4110	PA4091_hpaA_at	11.7	61.9	105.6	98.4	80.8
4111	PA4092_hpaC_at	28.5	25.0	32.8	20.3	44.7
4112	PA4093_at	54.6	46.1	60.7	47.6	70.0
4113	PA4094_at	571.9	518.5	457.5	530.6	610.1
4114	PA4095_at	42.5	22.9	50.0	30.1	29.1
4115	PA4096_at	20.9	11.6	9.0	11.4	9.4
4116	PA4097_at	33.0	12.3	41.8	56.9	11.5
4117	PA4098_at	53.7	33.4	34.8	30.7	23.1
4118	PA4099_at	22.0	3.3	39.5	21.6	4.2
4119	PA4100_at	5.8	7.0	7.7	19.0	7.7
4120	PA4101_at	178.8	136.4	138.2	202.7	188.7
4121	PA4102_at	95.6	123.7	131.2	142.3	95.8
4122	PA4103_at	9.6	24.8	5.0	17.5	2.0
4123	PA4104_at	67.4	42.9	43.3	48.1	50.8
4124	PA4105_at	14.1	8.7	5.9	8.8	6.2
4125	PA4106_at	64.2	13.5	26.5	33.3	13.8
4126	PA4107_at	8.2	33.8	37.6	46.6	25.6
4127	PA4108_at	128.8	82.5	125.2	130.7	120.5
4128	PA4109_ampR_at	63.5	70.6	149.4	160.1	133.7
4129	PA4110_ampC_at	111.5	106.0	94.3	69.3	80.5
4130	PA4111_i_at	668.1	694.3	498.2	610.7	683.7
4131	PA4112_at	66.3	92.1	90.9	57.8	52.3
4132	PA4113_at	44.5	31.6	42.3	38.4	31.0
4133	PA4114_at	190.2	80.1	250.9	249.9	285.4
4134	PA4115_at	565.4	430.1	716.5	799.3	710.5
4135	PA4116_at	313.2	186.9	383.7	310.2	279.1
4136	PA4117_at	316.9	442.1	490.7	373.3	378.1
4137	PA4118_at	83.8	81.4	117.2	115.0	105.7
4138	PA4119_aph_at	63.9	27.4	26.1	36.0	38.7
4139	PA4120_at	13.5	33.5	31.3	34.8	47.4
4140	PA4121_at	75.8	40.7	51.8	72.7	56.2
4141	PA4122_at	27.9	25.7	31.8	56.3	11.2
4142	PA4123_hpcC_at	35.3	48.7	8.1	41.4	10.9
4143	PA4124_hpcB_at	3.8	27.0	41.9	51.4	32.9
4144	PA4125_hpcD_at	87.8	48.4	51.7	47.3	45.3
4145	PA4126_at	44.3	30.1	32.6	53.4	44.9
4146	PA4127_hpcG_at	34.4	14.6	8.2	13.3	16.1
4147	PA4128_at	97.6	56.3	55.7	34.6	47.3
4148	PA4129_at	62.1	49.4	77.0	60.5	90.1
4149	PA4130_at	48.0	98.2	225.8	139.2	103.5
4150	PA4131_at	6.7	46.4	125.2	59.7	77.6
4151	PA4132_at	90.1	46.6	110.7	89.9	82.3
4152	PA4133_at	63.7	76.0	95.1	82.0	51.5
4153	PA4134_i_at	9.2	6.4	9.9	23.9	6.1
4154	PA4135_at	48.4	48.0	88.4	88.6	78.7
4155	PA4136_at	30.1	30.3	51.5	82.4	46.1
4156	PA4137_at	33.1	16.9	5.0	5.1	14.3
4157	PA4138_tyrS_at	95.5	68.2	56.7	35.4	43.1

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4158	PA4139_at	67.6	111.7	94.5	60.5	53.6
4159	PA4140_at	10.1	43.7	61.3	43.3	50.3
4160	PA4141_at	330.3	518.2	224.8	299.7	320.0
4161	PA4142_at	73.8	123.9	112.4	83.6	107.0
4162	PA4143_at	20.9	57.2	64.7	56.1	45.9
4163	PA4144_at	47.9	72.3	51.8	48.6	43.7
4164	PA4145_at	100.3	40.9	104.8	70.1	70.5
4165	PA4146_at	6.8	33.8	42.4	56.3	44.8
4166	PA4147_acoR_at	198.5	76.6	127.2	127.3	106.2
4167	PA4148_at	8.4	4.2	4.9	13.3	4.3
4168	PA4149_at	20.2	18.5	42.7	21.4	20.5
4169	PA4150_at	15.7	13.5	29.8	54.6	48.4
4170	PA4151_acoB_at	46.2	4.1	7.8	13.6	25.1
4171	PA4152_at	86.4	39.9	24.1	35.9	25.2
4172	PA4153_at	13.5	28.8	24.1	33.2	31.0
4173	PA4154_at	88.3	56.1	43.3	50.9	41.7
4174	PA4155_at	136.4	73.4	123.7	120.3	138.1
4175	PA4156_at	511.4	273.5	440.2	276.5	345.7
4176	PA4157_at	41.1	32.3	62.9	74.7	75.2
4177	PA4158_fepC_at	168.6	95.1	65.7	54.1	90.7
4178	PA4159_fepB_at	270.4	143.2	59.2	65.0	57.0
4179	PA4160_fepD_at	130.5	38.0	60.2	76.1	51.0
4180	PA4161_fepG_at	101.0	42.8	79.7	48.6	50.1
4181	PA4162_at	144.5	74.3	144.0	197.2	186.9
4182	PA4163_at	272.9	164.6	382.3	425.5	421.4
4183	PA4164_at	124.4	133.3	149.0	179.0	161.5
4184	PA4165_at	31.4	22.1	107.7	97.2	91.6
4185	PA4166_at	53.1	18.8	5.9	27.0	6.3
4186	PA4167_at	29.4	43.8	18.9	33.6	33.7
4187	PA4168_at	297.6	211.0	394.1	257.2	315.4
4188	PA4169_at	64.2	27.5	14.2	70.6	45.6
4189	PA4170_at	115.5	42.6	68.0	67.7	66.0
4190	PA4171_at	123.8	55.4	87.7	78.2	88.0
4191	PA4172_at	39.8	30.3	39.4	54.7	52.5
4192	PA4173_at	19.5	30.8	37.2	36.8	22.5
4193	PA4174_at	88.1	54.0	61.1	82.6	61.6
4194	PA4175_at	117.5	244.4	162.3	105.2	148.6
4195	PA4176_ppic2_at	200.9	217.7	291.4	286.4	259.0
4196	PA4177_at	15.6	6.2	8.3	15.6	15.5
4197	PA4178_at	35.7	18.7	35.6	28.5	22.0
4198	PA4179_at	28.9	42.6	8.2	34.4	5.6
4199	PA4180_at	235.6	142.3	293.8	324.5	396.8
4200	PA4181_at	229.5	120.6	164.0	163.5	188.1
4201	PA4182_at	179.0	84.6	166.8	181.1	256.9
4202	PA4183_at	155.9	87.6	136.6	115.2	117.6
4203	PA4184_at	221.3	163.9	343.7	291.2	303.0
4204	PA4185_at	265.5	211.7	266.0	255.2	311.6
4205	PA4186_at	53.9	59.7	39.8	41.8	47.9
4206	PA4187_at	54.0	21.7	49.6	37.9	30.4
4207	PA4188_at	67.8	43.2	35.3	32.1	20.4
4208	PA4189_at	32.0	2.5	3.6	5.0	4.6
4209	PA4190_at	94.2	135.3	175.7	164.8	204.7
4210	PA4191_at	58.2	29.7	43.0	23.6	39.9
4211	PA4192_at	54.5	25.4	30.0	37.2	37.8
4212	PA4193_at	48.8	14.2	25.7	25.7	20.2
4213	PA4194_at	236.9	44.1	43.7	53.7	39.4
4214	PA4195_at	442.7	55.7	34.5	50.4	30.8
4215	PA4196_at	165.1	138.0	157.1	103.2	136.2
4216	PA4197_at	107.1	122.9	88.8	90.1	94.3
4217	PA4198_at	144.5	94.9	86.5	105.0	83.1
4218	PA4199_at	109.0	179.7	135.4	152.8	191.4
4219	PA4200_at	79.7	76.3	21.1	66.6	33.1
4220	PA4201_ddlA_at	179.9	136.3	225.3	209.1	200.0
4221	PA4202_at	377.2	271.9	306.0	331.7	313.1
4222	PA4203_at	243.8	184.8	229.6	218.0	253.1
4223	PA4204_at	216.3	196.5	177.2	181.6	163.7
4224	PA4205_at	319.9	281.6	203.9	157.1	171.6
4225	PA4206_at	356.7	255.9	287.4	344.9	239.5
4226	PA4207_at	232.4	124.1	147.2	136.6	114.8
4227	PA4208_at	385.8	163.2	95.7	133.9	100.6
4228	PA4209_at	8.2	64.4	132.7	137.6	111.3
4229	PA4217_at	13.3	64.8	56.3	37.6	52.5
4230	PA4218_at	535.6	7.5	136.7	187.6	135.1

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4231	PA4219_at	281.7	16.0	133.6	168.0	127.3
4232	PA4220_i_at	851.0	15.8	582.5	621.3	508.0
4233	PA4221_fptA_at	2185.5	133.7	1185.8	958.9	1017.1
4234	PA4222_at	75.7	12.9	60.3	49.9	40.5
4235	PA4223_at	140.5	22.8	83.2	68.5	55.6
4236	PA4224_at	175.9	31.4	110.7	110.1	48.3
4237	PA4225_pchF_at	124.4	2.2	17.8	40.5	32.8
4238	PA4226_pchE_at	798.7	26.0	226.6	265.4	227.4
4239	PA4227_pchR_at	1127.9	894.0	772.0	698.9	757.5
4240	PA4228_pchD_at	1474.0	130.8	1027.1	820.8	901.4
4241	PA4229_pchC_at	1280.3	135.3	915.9	736.8	718.6
4242	PA4230_pchB_at	787.5	58.9	480.2	441.3	429.0
4243	PA4231_pchA_at	331.7	8.0	180.5	223.9	175.8
4244	PA4232_ssb_at	722.4	841.3	1238.9	963.3	965.2
4245	PA4233_at	19.0	48.8	65.8	72.0	64.8
4246	PA4234_uvrA_at	115.1	162.0	260.9	219.2	263.2
4247	PA4235_bfrA_at	664.9	380.3	908.5	925.1	947.1
4248	PA4236_katA_at	16689.4	8171.4	7845.3	7493.0	7504.3
4249	PA4237_rplQ_at	2053.2	2729.6	1228.9	1327.3	1284.0
4250	PA4238_rpoA_at	4444.1	5774.8	2877.1	3055.0	3011.4
4251	PA4239_rpsD_at	2139.4	3492.8	1551.7	1626.5	1378.7
4252	PA4240_rpsK_at	3907.6	5496.1	2226.9	2531.1	2569.3
4253	PA4241_rpsM_at	3094.3	5128.2	2206.1	1965.8	1948.3
4254	PA4242_rpmJ_at	6350.9	8548.7	3175.6	2693.3	2607.7
4255	PA4243_secY_at	2229.2	2532.2	1009.6	631.5	662.6
4256	PA4244_rplO_at	2696.4	4062.4	2244.4	1967.8	1892.5
4257	PA4245_rpmD_at	3799.0	6599.2	2098.9	1554.6	1440.5
4258	PA4246_rpsE_at	3649.6	7192.3	2515.5	1953.5	1869.1
4259	PA4247_rplR_at	3166.6	5012.9	2142.3	1796.9	1579.5
4260	PA4248_rplF_at	2730.2	3897.8	2192.0	1754.0	1709.0
4261	PA4249_rpsH_at	3743.9	6242.2	3172.5	2727.1	2868.1
4262	PA4250_rpsN_at	3938.7	4895.7	2217.2	2551.9	2627.4
4263	PA4251_rplE_at	8557.0	11029.6	4428.9	4752.6	5145.4
4264	PA4252_rplX_at	3235.4	6175.1	1774.1	1638.7	1990.9
4265	PA4253_rplN_at	4980.2	7283.5	2478.2	2520.1	2613.6
4266	PA4254_rpsQ_at	6020.7	8731.6	2832.3	2852.6	3012.4
4267	PA4255_rpmC_at	458.8	1513.0	248.9	349.2	306.4
4268	PA4256_rplP_at	2117.2	4970.3	1133.2	1462.4	1428.5
4269	PA4257_rpsC_at	1992.2	4441.1	1092.5	1109.1	1078.1
4270	PA4258_rplV_at	2420.1	5358.8	1497.8	1641.5	1758.2
4271	PA4259_rpsS_at	2762.7	6115.4	1333.3	1279.3	1413.0
4272	PA4260_rplB_at	2444.5	4534.7	1835.0	1831.1	2189.4
4273	PA4261_rplW_at	1579.1	4581.1	1213.5	1266.4	1247.6
4274	PA4262_rplD_at	1087.0	3084.0	1201.9	1047.2	953.7
4275	PA4263_rplC_at	1730.8	3705.9	1512.6	1228.8	1256.9
4276	PA4264_rpsJ_at	2392.7	4161.9	1747.1	1802.3	1762.2
4277	PA4265_tufA_s_at	1353.5	3014.5	1181.9	987.0	975.0
4278	PA4266_fusA1_at	1532.3	2493.3	1361.3	1256.3	1152.0
4279	PA4267_rpsG_at	3330.0	3666.6	2669.5	2564.7	2565.2
4280	PA4268_rpsL_at	1257.6	1568.0	995.1	747.3	748.6
4281	PA4269_rpoC_at	2465.6	4513.6	2168.2	2237.9	2413.7
4282	PA4270_rpoB_at	720.4	1978.6	484.3	540.7	586.7
4283	PA4271_rplL_at	3162.4	6879.3	2584.1	2939.5	2106.5
4284	PA4272_rplJ_at	8065.9	10063.7	4476.8	4425.3	4511.3
4285	PA4273_rplA_at	3703.3	5015.7	2055.0	2122.8	2218.6
4286	PA4274_rplK_at	9339.1	8988.8	3726.3	4215.0	4094.1
4287	PA4275_nusG_at	136.9	154.2	275.0	245.2	211.9
4288	PA4276_secE_at	280.9	157.9	767.1	581.1	593.7
4289	PA4278_at	42.2	88.1	57.8	89.1	72.8
4290	PA4279_at	130.3	162.9	221.0	202.3	189.9
4291	PA4280_birA_at	172.8	142.9	172.4	202.0	172.5
4292	PA4281_sbcD_at	186.2	157.7	304.1	374.3	341.8
4293	PA4282_at	110.5	110.1	95.6	126.1	97.5
4294	PA4283_recD_at	154.3	219.4	187.3	147.1	186.3
4295	PA4284_recB_at	246.1	361.5	247.8	255.4	246.6
4296	PA4285_recC_at	301.8	138.9	136.3	172.2	130.4
4297	PA4286_at	376.2	283.8	405.6	419.2	438.6
4298	PA4287_at	25.1	28.3	39.3	53.0	56.4
4299	PA4288_at	407.4	503.8	271.5	300.4	298.3
4300	PA4289_at	52.6	79.4	107.0	122.4	106.6
4301	PA4290_at	315.3	583.2	369.2	473.5	448.4
4302	PA4291_at	175.4	65.6	102.1	140.6	133.5
4303	PA4292_at	61.7	126.1	137.3	94.5	89.0

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4304	PA4293_at	19.2	44.7	33.9	47.8	38.4
4305	PA4294_at	150.5	154.4	113.0	115.2	109.3
4306	PA4295_at	54.0	60.4	49.6	52.2	65.1
4307	PA4296_at	2169.4	1367.7	1621.8	1945.2	1944.3
4308	PA4297_at	10.4	8.2	8.6	28.4	6.0
4309	PA4298_at	44.9	16.0	21.2	19.1	17.6
4310	PA4299_at	119.0	74.0	53.5	78.3	58.5
4311	PA4300_at	38.2	36.6	36.6	46.0	33.3
4312	PA4301_at	135.1	37.6	52.4	40.6	38.3
4313	PA4302_at	69.0	19.7	24.7	14.7	6.9
4314	PA4303_at	49.0	43.4	29.6	48.7	41.8
4315	PA4304_at	37.2	32.1	67.8	53.4	39.4
4316	PA4305_at	74.3	73.2	121.3	133.5	87.3
4317	PA4306_at	99.7	178.0	67.0	88.8	95.4
4318	PA4307_pctC_at	52.7	54.9	97.1	85.9	44.2
4319	PA4308_at	95.7	60.1	113.8	115.1	156.8
4320	PA4309_pctA_at	382.5	303.8	803.9	641.1	701.5
4321	PA4310_pctB_at	444.5	345.3	760.6	792.9	796.7
4322	PA4311_at	195.8	168.5	254.0	327.3	323.6
4323	PA4312_at	246.3	204.7	291.1	332.1	401.0
4324	PA4313_at	63.5	58.4	56.3	63.7	40.5
4325	PA4314_purU1_at	576.1	276.9	847.0	743.7	794.1
4326	PA4315_mvAT_at	13831.4	11032.5	7681.9	7901.9	8611.7
4327	PA4316_sbcB_at	211.5	151.8	356.0	278.0	264.7
4328	PA4317_at	2015.7	987.0	1896.6	1773.8	1839.2
4329	PA4318_at	280.6	102.8	277.9	252.9	229.8
4330	PA4319_at	94.9	74.1	134.2	135.1	117.2
4331	PA4320_at	140.1	150.9	107.9	99.7	89.7
4332	PA4321_at	222.6	489.1	175.8	185.7	179.7
4333	PA4322_at	237.7	467.8	196.8	181.7	179.5
4334	PA4323_at	147.1	327.9	180.4	229.9	178.1
4335	PA4324_at	417.9	280.3	369.2	548.8	481.2
4336	PA4325_at	243.7	144.6	183.2	187.7	225.5
4337	PA4326_at	135.4	102.4	260.8	284.9	299.2
4338	PA4327_at	194.2	177.1	159.6	173.4	173.1
4339	PA4328_at	44.7	110.3	99.8	112.0	119.3
4340	PA4329_pykA_at	396.1	408.2	571.5	445.6	527.5
4341	PA4330_at	7.0	86.9	152.6	133.2	107.3
4342	PA4331_at	147.6	148.8	224.7	193.7	202.5
4343	PA4332_at	161.2	121.4	212.8	194.4	203.4
4344	PA4333_at	220.9	510.2	281.9	317.2	319.5
4345	PA4334_at	86.8	63.2	105.8	122.1	109.1
4346	PA4335_at	156.2	179.4	179.8	214.0	205.9
4347	PA4336_at	748.5	880.0	869.5	666.4	835.8
4348	PA4337_at	125.6	45.3	123.3	156.7	99.6
4349	PA4338_at	5.0	37.4	62.3	71.4	53.6
4350	PA4339_at	95.5	68.2	64.6	77.9	65.5
4351	PA4340_at	128.0	79.6	163.0	158.6	200.0
4352	PA4341_at	49.2	20.5	33.3	29.1	25.0
4353	PA4342_at	111.5	53.9	46.5	51.4	50.3
4354	PA4343_at	33.7	3.4	6.5	26.9	3.5
4355	PA4344_at	108.5	47.6	56.3	70.8	43.2
4356	PA4345_at	80.5	98.3	98.4	148.1	155.7
4357	PA4346_at	17.3	26.2	3.2	25.7	4.5
4358	PA4347_at	16.6	50.1	56.2	60.3	62.8
4359	PA4348_at	15.8	48.2	32.5	50.8	43.5
4360	PA4349_at	163.0	88.6	146.0	183.3	138.0
4361	PA4350_at	76.7	67.5	57.9	54.9	42.3
4362	PA4351_at	77.9	38.4	17.5	28.1	1.4
4363	PA4352_at	268.5	398.9	251.9	237.3	233.5
4364	PA4353_at	358.3	206.0	247.5	346.6	299.2
4365	PA4354_at	643.6	318.7	225.5	247.4	317.4
4366	PA4355_at	121.1	108.4	131.5	87.1	94.4
4367	PA4356_xenB_at	152.9	91.7	76.4	60.5	65.6
4368	PA4357_r_at	7.5	45.1	30.6	25.5	49.8
4369	PA4358_at	69.6	57.0	77.7	75.2	75.3
4370	PA4359_i_at	80.1	88.0	87.2	62.5	43.2
4371	PA4360_at	1108.0	895.7	1179.3	1066.1	1113.9
4372	PA4361_at	147.3	113.2	143.8	153.5	152.1
4373	PA4362_at	43.0	22.5	78.0	65.5	49.4
4374	PA4363_iciA_at	18.4	58.8	127.3	107.8	123.1
4375	PA4364_at	56.7	25.6	25.0	37.4	33.2
4376	PA4365_at	57.5	41.3	29.0	30.7	41.5

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4377	PA4366_sodB_at	829.9	2210.3	1936.1	1976.4	2035.0
4378	PA4367_at	200.6	291.6	299.8	311.7	283.0
4379	PA4368_at	141.7	127.8	97.5	119.8	109.8
4380	PA4369_at	180.5	280.5	157.0	184.6	181.0
4381	PA4370_at	927.8	499.8	1852.2	1257.8	1494.2
4382	PA4371_at	95.0	26.9	173.6	179.4	152.9
4383	PA4372_at	44.4	63.1	190.9	174.6	289.8
4384	PA4373_at	118.0	66.0	77.0	94.2	99.7
4385	PA4374_at	97.8	61.3	129.5	166.3	125.0
4386	PA4375_at	52.5	24.1	31.2	34.9	21.4
4387	PA4376_pncB2_at	207.3	178.4	409.9	451.7	469.1
4388	PA4377_at	104.0	87.1	128.4	145.8	136.0
4389	PA4378_inaA_at	44.7	98.8	109.9	101.0	131.3
4390	PA4379_at	232.8	183.0	205.3	268.0	284.0
4391	PA4380_at	20.4	35.2	88.6	64.9	40.9
4392	PA4381_at	121.9	105.3	165.7	163.9	162.9
4393	PA4382_at	32.2	31.0	36.6	24.3	35.3
4394	PA4383_at	114.1	68.9	112.3	156.0	160.4
4395	PA4384_at	75.9	140.5	157.7	195.1	206.3
4396	PA4385_groEL_at	1353.7	3856.7	949.3	1325.2	1363.6
4397	PA4386_groES_at	4128.8	4308.9	2910.7	3609.7	3681.9
4398	PA4387_at	206.4	134.4	227.8	259.3	219.4
4399	PA4388_at	284.3	242.3	329.4	373.0	374.2
4400	PA4389_at	121.9	79.0	154.6	167.0	187.7
4401	PA4390_at	53.9	35.3	65.8	63.6	61.0
4402	PA4391_at	87.2	23.4	58.4	69.0	59.2
4403	PA4392_at	99.3	77.1	158.3	118.7	125.2
4404	PA4393_at	109.5	95.4	78.3	59.6	62.5
4405	PA4394_at	122.9	117.5	130.4	149.4	115.8
4406	PA4395_at	1362.4	1170.0	1009.5	959.1	892.9
4407	PA4396_at	76.2	60.3	70.4	74.8	75.1
4408	PA4397_panE_at	87.5	66.9	168.9	176.8	185.0
4409	PA4398_at	88.8	50.9	98.3	68.8	74.8
4410	PA4399_at	71.2	112.7	94.6	105.0	100.6
4411	PA4400_at	203.1	141.9	153.5	145.2	145.1
4412	PA4401_at	183.9	147.1	273.8	256.9	219.0
4413	PA4402_argJ_at	108.4	173.7	121.6	82.0	86.2
4414	PA4403_secA_at	373.2	480.1	696.9	509.2	539.2
4415	PA4404_at	106.4	71.4	98.4	66.0	62.7
4416	PA4405_at	157.4	59.1	82.8	134.5	127.3
4417	PA4406_lpxC_at	711.6	1239.4	1177.1	1288.8	1175.1
4418	PA4407_ftsZ_at	4383.8	5445.9	3668.6	3798.0	4206.8
4419	PA4408_ftsA_at	776.9	1189.8	567.0	687.1	766.2
4420	PA4409_ftsQ_at	1332.7	2093.0	1101.9	1177.8	1134.7
4421	PA4410_ddlB_at	653.1	1129.5	615.6	696.3	621.8
4422	PA4411_murC_at	1057.1	2085.1	997.8	988.9	956.5
4423	PA4412_murG_at	738.8	905.2	935.9	946.3	910.5
4424	PA4413_ftsW_at	599.6	1141.1	573.4	617.0	632.5
4425	PA4414_murD_at	402.0	884.7	396.7	411.3	515.5
4426	PA4415_mraY_at	461.7	746.1	416.0	490.9	510.0
4427	PA4416_murF_at	519.3	850.8	355.7	503.0	536.8
4428	PA4417_murE_at	516.8	830.2	332.6	380.1	387.1
4429	PA4418_ftsI_at	450.6	575.1	369.8	317.4	207.7
4430	PA4419_ftsL_at	202.7	222.9	307.5	313.8	247.3
4431	PA4420_at	454.6	302.7	700.0	729.1	684.4
4432	PA4421_at	1066.1	889.0	1540.9	1384.9	1528.0
4433	PA4422_at	257.0	146.5	359.4	323.8	300.8
4434	PA4423_at	619.1	530.4	736.7	653.4	719.8
4435	PA4424_at	552.6	577.2	590.6	635.8	635.2
4436	PA4425_at	821.4	718.4	1279.6	1172.6	1236.6
4437	PA4426_at	468.9	583.8	642.0	506.7	510.2
4438	PA4427_sspB_at	100.9	286.9	190.5	196.7	196.6
4439	PA4428_sspA_at	128.1	156.9	135.2	139.5	152.2
4440	PA4429_at	37.0	422.1	166.7	167.0	154.6
4441	PA4430_at	153.9	306.1	230.4	207.2	206.7
4442	PA4431_at	267.6	491.4	893.5	735.4	789.9
4443	PA4432_rpsI_at	172.4	292.5	261.3	229.1	207.6
4444	PA4433_rplM_at	746.5	1181.7	1065.9	810.9	856.2
4445	PA4434_at	134.7	180.1	393.5	343.5	357.1
4446	PA4435_at	123.2	155.2	221.2	150.8	119.2
4447	PA4436_at	245.9	100.8	223.6	188.9	224.0
4448	PA4437_at	93.4	112.3	172.8	197.1	149.3
4449	PA4438_at	45.6	60.1	129.2	142.9	133.1

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4450	PA4439_trpS_at	533.9	243.1	696.8	484.2	557.2
4451	PA4440_at	460.9	271.7	772.9	699.8	684.1
4452	PA4441_at	2544.4	2185.9	2766.0	2440.8	3018.1
4453	PA4442_cysN_at	457.6	221.6	123.8	116.6	335.8
4454	PA4443_cysD_at	1213.9	377.5	308.2	272.2	1063.1
4455	PA4444_mltB1_at	236.5	126.3	365.8	347.2	338.7
4456	PA4445_at	104.2	32.6	65.4	62.5	59.3
4457	PA4446_algW_at	232.7	229.9	344.2	334.4	312.8
4458	PA4447_hisC1_at	281.2	307.7	336.4	348.1	323.7
4459	PA4448_hisD_at	265.9	170.9	299.9	244.0	266.2
4460	PA4449_hisG_at	372.6	429.0	585.9	428.4	409.6
4461	PA4450_murA_at	914.9	589.9	1345.2	1152.5	1151.3
4462	PA4451_at	491.4	332.7	1105.2	1083.0	1172.4
4463	PA4452_at	128.5	196.3	116.8	132.5	114.6
4464	PA4453_at	373.6	618.6	479.2	401.2	460.4
4465	PA4454_at	244.1	359.4	261.2	222.1	293.8
4466	PA4455_at	49.1	100.6	138.7	128.9	113.3
4467	PA4456_at	63.6	85.2	160.7	146.6	173.7
4468	PA4457_at	452.9	299.9	656.9	563.5	664.0
4469	PA4458_at	380.7	239.4	490.1	510.0	498.4
4470	PA4459_at	386.4	410.5	512.6	404.3	368.8
4471	PA4460_at	1331.4	1300.1	1241.2	1053.1	1095.3
4472	PA4461_at	679.1	658.7	622.5	567.6	537.8
4473	PA4462_rpoN_at	518.9	339.4	613.5	507.1	546.5
4474	PA4463_at	4493.8	4899.1	2412.8	3214.0	3861.7
4475	PA4464_ptsN_at	4533.5	4407.4	3646.6	3977.6	4343.3
4476	PA4465_at	2265.9	2010.6	2020.8	2128.8	2342.0
4477	PA4466_at	1435.7	1161.2	1304.8	1390.5	1327.0
4478	PA4467_at	487.0	148.5	387.7	363.6	294.8
4479	PA4468_sodM_at	1686.0	1164.5	2108.5	1945.5	1639.2
4480	PA4469_at	5601.0	4046.3	5159.4	4411.2	4363.7
4481	PA4470_fumC1_at	4680.5	2697.7	3329.4	2598.9	2595.7
4482	PA4471_at	4735.5	2105.3	1825.0	1388.8	1597.2
4483	PA4472_pmbA_at	134.5	72.2	166.1	124.5	138.4
4484	PA4473_at	746.6	464.2	907.9	800.0	937.1
4485	PA4474_at	254.3	183.3	221.4	289.2	279.8
4486	PA4475_at	235.4	140.9	228.3	287.7	284.2
4487	PA4476_at	142.8	121.5	74.6	154.5	147.1
4488	PA4477_cafA_at	287.7	281.6	323.4	344.6	350.3
4489	PA4478_at	125.2	142.7	99.6	137.6	117.5
4490	PA4479_mreD_at	196.9	472.5	121.4	153.2	143.8
4491	PA4480_mreC_at	142.3	181.3	94.3	97.4	92.4
4492	PA4481_mreB_at	173.4	219.4	249.2	202.1	191.0
4493	PA4482_gatC_at	249.8	129.7	685.2	748.4	728.5
4494	PA4483_gatA_at	343.2	396.1	625.6	591.3	609.6
4495	PA4484_gatB_at	290.6	557.8	264.4	205.9	192.2
4496	PA4485_at	64.1	19.8	25.3	17.4	21.5
4497	PA4486_at	47.5	60.3	125.4	114.1	109.8
4498	PA4487_at	287.7	421.9	245.6	281.7	242.7
4499	PA4488_at	143.3	206.6	131.7	115.2	104.3
4500	PA4489_at	310.4	657.5	180.9	200.7	213.7
4501	PA4490_at	457.1	499.8	430.7	470.8	518.2
4502	PA4491_at	524.8	452.4	467.4	571.2	492.0
4503	PA4492_at	1645.7	859.6	1281.1	1191.5	1271.3
4504	PA4493_at	545.4	537.5	630.1	479.7	541.8
4505	PA4494_at	38.4	59.0	91.3	100.4	88.0
4506	PA4495_at	305.8	368.2	598.1	524.5	518.8
4507	PA4496_at	632.3	1164.6	1185.5	1004.7	995.4
4508	PA4497_at	140.3	144.1	143.0	133.4	133.8
4509	PA4498_at	161.8	291.8	251.1	251.1	277.6
4510	PA4499_at	296.3	243.9	493.1	457.1	473.9
4511	PA4500_at	8734.4	8984.0	5815.4	5936.7	6286.4
4512	PA4501_at	3439.5	3345.2	3013.9	2677.6	2685.2
4513	PA4502_at	1992.9	2502.0	1464.7	1807.1	1555.5
4514	PA4503_at	620.6	1993.1	431.4	523.1	547.9
4515	PA4504_at	675.4	2362.2	414.4	593.5	565.4
4516	PA4505_at	514.7	2588.1	475.7	512.1	531.0
4517	PA4506_at	741.0	5217.8	1064.9	1022.5	1182.3
4518	PA4507_at	8.1	152.3	157.4	164.6	162.3
4519	PA4508_at	141.6	136.3	100.5	129.1	87.2
4520	PA4509_at	49.2	85.8	72.1	79.2	81.6
4521	PA4510_at	140.8	79.3	138.1	129.2	147.1
4522	PA4511_at	351.7	179.1	410.8	418.7	415.0

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4523	PA4512_at	92.4	53.7	206.5	182.0	169.9
4524	PA4513_at	90.1	23.7	66.9	49.8	51.8
4525	PA4514_at	164.1	113.8	128.3	135.1	132.7
4526	PA4515_at	1521.1	1011.1	1196.0	737.1	857.3
4527	PA4516_at	390.0	254.4	499.0	505.3	538.5
4528	PA4517_at	103.9	60.9	55.8	47.3	43.8
4529	PA4518_at	68.0	66.9	98.2	137.4	106.1
4530	PA4519_at	53.1	94.4	92.9	103.8	84.1
4531	PA4520_at	298.0	214.4	435.0	381.3	430.7
4532	PA4521_at	146.0	134.7	276.6	280.3	257.3
4533	PA4522_ampD_at	241.0	141.0	355.0	323.5	331.1
4534	PA4523_at	250.2	277.1	287.4	324.7	292.2
4535	PA4524_nadC_at	63.9	61.8	149.3	133.6	125.5
4536	PA4525_pilA_at	3012.6	1918.3	1537.5	1571.9	1570.2
4537	PA4526_pilB_at	552.8	212.4	616.7	628.3	681.2
4538	PA4527_pilC_at	264.8	295.0	242.7	221.8	215.3
4539	PA4528_pilD_at	180.5	106.2	255.6	301.6	316.0
4540	PA4529_at	546.4	304.8	671.2	662.4	698.7
4541	PA4530_at	246.7	141.1	345.1	432.1	390.9
4542	PA4531_at	28.3	55.3	59.4	36.6	23.3
4543	PA4532_at	44.2	107.0	139.6	134.9	122.1
4544	PA4533_at	72.7	55.9	122.0	135.1	80.8
4545	PA4534_at	124.4	60.9	93.1	104.9	81.3
4546	PA4535_at	2089.3	2518.6	1132.0	1218.3	1417.3
4547	PA4536_at	1298.6	1040.2	912.8	1098.4	1130.7
4548	PA4537_at	965.4	941.0	900.5	950.5	1163.6
4549	PA4538_ndh_at	317.6	255.7	372.8	369.7	361.8
4550	PA4539_at	162.3	79.2	127.0	131.8	146.4
4551	PA4540_at	17.7	4.8	5.1	13.0	3.1
4552	PA4541_at	71.6	62.4	58.3	53.9	56.0
4553	PA4542_clpB_at	310.4	178.7	192.9	232.1	214.0
4554	PA4543_at	116.5	37.5	50.6	58.3	51.8
4555	PA4544_rluD_at	276.5	195.2	216.5	217.5	212.9
4556	PA4545_comL_at	284.3	157.5	612.9	538.9	399.2
4557	PA4546_pilS_at	230.7	176.7	202.8	202.1	225.8
4558	PA4547_pilR_at	191.0	260.4	209.1	198.5	171.8
4559	PA4548_at	53.2	51.2	98.0	113.6	84.8
4560	PA4549_fimT_at	12.1	6.9	25.8	35.9	38.0
4561	PA4550_fimU_at	124.2	86.8	88.2	75.9	77.9
4562	PA4551_pilV_at	175.8	116.1	182.7	177.3	160.4
4563	PA4552_pilW_at	114.2	107.0	88.2	85.0	81.9
4564	PA4553_pilX_at	33.5	78.9	54.8	57.2	59.8
4565	PA4554_pilY1_at	153.7	212.4	119.7	138.7	131.6
4566	PA4555_pilY2_at	134.1	236.7	133.0	135.3	151.0
4567	PA4556_pilE_at	262.0	262.8	241.4	211.9	227.5
4568	PA4557_lytB_at	86.8	261.7	79.8	89.8	62.4
4569	PA4558_at	288.7	1260.2	457.3	394.2	525.4
4570	PA4559_lspA_at	119.6	411.5	159.6	97.7	139.0
4571	PA4560_ileS_at	167.3	339.1	283.4	267.4	320.5
4572	PA4561_ribF_at	318.6	179.0	719.1	611.7	629.3
4573	PA4562_at	63.5	37.7	74.7	76.9	51.5
4574	PA4563_rpsT_at	314.6	435.0	936.6	695.4	833.0
4575	PA4564_at	144.7	140.9	118.7	141.7	155.4
4576	PA4565_proB_at	661.3	882.2	709.5	596.7	635.9
4577	PA4566_obg_at	446.7	423.2	783.4	670.3	722.2
4578	PA4567_rpmA_at	860.8	654.5	1364.6	1057.3	1084.6
4579	PA4568_rplU_at	2377.0	2606.9	3388.4	2886.5	3207.0
4580	PA4569_ispB_at	132.3	136.5	175.9	177.8	152.1
4581	PA4570_at	2123.8	1709.1	607.7	638.3	797.0
4582	PA4571_at	87.3	207.2	78.5	47.1	70.8
4583	PA4572_fklB_at	80.6	114.8	118.8	95.0	97.3
4584	PA4573_at	69.4	47.2	74.3	121.0	87.0
4585	PA4574_at	94.4	56.2	92.2	85.4	84.4
4586	PA4575_at	636.9	951.8	336.7	399.6	500.8
4587	PA4576_at	547.7	399.8	582.2	612.7	612.6
4588	PA4577_at	79.0	93.3	79.6	89.7	94.7
4589	PA4578_at	3430.3	2774.9	3002.3	2657.8	2948.9
4590	PA4579_at	167.6	85.4	157.8	160.8	170.0
4591	PA4580_at	193.6	99.1	201.6	179.9	177.1
4592	PA4581_rtcR_at	94.2	90.9	112.8	103.0	106.4
4593	PA4582_at	3788.3	1093.1	3157.3	2741.8	2763.8
4594	PA4583_at	4107.1	753.5	2566.5	2063.3	1908.3
4595	PA4584_at	1132.9	169.8	826.5	678.4	730.7

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4596	PA4585_rtcA_at	982.0	123.5	422.4	341.9	343.6
4597	PA4586_at	160.1	40.9	48.0	51.5	42.9
4598	PA4587_ccpR_at	55.8	116.6	55.2	57.5	26.2
4599	PA4588_gdhA_at	56.8	39.5	67.5	65.7	53.6
4600	PA4589_at	11.2	35.6	65.5	48.9	53.5
4601	PA4590_pra_at	71.1	142.1	300.3	206.3	188.2
4602	PA4591_at	111.6	109.7	34.4	77.8	52.8
4603	PA4592_at	139.5	163.6	162.9	166.7	129.3
4604	PA4593_at	87.6	49.2	89.0	66.6	43.1
4605	PA4594_at	45.5	64.9	218.3	173.9	181.5
4606	PA4595_at	1093.8	728.3	1346.2	1391.2	1393.4
4607	PA4596_at	111.5	164.3	120.5	121.0	137.4
4608	PA4597_oprJ_at	159.8	70.9	87.5	75.9	62.7
4609	PA4598_mexD_at	64.7	39.6	37.0	54.2	27.5
4610	PA4599_mexC_at	51.4	2.9	13.8	21.7	16.5
4611	PA4600_nfxB_at	163.1	102.9	163.5	150.4	169.7
4612	PA4601_at	147.6	113.6	63.8	90.5	115.5
4613	PA4602_glyA3_at	167.7	300.0	269.0	235.0	277.6
4614	PA4603_at	39.4	56.7	33.5	24.5	24.7
4615	PA4604_at	135.4	165.9	93.2	135.5	111.1
4616	PA4605_at	175.4	389.7	166.2	140.1	141.6
4617	PA4606_at	544.4	1014.4	612.3	783.3	804.6
4618	PA4607_at	477.5	653.4	768.8	778.0	916.8
4619	PA4608_at	776.1	649.7	702.2	822.5	782.1
4620	PA4609_radA_at	86.9	35.7	77.6	102.4	72.8
4621	PA4610_at	18.7	6.5	19.1	45.8	35.4
4622	PA4611_at	1653.5	1277.4	1892.5	1926.0	1944.0
4623	PA4612_at	1129.6	425.2	1880.0	1643.1	1547.4
4624	PA4613_katB_at	8932.8	2781.9	5453.0	5225.1	5488.4
4625	PA4614_mscL_at	861.1	774.5	1059.0	955.4	1089.0
4626	PA4615_at	720.8	705.9	511.4	530.8	601.4
4627	PA4616_at	97.1	38.0	32.0	35.1	40.6
4628	PA4617_at	235.9	190.6	235.3	260.8	224.1
4629	PA4618_at	133.2	102.0	125.1	120.8	104.4
4630	PA4619_at	194.5	176.5	144.7	100.1	111.5
4631	PA4620_at	241.1	296.9	128.2	160.0	165.1
4632	PA4621_at	125.7	124.1	122.4	118.4	96.0
4633	PA4622_at	30.9	16.8	44.3	54.7	42.9
4634	PA4623_r_at	129.8	99.9	81.5	110.3	130.8
4635	PA4624_at	82.4	81.2	76.8	77.4	82.0
4636	PA4625_at	128.2	234.2	135.7	117.1	109.6
4637	PA4626_hprA_at	130.3	121.1	251.0	211.2	206.1
4638	PA4627_at	93.8	108.4	135.7	124.6	128.4
4639	PA4628_lysP_at	25.3	48.6	29.3	32.7	33.9
4640	PA4629_at	76.0	37.9	53.2	82.8	45.3
4641	PA4630_at	17.2	55.7	37.3	67.0	51.7
4642	PA4631_at	111.3	82.9	135.5	153.5	129.3
4643	PA4632_at	348.9	423.0	481.6	440.4	486.9
4644	PA4633_at	2218.7	1473.9	2148.1	2219.8	2430.5
4645	PA4634_at	15.5	43.0	77.8	100.3	76.6
4646	PA4635_at	25.4	4.6	2.0	4.6	4.4
4647	PA4636_at	172.1	133.4	370.8	337.6	317.5
4648	PA4637_i_at	90.3	33.9	26.3	52.9	35.2
4649	PA4638_at	81.3	64.1	31.8	27.2	28.9
4650	PA4639_at	449.6	206.3	616.1	570.3	812.8
4651	PA4640_mqoB_at	84.8	231.8	238.7	251.4	258.9
4652	PA4641_at	95.5	74.2	86.7	66.2	83.0
4653	PA4642_at	135.1	117.6	327.6	353.9	341.5
4654	PA4643_at	255.6	204.3	410.5	365.4	417.0
4655	PA4644_at	71.4	34.0	7.2	37.6	33.2
4656	PA4645_at	119.9	81.7	173.6	168.1	159.5
4657	PA4646_upp_at	79.9	95.4	130.3	161.9	160.1
4658	PA4647_uraA_at	48.6	89.4	66.5	76.7	77.8
4659	PA4648_at	22.6	56.1	109.9	83.8	99.2
4660	PA4649_at	57.4	41.2	41.5	46.0	63.1
4661	PA4650_at	33.5	9.2	17.8	30.8	27.2
4662	PA4651_at	7.4	11.0	19.8	28.2	30.8
4663	PA4652_at	19.4	5.9	6.8	17.8	18.2
4664	PA4653_at	61.0	29.0	20.1	30.0	14.8
4665	PA4654_at	65.2	23.9	125.5	30.3	30.0
4666	PA4655_hemH_at	2668.1	1199.5	3193.5	3248.0	3275.2
4667	PA4656_at	259.1	96.8	232.5	330.6	305.7
4668	PA4657_at	616.7	413.8	442.2	425.3	509.4

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4669	PA4658_at	1002.5	439.7	570.2	623.3	646.3
4670	PA4659_at	238.8	83.9	94.3	139.0	114.8
4671	PA4660_phr_at	461.2	198.9	210.5	237.5	227.3
4672	PA4661_at	809.2	1031.2	1003.0	1152.4	1108.0
4673	PA4662_murI_at	90.8	193.6	136.2	159.1	147.2
4674	PA4663_moeB_at	148.6	186.9	132.8	138.3	162.9
4675	PA4664_hemK_at	279.0	297.6	213.2	219.1	221.3
4676	PA4665_prfA_at	239.0	153.6	358.2	416.8	332.9
4677	PA4666_hemA_at	283.0	148.5	500.1	533.0	505.9
4678	PA4667_at	549.6	328.7	767.9	652.1	677.2
4679	PA4668_at	212.4	159.0	297.6	337.3	287.7
4680	PA4669_ipk_at	289.7	236.4	155.1	154.2	140.0
4681	PA4670_prs_at	166.3	162.4	418.1	347.0	319.6
4682	PA4671_at	1815.2	3675.8	1274.8	826.7	946.0
4683	PA4672_at	206.8	150.4	113.8	96.2	105.9
4684	PA4673_at	39.1	136.9	63.3	38.1	61.7
4685	PA4674_at	124.1	121.9	164.9	161.5	160.5
4686	PA4675_at	203.3	64.7	129.4	140.8	167.2
4687	PA4676_at	98.0	91.6	121.6	143.6	138.9
4688	PA4677_at	247.7	307.0	370.3	546.8	542.2
4689	PA4678_rimI_at	185.2	71.5	165.8	139.6	141.6
4690	PA4679_at	286.9	114.7	348.9	280.2	346.9
4691	PA4680_at	15.6	46.8	53.5	68.5	42.9
4692	PA4681_at	37.5	94.7	114.1	111.3	88.9
4693	PA4682_at	140.6	186.2	160.9	181.5	149.1
4694	PA4683_at	344.6	212.8	232.5	166.3	194.4
4695	PA4684_at	123.4	113.6	172.6	157.0	138.3
4696	PA4685_at	163.9	185.1	90.3	102.0	76.9
4697	PA4686_at	274.8	1015.2	190.6	182.1	230.3
4698	PA4687_hitA_at	1836.6	1665.3	1042.5	836.6	1040.1
4699	PA4688_hitB_at	405.2	275.2	400.8	325.6	349.9
4700	PA4689_at	115.7	79.7	107.0	103.9	90.2
4701	PA4690_at	285.2	219.4	222.6	258.8	208.4
4702	PA4691_at	98.0	65.7	65.5	101.1	61.5
4703	PA4692_at	120.2	101.7	195.0	305.9	222.7
4704	PA4693_pssA_at	270.2	161.0	400.7	374.6	399.7
4705	PA4694_ilvC_at	631.9	1500.4	759.0	623.2	632.8
4706	PA4695_ilvH_at	566.9	743.9	590.2	411.9	412.2
4707	PA4696_ilvI_at	295.7	241.8	469.7	363.2	378.1
4708	PA4697_at	825.0	681.5	900.6	839.8	967.1
4709	PA4698_at	341.6	537.6	369.9	397.8	426.2
4710	PA4699_at	215.7	361.3	362.8	309.7	369.2
4711	PA4700_mrcB_at	116.3	125.5	173.8	195.9	170.9
4712	PA4701_at	252.9	212.2	616.5	578.1	582.7
4713	PA4702_at	63.5	55.3	102.1	120.5	119.3
4714	PA4703_at	128.3	96.4	115.6	151.0	152.9
4715	PA4704_at	44.7	88.8	105.2	84.4	86.9
4716	PA4705_at	176.6	86.3	194.9	186.7	152.6
4717	PA4706_at	383.9	177.3	479.3	456.0	399.7
4718	PA4707_at	330.6	99.8	387.4	395.4	341.6
4719	PA4708_at	1025.4	500.9	1435.6	1212.6	1208.6
4720	PA4709_at	1545.2	863.8	1555.2	1204.8	1215.9
4721	PA4710_at	262.2	175.7	300.0	196.8	197.4
4722	PA4711_at	637.4	626.6	298.3	368.9	308.7
4723	PA4712_at	128.8	142.0	92.3	110.2	134.8
4724	PA4713_at	30.7	46.4	42.2	71.4	45.8
4725	PA4714_at	193.7	142.2	205.1	242.9	260.5
4726	PA4715_at	390.2	171.5	474.1	436.7	417.7
4727	PA4716_at	160.5	73.5	155.4	139.3	137.8
4728	PA4717_at	183.3	286.1	282.9	286.4	310.1
4729	PA4718_at	168.2	90.6	129.4	127.5	133.9
4730	PA4719_at	111.1	74.4	46.1	50.5	47.8
4731	PA4720_trmA_at	169.8	129.8	115.2	130.3	128.0
4732	PA4721_at	115.0	100.7	142.4	115.4	123.9
4733	PA4722_at	290.3	179.1	530.6	533.4	655.0
4734	PA4723_dksA_at	298.3	262.0	493.9	378.1	431.1
4735	PA4724_at	16.8	18.8	22.8	10.8	45.7
4736	PA4725_at	106.8	82.9	89.4	72.0	53.0
4737	PA4726_at	618.8	488.6	805.3	820.1	892.0
4738	PA4727_pcnB_at	537.0	285.2	666.4	673.5	740.9
4739	PA4728_folK_at	256.9	255.3	221.3	249.6	269.8
4740	PA4729_panB_at	431.9	313.6	687.2	605.3	702.3
4741	PA4730_panC_at	240.8	183.6	366.3	321.5	318.7

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4742	PA4731_panD_at	81.0	102.7	163.5	106.2	135.0
4743	PA4732_pgi_at	849.0	648.5	785.2	768.4	841.7
4744	PA4733_acsB_at	498.1	480.5	516.6	439.8	455.6
4745	PA4734_at	481.2	274.8	600.7	496.6	663.5
4746	PA4735_at	247.9	253.9	399.3	399.4	354.1
4747	PA4736_at	146.3	158.6	182.6	223.5	209.8
4748	PA4737_at	97.0	94.0	107.3	93.5	120.7
4749	PA4738_at	48.0	134.0	83.6	99.7	60.8
4750	PA4739_at	147.5	80.1	64.9	90.7	62.8
4751	PA4740_pnp_at	1698.7	2933.1	1045.3	1002.3	979.3
4752	PA4741_rps0_at	1350.3	1718.4	1264.8	1034.1	1104.4
4753	PA4742_truB_at	222.3	470.1	268.1	207.1	216.6
4754	PA4743_rbfA_at	243.5	778.2	165.6	140.6	166.5
4755	PA4744_infB_at	387.8	1218.7	257.2	240.5	323.1
4756	PA4745_nusA_at	331.8	545.7	271.6	282.5	274.5
4757	PA4746_at	109.1	64.9	139.4	100.9	91.3
4758	PA4747_secG_at	623.3	558.4	359.1	288.6	360.0
4759	PA4748_tpiA_at	316.2	308.3	410.7	414.1	408.9
4760	PA4749_glmM_at	1023.1	881.7	890.6	1024.7	893.7
4761	PA4750_folP_at	647.0	570.6	546.9	638.9	483.0
4762	PA4751_ftsH_at	3993.4	3822.2	3490.6	3463.2	3480.6
4763	PA4752_ftsJ_at	229.7	196.6	192.7	188.7	169.4
4764	PA4753_at	145.5	86.6	259.4	293.6	315.5
4765	PA4754_at	147.6	186.3	136.6	141.4	110.7
4766	PA4755_greA_at	161.9	486.2	193.3	142.9	171.8
4767	PA4756_carB_at	403.7	983.0	255.8	274.2	270.5
4768	PA4757_at	102.9	101.3	131.1	130.1	87.9
4769	PA4758_carA_at	126.8	99.4	164.7	159.0	177.2
4770	PA4759_dapB_at	126.4	228.2	59.1	95.4	91.8
4771	PA4760_dnaJ_at	231.1	248.0	103.2	107.0	82.7
4772	PA4761_dnaK_at	762.8	831.2	333.5	353.6	367.0
4773	PA4762_grpE_at	1107.1	478.5	885.6	842.2	940.6
4774	PA4763_recN_at	5054.4	1941.3	3219.4	2848.7	2669.7
4775	PA4764_fur_at	971.1	951.6	900.1	1045.0	1024.7
4776	PA4765_omlA_at	393.7	495.9	885.3	815.6	820.8
4777	PA4766_at	116.7	54.4	95.4	91.8	75.4
4778	PA4767_at	174.1	151.4	324.2	346.0	359.7
4779	PA4768_smpB_at	174.7	114.0	198.6	159.0	154.7
4780	PA4769_at	105.1	88.4	196.0	223.3	213.9
4781	PA4770_lldP_at	103.0	135.3	93.8	84.8	66.2
4782	PA4771_lldD_at	6.0	39.2	56.6	44.3	47.4
4783	PA4772_at	69.1	47.9	7.3	42.9	11.5
4784	PA4773_at	84.6	283.7	78.5	82.3	85.6
4785	PA4774_at	59.7	176.7	133.7	92.6	79.4
4786	PA4775_at	163.0	191.0	117.2	105.0	113.6
4787	PA4776_at	227.3	381.1	233.7	255.2	270.4
4788	PA4777_at	84.0	111.7	71.0	71.2	45.1
4789	PA4778_at	751.2	607.4	1025.2	916.8	1028.9
4790	PA4779_at	7.7	21.4	53.7	25.5	43.6
4791	PA4780_at	215.0	169.2	204.1	159.0	154.7
4792	PA4781_at	111.1	43.9	82.2	88.2	75.5
4793	PA4782_at	72.3	270.1	139.9	166.7	170.4
4794	PA4783_at	95.1	72.1	98.3	117.0	117.8
4795	PA4784_at	103.3	86.6	202.4	188.7	221.5
4796	PA4785_at	10.3	13.0	41.3	64.4	73.7
4797	PA4786_at	120.6	81.3	95.2	117.6	81.9
4798	PA4787_at	559.7	548.2	627.6	740.2	742.8
4799	PA4788_at	74.6	37.1	109.4	99.3	98.4
4800	PA4789_at	99.0	46.0	163.1	139.3	145.7
4801	PA4790_at	30.2	43.9	73.4	71.7	81.5
4802	PA4791_at	512.7	520.3	325.7	325.0	369.3
4803	PA4792_at	95.3	65.9	108.0	114.4	94.3
4804	PA4793_at	4091.8	3360.5	2481.7	2600.1	3111.7
4805	PA4794_at	825.9	702.2	698.2	712.9	742.5
4806	PA4795_at	737.7	753.8	807.9	929.8	818.3
4807	PA4796_at	376.0	254.7	313.4	321.2	286.0
4808	PA4798_at	39.6	67.6	107.1	85.0	89.3
4809	PA4799_at	11.2	26.4	40.0	23.5	13.7
4810	PA4800_at	79.8	46.8	47.3	63.3	53.9
4811	PA4801_at	81.6	55.0	87.9	68.4	87.1
4812	PA4802_at	132.7	52.8	91.0	110.3	71.9
4813	PA4803_at	330.8	282.9	212.9	245.0	274.3
4814	PA4804_at	84.0	67.4	60.5	70.4	58.1

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4815	PA4805_at	51.0	51.9	28.7	33.8	32.5
4816	PA4806_at	121.1	89.9	103.8	84.3	69.1
4817	PA4807_selB_at	232.9	189.9	175.0	221.5	240.1
4818	PA4808_selA_at	537.8	476.9	480.4	522.9	482.3
4819	PA4809_fdhE_at	56.0	66.0	79.5	72.5	76.0
4820	PA4810_fdnI_at	113.0	321.6	79.0	184.7	88.6
4821	PA4811_fdnH_at	329.9	783.6	210.7	257.9	215.8
4822	PA4812_fdnG_at	464.0	952.3	586.1	715.6	575.1
4823	PA4813_lipC_at	12.6	1.7	13.3	5.1	9.2
4824	PA4814_fadH2_at	32.4	35.0	22.9	37.4	34.2
4825	PA4815_at	86.2	54.7	130.2	101.0	93.7
4826	PA4816_at	155.8	58.5	79.9	51.6	99.3
4827	PA4817_at	15.6	62.8	36.3	36.6	23.8
4828	PA4818_at	45.8	42.9	39.9	40.9	27.7
4829	PA4819_at	25.2	29.8	57.2	47.8	42.3
4830	PA4820_at	20.7	8.1	8.3	17.6	5.2
4831	PA4821_at	77.6	42.8	65.8	40.7	49.5
4832	PA4822_at	16.5	25.2	6.3	17.5	21.8
4833	PA4823_at	63.5	15.9	2.4	27.2	4.7
4834	PA4824_at	41.3	11.7	33.0	41.3	11.2
4835	PA4825_mgtA_at	34.3	32.3	37.2	32.7	31.6
4836	PA4826_at	14.7	7.6	9.6	28.9	14.1
4837	PA4827_at	42.8	50.1	97.4	105.9	82.8
4838	PA4828_at	82.2	37.5	40.3	43.6	40.3
4839	PA4829_lpd3_at	38.2	93.0	68.6	97.5	80.9
4840	PA4830_at	107.5	71.5	62.2	69.9	134.2
4841	PA4831_at	177.4	198.6	180.7	227.5	227.1
4842	PA4832_at	76.8	39.0	47.8	64.7	47.6
4843	PA4833_at	337.8	294.4	224.0	285.4	326.6
4844	PA4834_at	10.4	5.2	18.8	35.5	18.1
4845	PA4835_at	44.3	24.8	16.3	44.4	30.8
4846	PA4836_at	91.6	42.4	64.0	94.3	34.4
4847	PA4837_at	55.0	66.1	37.9	80.8	21.5
4848	PA4838_at	32.9	28.8	84.2	68.8	69.2
4849	PA4839_speA_at	111.9	166.7	120.7	115.9	109.3
4850	PA4840_at	123.4	71.5	66.4	72.0	100.9
4851	PA4841_at	275.7	141.8	315.5	301.1	291.8
4852	PA4842_at	730.0	836.6	797.9	927.9	873.4
4853	PA4843_at	1805.5	1591.2	816.3	885.6	1027.2
4854	PA4844_at	90.4	129.2	65.5	50.4	44.6
4855	PA4845_dipZ_at	62.8	53.2	57.1	77.4	33.4
4856	PA4846_aroQ1_at	286.8	151.5	715.7	653.6	961.7
4857	PA4847_accB_at	700.9	1018.7	1452.4	1230.7	1442.5
4858	PA4848_accC_at	599.0	790.5	835.0	704.2	853.2
4859	PA4849_at	20.0	26.9	49.8	61.1	14.4
4860	PA4850_prmA_at	263.3	211.9	414.7	330.2	450.0
4861	PA4851_at	241.2	160.7	314.5	346.3	347.7
4862	PA4852_at	185.9	182.0	329.8	432.9	275.6
4863	PA4853_fis_at	159.1	226.9	244.8	126.9	146.6
4864	PA4854_purH_at	105.8	95.9	67.1	70.7	60.6
4865	PA4855_purD_at	68.9	267.3	67.1	68.8	64.3
4866	PA4856_at	361.9	457.5	361.0	403.6	385.0
4867	PA4857_at	66.5	27.7	43.2	43.1	23.9
4868	PA4858_at	11.2	24.8	16.4	18.3	5.8
4869	PA4859_at	92.3	59.7	61.4	73.9	58.3
4870	PA4860_at	14.8	7.2	14.3	26.8	16.4
4871	PA4861_at	8.4	22.3	27.1	29.2	36.1
4872	PA4862_at	12.3	31.7	24.6	46.4	22.5
4873	PA4863_at	157.4	105.8	350.8	321.2	318.0
4874	PA4864_ureD_at	12.0	47.9	98.6	56.3	72.4
4875	PA4865_ureA_at	66.2	92.3	158.8	158.4	139.0
4876	PA4866_at	73.8	52.5	52.1	77.4	67.6
4877	PA4867_ureB_at	12.3	52.0	31.5	42.7	39.8
4878	PA4868_ureC_at	60.9	88.7	57.4	50.7	30.5
4879	PA4869_at	42.7	46.5	71.6	79.8	87.7
4880	PA4870_at	545.6	382.7	267.4	307.8	272.1
4881	PA4871_at	29.5	20.3	22.6	22.7	31.5
4882	PA4872_at	187.3	117.9	540.7	554.9	509.7
4883	PA4873_at	68.0	70.1	48.5	58.0	60.0
4884	PA4874_at	181.5	107.8	239.6	310.6	302.8
4885	PA4875_at	84.4	82.7	112.0	117.7	114.1
4886	PA4876_osmE_at	360.4	364.2	227.0	282.9	229.3
4887	PA4877_at	136.8	135.8	163.3	93.4	76.9

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4888	PA4878_at	272.5	348.1	257.5	1003.1	280.6
4889	PA4879_at	116.5	40.5	78.8	93.4	109.6
4890	PA4880_at	493.7	387.4	216.2	204.6	242.7
4891	PA4881_at	504.2	427.6	185.2	207.3	165.8
4892	PA4882_at	14.4	7.3	20.0	20.2	12.5
4893	PA4883_at	6.0	3.3	2.9	12.4	2.6
4894	PA4884_at	51.8	9.6	56.1	35.3	23.7
4895	PA4885_irlR_at	168.5	154.3	167.1	154.6	156.1
4896	PA4886_at	16.2	21.6	31.9	35.3	25.6
4897	PA4887_at	78.6	63.0	67.7	69.7	57.8
4898	PA4888_at	100.7	115.8	63.4	62.0	64.7
4899	PA4889_at	18.0	80.0	52.6	39.2	53.4
4900	PA4890_at	65.8	52.0	89.5	90.8	105.6
4901	PA4891_ureE_at	7.1	23.9	9.7	37.4	7.1
4902	PA4892_ureF_at	110.0	84.1	86.9	77.6	70.5
4903	PA4893_ureG_at	44.0	122.5	72.1	73.1	73.7
4904	PA4894_i_at	24.0	29.8	23.8	57.8	35.7
4905	PA4895_at	133.3	76.7	166.8	178.9	142.9
4906	PA4896_at	1067.9	709.3	656.1	593.5	660.2
4907	PA4897_at	121.8	83.6	126.2	130.4	99.1
4908	PA4898_at	61.1	71.0	53.1	63.8	41.9
4909	PA4899_at	56.5	27.1	39.8	59.6	50.7
4910	PA4900_at	28.3	42.1	55.4	85.0	63.4
4911	PA4901_md1C_at	16.6	6.9	57.3	44.0	43.2
4912	PA4902_at	77.9	60.7	134.3	113.8	172.8
4913	PA4903_at	33.1	62.6	15.3	69.8	49.2
4914	PA4904_vanA_at	131.3	94.2	82.6	107.1	96.1
4915	PA4905_vanB_at	8.6	18.3	36.4	27.8	16.8
4916	PA4906_at	146.6	176.8	181.2	175.7	221.9
4917	PA4907_at	257.2	258.8	563.9	504.2	504.6
4918	PA4908_at	118.7	46.6	30.7	31.3	42.6
4919	PA4909_at	24.2	19.1	41.6	32.3	34.1
4920	PA4910_at	81.2	66.2	76.5	105.4	83.4
4921	PA4911_at	45.1	45.0	71.1	71.1	42.9
4922	PA4912_at	101.6	74.6	68.3	86.9	74.5
4923	PA4913_at	226.0	303.3	413.2	458.9	523.3
4924	PA4914_at	46.8	71.1	93.5	93.3	174.1
4925	PA4915_at	219.9	209.5	278.3	368.7	218.7
4926	PA4916_at	260.9	185.2	454.1	406.5	451.9
4927	PA4917_at	284.6	274.3	371.3	390.8	492.4
4928	PA4918_at	879.0	679.4	824.9	752.8	914.7
4929	PA4919_pncB1_at	731.6	749.3	848.9	842.7	915.1
4930	PA4920_nadE_at	1396.3	1561.5	1597.4	1556.1	1740.7
4931	PA4921_at	188.0	149.3	161.9	215.7	237.4
4932	PA4922_azul_at	2630.4	3552.4	2633.9	2881.6	3059.6
4933	PA4923_at	93.2	62.2	90.4	96.3	90.2
4934	PA4924_at	105.2	72.2	126.1	120.2	114.0
4935	PA4925_at	42.3	44.6	93.6	78.2	86.1
4936	PA4926_at	24.4	53.3	50.1	42.7	31.1
4937	PA4927_at	45.0	33.9	43.5	52.2	36.0
4938	PA4928_at	72.3	87.6	109.6	103.2	93.0
4939	PA4929_at	103.4	72.0	77.3	102.3	85.9
4940	PA4930_alr_at	123.6	87.1	148.1	157.9	180.5
4941	PA4931_dnaB_at	274.8	281.7	441.0	336.0	382.6
4942	PA4932_rplI_at	1915.7	2428.8	1269.1	1501.6	1331.5
4943	PA4933_at	1622.0	1884.8	817.9	965.7	790.2
4944	PA4934_rpsR_at	3377.2	4155.9	1344.8	1797.9	1787.3
4945	PA4935_rpsF_at	3884.0	5726.6	1485.2	1505.1	1530.7
4946	PA4936_at	1464.2	1184.5	1391.0	1025.8	1233.0
4947	PA4937_rnr_at	3946.5	3565.3	3218.2	3083.8	3209.3
4948	PA4938_purA_at	510.0	650.1	551.6	557.1	493.2
4949	PA4939_at	289.2	228.8	328.3	275.4	237.2
4950	PA4940_at	406.8	307.9	545.1	528.8	519.8
4951	PA4941_hflC_at	713.8	737.6	894.7	741.8	673.2
4952	PA4942_hflK_at	679.2	529.9	853.4	833.0	801.7
4953	PA4943_at	1041.0	861.0	1498.8	1317.1	1270.0
4954	PA4944_at	2579.9	2864.4	2712.7	2656.4	2700.7
4955	PA4945_miaA_at	123.2	124.5	232.8	185.1	209.6
4956	PA4946_mutL_at	219.7	286.9	189.5	215.9	210.7
4957	PA4947_amiB_at	575.4	422.8	784.8	772.3	828.2
4958	PA4948_at	306.9	248.0	284.5	391.6	354.4
4959	PA4949_at	326.6	168.8	219.2	198.4	199.4
4960	PA4950_at	175.5	152.4	138.5	162.2	149.2

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

4961	PA4951_orn_at	798.7	641.8	861.2	1051.4	1111.1
4962	PA4952_at	260.4	191.3	255.8	249.5	251.6
4963	PA4953_motB_at	432.3	309.8	450.3	393.4	358.6
4964	PA4954_motA_at	167.5	143.7	375.4	361.1	313.2
4965	PA4955_at	165.4	133.9	273.8	332.3	293.4
4966	PA4956_rhdA_at	149.8	83.1	327.9	260.8	263.7
4967	PA4957_psd_at	216.9	152.2	238.2	198.4	235.6
4968	PA4958_at	331.2	243.6	377.6	331.5	360.2
4969	PA4959_at	152.3	128.4	126.0	106.7	120.0
4970	PA4960_at	37.0	40.5	184.3	148.6	161.8
4971	PA4961_at	319.1	259.1	379.3	326.2	316.6
4972	PA4962_at	80.3	21.6	32.7	75.3	38.0
4973	PA4963_at	154.0	158.9	351.4	307.6	312.0
4974	PA4964_parC_at	120.9	384.3	153.6	159.1	153.1
4975	PA4965_at	86.1	262.8	88.7	125.1	110.1
4976	PA4966_at	90.9	115.1	96.7	103.2	103.8
4977	PA4967_parE_at	112.3	146.4	220.0	214.2	196.3
4978	PA4968_at	242.1	108.4	397.0	362.8	398.0
4979	PA4969_at	41.8	40.1	146.9	141.2	111.4
4980	PA4970_at	490.9	346.3	651.0	634.1	650.9
4981	PA4971_at	331.3	226.7	529.9	511.6	543.6
4982	PA4972_at	81.7	63.5	350.3	370.6	379.0
4983	PA4973_thiC_at	49.1	79.2	85.3	82.9	63.9
4984	PA4974_at	89.8	211.7	523.9	425.0	437.8
4985	PA4975_at	76.7	54.6	17.3	59.0	29.6
4986	PA4976_aspC_at	81.2	112.5	100.8	105.0	120.5
4987	PA4977_at	111.8	83.1	87.1	97.9	132.0
4988	PA4978_at	193.0	75.0	97.5	100.3	96.3
4989	PA4979_at	157.9	149.0	147.1	195.6	172.2
4990	PA4980_at	626.1	464.7	385.0	373.4	390.2
4991	PA4981_at	76.4	35.7	44.2	52.1	49.6
4992	PA4982_at	47.1	82.0	76.7	46.8	44.1
4993	PA4983_at	206.0	115.8	252.1	258.9	323.7
4994	PA4984_at	134.3	139.7	251.3	233.1	184.8
4995	PA4985_at	51.4	31.8	65.0	70.6	29.5
4996	PA4986_at	17.5	36.5	28.1	21.6	33.5
4997	PA4987_at	33.0	25.5	54.5	72.1	84.6
4998	PA4988_waaA_at	109.8	64.6	119.2	125.5	115.0
4999	PA4989_at	61.9	49.8	108.1	161.9	101.2
5000	PA4990_at	51.4	9.4	47.1	46.9	34.5
5001	PA4991_at	223.0	127.7	270.4	311.0	300.6
5002	PA4992_at	20.3	82.9	110.3	146.3	128.6
5003	PA4993_at	69.0	67.8	117.5	85.1	87.2
5004	PA4994_at	114.4	100.3	103.9	72.0	71.1
5005	PA4995_at	6.7	29.2	26.2	35.3	26.7
5006	PA4996_rfaE_at	287.1	372.4	464.2	498.9	508.8
5007	PA4997_msbA_at	155.8	127.9	407.5	327.5	285.2
5008	PA4998_at	249.4	180.3	528.7	419.0	447.7
5009	PA4999_at	64.9	62.0	56.9	65.7	81.9
5010	PA5000_at	515.3	1037.6	535.8	484.6	524.0
5011	PA5001_at	231.8	499.8	231.6	294.1	263.0
5012	PA5002_at	187.6	352.8	114.5	198.9	207.1
5013	PA5003_at	263.6	371.1	229.1	199.2	188.3
5014	PA5004_at	220.3	331.2	207.1	205.0	181.9
5015	PA5005_at	333.0	433.8	434.8	406.5	413.1
5016	PA5006_at	125.4	181.1	112.1	118.9	148.6
5017	PA5007_at	131.1	313.2	132.7	138.2	173.5
5018	PA5008_at	211.1	340.4	192.2	234.1	272.9
5019	PA5009_waaP_at	115.7	179.1	132.9	122.2	103.8
5020	PA5010_waaG_at	169.2	271.3	124.9	128.7	126.8
5021	PA5011_waaC_at	292.7	297.0	210.1	240.6	241.6
5022	PA5012_waaF_at	99.0	119.7	136.0	152.1	101.6
5023	PA5013_ilvE_at	556.5	466.1	882.7	685.4	664.3
5024	PA5014_glnE_at	357.7	284.5	344.4	309.9	287.2
5025	PA5015_aceE_at	887.9	1173.0	1966.2	1811.5	1920.6
5026	PA5016_aceF_at	584.3	1083.5	761.4	639.5	736.2
5027	PA5017_at	753.5	602.5	620.6	718.3	670.1
5028	PA5018_msrA_at	572.4	419.1	959.4	858.1	1004.5
5029	PA5019_at	156.9	177.3	124.4	194.9	141.1
5030	PA5020_at	38.0	60.1	118.0	43.4	23.1
5031	PA5021_at	150.0	79.2	127.8	131.8	128.8
5032	PA5022_at	148.5	337.1	142.3	138.4	151.4
5033	PA5023_at	382.6	217.1	363.4	439.5	482.6

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

5034	PA5024_at	77.1	25.7	25.3	41.8	78.4
5035	PA5025_mety_at	131.0	90.8	101.2	78.4	108.5
5036	PA5026_at	151.2	120.7	127.3	82.8	85.0
5037	PA5027_at	4.3	83.3	38.3	30.7	29.2
5038	PA5028_at	796.7	571.9	1114.4	876.1	924.0
5039	PA5029_at	245.3	252.3	273.6	330.6	316.4
5040	PA5030_at	72.1	65.6	140.7	110.4	101.3
5041	PA5031_at	98.8	39.3	42.8	46.0	38.7
5042	PA5032_at	17.2	32.1	25.6	38.9	35.4
5043	PA5033_at	110.2	5.2	18.0	27.7	28.3
5044	PA5034_hemE_at	31.9	70.2	87.9	78.1	61.4
5045	PA5035_gltD_at	101.2	325.7	235.5	192.7	252.0
5046	PA5036_gltB_at	134.0	216.9	213.7	213.8	175.5
5047	PA5037_at	429.5	372.6	610.0	618.1	610.3
5048	PA5038_aroB_at	146.9	196.7	270.0	249.3	221.7
5049	PA5039_aroK_at	903.8	940.3	831.2	974.6	1024.4
5050	PA5040_pilQ_at	1151.5	1036.2	663.1	582.2	789.7
5051	PA5041_pilP_at	1130.5	1468.1	798.1	838.2	817.1
5052	PA5042_pilo_at	1145.8	1415.9	598.3	720.9	711.6
5053	PA5043_pilN_at	1298.2	1779.7	967.8	958.0	995.4
5054	PA5044_pilM_at	2490.3	2221.5	1707.8	2381.4	1966.5
5055	PA5045_ponA_at	201.6	259.9	282.0	271.1	247.3
5056	PA5046_at	408.0	488.8	934.6	728.6	803.5
5057	PA5047_at	169.4	261.8	146.5	209.2	181.6
5058	PA5048_at	107.8	164.7	93.1	86.8	89.8
5059	PA5049_rpmE_at	159.2	328.5	131.6	119.0	123.3
5060	PA5050_priA_at	91.5	95.0	115.4	130.4	115.4
5061	PA5051_argS_at	104.5	145.7	108.1	116.9	125.0
5062	PA5052_at	140.8	434.9	149.1	153.2	127.1
5063	PA5053_hslV_at	526.8	297.4	235.6	330.0	323.8
5064	PA5054_hslU_at	1161.3	816.7	464.3	482.1	407.1
5065	PA5055_at	396.8	288.0	259.6	251.3	309.7
5066	PA5056_phaC1_at	951.4	917.9	829.9	805.8	896.0
5067	PA5057_phaD_at	153.7	173.1	185.3	254.6	209.9
5068	PA5058_phaC2_at	67.1	93.3	127.3	123.5	131.6
5069	PA5059_at	8.9	4.6	6.1	19.6	47.7
5070	PA5060_phaF_at	1300.3	1455.7	1158.9	1374.7	1392.0
5071	PA5061_at	418.4	203.2	296.6	326.4	338.3
5072	PA5062_at	437.8	402.5	454.5	606.5	619.0
5073	PA5063_ubiE_at	497.9	273.3	723.6	673.4	759.2
5074	PA5064_at	328.1	420.5	561.8	487.8	509.4
5075	PA5065_at	130.0	153.5	214.9	228.5	179.7
5076	PA5066_hisI_at	1478.9	1566.8	1730.8	1706.6	1830.6
5077	PA5067_hisE_at	1749.3	1407.0	1534.5	1883.6	1902.4
5078	PA5068_tatA_at	931.9	1262.6	1066.1	1048.1	995.6
5079	PA5069_tatB_at	1224.3	1553.4	985.4	1010.4	1135.4
5080	PA5070_tatC_at	316.4	250.4	285.3	335.0	300.0
5081	PA5071_at	134.2	101.7	147.1	148.3	127.9
5082	PA5072_at	127.4	123.1	131.7	117.6	124.3
5083	PA5073_at	283.2	175.9	360.2	344.4	379.2
5084	PA5074_at	5.0	97.0	75.3	64.4	55.0
5085	PA5075_at	70.4	91.4	151.2	141.6	117.6
5086	PA5076_at	109.4	79.2	128.1	128.8	106.9
5087	PA5077_mdoH_at	149.6	175.9	122.1	141.8	147.7
5088	PA5078_at	359.3	508.2	541.9	556.5	566.6
5089	PA5079_at	138.5	97.5	211.2	223.4	256.6
5090	PA5080_at	271.8	199.0	454.9	403.7	472.5
5091	PA5081_at	93.4	58.9	89.4	97.6	64.3
5092	PA5082_at	62.6	73.5	145.5	158.1	134.8
5093	PA5083_at	59.5	30.9	58.2	91.8	60.1
5094	PA5084_at	6.9	27.4	49.3	28.3	21.2
5095	PA5085_at	253.1	239.9	306.2	281.4	330.5
5096	PA5086_at	124.3	118.7	153.6	295.2	224.2
5097	PA5087_at	29.0	57.9	55.5	36.5	42.6
5098	PA5088_at	20.7	31.8	10.0	25.1	18.2
5099	PA5089_at	72.2	75.6	53.4	54.7	30.2
5100	PA5090_at	151.1	89.8	77.0	69.9	79.1
5101	PA5091_hutG_at	11.4	147.1	103.7	104.4	117.0
5102	PA5092_hutI_at	57.0	43.5	40.1	51.2	45.8
5103	PA5093_at	15.0	7.0	32.6	53.9	33.8
5104	PA5094_at	134.4	102.2	72.3	129.3	93.1
5105	PA5095_at	88.6	90.9	93.8	127.3	75.3
5106	PA5096_at	64.9	99.2	62.2	57.8	41.7

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5107	PA5097_at	27.3	24.4	8.1	38.9	13.4
5108	PA5098_hutH_at	4.2	30.6	30.5	39.1	14.9
5109	PA5099_at	10.3	33.9	11.9	21.2	21.1
5110	PA5100_hutU_at	89.7	156.3	75.5	115.5	166.4
5111	PA5101_at	186.0	112.6	117.6	137.3	128.7
5112	PA5102_at	83.5	28.4	5.0	31.1	37.7
5113	PA5103_at	267.4	44.4	86.5	145.0	103.1
5114	PA5104_at	139.7	161.7	130.1	132.6	108.5
5115	PA5105_hutC_at	374.2	492.8	292.2	274.4	248.9
5116	PA5106_at	527.8	717.5	227.6	274.1	298.2
5117	PA5107_blc_at	120.6	81.6	189.4	193.3	178.1
5118	PA5108_at	173.2	117.6	239.8	236.1	191.5
5119	PA5109_at	193.6	117.1	255.8	241.5	173.5
5120	PA5110_fbp_at	539.8	363.4	724.3	703.3	726.4
5121	PA5111_gloA3_at	389.7	334.7	406.4	372.2	416.6
5122	PA5112_estA_at	1801.3	1835.0	2088.6	2009.7	2092.7
5123	PA5113_at	187.4	311.4	150.8	199.5	189.2
5124	PA5114_at	127.6	111.0	105.8	94.7	88.4
5125	PA5115_at	96.3	76.0	83.9	75.1	57.5
5126	PA5116_at	29.7	55.4	47.3	86.6	81.2
5127	PA5117_typA_at	156.6	350.3	133.2	114.6	101.1
5128	PA5118_thiI_at	71.6	75.6	144.9	100.2	117.8
5129	PA5119_glnA_at	3734.8	5000.7	1659.2	1573.6	1758.5
5130	PA5120_at	42.9	106.5	108.9	111.5	88.9
5131	PA5121_at	149.8	92.4	155.7	117.3	110.4
5132	PA5122_at	346.2	255.1	411.5	378.9	413.6
5133	PA5123_at	178.0	84.6	212.3	211.7	245.7
5134	PA5124_ntrB_at	141.0	86.5	63.1	106.6	100.5
5135	PA5125_ntrC_at	103.3	205.3	124.4	86.5	107.1
5136	PA5126_at	257.3	186.1	227.5	252.9	264.9
5137	PA5127_at	45.7	33.4	68.7	68.1	65.9
5138	PA5128_secB_at	127.1	342.7	364.6	321.1	307.1
5139	PA5129_grx_at	190.9	218.2	432.0	401.2	385.9
5140	PA5130_at	142.1	111.3	446.8	394.9	363.6
5141	PA5131_pgm_at	1389.9	893.2	1239.9	1277.5	1370.7
5142	PA5132_at	119.0	70.1	71.2	122.4	99.4
5143	PA5133_at	750.1	333.4	712.8	770.5	782.3
5144	PA5134_at	861.1	746.1	860.3	764.2	797.4
5145	PA5135_at	324.3	413.0	282.9	290.7	273.8
5146	PA5136_at	133.3	117.0	159.1	97.0	137.5
5147	PA5137_at	10.7	39.6	58.6	49.2	44.4
5148	PA5138_at	135.3	62.3	190.8	159.9	178.7
5149	PA5139_at	51.4	69.0	45.0	36.7	38.6
5150	PA5140_hisF1_at	108.4	156.3	151.2	184.6	153.0
5151	PA5141_hisA_at	253.6	148.2	191.0	198.9	132.9
5152	PA5142_hisH1_at	404.1	249.3	600.1	525.4	588.5
5153	PA5143_hisB_at	487.6	327.6	646.1	607.6	654.2
5154	PA5144_i_at	38.2	3.0	21.0	21.0	24.4
5155	PA5145_at	105.2	56.4	133.6	160.2	146.6
5156	PA5146_at	196.9	192.8	285.8	247.3	197.4
5157	PA5147_mutY_at	241.1	239.3	195.4	187.4	194.9
5158	PA5148_at	746.3	1166.9	710.1	625.5	698.2
5159	PA5149_at	55.0	94.9	49.8	63.3	63.6
5160	PA5150_at	103.2	78.2	67.6	103.8	98.8
5161	PA5151_at	158.1	66.0	133.9	140.4	132.9
5162	PA5152_at	5376.9	3475.5	4336.7	3815.4	4430.8
5163	PA5153_at	4712.3	4252.8	4470.8	4384.8	4772.5
5164	PA5154_at	516.7	313.6	911.1	811.9	754.3
5165	PA5155_at	236.4	191.3	226.2	278.0	205.2
5166	PA5156_at	103.6	96.4	43.6	57.1	41.0
5167	PA5157_at	84.3	78.0	128.2	128.4	85.2
5168	PA5158_at	101.1	69.7	94.3	73.2	63.1
5169	PA5159_at	87.0	74.7	46.3	28.4	35.7
5170	PA5160_at	101.2	83.5	56.5	39.1	33.4
5171	PA5161_rmlB_at	322.0	192.0	470.6	528.9	477.0
5172	PA5162_rmlD_at	307.7	322.0	250.8	255.8	251.3
5173	PA5163_rmlA_at	308.2	510.4	541.7	472.5	474.4
5174	PA5164_rmlC_at	262.2	467.7	311.6	320.7	327.9
5175	PA5165_at	274.6	249.4	259.0	266.5	297.1
5176	PA5166_at	272.2	179.3	317.7	264.6	298.9
5177	PA5167_at	92.6	243.7	244.3	216.7	221.6
5178	PA5168_at	5.0	42.9	65.3	79.0	54.9
5179	PA5169_at	50.5	57.9	57.4	46.0	41.8

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5180	PA5170_arcD_at	178.7	1560.7	268.9	265.4	209.2
5181	PA5171_arcA_at	1222.0	4346.1	1280.5	1077.7	929.7
5182	PA5172_arcB_at	1050.2	3990.0	1163.3	1003.9	742.8
5183	PA5173_arcC_at	358.4	579.9	383.1	355.1	299.2
5184	PA5174_at	203.2	234.8	451.1	361.2	436.1
5185	PA5175_cysQ_at	229.6	136.2	175.3	148.7	171.2
5186	PA5176_at	343.4	232.2	437.7	441.2	481.4
5187	PA5177_at	422.6	269.1	346.7	337.9	358.2
5188	PA5178_at	718.9	733.3	935.0	1001.2	938.6
5189	PA5179_at	137.9	63.0	169.0	136.4	122.5
5190	PA5180_at	209.7	412.7	909.8	559.9	602.9
5191	PA5181_at	129.2	227.2	437.2	403.4	357.3
5192	PA5182_at	2027.9	1082.5	1391.1	1851.5	2066.8
5193	PA5183_at	232.0	158.8	247.8	239.6	260.2
5194	PA5184_at	400.8	160.6	417.5	390.8	438.0
5195	PA5185_at	122.0	79.5	113.1	83.8	59.1
5196	PA5186_at	133.2	93.0	89.7	66.4	53.7
5197	PA5187_at	98.9	112.2	101.6	100.3	83.9
5198	PA5188_at	51.1	32.9	77.0	70.6	43.0
5199	PA5189_at	62.0	43.4	55.9	52.3	48.3
5200	PA5190_at	142.1	130.5	117.7	173.8	142.5
5201	PA5191_at	327.3	176.4	273.1	290.8	343.6
5202	PA5192_pckA_at	182.1	218.5	264.1	233.5	264.5
5203	PA5193_yrfI_at	34.4	56.7	197.9	185.8	164.1
5204	PA5194_at	18.5	43.6	89.5	88.0	59.1
5205	PA5195_at	316.2	228.5	400.6	369.7	427.6
5206	PA5196_at	365.1	191.0	358.1	394.4	430.7
5207	PA5197_rimK_at	163.6	118.4	144.3	171.3	147.3
5208	PA5198_at	306.8	133.7	146.7	204.6	220.6
5209	PA5199_envZ_at	207.8	190.4	245.3	196.2	183.3
5210	PA5200_ompR_at	676.6	420.4	1102.9	1064.9	978.4
5211	PA5201_at	104.8	177.1	159.4	190.2	159.3
5212	PA5202_at	17.6	132.8	68.1	49.9	32.8
5213	PA5203_gshA_at	324.5	256.1	380.0	369.2	358.6
5214	PA5204_argA_at	80.0	126.9	148.1	137.7	144.1
5215	PA5205_at	55.7	53.5	77.2	75.9	72.2
5216	PA5206_argE_at	677.4	789.6	696.4	676.0	703.6
5217	PA5207_at	10.3	11.3	18.6	24.7	11.5
5218	PA5208_at	97.2	141.2	145.9	171.9	162.6
5219	PA5209_at	115.0	123.8	112.6	121.7	85.0
5220	PA5210_at	278.9	285.9	260.9	250.6	236.6
5221	PA5211_at	169.8	136.4	160.7	168.9	131.8
5222	PA5212_i_at	2970.0	1829.6	1282.2	1523.7	1546.2
5223	PA5213_gcvP1_at	122.7	77.0	72.2	69.2	49.1
5224	PA5214_gcvH1_at	301.3	261.7	281.1	311.4	321.6
5225	PA5215_gcvT1_at	155.1	126.1	150.8	184.5	194.9
5226	PA5216_at	135.7	44.8	110.1	156.6	114.2
5227	PA5217_at	1335.9	621.1	1022.5	887.0	891.2
5228	PA5218_at	143.2	102.8	126.8	129.1	127.6
5229	PA5219_at	37.0	36.0	113.4	74.0	67.3
5230	PA5220_at	32.9	135.4	186.3	136.7	190.1
5231	PA5221_at	99.1	171.4	89.9	122.4	113.0
5232	PA5222_at	152.3	137.0	135.5	203.1	141.5
5233	PA5223_ubiH_at	185.9	163.9	215.6	186.4	190.1
5234	PA5224_pepP_at	405.3	246.2	550.1	528.7	466.1
5235	PA5225_at	499.4	224.7	968.8	799.8	814.5
5236	PA5226_at	1049.7	802.3	1067.6	1114.0	979.4
5237	PA5227_at	910.3	541.4	767.7	866.5	879.6
5238	PA5228_at	236.6	188.3	207.5	174.6	148.6
5239	PA5229_at	217.0	216.9	153.3	239.0	226.2
5240	PA5230_at	40.6	250.5	95.8	69.4	71.7
5241	PA5231_at	100.3	359.9	96.5	94.7	91.4
5242	PA5232_at	114.3	258.5	257.7	254.4	245.3
5243	PA5233_at	365.2	278.9	337.7	317.5	357.7
5244	PA5234_at	157.7	166.5	534.4	163.6	155.8
5245	PA5235_glpT_at	245.1	217.5	336.1	230.6	241.1
5246	PA5236_at	163.6	237.9	310.8	311.7	307.2
5247	PA5237_at	280.6	182.5	394.9	374.6	422.6
5248	PA5238_at	71.3	45.8	54.0	37.5	40.9
5249	PA5239_rho_at	179.3	206.4	167.5	159.7	153.0
5250	PA5240_trxA_at	814.1	497.1	1513.1	1254.0	1258.3
5251	PA5241_ppx_at	446.5	245.9	504.5	500.5	541.2
5252	PA5242_ppk_at	696.2	792.1	755.0	656.6	769.3

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5253	PA5243_hemB_at	433.2	254.4	458.8	448.4	498.9
5254	PA5244_at	112.1	43.8	89.2	100.2	89.1
5255	PA5245_at	555.6	453.8	676.9	569.7	642.4
5256	PA5246_at	109.4	108.4	135.9	121.1	88.2
5257	PA5247_at	645.3	464.8	605.2	618.8	611.4
5258	PA5248_at	125.8	71.1	113.6	124.9	141.5
5259	PA5249_at	76.2	82.5	134.1	136.9	89.8
5260	PA5250_at	126.5	187.6	84.9	72.2	89.0
5261	PA5251_at	88.4	101.0	83.9	138.7	124.6
5262	PA5252_at	126.8	100.0	238.3	348.1	325.8
5263	PA5253_algP_at	6633.1	5693.8	5032.1	5295.8	5430.5
5264	PA5254_at	85.4	113.3	169.6	145.3	147.6
5265	PA5255_algQ_at	2752.3	2501.7	2618.6	2631.7	2948.8
5266	PA5256_dsBH_at	7.6	31.7	75.7	62.9	69.8
5267	PA5257_at	159.5	153.3	132.5	147.7	143.3
5268	PA5258_at	268.6	162.7	323.7	348.4	297.0
5269	PA5259_hemD_at	235.6	164.4	163.6	280.2	199.0
5270	PA5260_hemC_at	494.1	381.8	445.6	523.5	633.2
5271	PA5261_algR_at	320.2	282.4	374.9	535.5	604.2
5272	PA5262_algZ_at	305.0	220.4	228.6	216.5	260.3
5273	PA5263_argH_at	420.4	321.4	763.8	791.0	649.4
5274	PA5264_at	173.3	138.4	124.2	146.2	134.5
5275	PA5265_at	6.9	23.5	18.9	38.5	37.9
5276	PA5266_at	114.7	58.7	57.5	44.6	29.5
5277	PA5268_corA_at	121.8	61.6	182.3	151.4	160.3
5278	PA5269_at	342.5	330.0	386.3	306.9	315.7
5279	PA5270_at	148.4	231.8	306.2	272.1	334.1
5280	PA5271_at	424.1	271.8	359.4	339.8	325.9
5281	PA5272_cyaA_at	192.3	174.5	202.3	168.0	180.9
5282	PA5273_at	83.3	57.7	113.5	122.0	125.2
5283	PA5274_rnk_at	450.1	242.9	1074.0	1141.9	1255.8
5284	PA5275_at	178.8	64.9	137.1	258.5	223.3
5285	PA5276_lppL_i_at	2406.8	1603.7	1926.0	2063.0	2164.5
5286	PA5277_lysA_at	629.5	304.7	943.2	688.8	693.7
5287	PA5278_dapF_at	250.5	141.0	323.3	245.5	251.5
5288	PA5279_at	877.7	771.7	1001.8	860.7	869.4
5289	PA5280_sss_at	153.4	174.9	149.7	162.4	138.0
5290	PA5281_at	165.0	218.5	126.8	142.5	133.5
5291	PA5282_at	93.8	27.3	27.9	12.2	5.4
5292	PA5283_at	119.0	44.5	79.9	69.2	48.0
5293	PA5284_at	7.4	8.2	3.7	17.8	9.1
5294	PA5285_at	910.3	1529.3	862.0	958.3	1060.5
5295	PA5286_at	109.7	141.7	142.6	132.8	129.0
5296	PA5287_amtB_at	140.6	174.7	125.1	173.7	144.8
5297	PA5288_glnK_at	2192.6	3011.9	1959.3	2217.0	2320.5
5298	PA5289_at	260.2	138.8	508.2	492.4	534.2
5299	PA5290_at	72.8	65.9	82.0	85.2	51.1
5300	PA5291_at	158.7	72.1	87.6	89.8	88.7
5301	PA5292_at	63.5	62.8	71.4	70.5	50.2
5302	PA5293_at	102.0	91.9	86.5	86.2	85.2
5303	PA5294_at	8.9	39.8	8.4	22.7	25.0
5304	PA5295_at	146.0	212.6	290.8	371.2	328.5
5305	PA5296_rep_at	79.3	58.7	86.3	76.8	58.5
5306	PA5297_poxB_at	28.6	101.9	64.2	79.6	83.4
5307	PA5298_at	185.3	160.7	184.1	147.0	156.2
5308	PA5299_at	128.2	76.6	92.9	76.9	95.5
5309	PA5300_cycB_at	177.9	180.9	395.3	368.3	361.9
5310	PA5301_at	1435.9	972.7	2233.6	2011.4	2325.1
5311	PA5302_dadX_at	560.1	157.6	445.4	461.0	440.7
5312	PA5303_at	1237.4	531.3	1166.7	1318.0	1214.9
5313	PA5304_dadA_at	2394.5	1243.1	1584.1	1998.2	2280.3
5314	PA5305_at	281.8	395.2	372.1	232.7	236.2
5315	PA5306_at	854.9	1272.1	830.6	895.7	831.5
5316	PA5307_at	121.8	102.4	98.1	104.5	140.9
5317	PA5308_lrp_at	594.5	404.8	427.0	507.8	550.9
5318	PA5309_at	168.8	130.3	217.7	171.7	225.4
5319	PA5310_at	85.6	62.4	63.5	96.1	93.3
5320	PA5311_at	5.6	40.1	39.8	28.5	34.4
5321	PA5312_at	4923.7	3037.4	4126.5	3921.9	4076.8
5322	PA5313_at	1686.4	603.8	1611.3	1543.5	1628.6
5323	PA5314_at	172.0	104.2	204.5	220.3	192.3
5324	PA5315_rpmG_at	98.8	139.0	74.1	88.1	103.6
5325	PA5316_rpmB_at	1322.2	1626.6	1062.5	784.5	882.2

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

5326	PA5317_at	165.9	187.2	216.0	199.0	211.7
5327	PA5318_at	123.5	56.8	55.4	60.2	56.8
5328	PA5319_radC_at	322.8	258.5	167.1	204.5	208.8
5329	PA5320_dfp_at	353.9	304.7	643.3	547.1	549.7
5330	PA5321_dut_at	119.2	163.9	155.6	121.0	173.1
5331	PA5322_algC_at	161.3	636.5	253.9	257.0	266.6
5332	PA5323_argB_at	111.9	545.7	136.3	118.6	114.3
5333	PA5324_at	329.2	321.4	324.5	332.5	340.8
5334	PA5325_at	12.2	40.4	22.9	45.4	30.5
5335	PA5326_at	5.9	11.6	7.8	24.1	18.0
5336	PA5327_at	96.2	54.2	83.8	67.1	74.8
5337	PA5328_at	11.8	5.6	26.1	16.6	19.3
5338	PA5329_at	461.1	414.6	402.1	455.3	505.1
5339	PA5330_at	486.7	324.1	445.9	467.4	474.6
5340	PA5331_pyrE_at	528.9	353.5	770.7	713.6	696.1
5341	PA5332_crc_at	2435.8	2525.2	2058.1	1704.9	2033.3
5342	PA5333_at	82.6	58.5	136.9	129.1	111.1
5343	PA5334_rph_at	335.4	318.0	491.6	454.3	486.9
5344	PA5335_at	302.8	158.8	418.2	365.8	363.7
5345	PA5336_gmk_at	88.8	86.2	176.1	195.2	188.9
5346	PA5337_rpoZ_at	898.5	729.8	1230.3	1236.1	1181.7
5347	PA5338_spoT_at	575.0	538.3	668.2	653.9	584.0
5348	PA5339_at	963.2	1654.2	912.1	782.4	719.4
5349	PA5340_at	247.4	421.3	431.6	335.4	379.7
5350	PA5341_at	72.8	38.8	45.4	53.1	28.2
5351	PA5342_at	34.8	32.8	76.5	60.8	57.3
5352	PA5343_at	61.4	77.4	126.2	123.9	104.0
5353	PA5344_at	446.4	227.0	671.8	710.4	750.6
5354	PA5345_recG_at	188.7	175.1	111.6	175.9	150.5
5355	PA5346_at	730.1	815.7	637.8	696.2	774.6
5356	PA5347_at	272.8	299.2	439.6	441.8	363.5
5357	PA5348_at	7189.4	6695.4	6009.3	5781.9	6494.2
5358	PA5349_at	93.2	38.7	111.5	169.5	129.1
5359	PA5350_r_at	763.2	577.5	743.0	847.3	887.0
5360	PA5351_at	168.5	215.8	188.8	167.0	147.3
5361	PA5352_at	113.3	55.6	31.7	62.3	46.9
5362	PA5353_glcF_at	57.7	34.6	36.7	34.2	30.3
5363	PA5354_glcE_at	14.0	9.9	29.8	17.7	27.2
5364	PA5355_glcD_at	32.9	61.3	86.3	76.6	75.2
5365	PA5356_glcC_at	1493.9	1593.9	1252.8	1395.0	1495.1
5366	PA5357_at	61.3	44.4	73.0	59.0	58.4
5367	PA5358_ubiA_at	192.3	143.0	192.4	173.0	215.8
5368	PA5359_at	191.4	169.7	188.8	205.6	212.1
5369	PA5360_phoB_at	202.1	199.7	210.3	190.7	213.2
5370	PA5361_phoR_at	89.6	24.3	69.8	53.5	26.8
5371	PA5362_at	277.4	125.9	671.8	613.3	604.3
5372	PA5363_at	191.4	104.1	189.4	200.6	197.3
5373	PA5364_at	723.3	706.3	883.6	877.9	1078.4
5374	PA5365_phoU_at	142.5	186.3	114.7	152.6	140.7
5375	PA5366_pstB_at	106.5	220.2	108.5	133.2	124.3
5376	PA5367_pstA_at	64.9	138.6	37.0	57.4	60.6
5377	PA5368_pstC_at	119.5	63.0	69.1	126.7	87.7
5378	PA5369_at	388.8	346.7	305.5	280.7	312.3
5379	PA5370_at	53.3	83.6	173.7	164.3	168.3
5380	PA5371_at	364.8	201.5	269.2	295.4	328.9
5381	PA5372_betA_at	59.3	48.9	50.7	54.9	53.7
5382	PA5373_betB_at	263.3	322.6	551.6	494.4	503.9
5383	PA5374_betI_at	197.6	366.7	499.9	456.7	550.5
5384	PA5375_betT1_at	59.0	37.9	104.5	111.8	125.8
5385	PA5376_at	89.6	101.5	80.5	80.7	87.7
5386	PA5377_at	232.6	188.8	315.3	354.8	289.6
5387	PA5378_at	231.9	211.2	292.8	301.1	309.8
5388	PA5379_sdaB_at	91.4	69.8	45.7	58.5	58.7
5389	PA5380_at	721.0	669.6	910.2	1000.2	1125.6
5390	PA5381_at	127.9	35.2	61.2	60.8	65.6
5391	PA5382_at	61.3	67.8	97.0	101.9	87.0
5392	PA5383_at	8.4	23.5	3.6	15.7	36.3
5393	PA5384_at	54.1	6.8	3.1	35.5	3.9
5394	PA5385_at	14.6	36.5	32.6	30.9	33.7
5395	PA5386_at	44.2	13.4	7.3	19.2	11.5
5396	PA5387_at	70.1	33.0	46.3	48.6	27.7
5397	PA5388_at	73.5	26.7	10.2	53.0	34.8
5398	PA5389_at	146.0	87.7	189.2	198.3	193.5

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5399	PA5390_at	5.3	14.1	15.1	59.0	43.9
5400	PA5391_at	71.6	18.0	11.5	26.1	11.1
5401	PA5392_at	20.9	10.4	36.5	30.8	30.7
5402	PA5393_at	113.9	30.0	50.5	54.5	37.0
5403	PA5394_cls_at	85.0	72.7	132.1	150.1	123.0
5404	PA5395_at	55.8	29.0	51.1	47.7	50.7
5405	PA5396_at	134.0	157.9	76.7	108.9	125.5
5406	PA5397_at	54.1	16.5	51.2	65.3	51.3
5407	PA5398_at	31.5	20.0	23.1	40.1	35.5
5408	PA5399_at	107.9	37.4	17.7	23.8	44.9
5409	PA5400_at	9.7	7.3	7.9	10.8	5.9
5410	PA5401_at	7.4	3.3	15.1	44.8	13.6
5411	PA5402_at	45.3	69.1	66.1	54.1	44.6
5412	PA5403_at	142.0	91.8	103.1	118.4	153.6
5413	PA5404_at	63.3	12.1	39.8	33.3	60.6
5414	PA5405_i_at	12.1	26.8	61.9	36.6	45.1
5415	PA5406_at	70.4	97.6	95.0	71.0	63.2
5416	PA5407_at	57.8	25.7	41.1	39.4	20.7
5417	PA5408_at	164.0	254.6	264.1	381.7	382.6
5418	PA5409_at	166.8	98.4	205.5	219.4	168.6
5419	PA5410_at	15.9	57.6	68.1	65.5	46.3
5420	PA5411_at	93.9	64.6	54.1	40.1	28.5
5421	PA5412_at	150.7	107.9	144.6	131.1	125.8
5422	PA5413_ltA_at	321.3	213.1	434.1	369.4	377.1
5423	PA5414_at	1320.5	727.5	1310.2	1309.6	1548.2
5424	PA5415_glyA1_s_at	170.6	1012.4	282.7	274.6	287.1
5425	PA5416_soxB_at	50.3	39.3	36.9	35.0	37.2
5426	PA5417_soxD_at	22.3	5.6	6.3	28.0	20.2
5427	PA5418_soxA_at	32.0	10.0	29.0	27.3	8.6
5428	PA5419_soxG_at	109.5	84.1	54.1	47.1	65.3
5429	PA5420_purU2_at	64.4	48.4	40.0	44.3	41.7
5430	PA5421_fdhA_at	111.1	47.3	45.3	36.9	40.8
5431	PA5422_at	431.8	473.5	368.2	412.8	420.4
5432	PA5423_at	423.1	252.7	433.3	729.7	523.3
5433	PA5424_at	418.8	360.6	407.5	493.0	492.6
5434	PA5425_purK_at	44.1	92.2	100.8	84.0	105.3
5435	PA5426_purE_at	268.3	188.2	341.7	227.2	274.9
5436	PA5427_adhA_at	85.2	205.9	59.1	80.1	45.7
5437	PA5428_at	350.1	111.9	242.4	256.0	225.7
5438	PA5429_aspA_at	4348.8	935.4	3364.6	2627.6	2607.3
5439	PA5430_at	89.8	76.3	61.4	79.6	97.8
5440	PA5431_at	71.1	61.4	62.7	66.9	52.9
5441	PA5432_at	386.7	360.3	349.7	308.7	429.0
5442	PA5433_at	107.6	118.0	118.1	137.6	138.9
5443	PA5434_mtr_at	61.6	31.4	31.0	38.7	25.7
5444	PA5435_at	834.8	2031.0	1019.3	1230.7	1114.7
5445	PA5436_at	3444.1	5070.6	2706.5	2658.3	3113.7
5446	PA5437_at	45.7	61.7	97.7	95.0	93.5
5447	PA5438_at	725.8	709.8	795.6	735.1	826.2
5448	PA5439_at	96.6	131.2	164.8	200.7	171.2
5449	PA5440_at	86.3	212.8	78.5	67.9	56.1
5450	PA5441_at	319.8	189.4	450.1	469.4	437.3
5451	PA5442_at	43.1	52.4	85.8	78.5	68.6
5452	PA5443_uvrD_at	337.0	260.3	443.4	420.9	453.0
5453	PA5444_at	56.0	52.3	55.0	60.0	46.3
5454	PA5445_at	82.8	228.1	78.2	106.2	98.1
5455	PA5446_i_at	20280.7	9449.5	7314.7	7703.7	8284.9
5456	PA5447_wbpZ_at	130.8	336.7	275.1	211.0	229.4
5457	PA5448_wbpY_at	74.3	296.4	136.1	175.9	112.7
5458	PA5449_wbpX_at	247.5	348.9	178.4	181.5	148.5
5459	PA5450_wzt_at	165.6	484.7	232.2	318.8	248.2
5460	PA5451_wzm_at	150.7	316.8	233.1	243.4	176.2
5461	PA5452_wbpW_at	295.0	252.8	309.1	322.1	267.3
5462	PA5453_gmd_at	835.3	722.5	1321.1	1416.8	1164.5
5463	PA5454_rmd_at	846.7	629.7	1100.4	980.4	849.7
5464	PA5455_at	485.4	308.9	621.6	604.5	576.0
5465	PA5456_at	415.5	365.0	364.5	341.9	379.6
5466	PA5457_at	102.4	160.0	167.2	165.8	119.3
5467	PA5458_at	143.0	177.2	108.8	146.0	101.2
5468	PA5459_at	221.8	533.9	179.3	192.2	206.5
5469	PA5460_at	164.9	395.0	185.0	232.9	293.0
5470	PA5461_at	1198.9	945.4	1059.7	1084.4	1285.7
5471	PA5462_at	417.7	172.4	581.0	631.6	646.4

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5472	PA5463_at	149.3	101.1	334.4	328.3	370.2
5473	PA5464_at	116.9	85.2	70.3	90.1	87.6
5474	PA5465_at	251.7	255.8	321.2	323.0	375.4
5475	PA5466_at	152.2	76.5	201.8	224.4	156.3
5476	PA5467_at	290.5	257.0	222.4	213.0	243.5
5477	PA5468_at	76.4	42.0	47.8	66.7	57.0
5478	PA5469_at	15.7	37.8	28.7	35.3	17.8
5479	PA5470_at	20.4	38.3	38.5	52.8	30.5
5480	PA5471_at	110.2	53.9	108.5	85.5	94.8
5481	PA5472_at	63.0	73.5	71.2	88.4	69.3
5482	PA5473_at	159.1	98.3	99.9	120.4	122.8
5483	PA5474_at	221.4	191.5	307.5	263.6	282.7
5484	PA5475_at	19.0	100.8	63.2	50.8	45.3
5485	PA5476_cita_at	73.5	51.0	42.1	44.6	37.2
5486	PA5477_at	208.1	103.6	109.8	123.6	122.9
5487	PA5478_at	87.5	58.2	121.0	110.1	96.7
5488	PA5479_gltP_at	7.9	26.5	28.2	41.0	15.3
5489	PA5480_at	8.6	3.1	2.1	14.0	6.4
5490	PA5481_at	18.1	26.8	49.6	61.1	69.3
5491	PA5482_at	9.7	24.5	40.9	53.1	43.1
5492	PA5483_algB_at	686.8	327.2	632.7	608.9	594.8
5493	PA5484_at	156.0	134.3	182.6	148.7	147.5
5494	PA5485_at	284.6	161.0	246.6	242.2	242.2
5495	PA5486_at	107.7	64.1	87.2	104.8	93.3
5496	PA5487_at	580.4	952.2	472.2	485.8	577.4
5497	PA5488_at	1147.2	926.9	830.6	891.8	950.4
5498	PA5489_dsbA_at	1157.3	1131.1	1381.8	1804.5	1900.3
5499	PA5490_cc4_at	596.7	622.5	965.4	671.2	844.4
5500	PA5491_at	449.9	250.5	654.2	587.4	613.8
5501	PA5492_at	1032.4	1211.0	727.5	700.8	766.1
5502	PA5493_pola_at	151.5	194.1	227.9	231.6	237.3
5503	PA5494_at	1229.0	1769.2	840.5	793.6	848.9
5504	PA5495_thrB_at	1152.3	1929.2	894.4	856.7	885.2
5505	PA5496_at	113.3	73.8	116.8	93.3	87.7
5506	PA5497_at	117.5	113.6	125.1	110.9	114.5
5507	PA5498_at	301.3	386.5	228.5	197.9	172.7
5508	PA5499_np20_at	403.3	949.8	465.5	450.7	558.8
5509	PA5500_znuC_at	206.7	427.3	280.2	255.6	299.4
5510	PA5501_znuB_at	100.3	178.3	123.2	156.2	157.8
5511	PA5502_at	67.5	86.3	117.6	152.9	149.6
5512	PA5503_at	93.5	74.7	136.8	94.4	83.9
5513	PA5504_at	133.8	123.4	96.5	102.0	92.9
5514	PA5505_at	225.2	540.8	273.6	251.6	263.4
5515	PA5506_at	393.2	280.6	735.0	625.7	756.0
5516	PA5507_at	584.0	497.3	940.3	764.8	849.9
5517	PA5508_at	265.2	270.9	430.1	423.5	344.2
5518	PA5509_at	118.6	112.5	163.2	111.4	134.5
5519	PA5510_at	62.0	63.6	57.1	44.5	45.9
5520	PA5511_at	17.3	79.1	128.5	139.6	123.2
5521	PA5512_at	102.3	58.9	74.8	100.2	115.9
5522	PA5513_at	183.1	125.3	270.5	211.8	161.4
5523	PA5514_at	7.0	7.0	33.4	30.1	46.1
5524	PA5515_at	304.8	176.6	328.1	381.2	402.4
5525	PA5516_pdxY_at	160.8	115.8	193.7	176.9	160.7
5526	PA5517_at	58.5	33.5	65.6	69.5	67.4
5527	PA5518_at	110.5	47.8	96.0	110.8	78.3
5528	PA5519_at	474.2	316.0	429.5	391.6	403.4
5529	PA5520_at	105.6	61.2	64.5	65.4	56.5
5530	PA5521_at	433.1	333.7	283.4	312.5	292.5
5531	PA5522_at	285.4	265.1	455.0	437.7	422.7
5532	PA5523_at	1325.9	589.0	1485.1	1671.9	1721.2
5533	PA5524_at	914.4	1465.5	803.3	718.8	766.1
5534	PA5525_at	549.9	478.1	529.5	617.9	620.9
5535	PA5526_at	241.5	158.8	136.3	147.9	165.3
5536	PA5527_at	33.8	128.5	112.9	149.2	122.5
5537	PA5528_at	613.2	311.4	756.3	889.0	811.8
5538	PA5529_at	46.1	101.9	129.4	121.3	146.6
5539	PA5530_at	60.9	25.2	19.3	22.8	21.7
5540	PA5531_tonB_at	3549.0	3271.3	993.7	832.0	898.5
5541	PA5532_at	114.2	21.5	54.4	44.6	55.3
5542	PA5533_at	39.2	62.1	112.3	89.4	86.2
5543	PA5534_at	42.4	2.4	15.5	21.0	16.9
5544	PA5535_at	74.8	62.8	58.5	47.0	75.7

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

5545	PA5536_at	53.0	24.9	11.5	24.2	10.8
5546	PA5537_at	39.9	70.0	74.9	78.9	61.3
5547	PA5538_amiA_at	36.2	6.6	15.9	31.7	17.0
5548	PA5539_at	59.1	22.6	44.3	24.9	28.8
5549	PA5540_at	49.7	84.1	33.6	39.0	28.9
5550	PA5541_at	17.1	42.8	51.6	60.7	45.2
5551	PA5542_at	15.6	31.4	51.6	43.9	46.9
5552	PA5543_at	109.0	73.7	70.8	101.7	74.2
5553	PA5544_at	107.3	82.2	92.6	125.7	107.8
5554	PA5545_at	343.8	374.2	751.1	870.8	996.6
5555	PA5546_at	5904.8	3169.5	4863.8	4302.8	4100.7
5556	PA5547_at	155.9	125.2	149.1	138.4	159.6
5557	PA5548_at	70.3	54.4	39.2	45.1	33.8
5558	PA5549_glmS_at	238.3	264.9	100.8	132.3	103.0
5559	PA5550_at	208.5	157.7	174.4	148.0	141.2
5560	PA5551_at	334.6	304.4	170.1	196.2	159.4
5561	PA5552_glmU_at	636.0	827.0	692.8	662.0	675.3
5562	PA5553_atpC_at	343.7	658.5	249.0	266.5	220.0
5563	PA5554_atpD_at	744.5	1691.7	448.9	435.9	473.0
5564	PA5555_atpG_at	1656.1	4359.5	1022.4	1101.4	1093.1
5565	PA5556_atpA_at	907.3	1895.2	781.5	849.2	829.8
5566	PA5557_atpH_at	991.3	1784.2	738.7	742.6	725.9
5567	PA5558_atpF_at	1881.6	3252.4	1600.5	1484.7	1602.0
5568	PA5559_atpE_at	1441.4	2621.1	935.9	1040.7	997.0
5569	PA5560_atpB_at	208.3	388.6	526.6	383.9	395.4
5570	PA5561_atpI_at	71.0	61.8	132.9	129.0	98.5
5571	PA5562_spo0J_at	208.3	417.3	377.5	393.4	356.8
5572	PA5563_soj_at	721.8	605.5	832.7	728.1	789.1
5573	PA5564_gidB_at	159.0	207.8	220.0	184.6	148.5
5574	PA5565_gidA_at	160.9	141.3	275.2	293.5	233.3
5575	PA5566_at	16.1	28.3	14.3	19.2	13.1
5576	PA5567_at	126.3	94.1	90.2	129.4	111.0
5577	PA5568_at	383.9	596.8	349.5	262.8	332.3
5578	PA5569_rnpA_at	668.7	557.1	1264.8	1072.8	1068.1
5579	PA5570_rpmH_at	341.7	239.8	601.3	513.6	544.8
5580	ig_53521_56546_at	46.0	30.4	40.8	40.3	42.1
5581	ig_64729_65339_at	31.1	21.9	33.0	50.1	29.4
5582	ig_65479_66303_at	14.5	14.0	2.1	9.9	7.8
5583	ig_68616_69272_at	435.3	254.7	209.8	292.0	274.3
5584	ig_188448_189120_at	104.7	83.6	31.0	59.6	43.7
5585	ig_223454_224101_at	145.3	96.4	83.3	88.5	92.7
5586	ig_297561_299081_at	64.5	23.7	18.1	34.4	18.5
5587	ig_326671_327284_at	485.8	60.4	73.9	25.6	97.7
5588	ig_517462_518083_at	22.6	27.7	42.9	41.3	54.2
5589	ig_545644_546334_at	35.1	79.6	32.7	44.4	47.6
5590	ig_629884_630527_at	69.4	63.3	47.8	77.6	51.8
5591	ig_721556_727608_s_at	2429.2	3812.7	1752.9	1915.2	1989.8
5592	ig_773696_774416_at	17.9	47.6	99.8	66.5	75.1
5593	ig_785174_785969_at	4.5	16.3	9.5	19.6	8.1
5594	ig_788253_789144_at	79.2	44.0	38.3	64.0	52.7
5595	ig_863300_864095_at	189.7	224.0	209.5	233.5	223.8
5596	ig_884172_884799_at	47.1	58.6	43.6	24.1	25.2
5597	ig_901046_901934_at	28.4	11.3	8.7	13.5	15.9
5598	ig_991198_991830_at	139.4	197.6	181.1	267.4	240.5
5599	ig_1046911_1047549_at	78.0	141.6	143.2	158.0	158.6
5600	ig_1063544_1064555_at	68.0	122.8	73.8	115.4	120.8
5601	ig_1087095_1087843_at	16.1	56.7	95.2	108.9	103.4
5602	ig_1117390_1118158_at	224.2	183.0	203.9	260.5	230.8
5603	ig_1204781_1205771_at	107.7	114.1	101.6	115.4	75.6
5604	ig_1246788_1247932_at	53.9	50.2	36.2	51.6	53.3
5605	ig_1254309_1255042_at	40.0	13.5	8.3	18.8	15.5
5606	ig_1324109_1324793_at	16.8	31.3	40.4	53.0	44.2
5607	ig_1348401_1349416_at	102.8	108.1	67.2	76.0	51.9
5608	ig_1427453_1428080_at	82.4	62.9	44.1	62.7	44.4
5609	ig_1489095_1489815_at	75.1	44.7	67.7	59.7	39.8
5610	ig_1553675_1554415_at	14.4	17.9	29.6	36.5	13.3
5611	ig_1637696_1638379_at	6.3	2.1	3.6	1.5	2.6
5612	ig_1802453_1803626_at	26.7	27.4	23.1	31.9	17.3
5613	ig_1947041_1948502_at	60.6	100.1	64.9	68.8	58.1
5614	ig_1996806_1997509_at	95.5	123.0	118.8	152.1	119.8
5615	ig_2068728_2069490_at	105.7	126.8	148.8	170.2	174.3
5616	ig_2116265_2117030_at	61.5	18.4	6.8	19.3	32.4
5617	ig_2164548_2165213_at	36.3	28.4	17.3	30.1	22.0

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

5618	ig_2226144_2226879_at	41.7	15.2	15.9	36.0	29.2
5619	ig_2239267_2240302_at	5.7	22.9	13.0	25.4	13.1
5620	ig_2243603_2244492_at	54.4	10.5	16.2	17.5	15.8
5621	ig_2250595_2251275_at	31.4	20.2	10.8	14.4	9.5
5622	ig_2281578_2282480_at	86.3	49.2	33.8	21.1	27.6
5623	ig_2341640_2342493_at	71.9	81.8	41.3	75.8	45.3
5624	ig_2450765_2451707_at	13.5	11.5	1.6	7.3	4.4
5625	ig_2557964_2558918_s_at	265.3	431.8	233.3	334.6	326.1
5626	ig_2568284_2568929_at	2.3	7.0	4.2	10.3	3.8
5627	ig_2721530_2722174_at	22.9	12.2	6.5	11.1	5.7
5628	ig_2737193_2737881_at	36.4	24.3	2.8	22.3	8.9
5629	ig_2893827_2894451_at	13.9	77.5	54.0	61.4	52.6
5630	ig_2901558_2902217_at	66.3	38.4	41.2	32.0	37.0
5631	ig_2905549_2906165_at	58.2	27.0	37.9	43.4	26.8
5632	ig_2918211_2918966_at	36.8	53.8	67.4	85.0	45.0
5633	ig_2922568_2923366_at	8.4	11.0	8.0	24.0	15.6
5634	ig_2927920_2928538_at	5.3	1.9	2.5	1.6	2.3
5635	ig_3051348_3051956_at	8.2	83.3	80.0	64.1	30.7
5636	ig_3087490_3088659_at	78.6	29.7	40.8	39.8	33.8
5637	ig_3112150_3112877_at	29.2	37.9	60.8	75.5	55.5
5638	ig_3115632_3116653_at	70.2	81.0	63.2	72.2	56.2
5639	ig_3122585_3123598_at	56.5	31.8	32.0	20.5	15.8
5640	ig_3129070_3129728_at	69.1	22.4	14.4	26.6	28.5
5641	ig_3206252_3206914_at	46.3	15.3	54.0	33.6	28.7
5642	ig_3265210_3265847_at	47.9	34.2	15.3	23.9	23.6
5643	ig_3475169_3475955_at	57.9	39.9	18.5	25.6	13.4
5644	ig_3514564_3515415_at	3.2	18.5	11.0	13.2	14.1
5645	ig_3526677_3527428_at	303.7	323.0	168.0	205.7	179.0
5646	ig_3545073_3545880_at	70.2	94.5	92.3	74.5	107.6
5647	ig_3546926_3547688_at	98.3	137.2	46.3	52.8	38.6
5648	ig_3648915_3649704_at	49.9	49.7	32.0	45.7	31.2
5649	ig_3677080_3677719_at	25.8	22.4	16.9	22.3	22.1
5650	ig_3705160_3705889_at	69.9	41.5	29.4	40.3	42.4
5651	ig_3961922_3962824_at	1.6	2.2	5.0	0.9	1.8
5652	ig_4240578_4241341_at	125.8	83.5	72.2	59.9	66.3
5653	ig_4294604_4297249_at	33.6	13.1	20.5	24.7	16.4
5654	ig_4320819_4321433_at	171.3	80.4	77.7	120.4	74.6
5655	ig_4326394_4327696_at	65.3	43.2	38.7	48.1	40.2
5656	ig_4448217_4448892_at	22.4	63.3	60.9	87.9	66.1
5657	ig_4509996_4510970_at	29.3	19.1	8.7	17.8	18.5
5658	ig_4559649_4560294_at	458.6	545.2	327.8	334.1	388.9
5659	ig_4584530_4585148_at	13.2	2.7	6.1	25.6	1.9
5660	ig_4629184_4629943_at	6.5	16.6	14.7	8.8	5.7
5661	ig_4705304_4705955_at	63.0	53.9	40.8	50.9	43.2
5662	ig_4713098_4713795_at	5.6	24.6	14.1	14.8	8.7
5663	ig_727608_721556_s_at	153.1	47.8	36.9	29.0	22.3
5664	ig_4888194_4889111_at	53.4	27.8	8.3	29.1	21.4
5665	ig_4956028_4956733_at	41.1	19.6	31.8	24.3	20.0
5666	ig_5086695_5087407_at	61.9	15.8	32.3	39.3	33.5
5667	ig_5130767_5131427_at	3978.9	553.3	2896.5	2104.7	2503.9
5668	ig_5207621_5208463_at	175.0	281.8	412.5	355.4	392.9
5669	ig_5242558_5243177_at	28.4	59.4	77.7	100.0	78.3
5670	ig_5308424_5309325_at	1106.2	1259.7	696.7	868.3	951.3
5671	ig_5457716_5458499_i_at	9.7	2.8	2.7	12.0	1.2
5672	ig_5513111_5513731_at	5.5	25.8	8.4	10.2	14.6
5673	ig_5541409_5542072_at	101.8	87.4	116.1	120.1	89.1
5674	ig_5563286_5563964_at	541.6	340.5	515.8	522.6	506.9
5675	ig_5774806_5775619_at	4.0	33.4	19.5	56.1	24.3
5676	ig_5820113_5820909_at	6.0	10.3	1.9	6.8	7.9
5677	ig_5991130_5992382_at	156.9	259.7	249.1	174.8	182.7
5678	ig_6090705_6092045_at	4.2	10.6	4.1	17.8	3.9
5679	ig_6125079_6125795_at	4.5	34.0	16.5	13.4	6.3
5680	ig_56546_53521_at	19.5	6.7	7.3	14.8	8.0
5681	ig_65339_64729_at	669.4	674.1	547.1	459.7	495.4
5682	ig_66303_65479_at	71.9	132.2	61.9	79.7	74.8
5683	ig_69272_68616_at	122.9	143.4	143.3	157.8	70.3
5684	ig_189120_188448_at	47.0	36.1	28.3	74.2	41.4
5685	ig_224101_223454_at	32.5	31.2	35.2	40.1	15.2
5686	ig_299081_297561_at	7.5	21.3	11.0	18.5	16.0
5687	ig_327284_326671_at	127.5	53.1	22.6	44.4	56.4
5688	ig_518083_517462_at	27.8	40.1	33.4	44.9	13.9
5689	ig_546334_545644_at	94.2	62.7	33.3	54.6	39.7
5690	ig_630527_629884_at	175.2	148.2	86.9	95.1	102.9

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5691	ig_774416_773696_at	142.6	28.3	5.5	32.5	6.7
5692	ig_785969_785174_at	65.4	396.1	68.7	125.7	123.4
5693	ig_789144_788253_at	104.4	60.4	98.7	96.5	110.6
5694	ig_864095_863300_at	5.2	53.7	32.4	64.2	49.4
5695	ig_884799_884172_at	39.6	46.2	15.0	27.1	34.0
5696	ig_901934_901046_at	218.7	384.2	227.1	256.1	220.7
5697	ig_991830_991198_at	32.8	17.8	22.0	6.6	12.2
5698	ig_1047549_1046911_at	704.8	489.2	726.9	733.6	663.2
5699	ig_1064555_1063544_at	123.0	115.0	39.3	24.6	39.3
5700	ig_1087843_1087095_at	256.6	193.8	215.0	208.7	270.0
5701	ig_1118158_1117390_at	76.2	77.9	60.6	58.3	33.2
5702	ig_1205771_1204781_at	218.9	214.1	220.1	232.0	207.5
5703	ig_1247932_1246788_at	5.5	0.3	2.3	6.0	6.3
5704	ig_1255042_1254309_at	112.0	52.0	97.0	161.9	124.6
5705	ig_1324793_1324109_at	35.0	14.2	20.9	17.7	13.6
5706	ig_1349416_1348401_at	269.1	307.2	122.6	118.0	188.8
5707	ig_1428080_1427453_at	9.6	5.4	5.7	14.8	33.8
5708	ig_1489815_1489095_at	114.4	83.2	77.6	76.7	84.2
5709	ig_1554415_1553675_at	80.8	83.6	88.1	127.3	98.5
5710	ig_1638379_1637696_at	24.1	3.4	17.8	26.5	18.9
5711	ig_1803626_1802453_at	52.1	52.5	63.4	59.3	70.4
5712	ig_1948502_1947041_at	86.9	70.2	26.2	51.0	42.2
5713	ig_1997509_1996806_at	61.0	94.0	103.8	89.4	109.7
5714	ig_2069490_2068728_at	72.5	133.8	89.0	75.4	70.2
5715	ig_2117030_2116265_at	98.8	55.3	101.7	72.4	68.8
5716	ig_2165213_2164548_at	137.0	96.9	75.3	86.7	67.5
5717	ig_2226879_2226144_at	28.5	28.1	12.0	27.3	26.5
5718	ig_2240302_2239267_at	76.7	33.2	39.8	37.4	33.2
5719	ig_2244492_2243603_at	91.7	41.0	155.6	140.5	155.2
5720	ig_2251275_2250595_at	55.2	31.5	33.8	23.0	19.3
5721	ig_2282480_2281578_at	61.4	20.2	5.6	22.1	24.2
5722	ig_2342493_2341640_at	324.1	292.7	220.6	353.9	307.7
5723	ig_2451707_2450765_at	29.7	13.1	7.6	10.7	6.4
5724	ig_2558918_2557964_s_at	162.4	135.4	162.9	186.3	156.1
5725	ig_2568929_2568284_at	8.9	26.2	10.4	31.2	24.9
5726	ig_2722174_2721530_at	135.3	96.6	34.8	40.1	10.3
5727	ig_2737881_2737193_at	5.4	3.4	4.2	8.4	12.9
5728	ig_2894451_2893827_at	259.3	248.1	344.5	277.3	287.1
5729	ig_2902217_2901558_at	21.5	10.4	7.0	22.3	12.8
5730	ig_2906165_2905549_at	113.2	77.7	72.7	74.8	82.2
5731	ig_2918966_2918211_at	63.3	68.5	53.6	71.1	47.5
5732	ig_2923366_2922568_at	51.8	28.6	35.8	21.5	10.2
5733	ig_2928538_2927920_at	8.7	4.5	12.8	26.4	10.1
5734	ig_3051956_3051348_at	43.3	0.9	5.0	17.0	2.3
5735	ig_3088659_3087490_at	16.0	13.0	26.7	43.4	25.5
5736	ig_3112877_3112150_at	55.5	40.9	37.9	52.3	50.6
5737	ig_3116653_3115632_at	86.3	51.3	88.8	55.7	100.8
5738	ig_3123598_3122585_at	94.0	55.1	53.7	50.3	51.0
5739	ig_3129728_3129070_at	91.6	76.7	100.3	114.1	96.5
5740	ig_3206914_3206252_at	56.2	25.5	6.9	10.1	31.2
5741	ig_3265847_3265210_at	20.4	27.9	20.9	27.9	7.8
5742	ig_3475955_3475169_at	46.8	33.5	20.2	35.3	23.1
5743	ig_3515415_3514564_at	5.2	25.3	26.4	32.5	42.0
5744	ig_3527428_3526677_at	132.0	159.8	130.7	187.0	188.3
5745	ig_3545880_3545073_at	527.4	517.3	706.7	722.9	664.6
5746	ig_3547688_3546926_at	549.1	803.7	669.2	744.4	728.1
5747	ig_3649704_3648915_at	114.3	84.9	120.1	148.8	125.8
5748	ig_3677719_3677080_at	122.2	60.2	97.9	103.0	104.0
5749	ig_3705889_3705160_at	255.2	209.4	160.4	182.1	187.0
5750	ig_3874653_3873835_r_at	9.0	27.5	41.2	29.7	4.4
5751	ig_3962824_3961922_at	2.7	0.6	1.3	3.3	1.0
5752	ig_4241341_4240578_at	7.6	48.8	40.4	40.4	40.9
5753	ig_4297249_4294604_at	16.6	18.9	31.9	33.2	33.8
5754	ig_4321433_4320819_at	56.8	35.3	61.5	61.7	32.7
5755	ig_4327696_4326394_at	96.6	128.7	67.5	72.0	63.1
5756	ig_4448892_4448217_at	103.0	97.2	120.2	108.4	120.5
5757	ig_4510970_4509996_at	29.3	29.6	23.1	37.7	28.4
5758	ig_4560294_4559649_at	3.6	22.1	7.5	9.3	11.9
5759	ig_4585148_4584530_at	51.4	14.3	39.6	23.6	19.5
5760	ig_4629943_4629184_at	4.9	1.3	1.0	23.4	5.6
5761	ig_4705955_4705304_at	9.9	25.5	39.8	27.1	60.8
5762	ig_4713795_4713098_at	21.5	6.7	26.5	31.8	24.2
5763	ig_4889111_4888194_at	117.6	56.1	149.7	145.1	132.0

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5764	ig_4956733_4956028_at	14888.9	13274.6	6036.7	8986.9	8452.2
5765	ig_5087407_5086695_at	79.7	46.7	61.6	61.3	35.8
5766	ig_5131427_5130767_at	207.4	151.3	187.3	155.5	119.2
5767	ig_5208463_5207621_at	50.8	42.6	45.9	50.1	35.4
5768	ig_5243177_5242558_at	254.7	203.4	190.4	330.2	338.5
5769	ig_5309325_5308424_at	40.4	49.3	43.9	54.6	48.2
5770	ig_5458499_5457716_at	10.0	3.6	6.6	11.3	3.4
5771	ig_5513731_5513111_at	23.3	50.0	35.7	48.7	30.9
5772	ig_5542072_5541409_at	262.0	140.7	234.1	276.6	356.4
5773	ig_5563964_5563286_at	56.6	144.1	132.6	114.4	102.9
5774	ig_5775619_5774806_at	71.3	73.3	136.3	125.9	86.2
5775	ig_5820909_5820113_at	65.8	37.7	11.3	35.6	41.7
5776	ig_5992382_5991130_at	75.0	75.1	56.7	55.4	50.3
5777	ig_6092045_6090705_at	14.7	8.4	26.0	29.3	33.3
5778	ig_6125795_6125079_at	173.3	231.2	211.0	183.4	145.7
5779	Pae_AF291700cnds_at	5.2	6.5	3.8	11.1	1.7
5780	Pae_AF191564cnds1_at	13.8	2.4	2.8	1.0	3.3
5781	Pae_AF191564cnds4_at	31.3	3.1	5.1	2.5	5.5
5782	Pae_AF140629cnds1_at	22.1	4.7	11.3	3.7	11.6
5783	Pae_AF140629cnds2_at	47.3	3.6	1.5	4.9	0.9
5784	Pae_AF133699cnds2_at	70.5	23.7	22.9	20.2	21.0
5785	Pae_AF133699cnds3_at	1.7	0.7	0.1	0.2	0.1
5786	Pae_AF133699cnds4_at	22.9	2.1	11.0	5.1	2.5
5787	Pae_AF133697cnds_at	7.0	1.1	2.9	0.5	5.8
5788	Pae_AF147795cnds2_at	5.9	1.1	0.1	1.6	4.8
5789	Pae_AF147795cnds3_at	76.3	1.6	1.1	0.5	3.3
5790	Pae_AF147795cnds4_at	6.8	0.4	1.1	1.4	0.4
5791	Pae_AF147795cnds5_at	3.7	2.0	3.1	2.1	0.4
5792	Pae_AF147795cnds6_at	32.9	11.1	3.4	0.4	3.3
5793	Pae_AF147795cnds7_at	24.8	0.9	9.2	0.4	0.9
5794	Pae_AF147795cnds8_at	5.7	10.7	0.7	7.0	4.5
5795	Pae_AF147795cnds9_at	24.5	2.4	1.8	0.8	0.5
5796	Pae_AF147795cnds10_at	5.1	1.8	5.7	6.3	1.7
5797	Pae_AF147795cnds11_at	4.6	0.4	0.5	0.2	0.4
5798	Pae_AF043558cnds_at	28.6	3.9	1.5	7.3	1.2
5799	Pae_AF080442cnds1_at	8.2	8.8	16.0	22.6	9.4
5800	Pae_AF080442cnds2_at	7.1	2.8	10.9	1.3	1.1
5801	Pae_M21651cnds_at	15.4	0.8	13.4	1.9	0.8
5802	Pae_M21652cnds_at	4.4	1.3	1.0	0.9	1.1
5803	Pae_L07945cnds_at	39.7	0.2	0.9	1.3	0.6
5804	Pae_L37109cnds1_at	34.6	1.7	2.2	6.1	6.7
5805	Pae_L37109cnds2_at	38.2	0.3	4.8	2.3	3.2
5806	Pae_AF027291cnds_at	6.7	31.4	26.9	6.1	21.1
5807	Pae_M57501cnds_g_at	40.3	4.3	2.3	1.5	10.0
5808	Pae_U97065cnds3_at	38.0	6.1	3.8	2.0	2.2
5809	Pae_U85514cnds_at	8.5	1.5	26.5	21.6	25.3
5810	Pae_L06157cnds2_at	14.5	2.1	6.9	1.1	2.1
5811	Pae_J05162cnds_at	1.2	3.4	0.1	0.1	0.2
5812	Pae_M14849cnds_at	52.2	1.7	1.4	0.6	0.9
5813	Pae_M14850cnds_at	24.4	11.8	3.2	1.1	0.8
5814	Pae_M98270cnds1_at	5.5	1.7	0.9	1.3	9.0
5815	Pae_M98270cnds2_at	37.3	5.7	15.0	6.9	3.2
5816	Pae_M98270cnds3_at	3.1	0.6	3.4	0.4	2.5
5817	Pae_M29695cnds1_at	5.6	6.1	1.3	1.5	1.8
5818	Pae_M29695cnds2_at	25.4	16.5	13.8	9.2	11.8
5819	Pae_L06161cnds_at	6.1	3.3	2.8	2.6	4.2
5820	Pae_L06160cnds_at	26.3	8.9	2.8	11.3	18.9
5821	Pae_AF035937cnds3_at	24.1	3.1	4.1	0.6	1.3
5822	Pae_AF035937cnds4_at	3.0	1.2	4.6	1.1	0.4
5823	Pae_AF035937cnds5_at	3.4	4.1	9.5	1.5	1.6
5824	Pae_AF035937cnds6_at	50.2	1.4	5.1	0.6	1.8
5825	Pae_AF035937cnds7_at	11.0	7.7	1.6	0.4	3.6
5826	Pae_AF035937cnds8_at	5.2	1.2	2.7	0.9	1.7
5827	Pae_AF035937cnds9_at	5.6	1.8	0.8	0.6	0.8
5828	Pae_AF035937cnds10_at	9.6	0.5	2.8	0.6	0.7
5829	Pae_AF035937cnds11_at	40.8	3.6	13.6	4.6	2.9
5830	Pae_AF035937cnds12_at	27.8	13.9	3.9	3.7	10.0
5831	Pae_AF035937cnds13_at	65.2	2.2	2.5	5.3	2.0
5832	Pae_L81176cnds3_at	54.1	34.5	44.2	40.6	28.6
5833	Pae_L81176cnds4_at	18.8	18.1	21.3	11.6	16.0
5834	Pae_L81176cnds5_at	34.6	21.3	10.4	9.8	17.7
5835	Pae_L81176cnds6_at	14.5	2.3	3.2	1.8	2.8
5836	Pae_AF241171cnds1_r_at	6.4	3.6	3.3	1.8	2.1

Table 4 (Palma *et al.*, 2004, Supplementary Material)

5837	Pae_AF241171cds4_at	47.9	20.2	20.3	3.6	18.9
5838	Pae_AF241171cds5_at	9.2	13.7	22.3	5.6	9.9
5839	Pae_AF241171cds6_at	10.4	14.6	4.4	11.7	6.7
5840	Pae_AF241171cds7_at	51.7	5.3	26.1	17.1	13.5
5841	Pae_AF241171cds8_at	26.9	7.1	21.2	3.6	15.9
5842	Pae_AF241171cds9_at	16.0	3.1	6.9	14.9	4.2
5843	Pae_AF241171cds10_at	6.7	2.4	2.9	2.2	1.8
5844	Pae_AF241171cds11_at	40.5	12.2	4.2	1.1	4.7
5845	Pae_AF241171cds12_at	58.0	2.2	5.0	2.9	1.4
5846	Pae_AF241171cds13_at	3.0	0.7	3.3	0.7	1.7
5847	Pae_AF241171cds14_at	5.8	3.9	2.0	1.9	1.5
5848	Pae_AF241171cds15_at	17.3	7.3	29.5	6.4	55.3
5849	Pae_AF241171cds16_at	43.2	4.2	4.8	12.7	12.1
5850	Pae_AF241171cds17_at	9.8	10.6	0.8	8.5	1.3
5851	Pae_AF241171cds18_at	75.9	15.1	17.3	4.7	21.3
5852	Pae_AF241171cds19_at	6.1	15.0	21.5	14.0	11.7
5853	Pae_AF241171cds20_at	42.8	16.7	2.5	3.7	3.3
5854	Pae_AF241171cds21_at	26.5	7.3	10.2	3.7	4.8
5855	Pae_AF241171cds22_at	12.2	10.9	15.1	3.2	1.1
5856	Pae_AF241171cds23_at	3.7	1.7	1.2	1.0	0.8
5857	Pae_AF241171cds24_at	2.2	8.6	0.7	9.7	1.2
5858	Pae_AF241171cds25_at	47.3	36.4	13.9	7.3	11.8
5859	Pae_AF241171cds26_at	27.0	13.8	14.6	13.0	18.2
5860	Pae_AF241171cds27_at	7.4	4.2	4.1	5.8	7.4
5861	Pae_AF241171cds28_at	14.0	1.2	3.3	14.4	3.1
5862	Pae_AF241171cds29_at	43.8	14.5	0.9	5.7	1.5
5863	Pae_AF241171cds30_at	29.9	2.4	5.7	4.5	4.0
5864	Pae_AF241171cds31_at	4.3	1.3	1.1	1.0	0.7
5865	Pae_AF241171cds34_at	24.6	23.3	11.6	2.8	14.0
5866	Pae_AF241171cds35_at	30.4	23.0	4.4	13.1	15.2
5867	Pae_AF241171cds36_at	2.0	0.7	0.6	0.3	0.3
5868	Pae_AF241171cds39_at	145.6	59.3	46.0	10.5	28.6
5869	Pae_AF241171cds40_at	32.1	4.3	10.1	11.5	20.0
5870	Pae_AF241171cds41_at	4.1	26.0	21.9	1.1	20.1
5871	Pae_AF241171cds42_at	3.6	7.5	2.3	6.8	6.9
5872	Pae_AF241171cds43_s_at	22.9	9.2	11.5	0.3	0.5
5873	Pae_AF241171cds44_r_at	45.7	2.8	3.2	1.9	1.4
5874	Pae_AF241171cds45_at	3.9	15.7	4.7	0.9	17.0
5875	Pae_AF241171cds47_at	7.7	16.4	1.3	0.4	0.5
5876	Pae_AF241171cds48_at	3.4	14.3	9.6	1.3	2.4
5877	Pae_AF241171cds49_i_at	3.4	0.7	0.8	0.1	3.0
5878	Pae_AF241171cds50_i_at	25.4	7.5	12.6	6.1	11.2
5879	Pae_AF241171cds51_at	1.9	2.7	1.4	5.0	0.3
5880	Pae_tRNA_Ala_f_at	422.6	819.3	206.9	249.1	245.7
5881	Pae_tRNA_Arg_s_at	9670.9	4754.9	3761.7	4235.8	4805.5
5882	Pae_tRNA_Asn_s_at	219.2	357.6	193.7	232.1	217.1
5883	Pae_tRNA_Gln_s_at	651.6	758.4	739.3	693.5	791.5
5884	Pae_tRNA_His_f_at	169.1	159.0	53.0	62.1	55.0
5885	Pae_tRNA_Ile_f_at	730.3	1647.7	223.8	342.6	316.7
5886	Pae_tRNA_Leu_s_at	336.1	1085.7	215.8	306.9	319.7
5887	Pae_tRNA_Lys_f_at	143.7	191.6	62.0	88.5	61.5
5888	Pae_tRNA_Met_s_at	9.7	9.8	0.6	7.8	2.8
5889	Pae_tRNA_Phe_f_at	254.4	416.5	152.7	166.0	143.1
5890	Pae_tRNA_Pro_f_at	38.9	24.6	18.3	16.8	17.0
5891	Pae_tRNA_Ser_f_at	108.9	156.2	126.8	101.6	78.7
5892	Pae_tRNA_Thr_s_at	27.9	39.8	34.1	17.8	11.5
5893	Pae_5SrRNA_s_at	3035.3	6569.6	1100.8	1947.1	1295.7
5894	Pae_23SrRNA_s_at	59221.5	15501.5	13134.0	11899.8	12974.5
5895	Pae_16SrRNA_s_at	51517.1	14761.9	12296.1	11013.9	12265.0
5896	Pae_tRNA_Cys_i_at	120.8	89.8	89.8	133.1	172.3
5897	Pae_tRNA_Gly_s_at	179.3	150.5	311.6	309.4	345.1
5898	Pae_tRNA_Trp_f_at	290.2	198.1	607.4	553.2	535.1
5899	Pae_tRNA_Tyr_s_at	23.0	36.4	37.2	63.2	68.9
5900	Pae_tRNA_Val_f_at	1817.4	2883.1	841.3	1027.7	1253.2

* Expression signals for each of the 5900 probe sets represented on an Affymetrix GeneChip *P. aeruginosa* PAO1 genome array were obtained by analyzing each array image (.dat file) with the Affymetrix software Microarray suite 5.0 as recommended by the Affymetrix GeneChip Expression Analysis Manual.